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A Cultural History of the Kathāsaritsāgara
in
Keywords

Complementary to the General Index in vol. X
of Tawney & Penzer's Translation

This world which is deluded by ignorance, wanders in the wheel of *saṃsāra*,
turns its face from his unique form due to many schools of thought
and it wanders round and round due to its many rituals.
It is restrained by many bonds and has decayed through the blades of karma which are inherent.

(Gaṇeśa-Purāṇa, Kṛīḍā-khaṇḍa 9,42 < Bailey 2008: II 106)

Preface

As a rule, when reading a text as a student, one notes vocables, which may be necessary at that stage, but for later scholarly work and to quickly have an example in class or for a lecture a detailed subject index is no doubt more useful. It can also provide material for a study, e.g., of animals or gestures and expressions of feeling such as Sternbach made of aphorisms of the Kathāsaritsāgara, when compared with similar material from related texts such as Bāṇa, Kṣemendra and Vasudevahiṇḍī.

The Śaiva brahmin Somadeva's *Kathāsaritsāgara* (composed between 1063-81 C.E. according to Winternitz¹ and below abbreviated as KSS), the pith of the Bṛhatkathā,² is an exhaustive source of information about many aspects of traditional Indian life³ which to a great extent may have irretrievably ended with the dissolution of native kingdoms and their integration into the Indian republic. It is well-known through Charles Tawney & Norman Penzer's translation (TP) each volume of which has a general index beside one of Sanskrit words, and the tenth volume combines these indices. The articles are, however, often impractically arranged and many details not included, such as similes (which are frequently more original than those of his younger contemporary Hemacandra), names (as in volume IV) and apparent proverbs or sayings. Their references pertain mixed to text, notes and appendices an order principle appearing absent, whereas the keywords in my index below refer to text places only. Recognizable motifs have often received their number from Stith Thompson's *Motif-index* (STh), vol. six, and Thompson & Balys' *The Oral Tales of India* (OTI).

Further, though a digitized version of Tawney's translation in two volumes⁴ and of TP in ten volumes⁵ is in the web, there is no lexicon of the text⁶, as there is of the Vedic corpus. Penzer's indices pertain to his *Ocean of Story*, not directly to Somadeva's Sanskrit text, as below, for which I have used the fourth edition by Pt Durgāprasād and Kāśīnāth Pāṇḍurang Parab, revised by Vāsudev Laxmaṇ Śāstrī Paṇḍīkar and published by the Niṛṃayasāgar Press (NSP) in Bombay,

¹ 1985: 353. For a discussion of Somadeva's lifetime see also Sternbach 1980: 36f.

² KSS I 3 *Bṛhatkathāyāḥ sārasya saṅgrahaṃ (racayāmy aham)*; E 12 (TP IX 89). See also Warder 1992 §§ 5208ff. and Zin 2002: 144.

³ Winternitz III 1985 (1963): 365.

⁴ Available under <http://www.archive.org/details/kathsaritsga01somaufit> and [-02somaufit](http://www.archive.org/details/kathsaritsga02somaufit)

⁵ <http://www.archive.org/stream/oceanofstorybein01somaufit/page/n5/mode/2up> for the first vol. For the others, 01 before [somaufit](http://www.archive.org/details/kathsaritsga01somaufit) must be changed in 02, 03, etc.

⁶ MW often gives a word as occurring in KSS but omits exact reference. In order to provide a proper reference I have inserted some words for which MW only refers to Lexicographers (L) (such as *kaṭi-taṭa*) or Wilson. Words absent in MW have been marked as: (not MW).

1930, abbreviated as: D.⁷ It was not possible for me to compare previous editions but for Brockhaus and the 3rd NSP ed. of 1915.

In order to help finding motifs and parallels, a complementary index of KSS with references to both NSP and TP (also to reduce errors), and often with synonyms of a lemma as found in secondary literature in order to avoid idle searching, when one does not have the relevant keyword, may therefore not appear superfluous, though I am conscious of the relativity of the term, the selection of course being subjective and thus imperfect. I could have abstained from noting the many aphorisms and just have referred to Sternbach's book which, however, is long out of print (the chance of a reprint being very slight) and the parallel volume with the text and notes, planned together with J. P. Sinha to appear soon, will after the demise of Subhāṣitavidvān, as Dandekar called Sternbach, remain unwritten under the present circumstances of cultural doomsday.

Where apparently somehow of interest, I have mostly added the text in brackets. Omissions due to Victorian prudishness have been supplied. Numbers in bold types show longer dealings with a theme. For many words in MW located with W(ilson) an exact reference could be stated. Some errors could be corrected⁸ or translations put more precisely, even with substantial research, as in the case of *karṇī-ratha*, *patra*, *maṇḍana*, *lilā-vajra* or the untying of the plaited hair of the Takṣaśilā queen Madanamañcukā. After the long time the KSS is known and has been worked on one is surprised at still discovering such apparently sofar open problems.

As this index is in English, it is based on TP and uses most of their translations, but also the new French rendering, *Océan des rivières des contes*, (ORC using the Nirnaya Sagar Press edition published in Bombay in 1915⁹; Balbir, 1997) with its copious notes, a *répertoire* (terms and a complete list of proper names), *liste typologique* and bibliography, has often been quoted, inter alia, because it is occasionally more accurate, and the *répertoire* puts together systematically various aspects of complicated items such as Śiva whereas I have usually just listed the places as they appear in the order of the text. ORC is, however, not easily compared to TP due to its referring to the eighteen books (*lambaka*) of KSS and their division into waves (*taraṅga* 'flot'). It would have been easy to put the chapter numbers of the text in the head rule, and thus have saved researchers much time, but the Pléiade books are obviously not meant for scholarly use as is also shown by the tiny letters of the notes and *répertoire* placed at the end of the book *à l'américaine*, which is very annoying; yet at least the sections are mentioned with the numbers of their stanzas. An ordinary size reprint of this valuable new rendering with the notes at the bottom of the page would be much appreciated.

Moreover, the new complete German rendering (M 1991) by Johannes Mehlig was frequently consulted, despite Hertel's opinion that after Tawney's such a translation would be superfluous (1903: XX). It is based on the first edition by Durgāprasād and Parab (Bombay, 1889) and

⁷ Newly edited by Pt Jagdīślāl Śāstrī and published by Motilal Banarsidass in Delhi, 1970, reprinted in 2008, with the same number of pages as the 1930 edition.

⁸ *Āhāra* is not 'meat', *kṣapaṇaka* is not a 'Buddhist monk', etc.

⁹ Page LIII note 1.

its revision by Paṅśīkar (1930), as well as various German (partial) translations, mainly the one by Brockhaus, of course (M II 836f.), whose language after some one hundred fifty years sounds a little antiquated now. M is meant for the general reader, more readable, sometimes a little free or even flowery, but nevertheless usually ad sententiam and well thought out. Regrettably, however, it has no chapter numbers in the headline, nor verse numbers in the margin to facilitate looking up passages, or explanatory footnotes.

Another French book recently appeared and often referred to below is Christine Chojnacki's magnum opus, her conscientious translation and exhaustive study of the Kuvalayamālā (Kuv), the notes of which often are of greater interest than the work itself, and an important contribution to CDIAL and PSM. It is no doubt the best and most extensive study of a difficult Prakrit text so far for many explanations fit also in the KSS.

A richer index of Daṇḍin's *Daśakumāracarita* and Bāṇa's *Kādambarī* turned out to be helpful and will appear also separately.¹⁰ An extensive evaluation of the Rājatarāṅgiṇī would have given many more parallels but would have delayed the present work and must therefore be left to another scholar for an independent study.

My index may also be considered a kind of supplement to Aparṇā Chattopadhyay's *Studies in the Kathasaritsagara* (1993), a Benares Hindu University dissertation of 1964 (p. vi), in so far as her "critical study of the profuse material found in the work helps us to have a clear and comprehensive grasp over the social life of ancient India and its evolution from earliest times upto the days of the Muslim conquest" (p. xxvi), which help not all users may find very effective if at all usable.¹¹

A word of thanks to my physician Dr H. Metzner and his staff who have enabled me to continue my scholarly engagement has long been due.

I dedicate this work in memoriam Dr Gerald Hiltensberger; he, a Germanist interested also in Sanskrit and Indian literature, was a good friend whose fate it was to pay with his life for his scientific efforts.

W. Bollée
Holi, 2014

¹⁰ For the former see Bibliography below; the Bāṇa index is in preparation.

¹¹ Significant is when, nearly thirty years after taking her degree with this work, she writes "no Index is also given in this book for ... preparing an Index will take again some time and I have to pay immediate attention to other publications. I also think that the topic of the present book is such that it will be consulted mostly by the researchers in Indian culture who will be able, even without an Index, to trace their required points and facts" (p. xi).

Abbreviations not found in Monier Williams

ABhORI	=	Annals of the Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute
AA	=	Artibus Asiae
AE	=	Anna Esposito
AJPh	=	American Journal of Philology
B	=	Brockhaus 1839 and 1862
BEI	=	Bulletin d'Etudes Indiennes
BIS	=	Berliner Indologische Studien
BKBh	=	Bṛhatkalpasūtra and bhāṣya (Bollée 1998)
BKŚS	=	Budhasvāmin, <i>Bṛhatkathāślokaśaṃgraha</i>
BHSD	=	Edgerton, Dictionary 1970
CDIAL	=	Turner 1973
CPD	=	Critical Pali Dictionary
cty	=	commentary
D	=	NSP ed. of KSS used here (Bombay, 1930)
E	=	Somadeva's epilogue
esp.	=	especially
EW	=	East and West
EWai	=	Mayrhofer 1992-2001
Ghatage	=	Ghatage, Dictionary of Sanskrit
HdA	=	Bächtold-Stäubli 1934f.
IT	=	Indologica Taurinensia
JEĀS	=	Journal of European Āyurvedic Society
JISOA	=	Journal of the Indian Society of Oriental Art
JOIB	=	Journal of the Oriental Institute of Baroda
KSS	=	Kathāsaritsāgara
Kuv	=	Chojnacki 2008 II and the text (Bombay, 1959)
M	=	Mehlig I-II 1991
MW	=	Monier Williams 1899
OCD	=	Oxford Classical Dictionary
OLZ	=	Orientalistische Literaturzeitschrift
opp.	=	opposite
ORC	=	Balbir 1997
OTI	=	Thompson & Balys 1958
p. c.	=	private communication, e-mail
PSM	=	Pāiasaddamahāṇavo
PTSD	=	Pali Text Society Dictionary
PWB	=	Böhtlingk & Roth, <i>Sanskrit Wörterbuch</i>
q.v.	=	<i>quod vide</i>
ref.	=	reference; refer(ring)

SI	=	Studia Indologiczne
StII	=	Studien zur Indologie und Iranistik
STh	=	Thompson 1932-4
Sūy	=	Sūyagaḍa (Bollée 1977; 1988)
TP	=	Tawney & Penzer 1924
Triṣaṣṭi	=	Hemacandra, <i>Triṣaṣṭiśalākāpuruṣacaritra</i>
Vdh	=	Vasudevahiṇḍī
v.l.	=	<i>varia lectio</i>
WB	=	the present writer
w.r.	=	wrong reading
WZKS	=	Wiener Zeitschrift für die Kunde Südasiens
Zs.	=	Zeitschrift

*Prasahya rasayanti ye vigata-vighna-labdharddhayo
dhuraṃ dadhati vaibudhīṃ bhuvī Bhava-prasādena te*

When those who can fully taste this story have overcome the difficulties and obtained the supernatural powers they are, even on earth, divinely loaded with Śiva's favour.

(KSS heading)

Namo Vighnāntakāya

ābaddha-kakṣa (not MW) ‘girding up one’s loins’¹² 73,284 (TP VI 121); – see also: girding
ābaddha-śāṭaka (not MW) ‘with wrappers bound around the head’ (*śiraḥsv ~āḥ*), said of slaves
 13,187 (TP I 163)

abandonment of baby, see: exposure

abduction, of lone princess in forest 10,118 and 131 (TP I 114f.); violent ~ of Tilottamā by
 two *Asura* brothers causes their death 15,139f. (TP II 14); ~ of king by horse 18,100 (TP
 II 57)¹³ and 123,79 (TP IX 49); Daitya abducts Deccan princess by treachery (*chalena*)
 26,180 (TP II 230); ~ of women is fated to bring death according to a curse 30,9 (TP III
 64); Vidyādhara prince carries off seven princesses 44,41ff. (TP IV 4); ~ of imperial
 princess by Siddhas 44,43 (TP IV 4); ~ of enamoured woman before her father’s eyes
 44,56 (TP IV 5); ~ of wives of others condemned by vow (*pratijñā*) 46,7 (TP IV 49);
 46,159 (TP IV 59); ~ of *vetāla* daughter by *vidyādhara* after killing her father 48,125 (TP
 IV 82); ~ of Sītā by Rāvaṇa 51,62 (TP IV 126); ~ of woman against her will 52,53 (TP
 IV 141); ~ of *vidyādhari* by mortal 56,174 (TP IV 150); ~ of the wives of others causes
 much guilt 52,255 (TP IV 155); kite carries off boy 60,244 (TP V 62); *vidyādhara* prince
 abducts at night sleeping brahmin beauty 87,8f. (TP VII 29), cf. 123,146 (TP IX 53); horse

¹² Cf. *baddha-kakṣya* 48,131 (TP IV 83); *kakṣābaddha* 52,325 (TP IV 161); *parikaraṇ baddhvā* 54,102 (TP
 IV 191); *baddhōttariyaka* 81,40 (TP VI 211).

¹³ Cf. Kuv 27.5.

abducts king to distant forest 94,14 (TP VII 88); 101,269 (TP VII 152); ~ of Śaśaṅkavatī behind future husband on horseback 103,73 (TP VII 180); ~ of Rukmiṇī by Viṣṇu 104,126 (TP VIII 10); 105,70 (TP VIII 26); ~ of woman by heavenly being 112, 2f. (TP VIII 105) and 112,210 (TP VIII 122); Asura carries off princesses to attend on his daughter 112,35 (TP VIII 108); ~ of queen by magic power (*māyā*) 114,7 (TP VIII 132); ~ of *Gandharva* maiden by two *rākṣasīs* stopped by deity presiding over her chariot 116,30f. (TP VIII 158); as father wants to give daughter to another she asks lover to abduct her 123,255 (TP IX 61); – see also: *māyā*; palace; Pātāla

ābhāva-lajjā (not MW) ‘shame of love’, maiden bends face down (*vinatānanā*) with ~ 74,236 (TP VI 157; ORC 891: “*par gêne, elle se couvrit le visage*”); – see also: gestures

a-bhaya ‘impunity’, woman asks husband for ~ 84,33 (TP VII 7)

a-bhaya-dinḍima (‘drum beaten at amnesty’)¹⁴ 118,104 (TP VIII 185); – see also: drum

abhicāra, see: spell

a-bhinnātman ‘without diverting one from his end’ 115,100 (TP VIII 151 “like-minded with”; ORC 1208: “*sans nous détourner de notre but*”; MW ‘of undaunted spirit, firm’)

Ābhīra¹⁵ wants sex in exchange for helping woman against monkey, but is cunningly put off 6,37ff. (TP V 141)

abhisārikā ‘woman who goes to lover at night’¹⁶, night as ~ 103,203 (TP VII 189 “wanton nymph”)¹⁷

abhiṣeka, see: inauguration

abjini 90,65 (TP VII 102), see: bee(s)

ablutions, K. goes near the water in the evening for ~ and sees a *rākṣasa* rise up (*jalôpânte sa Kesataḥ upaspraṣṭum gato ’drākṣīd rākṣasaṃ utthitam*) 123,17 (TP IX 55 “having gone to rinse his mouth, saw a *rākṣasa* rise up near the water”; ORC 1296: “*se rendit au bord de l’eau pour ses absolutions*”)

abrus precatiorius, see *guñjā*

abscess (*gulma*) caused by grief is healed by physician with a lie 15,15 (TP II 2); ~ (? *vyādhi*) caused by lying ministers 17,42 (TP II 37)¹⁸; ~ in leg, healed by Piśāca with herbs 28,169 (TP III 33);

abuse¹⁹: police chief addresses *rākṣasa* by: “You fool !” (*mūrkhā*) 5,51 (TP I 52); brahmin calls himself stupid beast (*mūrkhāṃ paśum*) 6,80 (TP I 66); “how can you be such a blockhead (*mūrkhā*) ?” says queen to king 6,117 (TP I 69); ~ of *rākṣasa* father by daughter: he is somewhat silly 39,108 (TP III 225); you are a fool 40,78 (TP III 246); “Give his gold-fodder back to that two-legged ass (*paśu*)” 6,63 (TP I 65); “out on you, fool (*dhiñ*,

¹⁴ ‘War-drum’ (MW < Lexx.).

¹⁵ See, e.g., Bollée 1998 III: 31; Kuv note 853.

¹⁶ See, e.g., Rossella 2004: 100.

¹⁷ ORC 1082: “*la nuit vint à son rendez-vous.*”

¹⁸ Penzer in a note thinks *vyādhi* here must pertain to an abscess.

¹⁹ Cf. Bollée 2008a: 6.

mūrkhā), devoted to your belly !” 97,28 (TP VII 114); “out on you, decrepit old creature !” (*dhig, jarā-jirṇa*) 97,29 (TP VII 114); ~ of king by messenger who calls him “fool” (*jaḍa*) 102,145 (TP VII 173); “you do not know your father” (*tava na jñāyate pitā*): bastard 124,204²⁰ (TP IX 82); – terms of ~, see: (*grdhi*) *kāmuka; jālma; pāpa; paśu; mithyā-panḍitā; mūrkhā; śaṭha*

accusation, false 32,191 (TP III 106); ~ of infidelity 51,79 (TP IV 127); ~ of killing a Bhilla husband 61,164 (TP V 82); ~ of rape 63,34 (TP V 122); ~ of stealing gold by hermit from robbers 72,264 (TP VI 88); ~ of hitting mother-in-law with stone 74,173 (TP VI 153); brahmin utters ~ (*mṛṣā-vadya*) of *brahma-hatyā* by his wife and chases her away 87,51 (TP VII 33);

“Achilles’ heel”²¹, left hand (*vāma-hasta*) of *rākṣasa* as ~ 11,65 (TP I 127); do, (*vāma-kara*) 112,52 (TP VIII 109);

acquiescence of father toward only son (*eka-putratayā ... yac cakre, pitā tasyāsahiṣṭa tat*) 28,114 (TP III 29)

act, reckless ~, voice from heaven tells suicidal merchant: “do not act rashly” (*mā kāṛṣiḥ sāhasaṃ*) 86,87 (TP VII 19), cf. 105,29 (TP VIII 23); Gaurīs’ voice from the air prevents suicidal Siddha princess from ~ 90,76 (TP VII 54); – see also: *mā kāṛṣiḥ sāhasaṃ*

act of truth (*satya*),²² when, after rinsing his mouth, minister speaks: “If I have been a benefactor to this king, and if the queen is free from stain, speak, ye guardians of the world; if it is not so, I will part from my body” (*ahaṃ hita-kṛd rājño devī śuddhimatī yadi, brūta bho, Loka-pālās ! tan na ced, dehaṃ tyajāmy aham*) 16,118 (TP II 30 with note on p. 31ff.); 18,161 (TP II 62); 26,97 (TP II 225); with ~ (against his own head) king entreats Agni to accept *bilva* fruit who then changes it against a golden one from his *sattva-taru* 35,68f. (TP III 160); 36,28 (TP III 171 and 179); if in six months a heavenly man should not visit courtesan she vows to enter the fire 38,113 (TP III 214); ~ of Sītā 51,81 (TP IV 127); ~ of Damayanī : *Bho ! Loka-pālāḥ ...* 56,274 (TP IV 239); ~ of *pati-vratā* to save husband from state of water-spirit 63,65 (TP V 124)²³; king, if he is really devoted to Śiva, implores *Lokapālas* in ~ to tell him his duty 112,135 (TP VIII 116); ~ of Daitya princesses, unable to get the husband of whom Śiva told their mother in a dream, and who wanted to enter the fire 118,169f. (TP VIII 189); – see also: oath; swearing; vow

acting rashly, see: rash act(s)

actions in previous life, decide everything 40,39 (TP III 243) and 40,78 (TP III 246); even gods cannot alter the influence of ~ 101,199 (TP VII 148); can (the effect of) ~ be avoided ? (*kiṃ śakyaṃ pūrva-karmātivartitum ?*) 101,296 (TP VII 154); – see also: karman

²⁰ See Bloomfield 1919: 195 (TP).

²¹ For the motif see STh: Z 311.

²² See TP III 17ff.; Luitgard Soni 2002 with literature in Bibliography, p. 201, in which Lüders 1944 and Tavadia 1954 should be added. For the motif see also STh H 252.

²³ Lüders 1951: 500.

actor (*nartaka*) performing as Hari-Viṣṇu in the form of a woman (Mohinī) carries off the *amṛta* from the Dānavas 74,36f. (TP VI 143)²⁴

adamant, Daitya cased in ~ (*vajramaya*) 11,65 (TP I 126f.)

adbhutālaya ‘home of marvels’ (not MW), ocean as ~ 26,8 (TP II 217)

addiction to dice, see: gambler

address direct²⁵, “bull” (*vṛṣabha*) as a term of respect, said of a minister 40,8 (TP III 240); ~ of princely husband to wife with “*tanvī*” 45,253 and wife to husband with *āryaputra* 255 (TP IV 34); ~ of *vidyādhari* by prince with “*kalyāṇī*” 59,8 (TP V 26); ~ of prince by *divya-Kanyakā* without noun: “*kas tvam ?*” 59,83 (TP V 32); ~ of brahmin by prince 74,115 (TP VI 148); king addresses hermit by “Bhagavan” 92,45 (TP VII 74); female ascetic addresses king as “Son” (*putra*) 42,13 (TP III 259); do, of Pāśupata ascetic addressing king with “*vatsa*” 92,60 (TP VII 75); brown cow addresses man in articulate voice: “Son ...” 108,34 (TP VIII 55); – see also: *ārya-putra*; *bharṭṛ-dāraka*; *yakṣiṇī*

address indirect, ~ by princess of queen disguised as brahmin woman through minister disguised as brahmin 16,20 (TP I 21); ~ of unwilling stranger by princess through her *sakhī* 30,74 (TP III 69); ~ of brahmin by merchant’s daughter through her confidante (*vayasyā*) 37,101 (TP III 190); ~ of man by woman through his companion 59,92 (TP V 32); ~ of father by daughter through her confidante (*sakhī-mukhena*) 65,250 (TP V 174); ~ of prince by princess through her maid 74,220 (TP VI 156); ~ of king by brahmin friend on behalf of princely suitor for king’s daughter 74,255 (TP VI 158); maiden has her mother tell her father and brother her marriage conditions 79,9 (TP VI 200); ~ of king by *Asura* maiden through her attendant 81,83 (TP VI 214); ~ of *Siddha* princess by *Vidyādhara* prince through her discreet (*sa-hṛdayā*) attendant 90,49 who asks prince’s friend for his name 51 (TP VII 52); ~ of hermit maiden by king through her confidante 94,30f. (TP VII 89); ~ of hermit maiden by prince through her confidante 101,247 (TP VII 151); ~ of companion of princess by prince 116,43f. (TP VIII 159)

adhaḥ reading for *adaḥ* 22,240 (TP II 155); idem 26,14 (TP II 218 note 1);

a-dharma, na ~*ś ciraṃ ṛddhaye* ‘unrighteousness’ does not long ensure success 26,254 (TP II 236); donkey as symbol of ~ 70,118 (TP VI 32); – see further: Buddhism

a-dharma-leśa ‘stain of unrighteousness’ because of attacking old men and children 117,151 (TP VIII 174)

a-dharma-yuddha ‘unfair combat’, a true *kṣatriya* would not desire to conquer in ~ 38,133 (TP III 215)

ādhi ‘mental agony’, see: disease

adhidevatā ‘presiding deity’, of lake in Kāma’s garden 59,5 (TP V 26); – see also: chariot

adhipa-kula (not MW) ‘royal family’ 37,176 (TP III 195: “race”; ORC 381: “*famille d’un souverain*”)

adho-mukha ‘with eyes or face cast down’, of a fearful robber in Yama’s hall 72,352 (TP VI

²⁴ Mbh I 15ff.; see O’Flaherty 1973: 277 and do, 1980: 320.

²⁵ Cf. Bollée 2008a: 6.

95); – see further: eyes; gestures; *natânana*
 adjuration, messenger makes *yakṣi* ~ by the touch of King Vikramāditya’s feet (*aṅgri-sparśa-sāpitā*) to tell him who she is 120,127 (TP IX 10);
 adoption,²⁶ of boy on lion by sonless king 6,92 (TP I 67); ~ by brahmin of merchant boy and girl 56,45 (TP IV 223); ~ of mind-born son of Śrī by hermit Dīdhitimat 59,97 (TP V 33); *yakṣa* adopts mendicant as son 66,60 (TP V 182); king adopts refugee as son 72,175 (TP VI 81f.); – see also: adoptive son; son
 adoptive son (*kṛtrima-putra*), Agni predicts poor brahmin in dream ~ who will end his poverty 73,60 (TP VI 105); do, (*kṛtrima-suta*), of Agni and *brāhmiṇi* adopted by Caṇḍālas 112,107 (TP VIII 114); – see also: son
a-droha-pratyaya (not MW; ‘guarantee against treason or injury’), fire as witness for ~ 16,84 (TP II 28)
 adulterer (*naraḥ saha para-striyā*) brought to *yakṣa* Maṇibhadra’s temple 13,167 (TP I 162); Indra as ~ with Ahalyā 17,138f. (TP II 45); Śavara kills ~ 32,69 (TP III 95); ~ thrown overboard ship 36,102 (TP III 176); ~ (*para-dāra-samāgama*) turned into monkey 37,130 (TP III 192); false friend as ~ designated as animal (*paśu*) 60,5 (TP V 41); king cuts off decorated (*racita-maṇḍana*)²⁷ head²⁸ of adulterer 112,31 (TP VIII 107)
 adulteress, cut off nose 19,49 (TP II 87f.)²⁹; ~ remains wantonly (? *yad-ṛcchayā*) with alien man 21,76 (TP II 131); ~ left asleep 32,70 (TP III 95); ~ beheads sleeping husband and accuses guests 32,77 (TP III 95); ~ throws husband, who killed paramour, in well 34,186 (TP III 141); 37,101 (TP III 190); 58,60f. (TP V 19); ~ banished after murdering husband 58,77 (TP V 20); ~ cuts off husband’s ears³⁰ and nose 58,99 (TP V 22); ~ and lover banished 60,7f. (TP V 41); ~ cut off ears and nose 61,166 (TP V 82) and 65,40 (TP V 156); ~ seemingly present at her own *śrāddha* 61,198f. (TP V 85)³¹; ~ (*ku-gehini*) cut off nose and hounded off 63,43 (TP V 123); ~ wife gives herself to leper 64,135 (TP V 149); ~ brahmin wife goes to bed with cowherd 68,43 (TP VI 4); ~ queen banished 71,304 (TP VI 58); nose of ~ bitten off by *vetāla* sticks in corpse of lover 77,68 (TP VI 188); – see also: Ahalyā; paramour
 adulterous couple revived by Caṇḍī goes home ashamed 95,90f. (TP VII 104)
 adultery³², heavenly beings do not make the wives of others (*para-dāra-gṛham*) their own

²⁶ See ORC 1530; Kane 1973: III 662ff.; STh N 825.1; Jolly 1910.

²⁷ TP VIII 107: “oiled and curled”; M II 558: “mit Puder und Schminke zurechtgemacht”; ORC 1172: “(tête) parée d’un bijou.”

²⁸ Beheading or cutting off ears and nose as pars pro toto and substitute are a common symbol of castration (Freud 1954: 366f.). This is especially evident in the case of Gaṇeśa who, after his first castration, received an elephant’s head which resembles much more male genitals with its trunk and tusks. At the second castration one of the latter was destroyed. See Courtright 2001: 117.

²⁹ On the motif see STh Q 451.5.1. On the difference in punishment for adultery between the sexes see, e.g. Rossella 2004: 111 with reference to Altekar 1999: 313ff.

³⁰ On the motif see STh Q 451.6.1.

³¹ The story corresponds to Avadāna 43 (Penzer).

105,18 (TP VIII 22);
 adventure, see: abduction; horse; king (lost on hunt); musk; night
 advice (*vākya*), of Nārada to king of Vatsa 15,142 (TP II 14); ~ of brahmin to others con-
 tending for headship (*nāyakatva*) 18,138f. (TP II 60); king marries against ~ of date
 given by astrologers 36,53ff. (TP III 173); ~ disregarded by ascetics 37,60 (TP III 187); ~
 of friend not to put oneself in the power of a female 37,148 (TP III 193); 57,127 (TP V
 10); ~ of a minister disregarded by a king 58,6 (TP V 15); 61,192 (TP V 84); 62,139 (TP
 V 110); 86,67 (TP VII 18); 101,276 (TP VII 153); ~ of ministers disregarded by emperor
 110,13 (TP VIII 83); – see also: blame
 affection persists through various births 22,169 (TP II 149); living beings produce hatred and
 ~ (*sneha*) due to recalling pre-birth impressions (*prāg-janma-vāsanābhyāsa-vaśāt*) 23,30
 (TP II 159); *pūrva-bhāryēyam asya* 86,88 (TP VII 19); 112,142 and 146 (TP VIII 117f.)
 et passim
 Agastya, *tejasvī* hero drinks up (*papau*) enemy’s forces as ~ did the water of the sea 71,110
 (TP VI 43); ~ vomits sea in dribbles (*pītvôdgīrṇam ivāgastyenābdhi-pāthaḥ pade pade*)
 102,54 (TP VII 166; ORC 1065: “*l’eau de l’océan qu’Agastya rejetterait de place en place*
après l’avoir engloutie”); 117,11 (TP VIII 164)
 age, only son born of middle ~ parents 104,20 (TP VIII 2); two sons born to middle ~ father
 114,84 (TP VIII 138); – see also: old age; *vayasi madhyame*
 age, of the same ~, see: coeval
 agha, see: (offence); *pāpa*; pollution; transgression
 agha-hara (not MW) ‘destroyer of faults’, epitheton of Hari-Viṣṇu 32,50 (TP III 94)
 Agni as witness 16,64 (TP II 28); brahmin gives merchant charm to appease ~ (*Agner*
ārādhanaṃ mantraṃ) 17,97 (TP II 42); ~ disguised as an old brahmin 17,99 (TP II 42);
 propitiated by *tapas* ~ gives to brahmin sword which comes when thought of 18,110 (TP II
 58); voice of ~ speaking to hero: “*ahaṃ *cārādhīpaḥ*”³³ (?) 18,315 (TP II 73); formula of
 evening oblation to ~ (*saṃdhyāgni-hotra-mantra*) 20,36 (TP II 97); ~ flees into the
 waters when asked to stop Śiva’s endless sex 20,75 (TP II 101); ~ curses speech of frogs,
 parrots and elephants to be inarticulate and flees on *mandara* tree in form of snail
 (*śambūka-rūpin*) 20,77f. (TP II 101)³⁴; ~ propitiated to obtain a son 27,164 (TP III 13);
 sacrifice of *bilva* fruits to ~ 35,56 (TP III 159); seven-rayed god ~ gives golden *bilva*
 fruit for ordinary one offered by king in act of truth 35,69 (TP III 160); ~ speaks in visible
 form (*sākṣāt*) 35,70 (TP III 160); crow asks as boon of ~ to be reborn as an owl 62,122
 (TP V 109); ~ propitiated in dream predicts poor brahmin adopted son 73,59f. (TP VI
 105); hermit-boy likened to ~ blazing with flame (*prajvalaṃs tejasā*) 101,17 (TP VII
 135); *Vidyādhara* king becomes yellow by worshipping ~ (*Agnī-ārādhana-piṅgala*) 106,73
 (TP VIII 33); ~ worshipped gives *vidyādhara* prince, his devotee, a daughter 106,74 (TP

³² See Kane 1973: III 531ff.; Bollée 2008a: 6 note 6.

³³ See below: **cārādhīpa*.

³⁴ Cf. Bāṇa, *Kādambarī* (Bombay, 1948) 27,7.

VIII 33); visible ~ stops suicide of desperate *caṇḍāla* in love with princess 112,101 (TP VIII 113); ~ begets son on brahmin maiden who flings the baby in the open street (*rathyā-mukhe*) out of shame 112,104 (TP VIII 113); ~ urges king Prasenajit in dream to find out truth about the *caṇḍāla* lover of his daughter 112,108 (TP VIII 114); ~ (*Hutabhuk*) appears himself before Daitya princess, consumes her *Asura* body, returns her *vidyādhara* body to her and appears in person to make prince take a wife 119,201ff. (TP VIII 207); – see also: fire; *sattva-taru*; tree

agni ‘digestion’ (q. v.)

agnihotra oblations in Kaśyapa’s hermitage 111,98 (TP VIII 103)

agni-kārya ‘oblation to the fire’, wife has to attend on husband in ~ 56,177 (TP IV 232)

agni-kriyā ‘rites of sacred fire’ boy initiated in ~ 56,40 (TP IV 222)

Agni-parvata ‘Mountain of fire’ 107,109 (TP VIII 50)

agni-pradakṣiṇa ‘circumambulation of the fire at wedding’ 16,81 (TP II 27)

agni-praveśa ‘(suicide by) entering fire’³⁵ atones for many transgressions (*aghâughā-vighāti*) 69,158 (TP VI 20); ~ planned by king without kingdom 72,171 (TP VI 81); ~ by Bodhi sattva 72,380 (TP VI 97); ~ of Bodhisattva’s wives and guests 72,389 (TP VI 97); ~ by wife of brahmin 73,71 (TP VI 106); ~ planned on fourteenth day by daughters and wife of imprisoned king at his decision that the maidens may not marry 118,152 and 159 (TP VIII 188); princess refuses to be burnt on pyre together with a strange man (?) 119,184 (TP VIII 206); – see also: immolation; suicide

agni-śālā ‘place for keeping the sacred fire, = *agny-agāra*’,³⁶ brahmin’s ~ occupied by *brahma-rākṣasa* 72,158 (TP VI 80)

agni-sauca (not MW) ‘bright like fire’ (Ghatage), snake gives garments called ~ to Nala 56,351 (TP IV 245 ‘fire-bleached’ with note; ORC 642: “[vêtements] ils s’appellent “purification par le feu””)

agny-agāra, bodily shape of Agni in ~ ‘place for keeping the sacred fire’ 112,102 (TP VIII 113);

agra-hāra ‘royal grant of land’ 7,41 (TP I 78); 28,156 (TP III 32); 73,200 (TP VI 115); 104,214 (TP VIII 17); – see also: grant; present

ague, cold, see: disease; fever; *śīta-jvara*

aguru ‘Aloe wood, *Aquilaria Agallocha*’, see aloe wood

Ahalyā, wife of Gautama, surpassing *apsaras* (*rūpa-jitâpsarāḥ*) 17,138 (TP II 45); ~ cursed to have nature of stone (*śilā-bhāva*) for adultery with Indra 17,143 (TP II 46)

ahaṃkāra ‘egotism’ as obstacle in the road to knowledge 5,137 (TP I 58); – see also : blood; pride; self-consciousness

āhāra-samaya ‘meal-time’, of king at 3rd watch of the day (*vāsara-praharais tribhiḥ*) 59,89 (TP V 32)³⁷; 63,94 (TP V 127)

³⁵ Filliozat 1963.

³⁶ See Macdonell & Keith 1912: 9f.

³⁷ Cf. Daś 259,7.

āhavârṇava ‘sea of battle’ (not MW) 116,67 (TP VIII 161)
ahimsā “main characteristic (*pradhāna*) of Buddhism” 27,25 (TP III 3)³⁸; ~ vow of hypocritical cat 62,51 (TP V 103);
aho dhig matsaro vidheḥ ! Out on the spite of Destiny ! She brings trouble on her handiwork, even when full of excellences 71,147 (TP VI 46 with note 2; ORC 818: “*Hélas ! Même dans ses créations les plus belles le destin est malveillant*”)
aho dhik ! ‘Alas’ 84,40 (TP VII 7); – cf. *dhig aho*
aho vata ! “‘Oho’, we have been cheated by this gambler” Yama says 121,199 (TP IX 26)
 Aindra grammar overcome by Pāṇini 4,25 (TP I 32)
 air, minister observes vow of silence feeding only on ~ (*vātâika-bhakṣa*) 6,159 (TP I 72); queen dreams of rising into the ~ 22,10 (TP II 138); living on ~ (*anilâsana*) as austerity 107,128 (TP VIII 52); *vāyu-bhug-varjitâsana* 115,19 (TP VIII 144); *vāyu-bhakṣa* 115,46 (TP VIII 147); – see also: chariot; dream; flying; sword; voice; witch
 air-castles, see castle-in-the-air
 airship³⁹ 7,61 (TP I 80); – see also: chariot
aja-gara ‘boa constrictor’, man turned into ~ after eating gourd (*karkaṭikā*) 123,32 (TP IX 45: ‘python’)
a-jñāna, see: ignorance
ākeka-vilocana (not MW) ‘with squinting eyes’, epitheton of *yakṣas* 73,245 (TP VI 118)
a-kheda ‘consolation’, tale told for ~ 77,4 (TP VI 183); – see further: consolation
ākheṭaka ‘chase, hunt(ing)’, king ranges forest every day on the ~ 16,5 (TP II 20); 42,1 (TP III 259); ~-*krīḍāṃ karoti* (‘to enjoy hunting’) 54,4 (TP IV 184: ‘sylvan sport’); – see further: hunt(ing); vice
ākhu, see: mice
ākrandā, see: cry and cf. *rava*
akṣa-jñāna (not MW) ‘dice-skill’ given by Ṛtuparṇa to Nala for chariot-driving 56,377 and 381 (TP IV 247f.)
akṣa-mālikā, *akṣa-sūtra*, see: rosary
 Alakā residence of Kubera 19,107 (TP II 93); ~ surpassed by Īrāvātī 42,53 (TP III 263); city in Niṣadha 101,41 (TP VII 137);
alakta (‘red lac’) marks garment of prince after his *gāndharva* marriage with princess 3,71 (TP I 23); Śambhu is smeared with *alaktaka* of Gaurī’s feet when he honours her 104,2 (TP VIII 1)
 alchemy⁴⁰ (making gold out of copper) by means of a powder (*cūrṇa-yuktyā*) 35,82 (TP III 161 with note)

³⁸ In vs 15 the merchant Vitastadatta speaking here is stated to be *bhikṣu-pūjâika-tatparaḥ*; in vs 20 the son asks his father “What have you to do with that Buddhist thought > creed (*kiṃ tena saugatena nayena te ?*)”. Somadeva seems not very familiar with the heretic creeds of Buddhism and Jinism.

³⁹ For the motif see STh *D 1118.

⁴⁰ See Balbir 1990 and 1992; Subbarayappa 2004.

alcohol, abuse of ~, see: drinking spirits; drunkenness; *pāna-mada*; vices; wine
ālekhyā-puruṣa, see: black magic
 alimony,⁴¹ son trusted to support mother 3,17 (TP I 19) and *ṛṭti-nibandhanam* ‘(son) who was destined to be the means of her her future maintenance’ 6,31 (TP I 62); ~ given to repudiated wife 23,50 (TP II 160 with note 1); king gives sonless widow one quarter of her husband’s livelihood (*jīvana*) 73,258 (TP VI 119)
a-lipi-jñā (not MW), see: illiterate
 alms, not given to woman 61,314 (TP V 96); 123,187 (TP IX 56); hermitage trees asked for ~ 101,28 (TP VII 136);
 almsfood (*bhāikṣya*), ascetic washes ~ on stone in order to appear pious 121,158 (TP IX 23)
 almshouse (*sattra*) 21,71 and *sattra-śālā* 74 (TP II 130f.); royal (*rāja-sattra*)⁴² ~ 33,54 (TP III 111); do, (*dāna-sattra*) 113,29 (TP VIII 126);
 Aloe wood (*kālāguru*)⁴³ given as dowry by king of Kauśāmbī 44,132 (TP IV 9); stupid merchant burns ~ to charcoal 61,5 (TP V 67)⁴⁴
ālohita-cchaviḥ ‘(with) reddish light’, of the moon 119,166 (TP VIII 204);
 alone, king leaving at night 69,111 (TP VI 17); idem of prince 71,22 (TP VI 37); king sets out ~ to the south at night to fetch corpse 75,49f. (TP VI 167); lone brahmin on boat 123,195 (TP IX 57); – see also: lone son; lone woman; night
alpa-sattva, raising a *vetāla* disagreeable to ~ ‘(man of little courage)’ 73,165 (TP VI 113);
 altruism, see: body; hair-style
*āmalkas*⁴⁵ ‘Myrobalan’, child given dish of ~ 60,242 (TP V 62); stupid servant tastes ~ before bringing them to his master 61,297 (TP V 94)⁴⁶; parrot throws ~ on his reflection in water which he imagines is his wife 72,246 (TP VI 86); Rājput lives ten years on ~ and offers ~ to his king 81,21 (TP VI 210);
a-manuṣa-go-cara ‘supernatural’ said of *Indra-jāla* 73,367 (TP VI 127);
 Amarêśa⁴⁷, female ascetic meets prince at temple of ~ 65,226 (TP V 172);
amarṣa-kaluṣa (not MW) ‘impure passion’, see: envy
Amartya-guru ‘counsellor of the immortals, Bṛhaspati’ comes to Indra when thought of 115,92 (TP VIII 150);
 amazon (*sāyudhā kanyakā*), female ascetic (*tāpasī*) saves king from ~s 122,39 (TP IX 36)
ambara, see: garment; sky
 ambassador, see: *haṃsa*; messenger

⁴¹ See Meyer 1952: 406ff.

⁴² The text in both cases reads *-santra*. In TP VIII 126 note 1 TP want to read *-satra* or *-sattra* for *-pātra* in 113,29. – *Santra* occurs also 122,63.

⁴³ Kuv note 119.

⁴⁴ STh J 2094.

⁴⁵ See ORC 1531.

⁴⁶ Avadāna 37 (Penzer).

⁴⁷ Here probably Śiva, see ORC 1443 note on p. 763.

- ambu-dānôtsava* 112,59 (TP VIII 110), see: festival; water of immortality
- ambu-sārāsa* (?)⁴⁸ ‘water-crane’, *haṃsas* playing with ~ 70,59 (TP VI 28 with note 3; ORC 805. “hérons”)
- ambho-vihāra* (not MW) ‘splashing game, water play’ 55,118 (TP IV 210); – cf. 67,92 (TP V 202)
- Ambikā = Durgā tells *vidyādhari* princess that a mortal should become her husband 26,62 (TP II 221); ~ as remover of sorrows (*arti-harā*) helps after being thought of 42,82 and 102 (TP III 264 and 266); ~ appears bodily (*sākṣād*) to penitent, predicts future 52,245 and ends curse after propitiation 258 (TP IV 155); ~ = Gaurī gives boon to Jimūtavāhana’s wife and reanimates him 90,182ff. (TP VII 61); Ganges imitating ~ as springing from Himavat 93,78 (TP VII 84); temple of ~ is mouth of death because of human sacrifice 101,300f. (TP VII 155); in dream ~ appoints husband for princess 103,37 and 181 (TP VII 177 and 187); *āśram* of ~ 119,125 (TP VIII 202); – see also: Gaurī
- a-medhya* ‘dirt’, women would even eat ~ if they had no noses 62,112 (TP V 108); – see also: flies
- ami*, *les amis de mes amis sont mes amis* (*eso ’pi na kim asmākaṃ mitram ?*) 54,196 (TP IV 196)
- amṛta*, see: gods; nectar; water of life
- amṛta-rasa* ‘water of life’, princess bathed in ~ after eating Vindhya fruits 29,57 (TP III 43)
- amṛta-seka* (not MW) ‘watering with nectar’: the tree of empire (*rājya-śākhin*) 33,163 (TP III 121)
- aṃśā*⁴⁹ ‘part-incarnation’: Naravāhanadatta ~ of Kāma 34,41-44 (TP III 130) and 44,9 (TP IV 1); Nāgārjuna ~ of a *bodhisattva* 41,10 (TP III 252), etc., see further: part-incarnation; portion
- aṃśuka* ‘cotton, cloth’ (MW), often wrongly translated by ‘silk’, see: banner
- amusement, of great men fruitful (*na toṣo mahatām mṛṣā*) 20,44 (TP II 98); princess sports in palaces ... like a wave of the sea of infancy that is full of passion for ~ (*grheṣu ... krīḍā-rasamayasyēva lahari śaiśavāmbudhe*) 28,99 TP III 27); ~s of king in his childhood 34,172f. (TP III 140); ~ by going about in flying chariots with wives 43,274 (TP III 300); prince and ministers continually roam through many countries in magic chariot for ~ (*līlayā*) 44,40 (TP IV 4); combat looks like Death’s playing with severed heads like in a ball game (*kṛtānta-kanduka-krīḍā*) 50,7 (TP IV 108); after duties king goes to garden for ~ (*viharan*) 59,1 (TP V 26); tale for ~ (*vinodāya*) 76,5 (TP VI 179); idem 78,4 (TP VI 191); story of Rāmāyaṇa told for ~ (*vinodārtham*) 107,12 (TP VII 43); marrying attendant maidens to each other as ~ (*kanyakānyonya-vivāhādi-vinodana*) of princess 122,52 (TP IX 37); – see also: tourism
- an-ācānta* ‘without rinsing the mouth’ (necessary in Piśāca rite) 28,165 (TP III 33)
- analāhuti* (not MW) ‘burnt offering’, of an enemy out of wrath 10,198 (TP I 120)⁵⁰

⁴⁸ Not in Dave 2005.

⁴⁹ See ORC 1579.

an-alīka-lagna ‘ornament on the front of the earth’ and ‘subject to no inauspicious moments’, epithet and pun on the name of Kalaśa, king of Kashmir E 9 (TP IX with note 1)

ānanda-bāṣpa, see: joy;

ānanda-dīvyā-tūrya (not MW) ‘divine festive instrument’, *hatâ°* 109,31 (TP VIII 72 “in which celestial drums were joyfully beaten”)⁵¹

ānanda-dundubhi, see: drum

ānanda-tūrya (not MW) ‘a festive instrument’⁵² 34,111 (TP III 136 ‘cymbal’);

¹Ananta, splendid city looks like ~ emerged from the earth⁵³ 10,49 (TP I 109)

²Ananta, son of Saṃgrāma and king of Kashmir, at whose doorway a royal head was rolled E 3 (TP IX 87 with note 6); ~ husband of Sūryavatī (q.v.) E 4 (TP IX 88)

an-anya-sevin (not MW) ‘no vassal of anyone else: independent’ 102,73 (TP VII 168)

an-ātma-jñā ‘not knowing oneself anymore > confused ? [said of a drunk person], comatose ?, reeling drunk ?’ 40,33 (TP III 242 “who did not understand a joke”; ORC 413: “*qui ne se connaissait plus*”)

Andha-tāmisra, name of a hell, three men shut up in trunk as if ... in ~ 4,63 (TP I 34)

[*aṅga-hāra* technical term of a fast dance of 32 kinds (the reference in Sundaram 1979: 757 could not be found)]

aṅga-rāga ‘unguent’, lake made slightly yellow by the ~ from bathing women’s bodies 104,89 (TP VIII 7); ‘body lotion, perfume’⁵⁴ of Sītā 107,14 (TP VIII 44); red ~ ‘unguent’ at coronation 110,81 (TP VIII 87); brahmin smears odorous ~ obtained in cave of *kāpālīka* on his body 124,22 (TP IX 69);

anger with adders, and killing water-snakes 14,83 (TP I 188); ~ causes abscess 15,15 (TP II 2); king feigning ~ 27,28 (TP III 3)⁵⁵; though his limbs are gashed (*kr̥ttāṅga*) by king muni is without ~ 28,33 (TP III 22); ~ pretended by minister 32,6 (TP III 90); ~ of hermit with peasant who did not hear him 33,32f. (TP III 109); man who is free from ~ has gained heaven 33,51 (TP III 110); brahmin witch conceals ~ 37,152 (TP III 194); wicked woman burns with ~ (*krodhena jvalantī*) 37,159 (TP III 194); king conquers ~ 39,31 (TP III 220)⁵⁶; king assumes ~ (*kr̥ta-kopa*) 39,33 (TP III 220); drunk minister speaks in ~ 40,33 (TP III 242); cheated princesses are angry, ashamed and terrified 45,263f. (TP IV 35); woman looking askance at her beloved with an eye red with ~ 45,274 (TP IV 35); ~ feigned 46,17 (TP IV 50); ~ pretended by spurned queen 49,56 (TP IV 88); one who has

⁵⁰ Cf. *homa-karma* at 11,37 (TP I 125).

⁵¹ ORC 1144: “où des instruments de musique merveilleux résonnèrent avec joie.” However, the word *ānanda-bheri* in Jātaka VI 157,8 and 589,17 proves that *ānanda-tūrya* is a kind of instrument. Thus in KSS 109,31 *hata-dīvyānanda-* is meant, but impossible because of the metre, and therefore the words are inverted. Special occasions have their own instruments such as *vadhya-dīṇḍīma*, the drum beaten on the way to execution.

⁵² Cf. perhaps *utsava-tūrya* below.

⁵³ This curious comparison can only pertain to the vastness of the city extending along the river Ganges.

⁵⁴ See various articles in Gode 1961 (I).

⁵⁵ Also Rājāt 7,241.

⁵⁶ The *Bṛhatsaṃhitā* 77,11 gives a recipe for an incense that calms the royal anger (McHugh 2012: 139).

conquered ~ conquers this whole world 52,240 (TP IV 154); stream shows frowns of ~ in the form of curling waves 55,117 (TP IV 210); ~ of crying queen⁵⁷ 55,124 (TP IV 210); people with ~ compared to lotus bed smitten by the wind (*padminîvânîlâhata*) 108,130 (TP VIII 63); ~ of Kâlarâtri at not being worshipped 109,96 (TP VIII 77); brows curved in ~ 110,130 (TP VIII 91) and 118,11 (TP VIII 178); king feigning ~ (*kopaṃ kṛtvâiva kṛtrimaṃ*) 111,76 (TP VIII 102); – see also: blackmail; gestures; wrath

a-nidra-svapna (not MW), see: daydream

anilâśana, see: air

animals, female, see: cuckoo; doe; female goose; hen-crow; hen-cuckoo; hen-koel; hen-maina; horse; *kari-kareṇû*; *nāgî*; she-elephant; she-jackal; she-partridge; snake;

animal(s)⁵⁸, weeping ~ listen to Guṇâḍhya's tales 8,26 and 29 (TP I 90f.); wild ~ desire depopulation of the earth and therefore king should slay them 27,147 (TP III 12); even ~ understand self-protection 33,80 and 104 (TP III 113f.); four ~ (*nakulôlûka-mârajâra-mûṣakâḥ*) in fig-tree 33,107 (TP III 115); female ~s such as *nāgî* not allowed to enter Kârttikeya's temple 55,174 (TP IV 214); celestial *haṃsa* addressing Damayantî with understandable words (*vyaktayâ girâ*) 56,243 (TP IV 237); speaking parrot 59,36 (TP V 28)⁵⁹; villager as stupid as an ~ 61,27 (TP V 70); fool lacks discernment as an ~ 61,243 (TP V 89); serpent speaking with human voice 61,311 (TP V 95); articulate speech of ~ 65,55 (TP V 158)⁶⁰; grateful ~ 65,70ff. (TP V 160ff.)⁶¹; deer in forest weeping at seeing weeping king and daughter after separation 66,148 (TP V 189); elephant sunk into mud is drawn out with its mate by hermit's disciples 68,27 (TP VI 3); witch wife turns husband into buffalo 68,45 (TP VI 5); after eating charmed meal woman turns into she-goat and is sold to butcher (*saunika*) 71,273 (TP VI 56); butcher's wife (*saunika-bhâryâ*) puts thread round sleeping man's neck who wakes up as a peacock 71,276f. (TP VI 56); deer listen to lyre being played 90,42 (TP VII 52); assuming the form of an elephant and lion by magic (*vidyâ*) 109,129f. (TP VIII 79f.); beasts and birds weep when crown-prince leaves for the forest 113,52 (TP VIII 128); *haṃsas* relating story 115,3 (TP VIII 144); trees and ~s are of gold in Siddhîśvara, Hara-Śiva's heavenly abode 115,114 (TP VIII 152); after eating a gourd a man is turned into a python 123,32 (TP IX 45); boar and elephant speaking articulate speech 123,121 (TP IX 51); maid eats mare 124,100 (TP IX 75); – pity of witch with overloaded ox, see: compassion; – see also: grateful animals; language; single species; snake; speech

a-nimiṣêkṣaṇâḥ 'unwinking eyes' 18,13 (TP II 50)

animism: stocks and herbs weep with compassion 101,255 (TP VII 151f.)

Aniruddha, Viṣṇu's grandson, dreamt of by Uṣâ 31,12 (TP III 82);

⁵⁷ Cf. Kuv 11.25ff. (five causes of women's anger).

⁵⁸ Cf. ORC 1535.

⁵⁹ STh B 400ff.; OTI B 210.

⁶⁰ STh B 216.

⁶¹ STh *B 350ff.; Rauch 2013.

an-īśvara ‘wanting in wealth’ 120,50 (TP IX 5 thus corrected for “health”)⁶² makes no sense as to wealth (*vasu*); with reference to Buddhists the word must mean ‘not possessing, without a Creator’.

añjalika ‘a kind of arrow’ (?) 48,59 (TP IV 78 with note);

añjana ‘magic ointment, antimony’ (note in TP I 211ff.⁶³); ~ for discovering invisible *vidyā dharas* 48,86 (TP IV 80); ~ on eyes makes invisible 49,74 and 81 (TP IV 90 with note 2); ~like black teardrops looking like bees 95,60 (TP VII 102); eyes of royal ladies reddened by ~ washing into them 108,147 (TP VIII 64f. with note 1)

añjanādri ‘mountain of antimony’, elephant compared to ~ 51,169 (TP IV 134); monstrous boar designated as ~ 112,38 (TP VIII 108 with note⁶⁴)

añjana-nibha ‘black as antimony’, epitheton of Śiva Bhairava 106,182 (TP VIII 42)

añka ‘figure or mark branded on (the forehead)’ in the shape of a dog’s paw as punishment (*śunaḥ pādena dattvânkaṃ lalāṭe*) 13,148 (TP I 160); ~ for conspiracy against husband’s life 65,40 (TP V 156), cf. dog’s paw

anklet (*nūpura*), heavenly ~ stripped off foot of fleeing *rākṣasī* 25,152 (TP II 203); two ~s compared to quivers of Kāma 34,15 (TP III 129);

añkuśa ‘elephant hook’, 103,204 (TP VII 189); – cf. *nāga-danta*

anointing with clay as austerity as if testing beforehand the mud in the Avīci hell 24,93 (TP II 176); ~ the head with ghee against centipedes in the ear 29,167⁶⁵ (TP III 52); king anoints (*abhyāñcat*) son as crown prince 34,107 (TP III 136); *vidyādhari* ~ man’s back with hand from inside pillar against which he is rubbing it 37,16 (TP III 184);

answer, king gives feigned ~ (*kṛtakam abhyadhāt*) 39,42 (TP III 221); do, 39,232 (TP III 234); positive ~, see: *dhanyāsmi*

ant (*pipīlikā*)⁶⁶, bites baby boy 13,59 (TP I 153); pitchers of gold in ~ hill 33,46 (TP III 110)⁶⁷

magically created ~s gather sown sesame-seeds 39,123 (TP III 227)

antaḥpura, Viṣṇu promises king devotee all ~s in the world as tribute 36,17f. (TP III 170)

antaḥpura-viplava (not MW) ‘corrupting the harem’, of a man disguised as woman 5,36 (TP I

⁶² ORC 1260: ‘indigent’ which is explained on p. 1516 note 2 as: “*Les moines bouddhistes ne possèdent rien et mendient leur nourriture.*”

⁶³ See also Schmidt 1904: 169 for the production of collyrium, e.g. from pulverized *Tabernaemontana coronaria*, *Costus* root and the leaves of *Flacourtia cataphracta* mixed with soot. In *Kathākośa* (Hoffmann 1974) 253,4 king *Harīṣeṇa* prepares collyrium for his daughter. Jackmuth 2002: 103f.

⁶⁴ The big-sized animal is compared to a mountain, or cloud, the colour of collyrium, just as a big elephant is compared to a dark cloud, *kāla-meghābho ... mahā-gajāḥ* in 89,42 (TP VII 43). *-adri* is an augmentative or collective suffix here, like the fierce elephant of love in 37,98 (TP III 177) stressing the magnitude of the experience. See further below under: collective suffix.

⁶⁵ To be added in Bollée 2010 (Svasti): 159.

⁶⁶ On ants see Hensgen 1958: 145; Balbir 2004.

⁶⁷ On gold-digging ants see *Mbh* II 48,4; Herodotus III 102; McCrindle 1960: 94f. < Strabo 705; König 1984: 62ff.; <http://www.Antlionpit.com/golddigging.html>

50)

antara-stha, see: witness*antar-ātman* ‘intuition?’ indicates beforehand the approach of good or evil fortune (*sūcayaty antar-ātma puro bhāvi śubhāśubham*) 111,49 (TP VIII 99 ‘spirits’; ORC 1166: ‘I’âme’)

antelope skin, black, see: black antelope skin; gestures

ant-hill, Varṣa’s house turned into ~ (? *kṛta-valmika*) by mice or moles 2,49 (TP I 13); gold under ~ 33,46 (TP III 110)⁶⁸; elephant flings monkey into ~ mud 37,132 (TP III 192); bull tearing up ~s with his horns 60,17 (TP V 42);antidote against poison (q.v.); ~ (*pratiyoga*) against poisoned water, etc. 19,84 (TP II 91); minister’s knowledge of ~ (*viṣa-vidyā*) prevents suicide by snake-bitten brahmin 75,14 (TP VI 165); ~ against old age and death (*jara-mṛtyu-hara*) in Mandara’s country 114,54 (TP VIII 136)anti-father complex⁶⁹ of brahmin son against Buddhist father 27,16 (TP III 2)antimony, see *añjana*ants (*pipīlikāḥ*) created by magic to collect sesame-seeds 39,123 (TP III 226)⁷⁰*anuloma*: spell spoken forwards makes one invisible 74,134 (TP VI 149; cf. *pratiloma*);*anusvāra* (*bindu-patha*) arises from breathing and becomes a magic spell of force 46,116 (TP IV 56);*anutāpa* ‘regret, remorse’, of horse for abducting king 18,100 (TP II 57); king dies of ~ after violating merchant’s wife 34,20 (TP III 129); royal ~, see also: gesturesanxiety (*cintā*) clouds the heart like a black spot the full moon 10,182 (TP I 119); sleeplessness from ~ 20,32 (TP II 97); sonless king tormented with ~ (*suta-cintātura*) to get son 93,52 (TP VII 82); princesses express ~ by turning their eyes inward (*cintāntar-mukhair netraih*) 107,83f. (TP VIII 48f.)anxiety trauma of brahmin whose hair on his head and body continue to stand on end (*ūrdhva-roma-keśatva*) after he found out that his wife had devoured his servant 124,100 (TP IX 75)Apabhraṃśa, Ahalyā speaking *majjāro* ‘cat’ and ‘my lover’ in ~ (*apabhraṣṭa-vakrayā*) 17,141 (TP II 46); ~ stanza (*jai viraho na sahijjai ...*) spoken by a crying queen 55,125f. (TP IV 210f.)*āpāna-bhū(mī)* ‘bar, drinking hall’ 110,124 (TP VIII 91)⁷¹*āpāna-goṣṭhī* ‘carousal, wine-party’ of male royalty after a marriage 103,200 (TP VII 188); – see also: *pāna(-goṣṭhī; -lilā)**āpāna-lilā* ‘drinking bout, binge’⁷² 106,55 (TP VIII 32), cf. *pānādi-lilā* 108,123 (TP VIII 63);*āpanna-rakṣaṇa* (not MW) ‘rescue of the distressed’, characteristic of *kṣatriyas* 66,16 (TP V⁶⁸ König 1984: 72.⁶⁹ See Michaels 2004: 104.⁷⁰ König 1984: 36. On ants in India see also Balbir 2004.⁷¹ Cf. Kuv note 262.⁷² Cf. *sukhair āpānādyair* 40,116 (TP III 249); *pānādi-lilā* in 108,123 (TP VIII 63).

179)

A-parāṅgita, name of sword given by Daitya maiden to king Caṇḍasiṃha 81,108 (TP VI 216); ~ by Śiva to king Trivikramasena 99,37 (TP VII 124); do, given to Mukṭāphalaketu 115,143 (TP VIII 154);

apara-mātar ‘stepmother’, son of dead mother entrusted to ~ who mistreats him 14,38 (TP I 185)

apatyâśā (not MW) ‘hope of offspring’ of a pregnant woman 34,39 (TP III 130)

aphorisms, see: sayings

aphrodisiacum for women, see *cūrṇa-miśra*; drug; fertility elixir; *śṛṅga-māṃsa*;

... *api* ... *api* ‘as well as’ 101,255 (TP VII 152)

apparition, see. *vikṛti*

appearance, personal ~ (*prakaṭita-nija-mūrtiḥ*) of Śaraṅyā-Durgā to Vararuci 5,140 (TP I 59); repulsive ~ of Kālarātri 20,108 (TP II 103f.); Gaurī in person (*sākṣāt*)⁷³ rains nectar on Jimūtavāhana 22,246 (TP II 155); in sleep, divine beings assume their own form 32,30 (TP III 92) and, of a *vidyādhari*, 105,61 (TP VIII 25); visible ~ of Ambikā 52,245 (TP IV 155); four attributes of Hari-Viṣṇu wait in bodily form (*sa-vigraha*) on the god 54,25 (TP IV 186); visible ~ of charm gives brahmin sword 68,66 (TP VI 6); ~ of snake Pārāvataḥśa looking like the cloud of doomsday 70,71 (TP VI 29); personal ~ of Indra 72,391 (TP VI 98); ~ of Gaurī (*pratyakṣam agāt*) 90,184 (TP VII 61); ~ of *brahma-rākṣasa* 94,68 (TP VII 91); ~ as main criterion of princess for husband 103,18 (TP VII 176); visible ~ of Bhairava 121,106 (TP IX 19); ~ on being thought of, see: coming; – see also: Kālarātri ; ugliness

appeasement, see: austerities; curse; propitiation;

appetite, see: hunger

applause of king at queen’s speech (*vākyam abhinandati*) 39,223 (TP III 234); celestial ~ (*saṃstava*) from Sarasvatī for royal orchestre 54,241 (TP IV 201)

aporia, see: doubt

*apsaras*⁷⁴ reborn as brahmin woman 6,17 (TP I 61); Indra curses ~ to become mortal 9,26 (TP I 96); Urvaśī sees king Purūravas 17,5 (TP II 34); ~ curses king, see: Tilottamā; 17,65ff. (TP II 39ff.); *divya-stri* who gave up her celestial rank wants sex with mortal 17,129-132 (TP II 44); ~, cursed by Indra for seducing *vidyādhara*, is brought into the domain of the gods 27,63 and 70 (TP III 5f.); cursed ~ is reborn in queen’s womb 27,71 (TP III 6); feet of ~ do not touch dust (i.e. the earth) and their eyes do not wink 28,61 (TP III 24), cf. 104,95 (TP VIII 8); after giving birth to human child ~ Rambhā must return to heaven 28,68 (TP III 25); ~ Menakā inflames hermit 32,100 (TP III 97); ~ degraded by curse of Indra 34,139 (TP III 138); ~ singing song in honour of Gaurī 34,252 (TP III 147); Indra sends ~ (*surāṅganāḥ*) to seduce brahmin who set three-world on fire by muttering prayers 45,89 (TP IV 23)⁷⁵; ~ dancing at divine concert 50,150 (TP IV 117) and 50,189 (TP IV

⁷³ For the body of the deities see Oberlies 2006.

⁷⁴ See ORC 1536.

120)⁷⁶; ~ sprung from sea of milk (*kṣīrôda*) and brought back from Indra by Nārada, as ordered by Hari 54,40 and 47 (TP IV 187); princess surpassing in beauty the ~ (*lāvanya-nyakkṛtâpsarāḥ*) 69,30 (TP VI 11); 106,9 (TP VIII 28); Bhairava tells gambler to snatch up the clothes of bathing ~ (*sura-yoṣit*) 121,110 (TP IX 20); – see also: life; mermaid; nymph

aqueous weapon of Kāma, see: sweat

ārādhita, probable reading at 18,315, see: *cārādhipa

ārakta-sura-, see: wine

arbhaka, see: boy

ardha-candra curved hand by which a person is seized on his throat in order to throw him out 6,59 (TP I 65); 121,65 (TP IX 16); – see also: crescent; half-moon; neck

Ardha-narīśvara 35,102 (TP III 163)

argha ‘respectful reception of a guest’ by sprinkling with tears of joy (*harṣa-bāṣpa*) 18,369 (TP II 77); after separation wife bestows ~ on husband with tears of joy 29,181 (TP III 53); ~ for king by hermit’s daughter 32,111 (TP III 98); Aśvins receive ~ at the house of Nāgārjuna 41,21 (TP III 254); ~ for Nārada 45,13 (TP IV 18) and 162 (TP IV 28); ~ to *vetāla* with human blood (*nara-raktaiḥ*) in a skull by way of an *argha* vessel 99,13 (TP VII 123; “teeth” instead of blood)

arghya ‘drinking water’, Daitya maiden gives royal guest ~ 81,99 (TP VI 215); princess gives Jimūtavāhana garland with ~ 90,54 (TP VII 53); minister gets ~ from hermit’s boy 101,27 (TP VII 136); king offers ~ to hermit 105,84 (TP VIII 27); ~ offered to king 118,180 (TP VIII 190)

arghya-vessel, *yakṣa* in frame of brahminy drake upsets ~ in Kubera’s hand and is cursed to remain brahminy drake 72,42 (TP VI 71); attendant gives royal guest garland with the *arghya* 90,57 (TP VII 53)

argument (*vāda*), conquering woman in ~ 72,69 (TP VI 73);

arka plant (*Calotropis Gigantēa*)⁷⁷ in window of lying-in chamber 23,61 (TP II 161)

arjuna (*Terminalia Arjuna*)⁷⁸ trees 100,14 (TP VII 129); ~ contrasted with dark *tamāla* trees 102,162 (TP VII 162);

¹arm of *rākṣasa* cut off by hero in princess’s bedroom at night 18,283 (TP II 71); four ~s of golden figures given to poor brahmin 38,10 (TP III 213); left ~ throbbing is evil omen 49,129 (TP IV 93); maiden whom Gaṇa seized by the ~ causes her father to curse him 52,249 (TP IV 155); ministers representing (king’s) ~s 70,125 (TP VI 33); ~s are gambler’s only clothing (*bāhū prāvaram*) 73,77 (TP VI 106); gambler sleeps in temple of

⁷⁵ See TaittBr 3,10.8.4 *agnir me vāci śrītaḥ*; ŚpBr 3,2.2.13 *vāg evāgniḥ*, etc.

⁷⁶ Apsaras are the dancers of the gods (Manu I,37). – See Wössner 1981: 65ff.

⁷⁷ The giant swallow-wort (TP VIII 96 note 5), called an inauspicious plant in Gonda 1985: 124 note 14. The presence of these leaves together with the auspicious *śamī* (KauśikaS 8,15) is remarkable. See also Syed 1990: 530f.; Duda 2006: 292.

⁷⁸ Macmillan 1991: 120: “A handsome tree to 26 metres Good timber.”

Mahākāla pillowing his head on his ~ (*upadhānī-kṛta-bhuja*) 121,76 (TP IX 17)
²arm(s) (weapons) fourfold 3,76 (TP I 24); belle as Kāma's sixth ~ 104,28 (TP VIII 3)
 army, flies when king besieged 44,155 (TP IV 11); 108,112 (TP VIII 62); 109,55 (TP VIII 74); – crescent formation of two ~ies (*vyūhāv ardha-candrau*)⁷⁹ 50,3 (TP IV 108); hero drinks > consumes enemy's ~ (*balaṃ papau*) like Agastya the water of the sea 71,110 (TP VI 43);
 arrow, golden ~ (*svaṛṇa-śaras*) pierces crane 39,66ff. (TP III 222); ~ crescent-headed 42,4 and adorned with heron feathers (*kaṅka-pattra*) 42,5 (TP III 259); ~s humming like bees 42,6 (TP III 259); ~s winged with feathers (*patrārūḍhāḥ ... śarāḥ*) 50,4 (TP IV 108); cutting head with *añjalika* and *bhalla* ~s 48,59f. (TP IV 78); Bhilla king killed with one ~ (*bhalla*) 51,168 (TP IV 133); ~ of desire (*kāmasya ... śarāḥ*) made by Creator in the form of man to conquer women 67,14 (TP V 197); fowler kills two *haṃsas* with one ~ 69,152 (TP VI 19); showers of flowers compared to showers of ~s of love 71,199 (TP VI 50); merchant youth robbed of his senses by ~ of love (*smara-bāṇa*) 84,8 (TP VII 5); king hit by ~ of love (*smara-śarāhata*) 86,81 (TP VII 19); showers of ~ descend on warriors like locusts on the tender herb 103,5 (TP VII 175); ~ with crescent head (*bhallī*) 104,206 (TP VIII 16); Rāma cleaves seven palm-trees with one ~ 107,31 (TP VIII 44); rain of ~s (*śara-varṣa*) 118,68 (TP VIII 182); king places net of ~s (*śara-jāla*) between Asuras and his men 118,79 (TP VIII 183); *kāpālika* killed by poisoned ~ (*kāṇḍena digdhena*) 124,15 (TP IX 69);
 arson to palace 10,110 (TP I 113f.); ~ to houses because of woman 52,40f. (TP IV 140);
artha 'wealth' and 'meaning' 52,380 (TP IV 164)
artha-saṃdarpa (not MW) 'bribing (?)' 52,39 (TP IV 140: 'power of wealth'; ORC 561: 'en le soudoyant'); – see also: corruption
artha-śāstra, see: science
 articulate speech, see: speech
 artificial insemination, see: *iṣṭi*; fecundation
arti-ghna (not MW) 'calamity-averting' > wishing-tree 90,30 (TP VII 51)
arti-harā (not MW) 'remover of sorrows' (epithet of Ambikā-Durgā) 42,82 (TP III 264)
 Arundhatī on earth,⁸⁰ simile of female virtue (*satī-dhura*) 27,80 (TP III 7)
āryā sent by wife in letter after eleven years waiting for husband serving abroad 124,58 (TP IX 72)
ārya-putra (address of husband by wife) 45,255 (TP IV 34 with note)
 Āṣāḍha, see: festival; fourteenth day; twelfth white fortnight
a-sāra 'unreal', the world is ~ 28,15 (TP III 19)
a-sasya-ghātīn (not MW) 'not injuring the crops', required of Nāgas by king by means of ordeal 119,36 (TP VIII 195)
āsava, see: wine

⁷⁹ Dikshitar 1987: 270.

⁸⁰ See, e.g., Kakar 1982: 69f.

āśaya, see: mind

ascetic(s) (*muni*), vegetarian (*śākāśin*) 5,133 (TP I 58); ~ hands over lost queen with her son to king like tranquillity with joy (*rājñīm sânanām iva nirvṛtim*) 10,205 (TP I 120)⁸¹; female ~ living in Buddhist sanctuary (*Sugatâyatana-sthitâ pravrajikâ*) 13,88 (TP I 156); hypocritical ~ breaks vow of silence with enigmatic utterance 15,30ff. (TP II 4)⁸² and 24,96 (TP II 176); ~ Durvāsas fond of deluding people (*vañcanâika-rasa*) 16,36 (TP II 23); ~ Gautama curses his wife Ahalyā to become a stone and Indra to be covered with a thousand vulvae which will become eyes when he sees Tilottamā 17,143ff. (TP II 46)⁸³; rogue (*dhūrta*) disguises as ~ belonging to the social classes > member of a caste (? *varṇi-veṣa*)⁸⁴ 24,91 (TP II 176 ‘religious’; ORC 210: “*déguisé en ascète*”; M I 301: “*in einen frommen Büßer verkleidet*”); ~ from childhood 24,187 (TP II 182); wicked man accuses rigid ~ of being a hypocrite (*kapaṭa-tāpasa*) and an eater of children 24,209 (TP II 185); skull-bearing ~ white with ashes (*bhasma-pāṇḍuṃ kapālinam*) predicts future 25,81f. (TP II 196); bathing ~ Agryatapas sprinkled with water by three *vidyādhara* princesses curses them to become mortals 26,57 (TP II 221); treacherous ~ becomes *vidyādhara* king 26,233 (TP II 234); ~ who deceives those who repose confidence in him (*viśvasta-vañciko vratī*) 26,242 (TP II 235); ~, practising penance heels-up (*ūrdhva-pāda*), is inflamed by *apsaras* Menakā 32,99 (TP III 97); ~’s seed falls on plantain-flower 32,101 (TP III 97); hypocritical female ~ addicted to jugglery (*kaitava-tāpasī ... māyā-kuśalā*) 32,126 and 141 (TP III 99 and 101 [*kūṭa-tāpasī*]); *tapasvinī* transforms monkey back into brahmin by spell 37,238f. (TP III 199); female ~ flies up into the air 42,21 (TP III 260) and 43,198 (TP III 294); speech of *siddha-tāpasī* cannot be false 42,26 (TP III 261); ~ becomes *vidyādhara* by conjuring up *vīra-vetālas* 55,208 (TP IV 216); hen-crow (*balākā*) incinerated (*bhasmasād abhūt*) by ~’s look 56,172 (TP IV 232); ~ laughs out of sorrow about a parrot 59,56 (TP V 30); ~ digs up necklace in mouse hole 61,111 (TP V 78); king returns from lustration of town (*nagara-bhrama*) after bowing to ~ 61,206 (TP V 85); female heretic ~ (*pākhaṇḍā kṣudra-tāpasī*) advises mother to kill son 61,290 (TP V 94); ~ turns mouse into girl 62,125 (TP V 109); young ~ (*muni-putraka*) terrifies another young ~ with a snake and is cursed 65,89 (TP V 161 “son of a hermit”; ORC 755 “*jeune ascète ... fils d’ascète*”); female ~ mediates between prince and *vidyādhara* princess 65,228 (TP V 172); female ~ carries man in her arms to heaven 65,240 (TP V 173)⁸⁵; ~ curses woman for sprinkling

⁸¹ For the hermit as helper see STh N 843.

⁸² See Balbir 2001: 389f.

⁸³ Cf. STh M 411.2.

⁸⁴ ORC 1373 s.v. p. 210 note 2: “*C’est à dire, sans doute, en yogi appartenant à une secte.*” If, however, the reading of this hapax legomenon is correct, the word *varṇin* ‘belonging to a *varṇa*’ must be comparable to *kulin* ‘of a good family’ what a *dhūrta* is not. The man apparently is an outcaste. This is also clear from the black goat-skin of his disguise by which he simulates performing brahmin sacrifices and thus belong to a (higher) *varṇa*.

⁸⁵ For a picture see Quintillana 2007: Fig. 234f. < Mathura, ca. 15 CE ?

him with water at bathing 67,92 (TP V 202)⁸⁶; ~ illuminates altar-platform as if a second fire (*vahni*) in human form 69,179 (TP VI 21); woman sent out as spy in ~ disguise (*tāpasī-veṣa*) with rosary, matted hair and deer skin 71,130 (TP VI 45); ~ mutilated by robbers 72,265f. (TP VI 88); ~ = Bodhisattva rescues love-sick man from delusion 72,315 (TP VI 92); Death (Kāla) cannot enter ~ Śveta's ashram beyond River Tarangiṇī 72,335 (TP VI 94); ~ performs nightly rites with king on charnel ground in order to evoke *vetāla* 73,278ff. (TP VI 120f., cf. 56,215ff. [TP IV 235]); ~ described as enchanter 73,283 (TP VI 121); shore of Ganges is full of leaf-huts (*uṭaja*) of ~ 74,110 (TP VI 148); suitor becomes ~ after death of beloved 76,15 (TP VI 180)⁸⁷; king leaves country in disguise of ~ 86,70 (TP VII 18); king worships ~ three times a day 91,42 (TP VIII 85); king sees ~ maiden, daughter of Kaṇva, in dress of bark 94,19f. (TP VII 88); ~ with matted hair and coats of bark resembling trees 94,36 (TP VII 90); ~ sorcerer first weeps, then dances for joy, enters dead boy's body and throws his own body into ravine 97,33 (TP VII 114); king beheads ~ Kṣāntiśīla in circle of yellow powder of bones 99,3 and offers his head and heart to *vetāla* in corpse 99,18 (TP VII 122f.); ~ boy with water-vessel in his left and rosary in his right hand 101,18 (TP VII 135)⁸⁸; young ~ (*muni-putra*) able to see the future (*āyati-darśin*) 101,25 (TP VII 135); female ~ Kātyāyanī is angry at prince not hearing her blessing 101,54 (TP VII 138); ~ maiden seized by crocodile which prince kills 101,236 (TP VII 150); **description** of ~ 109,10 (TP VIII 70); ~ wearing matted hair and a bark garment (*jaṭā-vaḥkala-dhāriṇī*) 110,24 (TP VIII 83 wrongly 'deerskin' for 'bark'); ~ with heavenly insight (*divya-dṛk*) 118,40 (TP VIII 181); female ~ (Buddhist?)⁸⁹ *tāpasī* saves king 122,39 (TP IX 36); hypocritic ~ washes almsfood in order to be considered very pious⁹⁰ 121,158 (TP IX 23); – see also: Buddhist nun; *mahā-vratika*; mendicant; Pāśupata; *pravrajaka-stri* asceticism⁹¹ performed on bank of Ganges to obtain knowledge 40,14 (TP III 241), cf. 114,46 (TP VIII 135); Daitya *Asura* prince performs ~ for three hundred years in order to besiege Indra 115,19 (TP VIII 145); princess persists in joys of ~ (*tapah-sukha*) 66,151 (TP V 189); ~ performed to find out wonder 114,46 (TP VIII 135)⁹²; *Asura* child performs ~ in order to get heavenly arms (*divyāstrāṇi*) 115,16 (TP VIII 145); ~ exhausted by crimes 115,96 (TP VIII 151); ~ of Viṣṇu c.s. to please Śiva who appears in *liṅga* 115,122 (TP VIII 152); princess performs ~ to ensure success of lover 116,57 (TP VIII 159)⁹³;

⁸⁶ The sprinkling may resemble donation water by which the woman apparently gives herself to the ascetic.

⁸⁷ STh T 211.5.

⁸⁸ Is this boy lefthanded ?

⁸⁹ According to TP IX 39 note 3 on 122,81 *vihāra-nirgatā*.

⁹⁰ In order to remove the evil of the giver; cf. the foolish ascetic Tāmali in Vinayavijaya's *Lokaparakāśa* 858 who washes his rice pudding twentyone times (Mette 2010: 135).

⁹¹ See, e.g. Dumont 1959.

⁹² This place and 116,57 below are taken to rank under *bāla-tapas* by Mette in her Würzburg paper 2013.

⁹³ This is a kind of transfer of merit (q.v.).

hypocritic ~ described 121,157 (TP IX 23); – see also: austerities; fast; washing ascetic’s staff like bed-post (*khaṭvâṅga*)⁹⁴ 70,3 (TP VI 23); ashes, Pāśupata ascetics sit in circle of ~ (*bhasman*) 37,62 (TP III 187); demon of fever has a handful of ~ by way of a weapon 71,216 (TP VI 51); ascetic’s body smeared with ~ 73,283 (TP VI 121)⁹⁵; suitor makes ~ of beloved his bed (*bhasma-śayya*) 76,14 and is then considered her husband 76,40 (TP VI 180f.); child revived by throwing dust with spell on its ~ 76,19ff. (TP VI 180); at rite with corpse mendicant smears his limbs with ~ 99,11 (TP VII 123); *kāpālika* throws ~ on pyre, extinguishes fire and so revives brahmin’s wife 124,9 (TP IX 68); – see also: ascetic; child; crane; dust; evil eye; hunter; Indra; *kāpālika*; magic circle; magic rite; nectar; Pāśupata ascetic; pyre; snake; spell(s); suitors; tree

āśi ‘blessing’, Śiva gives married couple ~ 24,167 (TP II 181); hermit’s ~ of a woman: “Obtain a husband” 28,80 (TP III 26)

askance, dice are the sidelong loving looks of (the goddess of) ill luck (*a-śrī-kaṭākṣa-pātāḥ ... akṣāḥ*) 73,76 (TP VI 106); looking ~, see: left hand; – see further: eye

āskandin ‘appropriating, robbing’ 24,87 (TP II 176 ‘[who] withholds’; MW ‘granting’; ORC 210 ‘*il s’ approprié*’); – see: *purohita*

aśoka tree (Jonesia Asoca Syn.),⁹⁶ nymph standing under ~ and summoning prince 35,8 (TP III 155); ~ in northern part of Vindhya forest under which is Nāga-king palace 70,58 (TP VI 28); ascetic princess sitting at foot of ~ 71,248 (TP VI 54); corpse at foot of ~ 73,286 (TP VI 121); woman, seeing husband and brother headless in Durgā temple, fastens creeper to ~ in order to hang herself⁹⁷ (*pāśaṃ viracayamāsa latayāśoka-pādape*) 80,42 (TP VI 207); woman unhappy due to separation from lover wants to hang herself on ~ in front of Gaurī temple 90,73 (TP VII 54); 95,31 (TP VII 100); weeping queen sits under shade of ~ 98,23 (TP VII 117); ~ beloved for suicide by hanging 103,42 (TP VII 178)⁹⁸; scarlet (*lohita*) ~ 104,91 (TP VIII 7); princess waiting under ~ for husband 105,43 (TP VIII 24); 119,185 (TP VIII 206); – see also: suicide

āśrama-krama ‘(fourfold) order of the stages of life’ 24,151 (TP II 180)

A-śrī, (goddess of) Ill-Luck 73,76 (TP VI 106);

ass, see: donkey

assassins, nocturnal 19,82 (TP II 91); ~ cut off brahmin’s hands and feet 33,48 (TP III 110);

assembly of learned men (*vidvat-sabhā*) compared to lotus-bed 72,74 (TP VI 74); ~ of the gods see: Caitra

⁹⁴ Gonda 1975: IV 160ff. does not deal with this word for the ascetic’s staff it being different from that used by a Vedic student. – See further infra sub *khaṭvâṅga*.

⁹⁵ For ashes as protection against evil spirits see Meyer 1937: I 107f.

⁹⁶ See ORC 1539f. In many scenes the poet may have had the supposed etymology of the word (‘without grief’) in mind. Kuv note 346, Further: Duda 2006: 289; Blatter & Walter 1954: 130ff. and plate XXVII; Cowen 1970: 5.

⁹⁷ ORC 930: “(elle) arrangea en forme de lacet une liane qui se trouvait sur un arbre aśoka.”

⁹⁸ Probably because of the red colour of the flowers red being connected with death. Condemnees wear red rags and garland (Bollée 2002 § 754).

assertion, false ~ of having seen Golden city (Kānaka-purī) 24,68 (TP II 174); – see also:
false information

association, see: comparisons

āstām ‘never mind!’ 117,167 (TP VIII 175; ORC 1228: “*il suffit!*”)

asterism of birth (*janmarkṣa*) 32,14 (TP III 91)

āsthāna ‘hall of audience’, see: durbar

astrologers’ (*gaṇaka*) prediction 12,13 (TP I 134); 32,5 and 22 (TP III 90 and 92); ~ fix time (*lagne parikalpīte*) for royal journey 15,127 (TP II 12); minister makes secret arrangement with ~ to fix a distant date (*saṃvidam dūra-lagna-pradānāya*) for royal marriage 31,79 (TP III 88; cf. 32,5 [TP III 90]); *mauhūrtikāḥ* 34,247 (TP III 147); king marries merchant woman against date advised by ~ 36,53-59 (TP III 173); ~ scorned with bad consequences 36,94 (TP III 176); ~ asked about prospective husband 52,139 (TP IV 147); ~ denies favourable moment for war 54,150 (TP IV 194); ~ kills son in sleep 61,256 (TP V 90); ~ (*astra-vedin*) prognosticate son to become thief 72,192 (TP VI 82); – see also: marriage

a-śuci ‘impurity’, see: flies

a-śūdrāna-bhuk ‘living on rice in the husk’, brahmin considered virtuous because ~ 33,134 (TP III 118)

Asura(s), brahmin hero enters (immense) city of Daitya maidens which looked like serpent Ananta emerged from the earth 10,49 (TP I 109); Maya’s daughter does not remember former birth 29,6 (TP III 39); Maya gives up *Asura*-ship and flees to Śiva 29,12 (TP III 40); delusive power of ~ Maya 29,60 (TP III 43); ~ *asurī* Uṣā finds husband of Caurī’s dream boon on magic painting of the world 31,19f. (TP III 82); fragrant breeze precedes appearance of ~ Maya 45,3 (IV 17); red garment of ~ Maya resembling flowing streams of cinnabar 45,4 (IV 17); ~ princess 45,234f. (TP IV 33) and, with a body dark as a *dūrvā*-grass stalk, 333 (TP IV 39); Diti and Danu as mothers of the ~ 45,365f. (TP IV 41); ~ as soon as killed by gods, reanimated by Namuci’s horse Uccaiḥśravas smelling them⁹⁹ 46,224 (TP IV 63); disguise of ~ Mahāmāya 50,38 (TP IV 110); gods flee from battle with ~ 50,83 (TP IV 140f.); gods and renounce enmity 50,97 (TP IV 114); ~ are ever generous (*nitya-saṃbhāvinaḥ*) 50,121 (TP IV 115); ~ killed by Vikramasena, a portion of Śiva 99,33 (TP VII 124) and by Śiva and Viṣṇu are reborn as Mlecchas 120,19 (TP IX 2); ~ devouring police officers at night 112,35 (TP VIII 108); *asurī* bewildered with love 112,50 (TP VIII 109); every year five ministers must perish unless water is sacrificed to (manes of) ~ 112,57 (TP VIII 110); Śiva kills ~ Andhaka, a mind-born son of Pārvatī 114,78 (TP VIII 138); after austerities ~ Vidyuddhvaja gets Brahmā weapon 105,19ff. (TP VIII 145); ~ gets boon from Śambhu 115,49 (TP VIII 147); sacrifice to deities with heads of ~ 116,60 (TP VIII 160); ~ seeking refuge in Pātāla¹⁰⁰ 118,15 (TP VIII 179); ~ impeding hermit’s sacrifice 118,50 (TP VIII 181); description of beautiful ~ princesses 118,162ff. (TP VIII 189); Agni-Hutabhuk consumes ~ body of Daitya princess 119,201

⁹⁹ On the smell of the Asura Maya see 45,3 (TP IV 17).

¹⁰⁰ Asuras live in Pātāla, see Mbh 5,97,1.

(TP VIII 207); *deva-loka* exhausted when ~ kill brahmins and gods no longer obtain sacrifices 120,21f. (TP IX 2f.); – see also: address; Agni; battle;
asurī nun (*brahma-cāriṇī*) in white garments (*su-sitāmbara-saṃvītā*) 29,52f. (TP III 42);
aśvamedha, heroic king who has offered ~ 44,123 (TP IV 9); Indra wants ~ to be performed before sacrifice to Rudra 45,18 (TP IV 18);
aśvattha (*Ficus religiosa*)¹⁰¹, fig tree, *yakṣa* speaks from ~ 20,37 (TP II 97); ascetic under ~ 25,14 (TP II 189); *yakṣa* princess emerges from ~¹⁰² 26,210 (TP II 233); *brahma-rākṣasa* dwelling in ~ 94,71 (TP VII 92); – see also: tree worship
 asylum for gamblers (*kitavānāṃ mahā-maṭha*) in Mālava 73,189 (TP VI 115)
 asylum seeker, see: economic emigrant
ātadā conjecture for *padā* 55,184 (TP IV 215)
a-tarkya-tapas (not MW) ‘whose penance surpasses imagination’ (?) 24,163 (TP II 181
 “whose asceticism is incomprehensible”¹⁰³, ORC 214: “*dont l’ascétisme défie l’imagination*”)
aṭavi ‘desert’, description of ~ 100,7ff. (TP VII 128); – see also: forest
 Atharva-vedin prescribed as *purohita* in Arthaśāstra (1,9,9) 34,193 (TP III 142);
ātma-ghātin ‘self-killer, suicide’ condemned 45,93 (TP IV 23)
ātmōpahāra ‘self-offering, suicide’ in order to propitiate Devī 72,19 (TP VI 69); – see also: appeasement
ātodya ‘percussion instrument, kind of drum?’, sound of festive ~ (*maṅgalātodya-vādya*) at royal coronation 15,404 (TP II 80); 34,171 (TP III 140)¹⁰⁴
ātodya-maṅgala (not MW) ‘auspicious drum (music)’ 104,127 (TP VIII 11; ORC 1095: “rituelles fanfares”); – see also: *ātodya*; drum
 attack by robbers at night 54,126 (TP IV 192); – see also: night
aṭṭa-hāsa-hasitā ‘with the loud laugh’ (epithet of Cāmuṇḍā)¹⁰⁵ 52,159 (TP IV 149)
 attendants, female ~ compared to sciences granting desires 22,4 (TP II 137); – see also: address; bee(s); confidante
 attractivity stereotype of hermit¹⁰⁶ 28,78 and 84 (TP III 26)
 attractivity stereotype, ~ (*nakha-sikhā*)¹⁰⁷ of man 26,64 (TP II 222); 28,51 (TP III 24); 103,22ff. (TP VII 176);
 attractivity stereotype of prince 23,69f. (TP II 162); ~ of royals: *rākṣasī*’s mind captivated by beauty of prince (*rūpāhṛta-mānasa*) 39,85 (TP III 223); when beholding one another’s

¹⁰¹ *Aśvattha* is the most prominent tree in Bhag X 26. – See further: Upadhyaya 1965: 3f.; Macmillan 1991: 462; Haberman 2013: 137 under: banyan.

¹⁰² Franziera 2010: 11.

¹⁰³ In a note TP remark that there is probably a double meaning in the word “incomprehensible”.

¹⁰⁴ Sivaramamurti 1970: 76; 1980: 181 and fig. 68, a 2nd century B.C.E. terracotta.

¹⁰⁵ Siegel 1989: 94ff.

¹⁰⁶ On the erotic powers of the ascetic see, e.g., O’Flaherty 1973: 55f.

¹⁰⁷ Sarup 1933; Meyer 1952: 434 note; Lienhard 1984: 144f.; Chojnacki 2008: I 62 note 38. The term properly belongs to the description of female beauties.

beauty the expanded eye of each was extended to the ear, as if to inform that organ that the report it had heard before was true 51,181 (TP IV 134)

attractivity stereotype of woman¹⁰⁸ **4,6ff.** (TP I 30f.) and of *Asura* princess 45,234f. (TP IV 33); miss Three-world / Universe (*trailokya-sundarī*) 11,39 (TP I 125) and 32,28 (TP III 92); illuminating power of female beauty emerging from two heavenly maidens sitting together seems as if the night is lighted by three moons (*tri-candrēva yāminī*) 17,111 (TP II 43); ~ of Ahalyā surpassing in beauty the *apsaras* (*rūpa-jitāpsarās*) 17,137 (TP II 45); ~ of merchant's daughter therefore called Unmādinī 15,65 (TP II 7); ~ (*ratnaṃ tri-bhuvane*) of merchant's daughter offered as present to king 18,75 (TP II 55); by her ~ princess makes three worlds seem worthless as a blade of grass (*jagat-trayaṃ tṛṇī-kṛtya*) 18,85 (TP II 55); flat nose (*nyañcac-cipīṭa-nāsika*) as character of ugly woman 20,108 (TP II 103); ~ of merchant's wife, steeped in the nectar of pure beauty, like a moving palace of Kandarpa **34,14** (TP III 129); ~ of Kaliṅgasenā's daughter Madanamañcukā like incarnation of Rati 34,99 (TP III 135); idem 34,230 (TP III 145f.); ~ of Ratnaprabhā 35,16 (TP III 156); *asurī*, whose beauty was the wonder of the world (*jagad-āścarya-rūpā*) 45,340 (TP IV 39); red and white (*raktāvadātā*) woman captivating the eyes 47,109 (TP IV 73); ~ of Madana sundarī 55,57ff. (TP IV 206); ~ of princess Anaṅgamañjarī pouring forth rays of beauty 73,341 (TP VI 125); ~ of *kanyā divyā* 81,47 (TP VI 212); ~ of merchant's daughter shows her to be Vidyādhari fallen by a curse 93,8 (TP VII 789; princess like Śrī Nāndanī and like another moon all composed of nectar 101,69ff. (TP VII 139); ~ of hermit maiden (*kanyā lokāika-sundarī*) 101,225f. (TP VII 149); ~ of *Gandharva* princess whose body the Dhātār seems to have mixed from nectar, the moon, sandalwood, etc. (*sudhā-candra-candanādi*) 106,10 (TP VIII 28); woman like visible dryad (*sākṣād iva vana-śrī*) 120,117 (TP IX 10); painter paints girls for king to show various models of female beauty (*anyānyayā rūpa-bhaṅgyā*) 122,21 (TP IX 35); – in proper names Trailokyaprabhā and Tribhuvana prabhā 119,61 (TP VIII 197)

attributes, four ~ of Hari-Viṣṇu wait in bodily form (*sa-vigraha*) on the god 54,25 (TP IV 186); – see also: visibility

aunt (father's sister) *nāgī* invisibly protects king 55,147 and enters his body to make him support the heavy rain poured out over his head by Svāmikumāra in order to impede his penance 152f. (TP IV 212f.)

aura of light of *vidyādhari* dispells darkness (*pranna-timirā*) 18,213 (TP II 66); ~ appears from head of brahmin after muttering prayers for two hundred *kalpas* 45,83 (TP IV 23); Nārada descends from heaven in ~ (*prabhā-baddha-maṅḍala*) like a second sun 105,82 (TP VIII 27); – cf. halo

auspicious ceremony (*maṅgala*) performed before journey, see: ceremonies

auspicious marks, see: marks; mole

austerity, -ies,¹⁰⁹ propitiated by ~ Kārttikeya gives brahmin knowledge of all sciences 2,60 (TP

¹⁰⁸ See Bollée 2008a: 8; Wojtilla 2006; Rossella 2003; Zimmer 1983: I 70ff.; Meyer 1952: 434f.

I 15); brahmin with only three daughters goes to Ganges to perform ~ (to get a son ?) 3,10 (TP I 19); brahmin living by (only) smoking (*dhūma-paś cāpi*) as ~ 7,53 (TP I 79), cf. Namuci smokes (lit.: drinks smoke) as ~ 46,218 (TP IV 63); Bālakhilyas perform ~ under branch of *kalpa-taru* 12,142 (TP I 144); Agni propitiated by ~ gives brahmin sword that comes to him when thought of 18,110 (TP II 58)¹¹⁰; by ~ Gaurī obtains Tryambaka-Śiva as a husband 20,61 (TP II 100); Kandarpa disturbs Śiva's ~ and is burnt 20,66 (TP II 100); king of Vatsa performs ~ to propitiate Śiva for his conquest of the regions 19,4 (TP II 84); hermit standing with head downward in river, afterwards looking into the sun,¹¹¹ etc. 24,94 (TP II 176); *rājput* says to rogue (*dhūrta*) ascetic: "I greet you whose ~ surpasses imagination (or: is incomprehensible ?)" 24,163 (TP II 181); hermit gives half of his (merit of) ~ to king in exchange for princess,¹¹² and king ascends to heaven 28,90 (TP III 26f.); happiness is procurable by ~ 30,10 (TP III 64); *vidyādhara* youth performs ~ on one foot in order to propitiate Ambikā's husband (Śiva) to give him an *apsaras* for wife 30,11 (TP III 64); ~ with heels upwards (*ūrdhva-pāda*) 32,99 (TP III 97; cf. 40,102 [TP III 248]); ~ as a sacrifice to a deity to obtain something 34,40 (TP III 130); ~ useless to acquire knowledge 40,20 (TP III 241); ~ in order to become beautiful (*rūpa-draviṇa-kāṅkṣayā*) 40,27 (TP III 242); ~ of hanging from banyan by the feet till body dried up and man died 40,102 (TP III 248); recollection of pre-birth and knowledge produced by ~ 40,106 (TP III 248); ~ on bed of *darbha* to get boon from Durgā 54,162 (TP IV 195); king's ~ impeded by heavy rain 55,152 (TP IV 212f.); ~ to get a son from Kārtikeya 55,156 (TP IV 213); ~ enable parrot to remember what it learned in a pre-birth 59,158 (TP V 37); part-incarnation of Bodhisattva engaged in ~ (*tapas*) 65,14 (TP V 154); *vedī* illuminated by *maharṣi* with ~ as by real fire (*mūrtena vahninā*) 69,179 (TP VI 21); prince vows to attain the condition of a wishing tree by ~ 72,223 (TP VI 85); Indra pleased with ~ (*tivra-tapas*) gives boon to prince 72,225 (TP VI 85); king propitiates Śiva with ~ to get a son 83,9 (TP VII 2); sleeping on *kuśa* grass as ~ 101,219 (TP VII 149); king sleeping on the ground, bathing in the early morning, eating fruits 107,81 (TP VIII 48); king propitiated Caṇḍī with ~ to get sword and wife 112,26 (TP VIII 106f.); brahmins desperate at being ordered to eat the food of a *caṇḍāla* perform ~ in shrine of Mahākāla 112,180 (TP VIII 120); ~ performed for Hara by royals to find out wonder of golden *haṃsas* offering unfading flowers 114,46 (TP VIII 135); ~ of living three hundreds years on fruits, etc. make Brahmā give *Asura* B.-weapon 105,19 (TP VIII 145); Daitya standing between five fires in summer 115,45 (TP VIII 147)¹¹³; ~ propitiate Śambhu for son 115,86 (TP VIII

¹⁰⁹ Austerities are giving up something and thus a kind of donation to the deity for whom one performs *tapas*, as is clear e.g. at 34,40 (TP III 130); see Dange 1987: 638, but when performed for a return gift confirm the proverb: no pain no gain (see also: *tapas*). In the Upaniṣads *tapas* is practised for creative power: the realisation of the Self (O'Flaherty 1973: 40).

¹¹⁰ Cf. STh D 855.2.

¹¹¹ Cf. the name *Sūryatapas* in 25,14 (TP II 189).

¹¹² For "*tapas* for spouse" see Doniger O'Flaherty 1973: 378 25ea. See also *infra*: transfer of merit.

150); there is nothing that ~ cannot accomplish **117,174** (TP VIII 76); ~ to get husband 117,179 (TP VIII 176); ~ performed by wife and daughters on behalf of imprisoned husband and father 118,108 (TP VIII 185)¹¹⁴; temple of ~ on slope of Mt Meru 119,90 (TP VIII 199); – see also: *a-tarpya-tapas*; fast
austerities, performed by *devas*, see: Hara (Hari, etc. propitiate Hara by ~)
auto-biography of mouse 61,107ff. (TP V 77f.); ~ of lion 65,57ff. (TP V 159f.); ~ of golden-crested bird 65,71ff. (TP V 160f.); ~ of snake 65,84ff. (TP V 161);
automata, wooden, of humans, horses and elephants, moving but lifeless (*nirjīva*) by their want of speech (*vāg-virahāt*) 43,11f. (TP III 281); – see also: human statues and TP III 56-9;
autumn, expedition facilitated by ~ as harbinger of good fortune (*siddhi-dūtyēva śaradā*) 19,64 (TP II 89); enemies treated as ~ treats clouds 19,94 (TP II 92); moon digit rides on ~ cloud 22,107 (TP II 145); face like an ~ cloud 47,107 (TP IV 73); flocks of geese in a hot ~ (*śarat-kāle sōṣmaṇi*) 55,33 (TP IV 205); riches pass away like an autumn cloud 96,24 (TP VII 109); ~ with open-lotus face and smile of unclosed flowers is time for journeys 122,71f. (TP IX 39); – see also: cloud
avadhi-jñāna (‘clairvoyance’), see Chojnacki 2008: II note 871.
avalambasva ! ‘be patient, *patienza* !’ 124,243 (TP IX 85)
Avanti represented by forest 70,123 (TP VI 33);
avarice as internal enemy of king 34,191 (TP III 142)
āvarta ‘curl of hair on a horse’ (neck or chest)¹¹⁵, see: *rocāmāna* and cf. *śrī-vṛkṣa*
avaśya-kārya ‘necessary duties’ of a king 59,1 (TP V 26)
avatāra, son of king Vatsa is ~ of Kāma 23,73 (TP II 163); prince is ~ of *vidyādhara* 66,171 (TP V 191); – see also: rebirth
aversion, from husband (*bhartr-vidveṣa*) 52,355 (TP IV 162); ~ to marriage,¹¹⁶ see: marriage; – ~ to the male sex, see: *punī-dveṣiṇī*
averting calamities, see: *iti-ghna*; ~ evil, see: meditation
Avīci hell, naked seducer thrown into ditch like ~ 13,149 (TP I 161); pseudo-ascetic anoints his body with thick clay, as if testing his destined smearing with mud of the ~ (*kardamālepa*) 24,93 (TP II 176)
awaking sleeping princess 3,65 (TP I 23); 86,99 (TP VII 20); 105,62 (TP VIII 25)
āyatanōddeśa (‘spot in the temple’) 71,97 (TP VI 42, see note 1);
a-yaśas, see calumny
ayo-daṇḍa ‘iron rod’ (not MW) as weapon 50,14 (TP IV 109)
Ayodhyā, famous in the three worlds 69,15 (TP VI 10)¹¹⁷; ~ Rāma’s capital 88,3 (TP VII 35);

¹¹³ See Bollée 2010: 74 note 450.

¹¹⁴ Cf. Gonda 1985: 125.

¹¹⁵ See Caland 2010: 12 and 14; further e.g., Kuv 23.17; 24.1-9; *Mānasollāsa* II 4,668ff. (p. 211f.).

¹¹⁶ STh T 311.1.

¹¹⁷ See Kuv p. 44ff.; Bakker 1986.

a-yoni-ja ‘not born in the usual way’ (best example: *Sītā*), see: birth

babies radiating at birth, see: light

bachelor or stag party (?) of *yakṣas* 73,39f. (TP VI 103);

Badarikā, a Vaiṣṇava hermitage north of Śrīnagar 52,313 (TP IV 159 with note);

-baddha in compounds,¹¹⁸ see: *prabhā-baddha* (see: aura of light); *mantra-baddha* (see: spell)

baddha-bhāva ‘enamoured of, in love with’ 93,38 (TP VII 81)

baddhōttariyaka ‘with upper garment girded around one’ [not MW] 81,40 (TP VI 211); – see also: girding up one’s loins

baddhvā, buddhvā 96,26 (TP VII 110), read: *ṽddhvā*?

bāhu-yuddha-keli (‘wrestling’)¹¹⁹ 74,51 (TP VI 144);

bail, to give ~ (*vastū-karoti*) 60,225 (TP V 60)

baka ‘heron’,¹²⁰ *rākṣasa* disguised as ~ 39,58 (TP III 222); snake eats young of ~ and is killed by mongoose following pieces of fish to its hole 60,236 (TP V 61 ‘crane’)

Bakakaccha, reading of TP for D: Marukaccha 6,166 (TP I 72); – see also: Bhṛgukaccha

baksheesh, see: gift

bakula (*Mimusops Elenği* Lin.) 111,15 (TP VIII 96 with note 3)¹²¹

Bālakhilyas do penance under branch of *kalpa-taru* 12,142 (TP I 144)

balance (*tulā*) of iron deposited with merchant and presumably eaten by mice (*ākhu*) 60,239 (TP V 62)¹²²

bāla-pravrājikā ‘female itinerant mendicant from childhood’,¹²³ because hit by father with foot 66,156-8 (TP V 190); – see also: childhood

bald, man (*khalita*) with head like copper pot pelted with wood-apples 61,50 (TP V 72); ~

idiot 61,180 (TP V 83); removing his head-dress rogue doctor showed ~ head (*khalvāṭaṃ bhisak chiraḥ apāsya veṣṭanaṃ ... adarśayat*) to ~ idiot 61,184 (TP V 83);

ball, prince playing at ~ hits female ascetic 42,9 (TP III 259)¹²⁴ and 65,217 (TP V 171f.);

severed heads of heroes compared to game of ~ (*kanduka-kriḍā*) with which Death is amusing himself 50,7 (TP IV 108)

bamboo(s) thrown into lake Mānasa turn into bows 46,99 (TP IV 55); snake concealed in ~ (*vaṃśa-nāḍī-niveśita*) 69,68 (TP VI 13)

¹¹⁸ Cf. Balbir 1998.

¹¹⁹ See, e.g., Raghavan 1979: 45f.; 49ff. et passim.

¹²⁰ Dave 2005: 389ff. *Baka* is the common name of ibis, storks and herons.

¹²¹ Dallapiccola 2002: 35; Macmillan 1991: 304; Syed 1990: 238f.

¹²² According to Strabo XV 1,53 and Nicolaus Damasc. 44 Indians have no suits about deposits and, if unable to recover a loan, have no remedy at law. All the creditor can do is to blame himself for trusting a rogue (McCrinkle 1960: 68 and 72).

¹²³ See Mette 2013.

¹²⁴ Cf. 22,138 (TP II 147) where a garland falls on the back of an ascetic who then curses a *vidyādhara*. – On the ball game see Syed 200a; Biarreau 1979.

bamboo wood, king of ~ , see: *veṇu-vanīśvara*

bandha ‘pawn’ 21,87 (TP II 132); – see also: ‘imprisonment’

bandhūka,¹²⁵ lips lovely as the ~ tree 34,231 (TP III 146)

bandits (*caura*), see: robbers

banishment, brahmins order ~ from city of ascetic for presumedly eating their children 24,214

(TP II 185); ~ of adulteress after murder of husband 58,77 (TP V 20); thief cut off tongue and hands, and banished (*nirvāsita*) 60,232 (TP V 61)¹²⁶; ~ of watchman as punishment for waking up dreaming king 122,31 (TP IX 36); – see also: expulsion; Kālarātrī; punishment

banner, of red cloth¹²⁷ (*dhvaja-raktāṃśuka-*) 18,9 (TP II 49 “red silk”; ORC 131: “mousseline rouge”; MI 186: “leuchtend roten Tüchern”); ~ like lightning 18,50 (TP II 53); cloth ~

displayed out of joy 18,121 (TP II 58); 19,72 (TP II 90); city dancing with delight, imitating with ~s uplifted the arms of a dancing-girl 20,222 (TP II 115); ~ of red cloth

(*raktāṃśuka*) on Durgā’s temple compared to tongue of Death 22,63 (TP II 141); *chatra-dhvajāṅka-nīrdhūli-pādābja* as mark on feet of *vidyādhara* king 33,178 (TP III 122);

patāka-paṭa- 34,121 (TP III 137); 38,20 (TP III 207); ~ of Sundarapura 52,12 (TP IV

139); scarlet (*sindūra*) ~s of Kauśāmbī 54,77 (TP IV 189); conquered queen as king’s ~ of victory 54,238 (TP IV 201); golden ~ rising from sea 81,34 (TP VI 211); king and Rājput

dive after ~ sinking into sea and reach splendid city of Pārvatī 81,74 (TP VI 214); temple

~s in Vārāṇasī cry out to come and attain salvation 93,83 (TP VII 84);

banquet of wine (*pāna-bhū*), filled with many crystal goblets of wine (*madhu-sphaṭikāneka-caṣaka*) 21,10 (TP II 126)

banyan-tree, see: fig tree

bar, see: *āpāna-bhū(mi)*

barber (*nāpita*),¹²⁸ cunning ~ 32,135 (TP III 99);

barber’s wife enjoyed by king 32,149 and declared witch 32,156 (TP III 102);

bard(s) (*bandī*) panegyricize the king and thus see to his public relations 18,8 (TP II 49)¹²⁹; ~ of *vidyādhara*s in divine concert 50,150 (TP IV 117); ~ in Kośalā recites stanza on Haṃsāvali

71,69 (TP VI 40); ~ as matchmaker 71,78 (TP VI 41); ~ enters monastery (? *maṭha*), gets food and pair of clothes,¹³⁰ and sees *citra-paṭa* ‘picture’ with female beauty 122,73f.

(TP IX 39); – see also: herald; minstrel

¹²⁵ *Pentapetes phoenicea* or *Terminalia tomentosa* (MW). In ORC 1542 with the above reference the red colour of this tree is mentioned as that of sunset.

¹²⁶ Cf. Daś 116.12 where also a merchant is expelled for theft.

¹²⁷ Cf. Kād 110,7f. of the adoration of Kāma with *ālohītāṃśuka-patākair pūjā*; Kād. 111,1 etc., and further, e.g. Sontheimer 1995: 280. *Aṃśuka* in MW is (cotton) cloth, muslin which makes better sense for banners. than silk as is also translated by Layne 1991. The use of flags, according to Crooke 1896: II 24, may, in the same way as waving the hand around the head, be explained as averting evil spirits.

¹²⁸ Barbers are considered low-caste, see TP III 100f. note.

¹²⁹ See, e.g., Bonisoli Alquati 2006: 98; Gonda 1969: 46f.; Saletore 1943: 253f.

¹³⁰ Bards erring between princely courts were honoured with clothes also in mediaeval Europe: Curtius 1965: 463.

bark, hermit-maiden shining in dress of ~ (*valkalâṃśuka-śobhinī*) 94,19 (TP VII 88)¹³¹;
 whistling of loose ~ (*tāra-cīra-cītkāra*) of dry creepers compared to screaming (*rodinī*)
 forest 73,240 (TP VI 118); 110,24 (TP VIII 83); – see also: *bhūrja*; garment; hermit
 barley (*yava*) sown in house by witch 71,266 (TP VI 56); – see: magic seed; witch
 barley-meal charmed and eaten turns witch into she-goat (*chāgī*) 71,273 (TP VI 56);
 bashfulness, see: eye; gestures
 basilisks (*drg-viṣāhi*) placed as guardians at cave-passage 109,69 (TP VIII 75)
 basket (*mañjūṣā*), exposition of beautiful daughter on river Ganges in ~ with lamp on top 15,38
 (TP II 4)¹³²; monkey in ~ 15,45 (TP II 5)¹³³; ~ (*karaṇḍikā*) with magic dolls 29,10 (TP
 III 39); woman receives every night lover with leather-covered ~ let down from window
 (*carma-peṭā gavākṣeṇa*) 64,100 (TP V 147)¹³⁴; 123,164 (TP IX 55); – see also: ear;
 exposure; winnowing basket
 bastard, see: abuse
 bathing discomfort eased by *liṅga* cake, see: cake
 bathing¹³⁵, in Ganges following vow 4,28 (TP I 32); 6,97 (TP I 67); ~ in blood as *dohada*
 9,46 (TP I 97)¹³⁶ and 30,46 (TP III 67); Buddhists are released from ~ 27,19 (TP III 2); ~
 as auspicious ceremony 65,234 (TP V 173); midday is ~ time for king (*snāna-velā*) 86,24
 (TP VII 15)¹³⁷; ~ in the early morning as penance 107,81 (TP VIII 48); stealing clothes of
 ~ women 108,68 (TP VIII 58) and 121,110 (TP IX 20); ~ three times a day 121,158
 (TP IX 23); – see also: garment
 bathing festival, see: *snāna-yātrōtsava*
 bathing place, see *tīrtha*
 bathing time, see: bathing; midday
 battle (*yuddha*),¹³⁸ between gods and Asuras 9,13 (TP I 95); ~ as joy 27,139 (TP III 11);
 women want to see great ~ (*mahāhava*) 46,27 (TP IV 50); (in a dream) stream of water is
 ~ 46,142 (TP IV 58); ~ (*saṃgrāma*)¹³⁹ as feast 47,35 (TP IV 69); ~ formation as
 needle (*sūci-vyūha*) 47,40 and crescent (*ardha-candra*) 42 (TP IV 69)¹⁴⁰; gods come to see
 ~ 47,45 (TP IV 69) and 48,2 (TP IV 75); ~ gives delight to heroes, jackals and *bhūtas*
 47,53 (TP IV 70); arrangement of ~ as disk (*cakra-vyūha*) or *vajra* 48,3 (TP IV 75); dis
 guised ~ of *devas* and *Asuras* 48,14 (TP IV 76); twelve heroes fleeing from ~ 48,87 (TP

¹³¹ The dress of people hunting and gathering (Ruben 1962: 89 note 2). See further Crooke 1919: 240f.

¹³² STh S 331.

¹³³ STh K 1625 (ad.).

¹³⁴ STh *K 1343.1.

¹³⁵ Vasu 1918: 12f.

¹³⁶ Cf. Maten 1973: 16 note 1.

¹³⁷ An extensive description of a royal bath is given in Kād 31,7ff. See further Gode 1961 I: 53ff.

¹³⁸ See ORC 1544.

¹³⁹ Malamoud 1976: 5.

¹⁴⁰ See Date 1929: 73 and 75; Dikshitar 1987: 241 and 271f.

IV 80); gods fleeing from ~ with *Asuras* 50,83 (TP IV 113); snake king fleeing from ~ is cursed by *Vāsukī* 72,34 (TP VI 70); **description** of ~ 74,281ff. (TP VI 160); do, 103,4 (TP VII 175); ~ (*yuddha*) between brother and sister 105,87 (TP VIII 27); **description** of ~ 107,99ff. (TP VIII 50; Zin 2003b: 157 note 41); feast of ~ (*raṇḍtsava*) 116,60 (TP VIII 160); – see also: combat; curiosity; dream; five days; flowers; goddess of Fortune; horse; joy; *mandāra* tree; *rākṣasa*; Śāstras; single combat; spectators

battle-arrangement: needle (*sūci-vyūha*) 47,40 or crescent (*ardha-candra*) 42 (TP IV 69); discus (*cakra-vyūha*) or *vajra-vyūha* 48,3 (TP IV 75)

battle-field compared to lake with the faces of heroes like full-blown lotuses 50,6 (TP IV 108); ~ to stage (*saṅgrāmāṅga-raṅga*) 74,285 (TP VI 160);

bawd,¹⁴¹ old ~ (*kuṭṭanī*) seems lump of poison (*viṣa-cchaṭā*) to young men 12,79 (TP I 139); ~ requires reward for giving birth to daughter (*sutā-phala*) 12,163 (TP I 146); ~ shaved and painted black and red as a *Gaṇa* to enter heaven 12,169f. (TP I 146 with note 2); naked ~ put on pillar at night 12,175 (TP I 147)¹⁴²; merchant's son entrusted to ~ to learn the tricks of courtesans 57,58 (TP V 5); ~ as embodiment of ugliness (with massive jaw,¹⁴³ long teeth, and snub nose¹⁴⁴) instructs daughter 57,60 (TP V 5); ~ throws out lover stripped of wealth 57,118 (TP V 9); ~ teaches victim of other ~ how to get back his wealth 57,140ff. (TP V 10)¹⁴⁵; ~ snaps up gold producing rice grains vomited by brahmin 108,81 (TP VIII 60); laughter for having been tricked by a ~ 108,87 (TP VIII 60);

bear curses prince to become insane (*unmatta*) for betraying friend 5,87 (TP I 53f.)

beard of a brahmin like swarm of bees come to feed on the lotus of his face 104,180 (TP VIII 14)

beauty (*rūpa*), female, male see: attractivity stereotype¹⁴⁶; goddess presiding over moon's ~ (*īndor lāvanya*) 17,109 (TP II 43); heavenly ~ looking as if she were the medicine to revitalize Smara (= Kāma) burnt by the fire of Hara's wrath (*Hara-kopāgni-nirdagdha-Smara-saṃjīvanāuśadhi*) 18,213 (TP II 66); with sea of ~ flowing between banks of her breasts (*āpūrṇa-tuṅga-stana-taṭāntayā lāvanyāmbu-taraṅgiṇyā*) *apsaras* will sweep away even a person who can restrain his passions 27,65 (TP III 6); ~ of Rambhā's daughter 28,76 (TP III 26); fascinating ~ (*rūpeṇa jagat-tritaya-mohinī*) of princess is like the bunch of peacock feathers of the juggler Kāma 30,3 (TP III 64); ~ of man (*rūpavattara*) is the **main criterion for marriage** 31,55 (TP III 87)¹⁴⁷; fascinating ~ (*kanyā jagad-unmāda-kāriṇī*) of merchant's daughter 33,62 (TP III 111) and of brahmin 123,318 (TP IX 65); matchless

¹⁴¹ Cf. STh T 452; Bollée 2008a: 9 note 21.

¹⁴² People's laughing at this incident would fit better 12,186 (TP I 148) than 57, 54ff. (Siegel 1989: 123).

¹⁴³ *Sthūla-hanu*. This seems to be a masculine mark for the Buddha Gotama's grandfather and the former king of Cambodia who were called Siṃhahanu, respectively Sihanuk.

¹⁴⁴ For the flat nose as mark of masculine ugliness see: nose.

¹⁴⁵ See Siegel 1989: 121.

¹⁴⁶ See, e.g., Mette 1973.

¹⁴⁷ An Indian kind of calocagathy ?

woman, captivated by his ~, wants that man for husband 33,185 (TP III 122) and 39,85 (TP III 273); idem, wherever any princess beheld a certain prince she was immediately fascinated by love and chose him for husband 44,42ff. (TP IV 4); Sūryaprabha, with same beautiful body as he has now (*anenāiva kāntena vapuṣā*)¹⁴⁸, can by magic become *khecarēśvara* 45,53 (TP IV 20); ~ of man (*rūpa*) and woman (*dr̥ṣṭi*) 45,207 (TP IV 31); princess as ~ of the three worlds (*triloka-sundarī*) 45,328 (TP IV 39); *Asurī*, whose ~ is the wonder of the world 45,340 (TP IV 39); painter paints king out of admiration of his ~ 51,140 (TP IV 131); *vidyādhara* prince refuses idem princess because she would be middle class ~ (*rūpeṇa madhyamā*) 52,74 (TP IV 143); brahmin suitor withholds ~ among his qualities 52,106 (TP IV 145); ~ as royal criterion for marriage 56,82 (TP IV 225); nautch-girl dances like wave of the sea of ~ (*rūpābdhi*) 57,75 (TP V 7); wife standing at window is captivated by good looks of male passer-by 58,120 (TP V 23); description of *vidyādhara* ~ 59,3ff. (TP V 26); ~ of mankind is short-lived like religious festival (*jīvaloko ... yātrādy-utsava-kṣaṇa-sundaraḥ*) 66,33 (TP V 180); ~ of a prince seems to outdo Skanda, Kandarpa and the *kalpa-druma* 71,68 (TP VI 40); *divyā stri* fascinates man with her wealth of ~ (*lāvaṇya-sampadā*) 72,342 (TP VI 94); *yakṣa* couple attracted by mutual ~ 73,34 (TP VI 103); woman as singular ~ (*lokāika-sundarī*) 73,251 (TP VI 119); princess is pouring forth rays of ~ 73,341 (TP VI 125); ~ of actor's daughter is like *amṛta* with which Hari-Viṣṇu as Mohinī bewildered the Dānavas 74,39 (TP VI 143); maiden of heavenly appearance (*divyākṛtiḥ kanyā*) fills tank with torrent of beauty 75,69 (TP VI 169), cf. 116,35 (TP VIII 158); woman shedding forth ~ like beams 75,129 (TP VI 173); providence creates novel and priceless ~ (*navānargha-lāvaṇyā*) 76,7 (TP VI 179); brahmin ~ remains unmarried because her father is afraid of suicide of two other of three suitors 76,10 (TP VI 179); princess beautiful enough to inspire love in chest of Kāma 83,13 (TP VII 2); pearl of (merchant) maidens ... illuminated with excessive ~ (*kanyā-ratna ... lāvaṇya-rasa-nirbhara-nirjhara*) 84,5ff. (TP VII 5); *vidhi* ('Disposer') makes pricelessly beautiful brahmin maiden after having acquired skill by making Tilottamā 87,5 (TP VII 29); hermit maiden as peerless ~ of the world (*lokāika-sundarī*) 101,225 (TP VII 149); physical ~ main criterion of princess for husband; she prefers death to an ugly one and sends a friend to look at suitor 103,18 (TP VII 176); moon as own brother to the curved corner of an angry, long-eyed beauty's eye 103,204 (TP VII 189); female ~ has white bodice (*dhavala-kañcukā*) 104,165 (TP VIII 13); brahmin looks like golden binding-post (*ālāna-kāñcana-stambha*) of elephant of ~ (*saundarya-dantin*) 104,179 (TP VIII 14); *caṇḍāla* ~ controls wild elephant with sidelong looks 112,68 (TP VIII 111); torrent river of the elixir of ~ (*lāvaṇya-rasa-nirjhara-vāhinī*) 116,35 (TP VIII 158), cf. 75,69 (TP VI 169); ~ of faces (*mukha-lāvaṇya*) of *Asura* princesses shines out in all directions 118,162 (TP VIII 189); *kanyā-ratna* 119,50 (TP VIII 197); ; two singular beauties, a dark and a white one, on sandbank in mid-ocean 120,105 (TP IX 8f. and 28f.)¹⁴⁹; Ceylonese princess is peerless ~

¹⁴⁸ ORC 470 takes this to mean that for S. *sa seule beauté physique suffit*.

of the world of mortals (*martya-lokâika-sundarî*) 120,96 (TP IX 8); ~ of princess is superior to Tilottamâ 120,102 (TP IX 8); ~ of princess astonishes even Creator 123,105 (TP IX 50); brahmin looks like second Kâma 123,157 (TP IX 54); brahmin's ~ captivates two women besides his bride and all three want to enter fire in his absence 123,317 (TP IX 65); – see also: bewilderment; *lāvanya*; Tilottamâ

beauty and beast¹⁵⁰, see: marriage (52,113 [TP IV 146])

beauty marks of Asurî dancer: pointed (eye) teeth, full bosom, etc. 45,235 (TP IV 33)

beckoning, lady from window ~ king to come to her 106,67 (TP VIII 33); lotuses bending to and fro seem like ~ hands 94,16 (TP VII 88); – see further: finger; gestures

bed, invited by his guru's wife pupil refuses going to the ~ of his guru (*guru-talpâbhi gamana*)¹⁵¹ 20,154 (TP II 109); *amṛta* on ~ of *kuśa* grass 22,196 (TP II 151); ~ of lotuses trampled upon by elephant 33,208 (TP III 124); 34,101 (TP III 135f.); 34,165 (TP III 140); lying on ~ of *kuśa* grass as penance 52,244 (TP IV 155); adulterous wife touches husband under ~ 62,109 (TP V 108); dust as gambler's ~ 73,77 (TP VI 106); princess sleeping on ~ covered with a quilt of pure white woven silk (*paryāṅka-śayane dhautā-sita-patṭottara-cchade*) 73,339 (TP VI 125); ~ with seven mattresses (*sapta-samkhyāka-tūlikā*) given to fastidious (*caṅga*) brahmin 82,39 (TP VI 219); mermaid leaves ~ out of excitement to see king 86,99 (TP VII 20); female lover tossing on ~ at night (*śayanīya-luṭhat-tanu*) 89,34 (TP VII 42) and male lover ... 104,32 (TP VIII 3); 95,48 (TP VII 101); lotus ~ like ~ of hot sand to princess in love 101,127 (TP VII 143); angry heroes are like a ~ of lotus 108,130 (TP VIII 63); 117,54 (TP VIII 168); twelve years old boy steals ~ (*śayyā-khaṭvā*) under sleeping father 124,212 (TP IX 83); ~ only to be had for telling a strange and wonderful story 124,216 (TP IX 83)

bed-room (*vāsaka*) of princess described 73,338ff. (TP VI 125); *rajanī-vāsa-grha* of royal couple 103,206 (TP VII 206); – see also: palace

bedstead (*khaṭvā*), see: bed

bee(s),¹⁵² change of men into ~s by magic (*yogena*) 17,104 (TP II 42); lotuses greet hero with hum of ~ 18,353 (TP II 76); bed of lotuses (*padmini*) trampled by elephant has its cluster of black ~s dispersed 33,208 (TP III 124); maids surrounding courtesan are like clustering ~s 38,116 (TP III 214); pleased woman who got handsome husband compared to ~ (*bhṛṅgī*) that has lighted on a flower 52,314 (TP IV 160); Brahmā is ~ with six feet (*ṣaṭ-caraṇāyate*) on lotus of Viṣṇu's navel 54,32 (TP IV 186); after resorting to *karṇikāra* tree¹⁵³ ~s leave it again finding it without perfume, just as good men leave a rich man of

¹⁴⁹ Zin 2003b: 223.

¹⁵⁰ STh D 735.1; T 268.

¹⁵¹ See Gonda 1968: 235. The man who violates his guru's bed will be reborn as grass (Hara 2003: 468).

¹⁵² Bees fascinate the Indians since the ṚV (Sur Das even wrote songs to them [Doniger O'Flaherty 1988: 145]); the same holds true for the Europeans since Homer. See further, e.g., Meyer 1937: III 73ff.; von Stackelberg 1956; Hensgen 1958: 145f. For metaphors serve the black hue against a light background, as in 33,208, or the humming, as in 18,353, also in Kālidāsa (Jackmuth).

mean character 54,55 (TP IV 188); rows of ~s clinging to blossoming mango-plants as bow-string for Kāma's bow 55,108 (TP IV 209)¹⁵⁴; rolling eyes of *vidyādhari* like circling ~s 59,4 (TP V 26); ~s leave a tree without flowers 61,118 (TP V 78); idem, as a young wife is averse to an old husband 62,84 (TP V 106); ~ swarm (*kriḍālina-bhṛṅgākṣarāvali*) around Gaṇeśa's trunk like host of syllables (of an inscription)¹⁵⁵ on a triumphal pillar (*kīrti-stambha*) 68,1 (TP VI 1), cf. *āli-maṇḍala* 114,2 (TP VIII 132); *vidyādhari* takes form of ~, drinks *jambu*-tree nectar,¹⁵⁶ thus ends curse of separation from her husband and drops tear of joy 69,96 (TP VI 15); woman causes to revolve wheel with ~s which turn into spiders 70,90 (TP VI 30); ~ represent living beings (*bhṛṅgās te ca jantavaḥ*) 70,107 (TP VI 31); ~s, attracted by liquor (*pāna*) smell of king's head (162), removed by young hermit 73,168 (TP VI 113); ~s kept away by black antelope skin with charm 73,173 (TP VI 114); awaking princess rolls her eyes¹⁵⁷ as ~ circling in cup of *kumudvatī* when opened under the rays of the moon 73,345 (TP VI 125); lover sporting like a ~ round lotus of mouth of beloved 74,240 (TP VI 157); does a ~ delight in a lotus on which another ~ has settled ? (*para-bhukte kamale kim aler jāyate ratih ?*) 84,24 (TP VII 6)¹⁵⁸; rows of ~s for strings of Anaṅga's bow 85,7 (TP VII 10)¹⁵⁹; bruised hands of queen look like lotuses upon which black ~s had settled 85,26 (TP VII 11); princess in love is afraid in her heart and bewildered (*baddha-mohā*) like many lotus (*abjini*) at (the appearance of) a swarm of ~s (*āli-pātala*) 90,65 (TP VII 53); collyrium-black tear drops looking like ~s 95,60 (TP VII 102); Sarasvatī as a ~ in the lotus on the lake of a poet's mind 104,3 (TP VIII 1); beard like swarm of ~s come to feed on the lotus of brahmin's face 104,180 (TP VIII 14); female ~s (*bhṛṅga-yoṣit*) keep up concert with humming 122,9 (TP IX 35); – see also: *añjana*; arrow; beard; bewilderment; black antelope skin; Bhramaravāsini; bow; Brahmā; curse; destiny; eyes; jambu-tree; Kāma; *karni-kāra*; lotus(-bed); *māyā*; *ṣaṭ-caraṇāyate*; sayings; skin; spell(s); spiders; spring; teardrop; tears; *vīrya*; woman;

beef, see: cow's meat; famine; *go-māṃsa*

beggar, see: ascetic; hermit

begging woman does not receive alms 123,87 (TP IX 56)

beheading, see: hair; head

Bel fruit, see: *bilva*

¹⁵³ *Pterospermum acerifolium*, 36 or more meters high with long, fleshy, spectacular, yellowish and scented flowers (Macmillan 1991: 119).

¹⁵⁴ In Śak VI 130 women offer mango blossoms as arrow-tips to Kāma (Anderson 2005: 55); at Kumārasambhava 1,27 the swarm of spring sits especially on a mango tree (Jackmuth 2002: 105).

¹⁵⁵ TP takes *a-kṣara* as a kind of pun in its two meanings of 'imperishable > continual' and 'letter', and pertains it also to *kīrti-stambha*; ORC 786 uses only the former meaning and refers it only to the presence of the bees.

¹⁵⁶ It is said to be enjoyed also by Gaṇeśa in Gaṇeśadhyaṇa vs. 30. In Bāṇa, *Kādambarī* (Bombay, 1948) 38,1 *jambū-phala-rasa* is drunk by a parrot.

¹⁵⁷ See Das 2003: 459.

¹⁵⁸ In a comparison of a man who refuses a woman used by someone else.

¹⁵⁹ Cf. Kālidāsa, *Kumāras*. 4,15, etc.

bell (*ghaṇṭā*), robbers as it were summon death with sound of ~s of Caṇḍikā temple 10,189 (TP I 119); – see also: Durgā temple; teeth

belly, see: paunch; stomach

beloved man like a second moon 37,182 (TP III 196);

benediction *bhadram asyāstu* ‘may good luck befall him’ ! 116,40 (TP VIII 159)

beryl-coloured lake (*vaidūrya-vāpi*) in third *pātāla* 45,130 (TP IV 26)

bet (*paṇa*) between physician and father of humpbacked son 62,231 (TP V 119); two ~s between parrot and hen-maina 77,13 (TP VI 184);

betel (*tāmbūla*),¹⁶⁰ given by grateful snake to Udayana, its saviour 9,81 (TP I 100); ~ eaten after meal before drinking spirits 43,64 (TP III 285); at the breast and on lap of beauties (*vara-nārī-kucōtsaṅga*) king is taking ~ 55,40 (TP IV 205 omits “at the breast”; ORC 611: “*il se penchait vers les seins et les hanches des jolies femmes*”; M I 856: “(Bild) auf dem er (der König) die Last seines Körpers an die Brust und in den Schoß einer schönen Frau lehnte und eine in ein Betelblatt gewickelte Betelnuß ... in seiner Hand hielt”); prince spits ~ from palace on head of minister below 70,5 (TP VI 23); ~ offered to honoured person 75,138 (TP VI 174); ~ eaten with ripe (or five) fruits 92,42 (TP VII 74); do, 104,46 (TP VIII 4); – see also: camphor

betrayal of Daitya father by his weeping daughter 112,51 (TP VIII 109)

bewildering science (*mohinī vidyā*) obtained after seven days enduring of snake bites 46,118 and 121 (TP IV 56)

bewilderment¹⁶¹, weapon of fascination (*su-saṃmohana- ... astra*) of the god of the flowery bow 14,29 (TP I 184); Urvaśī as stupefying weapon (*mohanāstram*) in the hands of Kāma 17,5 (TP II 34); beautiful princess as incarnation of the magic art with which Kāma bewilders the world (*rāja-tanayā ... Kāmasyēva jagan-moha-mantra-vidyā śaririṇī*) 33,59 (TP III 111); ~ of looking (*darśana-kṣobha*) at beautiful princess 33,60 (TP III 111); ~ of Love (*Kandarpa-moha*) 35,130 (TP III 165); ~ by destiny (*vidhi-vimohita*) 54,109 (TP IV 191); distracted with love (*madanā-vega-vivaśa*) king wanders through Vindya forest in state of ~ (*unmanī-bhūya*)¹⁶² 55,199 (TP IV 216); robber bewildered with love and wine (*surata-śrāntaḥ pāna-mattaḥ*) falls asleep in princess’ chamber 64,48 (TP V 143); woman *vignā kiṃkāryatā-mūḍhā* at her transposition of the heads of her husband and her brother 80,50 (TP VI 207); ~ (*udbhrānta*) of king at seeing his vassal weeping in the anguish of disappointed passion 81,64 (TP VI 213); ~ by demon of love (*smara-graha*) 84,15 (TP VII 6); king, bewildered (*vihvala*) by bruised (*kiṇāṅkitau*) hands of his queen 85,27 (TP VII 12); ~ of king at seeing his *vidyādhari* wife swallowed by *rākṣasa* and emerging from that being when killed 86,128 (TP VII 22); ~ of *vidyādhari* at being cursed by father 86,143 (TP VII 23); deep darkness of ~ (*mohāndha-tamasa*) settled on brahmin whose wife

¹⁶⁰ On betel see TP VIII 237ff.; Mānasollāsa II 3,959ff. (p. 83f.); Gode 1961: I 113ff.; Moser-Schmitt 1982; Stöhr 1982.

¹⁶¹ In many cases ‘fascination’ seems a better translation than ‘bewilderment’ = ‘puzzling, confusement.’

¹⁶² ORC 619: “*l’esprit absent.*”

was abducted 87,18 (TP VII 30); ~ by love (of man) 89,9 and (of woman) fear, love and shame (*bhaya-prema-trapâkula*) 89,17 (TP VII 40f.); ~ of maiden at seeing man so that her lyre becomes mute 90,48 (TP VII 52); a love-sick princess passes the night the moon makes disagreeable to her and she is afraid (*saṃkocam etya*) in her heart ~ hanging round her (*moha-baddhā*) like many lotus (which closes at night) at (the appearance of) a cloud of bees (*āli-paṭala*) 90,65 (TP VII 53); ~ of Garuḍa when eating Jīmūtavāhana 90,172 (TP VII 61); ~ of king at three hands rising from the well of Gayā to take the sacrificial cake (*piṇḍa*) for his father 93,88f. (TP VII 85); ~ of maiden's eyes by king's beauty 94,24 (TP VII 89); ~ of queen at seeing husband slain 98,21 (TP VII 117); ministers bewildered with grief (*duḥkha-mohita*) for having lost prince 101,205 (TP VII 148); queen deprived of daughter is bewildered like *vidyādhari* who lost her magic science 105,13 (TP VIII 22); bewildered king is as struck by a thunderbolt (*vajrâhata iva*) 105,80 (TP VIII 26); bewildered by terrible obstacles (*vighna*) 108,201 (TP VIII 68); *Asura* daughter is bewildered with love for king (*madana-mohitā*) 112,50 (TP VIII 109); princess is bewildered with doubt (*saṃjajñe saṃśayâkulā*) 119,119 (TP VIII 201); – see also: confusion; fascination; feet; gestures; king; *mohanâstra*

bhadra-ghaṭa(ka) ‘inexhaustible pitcher, cornucopia’ 57,31 broken by drunk man 57,46 (TP V 4; MW: ‘vase of fortune, lottery vase’); – cf. *ghaṭaḥ kâma-daḥ*;

bhadra-kṛt prâṇnyād bhadram a-bhadram câpy a-bhadra-kṛt “he who does good will¹⁶³ obtain good, and he who does evil will obtain evil” 20,35 (TP II 97)

Bhagavân, see: Śiva; Viṣṇu

Bhagavatī = Durgā, queen with rosary and skin of black antelope like an incarnation of ~ 107,63 (TP VIII 47); – see also: destiny; sacrifice

Bhagavat-sāyujya (not MW) ‘union with Śiva’, king Trivikramasena attains ~ 99,41 (TP VII 125)

Bhairava (Śiva) curses *yakṣa* to be eunuch 56,102 (TP IV 227); as ~ lord of the company of the “Mothers” 56,105 (TP IV 227); ~, invisibly present on charnel ground, speaks from the air 88,45 (TP VII 38); ~ statue on Mahākāla charnel ground outside Ujjayinī 102,9 (TP VII 162); ~ appears to gambler and tells him to stay with him 121,106 (TP IX 19); ~ orders gambler to pinch garments of bathing *apsaras* and bring them to his temple 121,110 (TP IX 20); – see also Hara; Śambhu; Śiva

bhakṣya-kośalikā (not MW) ‘edible present, sweet’ (mixed with datura), robber gives ~ to guards of dead mate and then takes his body to burn it 64,76f. (TP V 145)

bhakti ‘devotion’ to Rudra 45,41 (TP IV 19); ‘loyalty’ to king, entering fire out of ~ 91,45 (TP VII 69); – see also: *bhartr-bhakti*

bhakti-rasa ‘ardour of devotion’ 34,12 (TP III 128);

bhālêkṣaṇa (Śiva's) ‘blazing eye’, may ~ befriend you for happiness ! 104,2 (TP VIII 1 and VI 31 note 1);

bhalla and *bhalli* ‘arrow with crescent head’, see: arrow

¹⁶³ For the optative pro futuro see Spijjer 1886: § 344*.

- bhāṇḍa* ‘casket’, see: jewel(s)
- bhāṇḍāgārika*, see: treasurer
- bhāṇḍa-mūlya* ‘capital consisting in wares’ (MW), mouse as ~ 6,38 (TP I 63)
- bhaṅgura* in *vāri-budbuda*^o (97,13 [TP VII 113]), see Jackmuth 2002: 84f.
- bhānu* ‘sun’ deity orders Bhilla king in dream to set imprisoned brahmin free 56,48 (TP IV 223)
- bhārika* ‘porter’, when drunk, admits to have obtained bracelet (*kaṭaka*) at palace door 57,7ff. (TP V 1)
- bhartṛ-bhakti* ‘devotion to husband’, by ~ wife has power of discernment (*viññāna-bala*) 56,180 (TP IV 232)
- bhartṛ-dāraka* ‘prince’ as polite address of higher person by one of lower rank 104,42 (TP VIII 4); – see: inconsistencies
- bhartṛ-droha* (not MW) ‘infidelity to / treachery of husband’ 52,209 (TP IV 152)
- bhartṛ-vidveṣa* (not MW) ‘aversion from husband’ 52,355 (TP IV 162); – cf. *pum-dveṣiṇī* [*bhāruṇḍa*], see: hair-style; vulture
- bhāryā-viyoga* (not MW) ‘loss of / separation from wife’ 123,20 (TP IX 44)
- bhāryā-vyatikara* (not MW) ‘allying with wives’, ~ by king serves acquisition of friends 108,194 (TP VIII 68); – see: policy
- bhāskarāstra* (not MW) ‘weapon of the sun’, weapon of darkness repelled with ~ 116,71 (TP VIII 161); – see also: weapon
- bhasma-kṣepa* (not MW) ‘throwing ashes’, see: ashes; magic rite
- bhasma-pāṇḍu* (not MW) ‘white with ashes’, said of a skull-bearing ascetic 25,81 (TP II 196)
- bhasma-sād bhavati* ‘to be reduced to ashes, incinerated’, crow looked at by hermit is ~ 56,172 (TP IV 232)
- bhasma-śayya*, see: ashes
- bhāṭi* ‘fee of a courtesan’, Garuḍa gives bawd ~ 61,175 (TP V 83); – see also: fee
- bhāva*, see: passion; – for ~ as a suffix, as in *silā-bhāva*, cf. English -ship and German -schaft which belong to a √ *skap* ‘to create’
- bhavāmbudhi* ‘ocean of temporal existence’ to be crossed on the six perfections (*pāramitā*) as on a ship 72,362 (TP VI 96);
- bhāvanā* ‘meditation’, four ~s 64,161 (TP V 151 with note 2)¹⁶⁴
- Bhavānī, mother of the three worlds 1,14 (TP I 2); feet of ~ as refuge of Śabara prince 22,88 (TP II 143); = Gaurī, propitiated for a son, gives king in dream two fruits 42,57 (TP III 263); Jayā sent by ~ gives garland to bride (*dadau ... Jayā Bhavānī-prahītā divyaṃ mālam*) 50,135 (TP IV 117: “Jayā gave her a ... guirland sent by ~”; ORC 540: “Jayā, sitôt arrivée sur l’ordre de Pārvatī, lui donna une guirlande”; M I 756: “Jayā überreichte der Braut auf Geheiß der Bhavānīs einen ... Kranz”); man to be sacrificed to ~ by Bhil 61,158 (TP V 81); appeased ~ (Caṇḍī) grants boon 61,160f. (TP V 82);

¹⁶⁴ < Sarvadarśanaśaṅgraha II, p. 19 *te ca Bauddhās caturvidhayā parama-puruṣārthaṃ kathayanti: ... sarvaṃ kṣaṇikam kṣaṇikam duḥkham duḥkham sbalakṣaṇam sbalakṣaṇam śūnyam śūnyam iti.*

bhavitavyam, bhavitavyatā see: destiny

bheda-saha ‘capable of being seduced [MW], corruptible’ (said of alien servants) 32,174 (TP III 104)

bherī loud drum used to assemble *vidyādhara*s and deities 106,163 (TP VIII 40)¹⁶⁵; – see also: drum

*bhikṣu*¹⁶⁶, as teacher of religion (*dharmā-pāṭhaka*) 28,8 (TP III 18); princely ~ tears out own eye 28,21 (TP III 19); ~ gives king Vikramāditya daily a box (*samudgagam*) with jewel 38,47 (TP III 209); ~ as wicked magician 38,53ff. (TP III 210); ~ gives *śātaka* garment to dependent for citron 53,38 (TP IV 170); ~ in Cashmere 63,57 (TP V 124); ~ provoking Hindu king into dispute 72,95 (TP VI 76); (non-Buddhist) ~ daily gives king fruit containing jewel 75,23 (TP VI 166);

bhikṣu-velā (not MW) ‘mealtime of Buddhist monks, 11-12h a.m.’ 63,83 (TP V 126)

Bhilla(s),¹⁶⁷ attack by ~ in Vindhya hills (*Dasyubhiḥ paryavāryata*) 13,39 (TP I 152); Pulindaka king of ~ 19,59 (TP II 89); their army slain 51,167 (TP IV 133) and fleeing 51,170 (TP IV 134); ~ beauty with parrot in cage who knows the four Vedas 59,28 (TP V 28; cf. Kād 25,1); ~ blow cow’s horns at deer hunt 59,41 and eat parrots 59,50 (TP V 29); ~ identical with Śabarā 71,4 and 7 (TP VI 36) and Mātāṅga 102,64 (TP VII 167); wife of jealous husband elopes with ~ 61,146 (TP V 81); ~ ties man to tree in order to offer him to Devī 61,158 (TP V 81); woman sets out at night with husband and head of ~ 61,163 (TP V 82); ~ on table land of Vindhya (102,55; TP VII 166) ~ live forest life like animals 102,62 (TP VII 167); ~ women wear peacock-tail skirts (*vāsāṃsi barhi-picchāni*) 123,50 (TP IX 46)¹⁶⁸; – see also: garment; hunt(ing); Mātāṅga; Śabarā

Bhilla-pallikā (not MW) village of Bhils = Śabarā 98,13 (TP VII 117; cf. Kuv 138.11ff.); - *palli* 102,60 (TP VII 167)

Bhilla-vāṭa (not MW) ‘quarter of the Bhillas’ 62,213 (TP V 117 omitted)

bhinna-jāti ‘of different rank’ (MW) 23,48 (TP II 160 ‘belonging to alien races’)¹⁶⁹

bhoga-śrī ‘great pleasure’ (not MW) preferred as boon from Devī to *artha-śrī* 54,209 (TP IV 198); – see also: boon

Bhramara-vāsini (= Durgā) Rājāt 3,423ff.

Bhṛgukaccha¹⁷⁰ on the bank of the Narmadā river 6,166 (TP I 72 “Bakakachchha”)

Bhū, the Earth goddess, personally (*āvir-bhūtā*) takes Sītā in her lap and brings her to the other

¹⁶⁵ Popley 1996: 121.

¹⁶⁶ Called *śramaṇa* in 63,76 (TP V 125)

¹⁶⁷ See ORC 1545; Bollée 2008a: 9 and 2010. 23 note 92; Delière 1985.

¹⁶⁸ See Crooke 1919: 1 note 1. Frazer 1923: 474 writes about the Mori clan of the Bhils in Central India that they worshipped the peacock as their totem, but that even setting foot on the bird’s tracks would make them suffer from some disease, and their women had to veil their face when seeing a peacock. Bollée 2008a: 9.

¹⁶⁹ ORC 201: “(vies antérieures) à des espèces différentes”; M I 289: “(Mädchen), deren Art und Gattung in ihrem früheren Dasein er ... erkundete.”

¹⁷⁰ D: Marukaccha for Bharukaccha.

side of a lake in an act of truth to show her faithfulness 51,82 (TP IV 127);
*bhū-grha*¹⁷¹ ‘dungeon, prison, cellar’ of the womb 29,110 (TP III 47); queen put into ~ 39,43
 (TP III 221)¹⁷²; king stays in ~ (*bhūmi-garbha*) with “medicine against old age” 40,57f.
 (TP III 244); wicked queen thrown into ~ 42,113 (TP III 266); couple has to live in
 subterranean dwelling 49,229 (TP IV 101); wife of absent merchant locked up in ~
 embraces leper 64,129 (TP V 149); – see also: cellar
bhujaga-hrada (not MW) ‘serpent lake’ 46,120 (TP IV 56)
bhujāṅga-nagara ‘city of Nāgas’ 112,159 (TP VIII 119 “city of snakes”)
bhujōpadhāna, see: pilgrim
bhūri-keśa (not MW) ‘with much or long hair’, five misshapen (*durākṛti*) brahmins with ~
 70,40 (TP VI 27)
 Bhūrivasu, see: Bhūtiivasu
bhūrja ‘Citragupta’s birch-bark register’ 72,360 (TP VI 95)
bhūta-bhāṣā see: language of demons
*bhūta(s)*¹⁷³, their *adhipa* Nandin brings command of Śiva to king Candraprabha 45,42 (TP IV
 20); ~ delight in battle 47,53 (TP IV 70); possession by demon (*bhūta*)¹⁷⁴ 71,143 (TP VI
 46); *śimśapā* tree, scorched with the smoke of funeral pyres and smelling of raw flesh, is
 compared to ~ 75,51 (TP VI 167); charnel ground full of ~ (*Bhūta-saṃkula*) 83,3 (TP
 VII 1); by hearing bad news man is as if possessed by a ~ (*ākṛānta iva bhūtena*) 104,65 (TP
 VIII 5); Tālajaṅgha, king of ~, dissuades man from ascending pyre 108,91 (TP VIII 61); ~
 , *vetālas* and witches roam about as if the first shoots (*aṅkura*) of Kālarātri’s anger 109,96
 (TP VIII 77); ~ in corpse bites off nose of unfaithful woman when she embraces it
 124,117 (TP IX 76); – see also: combat; dancing; demon
bhūtāsana name of flying chariot / vehicle / vessel (*vimāna*) 44,36 (TP IV 3);
 Bhūtiivasu (thus D and ORC 858), son of a Deccan brahmin and guru of magicians (*yoginām*)
 73,103 (TP VI 108: Bhūriivasu)
 bigamy, see: brahmin; two wives; *vidyādhari* (37,211 (TP III 198)
 big-game hunt (*ākhetaka*) 42,1 (TP III 259)
 bilocality¹⁷⁵: the bodies of four *vidyādhara* princesses remain in their cities when due to a curse
 they are reborn as mortals 26,267 (TP II 237); ~ of mortal prince who divided his body by
 magic science (*vidyā-vibhakta-deha*) in order to live with many Asura ladies 45,342 (TP
 IV 39); king divides himself by his science into many forms and sleeps with all his queens
 110,134 (TP VIII 92); – see also: body
*bilva*¹⁷⁶, sacrifice to Agni with ~ fruit which the god changes for a golden one 35,56 and 68 (TP

¹⁷¹ See Schlingloff 1968.

¹⁷² STh R 41.3.

¹⁷³ See ORC 1547.

¹⁷⁴ See Meulenbeld 1974: 110ff. with ref. to Suśruta and Caraka.

¹⁷⁵ Cf. Śaṅkara, *Brahmasūtrabhāṣya* IV 4,15.

III 159f.); ~ leaf apron worn by dark Śabara messenger 101,355 (TP VII 158);
Bindezauber, see: string
bindu-patha, see: *anusvāra*
 birch-bark register (*bhūrja*)¹⁷⁷ of Citragupta, Yama's clerk, recording people's transgressions
 (*agha*) 72,360 (TP VI 95);
 bird(s), brahmin overhears conversation (*saṃlāpa*) of gigantic ~s (*mahā-vihaga*) speaking
 with articulate voice 26,26 (TP II 219) and 117,84 (TP VIII 170)¹⁷⁸; prince cursed to
 become ~ with golden crest (*svarṇa-cūla*)¹⁷⁹ 65,78 (TP V 160); rebirth as ~ 69,158 (TP
 VI 20); ministers understanding cries of ~ 101,49 (TP VII 137); ~s will loose *eka-veṇī* of
 queen at her death 106,114 (TP VIII 37); *vidyādhara*s riding on ~ (*pakṣibhir vāhini-*
bhūya) 117,21 (TP VIII 165); do, of Gandharva princess (*pakṣi-vāhanam āsthitā*) 117,68
 and (*khaga-stha*) 117,81 (TP VIII 169); king flying on a ~ (*pakṣi-vahana*) 118,68 (TP
 VIII 182); – language of ~s see: language; – see further: *ambu-sārasa*; *baka*; *cakora*;
cakrāhva; *cāṭaka*; *Garuḍa*; *haṃsa*; *madgu*; owl(s); parrot; *pika*; pigeon(s); vulture(s)
 birth of celestial being as mortal, see: curse; part-incarnation; rebirth
 birth-chamber, see: lying-in chamber
 birth, human ~ as curse 2,21 (TP I 10) et passim; reward for giving ~ (*sutā-phala*) 12,163
 (TP I 146); speaking just after ~ 17,66 (TP II 39); ~ of grandson induces grandparents to go
 to Ganges and die 22,155 (TP II 148f.); prognostication by celestial voice at ~ 35,118f.
 (TP III 165); brahmin experiences in his present ~ more than one ~s (*anubhūtādbhutān-eka-*
janmāmutrāiva janmani) 37,165 (TP III 194); woman must endure sufferings of eight births
 in one ~ 52,176 (TP IV 150)¹⁸⁰; of equal ~ (*tulyā*), said of queen 74,35 (TP VI 143);
 maiden of equal ~ with prospective husband 80,16 (TP VI 205); brahmin starts pilgrimage
 with his brahmin ~ as only fortune (*brāhmaṇya-mātra-vitta*) 87,28 (TP VII 31); kings
 consider ~ not in vain (*ḥṛtārthaṃ janma menire*) 110,122 (TP VIII 91); Pārvatī curses five
gaṇas to rebirth as mortals 114,66ff. (TP VIII 137); tree of ~ 119,207 (TP VIII 208); –
 see also: Caesarean section; curse; part-incarnation; rebirth; remembering
 birth in unusual way: daughter not sprung from the womb 27,71 (TP III 6); *kadalī* produces
 daughter from hermit's seed fallen on it 32,102 (TP III 97); ~ of Rati in world of mortals
 without being conceived in a mortal womb 34,42 (TP III 131); *yakṣiṇī* cursed to become
 mortal without being born (*a-yoni-jā*) 34,81 and 90 (TP III 134f.); hermit makes Sītā take
 second son Kuśa he created from *kuśa* grass 51,92 (TP IV 128); Asura Andhaka, mind-

¹⁷⁶ On the Aegle marmelos (L.) tree see, e.g. ORC 1547; Duda 2006: 290f.; Macmillan 1991: 290; Syed 1990: 467ff.; Banerjee 1980: 35; Nair 1965: 94f.; Upadhyaya 1965: 7. Haberman 2013: 50 mentions the late Bilvopanisad (sic!) in which the *bilva* tree is identified with Śiva. In our above passage the brahmin apparently only wants the gold-coloured deity to turn his bel fruit the size of a large grapefruit into gold.

¹⁷⁷ Jackmuth 2002: 137ff.

¹⁷⁸ See sub vulture below and further cf. Chojnacki 2008 (I): 358 s.v. *oiseaux, conversation des*.

¹⁷⁹ Dave 2005: 22 *Coracias benghalensis*, Indian Roller (against TP V 160 note).

¹⁸⁰ The idea that children mean poverty is very rare in literature, and that women must carry the can for it is of no importance for the (male) authors.

- born¹⁸¹ son of Pārvatī, killed by Śiva 114,80 (TP VIII 138); – birth from ear, see: Jāhnavī; – see further: blessing; parthenogenesis
- birth symbol, see: science; ship-wreck; tank; tree
- bitch fastened with chain (*śunī śṛṅkhalâbaddhā*) 13,118 (TP I 158)¹⁸²
- black and red¹⁸³, see: bawd; colour; fruit
- black antelope skin (*kṛṣṇa-mṛgâjina*) keeps bees away 73,173 (TP VI 114); ~ worn by queen Dhanavatī 107,63 (TP VIII 47); – see also: gestures
- black, snake-bite causes Nala to become ~ 56,347 (TP IV 245); though ~, not beautiful (*a-sudarśanaḥ kṛṣṇo 'pi*), said of king of Mātāṅgas 102,73 (TP VII 168)¹⁸⁴; 123,164 (TP IX 55)
- black blanket (*kṛṣṇa-kambala*)¹⁸⁵ stripped off king by woman in dream 29,165 (TP III 52); ~ (*kāla-kambala*) of a herdsman 64,118 (TP V 148)
- black female dragging away king in dream 111,51 (TP VIII 99f.)
- black fortnight (*kṛṣṇa-pakṣa*), at nightfall of ~ Trivikramasena goes to charnel ground 75,37 (TP VI 166f.); black boar is like incarnation of ~ 123,8 (TP IX 43)
- black garment (*a-sita-vāsana*) of enchanter 73,283 (TP VI 121);
- black magic¹⁸⁶ (*kṛtyā*) causing fatal fever on seventh day 5,121f. (TP I 57); ~ performed by *bhikṣu* with magic circle (*arcita-maṇḍala*) 38,64 (TP III 211); ~ of summoning with spell attendant of fever demon 71,217 (TP VI 51); sympathetic ~: at a distance king cuts off head of a man's figure drawn (*ālekhyā-puruṣa*; on the ground) 121,208 and of a hand 212 (TP IX 27); – see also: human sacrifice; *kṛtyā*; magic circle
- blackmail of brothers with suicide to get golden arrow back 39,72 (TP III 223); king presses brahmin to dance by threatening to fast 49,15 (TP IV 86); ~ of Devī-Durgā by austerities to get boon 54,161f. (TP IV 195); ~ of son with father's anger 57,92 (TP V 8); ~ of daughter with her mother's anger 57,160 (TP V 12); ~ of husband by wife 62,227 (TP V 118); ~ (*jīvitena me śāpito 'si*) of father by son 98,33 (TP VII 118); Gandharva princess ~s Śiva to give her a husband 117,72 (TP VIII 169); two princesses ~ *Deva* (Śiva) with hunger strike and possible suicide by fire for husband 119,62 (TP VIII 198); gambler ~s deities to pay their gambling losses in gold 121,86 (TP IX 18); – see also: *dharnā*; gambler; saw; suicide threat
- black man, shipwrecked merchant sees on shore ~ with noose (*a-sitākṛtim pāśa-hastaṃ dadarśa*)

¹⁸¹ For persons born from the mind, a frequent statement in Vedic and post-Vedic literature, see Gonda 1957: 4.

¹⁸² The Metropolitan Museum of Art has a relief with a sitting man holding a dog with a chain (p.c. from M. Zin).

¹⁸³ Hanchett 1988: 286ff.

¹⁸⁴ For “black is beautiful” cf. Hemavijaya, *Kath.* 113,1ff. and see Zin 2003b: 147.

¹⁸⁵ The black blanket may represent the king's disease following the penetration of his ear by a female centipede which reproduced actively by parthenogenesis. Yet the cause of the disease which led to the king's *snāyu-śeṣa* is said to be unknown to the physicians. – Hanchett 1988: 289 states that some farmer caste groups require that a black blanket be the seat of a bride and groom during the wedding rites; here black plays a role in auspicious events.

¹⁸⁶ Cf. ORC 1600.

- puruṣam*) 56,145 (TP IV 230); ~ (Kali) leaves Nala's body 56,383 (TP IV 248); ~ but not comely (*a-su-darśanaḥ kṛṣṇo 'py*) king Durgapiśāca 102,73 (TP VII 168);
- black night, charnel ground compared to palace of ~ (*kṛṣṇa-rajani-nivāsa-bhavana*) 25,136 (TP II 201);
- black nipples (*mecakâgra-payo-dhara*) sign of pregnancy 124,196 (TP IX 82); – see also: pregnancy
- black snake (*sarpa kṛṣṇa*), krait on painting 72,302 (TP VI 91); saliva from dead ~ (*kṛṣṇâhi*) poisons brahmin's rice 87,43 (TP VII 32)
- black as *tamāla* (*tamāla-malina-cchavi*), Mātāṅga king ~ 102,71 (TP VII 167); boar ~ (*tamāla-śyāmala-cchavi*) 123,8 (TP IX 43)
- black teeth, see: *surā*; teeth
- black woman, (*Asurī*) 45,333 (TP IV 39); king dragged to the south by ~ (*dakṣiṇām āsām kṛṣṇayā striyā*) in a dream¹⁸⁷ 111,51 (TP VIII 99)
- blade of grass (representing something insignificant), princess makes three worlds seem as worth less as ~ 18,85 (TP II 55); by Sarasvatī, Skanda and Jina (?)¹⁸⁸ love is thrown away (*kṣiptaḥ ... smarāḥ*) like ~ 51,205 (TP IV 136); falling in love at sight compared to ~ 52,283 (TP IV 157); – see also: grass
- blame, king fears (people's) ~ (*apavāda*) 5,63 (TP I 52); king blames Skanda for giving him boon joined with curse 55,196 (TP IV 215); friend blames merchant for disregarding his advice 57,127 (TP V 10); bawd blames herself for not teaching young man trick (*māyā*) 57,134 (TP V 10); ~ of king for injustice 67,45f. (TP V 199); ~ (*na yuktam*) of Durgā by woman 80,39 (TP VI 207); hermit blames pupil for cursing prince 117,147 (TP VIII 174);
- blessing, hermit's ~ of a woman, see *āśī*; ~ of hermits produces Sītā's pregnancy 51,85 (TP IV 128); 101,59 (TP VII 138); mother-in-law blessed (*āśīrbhir avardhayat*) son-in-law 108,9 (TP VIII 53);
- blind,¹⁸⁹ executioners of brahmin become ~ 20,19 (TP II 96); brahmin is ~ with darkness of grief 37,131 (TP III 192); ~ with passion (*rāgāndha*) 52,67 (TP IV 142)¹⁹⁰; ~ by affection (*snehāndha*) 58,61 (TP V 19); snake curses prince and ministers to become ~ (*dhvānta-ruddha-dṛś*) and deaf 70,75 (TP VI 29); Nāga curses royal servant to become ~ 74,14 (TP VI 142); ~ with wrath (*kopāndha*) 106,154 (TP VIII 39);
- bliss, eternal (*paramā gati*) by *tapas* king reaches ~ 41,55 (TP III 256); – see also: emancipation; *siddhi*
- blister, see: *visphoṭa*
- blood of Śiva fallen into water turns into egg from which springs *Pumān* 2,11 (TP I 9)¹⁹¹; ~

¹⁸⁷ Cf. Bharata's dream about his father being borne away southward by a hideous female demon dressed in red in Rām 2,19 (Bollée 1984: 176f.).

¹⁸⁸ TP: "Buddha". ORC 1421 ad p. 557 dealing with the three persons here remarks that Sarasvatī in this context is unclear. Somadeva may have thought of her incestual relation with her father Brahmā. MI 780: Buddha.

¹⁸⁹ See Hara 2006.

¹⁹⁰ Also Daṇḍin, *Daś* 82.5 (*rāgāndha*).

turned by magic into vegetable sap (*śāka-rasī-kṛta*) as test of vegetarian (*śākāśin*) hermit's egotism (*ahaṃkāra*) 5,134 (TP I 58)¹⁹²; naked queen offers oblation of ~, spirits and human flesh (*asṛk-surā-mahāmāṃsa*) 20,51 (TP II 99); Guṇāḍhya writing with ~ 8,3 (TP I 89); *dohada* of bathing in tank of ~ 9,46 (TP I 97)¹⁹³; track of *vidyādhara* king's ~ followed by snake 22,228 (TP II 154); Durgā-Bhagavatī drinks ~ of giant Ruru 26,146 (TP II 228); hero follows wounded *rākṣasa* by trace of drops of ~ 39,76 (TP III 223); rain of stream of ~ (*raktāugha*) in dream indicates success preceded by a struggle 46,141 (TP IV 58); rain of a stream of ~ means destroying of fear (*raktāugha-varṣaṇaṃ ... bhayasya vināśanaṃ*) 46,146 (TP IV 58); king refuses to drink ~ of corpses 73,153 (TP VI 112); pitchers of ~ in corners of magic circle (*koṇa-nyastāsra-kumbhaka*) 73,305 (TP VI 123); magician sitting in circle with pitchers of ~ put on the cardinal points 99,3 (TP VII 122); reception offering (*argha*) of human ~ to a *vetāla* 99,13 (TP VII 123); *vidyādhara* violator of queen vomits ~ after being addressed by angry Bhagavān (Śiva) 106,129 (TP VIII 38); blow (*āhati*), brahmin daily gives wicked wife transformed into mare seven ~s with stick (*laguḍa*) 68,56 (TP VI 5); – see also: combat

blue eyes, blue lotus; – see: eyes; *indīvara*; lotus; *nilōtpala*; smell

boa constrictor, see: *aja-gara*

boar, a Daitya, like darkness of night condensed into a solid mass in the daytime, breaks king's chariot before fleeing into cavern 11,44f. (TP I 126); wounded ~ flees into cave 26,182 (TP II 230); story of wise ~ (part-incarnation of Buddha), monkey and lions 72,121 (TP VI 78); ~ offers himself to hungry lions as food 72,132 (TP VI 78); ~s (*sūkara*) hunted 94,9 (TP VII 87); *Asura* in ~ form 112,38 is Daitya 53 (TP VIII 108f.); ~ (*kroḍa*) described **123,7f.** (TP IX 43); king kills ~ with five arrows and a smart man emerges from it 123,87 (TP IX 49); ~ killed and touched on the neck becomes celestial sword 123,96f. (TP IX 50); – see: *añjanādri*

boast, see: Kailāsa; swordmanship

boat of stone (*pāśāṇa-nau*), crossing sea on ~ 66,15 (TP V 179)¹⁹⁴;

bodhi 'highest illumination' with supernatural powers (*mahā-siddhi*) 72,368 (TP VI 96)

Bodhisattva, Jīmūtavāhana as ~ 22,35 (TP II 139); drug specialist Nāgārjuna sprung from portion of ~ 41,10 (TP III 252)¹⁹⁵; incarnation of ~ saves mutilated man from river 65,9f. (TP V 154); idem saves woman and three animals from well 65,54 (TP V 158); ~ loses power by speaking to sinful woman 65,100 (TP V 162); lion brings ~ deer meat 65,101 (TP V 162); rule for discipline leading to the rank of ~ (*°caryā*) 72,100 (TP VI 76); boar as incarnation of ~ 72,120 (TP VI 78); ~ gives life for others (*prāṇa-dāyin*) 72,147 (TP VI 79); prince reaches state of ~ by *tapas* 72,235 (TP VI 86); hermit = ~ saves lovesick man

¹⁹¹ For divine blood see note on ichor.

¹⁹² Cf. Dossi 1998: 54.

¹⁹³ Maten 1973: 16.

¹⁹⁴ Cf. STh D 1524.3.

¹⁹⁵ Cf. *osadhi-kumāra* ?

from delusion 72,315 (TP VI 92); *vidyādhara* prince as part *avatāra* of ~ with *jāti-smara* 90,8 (TP VII 49); – see also: part-incarnation

bodice, see: bra; *kañcuka*

bodiless voice, see: voice

bodily form, see: attributes; *sākṣād*; *sa-vigraha*;

bodily transgression (*pāpaṃ kāyikam*) should be avoided 56,114 (TP IV 228);

body¹⁹⁶, queen's ~ tender as a *śiriṣa* flower 6,113 (TP I 69) and 34,2 (TP III 146) and 101,156 (TP VII 145) et passim; magician enters dead ~ of king and asks grammar teacher to guard his own ~ 4,99f. (TP I 37f.); ~ perishes in a moment (*śarīre kṣaṇa-naśvare*) 4,133 (TP I 41); smell of queen's ~ is as that of *nilōtpala* 16,28 (TP II 22)¹⁹⁷; radiance of Nārada's ~ compared to sun 21,18 (TP II 126); ~ compared to water bubble (*jala-budbuda*) 22,40 (TP II 140); lifeless ~ of *vidyādhari* princess is in heaven while she is a mortal on earth 26,79 (TP II 222); princess leaving mortal ~ for own *vidyādhari* one 26,109 (TP II 225)¹⁹⁸; as everything corporeal is unreal (*a-sāraṃ viśvam ... idaṃ śarīrakam*) seven princesses want to lay their ~ while still alive on charnel ground to do good to their fellow-creatures, the eaters of raw flesh (*kravyād-gaṇa*) 28,16f. (TP III 19); ~ of nymph yellow with dust of flowers (*parāga-puñja-gaurāṅgi*) 35,12 (TP III 156); yellow bodies of *vidyādharas* 35,20 (TP III 156); from joy of meeting his beloved, lover cannot be contained in his own ~ and as it were enters hers and marries her by the *gāndharva* ceremony 37,185 (TP III 196); ~ as fruitless concentration of delusion (*māyā-samāhāra*) 38,111 (TP III 214); ~ of man of heavenly appearance framed of diamond 44,6 (TP IV 1); Chinese princess with limbs yellow as gold (*hāri-hemāvadātāṅgi* [read: *hari-haimā°* ?]) 44,46 (TP IV 4); taking many bodies by his magic skill (*vidyā-viracitāneka-dehaḥ*) king associates with many wives at the same time 44,50 (TP IV 4); ~ of Dānava embalmed with heavenly drugs and ghee 45,50 (TP IV 20), 45,117 (TP IV 25) and 45,127 (TP IV 26); king should enter embalmed previous ~ by spell 45,51 (TP IV 20); has someone died who enters another's ~? 45,56 (TP IV 20); whoever of his own free will enters another's ~ ... remembers all 45,60 (TP IV 21); king leaves his ~ to enter his embalmed previous ~ (of hero in second *pātāla*) 45,119 (TP IV 25); divine ~ (*divya-deha*) obtained by nectar drunk from beryl-coloured lake in 3rd *pātāla* 45,130f. (TP IV 26); *Asura* princess with ~ black as *dūrvā* grass stalk (*dūrvā-latā-śyāmalāṅgi*) 45,333 (TP IV 39); ~ of mortal prince divided by magic science (*vidyā-vibhakta-deha*) so as to live at the same time with many *Asura* women 45,342 (TP IV 39, cf. below 110,134 [TP VIII 93]); bodies of heroes move in rivers of blood like alligators 47,52 (TP IV 70); ~ of *vidyādhari*, cursed to be born a mortal, remains in heaven 52,63 (TP IV 142)¹⁹⁹; *vidyādhara* throws left ~ of mortal pre-birth into Ganges 52,88 (TP

¹⁹⁶ See Bouillier & Tarabout 2010; Ciurtin 2010; ORC 1555.

¹⁹⁷ Cf. Pieruccini 2000.

¹⁹⁸ Cf. 52,63 (TP IV 142); 118,35 (TP VIII 180), etc.

¹⁹⁹ Cf. 26,109 (TP II 225), etc.

IV 144); *Gaṇa* of Durgā obtains fiery meditation (*āgneyī dhāraṇā*) with which he burns his mortal ~ (*martya-deha*) 52,260f. (TP IV 156); sixty-eight parts of ~ 54,125 (TP IV 199); Kali enters drunken ~ of Nala 56,288f. (TP IV 241); Nala's ~ cannot endure sandal-wood powder 56,322 (TP IV 243); man with ~ like mass of flame (*tejah-puñjākṛti*) descends from sky 59,111 (TP V 34); king enters former ~ that falls from heaven and becomes son of hermit 59,176 (TP V 38); ~ of *vidyādhari* gleaming as sunlight 69,169 (TP VI 21); as long as we retain this ~ how can woes come to an end? 73,169 (TP VI 113); maiden's ~ resembling a blue lotus (*nīlōtpala*) 73,196 (TP VI 115); female beauty's ~ smells of goat 82,31 (TP VI 219); this ~ cannot be relied on (*a-viśvāsyā*) 86,22 (TP VII 14); ~ full of indescribable impurities and an abode of pain (*a-vācyāśuci-saṃpūrṇam duḥkh- kṣetram*) 94,106 (TP VII 94)²⁰⁰; Pāśupata ascetic enters ~ of brahmin boy 97,33, then throws his own old ~ into ravine (*śvabhre tat kṣiptvā pūrva-kalevaram*) 97,41 (TP VII 114f.); king divides himself into many forms (*bahudhā vapuḥ vibhajya*) and sleeps with all queens 110,134 (TP VIII 92, cf. above 45,342 [TP IV 39]); ~ of princess delicate as a *śirīṣa* flower (q.v.); ~ (*tanus*) of *vidyādhara* king remains in his city kept by magic from corrupting (*vidyā-prabhāvād a-mlānā*) while soul is reborn as mortal 118,35 (TP VIII 180); prince with *vidyādhara* and mortal ~ 119,173 (TP VIII 205); beautiful Dānava women conceal their bodies within trees 118,107 (TP VIII 185); man in another's ~ 119,137 (TP VIII 202); ~ of *Asuras* are material and can be burned 119,201 (TP VIII 207); two singular beauties (*adbhuta-rūpe ... kanyake*), one with a ~ as dark as panic seed (*priyaṅgu*), the other gleaming white like the moon (*candrāmala-dyuti*) 120,105 (TP IX 8f.); – Vedas in bodily form, see: Vedas; – having many bodies, see: division of personality; ~ smell (q. v.); ~ colour of *vidyādharas*, see s.v.

bodyguard of king consists of women Strabo, *Geography* XV 1,55

body odour, see: goat; smell

bone(s), Garuḍa restores to life ~s of snakes along sea-shore by *amṛta* 22,248 (TP II 156); *yakṣiṇī* plays on lute of ~ (*kaṅkāla-kiṃnari*) 37,64 (TP III 187); ~s of executed friend thrown into Ganges 64,83 (TP V 146); oblation of ghee with ladle and spoon of human ~ (*narāsthī-srak-sruva*) 73,307 (TP VI 123); suitor brings ~s of beloved to Bhāgīrathī 76,15 (TP VI 180); heaps of ~s of snakes eaten by Garuḍa near southern sea 90,95 (TP VII 55); prince wants to throw his father's ~s into Ganges but ministers advise against 93,65 (TP VII 82f.) and 93,80 (TP VII 84); four brahmins find lion's ~s, create the animal, give it life and are killed by it 96,37ff. (TP VII 110f.); magician sitting in circle made with yellow powder of ~ (*gaureṇāsthī-cūrṇena*) 99,3 (TP VII 122); ~ and skin remain of *Asura* Andhaka, a mind-born son of Pārvatī, when killed by Śiva 114,80 (TP VIII 138); book (*pustaka*),²⁰¹ the Ms of the Kathāsaritsāgara 8,11 (TP I 89); Guṇāḍhya reads his ~ to beasts and birds and then throws leaf after leaf into a fire 8,19 (TP I 90); hermit steals ~ (*pustikā*) with spell to raise the dead 76,25 (TP VI 180); unknown traveller gives ~ with

²⁰⁰ Cf. Manu 6,76f.

²⁰¹ Cf. Karashima 2012: 74 note 2.

picture of girl on canvas (*paṭe*) to painter 122,24f. (TP IX 35)
 boon (*vara*)²⁰² Śiva gives three women in a dream ~ of a boy who every day when waking up from sleep will have a hundred thousand gold pieces under his pillow 3,21f. (TP I 19); ~ for reviving person 10,82 (TP I 112); ~ of Durvāsas to Kuntī after burning her back with a hot vessel with rice 16,42 (TP II 24); ~ from Śiva of son 21,144 (TP II 136); Gaurī grants *asurī* Uṣā ~ of husband she dreamt of 31,11f. (TP III 81); Agni gives king golden bilva fruit from his tree of valour (*sattva-taru*) and a ~ 35,70 (TP III 160); brahmin muttering prayers refuses ~ from gods for stopping it 45,96 (TP IV 24); brahmin gives king ~ of half his muttering 45,110 (TP IV 25); Kāśyapa gives Maya ~ of obtaining diamond-like limbs (*ajarāmaro 'ṅgair vajramayair a-kṣataḥ*) 45,407 (TP IV 45 “[thou shalt remain unharmed by the plagues of sickness and old age,] which are strong as the thunderbolt”)²⁰³; ~ of devotion to Śambhu = Śiva 46,21 (TP IV 50); ~ of great wealth (*artha-śrī*) or great pleasure (*bhoga-śrī*) offered by Durgā 54,165 (TP IV 195); *yakṣa* gives ~ of *liṅga* to eunuch 56,97 (TP IV 226); Nārāyaṇī, chief of the “Mothers”, gives poison-destroying lotus as ~ to brahmin 56,115 (TP IV 228); five gods give Nala the ~ of being his servants at being thought of (*vaśyāḥ ... smṛta-mātrôpagāminah*) 56,267 (TP IV 239); *yakṣas* give wood carrier ~ of inexhaustible pitcher (*bhadra-ghaṭa*) with warning to choose something else 57,39 (TP V 4); daughter, born as ~ of Gaurī, obtains all sciences from her 59,11 (TP V 25); *yakṣa* gives ~ of sciences 63,80 (TP V 125); man asks (as a ~) identity from leper, who calls himself Kāma, in order to visit woman described by leper in the latter’s disguise (*veṣa*) 64,139f. (TP V 150); mendicant obtains ~ of his adoption as son of *yakṣa* 66,60 (TP V 182); ~ of invincibility in disputation, altercation and gambling 66,61 (TP V 182); son given as ~ by Lakṣmī 69,80 (TP VI 14); as ~ Caṇḍikā has sleeping king conveyed by attendants across sea 69,115 (TP VI 17); prince gains ~ from Indra and becomes wishing tree 72,225 (TP VI 85); Citragupta gives ~ to robber 72,331 (TP VI 93); ~ from Śaṅkara / Śiva: birth as *Gandharva* 74,27 (TP VI 142); king asks Durgā for ~ (*anugraha*) of reviving (people) in exchange for his head 78,99 (TP VI 197); woman about to commit suicide asks Durgā ~ of getting same husband and brother in future births 80,40f. (TP VI 207)²⁰⁴; Śiva gives merchant’s daughter ~ of onehundred sons to her father 88,49 (TP VII 38); brahmin rogue disguised as woman tells real woman he has ~ (*prasāda*) from Viṣṇu to change gender at night and become a man 89,95 (TP VII 47); ~ of Gaurī to Jimūtavāhana’s wife that she should have for husband a destined sovereign over all *vidyādhara* kings 90,182f. (TP VII 61); hermit Kaṇva gives his daughter as ~ to king who gave up hunting 94,47 (TP VII 90); *vetāla* gives ~ of *śravaṇa-phala* to king 99,22 (TP VII 123); bride craves ~ (*vara*)²⁰⁵ from Kāma 104,136 (TP VIII 11); *Asura* gets ~ from Śambhu of slaying Indra in fight 115,49 (TP VIII 147); hermit gives king ~ of

²⁰² STh Q 115.

²⁰³ ORC 490: “aussi seras-tu épargné par la vieillesse et la mort, et avec ton corps fait de diamant”

²⁰⁴ Cf. 104,136 (TP VIII 11).

²⁰⁵ *Vara* means ‘boon’ and ‘bridegroom’ (TP). This craving sounds like a *nidāna*.

invulnerability (*a-bhedyāḥ sarva-śāstrāṇaṃ bhūyās te*) 118,65 (TP VIII 182); – see also: world

bosom, full ~ (*pīna-stanā*)²⁰⁶ of Upakośā 4,6 (TP I 30 with note 2); *vidyādhari* will sweep away with the sea of beauty flowing between the banks of her breasts (*stana-taṭa*) even one who can restrain his passions 27,65 (TP III 6); ~ (*pīna-stana-stabaka-*) of *vidyādhari* 35,11 (TP III 156); princess with full ~ (*stanau uro-maṇḍalinau*) 45,235 (TP IV 33); stiffness and hardness (*stabdhatva-kārkaśye*) of ~s in Ujjayinī 92,11 (TP VII 71); – see also: breast; *ghana-stanī* ; *stana-taṭa*

boudoir, see: *kopa-grha*

bow¹, deep ~ or proscynesis,²⁰⁷ when approaching or leaving a person of respect: new king is *pūjitāṅghriḥ* 18,405 (TP II 80); – see: crest-jewel

bow² made of bamboo 27,8 (TP III 1); ~ and string, magic ~ arisen from black snakes (*nāgaḥ kālah*) falls from heaven and is seized by *vidyādhara* prince 46,92ff. (TP IV 55); imperial bows called *Amitabala*²⁰⁸ 46,101 (TP IV 55); self-acting ~ kills greedy jackal 61,104 (TP V 77); prince's ~ bent by string reaching the notches (*koṭi-prāpta-guṇānata*) 69,17 (TP VI 10); ~ of Kāma with string of excellence, princess walking bent like ~ 72,76 (TP VI 74); mango-cluster with bees compared to ~ of Kāma (*smara-cāpa*) 104,6 (TP VIII 1)²⁰⁹; Mango shoot looks like Kāma's ~ with loosened string, as he reposes after conquering the world 111,12 (TP VIII 95)

boy on lion to be adopted by sonless king 6,92 (TP I 67)²¹⁰; ~ bitten by snake is saved by smelling magic lotus 56,129 (TP IV 229); kite (*śyena*) carries off ~ (*arbhaka*) 60,244 (TP V 62); ~, caused to be possessed by spells, tells hermit where to find drugs and the palace of a snake who has a magic sword 70,75ff. (TP VI 28); brahmin ~ willing to be sacrificed to Caṇḍikā in order to save king 78,68 (TP VI 105)²¹¹; seven years old brahmin ~ to be sacrificed by king to *brahma-rākṣasa* 94,78 (TP VII 92); gold statue of seven years old ~ carried around in towns, etc. on *karṇī-ratha* 94,90f. (TP VII 93); brahmin ~ (*śīśu*) as human sacrifice laughs loudly 94,124 (TP VII 96); *brahma-rākṣasa* as tutelary deity of brahmin boy 94,133 (TP VII 96); ~ crying in front of rice-pudding (*paramānna*) 124,135 (TP IX 78)

bra (*kañcuka*), breasts that want to leap out of ~ because of curiosity to see king 18,16 (TP II 50 with note)²¹²; ~ bursting from erotic excitement 74,238 (TP VI 157)

²⁰⁶ See Oberlies 1991: 108 sub 1).

²⁰⁷ Equivalent of Italian *ciao* < *sciavo* and German *servus*.

²⁰⁸ Text: Amṛtabala as against vs 95 Amitabala.

²⁰⁹ Anderson 2005: 55.

²¹⁰ See also Bollée 2010a: 147 note 81.

²¹¹ Cf. STh S 260.1.1.

²¹² Cf. Kuv 25.16 and the *gaṇikā* in Bhāsa's *Cārudatta* who did not lean out of the window with breasts hanging down to see the heroic deed of Karṇipūra (Esposito 2004: 128 and 269). In Veṅṣaṃhāra 2,11 the bra is called *stanāṃśuka*. See further Ghurye 1966: 247ff., esp. 249.

bracelet (*kaṭaka*) with name given by mother to son 9,78 (TP I 100); ~ of lotus fibres worn by women in love 33,166 (TP III 121); necklace and ~ worn (*hāra-keyūra-rājita*) by *vidyā-dhara* prince 33,211 (TP III 124); poor porter gets ~ at palace door 57,9 (TP V 1)

Brahmā²¹³ no longer worthy of worship by asking Śiva to become his son 1,30 (TP I 4); ~ curses Vasu and *apsaras* to become mortals 9,26 (TP I 96); by a sign from a distance (*dūrāt*) ~ forbids Prahasta to decapitate enemy 50,19 (TP IV 109); ~ as bee on the lotus of Viṣṇu's navel humming the Veda 54,32 (TP IV 186; ORC 1424 note 4 on p. 596); Viṣṇu's stomach is the egg of ~ 54,33 (TP IV 186); ~ husband of Sarasvatī 106,24 (TP VIII 29); Dāitya king obtains son by favour of ~ 115,4 (TP VIII 144); ~ weapon can only be repelled by weapon of Paśupati-Rudra 115,21 (TP VIII 145; see further: Brahmāstra); ~ criticized by unsatisfied receiver of boon 115,47 (TP VIII 147); ~ shelters Indra, Śacī and Airāvaṇa in Brahma-loka 115,76 (TP VIII 149); egg of ~, see: egg;

brahma-cārī 'colleague', see: hand

brahma-cārīṇī (*asurī* nun) in white clothes 29,52f. (TP III 42); ~ dies on Gandhavaī shore meditating on love for brahmin youth and is reborn as courtesan (*veśyā*) 162f. (TP VI 20)

brahma-carya-vrata 'vow of perpetual celibacy' 6,90 (TP I 67)

brahma-hatyā by gods 45,90 (TP IV 23); ~ by inconsiderate judge 72,215 (TP VI 84); father of daughter with three brahmin suitors has fear of ~ of those who do not get her and thus she remains unmarried 76,10 (TP VI 179); ~ washed away by pilgrimage (*tīrtha-yātrā*) to Kāśmīr 39,38 (TP III 220); brahmin animating lion which devours other brahmins is guilty of ~ 96,50 (TP VII 111); – see also: beauty

*brahma-rākṣasa*²¹⁴ Yogêśvara 12,49 (TP I 136); ~ appears when thought of (*dhyānād upasthīta*) 32,25 (III 92); ~ as 'wise friend' (*jñānin*) 34,241 (TP III 146); ~ occupies place of brahmin's sacred fires (*agni-śālā*) and seizes his son 72,158 (TP VI 80); brahmin called ~ whose wife throws crying child into fire 76,20 (TP VI 180); ~ Jvālāmukha black as soot, with yellow hair like lightning, etc. (**description**) 94,68 (TP VII 91); ~ laughing and reciting the Veda, drunk with a full draught of blood, yawning and panting frequently (*muktātṭa-hāsaḥ so 'dhyayanaṃ paṭan ghūrṇan raktāsava-kṣībo jṃbhamāṇo muhuḥ śvasan*) 94,115f. (TP VII 95); ~ as tutelary deity (*daivata*; ORC 1013: "divinité gardienne") of brahmin boy 94,133 (TP VII 96); **description** of ~ 114,107 (TP VIII 140); ascetic curses ~s to become first *Piśācas* and then, cursed by a brahmin, *caṇḍālas* 114,108f. (TP VIII 140);

Brahmāstra 'Brahmā weapon' 50,66 (TP IV 112); 105,19 (TP VIII 145); 115,21 (TP VIII 145); 116,76 (TP VIII 162)

brahmin boy, seven year old ~ to be sacrificed by king to *brahma-rākṣasa* 94,78 (TP VII 92)

brahmin district Bahusuvarṇaka by royal charter (*agrahāra*) 7,41 (TP I 78); – see further:

agrahāra

brahmin owners in parties of seven like malignant planets oppress villages 18,130 (TP II 59)

²¹³ See ORC 1548.

²¹⁴ See ORC 1549.

brahmin soldier 53,80 and, from Mālava, 89 (TP IV 173f.); 78,11 (TP VI 191)

brahmin(s) stupid (*mūrka*) 2,47 (TP I 13) and 6,53 (TP I 65) and 35,76 (TP III 161), see also infra; ~ burnt 4,112 (TP I 39); ~ always soft-hearted (*mr̥davo hi dvijātayaḥ*) 5,5 (TP I 45); ~ not executed 5,17 (TP I 47); ~ king 5,46 (TP I 50) and 18,403 (TP II 80); ~ Nāga prince weds cursed ex-*apsaras* by *gāndharva* marriage 6,17 (TP I 61); Durgā orders desperate ~ to remain near her and thus makes him attain divine nature (*divyatā*) 6,82 (TP I 66); ~ reborn as Gaṇa 7,106 (TP I 85); ~ can accomplish everything by ceremonies (*śrautena karmaṇā*) 13,56 (TP I 153); ~ appointed *purohita* with sunshade and elephant 18,125 (TP II 59); ~ as king 18,403 (TP II 80); ~ kicked (*pāda-prahāreṇa jaghāna*) 20,14 (TP II 96); fraudulent ~ 24,80 (TP II 175); ~ offers human flesh for sale on charnel ground 25,183 (TP II 205); ~ with corpse (*preta-kāya*) hanging over his shoulder 25,189 (TP II 205); ~ marries *rākṣasī* 25,206 (TP II 207); ~ after death eaten by dogs 27,128 (TP III 10); undisciplined ~ reborn fisherman (*kaivarta*) 27,129 (TP III 10); stupid ~ with many children 30,93 (TP III 70); seven ~ fools 32,44 (TP III 93); miserly ~ buries treasure in forest, see: treasure; *yakṣa* kills ~ treasure-hunters and is cursed to become mortal 34,74 (TP III 134); ~ must not be slain 46,166 (TP IV 59); ~ able to resuscitate dead woman 52,104 (TP IV 145); ugly ~ 52,113 (TP IV 146); five hundred dinars as daily pay for ~ soldier 53,92 (TP IV 174); thief and *rākṣasa* wake up ~ with two cows and flee 62,97 (TP V 107); ordinary (*sāmānya*) ~ villager with two wives 63,56 (TP V 124), cf. 73,417 (TP VI 130); characteristic of ~s is patience 66,16 (TP V 179); inconsiderate judge causes death of ~ (*dur-avadhārako brahma-hā*) 72,215 (TP VI 84); stupid ~ tries flying by fastening wings of grass to his sides 72,279 (TP VI 89); chief of robber gang (*caura-camū*) is ~ only by name 73,206 (TP VI 116); fastidious ~ notices female beauty's smelling of goat 82,31 (TP VI 219); ~ who can reanimate the dead 83,29f. is a sorcerer (*indra-jālin*) 37 (TP VII 3f.); ~ saves princess from must elephant 89,17 (TP VII 41); exhausted ~ refuses alms-food offered by Pāśupata ascetic 92,34 (TP VII 73); ~ is paid 500 dinars for sex 93,42 (TP VII 81); ~ boy to be sacrificed to his *daivata*, a *brahma-rākṣasa* 94,77f. and 133 (TP VII 92 and 96); stupid ~ makes pilgrimage to Durgā Vindhya-vāsinī shrine 108,23 (TP VIII 54); ~s ask crown-prince for state elephant, then for his horses, chariot, sons and wife, and obtain them 113,41ff. (TP VIII 127ff.); – feeding ~ see: feeding;

brahmin woman knows *prātiśākhya* 2,38 (TP I 12);

brahminy ducks (*cakra-ḥaṃsa, cakrāhva*), perturbed at night 67,72 (TP V 201); two *yakṣas* cursed by Kubera to become ~ 72,43 (TP VI 71 with note 3);

brains entering mouth, boy becoming *rākṣasa* on ~ 25,105 and 272 (TP II 198 and 211);

branches, twelve Veda ~ (*śākha*) 49,156 (TP IV 95);

branding with dog's foot (*śunaḥ pāda*) on forehead²¹⁵ 13,142 (TP I 160)

breasts compared to full pitchers (*pūrṇa-kumbha-kuca-dvaya*)²¹⁶ 18,9 (TP II 50); *ucchvasitau*

²¹⁵ This looks like the showing, or even throwing, of shoes to unpopular people in Muslim countries nowadays.

stanau of woman curious to see king from house top 18,16 (TP II 50)²¹⁷; the sea of beauty of *apsaras* flows between the banks of her ~ 27,65 (TP III 6); ~ compared to “treasure-vessels (*kumbhau*) of Love, marked with his seal of joy” 34,32 (TP III 130); ~ likened to clusters of *mandāras*²¹⁸ (*mandāra-stabaka-stanī*) 34,231 (TP III 146); ~ of *apsaras* firm as clusters 35,11 (TP III 156); ~ like golden pitchers (*kanaka-kumbha*) 47,107 (TP IV 73) and *kuca-kāñcana-kumbha* 118,163 (TP VIII 189); ~ uncovered by brother to show mole 49,206 (TP IV 99); maiden with protruding jug-breasts (*kuca-kumbhâgrā*)²¹⁹ 84,7 (TP VII 5 ‘like half-revealed pitchers’; ORC 944: “*ses seins étaient l’ébauche de deux amphores*”); ~ of merchant’s daughter compared to golden rooftops of palace and frontal lobes of elephant 91,30 (TP VII 68 omitted; see: *pīna-tuṅga*); ~ compared to two pitchers of Kāma’s regal coronation 101,85 (TP VII 140); *vidyādhari* princesses place hands on their ~ showing that the king had at once entered their hearts 107,84 (TP VIII 49); nymph whose clothes were taken goes with arms crossed in front of her ~ (*sva-hasta-svastika-stanī*) 108,69 (TP VIII 58); pendulous ~s and bellies (*lambōdara-payodhara*) of *rākṣasīs* 116,29 (TP VIII 158); ~ as banks, see: beauty and cf. bosom; ~ as eyes, see: bra; pitcher; water vessels

breath of love-sick woman stops after putting her arms around her lover’s neck and she dies 95,74 (TP VII 103)

Bṛhaspati, councillor of the gods (*amartya-guru*), appears before Indra when thought of (*saṃsmṛtōpasthita*) 115,92f. (TP VIII 150)

Bṛhatkathā of Guṇāḍhya when concluded ends his curse 8,34 (TP I 91)

bribe (*dhana*)²²⁰ given to mahout (*hasty-āroha*) 13,8 (TP I 150); ~ (*upapradāna*) attracts the greedy 24,119 (TP II 178); alien servants are easily corrupted 32,174 (TP III 104); delicious food given as ~ to go-between 75,109 (TP VI 171); boatmen bribed (*ātta-dhanāḥ*) to leave brahmin husband alone, without his wife on boat which is carried to the sea 123,195 (TP IX 57); – see also: *artha-saṃdarpa*; mahout; warder

bride sought 11,7 (TP I 122); idem 11,35 (TP I 125); heavenly ~ (*svar-vadhū*) 17,16 (TP II 35); ~ killing every husband 18,262ff. (TP II 69f.)²²¹; ~, descending from *karṇī-ratha* (q. v.), is attacked by elephant and abandoned by merchant groom, elopes with saviour

²¹⁶ Cf. Bāṇa, *Kād.* 48,2 *kuca-kalaśa* ‘jug-breasts’ (Layne 1991: 24). See Oberlies 1991:108 sub 3); Meyer 1937: I 170 note 3. – As to the word *thana-vaṭṭam* in Kuv note 173 which Choj. translates by “*la coupe de tes seins*” taking it as a *deśī* word with the meaning ‘drinking vessel’ I would like to refer to the Pali word *thana-paṭṭa* ‘cloth for binding the breasts (Cone), bra.’

²¹⁷ Cf. Kuv 25.16.

²¹⁸ Given the look of the clusters and the red colour of the blossoms this seems a curious parable whose intention may show that the breasts touch each other and thus are large; see *mandāra*, Gonda 1949: 115 note 8, and Syed 1990: 436 who does not comment it.

²¹⁹ *Metṛī causā* for *ālakṣyāgra-kuca-kumbhām*.

²²⁰ On corruption see Thakur 1979; Schuller 1982; Bollée 2008a: 10.

²²¹ Cf. STh T 173.

27,168ff. (TP III 14); king seeks ~ 28,54 (TP III 24); ~ in the power of treacherous mother-in-law in difficult position 29,74 (TP III 44); idem 33,26 (TP III 109); ~ is husband's *śakti* incarnate (*mūrtimatī*) 45,340 (TP IV 39); ~ substituted 71,158f. (TP VI 47); new ~ bound by oath leaves husband to visit lover 84,41 (TP VII 7); ~ procured by present to her father 119,28ff. (TP VIII 195); – see also: bridegroom; present

bridegroom killed at entering bride's chamber 18, 262 (TP II 69); ~ sought by Gaurī 20,61 (TP II 100); Naravāhanadatta as ~ of Science (*vidyā-svayaṃvara-vṛta*) 34,173 (TP III 140); royal ~ is adorned by his wife as is rainy season with a lightning garland 44,179 (TP IV 13); bride desiring victory for ~ performs austerities to propitiate Gaurī 116,23 (TP VIII 158); substituted ~ 123,169 (TP IX 55)

bridge, of sand (*sikatā-setu*) is impossible 40,19 (TP III 241); lion's tongue (*rasanā*) as ~ over river in dream 69,24f. (TP VI 10); – see further: dream; impossibilities; tongue

brother(s), organizes royal marriage feast of sister 14,26 (TP I 183); two *Asura* ~s abduct Tilottamā 15,139f. (TP II 14); three pious brahmin ~, two married, the youngest bachelor 33,36 (TP III 109); two Gandharva ~s cursed by Siddha 36,118ff. (TP III 177)²²²; ~ decides (after father) about sister's marriage 79,9 and 19 (TP VI 200f.)²²³; ~ hates younger sister 105,67 (TP VIII 25); five ~s and a daughter born to *vidyādhara* king 59,12 (TP V 26); two brahmin ~s dividing heritage and thus cutting female slave in two punished by confiscation 62,176f. (TP V 114); confused woman causes ~ and husband to change heads 80,47 (TP VI 207); four brahmin ~s resuscitate lion 96,5ff. (TP VII 108); elder ~ renounces his right to the throne in favour of younger ~ 111,63ff. (TP VIII 101); younger ~ refuses to marry before elder ~ 118,124 (TP VIII 186); younger ~ solicited by wife of elder ~s see: *niyoga*; – see also: golden-crested bird; marriage

brotherhood (*maitrī*), *rākṣasa* chooses brahmin with sworn ~ (*maitryā varayitvā*) 18,342 (TP II 75)²²⁴; – see also: oath

brown cow (*kapilā*), incarnation of Surabhi 108,29 and speaking in articulate voice 108,34 (TP VIII 55)

brows curved in anger (q.v.); – *apsaras* looking askance with wrinkled ~ 17,128 (TP II 44); 110,130 (TP VIII 91); ~ meeting, see: witch;

Buddha, bridegroom of Tārā (? *Tārā-vara*) 27,12 (TP III 2 with note 2 suggesting that *Tārā-vara* = *Tārā-pati* = Śiva)²²⁵; ~²²⁶ offers himself up for another as if he were worthless straw 28,10 (TP III 18); Nāgārjuna becoming a ~ after being beheaded 41,53 (TP III 256); boar as part-incarnation of ~ (*Buddhāṃśa-saṃbhava*) 72,121 (TP VI 78); man becomes continent (*ūrdhva-retas*) like ~ 72,258 (TP VI 87); Gaurī curses *rājarṣi* Iḍa to become female who falls in love with and marries ~ in Gandharva style 89,86 (TP VII 46); – see

²²² Zin 2003b: 165 note 12.

²²³ STh T 131.1.

²²⁴ For swearing brotherhood see Bollée 2008: 89.

²²⁵ ORC 255: “*époux de Tārā*”; 1383 note 3. *Tārāvara* is not in PWB, MW or BHSD.

²²⁶ Bodhisattva is meant.

also: *Sugata*

Buddha-like status (*gati*), Nāgārjuna will not be reborn and attains a ~ 41,53 (TP III 256); – see also: emancipation; *siddhi*

Buddhāṃśa, see: Buddha; part-*bodhisattva*; part-incarnation; *Sugatāṃśa*

Buddhism, called irreligion (*a-dharma*)²²⁷ 27,18 (TP III 2; ~ as irreligion (or: negative religion) is resorted to by low-caste people (*adhama-jātayaḥ*) 27,20 (TP III 2); vanquished in dispute, king adopts ~ (*saugata-mata*) rich in the merit of benefiting creatures (*sattvôpakāra-puṇyâḍhya*) 72,98 (TP VI 76);

Buddhist (?) monk(s) (*śramaṇa*) are released from bathing and brahminical hairlock, and have only a rag around their loins (*kaupīna*) 27,19 (TP III 2)²²⁸; ~ (*bhikṣu*) as wicked magician 38,53ff. (TP III 210); two ~s (*śramaṇau*) recommend princess to king of Pratiṣṭhāna 51,118 (TP IV 130) and are honoured with garments and ornaments (*vastrâbharaṇaiḥ*) for it 51,183 (TP IV 134), and wealth as they deserved (*yathôcitam*) 194 (TP IV 135); bitten by dog on knee, foolish ~ (*bhikṣu*) sounds gong (*granthi*) of monastery 65,136f. (TP V 165)²²⁹; ~ (*bhikṣu*) challenges king to dispute for seven days and vanquishes 72,96f. (TP VI 76)

Buddhist robe (*kāṣāya*), hue of sunset like that of ~ 72,364 (TP VI 96);

Buddhist temples in Takṣaśilā 27,10 (TP III 2); ~ monastery (*vihāra*) 28,7 (TP III 18); *jagmatuś ca vihārāya vihāraṃ* 29,37 (TP III 41)²³⁰

buffalo(es) hunted 21,14 (TP II 126); ~ killed under fig tree and eaten 62,213 (TP V 117); witch turns husband into ~ by throwing dust in his face 68,44f. (TP VI 5)²³¹, but *yoginī* sprinkles ~ with charmed water (*mantra-toya*) and returns him into man 68,51 (TP VI 5)

bug (*matkuṇa*) bites king, but louse (*yūkā*) is killed 60,132f. (TP V 52)²³²

bull (*vṛṣabha*) as term of respect, said of a minister 40,8 (TP III 240 ‘a great or distinguished minister’)²³³; draught-bull falls down, is left and recovers by eating green grass 60,14ff. (TP V 42)²³⁴; jackal tells lion that ~ wishes to kill him 60,112 (TP V 51)²³⁵; ~ ploughs up bank of tank with its horns 65,183 (TP V 169); fool ascends heaven (Kailāsa) by holding tail of divine ~ (of Śiva) 65,185 (TP V 169); woman with wheel, ~ and donkey 70,89 (TP VI 30f.); Māyā with ~ as symbol of Righteousness 70,118 (TP VI 32); *vetāla* with legs like a

²²⁷ ORC 255: “immoralité”; M I 362: “Unglaube”. “Negative religion” may be better.

²²⁸ This seems a calumny or different ascetics are meant.

²²⁹ Cf. Sūy 1,3,1,8.

²³⁰ TP: “they went, in order to amuse themselves, to a temple of Buddha”; Fezas in ORC: 282: “pour se distraire ... elles se rendirent dans un monastère bouddhique.”

²³¹ In the Arabian night no 749 Jauhara spits king Badr Bāsim in his face and makes him turn himself into a white bird.

²³² Cf. the question whether crows are at fault when *haṃsas* eat rice 75,191 (TP VI 176).

²³³ ORC 411: “un taureau parmi les ministres”; M I 574: “ein Ochse von einem Minister.” Powerful males such as Indra, the archetypical man, are often called a bull (Whitaker 2011: 30). See also Ciurtin 2010f.: 341ff.

²³⁴ Cf. Sūy 1,2,3,5; 1,3,3,21.

²³⁵ STh B 182.3.

~ (*mahiṣāṅghri*) 102,19 (TP VII 163); – see also: ant-hill; elephant’s hide
 bullshit: queen tells king fictitious tale in order to cover up adultery 66,42 (TP V 181)²³⁶
 burden (*bhara*) of realm, king, when in harem, delegates ~ on ministers 15,4 (TP II 1); idem,
 19,57 (TP II 89); idem, of Rāma on his sons 51,112 (TP IV 130); idem, 86,6 (TP VII 13);
 king delegates ~ on ministers during pilgrimage 93,71 (TP VII 83); at last *vidyādhara* king
 throws ~ of kingdom on son and goes with queen to hermitage 119,213 (TP VIII 209); –
 see also: ministers; realm
 burglary, see: wall (77,58 [TP VI 187])
 burning ground (Mahākāla-*śmaśāna*) described 12,47 (TP I 136); Sāmaveda brahmins take
 king to be (impure) keeper of ~ 18,107 (TP II 57); ~ described 18,146 (TP II 60f.); do,
 25,180ff. (TP II 205); seven princesses consider ~ as natural home of happiness (*nisarga-*
sukha-sadman) 28,42 (TP III 23); 73,281 (TP VI 120); do, 75,42ff. (TP VI 167)²³⁷; do,
 of Mahākāla outside the city of Ujjain with statue of Bhairava 102,9 (TP VII 162); – see
 also note at: hair-style
 burning palace, princess secretly conveyed out of ~ 10,110 (TP I 113f.); idem 15,21 (TP II 3);
 butcher (*māmsa-vikraya-jīvin*), dharmatic ~ 56,181 (TP IV 232f.); – see: meat-seller
 butcher’s wife (*saunika-bhāryā*) turns man into peacock 71, 276 (TP VI 56);
 butter, see: cow-butter
 buxom, see *ghana-stanī*

c / kh confusion, see *khaṇḍa-kāpālika*

Caesarean section²³⁸ in the eighth month 26,166 (TP II 229 with note 2); idem 26,224 (TP II
 234); 26,257 (TP II 236)
 Caitra, Indra holds assembly of the gods (*devāsthāna*) on full moon day in ~ (*Caitra-śukla-dina*)
 118,17 (TP VIII 179)
 cake in *liṅga* form²³⁹ made in monsoon and given by them to stupid (*mūrkhā*) brahmins in order
 to remove discomfort caused by bathing in cold season, 2,57 (TP I 13f. with note 3); – Cf.
 Priapic roll(s)
cakora (*Perdrix rufa*)²⁴⁰, man being to the eyes of beloved what the moon is to ~ 26,246 (TP II
 235); ‘partridge’ loves moonlight 114,22 (TP VIII 134);

²³⁶ See Meibauer 2013.

²³⁷ Cf. Liberale 2005: 3 note 13. – Though the smell on charnel grounds must be repulsive, this curiously enough is hardly ever mentioned in descriptions. An exception is AnguttaraN III 268,26ff. where the *sivathikā* is stated to be *dugandha* (Kieffer-Puelz 1983: 13).

²³⁸ See Jolly 1977 § 48; Müller 2008: 33 and 357ff. In the country nowadays, which may still represent history, there is sometimes opposition against this operation, see Jeffery 1989: 114, perhaps not only because of the cost presently.

²³⁹ The time and reason given for their preparation and why they are given to stupid brahmins with a *dakṣiṇā* is not very clear. In Germany Priapic rolls are sold in November. See also HdA 3: 387ff., Seligmann 2001: 238 and in Google under “erotische Backwaren”.

²⁴⁰ Dave 2005: 282 Chukar.

cakora-vrata ('vow to imitate partridge and gaze at the moon') 76,11 (TP VI 179);

cakorāyati 'to emulate the partridge' 89,41 (TP VII 43);

cakra-haṃsa 72,40 (TP VI 71) = *cakrāhva*

cakrāhva (*cakravāka*,²⁴¹ Brahminy duck or Ruddy sheldrake, *Anas Casarca*) hero, lost in wood, is moaning like ~ 10,130 (TP I 115); royal couple compared to ~ 14,62 (TP I 187); *Urvaśī* like female ~ during the night 17,28 (TP II 36); the sad are like ~ at the end of the day 51,56 (TP IV 126); ~ perturbed at night 67,72 (TP V 201); *yakṣas* cursed to become ~s 72,42 (TP VI 71); day (*vāsara*) passes away for lover as if he were a ~ 84,10 (TP VII 5); 87,19 (TP VII 30); longing for sleep and a dream of her lover a woman weeps all night with the female ~s 104,189 (TP VIII 15); at rise of reddish (*ālohita*) moon prince laments like ~ 119,166-8 (TP VIII 204);

cakra-melaka 'meeting of covens' of witches in Cakrapura 123,213 (TP IX 58; cf. MW s.v.);

cakra-vartin 'emperor' whose sway extends over the whole earth²⁴² 90,188 (TP VII 62); 107,130 (TP VIII 52); 109,19 (TP VIII 72 note); etc.

cakra-vyūha, see: battle-arrangement

cakra-yantra (not MW) 'wheel-machine' guarding the water of immortality 29,47 (TP III 42); similar M I 401; ORC 282: "*le mécanisme de la roue qui veille sur le breuvage d'immortalité*"²⁴³

caṣur-bhrānti 'treat for the eyes' 55,45 (TP IV 205); – cf. *darśanōtsava*

calamity (*vipad*), with black eyes like those of an antelope 92,16 (TP VII 72); – see also:

comparisons; dice; disease; *Durgā*; greed; *Hari*; *īti-ghna*; jealousy; love-sick; magic; old age; omen; sayings; women

calita (kind of heavenly dance²⁴⁴) performed by *apsaras* *Rambhā* 17,20 (TP II 35 with note 2)²⁴⁵

²⁴¹ See ORC 1550; Hensgen 1958: 136f.; Dave 2005: 450f.; Jackmuth 2002: 135f.; Kuv note 42.

²⁴² See Norman 1969: 241f. ad *Theragāthā* 822. For a Jaina explanation of *cakravartin* from the *Jambūdivapannatti* see Mette 2010: 263.

²⁴³ This *yantra* may be a kind of *araghaṭṭa*; see Zin & Schlingloff 2007: 5ff. where, however, our passage is not dealt with.

²⁴⁴ This meaning is not in MW. An account of *Rambhā*'s dance in the court of *Indra* is given in the *SkandaPur* 5,2,3,4f.

²⁴⁵ Referring to *Kālidāsa*, *Mālavikāgnimitra* (NSP ed; Bombay, 1950) I prose after vs 3 where *Mālavikā*'s friend *Bakulāvalikā* says: "*āṇatt'-amhi devīe dhāriṇīe aira-ppauttōvadesaṃ chali(y)aṃ nāma naṭṭa(y)aṃ ... Queen Dhāriṇī orders me to ask the dancing teacher Mr Gaṇadāsa about a recently performed dance called chaliya ...*". It is said to consist of four parts and to be difficult to perform (Sundaram 1979: 760). *Chaliya* may be wrongly sanskritized as *calita*, but in the commentary it appears as *chalika* which dance is performed by men (MW). The ed by Shankar P. Pandit (Bombay, 1869), though, has *caliaṃ* in the text. Scharpé 1954: II 11 states also *calidaṃ*. Sastri 1955: 188 writes "*chalitaṃ* and *chalikaṃ* are indifferently used in the same sense" and Kale 1960: 213 annotates "*calitaṃ* (also written *chalikaṃ*)". *Calita* is not mentioned in MW in this sense, but Apte gives the above reference as "a kind of dance". See also Wössner 1981: 65ff. The *yakṣagaṇa* passages of pure dance called *cālu* may be related (p. c. Dr Katrin Binder), the *chali* compositions in Manipuri *bhangī pareng* (Baldissera & Michaels 1988: 168), however, perhaps rather to *chalika*.

call for help, parents and husband ~ed by lost princess 101,148 (TP VII 144); do, 123,281 (TP IX 63); – see also: help

call of nature, details of satisfying ~ Gaṇeśapurāṇa I 3,15ff.: Vasu 1918: 12; Kāmasūtra 1,4,5.
For the open air convenience in a monastery see Bṛhatkalpa-niryukti 1265 and 2068; for a toilet on a ship see Kuv 67.16

calumny, people are prone to ~ of a distinguished person (*uttamasya ... kalaṅkôtpādako janah*) 24,205 (TP II 184)²⁴⁶; ~ (*a-yaśas*) of minister by rumour of common people 86,12 (TP VII 14); – see also: report; rumour; slander

cāmara, -ī see: chowry; hair; tail

camel, lion sees ~ of ridiculous appearance 60,146 (TP V 53); ~ who offered himself is killed and eaten by lion 60,160 (TP V 54); overloaded ~ gives way 62,193 (TP V 116)²⁴⁷; king, shocked (*śokākrānta*), when seeing ~ approaching (?) a couple of snakes intertwined in sex (*sambhoga-saṃsakta-bhujaṅga-mithunâśane pravṛttaṃ karabhaṃ*²⁴⁸), kills the ~ which becomes *vidyādhara* 69,87 (TP VI 15); ~ as ugly animal 69,107 (TP VI 16); *vetāla* with neck like a ~ (*uṣṭra-grīva*) 102,19 (TP VII 19); *vidyādhara* prince and friend riding on heavenly ~ (*divya-karabha*) 117,130 (TP VIII 173); – see also: wedding present

camphor (*karpūrikā*; not MW),²⁴⁹ lumps of ~ given as royal wedding present to husband of Princess Karpūrikā 43,213, 234 and 250 (TP III 296ff.); king of Kauśāmbī gives ~ and aloe wood as dowry 44,132 (TP IV 9); women are like flies that leave ~ (*karpūra*) and haste to dirt 58,136 (TP V 24)²⁵⁰; old go-between hit by woman with both hands white with ~ meaning ten nights of white fortnight 75,101 and 104 (TP VI 171); lover is presented with garland, betel leaves, ~ and the five fruits (*mālā sa-pañca-phala-karpūrain nāga-vallī-dalair yutā*) by his love 104,46 (TP VIII 4)

Cāmuṇḍā in vain asked with charmed water (*abhimantritaḥ toyais*) to resuscitate woman for she is a cursed *vidyādhari* and has returned to heaven and taken her own body leaving the mortal one for which relatives should not mourn 52,158 (TP IV 149); ~ sends dream 52,168 (TP IV 149f.); ~ advises despondent Mātaras to tell gambler that they sit out of the game 121,89 (TP IX 18); – see also: *Mātaras*

**caṇḍa-kāpālika*, see: *khaṇḍa-kāpālika*

cāṇḍāla,²⁵¹ dead ~ rots in the Ganges 27,128 (TP III 10) and, because self-controlled, is reborn as king 27,131 (TP III 11); ~ hunter sets traps 33,112 (TP III 116); good-looking ~

²⁴⁶ See Hara 1968: 262.

²⁴⁷ See Alsdorf 2010: 16 note 44.

²⁴⁸ Camels do of course not eat snakes as rendered by all previous translators. *Karabha* ‘camel; young elephant’ will occasionally have been confused with *śarabha*, for which MW gives the same meanings, but also that of a fabulous animal stronger than a lion or an elephant. I do not know if this animal stated to eat snakes. Taking *aśana* from the other root *Aś* ‘to come, reach; penetrate, pervade; master’ might be slightly better, yet properly not exactly what one would expect, viz ‘to tread upon, kill’ or ‘to interrupt (the copulation)’. The passage is curious.

²⁴⁹ See Kuv 119; McHugh upcoming and www.camphor-allied.com/home.html

²⁵⁰ Camphor has for Indians a nice smell (*Svapnacintāmaṇi* I 142).

²⁵¹ See ORC 1551.

maiden wishes *cakravartin* for husband 61,204 (TP V 85); prince loves ~ beauty 112,74 (TP VIII 111); ~ maiden cannot be beautiful 112,83 (TP VIII 112);

cāṇḍāla-kanyakā, see: *svayaṃvara*

Caṇḍī, -ikā, awful temple of ~ (*Caṇḍikā-sadma bhīṣaṇam*) in the Vindhya forest²⁵² 10,189 (TP I 119); king worships ~ in Caṇḍikā-*gr̥ha* outside town²⁵³, and is promised fulfilment of his wish 11,13 (TP I 122); offering his own flesh in burnt-offering (*homa-karma*) king obtains from the visible ~ magic sword making bearer invisible 11,36 (TP I 125)²⁵⁴; do, 25,86 (TP II 196); temple of ~ in village (*pallī*) of robbers 22,62 (TP II 141); ~ grants Śabara king to befriend merchant also in another birth 22,68 (TP II 142); brahmin son to be sacrificed to ~ in order to save king 53,133 (TP IV 177); captive man prays to ~ and is freed 61,160 (TP V 82); ~ gives robber bewildering charm (*moha-mantra*) 64,81 (TP V 146); empty (*sūnya*) temple of ~ on coast of western ocean 69,112f. (TP VI 17); ~ famous for readily showing herself to votaries (*sāmnidhyôtkarṣa-śālinī*) 78,50 (TP VI 194); temple of ~ 78,66 (TP VI 195); ~ lauds hero who sacrificed his only son to her 78,71 (TP VI 105); before suicide, merchant daughter offers prayer to ~ to get brahmin husband in next birth 95,30 (TP VII 100); affording protection ~ revives three devotees 95,88 (TP VII 104); ~, family goddess of Rājputs and boon-giver (*vara-pradā*), reanimates dead couple out of compassion 111,45 (TP VIII 99); ~ propitiated by king to get sword and wife 112,26f. (TP VIII 106f.); – see also: Cāmuṇḍā; Devī; Durgā

candle made of human fat (*māṇuṣa-vasā-dīpa*) shows hidden treasure 34,70 (TP III 133)²⁵⁵; baby girl clings to nurse's face as ~ flame clings to wick 34,98 (TP III 135); ~ in the face of the sun is of no avail 46,114 (TP IV 56); ~ (*mahā-taila-pradīpa*) illuminate magic circle 99,4 (TP VII 122)

candrikā, 'moonlight', one of the seven imperial jewels of the *vidyādhara*s 109,22 (TP VIII 71)

caṅgatā, see: fastidiousness

cannibalism,²⁵⁶ at night woman slays hero and eats his flesh 10,72 (TP I 111); ~ enables to fly by witches' spells 20,104 (TP II 103); Kālārātri gives princess human flesh to eat and thus makes her a witch 20,112 (TP II 104); witches eat many men 20,114 (TP II 105); royal couple unknowingly eats flesh of son 20,208 (TP II 113); hermit falsely accused of ~ 24,209 (TP II 185); brains from a burning pyre fall into mouth of boy who then becomes *rākṣasa* with hair standing on end, etc. 25,104 (TP II 198f.); wife eats flesh of impaled husband 25,149 (TP II 202); ~ by hermit to become *vidyādhara* 26,232 (TP II 234); sons eat

²⁵² Fierce, "wilderness" gods are most frequently found in forested shrines (Kent 2013: 42 quoting Mines 2005).

²⁵³ "Deities are arranged in a spatial order such that gods with a wilder, more dangerous character are found farthest from the settled center" (Kent 2013: 42 quoting Masilamani-Meyer 2004).

²⁵⁴ Cf. Rodrigues 2003: 52.

²⁵⁵ See TP III 150f.

²⁵⁶ Also in famine Daś 218,12. For cannibalism in India now, not only among the Aghoris, see Google s.v. Herodotus noticed the practice among certain Indian tribes (*Enneads* III 38,4; 99).

father like crabs 28,48 (TP III 23); mother-in-law eats daughter-in-law 29,67 (TP III 43); before leaving at end of her curse nymph (*dyu-strī*) tells hermit-husband to cook and eat their child in order to be reunited with her 108,74f. (TP VIII 59); wife devours servant and her maid eats mare 124,98 (TP IX 75); – see also: flesh; nude; witch

canvas, princess painted on ~ (*paṭe*) for merchant in love with her 72,294 (TP VI 90); foreign kings painted on ~ for nubile princess 83,14 (TP VII 2); princess painted on ~ by female mendicant 101,74 (TP VII 139); beauty on ~ given to king 122,25 (TP IX 35); king paints city on ~ 122,61 (TP IX 38)

capēṭa ‘box on the ear’, king gives disobedient daughter ~ by which humiliation (*avamāna*) she flees into the forest 66,139f. (TP V 189)

capital punishment, wealth of merchant confiscated instead of ~ 18,387 (TP II 78)²⁵⁷; ~ for harem violator 71,303 (TP VI 58); ~ of inconsiderate judge for killing brahmin 72,215 (TP VI 84)

capite velato: princess covers face before dying 52,150 (TP IV 148)²⁵⁸; covering head at night 73,7 (TP VI 100); face of a sleeping *vidyādhari* should not suddenly be unveiled 105,60 (TP VIII 25); – see also: *ābaddha-śāṭaka*; covering; face

captives, female ~ wave chowries for victorious king 78,6 (TP VI 191)

**cārādhīpa* (? Reading of D) ‘lord of wanderers / spies’, *ahaṃ ~ḥ pūrvaṃ bhavatā havya-kavya-bhuk* 18,315 (TP II 73: “But I am the Fire, the consumer of the oblations to gods and the spirits of deceased ancestors, whom thou didst before propitiate” ; ORC: “*Je suis Agni, qui consomme les offrandes aux dieux et aux mânes que tu m’as faites auparavant*”, MI 211: “*Ich bin ... Agni, den du früher erfreut und für dich gewonnen hast*”). Copyist error for *cārādhitaḥ* as in the Brockhaus edition; translate “for (also) before I have been pleased by you as an enjoyer of the sacrifices to the Manes”

cāraṇa ‘drummer’ 110,86 (TP VIII 88)

cāraṇarddhi (not MW) ‘good fortune of an actor > popularity ??’ 52,277 (TP IV 157: ‘a bard’s fortune’)

carcarī ‘spring dance’ 54,58 (TP IV 188)²⁵⁹

cardamom tree (*elā*), garden with ~s 111,15 (TP VIII 96)²⁶⁰

cardiac infarct, see: heartbreak

²⁵⁷ STh Q 410ff. Daś 116.9 states that the Mauryas exempted merchants from the death penalty.

²⁵⁸ A device to avoid fascination or other dangerous influence so as to prevent the evil glance reaching the victim for whom it is intended (Crooke 1896: II 47). According to Mette (p. c.), the KSS poet wanted to raise the empathy of the hearer or reader for the princess described by showing her human feeling: the person about to die did not like to expose her face, the features of which, marked by mortal dread, grief or pain, she could no longer control, to curious looks. This will be generally correct. In the present case, however, the princess remembered her pre-birth as *vidyādhari* and knew that her time as a mortal due to a curse was over which could only be a pleasant fact. Nowadays a woman’s covering her face is a sign of shame or modesty (Jeffery 1989: 28f.), if not against the evil eye (Michaels 2004: 231). – See also below the note on hair-style.

²⁵⁹ Sundaram 1979: 759

²⁶⁰ See Macmillan 1991: 374f.

cardinal points, hero makes sacrifice to deities of ~ (*dig-devatā-bali*) with heads of *Asuras*
 116,60 (TP VIII 160); ~ as Viṣṇu's ears, see: ear
 carnac, see: mahout
 carousal, see: *āpāna-goṣṭhī*
caru, see: oblation ; pregnancy
 carpenter, two ~ brothers (*takṣāṇau*) making ingenious automata of wood 43,22 (TP III 282);
 ~ carries adulterous wife on his head 62,114 (TP V 108);
caṣaka 'cup, goblet', decorated with various jewels in royal banqueting hall 110,125 (TP VIII
 91)
 casket (*bhāṇḍa*) with jewels, see: jewel(s)
 castle-in-the-air motif: brahmin building ~ left out by Somadeva, see TP V 228f.; Pañcat V 1
 (Edgerton 1924: 401); STh F 771.2.1; H 1133.2
 castration, see: adulterer
 cat (*mārjāra*), mouse as cat's meat 6,40 (TP I 63)²⁶¹; out of fear of Gautama Indra assumes form
 of ~ 17,140 (TP II 46)²⁶²; ~ caught in a hunter's noose 33,107 and freed by a mouse 127
 (TP III 115ff.); kings oppressing the poor (*kṣudra*) are ravenous like ~s 52,372 (TP IV
 164); ~, being useful, is bought with money, brought from a distance 60,43 (TP V 44);
ahiṃsā-vow of hypocritical ~ 62,51 (TP V 103)²⁶³; pseudo-ascetic ~ kills bird and hare
 62,55 (TP V 103); description of ~ **65,161ff.** (TP V 167);
cāṭaka 'a kind of cuckoo'²⁶⁴ joys at seeing cloud 6,162 (TP I 72); king stays pining like ~
 longing in summer for fresh rain-water (*navya-rasa*) 73,98 (TP VI 108)²⁶⁵; female ~
 joyfully
 beholding rain-cloud 119,192 (TP VIII 206); after long time man finds and refreshes his
 wife as a cloud (*toya-daś*) does with a *cāṭakī* 123,335 (TP IX 66);
 catalogue of women, see: ethnic catalogue
catuḥ-śāla 'palace, (mansion?)', queen placed in empty ~ 36,57 (TP III 174)
catuṣ-patha 'crossroads', at ~ two handfuls of rice must be put down for a Piśāca to invoke his
 help 28,165 (TP III 33)
caura-camū (not MW), see: robber gang; thug(s)
caura-pallī (not MW) 'village of robbers' 114,110 (TP VIII 140)
caura-yātanā 'punishment for thieving' (not MW) 38,111 (TP III 214)
 cave (*guhā*), wife hides husband in ~ 61,155 (TP V 81); ~ of Vāmadeva with imperial jewels
 109,14 (TP VIII 71); ~ of Triśīrṣa through which Mt. Kailāsa can be passed 109,66 and 75

²⁶¹ STh A 2435.3.2.

²⁶² Vettam Mani 1975: 17 sub Ahalyā.

²⁶³ Picture in Snead 1989: 84 plate 48 < Mamallapuram 7th century.

²⁶⁴ *Cuculus melanoleucus* (MW), but according to Dave 2005:133f. either the Hawk Cuckoo or the larger Pied Crested Cuckoo the Sanskrit authors apparently "not worrying what particular kind of bird they are actually referring to." The latter bird may be meant as the 'drop-craving bird.' Hensgen 1958: 141 follows MW.

²⁶⁵ Jackmuth 2002: 169f.

(TP VIII 74f.); ~ of *kāpālika* with two maidens 124,11 (TP IX 69); – see further: ceremony; crow(s); doomsday; four *rākṣasas*; jewel(s); *kiṃnara*; *mahāuṣadhi*; Pātāla; robber(s); seven herbs; window

celestial, see: heavenly

celibacy (*brahma-carya*), king takes vow of ~ after death of his wife 6,90 (TP I 67)

cellar (*bhū-grha*), entering ~ like second prison of womb 29,110 (TP III 47), – see also: *bhū-grha*

cemetery, see: burning ground; note at hair-style

centipede (*śata-padī*) enters ear of king and reproduces 29,136 (TP III 49f.)²⁶⁶; one hundred and fifty ~s extracted from ear 29,170f. (TP III 52);

ceremony, -ies, due ~ (*vidhi*) at marriage necessary 14,5 (TP I 182) et passim; Kālarātri makes woman take off her clothes and perform, standing in a circle, a horrible ~ in honour of Śiva-Bhairava, in order to become a witch 20,110 (TP II 104); ~ of observing and fixing the quarters (? *dig-bandhādi-puraḥsaram*, q.v.) 73,116 (TP VI 109); auspicious ~ by mother-in-law before journey of prince (*racita-maṅgala-saṃvidhānaḥ*) 35,160 (TP III 168), cf. 115,156 (TP VIII 155); marriage by *gāndharva* ~ 37,185 (TP III 196); 51,190 (TP IV 135); bathing as auspicious ~ (*snānādi-maṅgala*) 65,234 (TP V 173); coronation ~ (*rājyābhiṣeka*) 103,231 (TP VI 191) and 110,75ff. (TP VIII 87); due ~ (*saṃvidhayaḥ*) before entering cave (*guhā*) 109,81 (TP VIII 76); ~ of pouring water over the hands, see: donation water; – see also: body; marriage; *pradakṣiṇā*; *prasthāna-maṅgala*; protocol; rites

chadma-ghātin ‘killing deceitfully’ *niśāsu* ~ 19,82 (TP II 91); 64,87 (TP V 146)

chāga-bhaṇḍa (not MW) ‘mime in the shape of a he-goat’ 121,135 (TP IX 21)

chain, see: bitch; garland; Śiva; ~ of love see: *māra-śṛṅkhala*

chamber of princess as mouth of death 18,324 (TP II 74); description of splendid ~ of princess 74,231f. (TP VI 157);

change one's form at will (*kāma-rūpiṇī*), I can ~ says *rākṣasī* 25,196 (TP II 206)

change of gender: Gaurī curses *rājarṣi* to become a woman 89,85 (TP VII 46); boon from Viṣṇu to change ~ at night 89,95 (TP VII 47); by magic *vidyādhari* gives king her own shape and disappears 106,121 (TP VIII 37); – see also: disguise; fee; illusion; transformation

chant by watchman 3,64 (TP I 23); ~ by *Gandharvas* for Keśava (Viṣṇu) 36,115 (TP III 177); do, 54,25 (TP IV 186); praise of Śiva sung as sweet song by *vidyādhari* princess sends brahmin to sleep 52,195 (TP IV 151)

chaperon (*prauḍhā*)²⁶⁷ of *vidyādhari* princess 51,10 (TP IV 122); (*jyeṣṭatarā*) 75,94 (TP VI 171); (*jyeṣṭhatarikā*) 75,133 (TP VI 173);

character is wealth to the wise (*śīlaṃ hi viduṣāṃ dhanam*) 5,98 (TP I 54)

characteristic (*śīla*) of brahmins is patience (*kṣamā*), of *kṣatriyas* the rescue of the distressed (*āpanna-rakṣaṇa*), quietism (*śama*) that of liberation seekers and disputatiousness / noise

²⁶⁶ See infra sub ear and Bollée 2010b (Svasti): 159 under 7.2).

²⁶⁷ In fact her mother 51,50 (TP IV 125). Cf. Daṇḍin, *Daś* 186,6 (*sthavirā*).

(*kalaha*) that of *rākṣasas* 66,16 (TP V 179)
charcoal (*aṅgāra*), stupid merchant burns his aloes-wood to ~ 61,5 (TP V 67)
chariot-driving, Nala is expert in ~ (*ratha-jñā*) 56,370 (TP IV 247)
chariot (*vimāna*), flying ~ 7,61 (TP I 80)²⁶⁸ and ~ (*vyoma-gāmī ... vimāna*) 42, 145f. (TP III 269) and 43,136 (TP III 290); *Asurī* travels in magic ~ (*vimāne yantra-nirmite*) 29,49 (TP III 42); prince of Takṣaśīla travels in magic ~ (*māyā-yantra-vimāna*); ~ coming when thought of (*dhyātōpanata*) 42,182 (TP III 273) and 44,170 (TP IV 12); ~ with pneumatic contrivance (*vāta-yantra-vimāna*) 43,38 (TP III 283); do, called *Bhūtāsana* 44,36 (TP IV 3); ~ in form of a white lotus (*mahā-padma-vimāna*) with 108 wings 46,123 (TP IV 57); ~ drawn by asses (*gardabha-ratha*) 48,54 (TP IV 78); ~ drawn by ghosts (*preta-vāhana*) 48,113 (TP IV 81); hunting ~ (*ratha*) for charioteer and king with minister behind him and drawn by more than two horses 54,3-5 (TP IV 184); flying ~ (*rathaṃ divyaṃ nabhaś-caram*) as wedding present to king 69,180 (TP VI 21); flying ~ (*dyu-cara-ratha*) produced by magic (*vijñāna*) 79,15 (TP VI 201); Rāma brings back Jānakī *devī* = Sītā in flying ~ 107,26 (TP VIII 45); Śiva Hara gives Naravāhanadatta ~ in lotus form made by Brahmā 107,133 (TP VIII 52) and 109,33 (TP VIII 72); deity presiding over ~ (*vimānādhideva*) of Gandharva princess 116,31 (TP VIII 158); ~ of prince 119,150 (TP VIII 203); – for ~ of snakes see: cloud; – see also: airship; *karṇī-ratha*; *govāṭa-vāhana*
charity (*pradāna*), *apsaras* as reward for ~ 17,133 (TP II 45); (*dāna*) in this life averts misery (*durgati*) in the next 61,216 (TP V 86); brahmin obtains two cows as ~ 62,92 (TP V 107); ladies of the court each take care of a sick person 66,38 (TP V 181); prince gives brahmin hermit enough money to enter the state of a householder 74,122 (TP VI 148f.); bathing-places, as against ~, lead to everlasting purity (*nitya-śuddha*) 86,21 (TP VII 14 : “salvation”); ~ to one’s neighbour (*parōpakāra*) is the only permanent thing in *saṃsāra* 90,20 TP VII 50); – see also: altruism; donation; fee; gift; reward
charm, see: spell
charmed barley-meal (*siddha-saktu*) 71,272 (TP VI 56)
charnel ground (*śmaśāna*), see: *Bhūta*(s); burning ground; note at hair-style
chase (*mṛgayā*) 9,9 (TP I 95), see: hunt(ing); vice
chastity, king takes vow of perpetual ~ (*brahma-carya-vratam*) after death of wife 6,90 (TP I 67); ~ of wife 36,30 (TP III 171f.); ~ of Sītā 51,76 (TP IV 27); wife’s proof of ~ 63,41 (TP V 123); nothing is unattainable by chaste women (*a-sādhyam satya-sādhvinām kim asti*) 63,67 (TP V 125); garland as index of ~ 123,148 (TP IX 53)²⁶⁹; – see also: fidelity to husband
chastity test motif²⁷⁰ 36,30 and 40 (TP III 171 fallen elephant rises only if touched by *sādhvī*);
child, ill-treated by stepmother (*apara-mātar*) 14,38f. (TP I 185); people with many ~ren are those who have committed many sins in a pre-birth; they are born to poor people in order that

²⁶⁸ STh F 861.2.1.

²⁶⁹ Is this connected with the idea of menstruation as a flower and deflowering as pregnancy ?

²⁷⁰ See TP I 165ff. and Bollée 2010: 63 note 359.

the parents may suffer for them 21,136 (TP II 135) and having many ~ren (*ati-bahu-bālaka*) is fruit of former misdeeds 30,93 (TP III 70)²⁷¹; ~ irradiates room at birth²⁷² 23,62 (TP II 161); description of newborn ~ren 23,66 (TP II 162); false rumour of ~ren eaten by hypocritical ascetic 24,209 (TP II 185); ~ cut out of mother's abdomen turns into sword 26,260 (TP II 236); crying ~ thrown into the fire is revived by charm on dust thrown onto the ashes 76,19ff. (TP VI 180); brahmin family with two ~ren (son and daughter) 78,9 (TP VI 191); merchant's daughter commanded by Hara in dream to leave newborn boy in cradle (*mañca-stham*) at king's gate 93,49 (TP VII 81); minister has golden image of seven-years-old boy made (*saptābda-deśīya-bālaka*) to be carried about in a small cart (*karṇī-ratha* [q.v.]) with a proclamation 94,90 (TP VII 93); ~ of hermit and nymph (*dyu-strī*) to be cooked and eaten enables hermit to see more of nymph flown away 108,75 (TP VIII 59); Tārāvaloka gives away his sons Rāma and Lakṣmaṇa to a brahmin 113,63 (TP VIII 128); brahmin sells ~ren in the market (*āpaṇe*) 113,81 (TP VIII 130); at birth ~, part-incarnation of Śiva, illuminates four quarters 115,130 (TP VIII 153); boy resembling sun (*arka-saṃnibha*) at birth 118,38 (TP VIII 180); mere boy is perfect gambler 124,210 (TP IX 83); after a hundred years of severe asceticism king of Daityas obtains son from Brahmā 115,5 (TP IX 144); – see also: filicide; son; substitution

childbearing, capability at ~ in middle life 104,20 (TP VIII 2)

childbed room, see: lying-in chamber

childbirth, see: death in ~ ; lying-in chamber

childhood, hermit from ~ (*ā bālyāt tāpasa*) 24,187 (TP II 182); – see also: *bāla-pravrājikā*

child labour Strabo, *Geography* XV 1,59

childless merchant wants son 13,55 (TP I 153); 39,5 (TP III 218); ~ king propitiates Ambikā 42,56 (TP III 263); – see also: son; sonless king

childlessness (*a-putratva*), though a major grief, 35,29 causes munificence (*dāna*) 34 (TP III 157); – see: sonlessness

child marriage, but wife being a child is left in her father's house (*bālatvāt sā sthāpitābhūt pitur grhe*) 124,92 (TP IX 74); 124,105 (TP IX 76)

child murder, see: filicide

children, deities substitute ~ in womb by *māyā*, see: substitution

chin (*cibuka*), old age seizes king by ~ 22,159 (TP II 149)

China, garments from ~ (“*crêpe de Chine*”) 43,75 (TP III 286)²⁷³; Suroha king of ~ with daughter, whose fair limbs are yellow as gold (*hāri-hemāvadātāṅgī* [read: *hari-haimā*^o ?]) 44,46 (TP IV 4);

cholera (*viṣūcikā*),²⁷⁴ king attacked by ~ 70,8 (TP VI 23);

choosing a king,²⁷⁵ state elephant (*maṅgala-gaja*) chooses merchant as king 65,25 (TP V 155)

²⁷¹ Cf. 21,135 (TP II 135) “this woman has five sons ... to such an extent is such a one the possessor of merit.”

²⁷² Cf. Bollée 2005: 16.

²⁷³ Cf. Chojnacki 2008: I 362 s.v. *soie de Chine*, and II 55 note 159; Daṇḍin, *Daś* 129,6.

²⁷⁴ Meulenbeld 1974: 622 who states that the arguments to equate *viṣūcikā* with cholera are insufficient.

and 175ff.)²⁷⁶; – see also: free will
chowries (*cāmara*), heavenly maiden fanned with white ~ 17,109 (TP II 43); ~ waved near king 18,403 (TP II 80); 20,178 (TP II 111); elephant ears compared to white ~ 19,68 (TP II 90); ~ distinguish old king and, waving, seem to repel young princess, as if saying: “Leave this old man” 31,40 (TP III 84 with note); bushy tails of *camari* deer compared to ~ 59,42 (TP V 29); ~ compared to long-maned lion-heads 75,65 and to blossom clusters of trees 66 (TP VI 168); ~ waved by captured wives of enemies 78,6 (TP VI 191);
churning (*manthana*) of the ocean ch. 9, opening stanza (TP I 94); maiden remains unmarried in her father’s house like the goddess of Prosperity (Kamalā) in the cavity of the ocean before its ~ 11,80 (TP I 128); 100,15 (TP VII 129); Kālarātrī was created by Viṣṇu at the ~ for the nectar, in order that she might destroy the Dānava chiefs who wished to steal it 109,90 (TP VIII 76)
*cīna-piṣṭa*²⁷⁷ ‘red lead, vermilion’, at a feast due to a royal birth people (*loka*) were ~-*maya* ‘smeared with red powder’²⁷⁸ 23,85 (TP II 164 with note 4 about *kunkam* ‘red or pink powder’ which, however, is saffron [Chojnacki 2008: I 361]; ORC 203f.: “*Les gens ? Rouges du vermillon festif !*”); – see also Appendix IV (TP I 244 and 256) and TP II 24 note; Selwyn 1979: 684
cinnabar (*dhātu*), Asura Maya looking like a mountain in the night ... and his robe (*raktāmbara*) resembles streams of ~ 45,4 (TP IV 17; ORC 467 “*Maya ... et le métal cuivré qui ressortait de son vêtement rouge lui donnaient l’apparence d’un mont, la nuit*”; MI 647: “*sein dunkelrotes Gewand gleich hervorbrechenden und überquellenden Erzen*” [?]); 51,169 (TP IV 134)
cintā-maṇi ‘wishing or philosopher’s stone’, town resembling ~ 43,65 (TP III 285); 46,247 (TP IV 66); ape daily giving a thousand *dinārs* as ~ 57,153 (TP V 12); king known as ~ 72,164 (TP VI 81)
cintā-ratna ‘gem yielding all desires, philosopher’s stone’, sword like ~ 42,145 (TP III 270);
cintitōpasthita, see: thought, coming on ~
cipiṭa-ghrāṇa ‘flat-nosed’, of a woman which husband considers a shortcoming 61,15 (TP V 68)
cīri-cītkāra ‘shrill sound of grasshoppers’ 73,240 (TP VI 118); 87,32 (TP VII 31)
circle, see: magic circle
circle incantation (*maṇḍalārcana*) 38,59 (TP III 210)

²⁷⁵ See Steermann-Imre 1977; Zachariae 1977: 784f.

²⁷⁶ STh H 171.1.

²⁷⁷ See the synonym *sindūram* in Mayrhofer’s CESD where Trudy pleads for Chinese origin; Bollée 2010a. For the etymology of China see Wade 2009.

²⁷⁸ According to Selwyn 1979: 684 the effect of this in a marriage ceremony is that the body is heated up for sexual intercourse. As not only the spouse but also his mother and many male and female relatives and guests are treated thus the intention is to heat up the atmosphere to which music helps. Thus it will also increase festivity in the birth festival in 23,85. For music at ceremonies as a means to ward off evil influences see note on: drum (91,23 [TP VII 67]). See also Hanchett 1988: 288, especially on the colour designation of turmeric.

circumambulation,²⁷⁹ see: *agni-pradakṣiṇā*; lustration; *pradakṣiṇā*; pre-birth; *vahni-pradakṣiṇa cīrikā* (notice) hung at the main gate (*siṃha-dvāre*) 55,37 (TP IV 205); bard puts up ~ about painter at gate of king's court 71,81 (TP VI 41);

Citragupta (Yama's secretary) disguised as brahmin (*brāhmaṇâkṛtiḥ*) visits robber 72,327 (TP VI 93); ~ asks wife of robber, his exclusive devotee 72,329 (TP VI 93); ~s *te prīto 'stu !* 72,326 (TP VI 93); through *māyā* ~ creates *divyā stri* in order to get hold of Siṃhavikrama 72,341 (TP VI 94); ~ writes transgressions (*agha*) in birch-bark register (*bhūrja*) 72,360 (TP VI 95);

citra-kalā 'art of painting' 44,52 (TP IV 4)

citra-kalpanā 'painting' in sky (*vyomni*), an impossibility 40,21 (TP III 241)

citra-paṭha 'painting on canvas' with female beauty on monastery wall seen by wandering bard (*bandī*) 122,74 (TP IX 39)²⁸⁰

citra-phalaka 'tablet for painting' 117,24 (TP VIII 165)

citron (*mātuluṅga-phala*)²⁸¹ with jewels given to *kārpaṭika* 53,33 (TP IV 170); being fresh fruit, ~ is good omen (*śakuna*) 53,50 (TP IV 171);

citrôj्jvala-sthiti 'seat of fine arts' said of Lāṭa 74,139 (TP VI 150);

city, (*pura*) of Daityas looking like snake Ananta emerged from earth²⁸² 10,49 (TP I 109); ~ (*nagarī*) of the gods Amarāvati 11,31 (TP I 125); Buddhist ~ (*purī*) of Takṣasīlā on river Vitastā 27,10 (TP III 2); ~ (*purī*) of Ujjayinī in Avanti and residence of Śiva Mahākāla 27,135 (TP III 11) and 120, 9 (TP IX 2); Valabhī ~ (*purī*) of learning 32,43 (TP III 92); ~ of Vajriṇ (Indra) made by the *Asura* Maya 34,149 (TP III 139); forest ~ (*pura*) like fruit of the finder's tree of merit (*punya-taru*) fallen to him for enjoyment 39,78 (TP III 223); Dhūmapura as home of all felicity (*sarva-sampad-gṛha*) 39,84 (TP III 223); empty (*śūnya*) ~ (*pura*) 43,46 (TP III 284)²⁸³; ~ resembling philosopher's stone (*cintā-maṇi-prakhyā-pura*) 43,65 (TP III 285); golden ~ (*pura*) in fourth *pātāla* 45,134f. (TP IV 26); ~ of Kanaka pura on river Ganges 55,26 (TP IV 204); ~ (*nagara*) of Kuṇḍina in Vidarbha 55,56 (TP IV 206); ~ of gold (*pura*) like peak of Mt Meru 81,97f. (TP VI 215); ~ built by the gods (Ujjayinī) 83,5 (TP VII 1); submarine ~ (*pura*) of Pārvatī 81,74 (TP VI 214) and (*nagara*) 86,90 (TP VII 19); two cities, the work of Viśvakarman, inherited by Asura princess 81,101 (TP VI 215); ~ (*nagarī*) of Ayodhyā, residence of Kubera 103,162 (TP VII 186); ~ (*purī*) of Vārāṇasī, bestows emancipation (*apavarga-dā*) 114,17 (TP VIII 133); – see also: Ananta; *deva-nirmita*; *Gandharva-nagara*; golden city

²⁷⁹ STh *D 1791.

²⁸⁰ Cf. 51,124 (TP IV 131).

²⁸¹ McHugh 2012: 68f.

²⁸² The snake had a thousand heads and there were a thousand Daitya princesses (10,39 [TP I 108]). The comparison of women to snakes is common because of their unreliability (e.g. 37,143 [TP III 141]), here perhaps referring to the hero being tricked by the Asura maid (vs. 53). Does the curious comparison also pertain to the largeness of the city (see supra: Ananta) ?

²⁸³ STh F 766ff.

city-guards (*pura-rakṣi*) 75,165-7 (TP VI 175f.)

clairvoyance, see: *avadhi-jñāna*

clapping of hands, loud sound of ~ (*lasad-uttāla*) by *vetālas* on charnel ground at night 25,136 (TP II 201), cf. 108,107 (TP VIII 62); of fool ~ with both hands and then falling from tree into river 65,211 (TP V 171)²⁸⁴

class (*varṇa*),²⁸⁵ mix of ~es (*varṇa-saṃsarga* or *-saṃhāra*): brahmin x princess 7,83 and 101 (TP I 83 and 85); idem, 18,287 (TP II 71) and 25,171 (TP II 204); idem, 28,92 (TP III 27); do, 89,55 and 58 (TP VII 44); do, 112,106 (TP VIII 114); brahmin x *kṣatriya* woman against her will 52,38 (TP IV 140); prince x merchant woman 15,44 (TP II 5); 21,59 (TP II 129); and 67,53 (TP V 199); prince ascribes adulterous beloved to her being a merchant's daughter 21,74 (TP II 131); king x merchant's daughter 18,80 (TP II 55); brahmin x *vidyādhari* 18,220 (TP II 66) and 26,280 (TP II 238)²⁸⁶; brahmin x merchant daughter 18,386 (TP II 78); idem 27,180 (TP III 15); brahmin x *rākṣasī* 25,208 (TP II 206); brahmin x *yakṣa* princess 26,218 (TP II 234); king x merchant beauty 33,72 (TP III 112); brahmin ex-*yakṣa* x mortal ex-*yakṣiṇī* 34,87f. (TP III 135); queen x shipwrecked merchant 36,86 (TP III 175); prince x *rākṣasī* 42,143 (TP III 269); prince x *cāṇḍāla* maiden 112,74 (TP VIII 111); fisherman x princess (112,144; TP VIII 117);); *apsaras* x gambler 121,116 (TP IX 20); – Lāṭa is a district (*deśa-viṣaya*) without mix of classes (*a-saṃkīrṇa-varṇa*) 74,138f. (TP VI 150); in Citrakūṭa the established divisions of the ~es (*varṇa-bheda*) are strictly kept 94,4 (TP VII 87; – see also: brahmin; four social classes; (*gāndharva*) marriage; merchant; polygamy; prince(ss); Sāmaveda singer; untouchability

clay as soap substitute, see: *snāna-mṛttikā*

clay (*mṛt*), pseudo-ascetic smears his body with ~ 24,93 (TP II 176); ~ figures 113,68 (TP VIII 129); – see also: *Avīci*; toy

clothes, see: garment; hunting-coat

cloud(s),²⁸⁷ suddenly arise, pelting down heavy shower which makes elephant's skin contract and it is swept into the Ganges 12,110 (TP I 141); king like ~ raining gold on dependents (*anujīviṣu*) 18,50 (TP II 53); enemies treated as autumn treats ~s 19,94 (TP II 92); maid sits on lion like digit of moon resting in the lap of autumn ~ 22,107 (TP II 145); king possesses queen like ~ holds lightning 24,20 (TP II 171); ~ black like a roaring *rākṣasa* with flickering lightning as his lolling tongue 25,41 (TP II 191)²⁸⁸; red evening ~ resembling raw flesh eaten by *rākṣasas* 25,237 (TP II 208); terrible ~ rises from lake and rains two black snakes which then become bow and string 46,91 (TP IV 54f.); ~s in

²⁸⁴ Cf. the chattering turtle at 60,176 (TP V 56).

²⁸⁵ The class system exists also with *nāgas*, *rākṣasas*, *yakṣas*, etc. (q.v.). In orthodox *smārta* tradition of Hinduism the classes consider themselves as quasi-biological human species whose differences “although less conspicuous, are as significant as those between cows and elephants” (Halbfass 1992: 274).

²⁸⁶ For the union of mortals and immortals see, e.g., Doniger O'Flaherty 1980a: 125f.

²⁸⁷ See Sivaramamurti 1980: 53ff.

²⁸⁸ Cf. *Bṛhatsaṃhitā* XXIV 14 where the moving tongues of cosmic snakes are compared to lightning in clouds.

dream mean fear 46,145 (TP IV 58)²⁸⁹; beautiful women captivate by faces like an autumn ~ 47,107 (TP IV 73); black ~ (*kāla-megha*) with flashing eyes of lightning 52,323 (TP IV 160: “~ of doom”); on the sixth night after birth of prince ~ appears covering the whole sky 55,186 (TP IV 215); what is the use of a ~ when winter has arrived? 66,35 (TP V 180); robber in the form of a ~ (*vārida-taskara*) 67,59 (TP V 200); when ~s roar, peacocks begin to dance 71,17 (TP I 37); *yakṣa* roaring like a monsoon ~ (*prāvṛṇ-megha ivôṇna dan*) 72,58 (TP VI 72); females are enveloped with a thick ~ of passion 72,256 (TP VI 87)²⁹⁰; blue lotuses like ~ of smoke (*dhūma-paṭala*) from the fire of snake-poison 74,212 (TP VI 155)²⁹¹; roaring ~ as a bandit and wind like fate destroy ship 101,141 (TP VII 144); chariots of snakes are ~ (*nāgānām vāhanā meghāḥ*) 124,222 (TP IX 84); – see also: autumn; *cāṭaka*; dice; elephant; sacrifice

clove-tree (*lavaṅga*)²⁹², garden with ~s 111,15 (TP VIII 96 with note 2)

clyster (*vasti*) drunk, see: rash act

cobra, spell makes ~ creep into bamboo 69,69 (TP VI 13); poison of dead ~ carried by kite falls into brahmin’s rice and kills him 87,44-50 (TP VII 32); – see also: black snake; krait

cobwebs (*jāla-kārālaya*) in prison 101,290 (TP VII 154); – see also: webs

cockcrow, see: daybreak

Coḍa-karṇa (‘projecting-ears’),²⁹³ name of brahmin muttering prayers 69,164 (TP VI 20); coeval (*vayasya*) prince and five ministers 101,47 (TP VII 137)²⁹⁴; 115,44 (TP VIII 147), – see also: age; *vayasya*

cohabitation of brahmin couple (*Sumanasā saha ... suptavān aham*) 123,220 (TP IX 59); – see also: sex

colander (*pavitra*) in hand of brahmin 93,92 (TP VII 85)²⁹⁵

coldness (*jāḍya*), see pearls

colic (*śūla*) followed by vomiting due to overeating 54,183 (TP IV 197)²⁹⁶

collective suffix, see: *añjanādri*; cloud; *-dvipa*; elephant of winter; lion of spring; mountain; ocean; *rūpābdhi*; *-sāgara*; sea; tree

collyrium, see *añjana*; *siddhāñjana*

colocynth fruit (*kiṃpāka-phala*)²⁹⁷ of bitter aftertaste, effort for a woman is like ~ 37,145 (TP III 193);

colour,²⁹⁸ dispute on black or white ~ of the sun’s horses 22,181 (TP II 150); *vidyādhara*s with

²⁸⁹ Clouds do not occur in Jagaddeva.

²⁹⁰ For a relation between women and clouds cf. *Ṛtusamhāra* II 19.

²⁹¹ Stubbe-Diarra 1995: 18ff.

²⁹² See Kuv note 119.

²⁹³ For such names see Bollée 2010b.

²⁹⁴ See Bollée 1981: 188f.; 2008a: 11 under co-natal.

²⁹⁵ Gonda 1965: 165.

²⁹⁶ Cf. BKBh 1024 (cty) and 5831. – Quod me nutrit me destruit (Chr. Marlowe).

²⁹⁷ On the bitter apple see http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Citrullus_colocynthis

yellow body 35,20 (TP III 156); very dark (*kṛṣṇa-kṛṣṇa*) *vidyādhara* with tawny hair (*kapila-mūrdha-ja*) 48,71 (TP IV 79); flowers of five ~s 63,15 (TP V 121); – see: black and red; darkness; eye; halo; light(ning); radiating; white; yellow

combat, unfair ~ (*a-dharma-yuddha*) refused by true *kṣatriya* 38,133 (TP III 215); single ~ 43,120 (TP III 289) and 44,150 (TP IV 11); consecration for ~ (*raṇa-dikṣā*) 46,172 (TP IV 60); single ~ (*dvandva-yuddha*) 47,56 (TP IV 70)²⁹⁹; idem 48,20 (TP IV 76); ~ with severed heads of heroes flying up and down, like game of ball with which Death was amusing himself (*kṛtānta-kanduka-kriḍā-saṃnibha*) 50,7 (TP IV 108); ~ as sacrifice for the demons which was full of blood for wine (*śonitāsava-saṃpūrṇa*), and in which the heads of enemies were strewn as an offering (*bhūta-mahā-yāga*) 107,103 (TP VIII 50; ORC 1125: “*comme un grand sacrifice aux démons avec du sang comme liqueur sacrificielle et les têtes répandues des ennemis comme offrandes*”); ~ yawned like demon of destruction 108,106 (TP VIII 62); – see also: battle

comedium of father and daughter among *vidyādhara* royals 86,131 (TP VII 22)

comforting (*āśvās*) a friend 4,115 (TP I 40); 17,13 (TP II 35); 101,195 (TP VII 146); 106,79 (TP VIII 34); 117,63 (TP VIII 168); 119,23 (TP VIII 194) et passim

coming late motif 21,75 (TP II 131)

coming, when thought of (*cintitōpasthitā*), of Sarasvatī 5,18 (TP I 47); ~ (*dhyātāgata*), of *rākṣasa* 5,47 (TP I 50); ~ (*dhyānād upasthitā*), of Gaṅgā 5,55 (TP I 51); ~ (*smṛta-mātrāgata*), of Nāga 6,16 (TP I 61); the Gaṇa Pañcaśikha comes when brahmin thinks of him 7,83 (TP I 83); Agni gives brahmin sword ~ 18,116 (TP II 58); ~ of *rākṣasa* 18,341 (TP II 75); ~ , of Madanavega 34,37 (TP III 130); ~ of Kubera 38,71 and 80 (TP III 211f.); ~ , of food 43,63 (TP III 285); ~ of Suvāsakumāra to dissipate delusive portents (*utpāta-māyāḥ*) 46,30 (TP IV 51); ~ of five gods as servants of Nala 56,267 (TP IV 239); 65,70 and 83 and 93 (TP V 160ff.); minister carried on shoulders of deformed man who comes ~ 75,4 (TP VI 164); the science *Prajñapti* is ~ to royal dreamer 111,52 (TP VIII 100); ~ (*saṃsmṛtōpasthita*) of *amartya-guru* Bṛhaspati by Indra 115,93 (TP VIII 150); ~ (*smṛtāyāta*) of *vetāla* by *kārpaṭika* 123,35 (TP IX 45)

company, after father’s death son gets into evil ~ 77,18 (TP VI 184);

comparison(s); *dr̥ṣṭānta*:³⁰⁰ splendid city of Daityas looks like serpent Ananta having emerged from the earth 10,49 (TP I 109); man and wife united like bed of white lotuses with night 10,181 (TP I 119); king adorns himself with a ... queen like an able poet who likes many ~ (*rājā śuśubhe ... nānā-dr̥ṣṭānta-rasiko bhāratyā su-kavir yathā*) 27,56 (TP III 5)

²⁹⁸ See ORC 1556.

²⁹⁹ STh H 1561.2

³⁰⁰ In Gonda 1949 I have not found references from KSS but some similes will occur also in other texts. The search for them, however, is much hindered by the absence of an index rerum of the book. This severe disadvantage also affects Jackmuth 2002 and compels the user to leaf through nearly twohundred pages one by one. It then still appears that Somadeva may hardly have read Kālidāsa or intentionally have made own comparisons (unless he found them in the material he was treating).

“(queen) was such an ornament to the king as language is to a poet”; ORC 258: “*Ce roi, tel un poète habile, trouvait plaisir à citer toutes sortes de paraboles, et la reine ... lui faisait honneur*”; M I 366: “*der König schmückte sich mit ... der Frau, wie sich ein wort gewandter, für zahlreiche Auslegungen Sinn besitzender Dichter sich mit der Sprache schmückt*”); king compared to wind (*vāyu*) chasing queens like creepers 6,112 (TP I 69); swing of doubt (*vicāra-dolā*) 9,87 (TP I 102); city of Daityas like snake Ananta 10,49 (TP I 109); policy (*nīti*) likened to Vindhya forest as *durgamā* 12,44 (TP I 136); white palaces of a city compared to smile 18,10 (TP II 50); king is surrounded by chiefs like polar star by planets 18,5 (TP II 49); king like cloud raining gold on dependents 18,50 (TP II 49); fatigue removed by Śiva’s favour like new moon by rays of sun 19,8 (TP II 85); armies compared to monsoon clouds 19,59 (TP II 89); elephant ears like white chowries 19,68 (TP II 90); antelopes, fleeing in terror, seemed like the sidelong glances of the quarters previously conquered (*pūrvābhībūtānām kaṭākṣāḥ kakubhām iva*) (by the king) 21,13 (TP II 126); resplendent woman looks like meteor fallen from cloud 21,72 (TP II 130); fortune of kings is ever bounding away like a doe 21,99 (TP II 132); unmarried maiden of good family is like song without tune 24,25 (TP II 172); rosary beads compared to transgressions 24,102 (TP II 177); black thunder-cloud like *rākṣasa* 25,41 (TP II 191f.); caprices of destiny compared to waves of the sea 26,18 (TP II 218); white palaces in Ujjayinī likened to peaks of Kailāsa 27,136 (TP III 11); enemies fleeing like deer 27,138 (TP III 11); five faults likened to fires 28,32 (TP III 22); princess as smokeless fire 28,77 (TP III 26)³⁰¹; your love is my life, even as the water is of the lotus 33,88 (TP III 113); dinars like second, external soul of brahmin 33,156 (TP III 120); daughter of Kaliṅgasenā clings to face of nurse as candle clings to the wick 34,98 (TP III 135); woman’s rolling eyes likened to bees 35,11 (TP III 156); king gives daughter to husband as the sea gave Lakṣmī to Viṣṇu 35,154 (TP III 167)³⁰²; monkey’s eyes like rubies 37,88 (TP III 189); queen sheds tear like knot of grief 43,245 (TP III 298); prince adorned by his wife like monsoon with lightnings = garland of sparkling ornaments, etc. 44,179 (TP IV 13); princess coming forward to dance compared to moon come to the underworld out of curiosity (*kautukād iva Pātālam āgatām*) 45,233 (TP IV 33); sword-blades like tongues of death 50,5 (TP IV 108); daughter grows like digit of moon 51,22 (TP IV 123); dead body like frost-smitten lotus 52,151 (TP IV 148); women like rivers 52,288 (TP IV 157); kings ravenous like cats 52,372 (TP IV 164); boon joined with curse compared to nectar mixed with poison 55,196 (TP IV 215); gait of she-elephant likened to that of queen 55,201 (TP IV 216); dancing-girl (*lāsikī*) dancing like a wave of the sea of beauty tossed up by the wind of youth 57,75 (TP V 7); what wise man looks for love in courtesans or for oil in sand 57,128 (TP V 10); women are like flies 58,136 (TP V 24); *vidyādhara* maiden like moon digit amid stars, etc. 59,3 (TP V 26); Rohiṇī tree resembles

³⁰¹ “I.e. fire kindled with dry wood and hence blazing brightly” (Van Buitenen 1962: 123 on MaitUp 1.2).

³⁰² Husband is god to his wife (Manu V 154).

the Vedas 59,37 (TP V 28); this world's beauty is short-lived like that of a religious festival 66,33 (TP V 180); expanded eye of woman likened to garland of blue lotuses which she threw at man thus choosing him for husband 67,22 (TP V 197); elephant sunk in mud like a mountain that has fallen due to its wings having been cut off by Indra's *vajra* 68,21f. (TP VI 3); prince equals singing of female cuckoos (*pikī*) to that of his wife 69,7 (TP VI 9); wife closely knit to husband as oblation to fire 69,16 (TP VI 10); dancing princess looks like creeper of the tree of love (*vallī smara-taror*) agitated by the wind of youth 71,77 (TP VI 41); showers of flowers likened to showers of arrows of love 71,199 (TP VI 50); moon like a splendid ear-ornament (*karṇa-pūra*) ... made of a shoot from the wishing-tree of love 72,27 (TP VI 70); a poor brahmin does not cut a good figure amidst rich people just as a word without meaning among words of a splendid poem 73,24 (TP VI 102); brahmin lives with *yakṣiṇī* like banyan-tree with glory of spring 73,27 (TP VI 102); dice as sidelong loving looks of the goddess of Ill Luck 73,76 (TP VI 106); king stays pining like *cātaka*-cuckoo (q.v.) 73,98 (TP VI 108); roaming dark deer compared to rolling eyes of the forest 73,239 (TP VI 118); sleeping princess on bed seems like the orb of the autumn moon lapped in a fragment of white cloud 73,340 (TP VI 125); blue lotuses likened to clouds of smoke from the fire of snake-poison 74,212 (TP VI 155); armies (*śainya-jaladhī*) likened to eastern and western seas 74,282 (TP VI 160); yellow pollen of flowers likened to fires of separation 81,63 (TP VI 213); eddies of sea compared to eyes with waves as curved brows 86,74 (TP VII 18); tumbling dice as rolling eyes of calamities the colour of black antelope 92,16 (TP VII 72); lotuses moved by the wind look like beckoning hands 94,16 (TP VII 88 note 2); hermits with coats of bark resemble trees 94,36 (TP VII 90); a husband distasteful to his wife is like a bitter medicine to a sick man 95,9 (TP VII 98); moon on heaven's western quarter compared to patch (*tilaka*) on the forehead 95,67 (TP VII 102); temple of Durgā like the mouth of Death ... 101,300 (TP VII 155); Mt Vindhya lofty as soul of prince Mrgāṅkadatta 102,71 (TP VII 167); three-furrowed frown on king's head like Durgā's trident 102,72 (TP VII 167f.); arrows flying through the air descend on warriors like locusts on the tender herb 103,5 (TP VII 175); moon as own brother to the curved corner of an angry, long-eyed beauty's eye makes, glowing with fresh reddish (*sindūra*) colour, itself the driving hook of the elephant of the eastern mountain (of sunrise) 103,204 (TP VII 189); waves like hands stroke waists of bathing women 104,90 (TP VIII 7); queen deprived of daughter is confounded like *vidyādhari* who lost her magic power 105,13 (TP VIII 22); warriors are like trees marked for the axe 108,105 (TP VIII 62); hermit Akampana looking like a great tree 110,24 (TP VIII 83); queen resembles night in being moon-faced 110,135 (TP VIII 92); pregnant queen compared to eastern quarter at sunrise 120,44 (TP IX 4); lake, deep and broad, like the heart of great men, looking like a material representation of Nirvāṇa that allays the fire of desire (*tṛṣṇā* lit. thirst') 120,116 (TP IX 9); boar black as a *tamāla* tree 123,8 (TP IX 43); after long time man greets his wife as the cloud does the *cātakī* 123,335 (TP X 66); – pining away with longing see: emaciation; – hue of sunset is like (colour of) Buddhist robe (q.v.); royal couple likened to partridges, see *cakrāhva*; – see further: breast; city; cloud;

elephant; enemies; exaggeration; fire; gambling; Gaṇeśa; gesture; *ketaka*; lion; partridge; prosperity; riches; spring; temple of Ambikā

compassion,³⁰³ Skanda-*jananī* = Pārvaṭī is moved with ~ (*sa-dayā*) at seeing the love of three women for the son of one 3,16 (TP I 19); ~ (*dayādra-dhī*) of *muni* with lost queen 9,63 (TP I 99); ~ (*kāruṇya*) with Daitya princess 10,37 (TP I 108); ~ (*dayā*) with lonely woman 10,71 (TP I 111); king's ~ with poor brahmin mother of twins 21,45 (TP II 128); innate ~ of Jīmūtavāhana with all creatures 22,24 (TP II 139), especially snakes 22,219 (TP II 153); ~ of Śavara with victim of human sacrifice 22,65 (TP II 141); king's ~ with abused husband 23,26 (TP II 158); ~ of people with father of son become *rākṣasa* 25,113 (TP II 199); ~ with impaled man begging for water 25,131 (TP II 201); great-hearted (*mahāśayāḥ*) feel ~ even for their enemies when terrified 26,248 (TP II 235); ~ of Buddha 28,10 (TP III 18); ~ of herdsman with lonely woman 29,155 (TP III 51); ~ of witch with ox 37,155 (TP III 194); ~ of queen with wicked concubines 39,226f. (TP III 234); ~ of prince for wicked brothers 39,236 (TP III 235); males show no ~ for their females though they are attached to them 43,161 (TP III 292); ~ of female warder (*prātihāri*) with wife fleeing husband 52,47 (TP IV 141); ~ of king with beggar 53,24 (TP IV 169); ~ of merchant with lost children 56,39 (TP IV 222); Buddhist ~ cancels sin of offenders 56,162-64 (TP IV 231); ~ with lonely woman 56,199-202 (TP IV 234); ~ of Nala with snake 56,344 (TP IV 245); ~ of *yakṣas* with poor forester 57,28 (TP V 3); ~ of physician with man whose wicked wife cut off his ears and nose 58,102 (TP V 22); ~ of hermit with parrot 59,54 (TP V 30); ~ of king with protection seeker 62,100 (TP V 107); ~ of hermit with mouse which he turns into maiden 62,125 (TP V 109); ~ of teacher with pupils who crush his feet 63,172 (TP V 134); out of ~ ascetic brings insensible man round 67,103 (TP V 203); ~ of *muni* with female jackal 68,19 (TP VI 2); ~ of hermit with elephant ; man rescued from poison out of false ~ 69,60 (TP VI 13); seemingly out of ~ with lonely woman, night disappears to let her see her way 71,191 (TP VI 49); moved with ~ at seeing lonely princess in forest heaven lets fall drops of dew as tears 71,192 (TP VI 49); ~ of *tāpasī* with planned suicidal 72,21 (TP VI 69); ~ of Siddha prince with stupid brahmin boy who tries to fly with wings of grass 72,279 (TP VI 88); ~ of hermit with merchant in love with painting of his loved princess 72,301 (TP VI 90); ~ parents deposit son after birth in house of brahmin 73,185 (TP VI 114); ~ of sister with brother 73,213 (TP VI 116); sun sets as if in ~ with people's sufferings 73,241 (TP VI 118); ~ with snake-bitten brahmin makes minister prevent his suicide by knowledge of poisons 75,14 (TP VI 165); corpse, rubbed by king out of ~, laughs (*aṭṭa-hāsa*) 75,53 (TP VI 167); ~ of king with vassal 81,24 (TP VI 210); brahmin woman gives brahmin traveller rice out of ~ (*saṃjāta-dayā*) 87,36 (TP VII 32); prince gives up realm out of ~ 90,36 (TP VII 51); ~ (*kṛpā*) of Jīmūtavāhana with mother of snake to be eaten by Garuḍa 90,127 (TP VII 58); world is full of people with self-pity (q.v.) 90,140 (TP VII 58); the good are easily melted with ~, and show causeless friendship to all 101,20 (TP VII 135); ~ of hermit with lost princess 101,153f. (TP VII

³⁰³ Bollée 2008a: 11.

144); stocks (*kāṣṭha*) and herbs weep with ~ 101,255 (TP VII 151f.); grain thrown into the fire compared to Kāmas laughter 103,93 (TP VII 188); forester (*vana-cara*) has ~ with brahminical status of traveller 104,210 (TP VIII 17); ~ of *dhātṛ* with brahmin refugee 108,47 (TP VIII 56); out of *kṛpā* family goddess Caṇḍī reanimates dead couple 111,45 (TP VIII 99); ~ of woman servant with king in robber's dwelling 112,161 (TP VIII 119); even beasts and birds weep seeing crown-prince and family going to forest 113,52 (TP VIII 128)³⁰⁴; two *caṇḍālas*, thought to be thieves and cut off ears and noses by robbers, set free by their chiefs out of ~ 114,111ff. (TP VIII 140ff.); even Buddha (Sugata) has little ~ with people wanting in pre-birth merit 117,32 (TP VIII 166); – see also: comforting; herb; herdsman; Kāma; Mahāyāna ideas; sidelong glances; social feeling

conception, in the nose by smell of human sacrifice (*gandhâghrāṇataḥ*) 13,64 (TP I 154); oral ~ of moon³⁰⁵ entering queen's mouth in dream 59,61 (TP V 30); Śrī conceives a son from a celibate ascetic by his auspicious viewing (*tvad-darśanān mamôtpannaḥ putraḥ*) 59,95f. (TP V 33); mysterious (*a-tarkita*)³⁰⁶ ~ 118,34 (TP VIII 180); – see also: birth in unusual way; parthenogenesis

concert (*saṃgīta*)³⁰⁷, king, roaming through many countries with wives and ministers, amuses himself with ~s, drinking parties, etc. 44,40-51 (TP IV 4)

concert hall (*gāndharva-śālā*) in palace 12,31 (TP I 135); ~ (*saṃgīta-veśman*) in royal garden 34,170 (TP III 140); ~ with Nārada and Rambhā (*Nārada-Rambhâdi-saṃgīta*) in Indra's heaven 118,117 (TP VIII 186); – see also: music room

conch, sound of ~ at midday 29,48 (TP III 42)³⁰⁸

condemnation, hasty ~ of man who accidentally becomes suspected of crime 54,115 (TP IV 191)³⁰⁹; – see also: rash act(s)

condemned invokes Śiva's protection 54,115 (TP IV 192)

condolence (*āśvāsana*), queens meeting at night for mutual ~ 47,96 (TP IV 73)

conduct, immoral ~ in shape of monkey 15,50 (TP II 5); after evil omen brahmin goes with friends against his will (*vivaśa*) 32,53 (TP III 94); attendant following king unwillingly 42,28 (TP III 261); – see also: gestures

confidante (*sakhī*) 31,1 (TP III 81); 46,174ff. (TP IV 60f.); 58,123 (TP V 24); 65,250 (TP V 174); wicked ~ 71,143 (TP VI 46); *ceṭī* 74,224 (TP VI 156); 94,29f. (TP VII 89); 95,39 (TP VII 100); 101, 247 (VII 151); 117,9 (TP VIII 164) et passim; – see further: address; *dhātreyī*; foster-sister; *rahasya-jñā*; *rahasya-dhāriṇī*; *sakhī*

³⁰⁴ Cf. Pieruccini 2006: 126ff.

³⁰⁵ The moon is *soma* (ŚatapathaBr 2,2,3,23), *soma* is seed (ŚpBr 3,3,2,1).

³⁰⁶ Perhaps when the woman first puts her foot into the hand of a *mantra-vādin*, as in Daś 232.16 (Bollée 2008a: 15 note 66).

³⁰⁷ *Saṃgīta* in fact is a dance recital with vocal and instrumental music (Sundaram 1979: 752), kind of *danse concertante*.

³⁰⁸ Also Bāṇa, Kād. 28,2 *madhyāhna-śaṅka-dhvani*.

³⁰⁹ For the motif see STh: N 342.

confiscation of wealth, instead of capital punishment 18,387 (TP II 78); ~ of adulterer 19,49 (TP II 88)

confluence (*saṅgama*) of rivers Candrabhāgā and Airāvātī, opening in the water (*vivaraṃ toyē*) at ~ leads to heavenly temple in Pātāla 45,67 (TP IV 22)

confusion makes woman transpose heads of husband and brother 80,50 (TP VI 207); – see also: bewilderment; doubt; gestures

congratulate (*abhinandati*), 45,128 (TP IV 26) and 155 (TP IV 28); 50,202 (TP IV 120); hermit comes to ~ (*diṣṭyā vardhayituṃ*) king on birth of son 118,40 (TP VIII 181);

consciousness, loss of ~ of two armies (*sainye niścetane*) caused by Dhanavātī 109,124 (TP VIII 79), Indra recovers ~ (*labdha-saṃjñā*) 115,74 (TP VIII 149)

consecration of Kārttikeya as army general (*śaināpatyābhīṣeka*) by Indra 24,95 (TP II 102); – see also: inauguration

consecration water (*abhiṣekāmbu*), pouring ~ 50,207 (TP IV 121); ~ of *cakravartin* by Gaurī 90,189 (TP VII 62); Lakṣmī visibly accompanies ~ 110,79 (TP VIII 87); – see also: inauguration

consent of first wife necessary for wedding others 26,186 (TP II 231); ~ of brother needed for sister's marriage 79,9 and 19 (TP VI 200f.)³¹⁰

consolation, tale told for ~ (*a-kheda*) 77,4 (TP VI 183)³¹¹; ~ (*āśvāsya*) of king by brahmin 100,27 (TP VII 130); ~ of prince by hermits 101,202 (TP VII 148); ~ of princess by attendant 117,165 (TP VIII 175); warder consoles army despondent after king's disappearance on hunt 123,83 (TP IX 49); – see also: condolence

conspiracy (*saṃvid*) of concubines against first queen 39,24 (TP III 219);

consternation, see: bewilderment

constitutional kingdom, see: democracy; *paura-svāmika-rājya*

consumption, see: *yakṣman*

contradiction, see: inconsistency

conversation (*kathā*) between Śaṅkara-Śiva and Brahmā, overhearing ~ 7,34 (TP I 77); ~ (*saṃlāpa*) with human speech of vultures in fig tree 26,28 (TP II 219); ~ of queens 47,97ff. (TP IV 73), see also: women; by ~ (*saṃbhāṣaṇa*) with a bad woman hermit loses his *tapaḥ-śakti* 65,52f. (TP V 158) and 100 (TP V 162); – see also: overhearing

conveyance, see: mount; peacock; *vahnī-bhūya*

cook (*sūpa-kāra*), ~s scolded because of innutritious meat 8,24 (TP I 90); queen blackmails king to have ~ kill brahmin and prepare his flesh for magic rite 20,191ff. (TP II 112)³¹²; king makes ~ eat poisoned sauce 49,41 (TP IV 87); Nala bitten by a snake becomes disguised as black and deformed ~ 56,347 (TP IV 246)³¹³; Nala is miraculous ~ 56,396 (TP IV 248)

³¹⁰ STh 131.1.

³¹¹ STh J 899.

³¹² See Wojtilla 2004: 341.

³¹³ Cf. Mbh 3,63,11.

copper, making gold out of ~ 35,82 (TP III 161)³¹⁴;
copper pot (*tāmra-kumbha*), bald man with head like ~ 61,48 (TP V 72); – see also:
kāṃsya-pātrī
coprophagous wife, see: entrails; vampire
copulating, king kills hermit who in shape of deer was ~ (*surata-sthita*) with is wife 21,23 (TP II 127); – see also: sex
coral, lips (*pravālābhara-danta-cchada*) of Upakośā 4,7 (TP I 31); *haṃsas* with beaks and feet of ~ (*pravāla-cañcu-caraṇa*) 114,40 (TP VIII 135);
coral tree, see: *pārijāta*
cord, sacred, see: *yajñopavīta*
corners of a magic circle (!), pitchers of blood placed in ~ (*koṇa-nyastāsra-kumbhaka*) 73,305 (TP VI 123; ORC 869: “*maṇḍala ... il avait placé des jarres pleines de sang aux coins*”)
cornucopia (*bhadra-ghaṭa*),³¹⁵ *yakṣas* give ~ to poor wood-carrier 57,31 (TP V 3)³¹⁶; – cf. *ghaṭaḥ kāma-daḥ*; magic vessel
coronation water,³¹⁷ wine with rosy glow (or: passion) compared to ~ in empire of love 21,7 (TP II 125); 50,203 (TP IV 121); ~ from many *ūrthas* falls on head of royal couple 103,233 (TP VII 191), cf. 110,77f. (TP VIII 87); – see also: inthronisation; water
corpse, of king entered by magician 4,99 (TP I 37); ~ of *vara-kanyakā* covered with a sheet (*paṭāvaguṇḥita-tanu*) 26,78 (TP II 223)³¹⁸; ~ of elephant entered by Lohajaṅga 12,109 (TP I 141); courtesans rather embrace a ~ than a poor man 12,92 (TP I 140); flying mendicant on shoulder of ~ 18,152 (TP II 62); dance of demons with ~s 47,92 (TP IV 72); ~ as plank in sea saves shipwrecked man 54,104 (TP IV 191); ~ with necklace 54,106 (TP IV 191); two men battling for ~ 73,288ff. (TP VI 121); dead sorcerer inside ~ eaten by *vetāla* 73,316 (TP VI 124); ~s dancing on battlefield 74,285 (TP VI 160); ~ looking like a Bhūt and possessed by *vetāla* crying out (*cakranda*) when dropped from *śiṃśapā* tree 75,51f. (TP VI 167); ~ with *vetāla* laughing 75,53 (TP VI 167) and 78,2 (TP VI 191); ~ groaning (*kūjanta*) 76,2 (TP VI 179); parents embrace ~ of dead son 97,18 (TP VII 113); ~ in magic circle 99,10 (TP VII 123) and 121,15 (TP IX 13); – see also: skeleton
corruption: alien servants are easily corrupted (*bheda-saha*) 32,174 (TP III 104); – see also: bribe; present; reward
cosmetic (*aṅga-rāga*), see: make-up; perfume
cosmic egg, Śivas thigh blood fallen into the (universal) water becomes ~ 2,11 (TP I 9)
cosmology, Vaiṣṇava ~: the earth is Viṣṇu’s foot, heaven his head, etc. 54,33 (TP IV 186)
cotton (*tūla*), fool throws ~ into the fire to purify it like gold 61,31 (TP V 70)³¹⁹; – see also:

³¹⁴ STh D 475.1.9.

³¹⁵ For a figure see Dallapiccola 2002: 158 (*puṇnaghata*)

³¹⁶ STh D 1470.2.3; Meyer 1952: 400 (*sthālī*).

³¹⁷ For a description of this in the Jain canon see Rāyapaseṇiyasutta § 190; see also Mette 1973a: 17f.

³¹⁸ Cf. 52,150 (TP IV 148).

banner

country, to virtuous man no ~ is foreign (*videśa*) 61,121 (TP V 78); native ~ (*janma-bhūmi*) 110,139 (TP VIII 92); – see also: *heimat*

coup de foudre, see: love at first sight

couple inseparable like Pārvatī and Śiva (Girijā-Śaṅkarau) 31,32 (TP III 83); Pārvatī tells dreamer he will marry his wife of a pre-birth 65,233 (TP V 172); heavenly ~ issuing from belly of elephant 123,90 (TP IX 49)

courage merits command (*vīro hi svāmyam arhati*) 18,140 (TP II 60); ~ of hero attacking *rākṣasī* 25,150 (TP II 202); prosperity dwells even in questionable deeds if they result from great ~ 27,208 (TP III 17)

court (*dharmārthā sabhā*) of the *vidyādharas* 106,157 (TP VIII 40)³²⁰; – see also: durbar
courtesan(s) prone to deceive (*vañcana-pravaṇā veśyāḥ*) 3,54 (TP I 22); ~ as *devadāsī* 12,80 (TP I 139)³²¹; ~ in love with poor brahmin 12,81 (TP I 139); ~s rather embrace corpse (*śava*) than a poor man 12,92 (TP I 140); palace (*vara-mandira*) of ~ (*vāra-vilāsini*) described 38,19ff. (TP III 207 with note 2); ~ in love with disguised king offered herself to him (*ātmānam arpayat*) 38,33 (TP III 208); ~ considers life to be poison-agony (*viṣa-vedanā*) and vows to enter the fire if heavenly man (= king Vikramāditya) does not return within six months 38,111ff. (TP III 214); ~s have no good character (*sad-bhāva*) 57,53 (TP V 5); bawd instructs ~ daughter to abandon passion 57,61 (TP V 6)³²²; ~ teaches merchant's son for thousand dinars ~s' skill 57,67 (TP V 6); what wise man looks for love in ~s or for oil in sand ? 57,128 (TP V 10); besieged king flees in disguise (*veṣa-cchanna*) to mansion of ~ (*vilāsini*) 58,15 (TP V 16); love of ~ tested by king's assumed death 58,29 (TP V 17); fivehundred elephants as fee of ~ 61,171 (TP V 83); ~ tells secret to bawd 61,174 (TP V 83); ~ (*veśyā*) was *brahma-kumārī* in pre-birth 69,163 (TP VI 20); ~ attains good state (*sad-gati*) 69,166 (P VI 21); ~'s fee five hundred dinars 93,34 (TP VII 80)³²³; deserted brahmin wife seeks husband as fake ~ 124,175 (TP IX 80)
courtesy (*vinaya*), out of ~ lady leaves chariot and goes on foot to palace 120,132 (TP IX 10)
coven, see: *ḍākinī-cakra*
covering, the face with garment by princess before dying³²⁴ 52,150 (TP IV 148); do, of man

³¹⁹ The story corresponds to Avadāna 71 (Penzer). – Cf. 56,351 *agni-śaucākhyā* (TP IV 245). Hierokles quoting Stephanos of Byzantium tells us that the brahmins' "dress is made of the soft and skin-like fibres of stones, which they weave into a stuff that no fire burns or water cleanses. When their clothes get soiled or dirty, they are thrown into a blazing fire, and come out quite white and bright" (McCrinkle 1901: 186).

³²⁰ On *sabhā* see e.g. Rau 1957: 75; Falk 1986.

³²¹ More on these see Sternbach 1953; Ambrose 1950: 32.

³²² In Daś 80.4ff. the duty of a courtesan is defined as "only readiness, no devotion" (*sajjatāiva, na saṅgaḥ*).

³²³ See Jamkhedkar 1984: 120 note 305; 143; Schmidt 1904: 557f.

³²⁴ The reason for this cannot be the same as for sleeping (see next). "Covering the head immediately after death is still practised in India. It is a kind of declaration that everything is over now" (p.c. Vijay Bedekar, of Thane). "In Bengal, though, the face is kept uncovered for everyone to keep *antya-darshana* of the deceased person" (p.c. Saraju Rath, of Leiden). In Vedic times the corpse is covered with a new white piece of cloth (Caland 1896 = 1967 § 8)

when sleeping 73,7 (TP VI 100 with note 1³²⁵); naked man covers himself out of shame with his hand (*hasta-chādita*) 73,383 (TP VI 128)³²⁶; brahmin woman uncovers face before uncle 123,241 (TP IX 60)

covetousness causes annoyance 61,108 (TP V 77);

cow captivated by grass, *purohita*'s mind captivated by jewels like ~ (*śaspair iva paśor manah*) 24,134 (TP II 179); strings of dry cow's sinew bitten off and fixed on her *viṇā* by *vidyādhari* cause her mortal rebirth in fisher family 26,170 (TP II 230); ~ given with *dakṣiṇā* 45,104 (TP IV 24); ~ (*paśu*) symbol of stupidity 61,23 (TP V); ~ not milked for a month by fool 61,46 (TP V 72); brahmin obtains two ~s as charity 62,92 (TP V 107); bull as sign of wealth 66,99 (TP VI 185); wife curses husband to become *mahiṣa* by throwing dust into his face (*dhūliṃ mukhe nyadhāt*) 68,45 (TP VI 5); brahmin beggar's brown ~ (*kapilā*), incarnation of Surabhi (the first ~), serves as nightly protection 108,29 (TP VIII 55);

cow-butter rubbed on head produces sleep 29,167 (TP III 52)

cowherd (*gopa*) singing with joy 64,112 (TP V 148); ~'s secret of adultery with brahmin wife 64,114 (TP V 148); – see also: *Ābhira*; disguise

cow of plenty, subjects (*prajāh*) are king's ~s (*kāma-dhenavaḥ*) 72,220 (TP VI 85)

cow's ear, stupid brahmin puts hands together in the shape of ~ so as to form a pipe and sings Vedic *sāmans* 6,57 (TP I 64)³²⁷;

cow's horn (*go-śṛṅga*) blown by Bhilla hunters 59,41 (TP V 29)

cowshed (*go-vāta-harmya*), *Kālarātrī* and her witches fly into the air in ~ 20,140 (TP II 107f.)

cow's meat venerated in the three worlds and carried for consumption by *cāṇḍāla* 26, 158 (TP II 228); horrible consequences of eating ~ 26,171 (TP II 230); travelling hungry brahmin pupils ritually sacrifice ~ and eat it 27,118 (TP III 9); villagers kill and eat *mahiṣa* in a Bhilla territory (*Bhilla-vāṭe*) 62,213 (TP V 117)³²⁸

cowry (*kapardaka*), cowries (used as money), gambler obtains daily one hundred ~ from others 121,73 (TP IX 17 with note 2)

crab(s) (*markaṭakāh*), sons eat father like ~s 28,48 (TP III 23); ~ (*jhaṣa*) advises crane to throw pieces of fish from dwelling of mongoose all the way to hole of snake 60, 235 (TP V 61)

and a piece of gold, or ghee is put on the seven openings of its head (do, § 26). In Europe especially the face of a corpse must be covered for which there may be two opposite reasons: either protection from the stare of the dead less the latter draws someone along with it (Seeligmann 1910 I 161 = 1980: 212), or the dead person must be protected from evil spirits or the evil eye (HdA V 1053). The latter seems most probable in the case of the princess above (see Croke 1896: II 47) though evil spirits can also enter the body via the unwashed feet, as in the case of Nala. The sacrificer in ancient Rome also covered his head as a protection against the evil eye (Samter 1901: 36). See also Rājat 2,43 (of a suicidal king), and the notes at “*capite velato*” supra and “hair-style” below.

³²⁵ “not merely as a protection against insects, but very possibly because of the ill-effects of moon-shine.”

³²⁶ At Ja I 72,15 a Nāga king who first had uttered praises of Siddhattha could not stay near him and retired to his palace under the earth laying down and covering his face with his hands: *ubhoḥi hatthehi mukhaṃ pidahitvā* .

³²⁷ Bollée 2010a : 154 note 180.

³²⁸ Cf. BKBh cty ad 993.

cradle (*mañca*), Hara commands merchant's daughter in dream to leave her newborn son in ~ at king's door 93,49 (TP VII 81)

crane (*baka*), *rākṣasa* in the shape of a ~ 39,60 (TP III 222); hen- ~ (*balākā*) drops faeces (*viṣṭā*) on ascetic and is reduced to ashes by his evil eye 56,171 (TP IV 232 'hen-crow'); ~ killed by *makara* 60,89 (TP V 49); ~ has snake killed by mongoose 60,236 (TP V 61)

crazy, expressions for ~: distracted with wind (*vātena kṣubhita*), planet-struck (*graha-grhīta*) 94,103f. (TP VII 94)

creator (*vedhas*) obedient to Śiva by placing his orders on his head (*Īśvarājñām ādāya mūrdhni vedhasy atho gate*) 34,45 (TP III 131); ~ (*vidhātar*) first created adultery³²⁹ (*sāhasa*), then women in imitation of it 34,177 (TP III 141 'recklessness'); even ~ cannot overstep destiny 37,236 (TP III 199); production of fools (*mūḍha-sarga*) by Prajāpati 39,192 (TP III 232); no one can do anything against the wish of the ~ 41,60 (TP III 256); ~ (*vedhas*) has made the courtesan to steal the wealth of rich young men 57,57 (TP V 5); every creature is such as he is made by the ~ 62,124 (TP V 109); ~ of Kāśmīra as second heaven 73,79f. (TP VI 106); *dhātar* 102,103 (TP VII 170); ~ composes woman of essence of all beauty 116,36 (TP VIII 159); *Gandharva* looks meaningfully at face of Disposer (*dhātuh sākūtam mukham aikṣata*) 116,85 (TP VIII 162);

creeper(s) (*latā*), queens compared to ~ (because of their slenderness and embracing of king) 6,112 (TP I 69); ~ representing love 17,73 (TP II 40, cf. 71,77 [TP VI 41] where a princess looks like a ~ of the tree of love)³³⁰; adulterous wife beaten with ~ 58,94 (TP V 21);

shrill whistling of the loose bark of dry ~ likened to screams of terror of a nocturnal forest 73,240 (TP VI 118); trees on Mt Rṣabha, like hermits, with their ~s like matted hair waving in the wind, shed their flowers before the emperor by way of respectful offering 110,64 (TP VIII 86); – ~ compared to queens, see: forehead

cremation³³¹ of brahmin wife on husband's pyre 27,165 (TP III 13); ~ of *ex-yakṣinī* on pyre of brahmin *ex-yakṣa* 34,89 (TP III 135); ~ of executed robber by companion (*agni-sāt niśi cakre Ghaṭo dehaṃ Karparasyāhṛtēndhanaḥ*) 64,77 (TP V 145); ~ of unmarried brahmin daughter by suitors 76,13 (TP VI 180); – see note on "hair-style" below

crêpe de Chine (*cīna-paṭa*), see: China

crescent (*ardha-candra*) of Śiva 108,82 (TP VIII 60)

crest-jewel (*cūḍā-maṇi*)³³², image of Maheśvara's toe-nails is reflected in the ~s of *devas* and Asuras kneeling before him 1,20 (TP I 20); ~ in dream represents crown-prince's duty 55,139 (TP IV 211); horse adorned with ~ 74,78 (TP VI 145); Prajāpati fastens ~ (*cūḍā-ratna*) on head of Muktāphalaketu 116,81 (TP VIII 162); magic city is ~ of the Himālayas (*Himādri-mauli-māṇikya*) 117,18 (TP VIII 165); ~ a gender-neutral present from Svayaṃ

³²⁹ ORC 344: *crime*.

³³⁰ Cf. Jackmuth 2002: 75ff.; 145.

³³¹ For the verbs see Bollée 2008a: 12.

³³² For *cūḍā-maṇi* see also Hildebeitel 1980-81: 194 and 197ff.; for illustrations see Jackson 2010: 18 and 152.

bhū, given by prince to princess and which stops all grief (*sarva-duḥkha-nibarhaṇa*) 117,115f. (TP VIII 172) and 170 (TP VIII 175); ~ (*śikhā-ratna*) protects princess while performing asceticism and is effective because sprung from Disposer's waterpot 117,156 (TP VIII 174f.); ~ (*cūḍā-ratna*) as (talisman) against poison, etc. (*viṣa-rakṣo-jarā-roga-hara*) 119,27f. (TP VIII 194f.); ~ of brahmins 123,235 (TP IX 60); ~ of cunning ones (*dhūrta-śiro-maṇi*) 124,216 (TP IX 83)

crime(s), of destroying realm 27,29 (TP III 3); hidden ~ (*pracchanna-pātakāḥ*) manifest themselves through fear 30,126 (TP III 73); ~ of selling one's wife 43,103 (TP III 288); ~ (*pāpa*) washed out at holy bathing-places 52,239 (TP IV 154)

criminal hanged 64,53 (TP V 144)

criticism of stupid brahmin 2,54 (TP I 13); ~ of mother by courtesan 12,95 (TP I 140); ~ of wife by husband 14,40 (TP I 185); ~ of father (*bhauta-prāyaś* ['idiot'] *ca tātaḥ*) by daughter 39,108 (TP III 225); ~ of stupid brahmin by all 40,14 (TP III 241); a king who is not intent on conquest is to be blamed as much as the effeminate (*kliba*) husband of a woman 52,370 (TP IV 164); ~ of son by king 67,29 (TP V 198); ~ of king by people 74,69 (TP VI 45); idem by *senāpati* 108,193f. (TP VIII 68); subjects tell king to take back state elephant given away by his son otherwise threaten to set up another king 113,45 (TP VIII 127); *Gaṇa* criticizes Pārvatī and is cursed 114,71 (TP VIII 137); Brahmā criticised by unsatisfied receiver of boon 115,47 (TP VIII 147); ~ of Śiva-Mahākāla by gambler 121,98ff. (TP IX 19); ~ of ugly brahmin, see: ugliness

crocodile (*grāha*)³³³, sword to keep off ~ in tank 10,51 (TP I 110); *apsaras* cursed to be ~ is rescued by Arjuna 33,29 (TP III 109); ~ seizing bathing hermit maiden is killed by prince 101,236 (TP VII 150); Pulinda king delivered from ~ in Narmadā 102,27 (TP VII 164); – see also: five *apsaras*; *makara*

crossroads (*catuṣ-patha*), drop rice at ~ in rite to get help from Piśāca 28,166 (TP III 33 with note on 37f.); ~ (*catvara*) are gambler's home 73,77 (TP VI 106);

croupier, gambler makes himself ~ (*sabhya*) in Mahākāla temple 121,80 (TP IX 17f.), see: gambler

crow and palm motif³³⁴ (*kāka-tāliya*) 30,90 (TP III 70 with note; ORC 298 leaves this out);

crow(s) reborn as golden *haṃsas* after fighting for *bali* in empty Śiva temple and dying in sacred vessel 3,32ff. (TP I 21); fearing ~s (*kāka-śaṅki*)³³⁵ as evil omen 32,52 (TP III 94); ~ in *śālmali* ('silk cotton or kapok tree') 61,58 (TP V 73); ~, mouse and tortoise as friends 61,84f. (TP V 75); war between ~ and owls 62,7 (TP V 98)³³⁶; ~ (*vāyasa*) advises against owl as king of birds 62,45f. (TP V 102); ~s destroy cave with owls by brand of pyre and sticks which each ~ carries in its beak 62,146 (TP V 111); are ~s (*kāka*) at fault when *haṃsas* eat rice ? 75,191 (TP VI 176); how can a ~ and a female goose ever unite ? 112,96

³³³ Hensgen 1958: 129.

³³⁴ See Bloomfield 1919a.

³³⁵ MW (under *śaṅkin*): "distrustful as a crow"; ORC 311: "qui s'inquiète des corbeaux."

³³⁶ Pañcatantra III 1 (Penzer).

(TP VIII 113); eyes rolling rapidly like those of a ~ (*kāka-cañcala-locana*) 112,152 (TP VIII 118); wicked gambler interpreting cry of ~ (*kāka-vāsita*) 121,169 (TP IX 24); crown-prince (*yuva-rājā*) inaugurated 34,107 and 125 (TP III 136f.)³³⁷; ~'s duty (*yuvarājatva-dhura*) 44,26 (TP IV 3); ~ in dream represented by crest-jewel 55,139 (TP IV 211); 113,52 (TP VIII 128)

cruelty, to dog, see: dog; ~ to monkey 57,167ff. (TP V 13); ~ to buffalo beaten by herdsman 68,46 (TP VI 5); ~ to horse 68,56 (TP VI 5);

cry and laugh motif, see: crying

crying (*ākraṇḍa*) of merchants on sinking ship 25,45 (TP II 192); ~ deer in forest 66,148 (TP V 189); impaled robber ~ (*aśru muktvā*) and laughing 88,43 (TP VII 38)³³⁸; boy ~ in order to cool his rice-pudding (*paramāṇna*) 124,135 (TP IX 78);

crystal lotus in Manasa lake gleams like head of Śeśa 72,38 (TP VI 70f.); ~ ball (as used by soothsayers), see: dish

cuckoo, spring refreshes female ~ (*madhuḥ pika-vadhūm iva*) 56,196 (TP IV 234)³³⁹; prince equals singing of female ~ (*pikī*) to that of his wife 69,7 (TP VI 9);

cūḍā-maṇi, -*ratna*, see crest-jewel

curiosity (*kutūhala*), of the *Gaṇa* Puṣpadanta to hear Hara-Śiva's stories told to Pārvaī 1,50 (TP I 6), cf. -*kautuka* 2,16 (TP I 10); ~ of merchants for the wealth of a *pravrajikā* (Buddhist nun) 13,93 (TP I 157); ~ of woman with *ucchvasitau stanau* to see king from house top 18,16 (TP II 50)³⁴⁰ and 52,347 (TP IV 162); king out of ~ meets man descended from heaven 20,181 (TP II 111); ~ of king to hear adventures of his son 25,271f. (TP II 211); entering forbidden place out of ~ 26,75 (TP II 222); queens are curious about a meditating *muni* 28,29 (TP III 22); divinities come for hearing a tale, out of (disappointed) ~ curse the story-teller to death when it was not told 28,133 (TP III 30); queen out of ~ (*kautukāt*) to see future daughter-in-law 34,97 (TP III 135); ~ of king to see woman sold by her husband 43,113 (TP III 289); ~ of princess, a *haṃsī* in her pre-birth, for Pāśupata ascetic calling: *hā haṃsī* 43,177 (TP III 293); ~ of prince about a man to become sovereign of the *vidyādhara*s 44,14 (TP IV 2); princess come forward to dance compared to moon come to underworld out of ~ 45,233 (TP IV 33); out of ~ prince, carried by *vidyādhara*, flies to see *vidyādhara* world 59,127 (TP V 33); king tells *vidyādhari* princess he has ~ to see *vidyādhara* world 59,127 (TP V 35); ~ of city women about prince on horse chariot 67,13 (TP V 197); sunlight come to visit forest out of ~ 69,169 (TP VI 21); 70,89 (TP VI 88); ~ of bard to see dancing princess 71,75 (TP VI 41); request for story out of ~ 75,8 (TP VI 164); Asura maiden invites king to see her city out of ~ 81,92 (TP VI 215); heavenly

³³⁷ Saletore 1943: 174ff.

³³⁸ Cf. STh *F 1041.11.

³³⁹ Cf. Kumārasambhava 6,2 where a mangotree stalk with a cuckoo (*para-bhṛta*) wishes for spring (Jackmuth 2002: 63f.; 167ff.).

³⁴⁰ See, e.g. the reliefs in Sānchi in Marchall & Foucher 1940: plates XXXa and b < Sparreboom 1985: 102f.; Jackson 2010: 79. For a full description of female curiosity to see the king riding out is Kād 182,9ff.

tree seems to be standing erect out of ~ to see the beauty of the garden of Nandana 100,19 (TP VII 129); prince's ~ about female ascetic's words 101,63 (TP VII 138); brahmin's ~ to see other countries 104,83 (TP VIII 7); ~ of celestial nymphs (*divya-kanyā*) gazing at court of justice of *vidyādhara*s 106,180 (VIII 40); ~ of gods to see battle 109,51 and 122 (TP VIII 74 and 79); do, 118,74 (TP VIII 182); ~ to hear story 121,228 (TP IX 29); out of ~ painter opens book given him by traveller 122,25 (TP IX 35); 122,112 (TP IX 42); 123,54 (TP IX 46); ~ of wife to see what happens to fresh husband gone out unobserved at night 123,183 (TP IX 56); – see also: *siddha*; sightseeing; spectators; sun; tourism; voyeurism

curl of hair on a horse's chest,³⁴¹ 18,88 (TP II 56); – see also : *āvarta*; *rocamāna*; *śrīvṛkṣa cūrṇa* as magic powder against *rasāyana* 'long life elixir' 41,50 (TP III 255); *cūrṇa-mīśra* (not MW) 'powder mix' (of goat's horn flesh as an aphrodisiacum) 39,17 (TP III 219)

curry (*vyañjana*), Nala asked to prepare Damayanī's ~ 56,404 (TP IV 249)

curse³⁴² of Puṣpadanta and Mālyavān by Pārvatī 1,57 (TP I 6f.); ~ of Supratīka by Kuvera 1,60 (TP I 7); ~ of *rakṣas* Sthūlaśiras by Śiva 2,19 (TP I 10); ~ of Vasudattā and Vararuci 2,31 (TP I 11); ~ of twelve years' drought 5,72 (TP I 52); ~ of insanity (*unmattaḥ*) of prince by bear for treason of friend 5,95 (TP I 54)³⁴³; ~ ends by hearing tale 5,131 (TP I 58); brahmin Nāga prince weds *ex-apsaras* cursed to become human by *gāndharva* marriage 6,17 (TP I 61); ~ on *yakṣa* to become a lion 6,99 (TP I 68); ~ of hermit Bhāradvāja by other hermits because of his falling in love 7,17 (TP I 75); offended brahmin guest curses host to become outcaste (*patita*) 7,48 (TP I 78); ~ of Mālyavān by Pārvatī 7,113 (TP I 86); fire of ~ 8,28 (TP I 90); Brahmā curses Vidhūma and Alambuṣā to become a mortal couple 8,26 (TP I 96); ~ of king Sahasrānīka by Tilottamā to 14 years's separation from his love 9,33 (TP I 96); ~ of *yakṣa* by Kubera to become lion 10,42 (TP I 109); ~ of *vidyādhari* to be an elephant 13,35 (TP I 152); Viśvamitra curses woman to become *rākṣasi* 10,75 (TP I 111); *Asura* becomes *rākṣasa* boar due to ~ (*śāpa-doṣāt*) 11,55 (TP I 126); ~ to offer water to manes 11,72 (TP I 127); ~ of Purūravas by Tumburu to separation from Urvaśī 17,23 (TP II 35); ~ of Ahalyā by Gautama to become stone-hard 17,145 (TP II 46); ~ of Indra by Gautama to have his body covered with *vulvae* which will turn into numerous eyes when he sees Tilottamā 17,145 (TP II 46)³⁴⁴; ~ of frogs by Agni to have inarticulate speech 20,77 (TP II 101); ~ of hunting king Pāṇḍu by dying deer/hermit to die in his wife's arms 21,25 (TP II 127); ~ of *vidyādhara* by Śiva to be born as mortal 22,57 (TP II 141); ~

³⁴¹ See Caland 2010.

³⁴² In Germany in late mediaeval and early modern times a faster female irascibility and cursing is found, which practice may be more obvious, in fact related to their otherwise common, often verbal magical activities, before in the 18th century the magical sense of cursing declines behind the profane insult, that men practise rather than women (Labouvie 1993:135). – A curse is a negative gift, but the water carrying the curse is not mentioned in KSS (see below note on donation water). On cursing see e.g. Beck 1983: 78f.

³⁴³ STh Q 556ff.

³⁴⁴ See Doniger O'Flaherty 1981: 248f.

of *vidyādhara* by hermit Nārada to be born as a lion carrying his daughter on his back 22,142 (TP II 147); ~ ended by Kauśika (q.v.) 25,258-60 (TP II 210); darkness of ~ 25,290 (TP II 212); ~ of three *vidyādhari* princesses by hermit Agryatapas to become mortals 26,58 (TP II 221); princess of fishermen is a cursed celestial female 26,151 (TP II 228); ~ by Indra of *apsaras* to become mortal 27,70 (TP III 6); ~ of *apsaras* ends with birth of her mortal daughter 28,67 (TP III 25); ~ pronounced by voices of heavenly women on man fallen asleep before ending story 28,124 (TP III 30); ~ of Sahasrānīka by Tilottamā 30,49 (TP III 67); ~ of brahmin destroys Nahuṣa with angry roar (*huṃ-kārād brahma-śāpataḥ*) 31,77 (TP III 88); five *apsaras* cursed to become crocodiles 33,29 (TP III 109); spurned Rambhā curses Arjuna to become impotent (*ṣaṇḍatā-śāpaṃ dadau*) 33,90 (TP III 114); ~ by Kubera of brahmin-killing *yakṣa* to be reborn mortal 34,77 (TP III 134); ~ of witch by another witch (*dhik-prāpsyasi*) 37,160 (TP III 194); *vidyādhara* king curses son who wants to retire to *āśram* because of jealous wives, to become mortal 42,205 (TP III 274); *vidyādhara* king curses proud daughter to be married to ugly brahmin by force 52,58 (TP IV 142); ~ of proud son by *vidyādhara* father to become ugly mortal with large mouth 52,76 (TP IV 143); father's ~ causes changes in character (*ativiparyaya*) of daughter 52,355 (TP IV 163); Kārttikeya gives king boon and then curses him 55,177 (TP IV 214); Bhairava curses *yakṣa* to become eunuch 56,102 (TP IV 227); parents ~ disobedient son³⁴⁵ to imprisonment with burning wheel on head 56,150f. (TP IV 230); ~ on gambling 56,307 (TP IV 242); parents ~ disobedient daughter to become Niṣāda without remembering pre-birth 59,154 (TP V 36); ~ by Gautama of *vidyādhara* king to become serpent 61,319 (TP V 96); brahmin curses snake to bear frogs on its back 62,156 (TP V 112); *vidyādhara* father curses disobedient son to be reborn a brahmin and, ~d by his then father, to become a lion and fall into a well 65,63 (TP V 159; double ~ !); prince ~d by sister to become bird with golden crest 65,78 (TP V 160 "hoopoe"); hermit's son ~s colleague to become a snake with three hoods 65,89f. (TP V 161); ~ by neglected hermit 65,243 (TP V 173); ~ of splashing couple by sprinkled hermit 67,92 (TP V 202); daughter ~d by *vidyādhara* king because of *gāndharva* marriage 69,91ff. (TP VI 15); ~ to become ugly camel 69,107 (TP VI 16); compassion of *jambu* tree with ~d *vidyādhari* by consoling her with sweetly buzzing bees 69,95 (TP VI 15); brahmin ~s son to become dry tree because of theft of two fruits 70,32f. (TP VI 26); snake ~s prince for helping ascetic 70,73 (TP VI 29); wind which stripped prince of his arms (ministers) as ~ of snake 70,124 (TP VI 33); for fleeing from battle the snake king Gandhamālin is ~d by Vāsuki to become slave of *yakṣa* Kālahijhva 72,35 (TP VI 70); Kubera ~s two *yakṣas* to become brahminy ducks 72,43 (TP VI 71); Nāga ~s ministers to separation 73,19 (TP VI 101); Naḍakūbara ~s *yakṣa* to become mortal 73,42 (TP VI 103); Nāga ~s royal servant to become blind 74,14 (TP VI 142); Śāṅkara predicts ~ by hermit because of penance driven by anger 74,31 (TP VI 143); unnoticed hermit Uttaṅka ~s king to become an elephant 74,307 ... ~ inflicted cannot be annulled 309 (TP VI 162); man ~d to become learned parrot 77,6 (TP VI 183); hungry

³⁴⁵ Censure by parents in a dream is calamitous (Svapnac 2,91). – See also Boss 1976: 107.

vidyādhara king by destiny (*bhavitavya-bala*) ~s beloved daughter and abandons her 86,135 (TP VII 22); king grants brahmin's petition fearing a ~ (*śāpa-bhityā*) 89,30 (TP VII 42); Gaurī ~s *rājarṣi* Iḍa to become female who falls in love with Buddha 89,86 (TP VII 46); Gaṇeśa in tree ~s impure people eating its fruit to become that on which their minds are fixed: fruits 100,39 (TP VII 131); Gaṇeśa removes ~ from ministers 100,51 (TP VII 132); *vidyādhara* prince with ~ of death when using violence against women 105,71 (TP VIII 26); Mānasavega ~d to have his head split into a hundred pieces when he would try to abduct woman against her will 106,133 (TP VIII 38); ~ of *yakṣiṇī* ends by marrying brahmin mortal 108,48 (TP VIII 56); *vidyādhari* ~d to be wife of hermit 108,72 and ending by bearing him child 108,74 (TP VIII 59); Dhanavātī ~s two armies and paralyzes them (*śaptvā ... niścetane vyadhāt*) 109,124 (TP VIII 79); Śiva ~s Mataṅgadeva and his innocent wife and daughter to become *caṇḍālas* to be released when 18000 brahmins eat in his house 112,194f. (TP VIII 121); Devī ~s two *Gaṇas* to become human, etc. up to bob-tailed dogs (*chinna-pucchau śvānau*) just for laughing 114,66ff. (TP VIII 137); two brahmin boys ~d to become *brahma-rākṣasas* for eating flesh of sacrificial goat 114,105 (TP VIII 140); hermit ~s *brahma-rākṣasas* to become *piśācas* 114,108 (TP VIII 140); for stealing his cow a brahmin ~s *piśācas* to become *caṇḍālas* 114,109 (TP VIII 140); pupil of hermit ~s prince for entering hermitage 117,138 (TP VIII 173); prince ~d by hermit's pupil to become mortal for disturbing hermit in garden 117,136 in consequence of his former use of Brahmā weapon against old men and children 117,151 (TP VIII 173f.); princess ~s pupil of hermit to become riding-animal 117,159f. (TP VIII 175); Siddha-princess ~s princess Padmāvātī for laughing at her austerities for getting a husband 117,179 (TP VIII 176); prince waiting for ripening of the fruit of the ~ (*śāpa-phalâgama*) pronounced on him 118,7 (TP VIII 178); Indra ~s the *apsaras* Kalāvātī to become mortal 121,115-122³⁴⁶ (TP IX 20) and to become a *sāla-bhañjikā* on a pillar 121,145 (TP IX 22); hermit Kaṇva *curses* two *deva-kumārau* to become a boar and an elephant 123,92 (TP IX 49); – fear of ~, see: fear; – see further also: ascetic

curse water “*Fluchwasser*”: Lüders 1951: 33.

custom (*ācāra*), ladies adorn bride only to satisfy (*iti*) ~ though she was of admirable grace (*kāntyāiva kṛta-kautukā*) 103,189 (TP VII 187)

cūta-pādapa (not MW) ‘(made of) mango tree (wood)’,³⁴⁷ see: shoes

cutting off impaled robbers' noses by night 18,140ff. (TP II 60); ~ ears and nose of adulterous woman 19,49 (TP II 87f.), 81,166 (TP V 82), et passim; – see further: adultery

dv, misprint of *vidārya* for *nivārya* 17,128 (TP II 44 note 2)

dadāti ‘to beat (a drum)’, see: *datta-ḍiṇḍima*

dāḍima, see: pomegranate tree

dāha-jvara (not MW) ‘burning fever’, Cāṇakya kills Yogananda through ~ 5,122 (TP I 57);

³⁴⁶ TP wrongly translate in vs 119 *Śakra-śāpa* by curse of Śiva.

³⁴⁷ Dastur 1963: 112 says that the mango wood is used inter alia for shoe heels.

58,62 (TP V 19); 76,12 (TP VI 180)

Daitya has adamantine frame (*vajrāṅga*), only his left hand is vulnerable (*marma*) 112,52 (TP VIII 109)

Daitya-*kanyā*, Viṣṇu excludes the thousand ~ granddaughters of Bali from their city 10,40f. (TP I 108); ~ as the most beautiful maiden in the three worlds 11,39 (TP I 125); ~ approaching dreamer, but invisible after his waking up 73,88f. (TP VI 107);

daiva, see: destiny

daivata ('tutelary deity' ? ORC 1013: "divinité gardienne"), *brahma-rākṣaka* as ~ of brahmin boy wants to devour him 94,133 (TP VII 96);

daiva-yogataḥ 'as fate would have it' 39,5 (TP III 218); 77,21 (TP VI 184);

dākinī-cakra ('coven, circle of witches') (not MW) 20,137 (TP II 106) and 142 (TP II 108)

dakṣiṇā, see: fee

dakṣiṇā āśā 'southern quarter' 111,51 (TP VIII 100), see: dream; night

dakṣiṇa-dik 'southern region,' on the confines of the ~ are dark *tamāla* forests 73,30 (TP VI 102); – see also: knowledge; sciences

dakṣiṇa-mārga in singing, see: singing

dakṣiṇā-patha, Rājput from ~ 24,114 (TP II 178); – see also: Deccan

ḍamaru, drum of a *kāpālika* 124,8 (TP IX 68)³⁴⁸

Damayantī catches goose that asks to be set free 56,243 (TP IV 237); ~ is earthly Tilōttamā

56,251 (TP IV 237); ~ with eyes like blue lotus (*indīvara*) 56,277 (TP IV 239);

dāna, see: charity;

dāna-pāramitā 'perfection of charity' 72,236 (TP VI 86)

**dāna-santra*, see: almshouse

dāna-toya (not MW), see: donation water

Dānava maidens concealing their bodies (*vigraha*) in trees 118,107 (TP VIII 185); two invincible ~s 121,229 (TP IX 29)

dance³⁴⁹, evening ~ (*saṃdhyā-ṅṛtta*) of Gaṇeśa 1,2 (TP I 1) et passim; ~ (*calita*) executed by Rambhā 17,20 (TP II 35), see also below; ~ of creepers (*latā-lāśya*) 35,5 (TP III 155); ~ of Daitya and Dānava maidens 45,231 (TP IV 33); with her curling hair, her pointed (eye ?) teeth, and her full breasts³⁵⁰ Mahallikā seems to create new style of dance (*ṅṛttaṃ nūtanam*) 45,235 (TP IV 33); evening ~ (*saṃdhyā-ṅṛtta*) of demons with corpses 47,92 (TP IV 72) and 48,118 (TP IV 82); brahmin asked by king to ~ refuses 49,10f. (TP IV 85); ~ in temple 57,74f. (TP V 7); ~ (*ṅṛtya*) of Rambhā, &c. which they accompany with their own voice 116,87 (TP VIII 162); Rambhā will perform new ~ (*nava-prayogaṃ nartīṣyati*) before Hari 121,124 and 130 (TP IX 21); – see also: *apsaras*; cloud; dancing; Gaṇeśa; peacock; *tāṇḍava*; *vicitra-karaṇa*

³⁴⁸ See Marcel-Dubois 1941: 67; Ambrose 1950: 29 or Dallapiccola 2002: 55 for a picture.

³⁴⁹ Sundaram 1979: 751. For worship through dance see Daś 209.13 and 250.9.

³⁵⁰ Sundaram 1979: 757f. takes the descriptive terms of the dancer, *lalāṭa-tilaka*, etc., also to belong to the *karaṇas* (q. v.).

dancing, mouse ~ for joy when seeing cat caught in noose 33,115 (TP III 116); queens ~ for joy 34,123 (TP III 137); ~ trees with waving creepers (*mārutāndolita-latāḥ*) 34,124 (TP III 137); city of Kauśāmbī, ~ with pennons, agitated by the wind, seemed like twining arms 34,263 (TP III 149); *yakṣiṇī* ~ outside magic circle enchants Pāśupata ascetic (*mahāvratin*) 37,64f. (TP III 187); after his daughter's marriage king Janamejaya gives a feast which only consisted of music and ~ 44,133 (TP IV 9f.); ~ unbecoming in king's court 49,11 and foolish ~ (*mūḍha-nṛttaṃ*) is ridiculous 49,12 (TP IV 85f.); inexhaustible pitcher falls from shoulder of ~ wood-carrier 57,46 (TP V 4); princess shows ~ skill (*nṛtta*) to the music of a great tabor (*āhata-mahā-todye*) 71,74-6 (TP VI 41); ~ trunks on battlefield 74,285 (TP VI 160) and 103,9 (TP VII 175)³⁵¹; *bhūtas* ~ with headless trunks 166,66 (TP VIII 161)³⁵²; divine goat ~ as a mime (*bhaṇḍa*) before Indra 121,132f. (TP IX 21); – see also: *apsaras*;

dancing Bhairava among the Mātaras = *yoginī* 56,106 (TP IV 227)

dancing Gaṇeśa³⁵³ 1,2 (TP I 1); 51,1 (TP IV 122); 73,377 (TP VI 127); 105,2 (TP VIII 21); 109,1 (TP VIII 70)

dancing-girl(s), feast with beautiful ~s (*praṇṛtta-vara-nārika*) 16,85 (TP II 28), cf. 17,19 (TP II 35 with note 1); 23,82 (TP II 164); ~ at royal festival 34,121 (TP III 137); ~ at marriage 34,262 (TP III 148); ~ perform after company's dinner (*bhukta-pitās*) 45,231 (TP IV 33); ~ (*lāsikī*) dancing like a wave of the sea of beauty 57,75 (TP V 7); beautiful temple dancers (*vara-striyaḥ*) dance in four styles (*catur-vidhena vādyena*)³⁵⁴ 123,132 (TP IX 52 'three³⁵⁵ nymphs of celestial beauty'); – see also: prostitutes; southern style

dancing hall (*raṅga-maṇḍapa*) in royal palace 71,75 (TP VI 41); – see also: *nāṭya-veśman*

dancing Śiva, boughs of tree moved by wind resemble ~ 100,18 (TP VII 129)

dancing-teacher Tumburu 17,20 (TP II 35); Naravāhanadatta, ~ of his wife 34,164 (TP III 140); Labdhavara as *nāṭyācārya* 52,265 (TP IV 156);

daṇḍa, hermit hits iron rams guarding a gate with a charmed wand (~*ena nyasta-mantreṇa*) on their head 73,132 (TP VI 110); pupil refuses to carry guru's ~ and water-vessel 97,30 (TP VII 114); – see also: magic staff; staff; *yaṣṭi*

danger, see: deity; *jīvita-saṃśaya*; life

danta-dṛṣṭādhārōtkāṭa 'terrible because their (eye-)teeth were seen on their lower lip' ?³⁵⁶ used

³⁵¹ Cf. Rājat 3,390.

³⁵² Sundaram 1979: 753.

³⁵³ Courtright 2001: 164 stresses Gaṇeśa's close association with the symbols of his father, whom he serves. Both are called Deva-deva (q. v.). For symbols such as dancing, see Coomaraswamy 1982: 84 according to whom, however, there is no special interpretation of this dance in Shaiva literature, but see Doniger O'Flaherty 1981: 378 31e and 379 31a; Capra 1976: 269ff.; Wössner 1981: 10ff.; Balsekar 1982: 141. The dancing Gaṇeśa is depicted, e.g. on a wall panel in the Mṛtyunjaya temple at Jageshwar, 10th century; see Snead et al. 1989: 174 plates 152f.; further Krishan 1999 plates 77, 81 et passim.

³⁵⁴ E.g. Ambrose 1950: 9ff.; Baldissera 1988.

³⁵⁵ 'Three' is not in the text.

of warders of doors (*dvāra-rakṣiṇaḥ*) 73,134 (TP VI 111 with note 1);
danta-ghāṭaka ‘ivory carver’³⁵⁷ 75,82 (TP VI 170);
danta-patra reading of TP VI 169 at 75,73 where the metrically corrupt NSP text reads *ciraṃ ca danta-racanām cakārādāya ca vyadhāt*. According to Penzer (note 1 on p. 170) the “tooth-leaf” probably was a special kind of ear-ring; in that case WB would with Sivaramamurti 1956: 109 prefer ‘ivory leaf’, cf. Śiśupālavadha I 60 *danta-patraka*.
danta-mālā (not MW) ‘row of teeth’, compared to row of bells (*ghaṇṭāvalī*) in mouth-like interior of temple, see: temple of Caṇḍikā
dāra-saṃgraha ‘taking a wife’, said of a prince 118,121 (TP VIII 187)
darbha grass³⁵⁸, brahmin Cāṇakya routes up ~ because it pricked his foot 5,110 (TP I 55); ~ cuts queen’s foot 13,43 (TP I 152); Garuḍa puts nectar on ~ for snakes 22,195 (TP II 151); ~ is called *kuśa* grass in vs 196), cf. 24,92-6 (TP II 176); sonless king and queens sleeping on ~ to propitiate Ambikā-Durgā for a son 42,56 (TP III 263); Damayantī’s feet pierced with ~ 56,309 (TP IV 242); king in sorrow practises *tapas* and sleeps on ~ (*darbha-śayana*) 101,219 (TP VII 149); – see also: *kuśa* grass
darbha-saṃstara ‘bed of *d.* grass’, austerities on ~ in front of Devī 54,162 (TP IV 195); poor householder lays himself on ~ at Durgā temple and performs *tapas* in order to obtain wealth 66,101 (TP V 185); out of grief for the loss of his guru Somaśūra takes to ~ to die 72,390 (TP VI 98); 73,223 (TP VI 117);
darkness, boar like ~ of night 11,44f. (TP I 126); aura of *vidyādhari* dispells ~ (*prabhā-bhinna-timira*) like a night set on fire 18,213 (TP II 66)³⁵⁹; ~ of curse 25,290 (TP II 212); ~ (*dhvānte dhāvati*) as vanguard of bandits 29,108 (TP III 46); blind with ~ of grief (*duḥkha-tamo-’ndhas*) 37,131 (TP III 192)³⁶⁰; snake curses prince and ministers, and their eyes then are dimmed with ~ (*dhvānta-ruddha-dṛś*) 70,75 (TP VI 29); charnel ground obscured (*malīmasa*) by dense ~ 75,42 (TP VI 167); king blinded with ~ of bewilderment (*moha-niśāndha*) 86,126 (TP VII 22); ~ of despondency of brahmin whose wife was abducted 87,18 (TP VII 30); ~ of night without and ~ of grief within³⁶¹ of fleeing women 93,12 (TP VII 79); black robe of ~ of the nymph of night 94,52 (TP VII 91) and *timirāsītāmśu* 103,203 (TP VII 189)³⁶²; maiden’s hair seems like ~ seeking shelter as if it feared her moon-like face (*vadanēndu-bhayenēva timiraṃ śaraṇam āgatam*) 104,94 (TP VIII 8)³⁶³; cave looking like birthplace of ~ of doomsday 109,83 (TP VIII 76)³⁶⁴;

³⁵⁶ V.l. for NSP text *danta-daṣṭa* ‘terrible because they were biting their lips’. This epithet may describe the face of demons such as Rāhu in Koṇārak (Zimmer II 1983:374).

³⁵⁷ Renou 1963: 206 still holds Tawney’s translation “dentist” for possible and considers the sense uncertain.

³⁵⁸ See Gonda 1985: 52ff. and 97ff.

³⁵⁹ STh F 574.1.

³⁶⁰ On the motif of the negative aspect of darkness see Jackmuth 2002: 29; 100ff.; 141; 205.

³⁶¹ Cf. μελαγχίτων said of the choir’s heart (φρήν) in Aeschylus’ *Persians* 115f. Examples for the negative meaning of darkness in Kālidāsa are given by Jackmuth 2002: 99.

³⁶² Cf. Rājāt 3,169.

weapon of ~ 116,71 (TP VIII 161); – see also: blind; cloud; dice; grief; night
darpa-dalana (not MW) ‘breaking the pride’ of Love (*Smara*) in its beauty, said of a prince
 75,62 (TP VI 168)
darśana (‘auspicious viewing’)³⁶⁵, of Skanda 7,9 (TP I 74); ~ of king, women’s eagerness of
 ~ 18,11 (TP II 50); by ~ of a celibate hermit Śrī gives him spiritual son 59,95ff. (TP V 33);
 ~ of pleased Śiva 73,424 (TP VI 130); 107,129 (TP VIII 52); – see also: curiosity;
 pollution; *rāja-darśana*; sight
darśana-vaśīkṛta (not MW) ‘at merely seeing one, at first sight’ 38,33 (TP III 208); – see
 also: first sight; love at first sight
darśanôtsava (‘feast for the eyes’) 18,11 (TP II 50); – cf. *cakṣur-bhrānti*
 darter, tree trunk causes ruin of ~ (? *madgu*) in it 24,132 (TP II 179 ‘mouse’, also MI 305;
 ORC 212 ‘*plongeon*’ with note on p. 1373); – see further: *madgu*
dāru-putrikā ‘wooden doll’ representing brahmin’s third wife 74,165 (TP VI 152);
daśa ‘ten’ and ‘bite!’ 56,346 (TP IV 245)
dāsya-mukti (not MW) ‘redemption from slavery’, money paid for ~ 13,193 (TP I 164)
 Dasyu,³⁶⁶ 105 ~s (*pañcôttaraṃ śataṃ*) killed 13,40 (TP I 152); – see also: Bhilla
 date palms (*kharjūrī*) fools cut down ~ in order to gather dates more easily 61,33 (TP V 71);
datta-dīṇḍima (not MW) ‘for whom the execution drum is beaten’ 112,166 (TP VIII 119
 “preceded by the drum”, ORC 1180 “*en battant le tambour*”)
datta-dṛṅ-mantra (not MW) ‘who gives someone a look and recites a spell’ 37,65 (TP III
 187)
datura (*dhattūra*)³⁶⁷ mixed in wine 13,142 (TP I 160f.); guards watching hanged criminal are
 stupefied by sweetmeats containing ~ 64,71 (TP V 145 with note 2)
 daughter,³⁶⁸ birth of ~ like moon³⁶⁹ predicted by Indra in dream 11,77 (TP I 128); mother asks
 for reward for giving birth to ~ (*sutā-phala*) 12,163 (TP I 146); royal ~ opposed to father
 (*pitṛ-pakṣa-parāṇmukhī*) 13,1 (TP I 150); ~ illuminates birth-chamber and speaks under
 standably 17,66 (TP II 39); ~ at birth refuses marriage and calls herself blessing (*śubhā*) in
 her father’s house 17,69 (TP II 40); negotiation termed “giving of a ~” (*kanyā-sambandha*)
 17,156 (TP II 47)³⁷⁰; ~ welcomed 18,79 (TP II 55); ~ dearer than life (*prāṇādhika-priyā*)
 to father 22,36 (TP II 147)³⁷¹; ~ given to unsuitable man is like learning imparted to unfit

³⁶³ Kumārasambhava 8,37 compares darkness with the (feminine) night’s hair (Jackmuth 2002: 99).

³⁶⁴ See Doniger O’Flaherty 1981: 375 sub 5d; Jackmuth 2002: 98.

³⁶⁵ Keltling 2001: 52. See also Michaels 2004: 230ff.; Bollée 2002: § 687 and 713; Dallapiccola 2002: 56; Eck 1998; Mallebrein 1998: 8; Rājat 2,27.

³⁶⁶ Perhaps the Indian aborigines at the Aryan invasion (ORC 1558).

³⁶⁷ See Schultes & Hofmann 1980: 106-111; Rātsch 1990: 89-95; Dallapiccola 2002: 57; Duda 2006: 292.

³⁶⁸ Among the many books on daughters see, e.g. Syed 2001; Reiter 1997; Meyer 1952: 6ff.

³⁶⁹ Cf. Tauer 1966: 36.

³⁷⁰ For the daughter as a gift see, e.g., Michaels 2004: 115f.

³⁷¹ Meyer 1952: 8.

person (*a-pātra*) 24,26 (TP II 172); ~ refuses to be married 24,30 (TP II 172); ~ is born for someone else 24,39 (TP II 172); ~ reaching puberty unmarried becomes a Śūdra woman (MW; *vṛṣalī*) 24,40 (TP II 173 'outcast'); ~ represents father's prosperity given away in marriage 24,161 (TP II 181)³⁷²; in his grief for three cursed ~s *vidyādhara* king goes to the forest 26,61 (TP II 221); getting ~ not sprung from the womb ends curse of *apsaras* 27,71 (TP III 6); a son, being embodied joy, is far superior to a ~, that is but a lump of grief (*śoka-kanda*)³⁷³ 28,6 (TP III 18); ~s are better than sons (*putrebhyo ... uttamāḥ*) and produce happiness 28,47 (TP III 23); marriage of ~ more important for the hereafter than obtaining son 28,50 (TP III 24); mortal ~ born by *apsaras* ends curse 28,67 (TP III 25); king devoted to ~ 28,73 (TP III 25); cunning brahmin ~ 28,175 (TP III 34); beautiful ~ dearer than life to her father (*prāṇebhyo py adhika-priyā*) 29,70 (TP III 44; cf. 22,36 TP II 147); birth of ~ lamented because of exposition to wicked female in-laws 29,92 (TP III 45); ~ given to prince as if she were goddess of Fortune (*Lakṣmīm iva*) 30,140 (TP III 74); *kadalī* produces ~ from hermit's seed fallen on it 32,102 (TP III 97); mother rejoices more at ~'s birth than at that of a son 34,49 (TP III 132); ~ of Kaliṅgasenā clings to face of nurse as the candle clings to the wick 34,98 (TP III 135); heavenly garden made for royal ~ 34,142 and 150 (TP III 138f.); Gaurī gives ~ to king 35,104 (TP III 164); ~ in womb causes pregnancy whims (*garbha-dohadā*) to roam in the sky 35,117 (TP III 164); king delighted at birth of ~ as well as of son 35,120 (TP III 165); ~ is great misery in the three worlds because she has not obtained a husband 35,125ff. (TP III 165); ~ given to husband as the sea gave Lakṣmī to Viṣṇu 35,154 (TP III 167); ~ superior to son promised by Śiva in dream 43,145 (TP III 291); king attached to ~ 43,264 (TP III 299); love of ~ (*duhitṛ-sneha*) 44,110 (TP IV 8); king Amīla loves his ~ Kalāvātī more than his life (*prāṇebhyo 'py adhikā*) 45,193 (TP IV 30); ~ given to king as hospitable entertainment (*prāghuṇātithyaṃ kāryaṃ*) 45,310 (TP IV 37); Gaurī orders Sumeru to give his ~, Gaurī's votary (*bhaktā*), to Sūryaprabha 50,125 (TP IV 116); ~ grows like moon digit (*śāśi-kalêva*) and becomes learned 51,22f. (TP IV 123); king has only beautiful ~ not wishing husband 52,93 (TP IV 144); father takes ~ on his lap and gives her sciences 52,398 (TP IV 166); father curses ~ because of disobedience 52,401f. (TP 52 166); ~ complains to father at being given to eunuch 56,88 (TP IV 226)³⁷⁴; ~ born due to a boon of Gaurī and dear to father as his life 59,11f. (TP V 26); *vidyādhari* dearer to father than his life 59,87 (TP V 32); *vidyādhara* parents die through grief at ~ they cursed 59,156 (TP V 36); affection for handsome ~ leads foolish king to have physicians prepare drug to make her grow quickly 61,266 (TP V 91); king slaps ~ 66,139 (TP V 189); ~ kicked by father leaves and becomes Śaiva ascetic 66,158 (TP V 190); merchant should not give away his ~ himself because she has another

³⁷² Cf. 14,20 (TP I 183) where a bride is characterized as a second *nṛpa-śrī*. Śak 4: 22) makes Kaṇva say that by giving in marriage a daughter, who is a deposit of others, feels as much satisfaction as is felt by one who returns a deposit to its owner.

³⁷³ See, e.g. Reiter 1997.

³⁷⁴ See 24,26 (TP II 172) and Kelting 2009: 201 note 11..

mother 67,77, her maternal grandfather (*mātā-maha*) should do it 67,79 (TP V 201f.); ~ distrusts her father as to which groom he wants to give her to 71,129 (TP VI 45); ~ as *femme savante* 72,66 (TP VI 73); only ~ of *yakṣa*-father ever amuses herself 73,32 (TP VI 103); ~ devoted to father asks for *saṃrāj* (*sarva-prṭhvīśvara*) as husband 73,331 (TP VI 125); father, fond of ~ who is ashamed of masculine ornaments, consoles her saying that his life is tied to her 73,364f. (TP VI 127); ~ of Candrāditya with a crore (*koṭi*) of physical perfections 74,217 (TP VI 156); beautiful ivory-carver's ~ gives signs (*saṃjñā*) to prince 75,68ff. (TP VI 169); father values ~ more than his life (*prāṇādhika-priyā*) 75,85 and (*prāṇebhyo 'py adhika-priyā*) 77,49 (TP VI 186); beautiful ~ courted by three brahmins but when not given remains unmarried 76,10 (TP VI 179; see also: *brahma-hatyā* supra); ~ wants to be married only to hero or husband with magic power (*viññāna*) or knowledge 79,9 (TP VI 200); Śiva promises king of Ujjain ~ whose beauty will put to shame the *apsaras* 83,10 (TP VII 2); beloved ~ offered *svayaṃvara* with portraits of all kings 83,16 (TP VII 3); *vidyādhara* father abandons beloved ~ with curse 86,107 and 135 (TP VII 20 and 22); ~ obtained by propitiating a deity (*devatārāadhanārjitā*) 88,6 (TP VII 35); ~ loved by father is *pum-dveṣiṇī* and refuses to be married 88,10 (TP VII 35); merchant's ~ able to bewilder even Kāma (Madana) 91,9 (TP VII 66); merchant's only ~ flees relations after father's death 93,11 (TP VII 79); hermit Kaṇva's ~ given as boon in marriage to king 94,48 (TP VII 90); merchant fond of ~ as only child 95,8 (TP VII 98); single ~ 98,7 (TP VII 118); ~ marries father 98,54 (TP VII 119); ~ promised by mother to one man and bestowed by father to another is abducted by the first man 112,10 (TP VIII 105); betrayal of Daitya father by weeping ~ 112,51 (TP VIII 109)³⁷⁵; Padmāvati declares a father is to ~s a divinity procuring all happiness (*daivataṃ sarva-siddhi-kṛt*) 116,20 (TP VIII 157) and desiring his victory in battle propitiates Gaurī in her temple with asceticism 116,23 (TP VIII 158); king makes marriable ~ sit on his lap and show her beauty to messenger of other king (*tām anke darśayitvā*) 120,100 (TP IX 8); – see also: grief; lamp-black

daughter-in-law eaten by mother-in-law 29,67 (TP III 43);

dawn, see: daybreak

day, magic fever causes death after seven ~s 5,113 (TP I 57); 27,120 (TP III 10); dense cloud of ~ of doom (*kalpānta-ghanāghana*) 70,71 (TP VI 29); seven ~s dispute 72,95f. (TP VI 76); woman is not her own mistress for four days in every month and does not wish to be questioned about it 86,110ff. (TP VII 21); seven ~s respite before separation from beloved 86,146 (TP VII 23); passing time by telling ~s (*dināni gaṇayan*) 101,161 (TP VII 145); birthplace of darkness of ~ of doom 109,83 (TP VIII 76); – see: ~ with various numerals

ḍayana 'palanquin', see note on *karṇī-ratha* below

daybreak³⁷⁶ announced by *paṭaha* drum in Cārudatta III 14 (Esposito 2004: 138)³⁷⁷; weeping

³⁷⁵ Cf. STh K 781; T 91.1; OTI G 530.2.

³⁷⁶ Cf. Bonisoli Alquati 2006; Smith 2009; Bollée 2008a: 12.

dancer like a bed of white lotuses, wet with dew at the hour of ~ 34,165 (TP III 140); ~ by *pratyūṣa-nāndī* (Harṣacarita [NSP. Bombay, 1946] 125,2) < Sivaramamurti 1956: 147; for ~ announced by a *bandin* see Chojnacki 2008 (I): 345 s.v. *barde*.

daydream (*a-nidra-svapna*) 12,116 (TP I 142); exhausted shipwrecked merchant on the shore sees black man with noose in hand, as if in a dream (*niḥsahaḥ svapna iva*) 56,145 (TP IV 230)

daydream motif, cf. Jean de la Fontaine, fable *La Laitière* (VII 10); see further: castles-in- the-air

dead body, all dead bodies burnt 4,107 (TP I 39); ~ like a frost-smitten lotus 52,151 (TP IV 148); – see also: corpse; hair-style

deaf (*dhvasta-śabda-śravaṇa-śakti*), see: blind 70,75 (TP VI 29)

dean of a guild, see: *vaṇiṇ-nivaha-nāyaka*

death,³⁷⁸ styled as “the long journey” (*yāto mahā-patham* ‘dead’) 2,43 (TP I 12) and 61,242 (TP V 88); ~ better than dishonour (*varaṃ hi mṛtyur, nâkīrtis*) 4,15 (TP I 31); escaping ~ by solving *rākṣasa*’s riddle (*praśna-mokṣād vadhôttirṇa*) 5,53 (TP I 51); robbers take brahmin to temple of Caṇḍikā to sacrifice him and, as it were, summoned ~ with the sound of their bells 10,189 (TP I 119); elephant’s ~ from polluted water 13,33 (TP I 152); 13,177 (TP I 163); king dies of love’s burning (*smara-jvara*) 15,79 (TP II 8); ~ of wife following separation from husband 15,90 (TP II 9); woman’s (threatening) forefinger (*tarjanī*) resembles decree of ~ (*Yamâjñā*) 17,88 (TP II 41); goddess of ~ entering a house as a wife (*Mārī mama gr̥he bhāryā praviṣṭā*) 17,90 (TP II 41); Deccan inhabited by god of ~ (*Dakṣiṇāpy antakâśritā*) 18,59 (TP II 54); Caṇḍikā temple with banner of red cloth (*raktâṃśuka-patāka*) like tongue of ~ 22,63 (TP II 141); ~ by heartbreak (*hṛdayam asphuṭat*) of merchant’s daughter due to discovered unfaithfulness 21,94 (TP II 132); king teaches merchant’s son, who falsely blames his father, fear of ~ (*prāṇa-bhaya*) by an artifice (*yuktyā*) 27,38 (TP III 4); ~ by starvation of brahmin and *caṇḍāla* 27,128 (TP III 10); howling she-jackal as messenger of ~ (*kṛtānta-dūtī*) 29,106 (TP III 46)³⁷⁹; queen’s ~ through king’s love of other wife followed by king’s ~ 33,73 (TP III 112); ~ of broken heart (of wife because of rival wife) 33,72 (TP III 112); ~ through fear of losing chastity (*śīla-bhraṃśa-bhayāt*) 34,19 (TP III 129); ~ out of remorse 34,20 (TP III 129); merchants about to be sacrificed are afflicted by dread of ~ (*maraṇa-trāsakâtara*) 37,42 (TP III 186); gods send ~ to brahmin who had set three-world on fire 45,90 (TP IV 23); hunt as sport of ~ (*kṛtānta-kriḍita*) 59,44 (TP V 29); sword-blades drinking blood and waving to and fro are like tongues of ~ (*kṛtānta-rasanā iva*) 50,5 (TP IV 108); ~ amuses itself with severed heads of heroes in combat like a game of ball 50,7 (TP IV 108); Nirṛti as goddess of ~ 50,35 (TP IV 110); ~

³⁷⁷ Cf. Bollée 2008b: 17 (vs 77) and Crooke 1906: 342: “The modern Rāja, following old-established custom, delights in the Naubat, a noisy medley of drums and trumpets, which echoes from the gateway of his palace at break of day.”

³⁷⁸ See also ORC 1609 s.v. *Mort*. Filippi 1996.

³⁷⁹ On the cries of jackals see Varāhamihira, *Bṛhats.* 90.

of maiden at sixteen 52,172 (TP IV 150); assumed ~ of king as test of courtesan's love 58,29 (TP V 17); Śābaras spending the day in the hunting-grounds in the sport of ~ (*kṛtānta-kṛīḍitaṃ kṛtvā dinam ākheṭa-bhūmiṣu*) 59,44 (TP V 29); ~ at rise of moon 59,109 (TP V 33); ~ of mother in childbed after birth of daughter 66,79 (TP V 184); ~ of ascetic by broken heart 70,72 (TP VI 29); temple of Devī, in which many living beings were offered, resembles palace of ~ (*kṛtānta-sadana*) 72,17 (TP VI 69); ~ (Kāla) consumed by Śiva but recreated because required³⁸⁰ 72,334 (TP VI 94); ~ leads moribundi off with noose he throws over their neck (*gala-kṣipta-pāśaḥ Kālah*) to Yama's hall 72,348f. (TP VI 94f.); fire of loud clashing swords seems kindled by gnashing teeth of angry god of ~ 74,283 (TP VI 160); seeing king's schadenfreude minister dies of heartbreak (*hṛt-sphotena*) in bed at night 86,162 (TP VII 24); all beings in *saṃsāra* fear ~ 94,39 (TP VII 90); ~ of woman due to excessive joy at seeing lover 95,74 (TP VII 103); grey hair as harbinger of ~ (*kṛtānta-dūta*) 103,226 (TP VII 190); ~ from insane desire to see not only woman's foot 106,65 (TP VIII 33); besieged kings dissuaded from ~ (by suicide) 110,7 (TP VIII 82); woman dies when her husband does not return at the appointed time and, when arriving, he sees her, he also dies; the *kula-devatā* Caṇḍī then reanimates them 111,40ff. (TP VIII 98f.); drum of ~ follows condemned person 112,166 (TP VIII 119); brahmin recovers his wife alive on pyre after her ~ due to fever 124,9 (TP IX 68f.); – see also: drum; hair; heartbreak; Kāla; letter of death; mouth of death

death in childbirth³⁸¹ (*sutaṃ prasūya ... pañcatvam āyayau*) 14,38 (TP I 184) and, of hen-parrot (*śukī*), 59,39 (TP V 29)³⁸²; ~ of mother after delivering daughter 66,79 (TP V 184) death penalty for injuring innocent wife 124,121 (TP IX 76f.)

decapitation, see: head

Deccan (*dakṣiṇāpatha*), brahmin from ~ with three sons who go to Rājagṛha to study 3,6 (TP I 18); shrine of Svāmikumāra in ~ 3,8 (TP I 18); brahmin Guṇāḍhya goes to and obtains all sciences from ~ 6,22 (TP I 61); wrestlers from ~ 10,20 (TP I 107) and 25,121 (TP II 200); ~ neighbored by *rākṣasas* and inhabited by god of Death 18,59 (TP II 54); wrestler (*mahā-malla*) from ~ 25,121 (TP II 200); king of *Dakṣiṇa-diś* 26,179 (TP II 230); city of Gokarṇa in ~ 33,25 (TP III 108); two discerning Buddhist monks (*śramaṇa*) tell king of Pratiṣṭhāna in ~ of beautiful match for him 51,118 (TP IV 130); alleged Rājput from ~ oppressed by relations seeks service with foreign king; four suitors from ~ 52,96 (TP IV 144); heroic brahmin from ~ 53,80 (TP IV 173); ~ king married to Mālava princess 58,108 (TP V 23), cf. 98,5 (TP VII 116); 66,110 (TP V 186); on confines of ~ (*dakṣiṇa-dik*) are *tamāla* forests dark like place of origin of monsoon (*prāvṛṣo janma-bhūr iva*) 73,30 (TP VI 102); ~ brahmin calls himself master magician (*yoginām guru*) 73,103 (TP VI

³⁸⁰ See Bollée 1977: 110f.

³⁸¹ Cf. 66,79 below and Bollée 2008a: 10f. s.v. childbed. The benchmark of this frequent sad event is that of the mother of the Buddha whose namelessness may be due to her magically dangerous misfortune (Meyer 1952: 393); an example from Jain literature is Vdh 298,27 *Isidattā ... pasūya-mattā c'eva sūya-rogeṇaṃ uvarayā*. In India every ten minutes a mother dies in childbirth at present (Mingels 2013: 54).

³⁸² Cf. Bāṇa, Kād. 54,5.

108); king of ~ (*dākṣiṇātya-nṛpa*) attacks Ujjayinī 79,11 (TP VI 201); ~ Rājput rags his garment and thus becomes king's vassal but is not rewarded for years 81,5f. (TP VI 209); four *viññānins* of different class from ~ come to Ujjain as suitors of princess too modest for *svayamvara* 83,17-20 (TP VII 3); ~ etc. conquered by Vikramāditya 120,76 (TP IX 6); Rājput from ~ with 500 clan members takes vow of *kārpaṭika* to serve king for twelve years 124,52 (TP IX 72);

deceive, gods intent to ~ (*vañcanēpsu*) Damayantī 56,268 (TP IV 239)

decoration, princess ashamed for wearing masculine ~ (*ābharaṇa*) 73,363 (TP VI 127); tiger skins as wall ~ (*maṇḍana*) 123,49 (TP IX 46); Bhilla women use ichor (q.v.) as (body) ~ 123,50 (TP IX 46); – see also: *mukha-maṇḍala*; vermilion

deer, king inconsiderately (*nirvimarśena*) kills hermit sporting with his wife (*bhāryā-sambhogakāle*) in the form of a ~ 21,25 (TP II 127); weeping ~ with weeping king in forest 66,148 (TP V 189); Bodhisattva turns himself into ~ due to his *yoga* and offers himself as food to guests 72,380 (TP VI 97); roaming dark ~ compared to rolling eyes of forest 73,239 (TP VI 118); Mārīci as a golden ~ entices Rāma away from Sitā 102,53 (TP VII 166); ~ are listening to sound of lyre 90,42 (TP VII 52); hermitage of Agastya where Mārīci assumed the shape of a golden ~ 102,52 (TP VII 166); Rāvaṇa beguiles Rāma with a golden ~ (*hema-hariṇa*) 107,19 (TP VIII 44); golden ~ (*hema-mṛga*) with two mermaids 120,109 (TP IX 9) and *sauvarṇo mṛgaḥ* 121,227 (TP IX 28); golden ~ (*hema-ratnamayaṃ mṛgaṃ*) made by Viśvakarman for Jayanta, Indra's son, to play with and animated by sprinkling with nectar (*sudhā-sekārpaṭa-prāṇaṃ*) 121,238f. (TP IX 30); do, marvel for the eyes of the three worlds 121,268 (TP IX 32)

deerskin (*ajina*) worn by female ascetic 71,130 (TP VI 45); hermit gives king black ~ to which charm is attached against bees 73,173 (TP VI 114); *vidyādhari* queen wears black ~ as garment 107,63 (TP VIII 47); *vidyādharis* seem to clothe king with the gleams of their eyes in black ~ 107,83 (TP VIII 48f.)

defloration, princess deflorated by *vidyādhara* (*vinaṣṭa-kanyakā-bhāvā*) 33,209 (TP III 124)³⁸³

deformed man, minister carried through the air by ~ who comes, when thought of 75,4 (TP VI 164)

deities, feet of ~ do not touch the dust, their eyes do not wink, but when visiting men they should not be asked who they are³⁸⁴ 28,61f. (TP III 24); sheth obtains daughter by propitiating ~ 88,5 (TP VII 35); brahmin boy says: “~ such as Brahmā, Indra, Viṣṇu and Śiva are transient”³⁸⁵ 94,135 (TP VII 96); – see also: propitiation

deity, enters king and makes him speak 34,56 (TP III 132); tutelary ~ (*yathā-sambhavi daivatam*) called upon by weak creature (*durbala*) in danger 94,131 (TP VII 96); ascetic worshipping favourite ~ (*svêṣṭa-daivata-pūjana*) 99,4 (TP VII 122); ~ presiding over evil

³⁸³ Bollée 2008a: 13.

³⁸⁴ Because gods tell the truth and when they visit men they will not like to be recognized.

³⁸⁵ This seems curious in a text of a Śaiva brahmin such as Somadeva.

- omen (*śakuna-devatā*) laughs at fool welcoming the omen 124,109 (TP IX 76); ~ presiding over chariot, see: *vimānādhideva*
- delay, see: procrastination
- delicious (*su-svādu*), said of fruit 123,30 (TP IX 45)
- delight, see: joy
- deliverance, see emancipation
- delivering, after ~ mortal daughter which ends her curse *apsaras* leaves for heaven 28,67 and 71 (TP III 25)
- delusion, the body is a fruitless accumulation of ~ (*dehaṃ niṣphala-māyā-samāhāraṃ*) 38,111 (TP III 214); hermit = Bodhisattva saves lovesick man from night of ~ (*moha-niśā*) 72,313 (TP VI 92); dream or ~ (*svapno 'yam uta māyā*) ? 86,129f. (TP VII 22); ~ by science (*vidyā*) 92,64 (TP VII 75); brahmin boy about to be sacrificed laughs at ~ of those (*vimūḍhānāṃ*) who ought to have protected him 94,124 and 129ff. (TP VII 96); Prabhāvatī by magic power causes ~ of the appearance of Śiva 107,5 (TP VIII 43); heavenly ~ (*dīvyā-māyā*) 121,134 (TP IX 21)
- delusive power (*māyā*) of *Asura Maya* 29,60 (TP III 43)
- “democracy”, see : constitutional kingdom
- demon, fire-breathing (*ulkā-mukha*) 18,147 (TP II 61); ~ of love (*sneha-graha*) 61,167 (TP V 82); exorcism of prince possessed by ~s (*Bhūtāviṣṭa*) 71,143f. (TP VI 46); bewilderment by ~ of love (*smara-graha*) 84,15 (TP VII 6); yawning ~ of destruction (*saṃgrāma-kālah*) 108,106 (TP VIII 62); ~ of man-hating (*puruṣa-dveṣa-durgraha*) flees from princess 122,82 (TP IX 40); – see also: *bhūta*; *brahma-rākṣasa*; *graha*; *rākṣasa*; *vetāla*
- departure at night 22,99 (TP II 144); 32,45 (TP III 93); ~ of two princes 42,97 (TP III 265); ~ of Nala 56,317 (TP IV 243); ~ alone in search of adventures 71,23 (TP VI 37); ~ (*niśā-mukhe*) of disinherited merchant widow 93,11 (TP VII 79); secret ~ of minister on pilgrimage 86,26 (TP VII 15); ~ of ejected king with wife and daughter 98,9 (TP VII 116); ~ of prince to abduct princess from Gaurī temple 103,31 (TP VII 177); ~ from temple of Mātaraś by couple of lovers 104,148 (TP VIII 12); ~ of king for the sandalwood tree 108,200 (TP VIII 68); ~ of *kārpaṭika* to granted village without telling others (*an-āvedya bhṛtyebhyaḥ*) 124,64 (TP IX 73); – see also: prince
- depopulation of the world wanted by animals, see: hunting
- deposit of wealth by merchant on business trip 4,26 (TP I 32ff.); ~ of woman with king 7,79 (TP I 83); brahmin ~s daughter with princess/queen (*etāṃ sthāpayāmy adya tava haste*) 16,22 (TP II 21); idem 16,100 (TP II 29)
- deposition of son, after birth by *yakṣa* parents 73,185 (TP VI 114); ~ at king’s gate 93,52 (TP VII 82); – see also: exposure
- depression of humiliated king Sātavāhana 6,122ff. (TP I 70); ~ (*sa-nirveda*) of young brahmin 7,52 (TP I 79); Indra removes ~ (*śoka, viṣāda*) of king Sahasrāṇika desiring a wife 9,20f. (TP I 96); ~ (*utkaṅṭhā-vimanā*) of princess as if by yearning / homesickness (remembering her father’s mansion) 17,62 (TP II 38: “with regret”; ORC 124: “*quelque peu abattue par la nostalgie*”; M I 176: “*gleichsam bestürzt und verwirrt vor Sehnsucht, in Erinnerung an ihr*”

Elternhaus"); ~ of princess at waking up without husband 18,222 (TP II 66); ~ of Garuḍa (*viṣaṇṇa*) 22,242 (TP II 155); ~ (*durmanāḥ*) of brahmin rejected by princess 25,1 (TP II 188); ~ of queen due to sudden recollection of pre-birth 27,84 (TP III 7); king is *śoka-kanda* because of daughter born instead of son desired 28,6 (TP III 18); ~ of seven princesses wishing to commit suicide on charnel ground 28,13f. (TP III 19); ~ for having caused harm 28,23 (TP III 21); ~ of queen because of rival wife 31,83 (TP III 88); ~ of brahmin after loss of gold: there was a void in his heart, but the whole universe seemed to him void also 33,138 (TP III 119); ~ of weeping woman not seeing lover is compared to bed of white lotuses wet with dew 34,165 (TP III 140); ~ (*cintā*) because of childlessness 35,27 (TP III 157); ~ because of wife imagined sick 37,220 (TP III 198); feigned explanation of ~ 39,42 (TP III 221); auspicious ceremonies at return of son end king's ~ (*kṛtôdāra-nirviccchamana-maṅgala*) 39,199 (TP III 232); ~ (*viṣāda*) from shame 39,215 (TP III 233); ~ of Nāgārjuna at being forbidden to prepare *amṛta* 41,22 (TP III 254); ~ of kings because of abduction of their wives 46,8 (TP IV 49); ~ (*viṣāda*) at slain *vidyādhara* chief 48,41 (TP IV 77); feigned ~ 60,109 (TP V 50) and 137 (TP V 53); ~ assumed (*kṛta-viṣādā*) by courtesan at leaving suitor 57,98 (TP V 8); sea of ~ (*śoka-sāgara*) 67,56 (TP V 199); ~ (*vignā*) of lonely princess in forest 71,198 (TP VI 50); ~ of people whose good king leaves for the forest 72,179 (TP VI 81f.); ~ because of parents' death 72,198 (TP VI 83); ~ of wife at disappearance of husband 72,383 (TP VI 97); brahmin despondent (*duḥkhīta-cetas*) because of sonlessness 73,28 (TP VI 102); ~ (*nirviṇṇā*) of mermaid of being abandoned by *vidyādhara* father 86,108 (TP VII 21); darkness of ~ (*mohāndha-tamas*) 87,18 (TP VII 30); ~ of *vidyādhari* wife at being unable to return to Mt Niṣadha due to forgotten *vidyā* of flying up 86,158 (TP VII 24); ~ due to inability to pay courtesan 93,34 (TP VII 80); hunting as means to dispell ~ (*udvega-vinoda*) 94,8 (TP VII 87); king very despondent at having to find boy as sacrifice to *brahma-rākṣasa* 94,83 (TP VII 93); faces of relatives of dead couple downcast from ~ (*khedād avāṅ-mukha*) 95,81 (TP VII 103); old brahmin gives prince Mrgāṅkadatta mantra against ~ (*viṣāda*) 99,45 (TP VII 125); ~ of Kailāsa at being pierced by Hara 109,67 (TP VIII 75); Rājput's wife afflicted by despair (*nairāśya-vidhurā*) because husband does not return 111,38 (TP VIII 98); king becomes despondent (*vimanaḥ*) by separation tale 111,48 (TP VIII 99); do, by not seeing couple of golden *haṃsas* 114,28 (TP VIII 134); ~ of princess at being separated (*virahāturā*) from Caṇḍāla who had saved her from mad elephant 112,94 (TP VIII 113); Indra fallen from his throne is depressed (*nirviṇṇa*) 115,95 (TP VIII 151); ~ of king because his daughters were refused for marriage 119,57 (TP VIII 197); army remains despondent in forest after king's being carried away by his horse 123,79 (TP IX 49); – see also: grief

deśa-dūṣaka (not MW) 'destroyer of the realm, revolutionary', crime of ~ 27,29 (TP III 3);

description, see: ascetic; *Asura* (princess); *aṭavi*; attractivity stereotype; battle; (*vidyādhara*)

beauty; cat; chamber (of princess); (newborn) child; Durga-piśāca; festival; gambler;

Gaṇeśa; goat; Hari; Himavat; horse; love; love-sick (princess); lying-in chamber; Mātāṅga

king; (brahmin) messenger; moon('s rise); night; palace; Pāśupata; procession; *rākṣasī*;

Śabara; sex; spring; Ujjayinī; *vetāla*; *vidyādhari*

descending from a vehicle and going on foot,³⁸⁶ by a princess going up to her castle with the messenger Anaṅgadeva 120.32 (TP IX 10)

desert, see *aṭavī*; ~ ('*maru-bhūmi*') as if created by Destiny to test king's firmness 72,180 (TP VI 82)

despair (*saṃtāpa*) due to silly judgement leads to suicide of brahmin couple 72,214 (TP VI 84);

despondency, see: depression; grief

destiny³⁸⁷, course of ~ (*vidhi*) cannot be barred 18,267 (TP II 70); ~ in the shape of hurricane wrecking ship 25,42 (TP II 192); who can calculate the caprices of ~³⁸⁸ or the waves of the sea ? 26,18 (TP II 218); goddess of ~ (*Bhagavatī bhavitavyatā*) putting foot on the heads of all men 26,24 (TP II 218); old bird whose flapping of wings was as extraordinary as customary of his kind (*pakṣī darśitāścarya-pakṣa-pāto vidhir yathā*) carries Śaktideva on his back 26,35 (TP II 219 "vulture, exhibiting a strange partiality (*pakṣa-pāta*) to the Brāhman like ~"; ORC 238: "*le vieil oiseau, dont les ailes donnaient des coups aussi extraordinaires que ceux du sort, ...*" with reference to the *śleṣa* in note on p. 1375: "*Appliqué à l'oiseau, il pourrait se traduire littéralement par "montrant un coup d'aile merveilleux"; appliqué au sort, par "[lui] montrant une faveur extraordinaire";* M I 340: "*Der alte Vogel aber beglückte Śaktideva mit einem so wundervollen Flug, daß es dem jungen Mann vorkam, als wolle ihm das Schicksal seine Gunst erweisen.*"); who knows the nature of ~ ? 26,90 (TP II 224); ~ cannot be altered 27,86 (TP III 7); all depends on ~ 30,71 (TP III 68); ~ (*vidhi*) watches to ensure the objects of those who are not on the look-out 30,91 (TP III 70); good objects are brought about by ~ for those whose actions in a pre-birth have been good 30,138 (TP III 74); ~ will educe prosperity (*vidhiḥ śreyo vidhāsyati*) 32,56 (TP III 94); ~ appoints unusual birth of heavenly beings on earth 34,90 (TP III 135); king places reliance on ~, whose power surpasses all thought (*a-cintyaṃ daivam*) 34,214 (TP III 144); who can overcome ~ (*kaḥ samarthaḥ syād saṃbhāvyam viceṣṭitam*) ? 36,96 (TP III 176) and 40,31 (TP III 242); even the Disposer cannot overstep ~ (*bhavitavyam dhātrāpi na śakyam ativartitam*) 37,236 (TP III 199); ~ provides fortunate with means to success 43,256 (TP III 299); what is ordained to be a man's ~ must be 49,195 (TP IV 98); gambler deprived of his senses (*daiva-hata-dhī*) by ~ 52,300 (TP IV 158); dispensations of ~ are irremediable (*a-śakya-pratikāraṃ ... vidhi-ceṣṭitam*) 52,332 (TP IV 161); when men are cursed by ~ even the wealth they obtain departs 57,24 (TP V 2); relying upon ~ brahmin couple sets out for forest 61,309 (TP V 95); ~ is fixed for any creature by works in a pre-birth (*pūrva-karma-vihitam bhavitavyam*) 65,255 (TP V 174)³⁸⁹; escaping one's ~ motif 66,108 (TP V 186 note one); headwind like powerful ~

³⁸⁶ A very old example is Bimbisāra visiting the Buddha at Mt Paṇḍava (Sn 418).

³⁸⁷ Penzer made a note on destiny in TP IV 182f., but see also especially Brown 1920, further ORC 1559; Bailey 1995: 381; Butzenberger 1996 was partly refuted by H. W. Bodewitz in IIR 42,2 (1999): 107-120. – Cf. fate in Daś (Bollée 2008a: 15).

³⁸⁸ STh N 130ff.

67,60 (TP V 200); cruel ~ (*ku-vedhas*) 71,232 (TP VI 53); who knows the mysterious way of a woman's mind as of ~ (*daivasya gahanā gatiḥ*) ? 71,236 (TP VI 53); terrible dispensation of unruly ~ (*duḥśikṣitaḥ ... vedhas*) 72,14 (TP VI 68f.; ORC 828: “*Quelle négligence venant d'un Créateur mal instruit*”; M I 77: “*Was ist das nur für ein Spiel des unverschämten Schöpfers ?*”); by ~ a man is captured by Śabarā as victim (*upahāra*) for Durgā / Caṇḍikā 72,402 (TP VI 99); *bhavitavyam* 73,61 (TP VI 105); hardships bring no reward to the unfortunate when ~ (*vidhi*) is against them 73,163 (TP VI 113); now ~ will dispose of me (*pramāṇam me 'dhunā vidhiḥ*) 73,209 (TP VI 116); Gaṇeśa knows and yields to ~ (*bhavitavyam*) 73,334 (TP VI 125); brahmin waking up with ornaments of princess on him thinks it is a ‘strange freak of ~ (*vilāsaḥ ... vidheḥ*) 73,354 (TP VI 126); no new thing for hostile ~ to conquer courage (*nāitan navaṃ jayati, yat pauruṣaṃ vidhuro vidhiḥ*) 74,104 (TP VI 147); what can ~ do against a firm unshaken man, any more than the wind against a mountain ? (*vāto 'drer iva kiṃ kuryād dhīrasyā-kampitasya (vidhiḥ)*) 74,105 (TP VI 147); ~ conquered by endurance (*dhairya*) 74,105 (TP VI 147); way of ~ is inscrutable (*vidher a-cintyāiva gatiḥ*) 74,205 (TP VI 155); *daiva-yogataḥ* 77,21 (TP VI 184); ~ (*vidhi-niyogataḥ*) makes nervous woman exchange heads of brother and husband 80,47 (TP VI 207); by ~ (*daivataḥ*) excessive delicacy (*atyabhijātavam*) of queens becomes *doṣa* 85,32 (TP VII 12); ~ cannot alter deeds in pre-birth 86,45 (TP VII 16); lonely *vidyādhari* princess as mermaid sings decrees of fate (*bhavitavyatā*) 86,79f. (TP VII 18f., see: *yat karma-bijam uptaṃ*) and 108 (TP VII 21); ~ written by Disposer (*Dhātr*) on the forehead in series of syllables (*yad yasya likhitaṃ dhātrā lalāṭākṣara-paṅktiṣu, tad avaśyam ... upatiṣṭhate*) that must be³⁹⁰ 86,155 (TP VII 24 with note); when ~ has turned against a man, everything in this world turns also 87,47 (TP VII 32); ~ performs everything (*sarvam āceṣṭate vidhiḥ*) 96,13 (TP VII 109); if ~ is adverse one cannot even die 96,22 (TP VII 109); wind compared to ~ destroys ship 101,141 (TP VII 144); ~ cursed (*hata-vidhe !*) by princess 101,147 (TP VII 145); who can decide the course of ~ difficult to know ? (*śākyā hi kena niścetum durjñānā niyater gatiḥ*) 101,196 (TP VII 148); course of ~ is strange (*gatiś citrā vidheḥ*) 101,298 (TP VII 155); when propitious, ~ brings about unexpected results (*vidhir ghaṭayaty arthān a-cintyān api saṃmukhaḥ*) 104,194 (TP VIII 15); ~ is decisive (*prabhu*) 106,57 (TP VIII 32); ~ tests *dhīratva* (‘firmness’) 107,1 (TP VIII 43); not even ~ comprehends why men fall into happiness or misery (*a-cintyo daivenāpy āpātaḥ sukha-duḥkhayoḥ*) 108,51 (TP VIII 57); even stones melt when ~ is propitious 108,92 (TP VIII 61); ~ never considers the feasibility of a union (*sādhyāsādhyā-vicāraṃ hi nêkṣate bhavitavyatā*) 112,114 (TP VIII 115); who can prevent ~ (*bhāvi vastu*) ? 112,170 (TP VIII 120); affliction by appointment of ~ (*daiva-yogād*) 119,8 (TP VIII 193); in the mind of ~ (*vidheḥ cetasi*) 119,60 (TP VIII 197); ship with princess is swallowed by *śaphara* (q.v.), and by ~ (*vidhi-gatyā*) it strands near an island 123,110f. (TP IX 51); *vidhinā dattā ... duḥkha-paramparā* 123,224 (TP IX 59); *ko veda*

³⁸⁹ STh N 120ff.

³⁹⁰ *Yad yasya likhitaṃ Dhātrā lalāṭākṣara-paṅktiṣu, tad a-vaśyam a-saṃbhāvyam api tasyōpatiṣṭhate.*

- daivasya gatiṃ* 123,341 (TP IX 67); – see also: *aho*; *dhig / k*; foot destruction, demon of ~ (*saṃgrāma-kāla*) yawning 108,106 (TP VIII 62)
- deva-daru-vana* ‘Pine Forest’ (q. v.)
- deva-dāsī*, see: duty; prostitution, sacred; *vāra-vilāsini*
- Deva-deva = Gaṇeśa 20,55 (TP II 99)
- Deva-deva = Śiva 112,135 (TP VIII 116);
- deva-loka* always nourished by *bhū-loka* and exhausted when *Asuras* kill brahmins, and gods no longer receive sacrifices 120,21f. TP IX 2f.)
- deva-nirmita* ‘god-built’, said of town of Kāñci 43,60 (TP III 285); Ujjaiyini 83,5 (TP VII 1)
- deva-putra(s)*, four ~ 54,11ff. (TP IV 184f.); – see also: knowledge
- devarṣi*, troops of ~ (‘divine hermits’) near Mānasa lake 109,41 (TP VIII 73)
- deva-sthāna* ‘assembly of the gods’ on full moon day in Caitra 118,17 (TP VIII 179);
- deva-yātrā* (procession of idols) 25,121 (TP II 200); 67,38 (TP V 198)
- Devī (= Durgā), assassins (*vadhaka*) in temple of ~ 3,39 (TP I 21); ~ tells Vararuci meditation arising from fire 5,140 (TP I 59); ~ Caṇḍī delivers the world with her form (*mūrtyā paritrātam jagat*) 26,146 (TP II 228); man to be sacrificed to ~ 61,158 (TP V 81); ~ tells man in dream that he will always have one ox 66,103 (TP V 185); ~ temple (*bhavana*) with bloody sacrifices and man who had killed himself 72,17f. (TP VI 69); festival of ~ (*Devī-pūjōtsava*) 80,20 (TP VI 205); king as favour of ~ in bodily form (*Devī-prasādena mūrtena*) 81,104 (TP VI 216); ~ announces in dream husband to woman loving him at merely hearing his name 103,37 (TP VII 177); 105,74 (TP VIII 26 Pārvatī); – see also: Durgā
- Devī-pūjōtsava* (Durgā festival) 80,20 (TP VI 205);
- devotee, behaviour of ~s inexplicable (*bhaktānām a-nirvācyam ceṣṭitam*) 91,45 (TP VII 69);
- devotion (*bhakti*) to parents provides power of discernment (*viññāna-bala*) 56,180-6 (TP IV 233)
- dew drops (*dyauravaśyāya*) as tears of heaven 71,192 (TP VI 49);
- dh* for *dy* (*dhūta-pāpa* for *dyūta-pāpa*) 121,196 (TP IX 26)
- dhairya* ‘courage’ in 37,140 (TP III 193 ‘presence of mind’, see: *yakṣiṇi*); by ~ ‘endurance’ everything is acquired 69,11 (TP VI 9; ORC 791 “*Montre-toi ferme. C’est en effet le moyen de tout obtenir*”; M I 23: “*Du mußt Mut und Ausdauer wiedergewinnen, wenn du das Ziel deiner Wünsche erreichen willst.*”); ‘self-command’ in *hṛta-*° 70,70 (TP VI 29); ‘endurance’, horse of ~ 74,105 (TP VI 147); – see also: patience
- Dhanada, Dhanādhipa, Dhanādhyakṣa see: *kāma-cārin*; Kubera
- dhana-mada* ‘pride of wealth’, brahmins with ~ 18,130 (TP II 59)
- Dhaneśvara, thus TP V 178 for D: Dhārēśvara (q.v.)
- dhanyāsmi* ‘I am highly favoured’ as reply of dancing-girl to merchant suitor’s request 57,77 (TP V 7; ORC 653: “*je suis bien chanceuse*”; M I 916: “*Ich bin beglückt*”.); *dhanyāham* said by a courtesan visited by a king 58,19 (TP V 16);

*Dhārādhipa (? not MW)³⁹¹ ‘ruler of flames, Agni’ 18,315 (TP II 73)
dhāraṇā ‘meditation’ given by Durgā 52,260 (TP IV 156);
 Dhārēśvara: habitat of Śaiva *siddhas* 66,2 (TP V 178: Dhaneśvara against ORC 765)
 Dharma as dove 7,89 (TP I 84); God of Justice ~, appeared visibly (*pratyakṣi-bhūya*), tempts
 boar-Bodhisattva and turns him into *munēndra* by touch of hand 72,145 (TP VI 79);
 Dharma (Buddhist) with secrets (*sa-rahasya*) 72,366 (TP VI 96); – see also: Buddhism;
 Religion
*dharmā*³⁹² ‘good, religious and social conduct’, parrot remembers pre-birth due to ~ 59,34 (TP
 V 28: ‘piety’); ‘salvation’, bathing places lead to an everlasting (*nitya-śuddha*) ~ as against
 charity 86,19ff. (TP VII 14 ‘purity’; ORC 951: ‘*pureté*’)
dharmānuśāsitr (not MW) ‘superintending religion’ (said of a king) 27,27 (TP III 3)
dharmā-pāṭhaka-bhikṣu ‘Buddhist monk preaching the Dharma’ 28,8 (TP III 18)
dharmā-rāja (‘officer in charge of religious affairs; superintendent of religion’) 87,53 (TP VII
 33 note);
dharmārthā sabhā, see: court of justice
dharmāsana ‘seat of judgement’, Naravāhanadatta only king without passion to influence his
 mind when sitting on ~ 113,3 (TP VIII 124)
dhārmika ‘student of religion’ going to Kāśmīra to conquer the paṇḍits in dispute (*vāda*)
 66,8 (TP V 178)
dhārnā,³⁹³ by determination to commit suicide (*maraṇa-niścaya*) citizens try to prevent king of
 Vatsa to be put to death 12,25 (TP I 135); of a brahmin at the door of a *kṣatriya* to get his
 daughter 52,37 (TP IV 140), and in order to get fifty *dinārs* 55,5f. (TP IV 202 with note);
 I will take no food until you tell me 89,37 (TP VII 42); merchant’s daughter induces father
 by suicide threat to offer king ten million coins (*dravya-koṭi*) for saving the life of a robber
 112,166f. (TP VIII 119); – see also: blackmail; protest; suicide III;
dhārtarāṣṭra-geese in lake 100,14 (TP VII 129)
Dhātṛ (‘Disposer’) 86,155 (TP VII 24); 100,30 (TP VII 130); ~ blends body of *Gandharva*
 Princess from nectar, moon, sandalwood, etc. 106,10 (TP VIII 28); ~ has compassion with
 brahmin refugee 108,47 (TP VIII 56); wishing to bestow Padmāvati on that prince
Gandharva looks meaningfully (*sākūtaṃ*) at the face of the ~ 116,85 (TP VIII 162); ~
 astonished at beauty of princess whose *nirmāṭṛ* he was 123,106 (TP IX 50); – see also:
 Disposer; *pumān*;
dhātreyī ‘foster-sister’ as confidante in love affairs 104,41 (TP VIII 4)
dhātu ‘cinnabar’ (q.v.)
dhavala-kañcukā (not MW) ‘with a white or beautiful bodice’, said of bride 104,165 (TP VIII
 13 “a white skinlike bodice”; ORC 1097: “*une ceinture blanche*”; M II 459: “*einen weißen*

³⁹¹ D reads: *cārādhipa*; no remark either in TP or in Balbir 1997.

³⁹² “Dharma ... is the principle of order, regardless of what that order actually is” (Doniger O’Flaherty 1976: 94); Malamoud 1976: 6f.

³⁹³ See Hopkins 1901. – Cf. Prabhācandra, *Kathakośa* 45,18 *dharaṇaka* (Upadhye 1974: Introduction, 25).

Wams.”)

dhig aho ‘alas ! shame !’, terrible is compliance with women ! (*kaṣṭām striṣv anurodhitām*) 20,197 (TP II 112); ~ (she said ..., the female heart is harder than the thunderbolt) 119,182 (TP VIII 205); – see also: *aho dhig*

dhig dhig 56,307 (TP IV 242 “curse on ...”); 58,129 (TP V 24), cf. 136

dhig grhān iti ‘out on family life’ 64,151 (TP V 150; cf. 64, 126 *yātu grhaṃ kṣayaṃ*);

dhik ‘shame !’ 46,58 (TP IV 53); *dhik-kāra* “saying: shame !” 45,394 (TP IV 43)

dhik-kathā (not MW) ‘bloody tale’ 28,133 (TP III 30)

dhiratva ‘firmness’ tested by destiny 107,1 (TP VIII 43);

dhobi covers meagre donkey with panther skin 62,19 (TP V 99); ~ hits pregnant brahmin woman who then has miscarriage (*vibhraṣṭa-garbhā*) 72,209 (TP VI 84); ~ falls in love (*hṛta-mānasa*) at *tīrtha* 80,9 (TP VI 204);

dhṛta-vartin (not MW) ‘pencil-holding’, tracing out a form with a ~ hand 55,67 (TP IV 207 with note; TP incomprehensibly reads: *amṛta-vartin* [not MW] ‘nectar-destilling’; ORC: “avec un pinceau”)³⁹⁴

dhṛtyā (TP VI 91: “under that belief”) for D: *vṛtyā* 72,296 (ORC 845: “avec cette disposition d’esprit.”).

Dhūr-jaṭi = Śiva, mango wood (*cūta-pādapa*) shoes of ~ 67,97 (TP V 203)

dhūrta ‘rogue’, two ~s rob town 24,82 (TP II 175)

dhyāna-pāramitā (‘perfection of meditation’) 72,283 (TP VI 89);

dice as sea of vice 19,29 (TP II 86); brahmin addicted to ~ (*dyūtāika-vyasānī*) 26,196 (TP II 231); hermit tells gambler he can escape from ~ by obeying him 26,204 (TP II 233); Kali and Dvāpara as deities of ~ 56,280 (TP IV 240); two ~ in the form of geese take Nala’s garment 56,311 (TP IV 242)³⁹⁵; Nala obtains ~ skill (*akṣa-jñāna*) from Ṛtuparṇa 56,377 (TP IV 247); ~ as sidelong loving looks of goddess of Ill Luck (*A-śrī-kaṣṭāka-pātāḥ ... akṣāḥ*) 73,76 (TP VI 106); vice of ~ (*dyūta-vyasana*) 73,186 (TP VI 114); do, 73,203 (TP VI 116); tumbling ~ as rolling eyes of calamities (*vipad*) the colour of a black antelope 92,16 (TP VII 72); Śiva-Vṛṣabhadhvaja plays ~ with Devī 110,55 (TP VIII 86); gambler forces Mātaraś and king Mahākāla to play ~ with him 121,80-93 (TP IX 17f.); if a gambler does not object to ~ being thrown, he agrees to play 121,82 (TP IX 18);– see also: cloud; croupier; darkness; gambler;

dig-ambara ‘naked’, drunk seducer left ~ 13,147 (TP I 160); ~ queen at magic rite 20,50 (TP II 98); Jain monk (*kṣapaṇaka*) 39,59 (TP III 222 “Buddhist monk”) and ~ interprets dreams 55,137 (TP IV 211)³⁹⁶; shame for being ~ 73,383 (TP VI 128);

dig-bandha-puraḥsaram ‘after observing and fixing the quarters’ ([?] MW) 73,116 (TP VI 109

³⁹⁴ See also. Karashima 2012: 145 note 6 on § 18.16.

³⁹⁵ Dice are compared to white objects such as geese as well as dark ones such as calamities (92,16 (TP VII 72)).

³⁹⁶ In both cases TP wrongly renders *kṣapaṇaka* by ‘Buddhist monk’. On Digambar monks in South India see Carrithers 1989.

“the ceremony of averting evil spirits from all quarters by waving the hand round the head” with note 1³⁹⁷; ORC 859: “*après avoir délimité l’espace sacré*”; M II 123: “*Zeremonien der Abwehr aller bösen Geister, indem er seine Hände nach allen Himmelsrichtungen ausstreckte.*”)

dig-devatā, see: cardinal points

digestion, with weak ~ (*mandâgni*) 54,174 (TP IV 196)

digestive fire, see: *jaṭharâgni*

digit of moon, daughter grows like ~ 51,22 (TP IV 123);

dig-jaya = *dig-vijaya*, *dharma* of a *kṣatriya* is not complete without wish for ~ 59,70 (TP V 31)

dignity, being seated is suited to ~ (*yathôcitâsanâsina*) 110,120 (TP VIII 90f.; ORC 1159:

“... *furent assis sur des sièges, conformément à l’étiquette*”)

dig-vijaya ‘conquest of the regions’ seems to serve carrying off the daughters of other kings

36,20 (TP III 170); ~ wanted by young *kṣatriyas* 42,80 (TP III 264) and 191 (TP III 273);

diśo jetuṃ vrajāmi 52, 370 (TP IV 164); 59,70 (TP V 31);

dik-pāla,³⁹⁸ see: cardinal points; *dig-devatā*; directions; *loka-pāla*

dinars, brahmin buries thousand ~ in forest 33,136 (TP III 119); ~ returned to brahmin like a second and external soul to his body (*prāṇān iva bahiś-carān*) 33,156 (TP III 120; ORC 329:

“*telle une vie extérieure à son corps*”; M I 464: “*Geld, das seinem draußen wandelnden*

Leben glich”); fifty ~ promised, but not given 55,4 (TP IV 202);

ḍiṇḍima ‘drum beaten at execution’ 88,33 (TP VII 37)³⁹⁹; 112,166 (TP VIII 119); *Daitya*

takes possession of territory of the *devas* with beat of drum (*bhramita-ḍiṇḍima*) 115,79 (TP

VIII 149); – see also: *abhaya-ḍiṇḍima*; drum; *udghoṣa-ḍiṇḍima*

directions (*diśaḥ*)⁴⁰⁰ filled with blood compared to great success (*rddhiḥ mahatī*) 46,141 and

146 (TP IV 58); ~ as sun’s garment (*ambara*) 92,30 (TP VII 73); – gods of ~, see:

cardinal points; *dig-devatā*; *dik-pāla*; *loka-pāla*

dirt (*a-medhya*), q.v. and see also: crane; flies; impurity; nose

discontent, of servants with wages 55,23 (TP IV 204); ~ harmful (*a-saṃtoṣo ’pi doṣāya*)

62,178 (TP V 114);

disease: insanity of prince caused by curse of bear 5,87 (TP I 53f.); cause of psychic ~

(*ādhi*)⁴⁰¹ cannot be found 6,128 (TP I 70 “mental disease”; cf. 104,115 [TP VIII 9]

below); idem, king healed by shock (*śoka*; “the queen is dead”) 17,38 (TP II 37); pretended

illness 24,135 (TP II 179) and 63,102 (TP V 128) and 73,217 (VI 116); cold ague (*śīta-*

jvara) seizes young brahmin 25,91 (TP II 196f.); ~ drying up all king’s sinews (*rogeṇa*

rājā snāyu-śeṣo vartate) caused by centipedes in the ear⁴⁰² 29,137 (TP III 49; ORC 288:

³⁹⁷ ORC 859: “*après avoir délimité l’espace sacré*”.

³⁹⁸ See Wessels-Mevissen 2001: 95ff.

³⁹⁹ Popley 1996: 123 states *ḍiṇḍimi* as tambourine.

⁴⁰⁰ See Wessels-Mevissen 2001 and Zin’s review 2003a.

⁴⁰¹ See ORC 1340 with note 1 on p. 42.

“*sous l’emprise de cette maladie le roi en est réduit à des ligaments.*”; MI 408: “*Mit dieser Krankheit lebt jetzt der König, von dem nur noch die Knochen und Sehnen übriggeblieben sind.*”); ~ appears as black blanket in king’s dream a woman strips off him 29,165 (TP III 52); wife of dolphin simulates illness (*māndya-vyāja*) 63,102 (TP V 128); king seized by incurable ~ (*yakṣman*) 73,259 (TP VI 119); madness (*unmāda*) cured by Pāśupata ascetic with a blow of his hand 73,381 (TP VI 128); lethal fever 97,11 (TP VII 113); headache (*śiro-’rti*) 104,109 (TP VIII 9); mental agony (*ādhi*) due to money or love 104,115 (TP VIII 9); old age, death and sickness (*jarā-mṛtyu-roga*) as calamities 115,114 (TP VIII 152); look (*dṛṣṭi*) of king heals eye-disease of *vetāla* 123,34 (TP IX 45); old age as ~ 123,65 (TP IX 47); – see also: abscess; cholera; colic; coprophagy; *dāha-jvara*; depression; faint; fever; headache; healing; heartbreak; leper; look(s); love-sickness; snake-bite

disguise of animal (*nāga* = snake) as man 61,170 (TP V 82); ~ of Garuḍa as man 61,175 (TP V 83); there are always disguised celestials on earth (*pracchannā divyāḥ sadā bhuvī*) 112,109 (TP VIII 114);

disguise of *Asura* Mahāmāya as Tārksya = Garuḍa, *vajra* and fire fighting with Kubera in the shape of snake, mountain and tree 50,38 (TP IV 110)

disguise of deity as animal: Indra as jackal 40,28 (TP III 242)

disguise of *vidyādhara* man as animal (lion) 22,134 and 139 (TP II 147)

disguise,⁴⁰³ of man as man 12,50 (TP I 136f.); idem 16,11 (TP II 20); ~ as Rājput 24,90 (TP II 176); ~ as hermit 24,91 (TP II 176); rogues ~d as Rājputs desiring service 24,121 (TP II 178); ~ of *vidyādhara* king as king of Vatsa 33,170 (TP III 121); ~ of Indra as brahmin 40,20 (TP III 241); ~ of prince as Pāśupata ascetic (*mahā-vratika-veṣaṇi kṛtvā*) 43,172 (TP III 293); ~ of minister Suveṇa⁴⁰⁴ as brahmin 56,331 (TP IV 244)⁴⁰⁵; besieged king flees in ~ to courtesan 58,16 (TP V 16); prince disguised as *mahā-vratika* (Pāśupata ascetic) 64,67 (TP V 144) and 70,2 (TP VI 23); man visits his adulterous wife in the dress of a leper, her lover 64,140 (TP V 150); ~ of rogue (*dhūrta*) as merchant 66,113 (TP V 187); prince in ~ of Pāśupata ascetic (*mahā-vratika-veṣeṇa*) secretly (*guptaṇi*) leaves town 70,2 (TP VI 23); minister ~s as Śaiva ascetic 75,162 (TP VI 175); king ~s as ascetic (*tāpasa-veśa-bhṛt*) 86,70 (TP VII 18); ~ of Mūladeva as aged brahmin 89,25 (TP VII 42); king disguised as

⁴⁰² Jolly 1977: 139 (§ 84) merely mentions centipedes in the ear as Kṛmi-karṇaka, Thite 1982: 32f. mentions worms in the head (AV II 31.4) but neither gives details of the disease which in the KSS is cured by heating the king’s head in the sun and inserting a bamboo tube into his ear for the centipedes, annoyed by the heat, to come out and fall into a pitcher with cold water. In Mahāvagga I 274 Jivaka Komārabhacca healed a merchant with worms in his head by trepanation (Zysk 1998: 67); in the Tibetan version of this story the worms are a centipede (Zysk 1998a: 57). Suśruta, *Kalpasthāna* 8,13 deals only generally with bites of centipedes which cause a burning sensation, violent epileptic fits and eruptions of white pustules. For a skull operation due to frog in the head see Hemavijaya 117,29 (Hertel 1920: I 256).

⁴⁰³ See, e.g., STh K 1821; Doniger O’Flaherty 1981: 379 masquerade. In a letter Schlingloff draws my attention to the fact that even after the Ajanta period men and women wore no clothes on the upper part of the body.

⁴⁰⁴ Text: Suṣeṇa.

⁴⁰⁵ Cf. STh K 1321.1 and 1817.1; H 384.1.

ascetic (*śānta-veṣa-bhṛt*) goes on pilgrimage in a horse chariot 93,73 (TP VII 83); ~ of brahmin (as a spy) in the shape of an ascetic (*bhikṣuka*) 103,12 (TP VII 176); ~ of gambler as ascetic 121,154 (TP IX 23); 124,150 (TP IX 79); Mūladeva c.s. ~ as Veda students 124,150 (TP IX 124,79); – see also: ascetic; hermit

disguise, of man as woman in royal harem 5,24 (TP I 48)⁴⁰⁶; idem 5,66 (TP I 52); idem 7,77 (TP I 83); 27,196 (TP III 16); Arjuna in woman's garb (*strī-veṣeṇa*) 33,91 (TP III 114); ~ of servant as bride (*vadhū-veṣa*) 64,71 (TP V 145); cowherd dressed as woman visits wife of brahmin absent on a journey 64,115 (TP V 148); ~ of brahmin as maiden 89,26 (TP VII 42); do, 89,85 (TP VII 46); do, 104,147 (TP VIII 12); 106,121 (TP VIII 37); *tāpasī* makes king put on female attire (*strī-veṣaṃ sā vyadhān mama*) 122,42 (TP IX 37); disguise of *rākṣasa* as crane 39,58ff. (TP III 222); ~ of *rākṣasī* as woodcutter (*kāṣṭhika*) 39,178 (TP III 230); do, as letter-carrier 39,186 (TP III 231)

disguise, of woman as man 13,179 (TP I 163)⁴⁰⁷; 27,196 (TP III 16); ~ as prince 29,99 and 102 (TP III 46); 39,175 (TP III 230); ~ in order to elope 52,274 (TP IV 156); ~ of adulterous wife as husband 58,100 (TP V 22);

disguise of Dānava woman as tree by means of *māyā* 118,107 (TP VIII 185)

disguise of woman as woman 16,10 (TP II 20); ~ of *apsaras* as human woman 28,59 (TP III 24); ~ of *Asura* daughter as mortal maiden 28,106 (TP III 28); ~ of heavenly maiden as royal wife 68,11 (TP VI 2); ~ of confidante as Hindu ascetic (*tāpasī-veṣa*, vs 138) with rosary, matted hair and deerskin, in order to spy 71,130 (TP VI 45); ~ of *vidyādhari* as mortal woman 105,43 (TP VIII 24); ~ of wife as courtesan (*veśyā*) 124,194 (TP IX 82)

disguised (*yuktyā*) fight of gods and *Asuras* 48,14 (TP IV 76)

disguising power lost when asleep 105,62 (TP VIII 25);

dish, emerald (*pātraṃ garuḍa-māṇikyamayam*)⁴⁰⁸ showing pre-births in reflection, used by Sinha parākrama 23,42 (TP II 160); child given ~ of *āmalakas* 60,242 (TP V 62); special ~ at change of moon (*parvaṇ*) 61,99 (TP V 76); snake poison falls into brahmin's rice ~ 87,44f. (TP VII 32); ; ascetic eats ~ of cooked child of nymph and rice 108,77 (TP VIII 59); – see also: golden dishes; plate

dishonour, see: death

disinterest of wife and relatives (*kā janma-bhūḥ kaḥ sva-janaḥ*) in native country 39,166 (TP III 229)

dislike, girl ~s the male sex (*pum-dveṣiṇī*) 88,9 (TP VII 35); – see also: misandry

disobedience, Pārvatī curses Śiva's servant for ~ to become mortal 1,56f. (TP I 6f.); king's ~ to Indra 45,18 (TP IV 18); ~ of son to parents punished by curse 56,150f. (TP IV 230)⁴⁰⁹; ~ of merchant's son to friend's good advice 57,117 (TP V 9); idem ~ of daughter 59,154 (TP V 36); *vidyādhara* prince curses disobedient son to become mortal 65,60 (TP V 159);

⁴⁰⁶ STh *K 1836.

⁴⁰⁷ STh K 1837.

⁴⁰⁸ Cf. the crystal ball used by our soothsayers.

⁴⁰⁹ STh *Q 325.

- 65,63 (TP V 159); father slaps (*capetaṃ dadau*) disobedient daughter 66,139 (TP V 189); ~ of princess to king 112,134 (TP VIII 116); ~ of prince to his father in refusing to take a wife (*dāra-saṃgraha*) 118,129 (TP VIII 187); hermit enjoins pupils not to disobey commands of Daitya maidens 73,139 (TP VI 111); – see also: obedience
- Disposer (*Pumān*) springs from egg, from ~ proceeds *prakṛti* 2,11 (TP I 9); ~ (*vidhi*) makes beauty after acquiring skill by creating Tilottamā 87,5 (TP VII 29); crest-jewel of great efficacy has sprung from waterpot of ~ 117,156 (TP VIII 174f.); – see also: creator; *dhātṛ*; looking
- disputation, dispute (*vivāda*) on the colour of the sun's horses 22,182 (TP II 150); ~ before king 24,184 (TP II 182); ~ of two brahmins on giving cow 45,103 (TP IV 24); student goes to Kashmere to conquer paṇḍits in ~ (*vāda*) 66,10 (TP V 178); boon of invincibility in ~ 66,61 (TP V 182); ~ about velocity of riding animals (elephant and horses) 67,7 (TP V 196); ~ for seven days between Buddhist monk and Hindu king 72,95f. (TP VI 76); ~ between parrot and maina on the wickedness of men or women 77,12 (TP VI 184); ~ about which suitor would get maiden 79,40 (TP VI 203); ~ about princess as legal wife never decided 89,110 (TP VII 47);
- disputatiousness, afflicted with madness of ~ (*vādī vyasanātura*) 66,13 (TP V 179); ~ (*kalaha*) characteristic of *rākṣasas* 66,16 (TP V 179); ~ of three fastidious brahmins 82,15 (TP VI 218); – see also: *jāti-vigraha*
- disregarding evil omens (*a-nimitta*) 36,54f. (TP III 173); 116,2f. (TP VIII 156)
- dissuasion from killing, see: old woman; ~ from suicide (q.v.)
- distraction (*udvigna*) pretended 32,10 (TP III 91)
- distress, see: depression; grief; melancholy
- distrust of father by daughter regarding man she is given to 71,129 (TP VI 45)
- diṣṭyā* 57,110 (TP V 9 'thank heaven'); ~ *vardhayitum* 'to congratulate' 118,40 (TP VIII 181);
- ditch (*khātaka*) compared to Avīci hell 13,149 (TP I 161)
- divination of king by elephant, see: choosing king
- divine being, excellent horse is a ~ (*daivataṃ hi hayōttamaḥ*) 18,100 (TP II 57); – see also: *apsaras*; dryad; mermaid; nereid; nymph, sylph; *vidyādhari*; *yakṣ(iṇ)ī*
- divine command forgotten by hero who is reminded by his wife through magic of *vidyādhari* 18,208 (TP II 65);
- divining, see: treasure (exhuming with candle 34,69f. [TP III 133])
- divi-ṣad-bhoga* 'heavenly joys' consist only in seeing says nymph 121,121 (TP IX 20)
- division of personality (*vidyā-viracitāneka-deha*) of prince Sūryaprabha who has intercourse with many wives at the same time 44,50 (TP IV 4 with note on *kāya-vyūha*); *vidyā-vibhakta-dehaḥ* 45,342 (TP IV 39);
- divya-haṃsa* 'divine gander; supreme soul > Viṣṇu' 54,30 (TP IV 186 wrongly: 'swan')
- divyā kanyā* 'divine maiden' 68,6-8 (TP VI 1); – cf. *apsaras*; mermaid; nereid; nymph
- divya-kanyakā* two ~ sitting on throne on a tree 17,111 (TP II 43); ~ singing in front of Śivaliṅga 59,81 (TP V 32); ~ emerges from *jambu* fruit 69,102 (TP VI 16); with a lyre

(*vīṇinī kanyā*) on a bough of a wishing-tree rising out of the sea a ~ sings about karman 86,44 (TP VII 16) and 79 (TP VII 19); king falls in love with her and when she disappears he plunges after her and finds her in her palace 86,96 (TP VII 20)⁴¹⁰

divyā kathā (the Kathāsaritsāgara) 8,6 (TP I 89)

divya-kautūhala (not MW) ‘celestial marvel’ (said of a temple built by Viśvakarman) 123,129 (TP IX 52)

divya-mānuṣa (demi-god), actions of ~s are very charming (*divya-mānuṣa-ceṣṭā tu para-bhāgena hāriṇī*) 1,47 (TP I 6; see ORC 1334 note 5 on p. 6); -*tā* ‘the status of a ~’ 110,139 (TP VIII 92)

divya-māyā (not MW) ‘divine delusion’ 121,134 (TP IX 21)

divya muni tells king in dream that he is free from faults 72,153 (TP VI 80);

divyā nārī ‘divine woman’ 56,207f. (TP IV 235); – see also: *divyā kanyā*

divyāṅganāḥ sing hymn to Gaurī at marriage of princess 34,253 (TP III 147)

divyaḥ pumān (*yakṣa*) with two *divya-nārī* restore exhausted minister’s health with a cool bath 73,13 (TP VI 101);

divya-siddhi-bhṛt ‘possessing divine power’, Pāśupata ascetic ~ 73,386 (TP VI 128);

divyā strī as wife of mortal sits with sister on trunk of *nyagrodha* tree⁴¹¹ 17,109ff. (TP II 43); ~ emerging from *śiṃśapa*-tree mutters *moha-mantra* and sheds glance of love on ascetic who then forgets his spells 70,68f. (TP VI 29); ~ picks up suicide candidate 72,199 (TP VI 83); Kāla (Death) creates ~ to catch Sinhalese robber and Citragupta devotee 72,341 (TP VI 94); 73,412 (TP VI 130); naked ~ follows man who took her clothes when she bathed⁴¹² 108,69 (TP VIII 58); – see also: *divya-kany(ak)ā*; *divyā nārī*; *divya-yoṣit*

divya-yoṣit tells king he would be husband of her daughter 106,36 (TP VIII 30);

doctor knowall motif, see: brahmin, stupid 30,93 (TP III 70ff. and note on 75ff.)

doe, lonely woman feels like ~ strayed from the forest 33,2 (TP III 107) or the herd (*mygīva yūtha-vibhraṣṭā*) 33,207 (TP III 124); eyes of ~s (*hariṇī*) recall to prince’s mind those of his wife 69,8 (TP VI 9); 72,199 (TP VI 83)

dog given meat with pepper⁴¹³ 13,125 (TP I 159); “weeping” ~ presented as companion in pre-birth 13,129f. (TP I 159); dogs eat dead brahmin 27,128 (TP III 10); ~ running from left to right evil omen 49,129 (TP IV 93); ~ is satisfied with a bone only 60,36 (TP V 44); ~ defiles sesame-seeds 61,106 (TP V 77); ~ piddles at Śiva’s idol 61,210 and rolls at the feet of a man it knows 61,212 (TP V 86); goat on brahmin’s shoulder is called ~ by rogues 62,66 (TP V 104); ~ bites knee of Buddhist monk who then sounds gong⁴¹⁴ to inform all other monks 65,132ff. (TP V 165); ~ (*sārameya*) poisoned by food sent by woman to kill

⁴¹⁰ Cf. OTI F 420.5.2.1; 420.6.1.3 and 5.

⁴¹¹ Nyagrodha and three other trees are the home of *gandharvas*, *apsaras*, etc. (TS 3,4,8,4; Gonda 1965: 339).

⁴¹² For the corrupt *hṛta-vastrārādra-vasanā* read: -*vasnā ca* ‘who had a wet skin because her garments had been taken away.’

⁴¹³ See Note in TP I 169ff. and Bollée 2006: 63.; – Debroy 2008: 231.

⁴¹⁴ See Hu-von Hinüber 1991. Cf. also PTSD sub *ganṭhikā* and *ganḍikā*.

minister 75,146 (TP VI 174)⁴¹⁵; Devī curses *Gaṇa* couple to become bob-tailed ~s (*chinna-pucchau śvānu*) just for laughing 114,68 (TP VIII 137); robbers become bob-tailed (*puccha-vinā-kṛta*) ~s 114,123 who remember their pre-birth 124 (TP VIII 141); ~s meditating (*dhyāna-stha*) and fasting 114,127, then become crows, etc., up to golden *haṃsas* 130ff. (TP VIII 142);
 dogfight, see: fight
 dog(s) biting expelled lover 4,69 (TP I 35); ~ eat dead brahmin 27,128 (TP III 10); 65,132 (TP V 165)
 dog's paw (*śunaḥ pāda*), branded on forehead of seducer 13,142 and 148 (TP I 160) and 190 (TP I 164)⁴¹⁶; – see also: *aṅka*
 dog used to taste poisoned royal plate dies 75,146 (TP VI 174)
dohada, see: pregnancy whim; Appendix III in TP I 221ff.; Lüders 1940: 44ff.; Pisharoti 1935⁴¹⁷
dolārūḍha ‘in doubt’ (Schmidt 1928: 217) 32,9 (TP III 91); 57,102 (TP V 8); 67,30 (TP V 198); 83,31 (TP VII 4); 119,190 (TP IX 206)
 doll, girl playing with ~ and making believe that it was a child (*kṛta-kṛtrima-putrakā*) refuses marriage 24,29 (TP II 172); magic ~ (*yantra-putrikā*) of wood⁴¹⁸ flying, bringing water, etc. 29, 1 and 18ff. (TP III 39f.); idem, without speech 43,11 (TP III 281); wooden ~ (*dāru-putrikā*) representing brahmin's third wife 74,165 (TP VI 152)
 dolphin (*śiśumāra*) eats *uḍumbara* fruits given by monkey 63,98 (TP V 128)
 Ḍomba,⁴¹⁹ with drum 13,96 (TP I 157); – see further : noose
 donation water,⁴²⁰ sprinkling queen with ~ when making her a witch and giving her spells for

⁴¹⁵ Cf. Rājat VII 688 where dogs die of poisoned test food for king.

⁴¹⁶ This may mean that the seducer when he does it again can be thrown to the dogs, cf. 102,72 where a king with a face with a three-furrowed frown is compared to his being marked by Durgā with the trident, to claim him as her own, see also: Durgā. See further Bollée 2006: 26. At Rājat 6,109 a brahmin ascetic is branded with a dog's paw.

⁴¹⁷ *Dohada* does not mean “the fertilizing of trees ... by the contact of a woman”, as Pisharoti writes (1935: 110), but for references the article is useful.

⁴¹⁸ See note on TP III 54ff.

⁴¹⁹ Low-caste or non-caste vagrant musicians (Kuv note 484).

⁴²⁰ As to the water, Mauss 1970: 53ff. does not mention it nor does Dange 1987: 632ff. or Michaels 2004: 197ff.; Kane 1974 II, 2: 854f. does, but gives no meaning of it. Gonda 1965: 428 takes it to be the confirmation or consecration of the gift which may be true but leaves open the question, why water and not dust (as in KSS 68,44) or anything else is used as power transmitter, or why not a different gesture is performed. Professor Feldhaus (p. c.) thinks of a magical cleaning of the hands by water, see ŚpBr 1,1,1,1 *pavitram vā āpaḥ*, as is practised with the child at Christian baptism (Bowker 1997: 125). According to Lüders 1951: 32 a gift, also a negative one such as a curse, is a contract between giver and donee, and the water is Varuṇa's water lethal for who commits a breach of it, originally the contract of an oath, of which Varuṇa is the tutelary deity, and at which one curses oneself when breaking the oath. For pictures of donation water to legalize the act of giving something in Ajanta see Schlingloff 1987: 146.

Finally, it may be remembered that Varuṇa is not only Lord of the waters, but also *ṛtasya gopāḥ* ‘guardian or confirmator of vows’ (RV 3,10,2). This will also be relevant for the official reception of a guest (*argha*), the royal *abhiṣeka* (of a queen, e.g. at 6,167 [TP I 73], and the consecration of Kārttikeya as general of the gods by Indra with

flying 20,111 (TP II 104); (right) hand moist with ~ (*dāna-toya*) 38,116 (TP III 214)⁴²¹; mother gives daughter to impaled thief with ~ on his hand (*ambu pāṇau caurasya sā ... pātayat*) 93,23 (TP VII 79)⁴²²; ~ at ceremony of *hastōdaka* by husband when giving away his wife to Indra 113,75 (TP VIII 129); donkey, war chariot drawn by ~es 48,54 (TP IV 78); ~ of dhobi (*rajaka*) in panther's skin to make it fat 62,19 betrays itself by braying 62,22 (TP V 99f.); sick lion, jackal and ~ 63,130 (TP V 130); ears and heart⁴²³ of ~ wanted by wounded lion 63,130 (TP V 130); (male) ~ milked in vain 63,187ff. (TP V 136); woman (*Māyā*) with wheel, bull and ~ 70,89 (TP VI 30); ~ (*khara*) symbol of *a-dharma* 70,118 (TP VI 32); ~ of dhobi breaks hoof (*bhagna-khura*) while fleeing brahmin woman 72,207 (TP VI 84); *vetāla* with ~ ears (*khara-karṇaka*) 102,19 (TP VII 162)⁴²⁴ doomsday (*kalpa-kṣaya*), at ~ the universe becomes water 2,10 (TP I 9); dense cloud of ~ 70,71 (TP VI 29)⁴²⁵; *kalpānta-megha*- 102,77 (TP VII 168); Śiva-Bhairava is terrible like a roaring great cloud of ~ (*garjan-mahā-pralaya-megha iva pracaṇḍaḥ*) 106,182 (TP VIII 42 “he was terrible like a roaring cloud of the great day of doom”; similar M II 487; ORC 1118: “avec la violence extrême du grondement du tonnerre lors de la fin du monde”); cave looking like birthplace of the darkness of ~ 109,83 (TP VIII 76); at ~ (*pralaya*) ocean overflows its bank 109,117⁴²⁶ with a rising wind (*kalpānta-pavana*) 119 (TP VIII 79); fire of ~ 118,76 (*kalpāntānala*) (TP VIII 183)⁴²⁷; promises of royalty will not change on ~ 119,16 (TP VIII 194) door, of paradise opened on morning of eleventh day 12,167 (TP I 146); east ~ (*pūrva-dig-dvāra*) principal entrance of palace 38,21 (TP III 207); ~ of shop carried off by stupid servant 62,210 (TP V 117); – cf. gate doorkeeper (*pratīhāra*), wealthy merchant as ~ 43,69 (TP III 286); female ~ (*pratīhārī*)

a pitcher 20,95f. [TP II 102f.]. Professor Hampana (p.c.) sees water as a symbol of sanctity and divinity because it stems from Śiva's topknot and points to the rite of giving as referred to as *dhārā-pūrvaka*. – Agarwal 2011 was not available to the present author. – See also Meyer 1952: 62 note 4; Bollée 2010: 38 note 220.

Professor S. R. Sarma writes me in a p.c. that in his *purohita* family in Andhra Pradesh water was poured clockwise around plates of food before the meal and anti-clockwise after the meal. This was apparently done to protect the food with a magic ring against the evil eye of jealousy, etc. – On donation water see also the long note 14 in Kieffer-Pülz 2013: 1052f.

⁴²¹ Cf. Rājāt 7,12.

⁴²² Cf. in Pali: *udak' -ūpassatthā* for a girl given to the bridegroom with the water of donation poured over his hand in *AnguttaraN* III 226,4 (CPD).

⁴²³ For the curious combination Isaacson (p.c.) refers to Pañcat III 17 where the jackal eats the heart and the ears of the donkey who then becomes *a-karṇa-hṛdaya* (Edgerton 1924: 385).

⁴²⁴ STh E 251.4.2; *F 511.2.2.

⁴²⁵ On the darkness of doomsday see STh A 1002; Doniger O'Flaherty 1973: 249 and 375: 5d; 1988: 71ff. Bāṇa compares an elephant with a bank of doomsday clouds (Smith 2006: 82). Rājāt 2,37.

⁴²⁶ Do, 1973: 376: 14d.

⁴²⁷ See Doniger O'Flaherty 1973: 175 sub 5d.

119,14 (TP VIII 194)⁴²⁸; – see further: *pratihāra*; warder
doṣa, cf.: *gha*; error; fault; *kilbiṣa*; transgression
doṣākara ‘home of crimes’, Lāṭa (South Gujarat) is not a ~ 74,139 (TP VI 150);
doubt, ascending swing of ~ (*vicāra-dolā*) 9,87 (TP I 102); ~ of reality (*kiṃ svapno ’yam uta
brāntir dhig etad*) 17,112 (TP II 43); ~ about maiden riding on lion 22,81 (TP II 143); ~
about sleep or death (*kim a-prabodha-suptēyaṃ kiṃ vā bhrāntir a-bādhakā*) 26,80 (TP II
222); ~ about the state of a man: can this be the moon ... ? 28,57 (TP III 24); ~ about the
state of a beautiful princess 28,102f. (TP III 27); ~ about the state of a disguised *asurī*
28,190 (TP III 36, cf. Zin 2003b: 145 note 40); king thinks: “Can a barber’s wife be a witch
?” 32,159 (TP III 103); king in ~ (*vicāra-patita*) 33,21 (TP III 108); has someone died who
enters another body ? 45,59 (TP IV 20); discovered woman doubts between shame and
jealousy 45,265 (TP IV 35); ascetics have ~ (*a-pratyaya*) about Sītā’s faithfulness 51,76
(TP IV 127); 52,225 (TP IV 153); ~ about girl, whether beloved or not 67,67 (TP V 200);
king waking up in a Nandana-like garden wondering if it could be dream or delusion
(*bhrama*) 72,185 (TP VI 82); illusion or confusion of mind ? (*kiṃ māyā kiṃ mati-bhramah
?*) 73,160 (TP VI 113); father’s ~ about what happened to daughter 73,367 (TP VI 127);
hero’s ~ at being all at once from sea in garden 81,59 (TP VI 212); dream or delusion
(*māyā*) 86,129f. (TP VII 22); 87,11 (TP VII 30); 89,10f. (TP VII 40); ~ of king which
corpse to choose 92,4 (TP VII 71); ~ to enter fire or not 92,74 (TP VII 76); ~ about a
person’s identity 94,21 and 25 (TP VII 88f.); ~ who can this great-hearted (*mahātmā*) one
be ? ... 101,241 (TP VII 151); dream or reality ? (*svapnaḥ satyam eva vā*) 104,169 (TP
VIII 14); king in ~ about lost head-queen 105,8 (TP VIII 21); princess full of ~
(*saṃśayākulā*) 119,119 (TP VIII 201); is this a wonder, a dream or delusion ? (*kim idam
āścaryaṃ, svapno māyā bhramo nu kim ?*) 120,108 (TP IX 9); – see also: *dolārūḍha*;
rivalry
dowry, immense⁴²⁹ 14,31 (TP I 184); 44,75ff. (TP IV 6); 44,95 (TP IV 7); ~ of aloes-wood
44,132 (TP IV 9); 55,102 (TP IV 209), et passim
dramatic performance, see: dance
draughtsman (*citra-kṛt*) and sculptor (*rūpa-kṛt*) decorate pillar with image of Gaurī 37,8 (TP
III 183)
Draupadī concealed in Virāṭa’s palace 16,30 (TP II 22)
drawing lines on the ground, princess ~ with bashful eye (*bhuvam ... likhanti hrītayā dṛśā*)
90,80 (TP VII 54)⁴³⁰; – see also: scratching

⁴²⁸ For a description of an female doorkeeper with a scimitar (*kaukṣeyaka*) at her left side see *Kād.* 15,2 and further Saletore 1943: 254.

⁴²⁹ A dowry apparently is a kind of compensation for the donation of an inferior present, but the wife, *bhāryā*, is not a “deliveress”, as Syed 2001: 27 suggests; that a woman is a misfortune (*kṛpaṇa*) is recorded since AitBr 7,13 (Syed, l. c.). See further Wezler 1998: 300ff. and the literature given in note 61; Syed 1999.

⁴³⁰ Drawing lines or scratching the ground usually indicates boredom, nervousness (Daṇḍin, *Daś* 239,9) or helplessness as in *Amaru* 8 and 46. The sorrowful Māra draws lines on the ground, *Māro ... domanassa-patto mahā-vagge nisīditvā soḷasa kāraṇāni cintento bhūmiyaṃ soḷasa lekhā kaḍḍhi* (Ja I 78,15). This old topic is depicted in

dread of death, see: death

dream⁴³¹ of Vararuci sent by Durgā 2,3 (TP I 9); ~ sent by Kārttikeya 2,45 (TP I 12); Śiva sends ~ to three women 3,21 (TP I 19); ~ of Sarasvatī, the goddess of learning continually living in his frame (*sadā śarīrāntarvāsini*), sent to brahmin 4,9ff. (TP I 31); ~ sent by Śiva to sonless king about boy on lion 6,91 (TP I 67); minister uses charm to produce a ~ (*svapna-māṇavaka*) 6,137 (TP I 70)⁴³²; ~ of Sarasvatī entering dreamer's mouth 6,139 (TP I 71); Indra predicts king birth of daughter in ~ 11,76 (TP I 128); Viṣṇu predicts in ~ Lohajaṅgha wealth 12,128 (TP I 143); Śiva gives red lotus to couple in ~ 13,78 (TP I 156); pretended ~ 13,121 (TP I 159)⁴³³; ~ of Śiva predicting king a son's birth 19,7 and worthy to be drunk in with the ears 19,11 (TP II 85); idem 21,143 (TP II 136); ~ by queen of hermit (Śiva) giving her a fruit 21,147 (TP II 136); queen's ~ of rising in the air 22,10 (TP II 138); ~ of woman promised husband by Śiva 22,122 (TP II 146); ~ of queen promised protection of her embryo by Śiva as hermit 23,5 (TP II 157); ~ by queen of hermit with trident telling story to prove credibility of earlier statement after which she wakes up in the morning 23,6ff. (TP II 157)⁴³⁴; ~ of Devī-Durgā showing hidden treasure 23,39 (TP II 159); female voice instructs queen in ~ to give daughter to pre-birth husband 25,166 (TP II 204); Durgā foretells *vidyādhari* mortal husband in ~ 26,62 (TP II 221); ~ by Durgā predicting future 26,148ff. (TP II 228); idem, commanding brothers' assent for marriage of sister 26,156 (TP II 228); flame from heaven entering queen's womb which ~ the king interprets 27,74 and 210 (TP III 6 and 17)⁴³⁵; king dreams of black blanket (*kṛṣṇa-kambala*) a lady stripped off him 29,165 (TP III 52); ~ as Uṣā's boon from Gaurī: unison with man in ~ who will be her husband 31,15 (TP III 82); Śiva in double ~ to royal couple promises son 35,103 (TP III 164); ~ sent by Gaurī to princess at end of night with instructions about future husband 35,135 (TP III 166); king's inauspicious ~ counteracted

Bharhut, Amarāvati and Kanaganagalli; in Ajanta X Māra keeps a small stick in his hand (p.c. Zin); Schlingloff 1988: 7.

At Hemavijaya, *Kathāratnākara* (Dharamsala, 1997) 19,1 a man, as if very sad, with his cheek in his hand, scratches the earth with his foot (*caraṅḥlīkhita-bhū-tala*) and gazes into space. See also Syed 1993; Bollée 2008: 75.

⁴³⁰ See, e.g., Bautze-Picron 2009 and ORC 1634.

⁴³¹ Osier 2009: 270.

⁴³² Cf. STh 1212.1.

⁴³³ According to Jagaddeva I 17 a dream seen at sunrise will realize at once. Kād 147,6.

⁴³⁴ Osier 2009: 263 argues that the interpreters are skilled people owing their abilities to their professions or sometimes to the personal acquaintance they have with the dreamer as relatives or friends; 267. On the light when a Bodhisatta leaves the Tusita heaven to be reborn see Bollée 2005: 9f.

⁴³⁵ On displacement in dreams see Freud 1954: 671.

⁴³⁶ In 74,282 (TP VI 160) armies are compared to seas (*śainya-jaladhi*).

⁴³⁷ On the fiery man see Osier 2009: 269.

by drinking spirits with queen 36,67 (TP III 174); Durgā sends ~ to merchants that their fetters are loosed 37,48 (TP III 186); in ~ Hari on Garuḍa instructs king to kill wicked mendicant (*śramaṇa*) 38,58 (TP III 210); in ~ Bhavānī = Gaurī gives two fruits to be eaten by queens for sons 42,58 (TP III 263)⁴³⁶; Durgā gives sword to prince in ~ 42,118 (TP III 267); threatening ~ (*duḥsvapna*) 42,153 (TP III 270); princess in white garments informs king in ~ (interpreted by minister) of future just before his waking up 43,2 (TP III 281); ~ of divine hero on peacock (Kārttikeya) at end of night orders dreamer to stay 43,50 (TP III 284); Śiva in ~ promises king daughter 43,145 (TP III 291); at end of night ~ of stream of water (= battle)⁴³⁷ sweeping away all who are drawn out by a fiery bright man (= Śiva)⁴³⁸ and thrown into fire (= war). A cloud rained blood (*raktāugham*) (= destroying fear) which filled the sky (= great success) 46,141 and 146 (TP IV 58)⁴³⁹; three kinds of ~ (*anyārtha*⁴⁴⁰, *yathārtha*, *apārtha*) **46,147f.** and causes of ~ 46,148f. (TP IV 58); ~ seen at end of night is quickly fulfilled 46,150 (TP IV 58)⁴⁴¹; ~ of Umā announcing future son to be devoted to *dharma* 51,17 (TP IV 123); ~ of Cāmuṇḍā explaining future 52,168 (TP IV 149f.); Śiva sending same ~ to royal couple 52,389-91 (TP IV 165); Durgā appeased by penance of *kṣatriya* servant offers one of two boons in ~ 54,163 (TP IV 195); *kṣatriya* dreams of violence reflecting intestinal colic of someone else 54,179-184 and of violence between quarreling men 201-204 (TP IV 197f.); king dreams that his necklace and crest-jewel were taken from him and he wrestled with a Vetāla 55,133 (TP IV 211); Digambara monk interprets king's ~ 55,137 (TP IV 211); ~ of Gaurī instructing *vidyādhari* at night's end about approaching marriage 59,16f. (TP V 27); ~ of moon (*soma*) entering mouth of pregnant queen 59,61 (TP V 30)⁴⁴²; in ~ Śambhu-Śiva instructs two people about future 59,168 and 172f. (TP V 37f.); in ~ at end of night Gaurī tells prince the end of his curse by touch of female ascetic, and prophesies to marry princess 65,232, cf. 236 (TP V 172f.); Durgā prophesies poor man to always have one ox 66,103 (TP V 185)⁴⁴³; princess (cursed *vidyādhari*) dreams of crossing river, mounting white elephant,

⁴³⁸ Somadeva uses this enigmatic dream of cosmic disaster getting a positive end as a kind of *fortissimo*, which emphasizes by anticipation the events to come (Osier 2009: 262), Bollée 1984: 183f.

⁴³⁹ Osier 2009: 265.

⁴⁴⁰ TP IV 58 note 1: reading *aneko dhanyārtho* (for NSP ed. *anekadhānyārtho*). – Jagaddeva I 17.

⁴⁴¹ The moon is symbolic of a beautiful person, see below: moon (12,24 (TP I 134), etc.

ascending mountain, meeting deity and flying up into sky 66,160f. (TP V 190); Naravāha nadatta dreams of being carried off by a *divyā kanyā* 68,6 (TP VI 1); minister dreams of lion crossing a river and sticking his long tongue at him which he then cuts off and uses as bridge to cross the river 69,23ff. (TP VI 10); prince dreams he and ministers want to drink water in a wood and are prevented by five men whom they kill. When they again try to drink, water and men have disappeared and Śiva appears on Nandi. From a teardrop of his a sea emerges from which the prince plucks a pearl necklace and drinks the sea with a bloody skull. Then he wakes up at the end of the night 69,34ff. (TP VI 11); Viṣṇu foretells prince in ~ healing of his fever by touch of Viṣṇu devotee and future bride's hand 71,122 (TP VI 44); faked ~ of *rākṣasi* seizing woman to eat her 71,173 (TP VI 48); king dreams three times of going to the hereafter, asking armed men for food and getting hot sand he once gave to a hungry brahmin. He then wakes up at night's end 72,105ff. (TP VI 77); *divya muni* tells king in ~, provoked through *svapna-māṇava* (q.v.), that he is now free from transgression 72,153 (TP VI 80); Agni predicts brahmin a son in ~ 73,59f. (TP VI 105); after worshipping Viṣṇu king ~s of Daitya maiden approaching him and waking up is astonished not to see her 73,88 (TP VI 107)⁴⁴⁴; goddess Gaṅgā gives brahmin fruits in his ~ 74,119 (TP VI 148); doubt: ~ or delusion (*māyā*) 86,129 (TP VII 22); ~ of Śiva telling mother to expose new-born son at king's gate 93,49 (TP VII 81); Śiva Varṣadhvaja tells sonless king in ~ of son lying at his gate 93,52 (TP VII 82); in twelfth night of penance Gaṇeśa sends Mṛgāṅkadatta ~ and removes curse from his ministers 100,51 (TP VII 132); Devī designates in ~ husband for princess 103,37 (TP VII 177); do, 105,74 (TP VIII 26); at night's end king dreams of his father being dragged away to the south by black female (*kṛṣṇayā striyā*) 111,51 (TP VIII 99f.)⁴⁴⁵; Agni in ~ urges king Prasenajit to find out truth about *caṇḍāla* lover of his daughter 112,98 (TP VIII 114); king's of two golden *haṃsas* 114,48 (TP VIII 136); Pārvatī in ~ intends to put wreath on princess but then delays it to future occasion 117,166 (TP VIII 175); Śiva in ~ promises king two sons 118,30 (TP VIII 180); Śiva promises Daitya queen in ~ husband to daughters after which she awakes at close of night 118,135 (TP VIII 187); after six nights of fasting prince sees in ~ celestial maiden in Śiva temple 119,70f. (TP VIII 198); in Gaurī *āśram* Padmāvatī dreams of *jaṭādhara* hermit coming out of Śiva temple and telling her end of trouble and husband near 119,88ff. (TP VIII 199); Śiva in ~ reveals childless king famous son and sons also to his ministers 120,36 (TP IX 4); harem servant shows king fruit given by Śiva to queen in ~ 120,42 (TP IX 4); ~ of pregnant queen: crossing seven seas, and being worshipped by *yakṣas*, *vetālas* and *rākṣasas* 120,46 (TP IX 4); ~ of king who wakes up after seeing girl from another continent 122,30 (TP IX 36); watchman (*yāmika*) interrupts king's ~ 122,31 (TP IX 36); man-hating princess sees in ~ *mahā-puruṣa* in *vihāra* 122,81 (TP IX 39 'great hero'); – see also: Agni; Durgā; Śiva

⁴⁴³ See Brown 1920: 98.

⁴⁴⁴ Cf. Bollée 1984: 175 (AV 7,101).

⁴⁴⁵ Cf. Bollée 1984: 176f.

dreamless sleep, see: sleep

dress (*rūpa*) of brahman woman 16,18 (TP II 21); turban and diadem (*paṭṭaṃ mukuṭaṃ ca*) of emperor of *vidyādharas* 50,206 (TP IV 121); king impressed by merchant's ~ (*veṣa-bhrānta*) 66,115 (TP V 187); – see also: garment; turban

dr̥g-viṣāhi (not MW) 'snake with poisonous look > laming stare' 109,69 (TP VIII 75 'basilisk'; ORC 1146: "*serpent au regard venimeux*"; M II 525: "*Schlangen, die schon mit ihren Blicken einen Eindringling vergiften konnten*"); – see also: *dr̥ṣṭi-viṣa*

drinking spirits (*pāna*) as enjoyment of queens 18,27 (TP II 51); ~ before sex 33,13 (TP III 107); 33,93 (TP III 114); 34,93 (TP III 135); ~ in the morning to counteract evil dream 36,67 (TP III 174)⁴⁴⁶; ~ and other diversions 38,33 (TP III 208); sluggishness due to ~ (*pītāsava-madālasa*) 40,2 and coming drunk into the presence of prince because of ~ in the morning 4 (TP III 240); king spends day and night in ~, etc. with parents 40,116 (TP III 249); Namuci drinks smoke. i.e. smokes 46,218 (TP IV 63); king ~ (*piban madhūni*) with ministers 54,82 (TP IV 190); ~ of Pāśupata ascetic as recreation with females 56,211 (TP IV 235); king stupified with ~ (*pāna-matta*) loses magic sword 56,222 (TP IV 235); vice of ~ leads to breaking wish-granting pitcher (*bhadra-ghaṭaka*) 57,46 (TP V 4); prince makes beloved drink so much as to be senseless 75,154 (TP VI 175); royal ladies ~ *mattāsava* in palace bar (*āpāna-bhūmi*) 110,126 (TP VIII 91); – see also: *pāna*; vices; wine

drinking-party, see: *pāna-goṣṭhī*

drought of twelve years as brahmin's curse 5,72 (TP I 52)⁴⁴⁷

dr̥ṣṭa-naṣṭa 'no sooner seen than disappeared' said of beloved 119,120 (TP VIII 201)

dr̥ṣṭānta, see: poet

dr̥ṣṭa-prabhāva (not MW) 'visible power > statue' (of Gaṇeśa) 20,55 (TP II 99)

dr̥ṣṭi 'seeing', (as against mortal enjoyments) divine enjoyments give joys that consist only in ~ (*diviṣad-bhogān dr̥ṣṭi-mātrōpabhogadān*) 121,121 (TP IX 20; ORC 1271: "*ils se limitaient à ceux de la vue*"; M II 693: "*Himmelsbewohner, die nur den Augen Wonne spenden*")

dr̥ṣṭi-viṣa 'having poison in the eyes', said of a woman's loving stare by which she kills king like a female snake 33,65 (TP III 111)⁴⁴⁸; – see also: evil eye

ḍṛti 'bag', fool finds ~ of gold 64,28 (TP V 140)

drug to procure a son (*auśadham putra-saṃbhavam*) made from flesh of wild goat (*vanya-cchagalaka*) 39,6f. (TP III 218); ~ (*divyābhiroṣadhi*) to embalm body 45,50 (TP IV 20); stupid bald man with head like copper pot (*tāmra-kumbhōpama-sirāḥi*) believes in ~ producing hair 61,180 (TP V 83); foolish king asks physicians for ~s for his daughter that she may grow up quickly 61,267 (TP V 91); ~ of Mahādevī 66,39 (TP V 181); boy tells hermit where to find ~ 70,75ff. (TP VI 28); – see also: sternutatory

drum⁴⁴⁹ beaten behind (*paścāt prahata-ḍiṇḍima*) robber to be executed 10,171 (TP I 118),

⁴⁴⁶ Perhaps for this purpose wine is asked for for the latter part of the night at 54,200 (TP IV 198).

⁴⁴⁷ Also Daś 218,3; Kuv 117.11-25.

⁴⁴⁸ Stubbe-Diarra 1995: 25.

77,82 (TP VI 189) and 112,166 (TP VIII 119); ~ of rejoicing (*ānanda-ḍundubhi*) 18,48 (TP II 53)⁴⁵⁰; proclamation by ~ (*sa-ṣaṭahaṃ*) in the evening to invite brahmin or *kṣatriya* to sleep with princess 18,321 (TP II 73); ~s of the gods (*deva-ḍundubhi*) sound at coronation of *yuva-rāja* 34,111 (TP III 136); *ḍundubhayah* at royal marriage 34,257 (TP III 148)⁴⁵¹; *deva-ḍundubhi* sounding in unison with the musical instruments (*tūrya*) of the earth 50,206 (TP IV 121); (*udghoṣa-ḍiṇḍima*) beaten to keep away women when king rides out 91,23 (TP VII 67)⁴⁵²; celestial ~s (*divyātodya-*) at a royal wedding 106,31 (TP VIII 30); loud ~ (*bherī*) used to assemble *vidyādhara*s and gods 106,163 (TP VIII 40); on coronation day drums sound like clouds (*ḍundubhi-megha*) 110,84 and *muraḥas* are beaten by *cāraṇas* 86 (TP VIII 88); gods beat their ~s (*ḍundubhi*) at *vidyādhara* king's setting out 116,11 (TP VIII 157); noise of ~s from heaven at birth of prince 120,48 (TP IX 4f.); ~ (*muraḥa*) announcing evening spectacle in temple 123,129 (TP IX 52); 124,8 (TP IX 68); – see also: *abhaya-ḍiṇḍima*; *ānanda-ḍundubhi*; *bherī*; *ḍamaru*; (*deva-ḍundubhi*); executioner; *muraḥa*; musical instruments; *ṣaṭaha*; proclamation drunk, *mahāmātra* of elephants made ~ 13,15 (TP I 151)⁴⁵³; merchant made ~ by four colleagues 13,85 (TP I 156); minister ~ (*pitāsava-mada*) 40,2-5 (TP III 240); ascetic steals magic sword from ~ king 56,222 (TP IV 235); Kali enters Nala's body which is ~ and senseless (*pāna-madena muṣita-smṛtiḥ*) 56,288 (TP IV 241); man made ~ (*kṣibatām nītvā*) questioned 57,8 (TP V 1); ~ man dances and breaks inexhaustible pitcher 57,46 (TP V 4); ~ wife embraces any man pulled up into the house in a basket every night 64,100 and 105 (TP V 147); princess makes servants ~ with wine (*pāna-matteṣu bhṛteṣu*) in order to escape to forest 66,141 (TP V 189); ~ people at *vidyādhara* festival 109,31 (TP VIII 72); – see also: drinking; intoxication
dryad (*vana-śrī*) descends from *karṇī-ratha* 120,117 (TP IX 10); – see also: Dānava maidens; *karṇī-ratha*; *vana-śrī*; tree spirit
duenna, see: chaperon
duhitṛ-sneha (not MW) 'love of daughter' 44,110 (TP IV 8)
duḥkha 'sorrow,' *nirduḥkho nāma kaś cātra saṃsāre jāyate?* "who is born without ~ in this world?" 73,20 (TP VI 102);
duḥkhāgni, see: fire; grief
duḥkha-granthī 'knot of grief', queen sheds tear like ~ 43,245 (TP III 298)

⁴⁴⁹ See e.g., Ghosh 1961: II 18 "drums called Bherī, Ṣaṭaha, Bhambhā, Ḍundubhi and Ḍiṇḍima are merely for very deep and loud sounds" (Nāṭyaśāstra 33,10ff.; Kād 240,3ff.); Sivaramamurti 1956: 147f. Śiva's laugh sounds with the noise of his *ḍundubhi* (Doniger O'Flaherty 1988: 87 quoting BrahmāṇḍaPur I 2,26).

⁴⁵⁰ Such drums occur also in the Arabian Nights, e.g. No 756 (Littmann 1953: V, p. 153). See also Bollée 2010: 107 note 559.

⁴⁵¹ *Ḍundubhīti ḍundubhiḥ ṣaṭahas tadvat gambhīreṇa svareṇa śabdena* (Kādambarī 358,21).

⁴⁵² Music at religious ceremonies is a means of warding off evil influences (Gonda 1969: 56). See also Anderson 2005: 108 note 9. On the reason why women should be invisible see below under: women 91,23 (TP VII 67).

⁴⁵³ Cf. Kurt 1986: 133 on the drinking customs of mahauts in Ceylon.

duḥkhâśani (not MW) ‘thunderbolt of grief’, see: grief

duḥkha-tamo-’ndhas, see: darkness

duṇḍubha, see: snake

duṇḍubhi-megha (not MW), see: drum

dungeon, see: *bhū-grha*

dūrād Ś. playing from afar on her lute 37,64 (TP III 187; ORC 374: “Ś., *venue de loin*”); M I 526: “Ś. *ließ schon von weitem ihre Laute ertönen*”)

dūrāgata ‘come from afar’, of a traveller (*pāntha*) 122,24 (TP IX 35); ~ of a bard (*bandī*) 122,73 (TP IX 39)

durbala (‘weak creature’), when in danger, calls upon parents, king and any deity whatsoever (*yathā-sambhavi daivata*) it is 94,130f. (TP VII 96 “his deity under whose special protection it is”, similar M II 340; ORC 1013: “*toute divinité qui vous vient dans l’esprit*”)

durbar (*āsthāna*)⁴⁵⁴, man of celestial appearance descends from heaven into ~ 44,3 (TP IV 1); king stays continually in harem instead of in ~ 86,7 (TP VII 13)

dur-bhara ‘unbearable’ 112,156 (TP VIII 119 ‘hard to keep’ with note 1: “I think it means that the supposed thief had many costly vices, which he could not gratify without stealing”; ORC 1380: “*difficile à supporter*”; M II 569: “*Räuber, dessen Laster die Menschen nur stönend ertragen*”)

durdina ‘bad weather’, ~ of five days 72,123 (TP VI 78: “storm”);

*Durgā*⁴⁵⁵ (*devī*) sends Kātyāyana dream 2,3 (TP I 9); D. asks Śiva about his delight in skulls and cemeteries 2,9 (TP I 9); ~ to be propitiated with animal sacrifice (*paśūpahāra*) 6,79 (TP I 66); ~ appears to poor brahmin, makes him attain divine nature near her and gives him heavenly seed for a beautiful garden 6,84 (TP I 66); ~ directs Guṇāḍhya in a dream to visit Kāṇabhūti 7,25 (TP I 76); ~ (Caṇḍī; Caṇḍikā) predicts future 11,14 (TP I 123); ~ gives king magic sword 11,38 (TP I 125); empty temple (*śūnyam ... devatā-grham*)⁴⁵⁶ of ~ (Kātyāyanī) 18,158 (TP II 62); ~ in

dream shows hidden treasure near tree 23,39 (TP II 159); Devī Ambikā informs *vidyādhari* dreamer she will get a mortal husband 26,62 (TP II 221); human sacrifice to ~ 26,144 (TP II 227); ~ (Bhagavatī) drinks blood of giant Ruru 26,146 (TP II 228); ~ in dream predicts future 26,148 (TP II 228); ~ in dream commands brothers’ assent for sister’s marriage 26,156 (TP II 228); ~ (Śarvāṇī) descending from heaven and bestowing rank of *vidyādhara* king on brahmin 26,251f. (TP II 236); ~ as deliveress from calamity (*āpad-vimocinī*) 37,43 (TP III 186); feet of ~ (*mahā-devī*) stained with red dye (*pāḍau yāvakāṅkitau*) 37,44 (TP III 186); ~ pronounces in dream fetters of captives loosed 37,48 (TP III 186); ~ identified with Bhavānī and Gaurī 42,57ff. (TP III 263); ~ (*Vindhya-vāsinī*)

⁴⁵⁴ Cf. Kād 133,5 where a king gives an occasional *durbar* out of love for his people: *prajānurāga-hetor antarāntarā darśanaṃ dadau*. – For illustrations see Jackson: 80f. and 85.

⁴⁵⁵ See ORC 1564; www.123durgapuja.com/goddessdurga; Meyer 1937: III 294; Kinsley 1986: 95ff.; Hansen 1992: 23f.

⁴⁵⁶ Is the temple deserted, not used that is, or solitary > isolated > forested ?

in a dream gives sword to prince 42,118 (TP III 267); ~ propitiated revives brother and restores lost sword 42,174 (TP III 271); ~ pleased gives boon to Prabala 45,381 (TP IV 42); ~ orders her votary to be married 50,125 (TP IV 116); son sacrificed to ~ (*Caṇḍikā-devī*) 53,148 (TP IV 178); ~ propitiated and offered head 53,175 (TP IV 180); ~ in dream prophesies poor man to always have one ox 66,103 (TP V 185); ~ Śārikā guards door to Pātāla 73,110 (TP VI 108); ~ festival (*Devī-pūjōtsava*) 80,20 (TP VI 205); with 18 arms 80,27 (TP VI 206); ~ blamed by woman votary for robbing her husband and brother 80,39 (TP VI 207); human sacrifice to ~ on fourteenth day 101,300 (TP VII 155); the face of the black king of the Mātaṅgas is rendered terrible by a three-furrowed frown, and so he appeared as if ~ had marked him with the trident, to claim him as her own 102,72 (TP VII 167f.); queen merits the respect of the best *vidyādhara*s, as if an incarnation of ~ 107,63 (TP VIII 47); – see also: Cāmuṇḍā; Devī; Śarvāṇī

Durgā temple in the Vindhya hills 2,2 (TP I 9)⁴⁵⁷; 3,38 (TP I 21); 6,78 (TP I 66); Guṇāḍhya in dream is directed by goddess in ~ to visit Kāṇabhūti 7,25 (TP I 76); ~ with human sacrifices 10,189 (TP I 119); 18,158 (TP II 62); ~ (*Caṇḍikā-grha*) terrible with banner of red cloth like the tongue of Death eager to devour the animals 22,63 (TP II 141); idem outside Benares 25,86 (TP II 196); 26,143 (TP II 227); empty ~ on the shore of the western sea 69,113 (TP VI 17); ~ in which were offered many living beings and which therefore resembled the palace of the god of Death (*Kṛtānta-sadana*) 72,17 (TP VI 69); *Gaurya-āyatana* 80,23 (TP VI 206); submarine ~ (*Kātyāyanī-devagrha*) 81,45 (TP VI 212)⁴⁵⁸; ~ like the mouth of Death, the flame of the lamp being its lolling tongue, the range of bells (to summon sacrifices, or apotropaeic⁴⁵⁹) being the row of teeth, to which the heads of men hung 101,301 (TP VII 155); 108,23 (TP VIII 54); despondent man goes to ~, to propitiate the goddess with asceticism 108,84 (TP VIII 60); – see also: Caṇḍī; teeth

Durga-piśāca, king of Mātaṅgas, description of ~ 102,71ff. (TP VII 167)

-*durgraha* ‘demon, evil spirit’, see: demon; *puruṣa-dveṣa-durgraha*

dūrva,⁴⁶⁰ dewdrops on the points of ~ blades sparkle like pearls fallen from the necklace of the night 103,213 (TP VII 189)

Durvāsas, deceptive hermit 16,36 (TP II 23)

dust, clouds of ~ (*rajo-rāśī*) from army 14,13 (TP I 182)⁴⁶¹; *apsaras*’ feet do not touch ~ 28,61 (TP III 24); body of nymph yellow with ~ of flowers 35,12 (TP III 156); ~ (*dhūli*) thrown into man’s face turns him into buffalo 68,44f. (TP VI 5)⁴⁶²; ascetic clears ~ from

⁴⁵⁷ Also Daś 276.9; Kād (Pūrva-bhāga) § 215f.

⁴⁵⁸ In 81,75 it is a temple of Pārvatī.

⁴⁵⁹ Bollée 2005: 37 note 201.

⁴⁶⁰ *Cynodon dactylon* Linn., a ritual herb associated with Gaṇeśa, Viṣṇu and Śiva, see Gonda 1985: 108ff. Its connection with Gaṇeśa mentioned by ORC 1564 is not found on p. 1083; for this see Gaṇeśa-Pur. ed Bailey I 620 and II 672.

⁴⁶¹ Cf. Smith 2006: 80 where the dust raised by an army is said by Bāṇa (*Kād* 115,5-8) to be gray like the belly of an old *śaphara* fish, like a camel’s mane, etc. Smith praises Bāṇa’s exceptional powers of realistic description.

water of Nāga king's palace with enchanted mustard-seeds 70,67 (TP VI 29); ~ is gambler's bed 73,77 (TP VI 106); ~ carrying spell thrown on ashes of dead child to raise it 76,22 (TP VI 180); footsteps of women in ~ 98,25 (TP VII 117); – ~ thrown on molten copper to turn it into gold, see: alchemy; – see also: wings of mountains dustless (*nīrdhūli*), feet of *apsaras* 28,61 (TP III 24); ~ *vidyādhara* 33,178 (TP III 122) duty¹ of a brahmin to preside at a *śrāddha* (*dāpayāmi te trayodaśī-śrāddhaṃ*) 5,112 (TP I 56); ~ (*niyoga*) of a *devadāsī* to the temple (*sura-kula*) 12,80 (TP I 139); necessary duties (*āvaśya-kārya*) of a king 34,191 (TP III 142) and 59,1 (TP V 26) duty² (*śulka*), merchants avoid ~ by using secret path 29,105 (TP III 46) *dvairājya-yukti* (?) 'embalmed by means of drugs (?) and ghee', said of body 45,127 (TP IV 26; ORC 474: "à l'aide de beurre clarifié" omitting the difficulty; M I 657: "unter Anwendung von Arzneien, Salben und Ölen"); – see also: body *dvandva-yuddha*, see: combat Dvāpara enters body of Puṣkara, Nala's brother 56,293 (TP IV 241) Dvāravatī in mid-sea, city of Aniruddha 31,24f. (TP III 83); -*dvīpa* 'elephant' as a kind of collective or intensive suffix, see *smara*-° and cf. -*hastin* *dvy-ahena dvy-ahena* 'every couple of days' 122,21 (TP IX 35) dwelling (*sadana*) of Bhīllas with high walls covered with elephant tusks (*danti-danta-citōttuṅga-bhitti*) and decorated with tiger-skins (*vyāghra-cchada-cchavi*) 123,49 (TP IX 46)⁴⁶³ dying one after another, of couple, but revived by family goddess Caṇḍī 111,44 (TP VIII 99) dying together,⁴⁶⁴ of seven princesses 28,43 (TP III 23); ~ of robbed merchant and his wife 69,128 (TP VI 18); brahmin couple commits suicide by poison 72,214 (TP VI 84); royal couple wants ~ 101,352 (TP VII 158); – further see: four *vidyādhara* princesses; *mahā-patha*; merchant; suicide *dyu-cara-viṣṭi* 'Vidyādhara slave', Naravāhanadatta orders *Vidyādhara* prince to send ~s as carriers of gold, etc. to king of Vatsa 110,142 (TP VIII 93) *dyūta-līlā* (not MW) 'gambling, play at dice', goddess Śrī is ever treacherous as ~ 62,164 (TP V 113) *dyūta-sthiti* (not MW) 'gambling rules' 121,97 (TP IX 18) *dyu-vadhū* 'heavenly woman, *apsaras*', sun as centre-jewel of the girdle of the ~ 81,17 (TP VI

⁴⁶² Dust as a magical article is also used by Indra when turning Kutsa into a Malla (JaimBr 3.199ff.). For the motif see TP I 25ff.

⁴⁶³ Cf. Yogavasiṣṭha (Mokṣōpaya) V 48.4 in the context of a description of a village of *sva-pacas* "these garlands made of tusks of dead elephants and placed on the wall are found even today just as the peaks of Mt Meru in every aeon" (*imās tā mṛta-mataṅga-danta-mālā vṛtau kṛtāḥ daṇḍa adyāpi saṃsthitāḥ kalpaṃ prati Meru-śikhā iva*) and Akam 172 in Varadaraja Iyer 1945: 23 "The hill-man of the Kurava ... directs the unerring missile or arrow on the elephant's chest, plucks the tusks of the elephant and plants them as a sort of fencing to his small abode" (p. c. Straube).

⁴⁶⁴ See, e.g. Gibbs 2009.

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dyu-yoṣit = prec. (Menakā) 14,77 (TP I 188)

ear, speech that pierces the ~ like a poisoned needle (*viṣa-sūcikā*) 1,37 (TP I 4); open ~ of listener as entrance for Kāma 3,59 (TP I 23); root of king's ~ reached by old age⁴⁶⁵ 10,216 (TP I 121); a woman's eager eye, expanded with desire to see the king, comes to the side of her ~ 18,15 (TP II 50); white ~s of elephant 19,68 (TP II 90); pouring nectar into ~ 25,224 (TP II 208); centipede enters ~ of king 29,136 (TP III 49); cardinal points are Viṣṇu's ~s 54,33 (TP IV 186)⁴⁶⁶; Gaṇeśa's ~s see: *śūrpa-karṇa*; ~s of donkey wanted by wounded lion 63,130 (TP V 130); promise of money as short-lived pleasure to the ~s (*śruti-sukha*) 63,161 (TP V 133); lovers first enter another's minds by the ~s,⁴⁶⁷ then by their eyes 65,248 (TP V 173); princess puts lotus in her ~ as a sign to prince 75,73 (TP VI 169f.); ~s filled with nectar of speech (*vāk-sudhayā pūrṇa-sva-śravaṇôdara*) 89,49 (TP VII 43)⁴⁶⁸; syllables of a name as nectar for the ~s 94,31 (TP VII 89); *vetāla* with ~s of ass 102,19 (TP VII 163); news, terrible to the ears (*śrotra-dāruṇa*) 104,64 (TP VIII 5); ~s as winnowing baskets⁴⁶⁹ (*śūrpa-karṇa-puta*) as mark of male ugliness 123,164 (TP IX 55); – see also: Coda-karṇa

ear-lotus, see: lotus (121,128 [TP IX 21])⁴⁷⁰

ear-nectar-distilling syllables of lady's name (*śrotrāmṛta-syandīny asyā nāmākṣarāṇi*) 94,31 (TP VII 89)

ear-ornament of the earth, see: Kauśāmbī; adulterous merchant-wife of prince looses richly studded ~ (*san-muktâdhyam vibhūṣaṇam*)⁴⁷¹ 18,82 (TP II 131); moon as ~ (*karṇa-pūra*)⁴⁷² on the dark eastern quarter 72,26f. (TP VI 70); – see also: *danta-patra*; eastern quarter earring lost by adulterous woman and found by husband 21,84 (TP II 131);

ears and nose of wicked Buddhist nun cut off 13,160 (TP I 161); adulterous wife cuts off ~ of husband 58,99 (TP V 22)⁴⁷³; ~ of adulterous woman cut off 77,87 (TP VI 189)⁴⁷⁴;

⁴⁶⁵ Cf. Suttanipāta 1120 *jīṇṇo 'ham asmi savaṇaṃ na phāsu*.

⁴⁶⁶ See also Bollée 2010b (Svasti): 143.

⁴⁶⁷ See Bollée 2010b: 151.

⁴⁶⁸ Accordingly, Daś 184,2 speaks of drinking with the ears (*karṇābhyāṃ pātum*).

⁴⁶⁹ Cf. Bollée 2010b 145.

⁴⁷⁰ In Punjab it is believed that this protects from fairies (OTI F 384.4).

⁴⁷¹ For an example see Jackson 2010: 151.

⁴⁷² Cf. Esposito 2004: 269 note 176.

⁴⁷³ STh Q 451.6ff.

⁴⁷⁴ Cf. Bollée 2010b: 157.

earth, as wife of king Arjuna 9,8 (TP I 95); 53,115 (TP IV 175); 78,43 (TP VI 194); prince gives his father the ~ (*medinī*) as tribute from conquered kings and then remembers his pre-birth 42,196 (TP III 274); ~ bent under the weight of dancing Gaṇeśa 51,1 (TP IV 122); ~ as goddess appears and carries Sītā over lake Tīṭibhī 51,82 (TP IV 127); woman wailing about the predestined death of the king says she is the ~ 53,114 (TP IV 175); ~ with four seas 69,181 (TP VI 22)⁴⁷⁵; ~ as bride (*vasudhā-vadhu*) the garland around whose head is the city of Trigartā 73,21 (TP VI 102); ~ goddess weeping in tank at night 78,43 (TP VI 194); Hari saved the ~ and bore it in his arm 93,4 (TP VII 78); ~ worships dancing Gaṇeśa 100,44 (TP VII 131); ~ full of wonders (*bahu-kautukā*) 120,10 (TP IX 2); – see also: scratching

Earth goddess, see: Bhū; Pṛthivī

earthquake (*utpāta*), conquered by snake-subduing spell 70, 67 (TP VI 29)

East, turning to the ~ (*prāṇmukha*) before swearing 16,117 (TP II 30); subduing ~ first before ascending throne 18,56 (TP II 53), because Indra presides over the ~ 18,60 (TP II 54);

east door (*pūrva-dig-dvāra*) principal palace entrance 38,21 (TP III 207);

eastern mountain (*udayādri*), moon ascends ~ 84,42 (TP VII 7); 103,204 (TP VII 189)

eastern ocean, beyond ~ (*pāre pūrvāmbudhe*) and River Taraṅgiṇī is death-free space 72,336 (TP VI 94);

eastern quarter, moon as ear-ornament on dark ~ 72,27 (TP VI 70); ~ adorns its face with the rising moon as with a *tilaka* 74,187 (TP VI 154); nymph of ~ (*pūrva-dig-aṅganā*) laughs touched by the moon's fingers/rays (*karākrāntā*) 84,42 (TP VII 7); ~ bears a laughing face to which the moon forms an extemporised ear-ornament 103,205 (TP VII 189); moon looks like face-ornament of nymph of ~ (*prāci-dig-vadhū-mukha-maṇḍana*) 106,50 (TP VIII 32); queen becomes pregnant like the ~ (*prāci*) in the morning when the sun is about to rise 120,44 (TP IX 4); – see also: ear-ornament

eating⁴⁷⁶ at convenient time by Buddhists 27,19 (TP III 2); brahmins ~ cow 9,118 (TP III 9f.); king refuses to eat unless brahmin dances 49,15 (TP IV 86); man always ~ outward 61,220 (TP V 87); hunger satisfied by ~ seventh cake 62,205 (TP V 116); false ascetic teaches ~ at night⁴⁷⁷ (*nakta-bhojiva-vādin*) 69,67 (TP VI 13); ~ charmed barley-meal turns witch into goat 71,273 (TP VI 56); wives eat after divine husband 73,14 (TP VI 101); *vidyādhara* king ~ only in presence of beloved daughter 86,131 (TP VII 22)⁴⁷⁸; Gaṇeśa in tree curses men ~ the fruits without having rinsed their mouth or washed their hands and feet (*an-ācāntā a-kṣālita-karāṅghrayaḥ*) to become fruits themselves 100,38 (TP VII 131); after ~ two grains of rice from vessel in which child was cooked Marubbhūti spits gold 108,77 (TP VIII 59); brahmins, desperate at being ordered to ~ food of a *caṇḍāla*, perform *tapas* in shrine of Mahākāla 112,180 (TP VIII 120); man ~ gourd is changed into python 123,32

⁴⁷⁵ Lüders 1951: 95.

⁴⁷⁶ Syed 2000.

⁴⁷⁷ See Balbir 1987-8.

⁴⁷⁸ From Vedic times onward women eat apart from men (ŚpBr 1,9,2,9).

(TP IX 45); ~ air = living on air (q.v.) only; – see also: barley-meal; cannibalism; iron eclipse of sun (*sūryôparāga*) permits king to give presents 54,156ff. (TP IV 195); economic refugee 61,252 (TP V 90); 61,303 (TP V 95); egg becomes Pumān and Creator (Sṛṣṭar) 2,11 (TP I 9); Hari-Viṣṇu’s stomach (*jaṭhara*) is ~⁴⁷⁹ of Brahmā 54,33 (TP IV 186); sea carries off ~ of *ṭiṭṭibha* 60,189 (TP V 57); Jīmūta vāhana’s generosity inscribed on wall of Brahma’s ~ 90,192 (TP VII 62); – see also: blood of Śiva

egotism (*ahaṅkāra*) is obstacle in road to knowledge 5,137 (TP I 58)

eight births, sorrows / labours of ~ (*janma-duḥkha*) endured in one birth 52,397 (TP IV 165); eight cakes (*pūpaka*) for one *paṇa* 62,204 (TP V 116)⁴⁸⁰

eight days, reaching the isle of Muktapura from Putrapura on the sea shore in ~ 51,175 (TP IV 134)

eight doors of Kailāsa⁴⁸¹ 50,171ff. (TP IV 119)

eighteen, arms of Devī 80,27 (TP VI 206); ~ thousand brahmins ordered to eat in house of *Mātāṅga* 112,176-179 (TP VIII 120);

eighth century, king in his ~ of age 41,33 (TP III 254)

eighth day of month, temple visit on ~ 7,71 (TP I 82); ~ of black fortnight of Phālguna, a high day (*mahā-tīthi*) 46,51 (TP IV 52); buffalo eaten on ~ of lunar month 62,219 (TP V 118); on ~ *bhikṣu* vanquishes king in dispute 72,97 (TP VI 76); on ~ robbers (*caurāḥ*) worship Senānī (Durgā) 114,115 (TP VIII 141);

eighth door in Mt Kailāsa opens to Śambhu-Śiva’s abode 50,187 (TP IV 119)

eight hundred years living⁴⁸² in hermitage 25,20 (TP II 189); chariot with pneumatic contrivance (*vāta-yantra-vimānam*) going ~ *yojanas* 43,38 (TP III 283);

eight leaves of lotus (*kamalaṃ sâṣṭa-pallavam*) 71,215 (TP VI 51);

eight limbs, prostration with ~ (*praṇāmam aṣṭābhir aṅgaiḥ*) 98,69 (TP VII 120f.) = 99,15 (TP VII 123)

eight months in *bhū-grha* to remove old age 40,49 (TP III 244);

eight special forms of ether, &c. (*vyomâdi-bheda-bhinnâṣṭa-mūrti*) which Śiva assumes 35,99 (TP III 163)

eight thousand names of Śiva 46,202 (TP IV 62)

eight years of austerities to propitiate Hara, two princesses practise ~ in vain and want to enter the fire 118,132 (TP VIII 187)

eighty thousand princesses, Viṣṇu tells king devotee he shall obtain ~ 36,18 (TP III 170); ~ unchaste 36,34 (TP III 171);

ejection of king from throne, see: forest

eka-bhikṣā-vrata, see: single alms-offering, vow of ~

⁴⁷⁹ “Egg” means origin here.

⁴⁸⁰ Avadāna 66 (Penzer).

⁴⁸¹ This may pertain to Śiva as *aṣṭa-mūrti*.

⁴⁸² For numerical exaggeration see Lüders 1940: 442.

ekādaśa-mārikā ‘woman who killed eleven husbands’ 66,97 (TP V 185)

eka-śruta-dhara, see: remembering

ekātapatra, see: umbrella

*eka-veṇī*⁴⁸³ ‘single-plait braid’ (Hiltebeitel), woman vows husband should loose her ~ only at the death of her abductor 106,77 (TP VIII 34) and 113f. (TP VIII 36)

elā (Cardamom) tree⁴⁸⁴ 111,15 (TP VIII 96)

elements,⁴⁸⁵ four ~ (earth, water, thorns and fire) thrown at pursuer to stop him 39,131 (TP III 227)

elephant(s),⁴⁸⁶ wild ~ overpowered by lute music 11,4 (TP I 122)⁴⁸⁷; kings fallen into vices are easily captured by enemies even as ~ caught in a pit 11,25 (TP I 124); mechanical ~ (*yantra-hastin*) as Trojan horse 12,4 (TP I 133)⁴⁸⁸; Lohajāṅgha creeps into carcass of ~⁴⁸⁹ 12,109 (TP I 141); ~ (*gaja*) in sea as Garuḍa’s food 12,140 (TP I 144); king gives daughter fast female ~ 13,6 (TP I 150); ~ presented as royal tribute (*kari-kṛta*) 19,114 (TP II 94); hunting Himālaya ~s for pearls⁴⁹⁰ in their heads 22,76 (TP II 142); king mounts ~ as lion ascends mountain⁴⁹¹ 19,63 (TP II 89); ~s compared to Vindhya peaks 19,93 (TP II 92)⁴⁹²; ~ beating horses 19,109 (TP II 93); brahmin saves merchant bride from ~ 27,173ff.

(TP III 14f.); woman falsely asserts pain in her limbs produced by falling down in her terror at an ~ (*hasti-bhaya-bhraṣṭa-bhaṅgāṅga-janitām rujam*) 27,186 (TP III 15)⁴⁹³; prince ascends ~ of victory (*jaya-kuñjara*) 34,125 (TP III 137); Viṣṇu promises king a flying white ~ and eighty thousand princesses 36,13-18 (TP III 170); *Gandharva* cursed to become white ~ 36,13 (TP III 170); white ~ able to fly 36,14 (TP III 170)⁴⁹⁴; idem attacked by Garuḍa 36,24 and to be saved only by faithful wife 30 (TP III 170f.); ~ able to

⁴⁸³ See ‘hair-style’ infra; further: Hiltebeitel 1980-1: 198 < Rāmāyaṇa 5,18,8 et passim and parallels from Kālī-dāsa; do, 1981: 184-86; Thieme 1971: 287 note; Bollée 1970: 98. – Olivelle in Hiltebeitel and Miller 1998: 17 states two prominent cases of the reverse where the hair is left loose until a vow of vengeance has been fulfilled: of Draupadī in Mbh and of Cāṇakya in Mudrarākṣasa Act I, vs 9.

⁴⁸⁴ Kuv note 119.

⁴⁸⁵ See Böhme 2004.

⁴⁸⁶ See ORC 1565; Smith 2006: 82f. quoting Bāṇa’s *Kād* 87,10–88,1.

⁴⁸⁷ For a (tame) elephant listening to music see Bāṇa, *Kād* 87,10.

⁴⁸⁸ See Alsdorf 1974: 395.

⁴⁸⁹ In this way also boars and crocodiles open an access to the inside of a dead elephant for the entrails they eat first (Kurt 1986: 201).

⁴⁹⁰ See also below under: pearls.

⁴⁹¹ Elephants are often hyperbolically likened to mountains as in Naḍāgiri, ‘Mountain of reed’ a proper name, 11,42 (TP I 125; Jackmuth 151; 196ff.), but see Edgerton 1931: 3f. where he states that in a comparison with a king a *giri-cara* is not a ‘mountain-ranging’ elephant (Śakuntalā II 4), but a particular species.

⁴⁹² Cf. Meghadūta I 19.

⁴⁹³ PWB did not understand *bhaṅga* in this compound.

⁴⁹⁴ For the motif of the flying elephant see STh B 45.

fly through the air 36,50 (TP III 173); ship whirled around like head of *mast* ~⁴⁹⁵ before sinking 36,82 (TP III 175); cursed ~ turns into divine man (*Gandharva*) 36,111 (TP III 177); white ~ as toy 36,120 (TP III 177); female ~ flings monkey into mud of ant-hill 37,132 (TP III 192); bleeding ~ resembles mount of collyrium with streams of cinnabar 51,169 (TP IV 134); woman drops from house top on king's lap on his ~ 52,354 (TP IV 162); ~ of female disdain (*mānini-māna-mātaṅga*)⁴⁹⁶ 55,107 (TP IV 209); king tramples on bandits as ~ tramples beds of white water-lilies (*kamalinīr*) 58,114 (TP V 23)⁴⁹⁷; ~ herd kills hares at lake 62,31 (TP V 101); ~ chooses part-Bodhisattva incarnation as king 65,25f. (TP V 155 and 175ff.); princess mounts white ~ in dream 66,161 (TP V 190); race between she-~ and horses 67,8ff. (TP V 196f.); hermit's pupils extricate ~ couple out of mud 68,27 (TP VI 3); ~ dies bitten in ear by snake 69,70 (TP VI 13); ~ addressing *vyaktayā girā* and caring for blind man in forest 74,5f. (TP VI 141); unnoticed hermit Uttanka curses king to become an ~ 74,307 (TP VI 162); ~ released from curse becomes *Gandharva* again 74,315 (TP VI 163); must ~ (*matta-hasī*) is rushing about, trampling men to death⁴⁹⁸ 75, 117 (TP VI 172); maiden resembles lake for ~ of youth (*yauvana-dvir-ada*) to plunge in in sport 84,8 (TP VII 5); ~ driven furious by smell of other ~ 89,14 (TP VII 41); brahmin saves princess from must ~ 89,17 (TP VII 41); big ~ likened to black cloud out of season 89,42 (TP VII 43)⁴⁹⁹; ~s uncontrollable (lit.: 'without hook', *niraṅkuśa*) 91,54 (TP VII 70); ~ of valour (*śaurya-kariṇ*) 94,6 (TP VII 87); ~s' tusks and deer-skins (*danti-dantājina*) in Bhilla villages 102,42 (TP VII 165; ORC 1064: "où s'accumulèrent les défenses et les peaux d'éléphants"); pearls from the frontal lobes of ~ 103,6 (TP VII 175) and 116,65 (TP VIII 161); ~ of eastern mountain (*udayācala-vāraṇa*) 103,204 (TP VII 189); man saves beloved maiden from wild ~ (*vanyēbha*, 101) and then looses her out of sight 104,106 (TP VIII 9); ~ of beauty (*saundarya-dantin*) 104,179 (TP VIII 14); wild ~ tamed by *caṅḍāla* maiden who then makes a swing with her upper garment fastened to the tusks 112,63-70 (TP VIII 110f.)⁵⁰⁰; princess attacked by ~ and saved by *caṅḍāla* who kills it 112,90 f. TP VIII 113); crown-prince gives away state ~ 113,41 (TP VIII 127)⁵⁰¹; *mahā-gaja* scatters other ~s by his smell (*gandha-bhagnānya-vāraṇa*) 113,44 (TP VIII 127)⁵⁰²; ~ with four tusks descends from heaven with Lakṣmī 113,91 (TP VIII

⁴⁹⁵ Kurt declares that the meaning of this behaviour is unknown to him (Kurt 1986: 136).

⁴⁹⁶ *Mataṅga* has here the function of an augmantative suffix indicating the degree of disdain. Similarly *Śrī-gaja* points to the greatness of Śrī, is a *karmadhāraya* compound and does not mean the 'elephant of Śrī' (Zimmer 1976: 42).

⁴⁹⁷ Cf. Rājāt 3,284f. and 527.

⁴⁹⁸ On the dangerousness of must bulls see Kurt 1986: 129ff.

⁴⁹⁹ In the Vessantara jātaḥ (Ja VI 487,16) the white elephant produces rain and in Thailand one of the epithets of a white elephants is "rain maker" (Wales 1971: 284).

⁵⁰⁰ Cf. BKŚS 3,14ff.

⁵⁰¹ Cf. Ja VI 488,10*ff.; Osier 2010: 109f.

⁵⁰² See McHugh 2012: 83ff.

130); Śakra gives two air-going (*vyoma-cara*) ~s to king Merudhvaja 118,24 (TP VIII 179); ~ of love (*smara-dvipa*) 118,164 (TP VIII 189); ~ of monsoon with loud thunder-roar and long *ketaka* tusks comes down on forest of heats (*grīṣma-vanam ... prāvṛṭ-kāla-mada-dvipaḥ*) 122,65f. (TP IX 38f.); human couple emerges from belly of wild ~ (*vana-dvipa*) when killed 123,90 (TP IX 49); ~ killed and touched on the back becomes celestial shield 123,96f. (TP IX 50); woman sleeping on palace roof swallowed (*nigīrya*) by ~ 123,99 (TP IX 50); confusion produced by a charge of wild ~s (*vanyēbhāpāta-sambhrama*) 123,276 (TP IX 62); – see also: cloud(s); she-elephant.
 elephant-catching (*gaja-bandha*) as royal passion 12,6 (TP I 133)⁵⁰³
 elephant-driver, see: bribe; mahout
 elephant of love, fierce ~ (*madana-vyāla-gaja*) 37,98 (TP III 190); idem (*kāma-kariṇ*) 38,116 (TP III 214); do, broad hips with girdles look like head of ~ adorned with a girdle of constellations (*nakṣatra-mālāṅkam iva smara-dvipa-śiraḥ-sthalam*) 118,164 (TP VIII 189);
 elephant of winter (*hemanta-hastin*) slain by lion of spring 91,20f. (TP VII 67);
 elephant's skin (*hasti-carma*) contracts due to shower 12,110f. (TP I 141); ~ (*kuñjara-carma*) of Śiva⁵⁰⁴, his moon and bull won at play by Devī 121,99 (TP IX 19)
 elephants of the quarters (*dṛg-dantin*), Hara-Śiva places ~ as guardians at cave-passage to north side of Mt Kailāsa 109,69 (TP VIII 75)
 eleven, woman whose ~ husbands died (*ekādaśa-mārikā*) 66,97 (TP V 184f.)⁵⁰⁵; after ~ years waiting for Rājput husband serving abroad wife sends him letter with *āryā* 124,56 (TP IX 72);
 eleventh day, on morning of ~ door of heaven is opened for Gaṇas to enter 12,167 (TP I 146); starting journey on ~ 51,190 (TP IV 135)
 elixir (*rasāyana*) given to king against old age 41,33 (TP III 254); ~ hardens Nāgārjuna's neck so much that it cannot be struck 41,45 (TP III 255); – see also: (water of) immortality
 ellipsis, see sun (91,57 (TP VII 70)
 eloping, with her saviour, of married woman saved from an elephant 27,180f. (TP III 15); married princess with paramour 89,99 (TP VII 47)
 emaciation and pining away of princess with longing compared to state like streak of moon during the wane (*kṛṣṇa-pakṣēndu-lekhēva*) 71,94 (TP VI 42)
 emancipation⁵⁰⁶ (*mokṣa*), Indra does not long for ~ 45,81 (TP IV 22); ~ (*sad-gati*) possible even as a prostitute (*śuddha-saṃkalpa*) 69,166 (TP VI 21); ~ of creatures by propitiating Śiva (*īśvarārādhanād vimucyante*) 70,119 (TP VI 32); that moment⁵⁰⁷ hermit attained ~

⁵⁰³ Cf. Strabo, *Geography* XV 1,42. – A modern example is the Spanish king Juan Carlos who in consequence of his safari lost his title of honorary president of the World Wildlife Fund on July 21, 2012.

⁵⁰⁴ Meghadūta 36 (as Assier de Pompignan in his edition [Paris, 1938] has no list of abbreviations, the reference to LB is unclear to me); for an illustration see Keilhauer 1983: 158.

⁵⁰⁵ STh Z 71.7.

⁵⁰⁶ A modern description of this experience is given by Suzanne Segal 1996. See further Dikshit 1973 (Nisargadatta is a 20th century Indian Vedānta exponent who very clearly explains the feeling of *jīvan-mukti*); Balsekar 1990, ch. 17 end, and p. 67, ch. 56, p. 163.

(*siddhi*) by *māhātmya* 72,276 (TP VI 89); merchant-hermit makes king and citizens obtain salvation by teaching them knowledge (*cakre jñānōpadeśena sa-pauram mukti-bhāginam*) (obtained from Bodhisattva) 72,317 (TP VI 92); Vārāṇasī bestows ~ 114,18 (TP VIII 133); – see also: *param jyotiḥ; siddhi*

embalming (*ā √ lip*), see: body; *dvairājya-yukti*

embracing, see: gesture; *vīci-vellad-bhuja-latā*; wave

embryo removed by *yakṣi* mother to be eaten by brahmin father is to become *vidyādhara* 26,225f. (TP II 234); ~ removed turns into sword 26,260f. (TP II 236)

emerald, dish (*pātram garuḍa-māṇikyamayam*), found under fig tree, reveals the past 23,41 (TP II 159f.); ~ throne (*marakatāsana*) of princess 72,78 (TP VI 75)

emigration of brahmin men caused by famine (leaving their wives) 3,11f. (TP I 19); do, taking their wives with them 25,80 (TP II 196); brahmin emigrates after buying off assassins 3,42 (TP I 22); relations oppose brahmin's ~ on account of insulting treatment by king (*rājāvamānena*) 20,21 (TP II 96); ~ due to poverty 61,303 (TP V 95); due to drought and famine brahmins move from Kāśī into the Karimaṇḍita forest 70,40f. (TP VI 27); ~ out of shame of poverty (*daurgatya-lajjā*) 77,19 (TP VI 184);

emotion, see: anger; compassion; desillusion; feeling; grief; illusion; joy; laughing; love; tears

emperor Naravāhanadatta created by Bharga-Śiva 24,5 (TP II 170); ~ of *vidyādhara*s crowned 50,205 (TP IV 121)

empty temple, dead brahmin in ~ 4,102 (TP I 38); ~ of Kātyāyanī-Durgā, mendicant enters ~ 18,158 (TP II 62); two men in ~ (*surālaya*) 27,152 (TP III 12); ~ of Śiva where *yakṣiṇī* devours visitors 37,58 (TP III 187); ~ of Śiva with *rākṣasa* 39,126 (TP III 227); hermit worships Śiva in ~ 62,208 (TP V 86); ~ of Durgā on the shore of the western sea 69,113 (TP VI 17); ~ of Śiva with one *liṅga* (*śūnyāika-liṅga ... Śivālaya*) 71,212 (TP VI 51); ~ of Śiva in forest 92,26 (TP VII 73); man recovered from river Veṇā seeks refuge in nearby ~ of the Mātaras 123,207 (TP IX 58); – see also: Caṇḍī

enchanter (*mantra-vādin*) described 73,283 (TP VI 121);

enchantment, see: *Indra-jāla; maṇḍala*

end of KSS should be with ch. 110 (TP VIII 93 note 2)

endurance, horse of ~ see: *dhairya*; horse

enemies, weak and pale ~ treated as clouds by autumn 19,94 (TP II 92); ~ (fleeing) like deer 27,138 (TP III 11); four internal ~ of king: love, anger, (avarice and delusion)⁵⁰⁸ 34,191 (TP III 142); ~ trampled as an elephant tramples bed of water-lilies 58,114 (TP V 23); enemy turned into friend 16,69 (TP II 26)⁵⁰⁹

⁵⁰⁷ Enlightenment – being intuitive understanding – is instantaneous insight (Klein 1991): 179; Balsekar 1982: 39 “some – though very few – see truth in a flash”; 67 “Awakening is nothing other than apperceiving – (a) that the seed of all manifestation is the impersonal consciousness, (b) that what is being sought is the unmanifested aspect of manifestation and (c) that, therefore, the seeker is the sought”; Balsekar 1989 on Aṣṭāvakraḡitā 4. Cf. for the immediately obtained knowledge of Kṛṣṇa Bhag XVIII 55. and *śānti* idem XII 12. “He who intuitively realizes that all we perceive is only the Self ... becomes Brahman indeed” (Śāṅkara ad Bhag XIII 30 in Sastry 1981: 373).

⁵⁰⁸ In the Mbh also only two enemies are mentioned, with “etc.” TP supplies the other two without giving a source.

enfant prodige, see: infant prodigy

enmity continues in birth after birth 23,47 (TP II 160); tree of ~ 42,77 (TP III 274); gods and *Asuras* renounce ~ 50,97 (TP IV 114)

entering, magician (*yoga-siddhimān*) ~ body of dead king 4,99ff. (TP I 37f.)⁵¹⁰; ~ forbidden place out of curiosity 26,75 (TP II 222); sciences in the shape of women ~ crown-prince 34,156 (TP III 139); not forgetting relatives when ~ another's body out of one's own free will 45,56 (TP IV 21); art of ~ another's body (*dehāntrāveśa*) 45,79 (TP IV 22; IV 46); *Dvāpara* ~ *Puškara*'s body 56,293 (TP IV 241); *Kali*, a black man, enters *Nala*'s body out of jealousy 56,384 (TP IV 248); magician abandons his old body and enters body of brahmin boy on pyre who then rises up with a yawn 97,34f. (TP VII 114); *Gandharva* king enters his city in triumph (*sphūrjad-utsava*) 117,1 (TP VIII 164); – *nāgī* aunt enters body of king, see: aunt; body; – ~ the fire, see: *agni-praveśa*; – see also: *bhakti*; brains; bridegroom; cellar; ceremony; conception; curiosity; death; dream; flame; forgetting; gesture; hanging; *Indra*; *Kālarātri*; king(dom); magic power; magician; *maṅgala*; *Maya*; moon; *nidāna*; picture gallery; *rākṣasī*; remembering; self-immolation; snake; suicide; *vahni-kunḍa*; weeping; woman

entrails, witch wife sucks husbands ~ and then replaces them 32,156f. (TP III 102); ~ of goat as garland around *Śiva*'s *liṅga* 71,213 (TP VI 51); *brahma-rākṣasa* makes himself wreath of ~ (*antra-mālā-kṛta*) 94,69 (TP VII 91); – see also: vampire

entrapped suitors motif ch. 4 (TP I 42ff.)

entry into many bodies, see: bilocality; body; division of personality

envoy, see: messenger

envy, brahmin's ~ of householders' wealth makes him propitiate *Śrī* who punishes him with death for offering in the fire with impure passion (*amarṣa-kaluṣa*) 10,10ff. (TP I 106)⁵¹¹; ~ of relations because of wealth 22,37 (TP II 139); ~ (*īrṣā*) as one of five faults of king compared to fires 28,32 (TP III 22); out of ~ a prince wants to have his merchant friend executed 28,144 (TP III 31); – see also: fire; jealousy; pupil(s)

epsur is wrong (TP IV 214 note 1 on 55,173), but *sa-viśeṣa-prasādēpṣur* is *-prasāda + īpṣur* 'desirous of showing (him) a special favour'

equality of birth, see: birth

error(s), see: *iva*; *mukta*; *m/ya*; transgression

escaping one's fate motif⁵¹² 53,125 (TP IV 176); 66,108 (TP V 186 note 1); 72,319ff. (TP VI 92 note 2);

escort given by father-in-law 51,191 (TP IV 135); 93,74 (TP VII 83); ~ by hermits to *Kaṇva*'s daughter up to the end of the hermitage 94,49 (TP VII 90); son gives father long ~ (*dūrānugata*) 110,145 (TP VIII 93);

⁵⁰⁹ Cf. STh *J 218.

⁵¹⁰ See Bloomfield 1971.

⁵¹¹ STh Q 302.

⁵¹² See Brown 1920.

ether, see: *vyoman*

ethnic catalogue of Indian women (Karnāta, Lāṭa, Saurāṣṭra and Madhyadeśa) as possible spouses of kings 47,106 (TP IV 73)⁵¹³

etiquette towards visitor: rising to meet guest 12,88 (TP I 139); 28,108f. (TP III 28)⁵¹⁴;

honouring guest by making him walk in front of host 67,18 (TP V 197); – see also: *arghya*;
frontier; gesture(s); given with own hand; hospitality

etymology of Kandarpa 20,64 (TP II 100); ~ of Sulocanā 28,73 (TP III 25); ~ of Udayana 30,54 (TP III 67)

eulogy, of king (q.v.)

eunuch (*na-puṃsaka*; *ṣaṇḍha*), princess married to ~ 56,86f. (TP IV 226)

evening, proclamation by drum in the ~ to invite people to sleep with princess 18,321 (TP II 73); words used at ~ oblation to Agni taught by *yakṣa* 20,36 (TP II 97); do, with human flesh left by jackals on charnel ground 25,135 (TP II 201); heaven becomes red, when ~ (*saṃdhyā*) sets her footprints there 47,91 (TP IV 72); ~ dance of demons (*bhūta*) with corpses 47,92 (TP IV 72); groom arrives in the ~ (*sāyam*) for wedding 71,156 (TP VI 47); lover visits beloved in the evening (*pradoṣa-samaye*) 74,230 (TP VI 157); peaks of Kailāsa reddened with ~ light (*saṃdhyāruṇā*) 109,94 (TP VIII 77); drum (*muraḥ*) announces ~ spectacle (*saṃdhyā-prekṣaṇaka*) in Śiva temple 123,129 (TP IX 52); – see also: ablutions; cloud(s); dance;

Eve-teasing (sexual harassment), see: rape; violation; violence

evil, doer of ~ will obtain ~ 20,41 (TP II 97f.); ascetic continued his meditation to avert ~ (*tapasvī duṣṭa-ghnīm abadhṇād yoga-dhāraṇām*) 73,135 (TP VI 111)

evil eye:⁵¹⁵ *yakṣiṇī* Śṛṅgōtpādīnī fixes ~ (*datta-dṛg-*) on Pāsupata ascetics and, while playing the *kaṅkāla-kinnarī vīṇā*, creates horns on their head with a charm 37,65 (TP III 187); hermit burns hen-crow by ~ 56,171 and 175 (IV 232); faithful woman burns tree to ashes with angry look (*krodha-vikṣita*) 63,41 (TP V 123); woman looked at by *kāpālīka* with ~ dies in fever (*dṛṣṭvāiva sājāta-jvarā sāyam vyapadyata*) 124,5f. (TP IX 68); – see also: *dṛṣṭi-viṣa*

exaggeration, stylistic ~ of boy with 100.000 gold pieces under his pillow every day 3,21 (TP I 19); ten millions as teacher's fee for new grammar 4,93 (TP I 36); ~ of 100.000 gold pieces offered to Cāṇakya as *dakṣiṇā* for presiding at a *śraddhā* 5,112 (TP I 56f.); Viṣṇu tells royal devotee he will obtain 80.000 princesses 36,18 (TP III 170); ~ of prince whom Creator made admirable in respect of the qualities of courage, beauty and generosity, as if to outdo Skanda, Kandarpa and the wishing-tree of heaven 71,68 (TP VI 40); breasts like rooftops of palace and frontal lobes of elephant 91,30 (TP VII 68 omitted); ~ of 18.000 brahmins eating in a *caṇḍāla*'s house 112,194f. (TP VIII 121)

exchange, mouse of gold in ~ for bride 6,48 (TP I 63); ~ of children at birth, by Creator

⁵¹³ Often foreign women from the north-west were provided for the harem as stated in Bollée 2002: § 804 and Rājat VII 520.

⁵¹⁴ See also: Crooke 1906: 181ff.

⁵¹⁵ See STh *D 2071ff.; Seligmann 1910; Michaels 2004 230ff.; Dundes 1992 and especially Maloney 1976.

through illusion (*māyā*) 34,44 (TP III 131)
 excitement, at sight of hero mermaid springs from her couch in state of ~ (*saṃbhrama*) 86,99
 (TP VII 20); – see also: *kañcuka*
 executed robbers reanimated by *vetālas* 18,149 (TP II 61)
 execution of substitute 5,42 (TP I 50); ~ of Jīmūtavāhana for a snake 22,223 (TP II 154)⁵¹⁶
 execution,⁵¹⁷ princess stops ~ of robber 10,173 (TP I 118); impaled robber is restored to life by
 Śiva's boon to merchant's daughter 88,50 (TP VII 38); ~ of robber in the morning stopped
 by merchant's daughter in love (*dr̥ṣṭy-anurāgiṇī*) 112,165 (TP VIII 119);
 execution place: stone of execution (*vadya-śilā*) of snakes 22,209 (TP II 152) and 22,222
 (TP II 153); (*śūlādhiropaṇa-sthāna*) 72,194 (TP VI 83); *vadhya-bhūmi* 88,33 (TP VII 37);
 (*vadhya-śilā-tala*) 90,143 (TP VII 59)
 executioner(s), Ḍomba with drum (*mṛdaṅga*) 13,96 (TP I 157); ~s of brahmin become blind,
 see: blind
 exorcism of horned (*viṣaṇṇayā*) demon (*bhūta*) 71,143 (TP VI 46 with note 1)
 experience, see: birth; feeling
 exposed child brought up on goat's milk 112,105 (TP VIII 114)
 exposure of princess in basket on river 15,38 and 44 (TP II 4f.)⁵¹⁸; ~ at birth in house of
 brahmin 73,185 (TP VI 114); Hara commands woman in dream to leave newborn son in
 cradle at king's gate 93,49 (TP VII 81); – see also: basket; deposition
 expulsion, after ~ prince goes to father-in-law 21,70 (TP II 130); ~ from throne by relations
 58,110 (TP V 23); do, by younger brother 74,25 (TP VI 142); – see also: banishment
 extortion, see: blackmail
 extravagance, see: vice of prodigality
 eye, fire of Śiva's ~ 9,1 (TP I 94)⁵¹⁹; eager ~ of a woman, expanded with desire to behold the
 king, came, as it were, to the side of her ear, that did not perceive him, in order to inform it
 18,15 (TP II 50); man's right ~ throbbing is auspicious 22,106 (TP II 144 with note) and
 51,4 (TP IV 122); own ~ when admired torn out by prince-hermit 28,21 (TP III 19); ~ of
 policy (*nīti-cakṣus*) 33,180 (TP III 122); woman is raining love with an ~ (*cakṣusā prema-*
varṣiṇā) 39,81 (TP III 223); ~ of longing affection (*sōtsukayā dr̥ṣā*) 45,142 (TP IV 27);
 looking with an angry red ~ (*tiryak-kopa-kaṣāyeṇa cakṣuṣā*) 45,274 (TP IV 35)⁵²⁰;

⁵¹⁶ See Zin 2002: 148.

⁵¹⁷ Saletore 1943: 284ff.

⁵¹⁸ STh S 331.

⁵¹⁹ Cf. 34,243 (TP III 146) and 56,238 (TP IV 237). By a beggar's evil eye a housewife gets fever and dies 124,6
 (TP IX 68). For Empedocles the eye also contains fire (Freeman 1946: 197) and Plato and Archytas thought that our
 eyes emit rays (do, p. 238). At 73,340 (TP VI 125) a princess pours forth rays of beauty (*amṛta-syanda-sundara-*
prasaraḍ-dyutī), cf. Kād 129,9 where a king is struck by rays shooting from the eyes of his mistresses as if by ear-
 lotusses: *karṇōtpalair iva locanāṃśubhir tāḍyamānaḥ*, cf. Seligmann 1980: 503ff. On the real seeing process see
 Eagleman 2011: 20ff. and Müller 2008: 282f.

⁵²⁰ Cf. Mbh XIV 89,10 where Draupadī throws an angry askance look at Kṛṣṇa: *Draupadī Kṛṣṇaṃ tiryak-sāsūyam*
aikṣata; Daś 27,3 *roṣāruṇa-nayanā māṃ dr̥ṣṭvā bahudhā nirabhartsayan*.

maiden looking on man with impassioned, loving and bashful⁵²¹ ~ (*sa-rasa-snigdha-mugdhenâlokya cakṣuṣā*) 51,8 (TP IV 122); Nala offers his body as burnt-offering in the fire of the ~ of Śiva 56,238 (TP IV 237); sun as flaming ~ (*jaḡac-cakṣus*) of the world 59,51 (TP V 29)⁵²²; woman throws lovingly upon man her expanded ~, which resembled a garland of full-blown blue lotuses (*dr̥ṣṭyāiva nīlâbja-mālayêva praphullayā premanikṣiptayā*), and so chose him as her husband 67,22 (TP V 197); man's right ~ throbbing as if with joy 67,68 (TP V 200 with note 3); tear drop from Śiva's right ~ becomes sea 69,38 (TP VI 11); rolling ~ of princess reveals her mortality 74,216 (TP VI 156); moon as ~ of the world (*jaḡan-netra*) 89,5 (TP VII 40); maiden has white ~ with black pupil which seemed to extend up to the root of her ear (*dadhatā tārakaṃ kṛṣṇa-marjunena svacakṣuṣā karṇa-mūlaṃ vivikṣatim*) 90,43 (TP VII 52)⁵²³; moon as own brother to the curved corner of an angry, long-eyed beauty's ~ (*kupyad-āyatâkṣi-kuṭilâpânga-sahôdaraḥ śaśâṅkaḥ*) 103,204 (TP VII 189); ~ on Śambhu's front (*bhālêkṣaṇa*) 104,2 (TP VIII 1); turning round, maiden looks at lover again and again with an ~ made more charming by the pupil coming down to rest in its corner (*apânga-viśrânta-tarakântena cakṣuṣā*) 104,99 (TP VIII 8); right ~ throbbing bad sign for a woman 117,141 (TP VIII 173); Śiva's blazing ~, see *bhālêkṣaṇa*; – see further: sidelong glance

eyebrows meeting (inauspicious mark) of witch 20,108 (TP II 103 with note)

eye-disease (*prâṇ-netra-roga*), king delivers *vetâla* from ~ by a look (*dr̥ṣṭi*) 123,34 (TP IX 45); – see also: blind

eyes, maiden with ~ like blue lotus (*nīla-nīraja*)⁵²⁴ 4,6 (TP I 30) and *indīvarâkṣi* 81,48 (TP VI 212); ~ reddened by collyrium (*añjanā-tāmra-netra*) 6,111 (TP I 69); ~ (*dr̥ś*) red with smoke (*dhūmrâbhitāmra*) as with wine, of bride at wedding 14,30 (TP I 184); at entering Kauśāmbī royal family is drunk in by the ~ of the citizens 10,211 (TP I 121); red ~ from

⁵²¹ ORC 146: “lui lança des regards pleins d’amour, de tendresse et d’ingénuité”. See also under: gestures.

⁵²² See Gonda 1968: 231.

⁵²³ Cf. TP I 90; ORC 978; Bollée 2010 (Svasti): 143 and on the photo in Pal 2009: 96. Sidelong glances often show anger.

⁵²⁴ Syed 1990: 652. Nearly 98 per cent of humans have dark eyes (http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Eye_color); blue ones like the *Nymphaea cyanea* may be rare in India and therefore, being also the colour of heaven, considered a mark of great beauties, but ORC 1597 takes the comparison *pour leur couleur sombre*; cf. also *abhinīla-netra* as *Buddha-lakṣaṇa*. Syed 1990: 609ff. states the colour of *indīvara* to be dark blue (*śyāma*). The *Nymphaea utpala* has a blue variety also. The comparison of (rolling) eyes with bees, as in 59,4 (TP V 26) and 73,345 (TP VI 125), may therefore less pertain to the colour than to the movements. See for the exact colour in Google under *Nymphaea caerulea*. On blue eyes Dr Ines Fornell writes me that these do occur even nowadays in northern mountain areas such as the Panjir valley, where some people also have red hair, and refers to Nuristani in <http://www.afghan-aid.de/sprache.htm> Moreover, in Bhisham Sahni's novel *Basantī* the young man Dinūrām has blue eyes and a light complexion, and the Bollywood superstar Aishwarya Rai is also blue-eyed, as is the girl the photographer Steve McCurry pictured in Peshawar in the *Welt am Sonntag* paper of May 8th, 2011, p. 1. Further, women with brown eyes may nevertheless wear the name Nīlākṣī, just as blondes with us can be called Melany. It may also be remembered that women often belonged to war booty (as in 45,70 [TP IV 22]), royal presents (44,78 [TP IV 6]), or otherwise were immigrants from the Northwest. Finally, the comparison may stem from an older stratum of the stories.

smoke (*ḍṛṣī dhūmâbhitâmrâyām*) 14,30 (TP I 184) and *agni-kriyâ-dhūmair yan me piṅgalite ḍṛṣau* 21,122 (TP II 134); one thousand vulvae turned ~ on Indra's body as Gautama's curse 17,144 (TP II 46); unwinking ~ (*a-nimiṣêkaṇāḥ*) of women curious to see the king 18,13 (TP II 50); people throw garlands of ~ expanded with joy so as to resemble blue lotuses 18,20 (TP II 51); king and queens are feast for ~ of population 18,22 (TP II 51); queen has ~ half closed (*nimīlita-vilocana*) in magic rite 20,50 (TP II 98); *vidyâdhara* princess is feast for the ~ (*netrôtsava*) of brahmin mortal 26,47 (TP II 220); Daitya with flaming ~ (*jvalita-locana*) 26,180 (TP II 230); ~ long as lotus leaf (*padma-patrâyatêkṣaṇa*) 28,19 (TP III 19); ~ of *apsaras* do not wink 28,61 (TP III 24); Sulocanâ named after her beautiful ~ 28,73 (TP III 25); as if to select him for her husband, princess throws garland of the blue lotuses of her ~ (*nayanôtpala-mâlikâ*) over hermit 28,79 (TP III 26), cf. eye (*ḍṛṣṭi*) of woman resembled to garland of blue lotuses (*ḍṛṣṭyêva nilâbja-mâlayêva praphullayâ prema-nikṣiptayâ*) she threw on man and so princess chose him as her husband 67,22 (TP V 197) and 106,29 (TP VIII 30);⁵²⁵ with delated ~ (*utphullayâ ḍṛṣṭyâ*) and hand placed on the heart she seemed to say: "He has entered my soul by this path" 31,46 (TP III 85)⁵²⁶; princess is nectar to the ~ (*netrâmṛta*) of future husband 34,99 TP III 135); baby is nectar to the ~ of royals and son a feast to the ~ of the world (*jagan-netrôtsava*) 34,100 (TP III 135); women's blue, white and red ~ compared to blue lotuses, parched grain and water-lilies 34,126 (TP III 137)⁵²⁷; ~ like opening blue water-lilies (*dalat-kuvalayêkṣaṇa*) 34,231 (TP III 145); rolling ~⁵²⁸ of woman likened to bees (*lola-locana-ṣaṭpadâ*) 35,11 (TP III 156); king returns like stream of nectar to his mother's ~ 35,161 (TP III 168); ~ of monkey like rubies (*padma-râgâv ivâkṣiṇi*) 37,88 (TP III 189); here comes your beloved like second moon giving feast to the ~ in the night 37,182 (TP III 196); loving woman has ~ fixed on the ground (*nyasta-ḍṛṣṭir mahi-tale*) 39,83 (TP III 223); prince with ~ like blue lotus 42,72 (TP III 264); *râkṣasî* ~ (lit.: face: *adho-mukhî*) cast down from shame 42,158 (TP III 270); blue lotus garland of ~ 43,205 (TP III 295); reddened ~ of enraged *vidyâdhara* females 44,53 (TP IV 4f.); streets of Tāmraliptî strewn with blue lotuses by means of the sidelong glances of women 44,74 (TP IV 6); nectar rained into ~ 45,233 (TP IV 33); woman with rolling ~ (*lolâkṣî*) 45,254 (TP IV 34); ~ of cook rolling fearfully 49,39 (TP IV 87); woman longs to drink man in with her ~, as the female partridge longs to drink the moon 49,211 (TP IV 99); three ~ of Gaṇeśa 50,177 (TP IV 119); beautiful king drunk in by the ~ of the ladies of the city 51,177 (TP IV 134); ~ extended to the ears 51,181 (TP IV 134)⁵²⁹; ~ compared to bees⁵³⁰ (*vyâvṛtta-netra-*

⁵²⁵ "C'est le regard qui suscite l'union ou le rejet" (Kuv II 334; *jo sandhî-viggaha-kâriṇiḥ diṭṭhîe paḍihâi* [107,30]).

⁵²⁶ See, e.g., Eagleman 2011: 4f.

⁵²⁷ See Pieruccini 2004.

⁵²⁸ See Das 2003: 459.

⁵²⁹ Also: Râjat 4,20.

⁵³⁰ See Ferenczi 1950: 270-76 (On eye symbolism).

bhramara) 52,152 (TP IV 148) and 59,4 (TP V 26); sun and moon are Viṣṇu's ~s 54,33 (TP IV 186); open flowers of trees as their expanded ~ 54,45 (TP IV 188); treat for the ~ (*cakṣur-bhrānti*) 55,45 (TP IV 205); ~s of hermit incinerate hen-crow 56,171f. (TP IV 232); ~s of Damayanṭī like blue lotus (*indīvara*)⁵³¹ 56,277 (TP IV 239); rolling ~ of *vidyā dhari* like circling bees (*lola-locana-ṣaṭpada*) 59,4 (TP V 26); ~ red with anger (*krodhāruṇḍkṣaṇa*) 60,101 (TP V 50); foolish minister has ~ of treasure-finder (*nidāna-darśin*) torn out so that he could not find the places with a treasure anymore 61,36f. (TP V 71); princess with ~ like a deer (*hariṇi-dṛś*) 71,78 (TP VI 41); ~ of goat used for incense at sacrifice to Śiva 71,214 (TP VI 51); *yakṣiṇī* belle surrounded by many *yakṣas*, with feet turned the wrong way and squinting ~ (*ākeka-vilocana*) 73,245 (TP VI 118); by looking at female beauty king washes from his ~ pollution contracted by looking at others 73,149 (TP VI 112); roaming black deer compared to ~ of the forest 73,239 (TP VI 118); princess wakes up and rolls her ~ as the *kumudvatī* opens ... and the bees begin to circle in its cup 73,345 (TP VI 125); hero bewildered by sidelong arrows of princess' ~ (*tiryag-valitaiḥ locana-sāyakaiḥ*)⁵³² 74,218 (TP VI 156); glances (*dṛṣṭi-pāta*) of heavenly maiden create in lake new forest of blue lotuses 75,69 (TP VI 169); three brahmins with ~ exclusively fixed on moon of beauty as if sustaining a vow of imitating a *cakora* (q.v.) 76,11 (TP VI 180); women's ~ feast on nice man like *cakoras* on moon-rays 77,50 (TP VI 187); eddies of sea compared to ~ with waves as curved brows 86,74 (TP VII 18); garland of blue ~ thrown on lover 90,56 (TP VII 53); tumbling dice as rolling ~ of calamities like the black antelope in colour (*kṛṣṇa-śārābhair netraiḥ*) 92,16 (TP VII 72); sacrifice of human ~ (*mānuṣa-netra*) to a *vetāla* 99,14 (TP VII 123); lotuses as expanded ~s of lake 101,11 (TP VII 134); prince sprinkled with blue lotuses of the ~ of curious women 101,376 (TP VII 160); do, of towns-women 103,164 (TP VII 186); black *vetāla* with ~ like an owl 102,19 (TP VII 163); princess with ~ fixed on the ground (*nyasta-nayanā*) 103,70 (TP VII 180); rolling ~ of curious women are like dancing blue lilies 103,164 (TP VII 186); look from reverted corner of woman's ~ as messenger of love (*prīti-dūtī*) 104,31 (TP VIII 3); winking of ~ mark of mortality 104,95 (TP VIII 8); feast for the ~s (*nayanōtsava*) 104,112 (TP VIII 9); ~ like blue lotuses (*phulla-nīlābja-mālā*) 106,29 (TP VIII 30); *vidyādhari* princesses have ~ like skin of black antelope and show anxiety about king by turning their ~ inwards 107,83 (TP VIII 49); ~ of bathing queens reddened by antimony (or: *qohl*) washing into them (*dhautāñjanāruṇa-dṛś*) 108,147 (TP VIII 65); ~ of a robber roll rapidly like those of a crow (*kāka-cañcala-locana*) 112,152 (TP VIII 118); golden *haṃsas* with ~ of pearl (*muktā-maṇimayêkṣaṇa*) 114,40 (TP VIII 135); squinting ~ (*kātara-locana*) mark of male ugliness 123,164 (TP IX 55); – see also: *cakṣur-bhrānti*; deer; doe; forest; gesture

⁵³¹ *Nymphaea Stellata* (MW); Syed 1990: 625f. (also *N. cyanea*).

⁵³² Cf. 74,284 “javelins flew with their long points resembling eyelashes, and seemed like the glances of nymphs of heaven, as they gazed on the warriors” (TP VI 160).

face, like full moon 4,6 (TP I 30 with note 1) and 45,333 (TP IV 39) and 75,129 (TP VI 173) and *pūrṇendu-mukhī* 82,29 (TP VI 219); ~ of women surpassing moon in beauty 18,12 (TP II 50), cf. 75,70 (TP VI 169) and 112,66 (TP VIII 111); boy Kārttikeya with six ~s 20,88 (TP II 102); ~ of princess like full-blown lotus (*utphulla-padma-vadana*) 34,231 (TP III 145)⁵³³; 43,204 (TP III 295); ~ of enraged *vidyādhara* females are furrowed with frowns and with reddened eyes 44,53 (TP IV 4f.); father curses son to rebirth with ugly ~ (*vikaṭānana*) 52,77 (TP IV 143 “with a large mouth”, similar M I 788; ORC 563: “*ton visage sera monstrueux*”); princess covering ~ with garment before dying 52,150 (TP IV 148)⁵³⁴; downcast ~ (*viṣaṇṇa-vadana*) of sulking queen 55,124 (TP IV 210); ~ of *vidyādhari* like opening lotus (*vikasat-padma-vadanā*) 59,4 (TP V 26); sorrowful man goes ~ cast down (*adho-mukha*) 64,31 (TP V 141); ~ downcast from shame (*lajjā-nata-mukhī*) 65,250 (TP V 174) and 116,40 (TP VIII 159); moon-face (*mukhēndu*) 72,32 (TP VI 70); ~ covered during sleep 73,7 (TP VI 100 with note 1 about the baneful effects of the moon’s rays as expressed by “moonstruck” and “lunatic”)⁵³⁵; maiden with downcast ~ (*vinatānanā*) from shame of love 74,236 (TP VI 157); girl’s ~ surpasses moon in beauty 75,70 (TP VI 169); woman asks husband with downcast ~ (*nata-mukhī*) impunity 84,32 (TP VII 7); ~ like moon’s orb (*candra-bimba-vadana*) 87,14 (TP VII 30); princess with ~ cast down from shame (*lajjā-natānanā*) 90,53 (TP VII 52); do, telling her story *trapānanā* 101,154 (TP VII 144); ~ of woman at king’s window at night 106,61 (TP VIII 33); ~s of royal ladies, expanded and red with wine, shine like lotuses in lake 110,128 (TP VIII 91); queen compared to night in being moon-faced and having eyes twinkling like stars 110,135 (TP VIII 92); ~ of prince full of nectar worthy of being drunk in with the eyes (*cakṣuḥ-peyāmṛta-rasa*) 110,140 (TP VIII 92); brahmin woman uncovers ~ (*mukham udghāṭya*) before uncle 123,241 (TP IX 60)⁵³⁶; – see also: bee(s); covering; eyes

faeces, see: crane

faint, removed by shower of nectar 7,7 (TP I 74); at death of his daughter king falls to earth motionless 52,153 (TP IV 148); hermit removes ~ of man shocked by sudden separation from his wife 67,103 (TP V 203); ~ cured by sprinkling with sandal-water 69,10 (TP VI 9); delicate queen faints (*mumūrcha*) by the blow of a lotus on her thigh and is brought round with cold water and fanning (*śītāmbhu-mārutaiḥ*) 85,12f. (TP VII 11)⁵³⁷; love-sick woman faints (*mohaṃ yayau*) 95,39 (TP VII 100) and *mohena mohitvā* 117,52 (TP VIII 167) and is brought round by confidante with cold water; ~ (*papāta bhuvi mūrccitaḥ*) of king at hearing of his father’s death 111,85 (TP VIII 102); princess faints (*mohena mohitā*) 117,52 (TP VIII 167); *mohād apatad bhuvi* 119,111 (TP VIII 201)

faithfulness, of woman to husband 36,40 (TP III 172); ~ of brahmin soldier at palace gate

⁵³³ Jackmuth 2002: 140.

⁵³⁴ See above under : covering.

⁵³⁵ See HdA 6: cols. 503-506.

⁵³⁶ It is said nowhere before why she had covered her face.

⁵³⁷ Cf. STh F 647.8.

(*siṃha-dvāra*) 78, 24ff. (TP VI 192f.); – see also: chastity; fidelity
 faithless, females, see: adulterous woman;
 falling in love, at mere mention 11,83 (TP I 128)⁵³⁸; ~ with woman in dream 31,12 (TP III 82) and 122,30 (TP IX 36); ~ with man in picture 51,144f. (TP IV 132); ~ at sight with blade of grass (*ṛṇa-dṛṣṭy-anurāgata*) 52,283 (TP IV 157); – see also: ear; eye(s); hearing; love at first sight
 false ascetic(s)⁵³⁹ 69,53 (TP VI 12); minister’s son disguises as ~ and prince as his disciple 75,162 (TP VI 175);
 false information of having killed someone 3,43 (TP I 22); do, of dead queen 17,41 (TP II 37); do, of dead daughter 17,70 (TP II 40); ~ pretention of illness 24,135 (TP II 179); ~ rumour of hermit’s cannibalism 24,209 (TP II 185); speaking falsely 25,203 (TP II 206); ~ representation 26,92 (TP II 224); ~ assertion of supernatural knowledge (*jñāninaṃ māṃ nivedaya*) 30,100 (TP III 71); rival wives bring many ~ accusations 32,191 (TP III 106); improbable accusation (*pravāda*) 39,31 (TP III 220); ~ charge scorched with the fire of king’s contempt 49,214 (TP IV 100); ~ accusation of unfaithfulness of woman 51,79 (TP IV 127); ~ report of king’s death makes queen enter fire 58,38 (TP V 17); ~ statement about a deposited balance 60,239 (TP V 62); ~ cause of royal displeasure 61,229 (TP V 87); queen gives king ~ information on intimacy with sick people as shown by scratches and bites 66,42 (TP V 181); prince gives ~ statement (*avadan mṛṣā*) of being a thief and gives hand to real thief as colleague (*sa-brahmacārī*) 71,29 (TP VI 38) and (*mṛṣābravīt*) 71,138 (TP VI 46); parrot king tells his grieved warder ~ tale (*mṛṣā*) for his good 72,240 (TP VI 86); pretended illness (*māndyaṃ vidhāya*) 73,217 (TP VI 116); good wife tells parents ~ story about her mistreatment by her husband 77,32ff. (TP VI 185); even ~ rumour (*loka-vāda*) injures great men 86,13 (TP VII 14); ~ information of king by ministers 91,17 (TP VII 67); cheating (*miṣaṃ kṛtvā*) of ignorant husband by disguised wife 124,202 (TP IX 82 “false excuse”); – see also: answer; lie; Pāśupata; rape
 falsehood, queen accuses minister of being prophet of telling ~ (*vitatha-vādin*) 31,83 (TP III 88); man does not know difference between truth and ~ 33,42 (TP III 110); magician tells people ~ of Śarva-Śiva telling him to become Pāśupata ascetic 97,38 (TP VII 114); – see also: lie; *satyān-ṛta*
 false jewels (*kṛtrima-maṇi*) 24,133 (TP II 179), cf. 24,164 (TP II 181)
 family, members of own ~ not to be slain 22,42 (TP II 140); deceived husband wishes ~ to perish (*yātu grhaṃ kṣayaṃ*) 64,126 (TP V 149); brahmin ~ with two children 78,9 (TP VI 191); do, 79,6f. (TP VI 200); merchant ~ with son and daughter 84,5 (TP VII 5);
 family goddess (*kula-devatā*) of Rājputs, see: *cāṇḍāla*
 famine, emigration because of ~ in Deccan 3,11 (TP I 19); ~ on the banks of the Yamunā makes brahmins leave for Benares 25,77ff. (TP II 196); 27,94 (TP III 8); ~ causes brahmins to eat beef 27,118 (TP III 9); ~ causes death of seven brahmins after seven days

⁵³⁸ Malamoud 1989: 241

⁵³⁹ See Bloomfield 1924.

27,120 (TP III 10); due to ~ king of Kamalapura becomes robber (*prârebhe taskarâyatum*) 56,13 (TP IV 220); emigration due to ~ is great offence 56,16 (TP IV 221); ~ in Kâśi makes five brahmins flee to Karimaṇḍita forest 70,40f. (TP VI 27); ~ in Kurukṣetra stops when prince enters *tapo-vana* 72,224 (TP VI 85); emigration due to ~ caused by drought in Kalinga territory 104,21f. (TP VIII 2); scourge of ~ (*durbhikṣya-viplava*) makes people flee 123,65 (TP IX 48)

farmer, (on account of wicked servants) a good servant cannot reach king just as ~ cannot get at a crop of rice enclosed with palisade 34,203 (TP III 143);

fascination of three worlds by *apsaras* with her beauty (*trigat kṣobha-śaktena rūpeṇâpsarā hṛtaḥ*) 27,68 (TP III 6); woman's mind fascinated by prince's beauty (*tad-rūpa-hṛta-citta*) 71,132 (TP VI 45); – see also: bewilderment

fast of three nights to propitiate Śiva for son 19,6 (TP II 85); idem 21,143 (TP II 136); ~ broken by festival 21,146 (TP II 136); ~ unto death 27,128 (TP III 10); ~ (*upoṣaṇa*) broken leads to rebirth as *jala-puruṣa* 63,60 (TP V 124); ~ of three days 93,84 (TP VII 84); after ~ of three nights dreamer is informed by Devī 108,85 (TP VIII 60); ~ as a means of suicide 112,139 (TP VIII 117); ~ of twelve days by king in order to find out who two golden *haṃsas* are 114,47 (TP VIII 136)

fastidiousness (*caṅgatā*) of three brahmins 82,11ff. (TP VI 217f.); – cf. sensibility

fat, human, mix of blood, wine and ~ offered to but refused by king 73,153f. (TP VI 112); – see further: candle

Fata Morgana, (*Maya-māyā*) 29,60 (TP III 43)⁵⁴⁰; is water ever really found in ~ (*maru-marīci*) ? 57,91 (TP V 8); this ~ of a world (*saṃsāra–Gandharva-nagara*) is frail as a bubble on water (*vāri-budbuda-bhaṅgura*) 97,13 (TP VII 113); ~ of man having lost beloved 119,155f. (TP VIII 204);

fate, see: destiny

father, died before son's birth 6,29 (TP I 62); second ~ in mirror 14,55 (TP I 186); ~ about to be killed by son 25,107 (TP II 199)⁵⁴¹; daughter calls ~ silly (*bhauta-prāya*) and without *buddhi* 39,108 (TP III 225); Vaidyādhara ~ curses son for inobedience 65,60 (TP V 159)⁵⁴²; ~ represented by hunter 70,123 (TP VI 33); daughter distrusts ~ as to groom she is given to 71,129 (TP VI 45); ~ dies at hearing of son's being led to execution 72,197 (TP VI 83)⁵⁴³; angry *vidyādhara* ~ abandons beloved daughter with curse 86,107 and 135 (TP VII 20 and 22); daughter marries ~ 98,54 (TP VII 119)⁵⁴⁴; Daitya daughter betrays ~ out of love of king 112,51 (TP VIII 109); ~ being alive, mother has no authority (to give away daughter) 112,211 (TP VIII 123); hermit gives his two sons Rāma and Lakṣmaṇa to brahmin

⁵⁴⁰ See Negelein 1912: 179f.

⁵⁴¹ See Michaels 2004: 104; Freud 1954: 255ff..

⁵⁴² For the Indians less importance is attached to physical relationship than to authority, representation of the older generation, experience, affection and tenderness (Gonda 1957: 9).

⁵⁴³ Cf. STh N 344.

⁵⁴⁴ STh T 411.

113,61ff. (TP VIII 128); ~ is to daughters a divinity procuring all happiness 116,20 (TP VIII 157); ~ loves daughter more than his life, see: daughter
 fatigue, removed by Śiva's favour (*prasāda-hṛta-klama*), is like new moon (growing) by rays of sun 19,8 (TP II 85; ORC 154: "on aurait dit la nouvelle lune devenue pleine sous l'effet des rayons du soleil"; M I 219: "er glich dem zunehmenden Mond, der durch die Sonnenstrahlen anwächst."); kings not generally exposed to ~ 27,146 (TP III 12)⁵⁴⁵
 fault, six ~s (*ṣaḍ-varga*) that are enemies of man 20,134 (TP II 106 with note 3); it is not my ~ (*na me 'parādho 'yam*) 60,100 (TP V 50); three ~s (*doṣa*) of women, see: three; women favour (*prasāda*), Vararuci as Skanda's ~ in bodily form 2,77 (TP I 17); 6,152 (TP I 71); ~ of Indra promises king matchless daughter 11,76 (TP I 128); fatigue removed by Śiva's ~ 19,8 (TP II 85); by ~ (*anugraha*) of Guhyakas king can bestow wealth 20,45 (TP II 98); – see also: boon; fatigue
 fear⁵⁴⁶, of being cursed (*śāpa-bhīta*) 7,101 (TP I 85); Bhadrā has ~ of injury by *vidyādharas*, gives her mortal lover her ring and flees to country of Siddhas 18,234ff. (TP II 67); ~ of death (*prāṇa-bhaya*), artificially (*yuktyā*) produced 27,38 (TP III 4); hidden crimes (*prachanna-pātakāḥ*) manifest themselves by means of ~ (*śaṅkayā*) 30,126 (TP III 73); three merchants in chains afflicted by ~ of death 37,42 (TP III 186); speak without ~ (*niḥśaṅkaṃ tvayōcyatām*) 60,46 (TP V 45); ~ of curse equals bribe 89,30 (TP VII 42); love-sick princess passes night in ~ (*saṅkocam etya*) 90,65 (TP VII 53); in *saṃsāra* living beings ~ death (*saṃsāre prāṇināṃ mṛtyuto bhayaṃ*) 94,39 (TP VII 90); robber frequently turns his neck out of ~ 112,152 (TP VIII 118)
 feast, see: festival
 feast to the eyes see: *netra-pīyūṣa*; *netrōtsava*
 fecundation by flame entering womb of queen in dream 27,74 (TP III 6); – see also: mind-born
 fee, ten millions as teacher's ~ for new grammar 4,93 (TP I 36); one hundred thousand gold pieces offered to Cānakya as fee (*dakṣiṇā*)⁵⁴⁷ for presiding at a *śrāddha* on the 13th of the lunar fortnight 5,112 (TP I 56f.); ~ (of *suvarṇa-lakṣa*) given to scouts for good information 12,9 (TP I 133); ~ for Sarasvatī-*pūjā* 12,68 (TP I 138); ~ to brahmins after their meal 17,93 (TP II 41); ~ of gold for messenger 31,59 (TP III 87); ~ of unhusked rice 33,135 (TP III 119); ~ for obtaining *mohinī* science 46,127 (TP IV 56); twenty-five lakhs of gold as ~ for courtesan in two days 57,83 (TP V 7); five hundred elephants as ~ (*bhāṭi*) of courtesan 61,171 (TP V 83); teacher ~ (*guru-dakṣiṇā*) 63,82 (TP V 126); musician to get reward of 2000 *paṇa* 63,158 (TP V 133); five hundred dinars as ~ (*bhāṭi*) of courtesan 93,34 (TP VII 80); idem, (offered in advance and refused) 124,177f. (TP IX 81); king offers hermit ~ for investing princes with sacred thread 118,49 (TP VIII 181); hundred villages as ~ of a painter 122,20 (TP IX 35); – see also: courtesan; grammar; messenger
 feeding 18.000 brahmins as way of a gift to purchase daughter (*tanayā-dāna-śulkena*) of *caṇḍāla*

⁵⁴⁵ But king Paesi in Bollée 2005: § 728 can hardly be an exception.

⁵⁴⁶ See ORC 1565 s.v. Emotions.

⁵⁴⁷ See, e.g., Gonda 1965a ch. VII.

112,194 (TP VIII 121; ORC 1182: “*en guise de cadeau de noce pour obtenir la main de ta fille*”; M II 572: “*Dies soll auch als Kaufpreis für deine Tochter gelten.*”)

feeling, (apparently) causeless affectionate ~ of the heart (*manaḥ snihyad-a-kāraṇam*) is (a sign of) friendship in pre-birth (*janmāntara-prīti*) 22,65 (TP II 141); – see also: anxiety; fire; gesture; love; shame; snow; social feeling
 feet (as pars pro toto)⁵⁴⁸ : *Piśāca* respectfully clasping ~ of Kātyāyana 2,6 (TP I 9); ~ of mother and gurus worshipped 4,90 (TP I 36); ~ of brahmin Śrīdatta in fetters (*nigada-samyuktau*) in Śavara village 10,138 (TP I 115); ~ of Bhavānī as refuge of Śabara prince 22,88 (TP II 143); dustless ~ of heavenly female are marked with umbrella and banner 33,178 (TP III 122); bewildered *rākṣasa* returns on ~ instead of flying 39,148 (TP III 228); hanging by ~ from fig tree as penance 40,102 (TP III 248)⁵⁴⁹; prince incited to propitiate soles of Durgā’s ~ 42,172 (TP III 271); mistress of the house orders maids to wash ~ of brahmin 52,224 (TP VI 153)⁵⁵⁰; ~ touched with cold hands to wake up person 45,189 (TP IV 30); king’s ~ like *aśoka* shoots 55,50 (TP IV 206); king falling at sulking queen’s ~ 55,130 (TP IV 211); Kali enters Nala’s drunk body when he once had gone to sleep without washing his ~ 56,288 (TP IV 241); Damayantī’s ~ pierced with *darbha* grass 56,309 (TP IV 242); ~ of teacher crushed by pupils 63,169-71 (TP V 134); because of deformation of his ~ (*pāda-vaikalpya*) leper is carried on servant’s shoulder to adulterous woman 64,136 and 143 (TP V 149f.); father kicks daughter because she fell asleep while shampooing his ~ (*saṃvāhayantī caraṇau*) 66,157f. (TP V 190); washing the ~ in a lake 73,195 (TP VI 115); ~ of *yakṣas* turned the wrong way (*viparītāṅghri*) 73,245 (TP VI 118)⁵⁵¹; woman’s ruby-coloured ~ (*padma-rāgāṅghri*) fascinate beholders 84,48 (TP VII 8); king embraces hermit’s ~ 94,38 (TP VII 90); small ~ belong to elder queen, large to younger princess who are thus married to prince and king 98,51f. (TP VII 119); son falling at ~ of parents 103,135f. (TP VII 184); red dye on ~ of Gaurī 104,2 (TP VIII 1); wife falls at ~ of husband and in-laws 107,51 (TP VIII 46); enemy seized by the ~ (*aṅghri-yuge*) and dashed to pieces on rock 108,111 (TP VIII 62); queens bow before ~ of father-in-law 110,118 (TP VIII 90); golden *haṃsas* with ~ of coral 114,40 (TP VIII 135); Lakṣmī Kamalā worships ~ (*aṅghri*) of Hari Viṣṇu 115,103 (TP VIII 151); ointment for the ~ (*pāda-lepa*) enables to walk long distances fast 123,19 (TP IX 44)⁵⁵²; crooked ~ (*vakrapāda*)⁵⁵³ as mark of male ugliness 123,164 (TP IX 55); – see also: foot; *viparītāṅghri* feigned, anger (q. v.); woman feigning ignorance how to use a noose to hang herself asks Domba

⁵⁴⁸ See Bollée 2008: 94.

⁵⁴⁹ See Oman 1905: 206f. and photo opposite to 46.

⁵⁵⁰ In a Mūlasarvāstivādin monastery a tub in the form of a tortoise is used (Karashima 2012: XIII note 23; see also idem, 250 and 323).

⁵⁵¹ See Bollée 2008: 101 note 451. Megasthenes in Plinius, *Hist. Nat.* VII 2,14 states people with feet turned backward to live on a mountain called Nulo (McCrinkle 1960: 79).

⁵⁵² See also below: ointment.

⁵⁵³ To be added to Bollée 2008: 49 under A 3.1.1.

to show her and thus kills him 13,100 (TP I 157), cf. the king who asks the mendicant to show him how to prostrate himself 99,17 (TP VII 123); with ~ madness (*unmatta-ceṣṭa*) 18,246 (TP II 68); ~ illness 24,135 (TP II 179); ~ answer 39,42 (TP III 221) and 232 (TP III 234); ~ grief 57,107 (TP V 9) and 58,30 (TV V 17); ~ death 58,29 (TP V 17); – see also: well

felicity, see: city 39,84 (TP III 223)

female animals, see: animals;

female ascetic, see: ascetic

females are never faithful, like prosperous circumstances 37,142 (TP III 193); ~ are wicked says parrot 77,12 (TP VI 184);

“*femme savante*”:⁵⁵⁴ two daughters are like couple of sciences incarnate (*mūrte vidye*) 10, 9

(TP I 106); ~ daughter instructs lover against her father 39,108 (TP III 225); (*sarva-vidyāsu śikṣitā*) motif 72,66 (TP VI 73); ~ (*dhīrā*) advises husband-minister (*mahā-mantrī*) to go on pilgrimage to avoid calumny 86,14 (TP VII 14)

fertility: in the monsoon as ~ period women start making Priapic rolls 2,56 (TP I 13)

fertility elixir (*rasakōttama*) made from wild he-goat’s flesh as powder mix (*cūrṇa-miśra*) 39,9 and 17 (TP III 218f.); fruit as ~ drug 42,69 (TP III 264); – see: aphrodisiacum; drug; *śṛṅga-māṃsa*

festival, of Indra (*Indrōtsava*) 4,3 (TP I 30); ~ of Śakra’s victory over enemies (*vipakṣa-vijayōtsava*) 9,19 (TP I 95); king holds ~ in honour of Indra at birth of princes 11,75 (TP I 128); royal wedding ~ 14,26 (TP I 183) and 34,253 (TP III 148); ~ to the eyes (*netrōtsava*), of king to subjects 16,73 (TP II 27); Indra holds ~ due to slaying *Asura* king 17,19 (TP II 35); ~ celebrated at the end of a fast (*utsava-vyagra-paure vihite vrata-pāraṇe*) 19,12 (TP II 85); great ~ held at birth of minister’s sons 23,59 (TP II 161); ~ at birth of *vidyādhara* prince 23,75 (TP II 163); ~ of Hari-Viṣṇu on 12th white fortnight of Āṣāḍha 26,4 (TP II 217); ~ with *apsaras* dancing 27,60 (TP III 5); king recovered from disease holds ~ 29,175 (TP III 53); 30,44 (TP III 67); battle as ~ 47,35 (TP IV 69); ~ of coronation of Sūryaprabha on Mt Rṣabha 50,165 (TP IV 118); of only son as ~ to the eyes of his relations 65,74 (TP V 160); this world’s (*jīva-loka*) beauty is short-lived like that of a religious ~ 66,33 (TP V 180); brother invites sister to ~ of Devī (*Devī-pūjōtsava*) 80,20 (TP VI 205); release of prisoners at royal wedding ~ 101,380 (TP VII 160); coronation ~ for seven days 103,235 (TP VII 191); ~ of winter solstice (*uttarāyana*) 104,152 (TP VIII 12 with note 1); ~ at Naravāhanadatta having returned to Kauśāmbī 107,49 (TP VIII 46); water-giving ~ (*udaka-dāna ... utsava*) 112,25 (TP VIII 106) and do to (the spirit of) Aṅgāraka (*Aṅgārakāmbu-dānaṃ*) and (*jala-dāna*) 59ff. (TP VIII 110); pulchritude of prince is ~ to the eyes of the world 116,39 (TP VIII 159); ~ of battle (*raṅgōtsava*) 116,60 and 66 (TP VIII 160f.); *Indrasya vijayōtsava*, description of ~ with Rambhā c.s dancing and singing 116,87 (TP VIII 162); 122,8 (TP IX 34); – see also: water-giving festival; water of life motif

⁵⁵⁴ This is not meant satirical, as in Molière.

festival of spring (*vasanta-samayôtsava*) 6,108 (TP I 68); (*madhu-māsa-mahôtsava*) 10,87 (TP I 112)⁵⁵⁵; (*madhûtsava*) 35,6 (TP III 155); (*vasanta-mahôtsava*) 91,22 (TP VII 67); feudal chief, brahmin becomes like ~ (*sāmanta-saṃnibha*) 30,138 (TP III 73)

fever, Cāṇakya causes death of Yogananda by ~ within seven days⁵⁵⁶ 5,119 (TP I 57); cold ague fit (*śīta-jvara*) 25,91 (TP II 196; ORC 124: “*fièvre glaciale*”); burning ~ (*dāha-jvara*) kills merchant 58,62 (TP V 19)⁵⁵⁷; ~ caused by sleeplessness due to care about finding husband for nubile girl 71,119 (TP VI 44); Viṣṇu devotee cures ~ with her hand 71,122 (TP VI 44); prince seized with quartan ~ (*jvareṇa caturthikena*)⁵⁵⁸ 71,202 (TP VI 50); imp of ~ demon (*jvara-ceṭaka*) 71,207 represented on lotus leaves on *vedi* at Śaiva sacrifice 71,217 (TP VI 50f.); demon of ~ with three heads / mouths and three feet painted with yellow mango juice on pericarp of lotus (*karṇikā*) **71,215f.** (TP VI 51); belle dies due to burning ~ (*dāha-jvara*) 76,12 (TP VI 180); ~ and death caused by evil eye 124,6 (TP IX 68);

fever of love (*smara-jvara*) 17,77 (TP II 40) and 73,358 (TP VI 126)⁵⁵⁹; do (*smara-saṃjvara*) 55,63 (TP IV 206); king’s body consumed by ~ 91,44 (TP VII 69); merchant’s wife affected by ~ (*kāma-jvara*) for brahmin 95,25 (TP VII 99); ~ through a painting 101,88 (TP VII 140); ~ produced by arrows (*smara-śara-jvara*) 117,95 (TP VIII 170); 119,1 (TP VIII 193); 119,156 (TP VIII 204); ~ (*madana-jvara*) together with burning separation (*viraha-jvāla*) 122,70 (TP IX 39)

fickleness (*capala-*) of king 14,65 (TP I 187)

fickleness of women, genetically conditioned (*nisarga-niyataṃ* [not MW] *vāsāṃ ... cāpalam*) 19,28 (TP II 86); a fickle woman is like sunset, momentarily aglow for everyone 52,285 (TP IV 157); queen curses her being of unstable mind (*a-pratiṣṭhita-mati*) 58,136 (TP V 24); 72,256 (TP VI 87)

fidelity to husband leads to omniscience 52,228 (TP IV 154); Damayantī proclaims her ~ (*sati-tejas*) 56,326 (TP IV 243 “chastity”); – see also: chastity; faithfulness

fifteen heroes fighting with one 48,12 (TP IV 75)

fifth day, of the white fortnight of Kārtika, marriage on ~ 101,119 (TP VII 142); on evening of ~ of battle brahmin politician informs king of his spying 103,11 (TP VII 176);

fifth note delights the happy 49,215 (TP IV 100);

fifty dinars promised, but not given 55,4 (TP IV 202);

⁵⁵⁵ See also below: Holī.

⁵⁵⁶ Seven-day fever or leptospirosis described by Meulenbeld 1974: 616 apparently is not lethal and therefore something different.

⁵⁵⁷ *Śīta-jvara* and *dāha-jvara* do apparently not occur in Suśruta or Caraka, but cold and hot fever are dealt with in Suśruta, *Uttaratantra* XXXIX 134f. The former patients should be cured by the embracement of a young and beautiful damsel skilled in the sport of love (Bhisagrātna 1963: III 204), the latter by the embracement of young women with cooling breasts smeared with sandal paste, a necklace of pearls, etc. (137; do p. 206).

⁵⁵⁸ See Meulenbeld 1974: 704.

⁵⁵⁹ Cf. Chojnacki 2008 (I): 344 s.v. *amoureuse*.

fig-tree (*aśvattha*; *Ficus Bengalensis*)⁵⁶⁰ worshipped by brahmin 20,26 (TP II 96 with note); meet with *rākṣasī* under ~ 25,215 (TP II 207); ~ (*vaṭa-druma*) looking like mountain with wings sits in ocean beyond mouth of submarine fire (*vaḍavā-mukha*) 26,10 (TP II 217); branch of ~ held by man from ship 26,20 (TP II 218); four animals living in ~ 33,107 (TP III 115); ~ with skeleton (*nara-karaṅka*) suspended 40,90 (TP III 247); princess passing the night in ~ 71,182 (TP VI 49); brahmin lives with *yakṣiṇī* like banyan-tree with glory of spring 73,27 (TP VI 102); two women of celestial appearance issue from ~ (*nyagrodha-śākhin*) 73,411f. (TP VI 130); splendid (*divya*) city inside ~ 73,415 (TP VI 130); *bhikṣu* under ~ waiting for Trivikramasena 75,45 (TP VI 167); dying thief tells wife to dig up gold buried under ~ 93,24 (TP VII 80); before marriage, unhappy *kṣatriya* beauty climbs ~ and fastens noose to it and around her neck in order to commit suicide but is saved 104,71 (TP VIII 6); 104, 129 (TP VIII 11)

fight of Arjuna with Śiva 9,7 (TP I 95); ~ (*mahāhava*) of *vidyādharas* 44,144 (TP IV 10); brown cow fights witches 108,33 (TP VIII 55)

fight, two dogs ~ for a bone motif: brahmin tells two demons fighting for inheritance to run a race and then flees with the inheritance himself 3,51f. (TP I 22)

figure, Kubera gives king a boon of five indestructible golden ~s 38,81 (TP III 212); ~ in pillar, see: *stambha-putrikā*

filicide, brahmins advise king to kill his only son and burn him from which smell all his wives will conceive 13,63 (TP I 154); ~ by fool after another son died in order not to let him go alone the long journey 61,242 (TP V 88f.)⁵⁶¹; ~ by astrologer to make false display of prescience 61,256 (TP V 90); ~ advised by young heretic nun (*pākhanda kṣudra-tāpasī* 61,290 [TP V 94]) prevented by good old woman 61,292 (TP V 95);

find brought to king (motif)⁵⁶² by merchant 54,89 (TP IV 190); – see also: treasure

finger, bride looked angrily at father-in-law, and whirled round her threatening fore~, as it were the decree of death (*krudhā vilokya bhrāmayāmāsa yamājñām iva tarjanīm*) 17,88 (TP II 41); minister points out prince to princess with his ~ 103,59 (TP VII 179); ~ of sun adorns lip of night 103,215 (TP VII 190); lady beckoning with ~ (*pradarśya kara-pallavam*)⁵⁶³ at king inside to come to her 106,67 (TP VIII 33); – see also: gesture; one finger; two fingers; three fingers; five fingers

fire, matted locks look like ~ of curse (*śāpāgni*) 8,28 (TP I 90)⁵⁶⁴; ~ of Śiva's eye 9,1 (TP I 94)⁵⁶⁵; circumambulation (q. v.) of ~ at marriage (*vahni-pradakṣiṇa*) 14,30 (TP I 184); plot

⁵⁶⁰ On fig trees see, e.g. Gonda 1970: 112f.; Crooke 1906: 46ff. According to Haberman 2013: 155 banyan trees are often associated with ghosts and death. Upadhyaya 1965: 5 states that throwing oneself from a banyan at Prayāga into the Ganges would lead to salvation.

⁵⁶¹ See Shulman 1993.

⁵⁶² Cf. Bollée 2008a: 15.

⁵⁶³ Jackmuth 2002: 56f. treating Kumārasambhava 8,18.

⁵⁶⁴ Cf. TaittBr 3,10,8,4 *agnir me vāci śritaḥ*; JaimUpBr 1,28,3 *sā yā sā vāg, agnis saḥ*.

⁵⁶⁵ Cf. 34,243 (TP III 146) and 56,238 (TP IV 237); see note on fire above.

to set ~ to queen's palace 15,21 (TP II 3); ~ as witness for *a-droha-pratyaya* 16,84 (TP II 28); charm for appeasing ~ (*agner ārādhanam mantram*) 17,97 (TP II 42); ~ of Hara's wrath (*Hara-kopâgni*) 18,213 (TP II 66); ~ impregnated by Śiva's seed 20,84 (TP II 102); pouring ghee (*ājya*) into the ~ 24,228 (TP II 187); sovereign power, jealousy, cruelty, drunkenness (*kṣibatva*) and indiscretion (*nirvivekitā*) compared to five ~s 28,32 (TP III 22); hermit compared to ~ free from smoke (*vidhūma iva pāvakaḥ*) 28,77 (TP III 26); magic ~, hard to cross, like Khāṇḍava, thrown in the way of pursuing *rākṣasa* 39,147 (TP III 227); ~ of passion causes grief 37,235 (TP III 199); ~ of king's contempt 49,214 (TP IV 100); Nala saves snake from ~ 56,341 and receives "fire-bleached" (*agni-śauca*) garments from it 351 (TP IV 245); fool throws ~ into water 61,12 (TP V 68); quenching heat with ~ 66,14 (TP V 179); putting out ~ by fanning it 66,15 (TP V 179); two stomach ~s (*jātharâgni*) and three sacrificial ~s of brahmin and wife 73,58 (TP VI 105); wife of dead brahmin enters ~ 73,71 (TP VI 106); smoke from ~ of snake-poison 74,212 (TP VI 155); ~ feeling cool as snow (*hima-sparśo vahneḥ*) 92,76 (TP VII 76); torments of the six ~s 101,285f. (TP VII 154); after marriage parched grain is thrown into the ~ which appears as the laughs of Kāma-Manobhu 103,193 (TP VII 188); oblation in ~ nourishes *devas* 120,21 (TP IX 3); – entering ~ see: *agni-praveśa*; setting ~ to palace, see: burning; – see also: Agni; ascetic

fire-cavity (*vahni-kunḍa*), golden *bilva* fruits, the bodily form of Agni, will come out of ~ 35,61 (TP III 159); magically self-igniting ~ for sacrifice 46,56 (TP IV 52); hermit gives prince in ~ chariot in the form of a white lotus (*mahā-padma-vimāna*) 46,123 (TP IV 57)

fire of desire (*trṣṇā*), *nirvāṇa* allays ~ 120,116 (TP IX 9)

fire of grief (*śokâgni*) 5,102 (TP I 55) and (*samtāpa*) 11,57 (TP I 127); do, 15,93 (TP II 9); ~ (*śoka*) 95,84 (TP VII 103); ~ (*duḥkhānala*) 100,8 (TP VII 128); ~ (*duḥkhâgni*) tortures those who lost relations 111,102 (TP VIII 104);

fire of hunger (*jātharâgni*), brahmin couple suffers from ~ 73,58 (TP VI 105)

fire of illusion (*māyâgni*) 92,61 (TP VII 75);

fire of knowledge (*jñānâgni*) 70,116 (TP VI 32);

fire of love (*kāmâgni*) for future husband burns woman 31,23 (TP III 83)⁵⁶⁶; ~ (*rāgānala*) 37,235 (TP III 199); ~ (*smarâgni*) 44,56 (TP IV 5) and 52,219 (TP IV 153); ~ 69,9 (TP VI 9) and 86,85 (TP VII 19); ~ consumes brahmin woman 69,161 (TP VI 20); king flings himself into sea as if to cool flames of ~ 86,85 (TP VII 19); ~ burns in bosom of princess 90,61 (TP VII 53); king burnt by ~ 91,32 (TP VII 68); brahmin burning with ~ (*smarâgni*) in his garden 95,49 (TP VII 101); ~ (*Kandarpa-vahni*) burning in woman's heart 95,59 (TP VII 102); ~ (*madanâgni*) 101,126 (TP VII 143); ~ (*madanānala*) 117,12 (TP VIII 164); ~ (*kāmâgni*) increases through separation from lover 117,23 (TP VIII 165); shame makes prince conceal ~ 119,3 (TP VIII 193);

fire of separation (*virahānala*) 43,186 (TP III 294); do, (*viprayogâgni*)⁵⁶⁷ 25,265 (TP II

⁵⁶⁶ For the erotic fire cf., e.g., Ovid, *Amores* 2,19,15; 3,1,20 et passim (see Index, p. 346 s.v. *ignis amoris*); Doniger O'Flaherty 1981: 375 sub 7c.

210); yellow pollen of flowers compared to ~s 81,63 (TP VI 213); ~ (*vīyogānala*) 87,20 (TP VII 30); do, (*virahānala*) 89,48 (TP VII 43); ~ (*preyo-viraha-vahnī*) tortures princess in garden 117,15 and alleviates its scorching in a shrubbery 19 (TP VIII 165); ~ from wife (*vīyogāgni*) 123,149 (TP IX 54);
 fire of valour (*pratāpānala*) 19,104 (TP II 93); (*ugra-pratāpa*) 101,43 (TP VII 157)
 fire of snake-poison 74,212 (TP VI 155)
 fire of wrath (*pratāpāgni*)⁵⁶⁸, do you wish to be shrivelled like a moth in ~ (*śalabhāyitum*) ? 124,34 (TP IX 70)
 fire-fly, see: *kha-dyota*
 first sight, friendship at ~ (*nave darśane*) 27,190 (TP III 15) and *dṛṣṭvā sadyaḥ so 'nena svayaṃvara-suhṛt-kṛtaḥ* 28,116 (TP III 28); *darśana-vaśīkṛta* 38,33 (TP III 208); love at ~ see: love at first sight
 fish, dead ~ laughing 5,16 (TP I 46)⁵⁶⁹; ~ swallows shipwrecked man 25,47 (Jonah motif; TP II 192f. with note); ~ eaten raw by Niṣādas, but avoided by fasting brahmin and *cāṇḍāla* 27,124 (TP III 10); three ~ in lake 60,178ff. (TP V 56f.); big sea-fish strands on bank of river Vipāśā and brahmin issues from its stomach 74,194 (TP VI 154); lover tossing up and down on his bed like ~ on dry land 104,32 (TP VIII 3); fisher-wife takes delicious (*hṛdya*)⁵⁷⁰ ~ to princess 112,118 (TP VIII 115 with note); ~ desired by starving man makes him be reborn fisherman 112,139f. (TP VIII 117); ~ swallows ship and strands near Suvarṇadvīpa where its belly is cut open and the ship comes out 123,110f. (TP IX 51); woman emerges from big ~ that was blocked from bank to bank of river 123,231 (TP IX 59);
 fisherman, -men (*dhīvara*), spreading nets on dry land 24,200 (TP II 184); king of ~ (*dāśa-pati*) 25,57 (TP II 194); brahmin about to be sacrificed to Devī-Durgā by ~ is saved by ~ princess whom he must marry 26,143ff. (TP II 227ff.); 26,168 (TP I 230); ~ given princess as wife 112,145 (TP VIII 117)
 five⁵⁷¹ *apsaras* cursed to turn into crocodiles at Pañcatūthī 33,29 (TP III 109);
 five arrows, of Smara-Kāma 104,28 (TP VIII 3); king kills boar with ~ 123,86 (TP IX 49)
 five brahmins, longhaired and misshapen, drink tank-water elixir (*vāpī-vāri rasāyana*) for a five hundred years' life 70,43 (TP VI 27)
 five brothers, and one wife 15,132 (TP II 13)⁵⁷²; one daughter with ~ born to *vidyādhara* king 59,11 (TP V 24)
 five colours, flowers of ~ 63,15 (TP V 121); *daśārdha-varṇa-vinyasta-puṣpa-* 74,232 (TP VI 157)

⁵⁶⁷ Cf. *viprayoga-nidāgha* 9,89 (TP I 102).

⁵⁶⁸ Cf. Rājat 3,389.

⁵⁶⁹ Cf. Śukasaptati 5.

⁵⁷⁰ TP renders 'from the lake'; ORC 1178 'délucieux'.

⁵⁷¹ On the auspicious number five see, e.g. Abbott 1974: 295ff.

⁵⁷² Cf. Bollée 2009 (Kuṇāljātaka): 132f.

- five Daityas, king with ~ of the same age performs asceticism 115,44 (TP VIII 147)
- five days, a white elephant lies down ~ after attack by Garuḍa 36,27 (TP III 171); shipwreck after ~ 36,81 (TP III 175); Nāgārjuna buries *amṛta* ~ before its preparation is finished 41,26 (TP III 254); shipwrecked reach shore in ~ 52,331 (TP IV 161); ~ bad weather (*dur-dinam*) 72,123 (TP VI 78); ~ and five nights of walking the road to Pātāla 73,118 (TP VI 109); ~ of battle 103,9 (TP VII 175);
- five elements, world consists of ~ 29,43 (TP III 42);
- five enemies to be captured 54,139 (TP IV 193);
- five fingers shown 5,11 (TP I 45)
- five fires (sovereign power, jealousy, cruelty, drunkenness, indiscretion), king slashes hermit with *aiśvarya*, etc. like ~ 28,32 (TP III 22); feminine nature, intoxication, privacy, presence of a man and absence of restraint likened to ~ 36,87 (TP III 175); with three sacrificial and two stomach fires, brahmin and wife with ~ 73,58 (TP VI 105); ~ plus one 101,285f. (TP VII 154); king performs asceticism amid ~ in summer 115,45 (TP VIII 147);
- five fruits 70,32 (TP VI 26); betel-nut flavouring ~ 92,42 (thus TP VII 74; ORC 995: “*noix de bétel assaisonnées des cinq fruits*”; M II 315: “*verzehrte reife Früchte und süße Betelnüsse*”)⁵⁷³; do, 104,46 (TP VIII 4);
- five gods (Indra, Vāyu, Agni, Yama and Varuṇa) as servants of Nala 56,260-7 (TP IV 238f.)⁵⁷⁴
- five golden lotuses (*sauvarṇam padma-pañcakam*) 40,84 (TP III 246)
- five hundred, brahmins fed to propitiate celestial elephant 36,22 (TP III 170); ~ Rājputs 38,18 (TP III 207); ~ dinars as daily pay for brahmin soldier 53,92 (TP IV 174); idem 78,11 (TP VI 191); ~ years’ life, see five brahmins; ~ dinars as fee for courtesan 93,34 and 93,42 (TP VII 80f.);
- five indestructible⁵⁷⁵ men (*a-kṣayān puruṣān*), heavenly man living long with courtesan leaves her ~ at his departure 38,110 (TP III 214)
- five insignia of royalty, see: insignia
- five locks (*pañca-cūḍa*), head of bawd with ~ left 12,168 (TP I 146)
- five *loka-pālas* 56,259 (Indra, Vāyu, Agni, Yama and Varuṇa) and 272 (TP IV 238f.)
- five men, with long hair and wild-looking (*bhūri-keśān dur-ākṛtīn*) 70,40 (TP VI 27)
- five ministers, coeval and knowing language of birds 101,47 (TP VII 137); ~ to perish unless yearly water is offered to (manes of) *Asura* 112,57 (TP VIII 110);
- five nights’ fast 33,30 (TP III 109);
- five pairs of garments made daily by Śūdra 83,22 (TP VII 3);
- five *palas* of flesh cut from body of thief 61,284 (TP V 93)
- five precious things (*mahā-ratna*) buried within city by gambler 121,156 (TP IX 23 with note 1)

⁵⁷³ Text reads: ripe (*pakva*) instead of *pañca* fruits.

⁵⁷⁴ See Zachariae 1977: 682f.

⁵⁷⁵ Golden figures, cf. 38,81 and 118.

- five princesses, see: five *vidyādhari*s
- five *ratnāni*, see: five precious things
- five or seven followers (*pañca-saptānugānvitah*) of false Pāśupata ascetic 69,53 (TP VI 12 “six or seven”; ORC 794: “*six ou sept*”)⁵⁷⁶;
- five sons are the effect of many pre-birth offences, ~ of potter 21,134 (TP II 135); ~ of intended husband-killer 23,13 (TP II 157); ~ of Skanda 50,183 (TP IV 119); ~ followed by daughter as boon from Gaurī 59,11f. (TP V 26);
- five stupid sons of brahmin laugh at guest 7,46 (TP I 78);
- five trees in Indra’s paradise ORC 1604 s.v. *mandāra*, but not in KSS
- five *vidyādhari*s, and one son of queen 65,72 (TP V 160); ~ want to marry Naravāhanadatta together 107,85f. (TP VIII 49); do, 108,181 (TP VIII 67); do, 110,36f. (TP VIII 84);
- five years of duty without pay 55,15 (TP IV 203)
- flag, see: banner
- flame (*vakrānalārciḥ*) issuing from mouth of corpse possessed by *vetāla* 18,165 (TP II 62); do, (*javāla*) frightens magician 73,308 (TP VI 123); divine being falling from heaven in dream and entering queen’s womb as ~ 27,74 (TP III 6) and 210 (TP III 179); ~ as hair 53,160 (TP IV 179)⁵⁷⁷; man with body like a mass of ~ (*tejah-pūñjākṛti*) descends from heaven 59,111 (TP V 34); woman looks like ~ from fire of love 91,25 (TP VII 68); Hara as ~*liṅga* manifests to Viṣṇu and Prajāpati 115,111 (TP VIII 152); – see also: dream; hair
- flatulence, foolish rash patient suffering from ~ (*vāyu*) uses medicine orally instead of as a clyster (*basty-artham*) 64,15 (TP V 139)
- flavour (*rasa*), see: six flavours
- flea (*matkuṇa*) in king’s bed 60,127 (TP V 52)
- fleeing, king Guṇaśarman ~ abroad 49,198 (TP IV 98); gods ~ from battle with *Asuras* 50,83 (TP IV 113); ~ Bhils 51,170 (TP IV 134); woman ~ from aggressive husband 52,38 (TP IV 140f.); Indra ~ to Brahmā 115,74 (TP VIII 149)
- flesh, offering own ~ to Durgā 11,37 (TP I 125); queen offers human ~ (*mahā-māṃsa*) in rite for king’s prosperity 20,51 (TP II 99); human ~ necessary for witches’ spells to fly 20,104 (TP II 103); ~ of son unknowingly eaten by royal couple 20,208 (TP II 113); meat-curry (*māṃsa-vyañjana*) for guest 54,170 (TP IV 196); seller of ~ (*māṃsa-vikraya-jivin*) 56,181 (TP IV 232f.); five *palas* of ~ cut from body of thief 61,284 (TP V 93); hero gives of his own ~ to *vetāla* 73,301 (TP VI 122); ; corpse hanging in tree and smelling after raw ~ 75,51 (TP VI 167); human ~ sacrificed to *vetāla* in corpse 99,14 (TP VII 123); old brahmin gives *vetāla* human ~ , even of his own 99,49f. (TP VII 126); gambler offers human ~ for sale (*vikrīṇe mahā-māṃsaṃ*) 121,54 (TP IX 15); – see also: cannibalism; human flesh
- flesh-eater (*kravyād*). See: body; *eka-veṇī*; *kravyād*; *rākṣasa*
- flies (*makṣikāḥ*)⁵⁷⁸, women are like ~ that leave camphor and haste to impurity 58,136 (TP V

⁵⁷⁶ Was the ORC translation here made from TP ?

⁵⁷⁷ The comparison of hair with fire is as old as the Rgveda, see Hirzel 1890: 41; Jackmuth 2002: 111.

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flight into forest motif:⁵⁷⁹ of princess after being given box on the ear by father 66,139f. (TP V 189); nocturnal ~ by merchant's widow with daughter to escape from relations 93,11 (TP VII 79)

flogging contemptuous wife with creepers renews husband's passion 58,94f. (TP V 21)

flour, see: cake; Priapic roll(s)

flower, woman dropping ~ from teeth as sign 7,68 (TP I 82); smile of a *kanyā divyā* like a ~ (*kusuma-smitā*) 81,48 (TP VI 212)

flowers raining from heaven (*sura-puṣpa-vṛṣṭi*) 23,92 (TP II 165), et passim; bright-coloured ~ offered to Viṣṇu 24,97 (TP II 176); two women gathering ~ 26,38 (TP II 220); golden lotuses from the lake of Kubera 51,97 (TP IV 128); open ~ of trees as eyes 54,53 (TP IV 188); ~ of five colours 63,15 (TP V 121) and 225,232 (TP VI 157); showers of ~ likened to showers of arrows of love 71,199 (TP VI 50); brahmin falling in love with princess gathering ~ 89,9 (TP VII 40); ~ of speech (*vāk-puṣpa*) 109,98 (TP VIII 77); golden *haṃsas* offering unfading ~ 114,46 (TP VIII 135); gods shower *mandāra* ~ (*mukta-mandāra-vṛṣṭi*) at end of battle 118,98 (TP VIII 184); rain of ~ at birth of prince 120,48 (TP IX 4); ~ as chastity index (q. v.) 123,148 (TP IX 53)⁵⁸⁰; – see also: *indīvara*; *kumuda*; *kumudvatī*; lotus; *padma*; *rakta-kamala*;

flying, by means of magic shoes 3,49 (TP I 22); mendicant flies with a *vetāla* 18,164f. (TP II 62); ~ with the help of witches' spells (*dākinī-mantra*) 20,104 (TP II 103) and 140ff. (TP II 107ff.); carpenter fears ~ in air chariot 43,264 (TP III 299)⁵⁸¹; *Asurī* princess ~ in the air 28,189 (TP III 35); brahmin, ~ due to magic sword, descends from heaven with woman in his arms 52,186 and 191 (TP IV 151); after infidelity to husband *vidyādhari*⁵⁸² is unable to fly with king in her arms 52,208f. (TP IV 152)⁵⁸³; king obtains from Asura maiden sword which enables ~ 56,218f. (TP IV 235); transmission of ~ knowledge (*vyoma-gamanī vidyā*) 59,106 (TP V 33); out of curiosity prince, carried by *vidyādhara*, flies to see *vidyādhara* world 59,127 (TP V 35); female ascetic flies up to heaven with prince in her arms 65,240 (TP V 173); stupid brahmin tries ~ with wings of grass on his sides 72,279 (TP VI 89); hermit travels through the air with his daughter 101,262 (TP VII 152); *vidyādhari* takes king and flies up with him to Śrāvastī 106,43 (TP VIII 31); king flying on a bird (*pakṣi-vahana*) 118,68 (TP VIII 182); – see also: chariot; *kāma-cārin* foam (*phena*), Indra kills Namuci with Ganges ~ 46,232 (TP IV 64)⁵⁸⁴; Narmadā gleams white with laughing ~ 71,2 (TP VI 36)

⁵⁷⁸ Hensgen 1958: 147.

⁵⁷⁹ Also Daś 9.9; 12.3

⁵⁸⁰ STh H 432ff.

⁵⁸¹ See STh F 861.2.1.

⁵⁸² On flying of *vidyā dharas* see Kuv note 869;

⁵⁸³ For the Jains, *karman* is a physical substance (Dundas 2002: 97) the weight of which could prevent flying.

⁵⁸⁴ See ŚpBr V 4,1,9; XII 7,3; Mbh cr. ed. 9,42,31; Mani 1975: 523.

foeticide, see: Caesarian section, where the premature baby changes into a sword 26,257 (TP II 236)

food trampled upon by madman⁵⁸⁵ 18,250 (TP II 68); ~ comes as soon as thought of 43,63 (TP III 285); heavenly ~ with six flavours 45,230 (TP IV 33); eversatisfying ~ of Sumeru produced by *kāma-dhenu* 50,148 (TP IV 117); ~ and drink produced by science 52,193 (TP IV 151); for guest: meat-curry (*māṃsa-vyañjana*) and ghee 54,170 (TP IV 196); mendicants become slim from eating ~ with six flavours 62,181 (TP V 114f.); importune brahmin asking a person in difficulties for ~ 72,84 (TP VI 75); ~ put on shoulder of *yakṣa* 73,248 (TP VI 118); poisoned ~ for prince given to dog 75,146 (TP VI 174); brahmin eats ~ poisoned by saliva of dead snake 87,47 (TP VII 32); royal banquet provided by magic power (*vidyā-vibhava*) 110,131 (TP VIII 91); washing ~ with water on stone as sign of great sanctity 121,158 (TP IX 23)

fool (*manda-buddhi*), throws fire into water for sacrifice 61,10ff. (TP V 68); tries to engraft guru's severed nose on that of his wife 61,16 (TP V 69); ~s following other ~s lose this world and the next 62,177 (TP V 114); ~ says to have been born three years after his father died and to be taught by him 62,223 (TP V 118); ~ with mouthful of uncooked rice is laughed at 63,182-186 (TP V 136); ~ finds bag of gold (*hema-bhṛtām dṛtim*) and starts counting it when owner returns and takes it away 64,28 (TP V 140); ~s ascending heaven by holding bull's tail fall down at question answered by first holder with his hands 65,197f. (TP V 170 with note 1); – see also: charcoal; cotton; palm-tree; salt; sesame-seed; son; treasure;

foot cut off by herdsmen because of lack of obeysance 18,29 and 36⁵⁸⁶ (TP II 51); awful goddess of destiny (*bhagavatī bhavitavyatā*) places her ~ on the head of all men 26,24 (TP II 218); bewildered *rākṣasa* returns on ~ 39,148 (TP III 228); ~ placed on head as expression for outdoing 39,222 (TP III 234); Viṣṇu's ~ is the earth 54,33 (TP IV 186); jealous pupils wash teacher's right and left ~ separately 63,164 (TP V 133); Brahmā shows Daitya Ātāpin single beautiful ~ of woman (*aṅghriḥ striyaḥ*)⁵⁸⁷ 106,65 (TP VIII 33); setting ~ (*nyasta-carāṇa*) on enemy's chest 109,136 (TP VIII 80); Gandharva princess unable to go on ~ 117,21 (TP VIII 165); having left her chariot out of good conduct (*vinayena mukta-vahanā padbhyāṃ vrajantī pathi*) princess conducts guest on ~ to her castle 120,132 (TP IX 10); – see also: feet

foot, penance of standing on one ~ 30,11 (TP III 64)⁵⁸⁸; – cf. austerities

footprint, see: dog; evening; mark(s); ointment

foot sole (*pāda-mūla*) of Kārttikeya worshipped 2,60 (TP I 15); ~ of Durgā 42,172 (TP III 271)

footsteps, of women 18,354 (TP II 76); heaven becoming red when evening sets ~ (*pada*) in it

⁵⁸⁵ See Bollée 2008: 74 note 246.

⁵⁸⁶ Bollée 2008: 94 note 382.

⁵⁸⁷ For the foot as pars pro toto see Bollée 2008: 92 and 94.

⁵⁸⁸ STh F 682.

47,91 (TP IV 72); ~ of women in dust 98,25 (TP VII 117);
 forbidden chamber motif 26,72 (TP II 222); 108,54 (TP VIII 57);
 forced marriage, see: marriage
 forefinger (*tarjanī*), (threatening) ~ resembles decree of death 17,88 (TP II 41); – see also:
 gestures
 forehead, snake gives king the art of adorning ~ with *tilaka* that never becomes indistinct 9,80
 (TP I 100); ~ covered with cloth because marked with iron dog’s paw 13,155 (TP I 161);
 king makes fleeing queens loose their ~ marks like the wind strips the creepers of leaves
 (*vidalat-patra-tilakāḥ sa cakre*) 6,112 (TP I 69; ORC 41: “*A ses lianes – ses amantes –, le
 roi arrachait les feuilles – leurs tilaka –*”; M I 58: “*wie im Wald der Wind die Lianen ihrer
 Blumen beraubt und deren Blätter zersaust, so entwand der König seinen Geliebten den
 Schmuck und zerstörte ihnen den Schönheitsfleck auf ihrer Stirn*”); unfading garlands and
 forehead-streaks 16,31 (TP II 22); what destiny has written in the row of syllables on one’s
 ~ (*likhitam dhātrā lalātākṣara-paṅktiṣu*) that must be 86,155 (TP VII 24 with note)⁵⁸⁹;
 moon on its western quarter likened to patch on ~ 95,67 (TP VII 102); – see also: dog’s
 paw
 foreign kings painted on canvas for nubile princess 83,14 (TP VII 2)
 forest (*vana*),⁵⁹⁰ longing for ~ because of old age 22,160 (TP II 149); retirement of king to ~⁵⁹¹
 26,269 (TP II 237); ~ (*kānana*) is like straw (*ṛṇa*) to sylvan fire fanned by wind 32,152 (TP
 III 102); waiting like a doe strayed from the ~ 33,2 (TP III 107); king, cheated by his wife,
 goes to ~ and takes refuge with Hari-Viṣṇu 36,106 (TP III 176); out of grief for his dead
 minister a king leaves his throne for the ~ 41,54 (TP III 256); young prince longs to go to ~
 and perform austerities in order to attain supreme felicity (*paramaṃ padaṃ*) 51,29 (TP IV
 124); ~ burst into flames of its own accord by Nala’s magic 56,395 (TP IV 248); unin-
 habited ~s to be crossed only with a caravan 57,176 (TP V 14); life in ~ preferable to
 being householder 64,108 (TP V 148); king anoints son and repairs to ~ 69,83 (TP VI
 14); ~ where austerities are practised (*tapo-vana*) 72,224 (TP VI 85); by *māyā* Indra burns
 ~ (*kānana*) to prevent king to show hospitality to wayfarers with fruits, etc. 72,372 (TP
 VI 96); roaming black deer compared to rolling eyes of ~ 73,239 (TP VI 118); despondent
 king goes to ~ to practice penance 73,410 (TP VI 130); ~ like (chosen) home of love
 75,65f. (TP VI 168); king ejected from his throne by relatives flees into Vindhya ~ (*aṭavī*)
 98,8ff. (TP VII 116f.); wandering through ~ by night 101,5 (TP VII 134); ~ as formidable
 as army 101,282 (TP VII 153)⁵⁹²; big ~ with armies encamped is confused with being

⁵⁸⁹ STh M 302.2.

⁵⁹⁰ Cf. ORC 1569f. KSS appears not to use the word *araṇa* which from the religious point of view corresponds to *vana* (Malamoud 1976: 6). Often the words for forest appear better translated as wilderness or desert, especially in the case of travelling through an *aṭavī*, etc., as in 191,10 (TP VII 134), particularly by night. The forest is also associated with native country, e.g. 70,122 (TP VI 33). A fascinating book on forests is Harrison 1992.

⁵⁹¹ For the association of kingdom with forest see 70,128 (TP VI 33).

⁵⁹² At Kuv 27. 29f. the Vindhya forest is compared to the army of the Pāṇḍavas,

assimilated to a city 102,83f. (TP VII 168); woman as a dryad in person (*sākṣād iva vana-śrī*) 120,117 (TP IX 10 “incarnation of beauty of ~”; ORC 1264: “*telle la véritable Beauté de la forêt*”; M II 682 similar); monsoon elephant (*prāvṛṭ-kāla-mada-dvipaḥ*) comes down on summer ~ (*grīṣma-vana*) 122,65f. (TP IX 38f.: “forest of heats”; ORC 1283: “*voyant le spectacle offert par la forêt estivale ... arriva ... cet éléphant en rut: la saison des pluies.*”; M II 712: “*war jener brünstige Elefant, die Regenzeit, ... über den sommerlichen Wald hereingebrochen*”); – see also: abduction; *aṭavī*; deer; eyes; king(dom); perfume

forest deity (*vana-devatā*)⁵⁹³, in cavern brahmin sees garden maiden of wonderful beauty like a ~ 26,177 (TP II 230); brahmin surmises if princess gathering flowers is Rati or ~ come to worship spring 89,11 (TP VII 409); prince asks if pretty hermit maiden is ~ 101,227 (TP VII 150);

forest-fire, fanned by wind 32,152 (TP III 102); ~ of grief (*duḥkha-davānala*) quenched by tears 56,412 (TP IV 250); ~ (*davāgni*) of separation from beloved in lover’s bosom 105,10 (TP VIII 22); 111,40 (TP VIII 98); 119,166 (TP VIII 204); – see also: forest; separation; *tejasvin*

forgetting, spells after hearing them (*śruta-vismṛta*)⁵⁹⁴ 20,159 (TP II 109f.; ORC 170: “*la formule ... qu’il avait entendue et oubliée*”; M I 243 similar); ~ relatives when entering another body like a man gone to the other world ? 45,56 (TP IV 20)

form, *vidyādhara* power to change ~ is suspended during sleep 33,177 (TP III 122)⁵⁹⁵; king sleeps with *vidyādhari* who had changed her ~ (*parivartita-rūpā*), as the sun with the shadow 105,59 (TP VIII 25)⁵⁹⁶; by magic power *vidyādhara* princess bestowes her ~ on king 106,121 (TP VIII 37); Śiva appears in terrible ~ (*bhairavākṛti*) 106,127 (TP VIII 37)

fortune, good ~ as result of austerities (*tapo-dhīnā hi saṃpadah*) 3,24 (TP I 20); ~ flees from ignorant king 34,204 (TP III 143); ~ of victory is fickle 52,375 (TP IV 164)⁵⁹⁷; ~ of enjoyment (*bhoga-śrī*) better than that of wealth (*artha-śrī*) 54,205f. (TP IV 198); do, coming unthought of (*a-cintitōpagāminī*) 54,209 (TP IV 198); ~ (*lakṣmī*) of short appearance 90,19 (TP VII 50); queen engaged in austerities for ~ on behalf of husband gone to war 116,16 (TP VIII 157); – goddess of ~ see: Lakṣmī; Śrī; – see also: mother foster-sister and kind of confidante (*dhātreyī*) 104,41 (TP VIII 4)

foundling, girl and *ex-yakṣiṇī*, becomes wife of brahmin 34,83-87 (TP III 134)

four as magic number STh D 1273.1.2

four animals (mongoose, owl, cat, mouse) in fig-tree 33,107 (TP III 115); ~ (crow, pigeon king, tortoise, deer) 61,124 (TP V 78);

four *bhāvanā* ‘meditations’ 64,161 (TP V 151 with ref. to Sarvadarśana-saṃgraha)⁵⁹⁸

⁵⁹³ Cf. STh A 435. See also Sivaramamurti 1970: 12f.; Kuv 106.33 et passim.

⁵⁹⁴ Text: *-vismitam*.

⁵⁹⁵ STh 621.0.1.

⁵⁹⁶ Zin 2003b: 169 note 53.

⁵⁹⁷ Cf. Rājat 5,36.

four brahmin brothers resuscitating lion 96,5ff. (TP VII 108ff.)
 four brahmin women fleeing from brigands 21,114 (TP II 134)
 four days of separation felt as if four years 54,79 (TP IV 189);
 four expedients (*upāya*) to obtain a princess from her father: conciliation, gifts, division and force (*sāma, dānaṃ ca bhedo, daṇḍaḥ*) 102,122 (TP VII 171)
 four-faced, Śiva becomes ~ for looking at Tilottamā⁵⁹⁹ 15,137 (TP II 14)
 four golden arms given to brahmin knower of four Vedas 38,118 (TP III 214)
 four heavenly men with special powers culling golden lotus for Viṣṇu 54,11-19 (TP IV 184f.);
 four heavenly voices cursing sleeping king 28,123ff. (TP III 30);
 four heroes sightseeing 52,117 (TP IV 146)
 four internal foes of a king: *kāma, krodha, lobha* and *moha* 34,191 (TP III 142); – see also: king
 four jars of gold buried 19,33 (TP II 87)
 four kinds of musical instruments, see: *liṅga; vādya*
 four lovers put off and then smeared with lampblack (*kajjala*) 4,47 (TP I 32ff.)
 four meditations (*bhāvanā*) 64, 161 (TP V 151)⁶⁰⁰
 four merchants set out for seducing colleague's wife 13,87 (TP I 156)⁶⁰¹
 four ministers 101,2 (TP VII 134)
 four months, stay of ~ in brahmin's house for Veda study 124,153 (TP IX 79)
 four mountains in the island of Nārikela 54,15f. (TP IV 185)
 four Pāśupata (*mahā-vratika*) ascetics 37,54 (TP III 186);
 four pitchers (*kalaśa*) with wife's ornaments buried by pseudo-ascetic 121,155 (TP IX 23)
 four *rākṣasas* guard cave with seven divine herbs (*divyāḥ saptāuśadhīḥ*) 46,208f. (TP IV 62)
 four *ratnāni* (magic sword, ring, horse and maiden), hero with ~ 72,65 (TP VI 73)
 four sciences (*viññāna*) to resuscitate animal 96,31ff. (TP VII 110);
 four sisters (princesses), king marries ~ 26,279ff. (TP II 238)
 four social classes (Sāmaveda chanters, brahmins, gamblers and merchants) in city of Suprati-
 ṣṭhita 6,25ff. (TP I 62)⁶⁰²
 four sons, king with ~ 96,5 (TP VII 108);
 four suitors 52,96 (TP IV 144); ~ from the four *varṇas* 83,20 (TP VII 3);
 fourteenth day of white fortnight of Āśāḍha, feast in Gaurī-tīrtha on ~ 80,6 (TP VI 204)

⁵⁹⁸ Cowell & Gough 1894: 15. These are Buddhist meditations and the three practitioners reached absolute beatification (*mokṣa*) 64,163.

⁵⁹⁹ Alluded to by Varāhamihira, *BrS* 54,20: *pun-stri-prayogeṇa ... vṛiddātra kā yatra catur-mukhatvam Īśo 'pi lobhād namito yuvatyaḥ ?*

⁶⁰⁰ Explained in Mādhava, *Sarvadarśanasamgraha* 2 p. 19, line 47 foll. in V.S. Abhyankar's 3rd ed. (Poona, 1978): *sarvaṃ kṣaṇikaṃ kṣaṇikaṃ duḥkhaṃ duḥkhaṃ sva-lakṣaṇaṃ sva-lakṣaṇaṃ śūnyaṃ śūnyaṃ ii bhāvanā-catuṣṭayam upadiṣṭaṃ draṣṭavyam.*

⁶⁰¹ This story has a counterpart in Hemacandra Maladhārin, *Upadeśamālā* 67 and auto-commentary pp. 200-206 (p.c. Paul Dundas), and in the Arabian Nights, see Tauer 1966; 319 ref. to 244ff. In Kṣemendras *Narmamālā* 2,10ff. a group of four young men try to seduce the wife of an old *kāyastha*.

⁶⁰² According to Strabo, *Geography* XV 1,39ff. there were seven social classes.

- fourteenth night of black fortnight, going to charnel ground on ~ 25,180 (TP II 205); idem 25,215 and 235 (TP II 207f.); idem 38,53 (TP III 210); idem 73,278 (TP VI 120); sacrifice (*paśūpahāra*) of ministers to Devī by Pulindas on ~ 101,297 (TP VII 155);
- fourteen years of separation from love, see: curse
- fourth palace door is that of lady's private apartments (*vāsa-grha*) 124,187 (TP IX 81)
- fourth watch, see: watch
- four *upāyas* (means of success) 11,16 (TP I 123 note 2); 34,200 (TP III 143 note 2)
- four *vādyas*, see: four kinds of musical instruments
- four *varṇas* 83,20 (TP VII 3)
- four Vedas, brahmin knowing ~ 38,118 (TP III 214); parrot knowing ~ (*catur-veda-dhara*) 59,28 (TP V 28)
- four *vidyādhara* princesses 26,54 (TP II 221); do, preparing suicide in fire because a fifth was married against her will 108,169ff. (TP VIII 66)
- four *vijñāna*, see: four sciences
- four *yakṣas* employ poor wood-carrier 57,28 (TP V 3)
- four *yugas* ('world age'), name of Ujjayinī in ~ 83,6 (TP V 7)
- fowler (*śākunika*) catches charmed peacock and gives it to warder as present (*prābhṛta*) 71,278 (TP VI 56)
- fragrance (*āmoda*), lake with ~ of lotuses 63,11 (TP V 120); heavenly (*saurabha*) ~ of liquor which Asura maiden threw on king's head 73,162 and 172 (TP VI 113); – cf. perfume; smell
- fragrant breeze from earth aperture precedes appearance of *Asura* Maya 45,3 (TP IV 17)
- free will (*svātantrya*) 45,60 (TP IV 21)⁶⁰³; – see also: entering
- friendship made between *rākṣasa* and brahmin hero (*maitryā varayitvā*) 18,342 (TP II 75); ~ between women, sworn by plighted hands (*anyonya-hasta-graha-puraḥ-saram*) 28,110 (TP III 28); ~ with royal children hard because of their immoderate passion 28,111 (TP III 28); intimacy in a pre-birth quickly knits ~ 28,117 (TP III 29); tasting of another's food as sign of ~ 28,118 (TP III 29); 28,191 (TP III 36); ~ shown by throwing arms around another's neck 34,135 (TP III 138); prince swears eternal ~ (*sakhyam śāśvatam*) to gamblers after returning their lost money to them 74,150 (TP VI 151); – see also: gestures; hand (71,29 [TP VI 38])
- frog(s) report Agni's presence in the waters to the gods 20,76 (TP II 101); ~ cursed by Agni to sound inarticulate (*jihvā-viparyāsa*) 20,79 (TP II 101); ~ (*bheka*) cannot relish fibres of red lotuses 30,78 (TP III 69); ~ (*maṇḍūka*) in pitcher 30,131 and as a pet name of a young brahmin 30,133 (TP III 73); snake cursed by father of bitten boy to carry ~ on its back 62,156 (TP V 112);⁶⁰⁴
- frog king lets snake eat his subjects 62,161 (TP V 112)

⁶⁰³ The so-called free will, e.g. in choosing a king, can be delegated to an elephant or horse representing fate, see: choosing a king.

⁶⁰⁴ A picture is in the fables in Bidpai (13th century) in the Louvre museum. See also Hensgen 1958: 129.

front¹, see: forehead

front², Prajāpati lets Śacī go in ~ of him (as sign of good manners) 116,81 (TP VIII 162); – see also: etiquette

frontier, Puṣkara's officers seeing off Nala at ~ (*sīmāntam*) 56,305 (TP IV 242); 93,74 (TP VII 83)

frown as sign of anger, see: gestures

fruit(s), young men obtain ~ of birth (*janmani phalam*) when waking sleeping maiden 3,64 (TP I 23); Śiva gives in dream son in form of ~ to queen 21,144 (TP II 136)⁶⁰⁵; ~ free men from old age 29,55 (TP III 42); many children are the ~ of former misdeeds 30,93 (TP III 70); Bhavānī gives king in dream two heavenly ~s to be eaten by sonless queens 42,58 (TP III 263)⁶⁰⁶; king's favour always bears ~ 53,63 (TP IV 172); heavenly maiden emerges from *Jambu* ~ 69,100f. (TP VI 16); three kinds of ~ (*tri-phalāḥ*) falling from tree and flavouring water 70,43 (TP VI 27 with note 1); magic *Jambu* ~ petrifies eater (*niśceṣṭaḥ sthāvarākṛtiḥ*) 73,128 (TP VI 110); Gaṅgā in a dream gives ~ to brahmin 74,119 (TP VI 148); daily ~ with jewel⁶⁰⁷ given by mendicant to Trivikramasena 75,23 (TP VI 166); father may reap ~ = merit of giving daughter in marriage (*kanyā-dāna-phala*) 84,23 and 36 (TP VII 6f.); Daitya maiden gives king ~ against old age and death 81,104 (TP VI 216; cf. 123,63ff. below); Gaṇeśa in tree curses men to become ~s themselves when they touched the ~s without having rinsed their mouths or washed their hands 100,38 (TP VII 131); penance of eating ~s for three hundred years 115,19 (TP VIII 144); ~ given by Śiva in dream to queen and shown by servant to king 120,42 (TP IX 4); grateful monkey gives man who saved his wife a divine ~ which prevents old age and disease 123,63ff. (TP IX 47); sight of king designated as perfect ~ 123,72 (TP IX 48); ~ of reciting or hearing the KSS 124 end (TP IX 86) and see: *śravaṇa-phala*; – see also: jewel(s)

funeral: human sacrifice of men to be thrown into someone's grave (*khāta*) 37,39 (TP III 185 with note)

funeral rites, see: burning ground; Ganges; grave; pyre; *śraddhā*; water

future, Vibhu-Śiva shows prince his ~ as if it had already taken place 70,129 (TP VI 33)⁶⁰⁸; ~ predicted, see *Ambikā*, *Durgā*, *Gaṅgā*, *Śiva*, etc.

gait of female elephant's compared to queen's languid ~ (*mantharatā gateḥ*) 55,201 (TP IV 216); ~ of *rāja-hamsīs* compared to that of queen 69,7 (TP VI 9)

gaja-kumbha (not MW) 'large boss, globe, or protuberance on either side of the top of an elephant's forehead' (Edgerton 1931: 117) 91,30 (TP VII 68 lacuna)

gaja-muktā 'pearl in the head of an elephant' TP II 142 note 1 on 22,76 *muktā-sāra*; – see

⁶⁰⁵ "As gifts made by a Hindu are decided by the nature of the boon desired by the donor, the giving of a fruit is a means whereby fertility may be obtained in return" (Abbott 1974: 323).

⁶⁰⁶ STh T 511.1.

⁶⁰⁷ In the Tretā-yuga *grha-saṃjñita* trees produced also fruits with jewelry (Mette 1973a: 28).

⁶⁰⁸ This is possible because of destiny.

also: pearl

gambler, there is not wealth enough in the whole world to satisfy ~s (*nāsti vyasaninām bhuvī paryāptaye dhanam*) 26,201 (TP II 233); young ~ (*dyūta-kāra*) strips teacher of dancing of his wealth 52,293 (TP IV 158); after death of parents son becomes ~ (*kitava*) 73,75 (TP VI 106), cf. 77,18 (TP VI 184); asylum for ~s (*kitavānām mahā-maṭha*) 73,189 (TP VI 115); description of ~s 73,264 (TP VI 120); ~s clothed in rags besieged by prince who returns their wealth to them 74,146 (TP VI 151); eternal friendship with ~ 74,150 (TP VI 151); wicked son is ~ 75,95 (TP VI 171); indebted brahmin ~ beaten with sticks (*lagudā hata*) 92,20 (TP VII 72); insolvent brahmin ~ left in forest 92,23ff. (TP VII 73); ~s beat up insolvent colleague unable to pay (debts) (*a-svatvād a-dadantaṃ*) 121,35 (TP IX 14); ~ flung into well is put out by two *brahma-rākṣasas* on condition to get food for them 121,50 (TP IX 15); *vetāla* gives ~ his shape and power for seven days 121,57 (TP IX 16); ~ pushes *vetāla* into pit 121,65 (TP IX 16); recklessness and disregard of all ties are ingrained in the nature of ~s 121,71 (TP IX 17); ~ sleeping with his head on his arm in temple of Mahākāla sees images (*pratimā*) of the Mātaras, etc. 121,77 (TP IX 17), cf. 49,226 (TP IV 100); ~ makes himself croupier (*sabhya*) in Mahākāla temple and plays dice with Mātaras, etc. 121,80 (TP IX 17); ~ becoming Indra for one day because of his charity 121,190 (TP IX 26); ~ cheats Yama 121,199 (TP IX 26); twelve years old boy conquers all ~s and takes his father's bedstead (*śayyā-khaṭvā*) 124,212 (TP IX 83); gambling,⁶⁰⁹ “whoever knows the art of ~ has a treasure in his grasp” 6,26 (TP I 62); brahmin addicted to ~ (*vyasanī*) 24,58 (TP II 174), cf. (*dyūtāika-vyasanī yuvā*) 26,196 (TP II 231) and *dyūtāika-vyasano yuvā* 92,14 (TP VII 72); goddess Śrī is treacherous as ~ (*dyūta-lilēva sacchalā*) 62,164 (TP V 113)⁶¹⁰; *yakṣa* gives mendicant (*pravraj*) boon of invincibility in ~ 66,61 (TP V 182); warder is ~ with his king 71,16 (TP VI 37; king is beaten in ~ 72,84 (TP VI 75); sinful vice of ~ (*dyūta-vyasana-pātakam*) 73,76 (TP VI 106); whoever says “I sit out of this game” (*ahaṃ nirgato dyūtād*) cannot be forced to ~ 121,90 (TP IX 18); – see further: dice

gambling-den (*dyūta-śālā*) 73,74 (TP VI 106)⁶¹¹; 73,179 (TP VI 114); 74,140 (TP VI 150); 74,177 (TP VI 153); in ~ (*thiṅṭhā*) the owner pays on behalf of insolvent gambler 92,22 (TP VII 72);

game, of ball (*kanduka-kriḍā*)⁶¹², Death amuses himself with severed heads like ~ 50,7 (TP IV 108); – water-~ (q.v.)

Gaṇa (Śiva's companion) coming on thought (*smṛta-mātrāgata*) 7,83 (TP I 83); bawd made to look like ~, shaved but for five locks, naked and painted half black and vermilion 12,169 (TP I 146 with note 2); ~ assume strange deformed countenances 46,201 (TP IV 62)⁶¹³; at

⁶⁰⁹ See, e.g., Hildebeitel 1987, Saletore 1985: 105ff.; Raghavan 1979: 54.

⁶¹⁰ Kṛṣṇa identifies himself with the gambling of the fraudulent (*dyūtām chalayatām asmi*, Bhag X 36).

⁶¹¹ Cf. Daś 96,2; 113,15; BKŚS 23,35ff.

⁶¹² See Bollée 2008a: 6 s.v.

⁶¹³ Zin 2003b: 173.

Gaṇeśa's order his ~s bring sleeping king to bedroom of sleeping princess 73,336 (TP VI 125); ~s stupefy couple to prevent *gāndharva* marriage 73,350 (TP VI 126); at prayer of her ~s goddess Caṇḍī revives lovers free from passion 95,88 (TP VII 104); – see also: bawd

gaṇaka, see: astrologer

gander, see: goose; *haṃsa*

Gandharva (celestial musician)⁶¹⁴ Tumburu is dancing teacher 17,23 (TP II 35); ~ cursed to become white elephant 36,13 (TP III 170); ~s return to native Mt Malaya 36,131 (TP III 178); ~s sing for Viṣṇu 36,115 (TP III 177); their concert in Kailāsa 50,189 (TP IV 120); birth as ~ as Śaṅkara's boon 74,27 (TP VI 142); ~ 74,239 (TP VI 157); elephant released from curse becomes ~ again 74,315 (TP VI 163); ~ saves Naravāhanadatta from dry well 106,3 (TP VIII 28); ~ kings go to the moon 115,78 (TP VIII 149); ~ maiden abducted by two *rākṣasīs* 116,28 (TP VIII 158); ~ prince Padmaśekhara wants to bestow ivory carver's daughter on prince Muktaḥpalaketu 116,85 (TP VIII 162); song of ~s Hāhā and Hūhū 116,87 (TP VIII 162); ~ princess, born in the world of the moon (17) and unable to go on foot from her apartment to city garden, is carried there by birds 117,21 (TP VIII 165) *gāndharva* marriage⁶¹⁵ of king and princess 3,67 (TP I 23); ~ of brahmin woman with brahmin Nāga prince 6,14f. (TP I 61); ~ of *yakṣa* with daughter of ṛṣi 6,98 (TP I 68); ~ of brahmin with princess 7,82 (TP I 83); ~ of hero with Śavara daughter 10,146 (TP I 116); ~ of king with princess in arbour of creepers in his garden 14,69 (TP I 187); ~ of prince with sylph exposed in basket on river 15,38 and 44 (TP II 4f.); ~ of hero with *vidyādhari* 18,220 (TP II 66); ~ of *vidyādhara* with princess 30,17 (TP III 65); ~ of Uṣā with man dreamt of 31,13 (TP III 82); ~ of disguised *vidyādhara* king Madanavega with Kaliṅga senā 33,173 (TP III 121); 37,186 (TP III 196); ~ of prince and *rākṣasī* 42,143 (TP III 269); ~ as best marriage in the world 45,216 (TP IV 32); prince marries heavenly maiden In the shape of his wife after *svayaṃvara* by ~ 68,14 (TP VI 2); *vidyādhari* chooses husband by ~ 69,90 (TP VI 15); ~ prevented by *gaṇas* 73,350 (TP VI 126); prince marries princess by ~ 74,239 (TP VI 157); prince marries daughter of ivory carver by ~ 75,131 (TP VI 173); king marries *vidyādhara* princess by ~ 86,113 (TP VII 21); brahmin marries princess by ~ 89,55 (TP VII 44)

Gandharva-nagara, see Fata morgana

gāndharva-śālā 'royal concert hall', in ~ king of Vatsa teaches princess Vāsavadattā to sing 12,31 (TP I 135)

Gaṇeśa⁶¹⁶ Vighnaji dancing in the twilight intervals between the Yugas and sweeping away the stars with his trunk 1,2 (TP I 1), cf. 109,1; 73,377 (TP VI 127); impure ministers eat fruits

⁶¹⁴ See Nāṭyaśāstra 3,61 where T. is a *Gandharva*; Ghosh 1961: 24 on T. as author (?); ORC 1570f. Zin 2003b: 153ff.

⁶¹⁵ See note in TP I 87ff. and ORC 1570; Zin 2003b: 155 note 28. The *gāndharva-samāgama* is a rendezvous by mutual agreement (Daś 83.1).

⁶¹⁶ On Gaṇeśa V. see, e.g. Courtright 2001: 164; Krishan 1999 (with large bibliography and many illustrations), Kakar 1982: 100ff. and ORC 1571f. – On Gaṇeśa's dance see Sundaram 1979: 752, Krishan 1999: figs 16, 27 et passim.

of ~'s tree⁶¹⁷ and are cursed to become fruits 100,37 (TP VII 131); may ~'s trunk he throws up in the dance at night protect you ! 105,2 (TP VIII 21); image (lit.: 'visible power') of ~, god of gods, grants boons and his power has been tested (*dṛṣṭa-prabhāvo vara-do deva-devo vināyakaḥ*) 20,55 worshipped he gives maidens a husband 56 (TP II 99); ~ painting the earth with vermilion (*sindūra*) 24,1 (TP II 170); reddening the sky with the vermilion dye on his ears ~ seems to create sunset, even when it is not due 44,1 (TP IV 1)⁶¹⁸; **description** of ~ sitting on *jyotī-rasa*⁶¹⁹ slab, in brightness like twelve suns⁶²⁰, with paunch and three eyes ... **50,176ff. (TP IV 119)**; earth bent under weight of dancing ~ 51,1 (TP IV 122)⁶²¹; ~ sends heavy rain and poisonous snake, and starts to kick king's chest with his tusk (*dantâghātān uraḥ-sthale etya dātum*) 55,159f. (TP IV 213 "began to give him bites on the breast" [*sic* !]; ORC 617: "se mit à lui donner des coups de défense sur la poitrine."; also MI 866); ~ praised as "one whose being implies success in all affairs like an optimum treasure-jar" (*sarvârtha-saṃsiddhi-nidhi-kumbhōpamâtman*) 55,162 (TP IV 213 "one whose body is like a swelling pitcher full of success in all affairs"⁶²²; ORC 617: "être suprême qui, comme une jarre à trésors, contient toutes les réussites"; MI 866: "der du einem Schatzbehälter gleichst, der das Gelingen aller Dinge und das Erreichen jedes Zieles enthält.")⁶²³; ~ with 68 names whose recitation removes fear 55,166 (TP IV 213); ~ invoked 57,1 (TP V 1); his trunk, a sword reddened with vermilion and destroying evil from a distance (*asiṃ dūram agha-cchidam*)⁶²⁴ 57,1 (TP V 1); 67,1 (TP V 196); ~ represented by man with paunch (*lambôdara-rūpiṇi*) 70,125 (TP VI 33); favour of ~-Vighnêśvara gained by worship before setting out 70,131 (TP VI 33); an image of ~ is carved in a *śālmali* (q. v.) tree and worshipped 71,59 (TP VI 40); an image of ~ carved out of a jewel found near tank in Mālava 73,325 (TP VI 124); ~ pleased by *yātrôtsava* (q.v.) foretells hero he will be *saṃrāj* 73,329 (TP VI 124); ~ recognizes Destiny (*bhavitavyam*) 73,334 (TP VI 125); ~ praised by Pāśupata ascetic 73,376 (TP VI 127); ~ (Vighnajit) dancing makes star shower 75,1 (TP VI 164; cf. 1,2 [TP I 1]); ~ residing in tree with fruits and transforming

⁶¹⁷ Despite 71,59 (TP VI 40) this cannot be the *śālmali* tree which is the seat of Garuḍa and whose cotton-wool filled fruits are inedible, but perhaps the Jambu tree whose fruit is mentioned in Gaṇeśa-dhyāna vs 30; it is rarely used at the Gaṇeśapūjā as being available only at the end of the monsoon, but it may be offered to the deity at his birthday and his rassel may be decorated with Jambu twigs (p.c. Dr Mrs Haripriyā Rangarājan). Sen 1965: 47 < BhaṇṣyaPur 11,1,10 only states *durva* grass as sacred to Gaṇeśa.

⁶¹⁸ In the Dvāparayuga, Gaṇeśa is red (Bailey 2008 II: 5).

⁶¹⁹ Cf. Rām II 94,6 < MW. The kind of jewel apparently cannot be specified.

⁶²⁰ Cf. GaṇeśaPur I 12,37.

⁶²¹ As a deity, Gaṇeśa should not touch the earth.

⁶²² Cf. 55,165 where Gaṇeśa is called *ghaṭôdara* 'pitcher-bellied'.

⁶²³ *Upamâtman* is not found in MW and I think *upama* belongs to *kumbha*.

⁶²⁴ B: *asindūra-madya-chidam*; Penzer reads *-mada-* for *-madya-* and renders: "dispelling great arrogance". ORC 647: "qui repousse au loin les péchés"; MI 910: "Ungemach weit von uns hält." A though late other attestation of *agha-cchid-* is in Mallinātha's commentary on KirātārjunIya 3.4 where he glosses *enaḥ-praṇudām* with *agha-cchidām*, and *kilbiṣacchid* in Raghuv 11,34 explained as *pāpa-hāriṇi*, is a parallel (p.c. Isaacson).

by a curse impure eaters into fruits 100,37ff. (TP VII 131), cf. 102,92 (TP VII 169); ~ eulogized 100,44ff. (TP VII 131); in twelfth night of penance ~ sends dream and removes Mṛgānkadatta's curse 100,51 (TP VII 132); tree of ~ Vighnajit worshipped 102,2 (TP VII 162); dancing in the twilight intervals between the *yugas* 104,1 (TP VIII 1); trunk of ~ dancing at night⁶²⁵ called upon as protection (*niśi Vighna-jito vo 'vyāt tāṇḍa vōddaṇḍitaḥ karaḥ*) 105,2 (TP VIII 21); benediction of Gajānana 120,2 (TP IX 1); ~ dancing at night 109,1 (TP VIII 70); – see also: adulterer

Gaṅgā–*dyu-sindhu* propitiated gives minister daily much wealth 4,137 (TP I 41); goddess ~ comes in human form (*mūrtā*) when thought of (*dhyānād upasthitā*) 5,55 (TP I 51); ~ gives brahmin ascetic fruit in dream and reality 74,119 (TP VI 148); ~ appears from middle of river, stops brahmin's suicide, foretells future and gives him spell of seven syllables “Forwards and Backwards” changing one's shape 74,131f. (TP VI 149); ~ playfully pulls Śambhu's hair 93,78 (TP VII 84);

Gaṅges⁶²⁶, sonless brahmin goes to ~ to perform austerities 3,10 (TP I 19); ~ as flowing in three worlds 4,30 (TP I 32); hand appears in the middle of the ~ 5,8 (TP I 45); hero seizes woman in the middle of the ~ by the hair and dives after her to Śiva temple 10,27ff. (TP I 107f.); golden lotuses in heavenly ~ (*vyoma-gaṅgā*)⁶²⁷ 14,19 (TP I 183); (Jāhnavi) flows to the East 18,60 (TP II 54); king sets up pillar of victory (*jaya-stambha*) in ~ delta (*velātaṭānte*) 19,90f. (TP II 92); corpse of *caṇḍāla* rots in ~ 27,128 (TP III 10); bones of executed thief thrown into ~ 64,83 (TP V 146)); robber observes vow of bathing in heavenly ~ (*vyoma-sarit-snāna-japa-vrata-parāyaṇah*) 72,358 (TP VI 95); Viṣṇu's foot creates in Kāśmīra another ~ named Ikṣvati 73,97 (TP VI 108); infernal ~ in Pātāla 73,119 (TP VI 110); waters of ~ impregnated with nectar of moon on Śārva-Śiva's head 74,111 (TP VI 148); ~ appears as necklace on neck of Vārāṇasī 75,60 (TP VI 168)⁶²⁸; suitor throwing bones of dead beloved into ~ is considered her son 76,39 (TP VI 181); ridges of ~ waves seem to make ladder for mortals to ascend heaven 93,77 (TP VII 83); far-reaching boughs of wonderful tree on lake shore, agitated by the wind, appear like arms, and the cloud-stream clinging to its head is like ~ so that it resembled Śiva dancing 100,18 (TP VII 129); queen with steadfastness of ~ (*Gaṅgā-sama-sthiti*) 113,18 (TP VIII 125)⁶²⁹; water of celestial ~ flows brown (*kapiśa*) with pollen of flowers and smells of ichor of elephants due to Śiva's bull playing with Indra's elephant 115,146 (TP VIII 154); ~ is white as the moon and Yamunā black as panic-seed (*priyaṅgu*) 121,226 (TP IX 28)

garbha-dohadā (not MW), see: pregnancy whim

⁶²⁵ For Gaṅeśa as a dancer see Courtright 2001: 6 and 164.

⁶²⁶ See ORC 1572; Darian 1978; Singh 1974.

⁶²⁷ Lüders 1951: 156.

⁶²⁸ Lüders 1951: 156.

⁶²⁹ ORC 1183: “*d'une conduite qui l'égalait au Gange*” to which runs the note (1503 no 1) “*La comparaison n'est possible que parce que le Gange est une divinité féminine, qui, d'autre part, symbolise la pureté.*” M II 575: “*in ihren Tugenden so lauter wie die Gaṅgā.*”

garbha-grāhikā ‘midwife’ tells marvel of substitution of children after inspecting foetus in utero 34,62 (TP III 133)

garbha-gr̥ha ‘inner cell’ of Devī-temple, heavenly maiden enters ~ 81,49 (TP VI 212); of Śiva temple, voice from ~ 118,3 (TP VIII 178);

garbha-śayyā ‘womb’, midwife inspects foetus in ~ 34,63 (TP III 133)

garbha-vāsa ‘stay in the womb’, a man’s wonderful ~ of a big fish 25,52 (TP II 193)

garden, magic ~ in Pratiṣṭhāna made with Durgā’s divine seeds 6,83 (TP I 66), cf. 110,137 (TP VIII 92)⁶³⁰; Kālarātri lands cow-house in vegetable ~ (*śāka-vāṭaka*) 20,142 (TP II 108); heavenly ~ made by king 28,52 (TP III 24); idem, made by Somaprabhā 34,142 (TP III 138); goddess of ~ (*upavana-devatā*) 35,12 (TP III 156); king sees wonderful ~ (*udyāna*) like Nandana due to his great virtue (*svaya-sattva-mahātmya*) 72,182 (TP VI 82); *divya-pādapa* seems to stand erect out of curiosity to see the beauty of the ~ of Nandana 100,19 (TP VII 129); Gaṇḍa-śaila, pleasure ~ of the celestial ladies (*dyu-yoṣit*) 109,41 (TP VIII 73); – see also: cardamom tree; clove-tree; concert-hall; doubt; fire

garjāñ-jalada ‘thundercloud’ 101,140 (TP VII 143)

garland(s) (*mālya*) offered to Śiva in order to become a *Gaṇa* 7,109 (TP I 86); snake gives king who saved it the art of weaving unfading ~s 9,81 (TP I 100); Nārada gives king ~ (*sraja*) from paradise tree (*pārijāta*) 15,129 (TP II 13)⁶³¹; unfading ~ (*a-mlāna-mālā*) made by queen 16,31 (TP II 22); ~ of eyes resembling blue lotus (*locanêndīvara-srajaḥ*) 18,22 (TP II 51), cf. 67,22 (TP V 196) and 106,29 (TP VIII 30) et passim; ~ of wife’s arms (*bhujā-latā*) around husband’s neck 18,369 (TP II 77); ~ of *vidyā-dhara* dropped on Nārada 22,138f. (TP II 147); princess throws ~ of blue eyes (*nayanôtpala-mālikā*) over hermit 28,79 (TP III 26); suitor puts ~⁶³² over neck of chosen bride 39,107 (TP III 225); monsoon with ~ of lightning 44,177 (TP IV 13); celestial ~ of Bhavānī given to bride 50,135 (TP IV 116); Damayantī’s ~ of Nala’s election (*varaṇa-mālā*) at *svayaṃvara* 56,277 (TP IV 239); wife blackmails husband with a request for a ~ of blue lotuses for a feast, otherwise she would leave him 62,227 (TP V 118); magician honours corpse with red ~⁶³³ and unguent 73,305 (TP VI 123 “with unguents and ~s of blood”; ORC 869: “... *avec des guirlandes et des onguents de sang*”)⁶³⁴; princess puts ~ of blue lotuses (eyes) on king 90,56 (TP VII 53); *brahma-rākṣasa* wears wreath of entrails (*antra-mālā*)⁶³⁵ 94,69 (TP VII 91); princess

⁶³⁰ Cf. STh A 151.2.

⁶³¹ Garlands just as necklaces transmit beneficial power (Gonda 1975 IV 196); cf., e.g., references such as KSS 119,21 which deal with *ratnaiḥ khecaratvādi-dāyibhiḥ* and 27 *cūḍā-ratnaṃ ... viṣa-rakṣo-jarā-roga-haraṃ*.

⁶³² For this purpose often Madhūka flowers (Bassia or madhuca latifolia) are used (Upadhyaya 1965: 16; Syed 1990: 490f. with many references). Macmillan 1991: 442 does not mention the flowers of this large spreading tree, common to Central India.

⁶³³ People to be executed also wear a red garland (Bollée 2005: 116) which represents their dedication to death just as when Roman soldiers wear a blood-red garment in combat (Samter 1901: 55). See also, e.g., von Duhn 1906.

⁶³⁴ Cf. Mbh 3,264,65 where Kumbhakarna, c.s. with these accessories of the condemned are dragged toward the south; in 10,8,64 it is an epitheton of Kālī who is said to have a bloody mouth and eyes, wears a red (or: bloody) garland and is smeared with red unguent.

throws a look on a prince as it were a ~ of blue lotuses and therewith chooses him as her husband 106,29 (TP VIII 30); coronation with ~ of (red) *mandāra* flowers 110,82 (TP VIII 88); Indra gives his own ~ (*hāra*) to victorious prince 116,82 (TP VIII 162); Indra gives ~ from *pārijāta* (Paradise) tree 118,118 (TP VIII 186); ~ to remain fresh as long as wife remains faithful 123,148 (TP IX 53); – see also: eyes; fidelity; Pārvatī garment,⁶³⁶ poor woman’s tattered and dirty ~ (*viśīrṇa-malinâmbarā*) 2,51 (TP I 13); prince’s ~ marked by princess with red lac for recognition after *gāndharva* marriage 3,71 (TP I 23); woman in white ~ (*śuklâmbara-dharā*) 4,9 (TP I 31); idem (*dhavalâmbarā*) 6,139 (TP I 71); bathing queens’ ~s cling to their bodies (*saktâmbara-*) 6,111 (TP I 69; cf. 108,147 [TP VIII 64]); *apsaras* whose robe is blown aside by the wind (*vāta-visraṃsitâṃśukā*) 9,24 (TP I 96); ~ with hidden necklace in corner, stolen and hidden in lake 10,167 (TP I 117); ~s taken away from drunk seducer leaving him *digambara* 13,147 (TP I 160); minister honoured with ~ (killut) 14,60 (TP I 187); ~s as royal present for ignorant brahmin amusing a king 20,44 (TP II 98); two ~s as presents for *purohita* 24,113 (TP II 178); white ~ (*sitâmbara*) of *brahmacāriṇī* 29,53 (TP III 42); hermit’s daughter clothed in ~ of bark 32,106 (TP III 98); woman with raiment pellucid like moonlight (*vyotsnâccha-vasanā*) 38,124 (TP III 215); princess in white ~s in dream 43,2 (TP III 281); ~ made in China, “*crêpe de Chine*” (*Cīna-deśaja-sad-vastra*)⁶³⁷ 43,75 (TP III 286); the sea adorned with its shore is like a ~ with a beautiful fringe 43,248 (TP III 298); red ~ of *Asura* Maya 45,4 (TP IV 17); Śūdra weaving five pairs of ~ daily 52,99 (TP IV 144); princess covering face with ~ (*svôttariyeṇa*) before dying 52,150 (TP IV 148; see above sub: capite velato); ~ of leather (*carma-khaṇḍa-vasana*) of a *kārpaṭika* 53,2 and 12 (TP IV 168f.); citron exchanged for ~ (*śāṭaka*) given by *bhikṣu* 53,38 (TP IV 170); ~ divided to make two (*vāsasī*) of it 53,55 (TP IV 171, cf. below 56,317 [TP IV 243]); four men with heavenly ~s 54,15 (TP IV 184); *aśoka*-like red ~ of royal attendants 55,113 (TP IV 210); Nala throws upper ~ over two dice in the form of *haṃsas* but they fly away with it 56,311 (TP IV 242); Nala cuts off half of Damayantī’s ~, and leaves 56,317 (TP IV 243); Nala becomes two magic ~s called *agni-śauca* ‘fire-bleached’⁶³⁸ from snake 56,351 (TP IV 245) and 411 (TP IV 250); four *yakṣas* with heavenly ~s 57,27 (TP V 3); ~s wrapped round leather trunks (*vastra-peṭā*) spoilt by rain 62,199 (TP V 116)⁶³⁹; Nereid keeps lovers’ rings in corner of ~ 63,31 (TP V 122); prince going out at night wearing dark ~s (*nīla-*

⁶³⁵ As garland or *yajñopavīta* ?

⁶³⁶ Schlingloff in a letter (17.7.2011) points out that even after the Ajanta period men and women went stripped to the waist. This was also the case in the Hindu island of Bali in Indonesia still in the early twentieth century, whereas the ladies on the Sigiriya reliefs (Ceylon, 14th century C.E.) wear a very thin and diaphanous kind of *cholis*. At Kād 186,3 a curious *yauvanônmatā* is told to cover her breasts as she can be seen by people; another woman whose upper garment has fallen, is laughed at (Kād 186,5). *Devaputras* wear heavenly garments (*divya-vastra*) at 54,12 (TP IV 184). – See further Ghurye 1966: 225ff.; Dange 1937: 591ff.

⁶³⁷ Cf. Amaru 86 *cīnâṃśuka*.

⁶³⁸ ORC 642: ‘*purification par le feu*’. Cf. 61,31 (TP V 70).

⁶³⁹ Avadāna 104 (Penzer).

vāsasi) 71,22 (TP VI 37)⁶⁴⁰; ~ as honourable present to guest 71,98 (TP VI 42); ~ on which princess wrote stanza 71,98 (TP VI 43); brahmin with no decent ~ (*an-ucitāmbara*) is ashamed to leave gambling hall 73,74 (TP VI 106); tattered ~ of ascetic (*cīra-vāsa*) 73,100 (TP VI 108); magician on charnel ground wears turban made of ~ of the dead and black ~ (*saṃvītāsita-vāsasa*) 73,283 (TP VI 121); clad in black ~, king goes out to charnel ground in black fortnight 75,41 (TP VI 166f.: “he enveloped his head in a black cloth” with reference to Speyer 1908: 133, ORC 899: “*vētu de noir*”; M II)⁶⁴¹; ragged ~ (*karpaṭa*), torn in the presence of a king, makes a *rājput* a vassal (*kārpaṭika*) 81,6 (TP VI 209); *sūdra* daily weaves five ~s 83,22 (TP VII 22); princess makes noose with upper ~ in order to hang herself 90,73 (TP VII 54) and 103,42 (TP VII 176); Jīmūtavāhana offers his body covered in ~s (*vastra-channa*)⁶⁴² to Garuḍa 90,135 (TP VII 58); sky as ~ of sun 92,30 (TP VII 73); hermit’s daughter with dress of bark (*valkalāmśuka*) 94,19 (TP VII 88); nymph of night veils her shape in black robe of darkness 94,52 (TP VII 91); merchant’s daughter sits in a window dressed in thin ~ of silk (*saṃvīta-tanu-kaśeya-*) 95,17 (TP VII 99); at rite with corpse, mendicant (*bhikṣu*) puts on ~s of corpse (*prāvṛtta-preta-vasana*) 99,11 (TP VII 123); moon puts on white bark-robe of moonlight (*candrikā-dhauta-valkala*) 101,32 (TP VI 136); Śabara wears loin-cloth (*kaṭi-nivasana*) of *bilva*-leaves 101,355 (TP VII 158); at royal wedding even trees had ~s fastened to them making them look like earthly wishing-trees 103,199 (TP VII 188)⁶⁴³; the wanton nymph Night is beautiful with her waving black robe of darkness (*vilasat-timirā-sitāmśu-kāntā ... rātrī*) 103,203 (TP VII 189); ~ white as moonlight (*jyotsnā-sitair vastraiḥ*) 106,137 (TP VIII 38); Sitā in ~ of bark (*valkala-dhāriṇī*) 107,14 (TP VIII 44); *vidyādhari* with white body and ~ (*sitātma-vastra*) 107,39 (TP VIII 46); *vidyādhari* queen wears black deerskin as ~ 107,63 (TP VIII 47); hermit advises minister to carry off ~ of bathing *divyā stri* 108,68 (TP VIII 58)⁶⁴⁴; emperor watches with pleasure moist skintight ~ (*aṅga-lagnārdra-vāsasaḥ*) on bathing wives 108,147 (TP VIII 64, cf. 6,111 [TP I 69]); Caṇḍāla maiden makes swing with her upper ~ (*uttariya*) fastened to tusks of elephant 112,70 (TP VIII 111); Indra gives own ~ to victorious prince 116,82 (TP VIII 162); Deva (Bhairava) tells gambler to pinch ~s (*vāsāṃsi*) from bathing *apsaras* 121,110 (TP IX 20); Bhillā women wear skirts of peacock-tails (*vāsāṃsi barhi-picchāni*) 123,50 (TP IX 46); deserted wife procures ~ suitable to a courtesan and enters Ujjayinī as a *lokāika-sundarī* 124,173 (TP IX 80); – see also: *baddhōttariyaka*; bark; Bhillā; *brahma-cāriṇī*; disguise; dress; hermit; hunting-coat;

⁶⁴⁰ Cf. Kād 132,6 where a king goes out at night in dark cloak to meet women (*nila-paṭa-viracitāvaguṇṭhana bahula-pakṣa-pradoṣa-datta-saṃketāḥ sundarīr abhisasāra*).

⁶⁴¹ B: *nila-vasana-samālaṃkṛta-śekharaḥ*. The reading of the stanza in D: *pradoṣe nila-vasanas tamāla-kṛta-śekharaḥ* is less conspicuous than in Tawney. Invisibility may be better guaranteed when clad in black than only by a black turban.

⁶⁴² See Zin 2002: 154 where in the notes 33-35 read: XC instead of XL. In the parallel versions the clothes are said to be red, the colour of execution rags (Bollée 2002: 114 with note 832), as desired by Garuḍa.

⁶⁴³ For dressed trees see, e.g., Haberman 2013: 148ff., especially 162f.

⁶⁴⁴ STh K 1335; T 56.3.

kāṣāya; *kaupina*; old woman

Garuḍa,⁶⁴⁵ ~ carries elephant carcass to other side of sea to Laṅkā 12,113 (TP I 142); ~ obtains snakes as food from Viṣṇu 22,190 (TP II 151); ~ carries off pregnant queen in lake of red liquid as if blood due to *dohada* 9,46ff. (TP I 98)⁶⁴⁶ and 30,47 (TP III 67); ~ attacks white elephant 36,24 (TP III 170); Hari on ~ appears king in dream 38,58 (TP III 210); Nala driving royal chariot faster than ~ (Tārksya) 56,374 (TP IV 247); ~ finds snake (*nāga*) in house of courtesan and eats it 61,178 (TP V 83); ~ gives up eating snakes 90,195 (TP VII 62); nectar in arms of ~ Sudhāhartṛ 110,126 (TP VIII 91); – see also: bewilderment; *bhāti*; bone(s), compassion; *darbha*; depression; disguise; dream; elephant(s); five days; garment; gift; hair; Hari; lie; Lohajaṅga; Nāga; nectar; old woman; overhearing; promise; rain; resuscitation; serpent-weapon; slavery; snake(s); son; turtle; Udayācala; Viṣṇu; weapon; wishing-tree

Garuḍāstra, see: *Garuḍa*-weapon

Garuḍa-weapon (*gāruḍa*) of Mukṭāphaladhvaḥja 116,71 (TP VIII 161); ~ set against snake-weapon of *Asura* king 118,81 (TP VIII 183);

gate in Pātāla guarded by two iron rams (*meṣa*) 73,131 (TP VI 110); child laid at royal ~ 93,52 (TP VII 82)⁶⁴⁷

gāthā, bard recites ~ in praise of prince 71,69 (TP VI 40)

gati, see: bliss; gait

gaurāṅgī 'fair-hued maid', reading of B, see: *sa-nīraṅgī*

Gaurī needs no sex to get son from Śiva 20,67 (TP II 101); ~ visibly (*sākṣād āgatya*) rains *amṛta* on Jīmūtavāhana 22,246 (TP II 155); ~ propitiated by Uṣā for a husband shows her the one in a dream 31,11 (TP III 81); hymn in praise of ~ by *divyāṅganāḥ* 34,253 (TP III 147); ~ playfully pulling Śiva's hair 35,1 (TP III 155); ~ gives instructions in dream 35,135 (TP III 166); figure of ~ sculpted on pillar 37,9 (TP III 183); ~ = Bhavanī propitiated for a son 42,56 (TP III 263); ~ orders Sumeru to give his daughter to Sūryaprabha 50,125 (TP IV 116); ~ propitiated gives king an only daughter 52,93 (TP IV 144); ~ propitiated gives *vidyādhari* magic sciences 59,13 (TP V 26) and instructions in a dream 59,16 (TP V 27); ~ appears in vivo and relates how Kuvera (Dhanada) curses two *yakṣas* to become brahminy ducks on lake Mānasa 72,43 (TP VI 71); ~ bestows magic sword and white horse on snake princess 72,47 (TP VI 72); temple (*āyatana*) of ~ in Śobhāvātī 80,5 (TP VI 204) and 80,23 (TP VI 206); *vidyādhara* princess worships ~ 86,133 (TP VII 22); ~ curses the *rājarṣi* Iḍa to become a woman 89,85 (TP VII 46); maiden plays *viṇā* in temple of ~ to please deity 90,41 (TP VII 51f.); ~ promises husband to princess 90,76 (TP VII 54); ~ appears visibly (*pratyakṣatām agāt*) and sprinkles dead Jīmūtavāhana with *amṛta* thus reanimating him 90,185 (TP VII 61); Jīmūtavāhana (Bodhisattva !) worships ~ 90,187 (TP VII 62); ~ worships Gaṇeśa 100,48 (TP VII 131); princess worships ~ to ensure her

⁶⁴⁵ See note in TP I 103ff.; ORC 1573. Cf. Hensgen 1958: 134.

⁶⁴⁶ Cf. Zin 2003b: 134 note 25.

⁶⁴⁷ Cf. STh S 335.

father's success in combat 103,15 (TP VII 176); ~ asked by princess for certain husband in next birth 103,51 (TP VII 178); ~ praised 103,72 (TP VII 180); ~ (Ambikā) appoints husband to princess in a dream 103,181f. (TP VII 187); *vidyādhara* queen as incarnated portion of ~ (*Gaury-aṃśā*) 115,126 (TP VIII 153); Meghavana temple of ~ 116,13 (TP VIII 157); lake near temple of ~ 116,25 (TP VIII 158); near death (*vadha-prāpta*) king calls to mind magic science of ~ (*Gaurī-vidyā*) 107,105 (TP VIII 50); *vidyādhara* princess as incarnated portion of ~ (*Gaury-aṃśā-jātā*) 115,126 (TP VIII 153); meet of lovers in *āśram* of ~ (Girijāśrama) 117,121 (TP VIII 172); – see also: Ambikā

Gaurīśa = Śiva as origin of the world's creation, preservation and destruction (*jagat-sarga-sthiti-saṃhāra-hetu*) and visible form of the eight special forms of ether, etc. (*vyomādi-bheda-bhinnāṣṭa-mūrti*) 35,99 (TP III 163)

Gaurī-vidyā 'science of G.' appears in visible form with three eyes and trident to *vidyādhara* king 107,105f. (TP VIII 50) and 132 (TP VIII 52);

Gaury-āyatana, see: Durgā temple

Gayā-kūpa, see: *piṇḍa*

gems, chest with false ~ (*kṛtrima-māṇikyā*-) in deposit 24,133 (TP II 179); – see also: jewels

gender, see : change of ~

gender-neutral jewelry, see: crest-jewel; necklace (117,116 [TP VIII 172])

generosity of woman grieved by separation from lover 38,101 (TP III 213), cf. charity and see also: sonlessness⁶⁴⁸; ~ of Jīmūtavāhana 90,192 (TP VII 62)

genetic/innate/natural, to have mercy upon the wretched is ~ quality/condition (*nisarga*) of the great 25,116 (TP II 200); ~ fickleness of women (q. v.); ~ hatred (q. v.); ~ robber 72,192 (TP VI 82); 72,324 (TP VI 193)

genitals, see: ascetic; *liṅga*; *varāṅga*; *vulva*; wound

geography of India 18,58ff. (TP II 53f.)

gesture(s)⁶⁴⁹: royal remorse (*anutāpa*) 5,67 (TP I 52); hermit becomes puffed up with pride 5,135 (TP I 58); king exalts queen above all others by sprinkling / inaugurating her with water through affection (*prītyābhiścīya*) 6,167 (TP I 73); rolling on the ground as love symptom 7,66 (TP I 81), see also: rolling; looking in the face intentionally 9,26 (TP I 96); knowing language of gestures (*iṅgīta-jñā*) 10,93 (TP I 112); ~ of bowing or falling at some one's feet (*caraṇā-nata*) 10,96 (TP I 113), see: feet; making sign to wait by lifting left hand 11,69 (TP I 127); woman clinging to man's neck in joy (*hr̥ṣṭā kaṇṭhe lagnā*) 12,88 (TP I 139); king crying out like common man (*prākṛta*) 13,60 (TP I 154); kissing mouth 13,108 (TP I 158); giving with own hand as honour 14,60 (TP I 187), cf. hand; ~ of remorse by king for adultery 14,66 (TP I 187); king regretful (*unmanas*) at rejecting lady offered to him previously 15,75 (TP II 8); boyish grimaces (*vikārās ca bālôcitāḥ*) 16,46 (TP II 25); king falls on the ground when told that his queen was burnt 16,49 (TP II 25)⁶⁵⁰; sister embracing

⁶⁴⁸ The principle seems to be kind of homoeopathic: to enable fate or some deity by own charity or generosity to give the important object one wants.

⁶⁴⁹ See Kuv note 832; Boss 1976: 106; 116; Coomaraswamy 2010..

(*kaṇṭhe jagrāha*) brother 16,95 (TP II 28), cf. brahmin embraces merchant 26,118 (TP II 226); rinsing mouth and turning to the east before swearing 16,117 (TP II 30); king seeing queen returned from banishment falls on the earth delirious with the poison of grief (*śoka-
viṣa-vihvala*) 16,106 (TP II 29); lifting up neck joyfully in imitation of peafowl at the coming of rain-clouds 16,121 (TP II 30); ~ of whirling around threatening forefinger as it were the decree of Death (*bhrāmayāmāsa Yamājñām iva tarjinīm*) 17,88 (TP II 41); *apsaras* looking askance with wrinkled brows (*sāci-kṛta-dṛśā mukhena valita-bhrūṇā*) at husband 17,128 (TP II 44); love-scratching of the earth by the hoofs of the king's horse 18,7 (TP II 49); confused hum of delight at return of king (*ānanda-lasat-kalakālā-rava*) 18,119 (TP II 58); savage ~ 18,108 (TP II 57); tears of joy (*harṣa-bāṣpa*) 18,369 (TP II 77); do, 69,96 (TP VI 15); clasped hands on head (*śirōvari-citāñjali*) as token of submission 19,87 (TP II 91); faces fixed on earth (*adho-mukha*) from confusion 20,215 (TP II 115); face cast down from modesty (*lajjayāvanatānanā*) 22,121 (TP II 146); old age seizes king by the chin 22,159 (TP II 149); hypocritical face (*sadambha-caturānana*) 24,96 (TP II 176); without alteration of facial expression (*abhinna-mukha-cchāyam*) 24,196 (TP II 183); fisher-king bestows blessing (*svasti-kāra*) on man crept out of fish belly 25,53 (TP II 194); embrace and tears of joy (*harṣa-bāṣpa*) 25,66 (TP II 195); eyes expanded with joy 25,230 (TP II 208); royal daughters bow at father's feet 26,280 (TP II 238); king feigns anger in order to stop merchant's son from falsely blaming his father 27,28 (TP III 3); hermit tears out one eye to show female admirer who praised his eyes by offering it to her as a mass of flesh and blood 28,21ff. (TP III 28f.); etiquette towards visitors: princess rising up politely (*ādarāt*) and embracing alien woman (disguised *asurī*), making her take a seat and asking her descent and name 28,108f. (TP III 28); two women swear friendship with plighted hands (*anyonya-hasta-graha-puraḥsaram*) 28,110 (TP III 28); tasting of another's food as sign of friendship 28,118 (TP III 29); laughing countenance (*hasad ivānana*) of princess with eyes wide open 29,25 (TP III 41); princess kneels before *brahma-cāriṇī* and receives her hospitably with fruits 29,54 (TP III 42); sun on western mountain, stretching forth rays like fingers, as if saying: "Wait patiently one night" 29,126 (TP III 48); tears as a second necklace 30,27 (TP III 65); delated eye, and hand on heart of woman in love 31,46 (TP III 85); distraction pretended 32,10 (TP III 91); minister leaves king after taking ceremonious farewell (*praṇāmya*) 33,86 (TP III 113); mouse dances for joy at seeing cat caught in noose 33,115 (TP III 116); queen bows before minister 33,192 (TP III 123); Creator puts Śiva's order on his head, i. e. obeys him 34,45 (TP III 131); daughter of Kaliṅgasenā clings to face of nurse as the candle to the wick 34,98 (TP III 135); prince with the lotus of his face expanded (*phulla-mukhāmbhoja*) beholds princess as the bed of water-lilies beholds ... the sun 34,101 (TP III 135f.); girl cannot gaze enough at lover, as the female partridge can never be sated with gazing on the moon 34,102 (TP III 136); king honours ministers' sons and servants with clothes and ornaments at good news 34,119 (TP III 137); friendship between women expressed by throwing arms around neck (*kaṇṭha-graha*) 34,135 (TP III 138); hospitable

⁶⁵⁰ Cf. 16,106 (TP II 29) when king falls on the earth delirious with poison of grief.

entertainment (*ātithya*) in magic garden 34,153 (TP III 139); eyes expanded with delight (*praharṣōtphulla-nayana*) 35,7 (TP III 155); brahmin blesses king and bows before him (*svasti-pūrvaṃ sa rājānaṃ praṇamya*) 35,81 (TP III 161); *yakṣa* lets king make gold from copper and leaves smiling 35,88 (TP III 162); princess' eyes cast down from modesty (*trapā-namra-mukha*) 35,150 (TP III 167); royal mother-in-law performs ceremonies for her son-in-law before he starts to return to his own city 35,160 (TP III 168); king arrives, like stream of nectar to the eyes of his mother 35,161 (TP III 168); *vidyādhari* anoints back of merchant out of affection 37,16 (TP III 184); eyes of woman fixed on face of beloved 37,21 (TP III 184); woman's shame disregarded by eagerness (*autsukyāgaṇita-trapā*) 37,103 (TP III 190); embracing (*kanthāśleṣam upāgacchati*) 37,104 (TP III 190); witch fastens string round man's neck as if in loving sport (*praṇaya-kriḍā-vyājād*) 37,153 (TP III 194); *yakṣi* bowing before departing 37,183 (TP III 196); embraces (*ālīṅgana*) 37,184 (TP III 196) and 38,126 (TP III 215); love expressed by timidly looking with sidelong glance (*kaṭākṣārdha-vilokinī*) 37,210 (TP III 198); loss of love expressed by non-embracing and pretended headache 37,213 (TP III 198); woman's face cast down for shame at discovered adultery 37,230 (TP III 199); woman, at a loss for an answer (*an-uttarā*), is weeping 37,233 (TP III 199); king secretly leaves realm for city of enemy 38,17 (TP III 207); king salutes courtesan without telling who he is 38,30 (TP III 208); attendants comfort grieved courtesan 38,92 (TP III 213); woman throws noose of arms around neck of lover 38,126 (TP III 215); queen shows assumed sadness in her face 39,25 (TP III 219); king conquers anger 39,31 (TP III 220); king assumes anger (*kṛta-kopa*) 39,33 (TP III 220); princess puts necklace on her head to enable prince to recognize her amid her sisters 39,113 (TP III 225); husband smiling at wife's magic 39,177 (TP III 230); king applauds queen's speech (*vākyam abhinandati*) 39,223 (TP III 234); performing ceremony to end despondency (*kṛtôdāra-nirvic-chamana-maṅgala*) 39,199 (TP III 232); minister bowing down with shame (*trapā-nata*) before prince 40,37 (TP III 243); queen performs auspicious ceremonies to ensure her sons' success in their conquest of the regions 42,83 (TP III 265); sign of *rākṣasa*'s sister allows prince to kill her brother 42,132f. (TP III 269); elder brother embraces younger 42,177 (TP III 272); shaking head in astonishment and joy (*sa-vismaya-pramadâkampita-mastaka*) 43,256 (TP III 299); faces of enraged *vidyādhara* females are furrowed with frowns and with reddened eyes 44,53 (TP IV 4); people with eyes the lashes of which were upraised through wonder 44,72 (TP IV 6); yawning 45,120 (TP IV 26); king congratulates (*abhinandati*) hero at resuscitation 45,128 (TP IV 26) and 155 (TP IV 28); looking with an eye of longing affection (*sôtsukayā dṛśā*) 45,142 (TP IV 27); when looking at hero *Asura* princess's skill in expressing sentiments by ~ forsakes her as if in anger at beholding her want of modesty 45,238 (TP IV 33); emotion of princess playing in theatre makes spectators end spectacle saying: "The princess is tired" 45,239 (TP IV 33); princess looking askance (*tiryak-paśyanti*) 45,240 (TP IV 33); looking askance with an angry red eye (*tiryak-kopa-kaṣāyena paśyanti cakṣusā*) 45,274 (TP IV 35) and 49,132 (TP IV 94) below; maidens shocked and ashamed at collectively being married to the same husband 45,301f. (TP IV 37); present of daughter as hospitable entertainment 45,311 (TP

IV 37); cheated princesses are angry, ashamed and terrified 45,263f. (TP IV 35); kissing on the head (*mūrdhni paricumbya*) and blessing 45,366 (TP IV 41); angry Maghavā (Indra) lifts up his *vajra* 45,393 (TP IV 43); Kaśyapa makes noise of anger (*kopa-huṃkāra*) 45,393 (TP IV 43); face red with anger 45,394 (TP IV 43); angry wives of hermit Kaśyapa cry "shame !" (*dhik-kāra*) 45,394 (TP IV 43); Indra seizes Maya by the hand to propitiate him 45,412 (TP IV 45); kings seeing Sūryaprabha arrived are weeping in despair, eager to die 46,3 (TP IV 49); feigned anger (*kṛtaka-krodha*) 46,17 (TP IV 50); Śiva's *gaṇas* assume strange, deformed countenances (*vicitra-vikṛtānana*) 46,201 (TP IV 62); triumphant shout of victory 48,67 (TP IV 79); rolling eyes of fearful cook 49,39 (TP IV 87); looking askance with an angry eye (*tiryak-krodhēddhayā dṛśā*) 49,132 (TP IV 94); ~ of rising when Indra comes 49,190 (TP IV 98); Indra curses brahmin for not rising at his entering 49,192 (TP IV 98); sign from a distance forbidding to kill enemy 50,19 (TP IV 109); angry roar of Śiva 50,89 (TP IV 113); gods and *Asuras* embrace each other (*kaṇṭha-lagna*) 50,97 (TP IV 114); when parched grain is thrown (*lāja-visarge*) into the marriage fire Bhavānī sends the bride a celestial garland, a necklace keeping off hunger, thirst and death, and a string of jewels conserving youth 50,135ff. (TP IV 116f.); Sumeru invites gods, *Asuras*, etc. with palms folded above his head (*baddho mūrdhni mayāñjaliḥ*) to eat in his house 50,142 (TP IV 117); Sūryaprabha flatters (*anurañjayati*) his wife 50,159 (TP IV 118); king's head wives address king with playfully sarcastic, sweet, affectionate and bashful⁶⁵¹ turns of speech 50,162 (TP IV 118); Śiva's hand on back of prostrated man to make him rise up 50,193 (TP IV 120); gods and *Asuras* congratulate king Sūryaprabha 50,202 (TP IV 120); Rāma burst into tears at seeing his sons 51,110 (TP IV 130); princess covering face with garment before dying 52,150 (TP IV 148); general Prabhāsa bringing inauguration water with his own hands 50,203 (TP IV 121); due performance of rites of hospitality 51,215 (TP IV 136); woman clasping round neck of king (*sā kaṇṭhe ṇṇpam agrahīt*) 52,356 (TP IV 163); woman desirous to be kissed (*paricumbana-lālasā*) 52,357 (TP IV 163); prince dismisses Mātali, Indra's charioteer, after honouring him (*pūjitam*) 54,67 (TP IV 189); names of *apsaras* inquired from their maids 54,75 (TP IV 189); queen crying out of indignation with head on palm of left hand 55, 124 (TP IV 210); king falling at feet of queen in order to propitiate her 55,130 (TP IV 211); washing one's feet in the evening 56,288 (TP IV 241); embracing at welcome 57,146 (TP V 11) and after remembering pre-birth 59,175 (TP V 38); minister feigns ~ not felt (*kṛtaka-duḥkhita*) 58,30 (TP V 17); weeping parrot 59,36 (TP V 28); *divya-kanyakā* performs duty of hospitality to prince 59,82 (TP V 32 "bash fully"); lion will attack when it erects tail and rises on four feet 60,196 (TP V 58); ~ of a dog, rolling at the feet of a man it knows 61,212 (TP V 86); young wife embraces old husband out of fear of burglar 62,85 (TP V 106); looking at someone's face with significant expression (*sākūtaṃ*) 66,121 (TP V 187); king and daughter weep after long separation so that even eyes of deer in the forest gushed with tears 66,148 (TP V 189);

⁶⁵¹ "The perhaps preferred quality of women, namely, bashfulness (*lajjā*) ... is very seductive ..." (Rossella 2004: 99).

honouring a person by letting him walk in front of one 67,18 (TP V 197); lion in dream puts out tongue at someone 69,25 (TP VI 10); Mātāṅga king puts head on ground to show himself as someone's slave 71,14 (TP VI 37); shaking hands as sign of agreement 71,29 (TP VI 38); peacock rolling on the ground at the feet of prince in order to show string tied round its neck 71,54 (TP VI 39); asking a guest whether he has spent the night pleasantly (*pr̥ṣṭa-rātri-saukhya*) 71,290 (TP VI 57); prohibitive shake of the head 72,20f. (TP VI 69); princess curving her hand like a shoot (*pāṇi-preṅkhita-pallavāṃ vallim iva*) in dancing⁶⁵² 71,77 (TP VI 41); honouring Indra with inclination of the head (*praṇamya*) 72,393 (TP VI 98); king takes adult daughter, downcast with shame at masculine ornaments, on lap and consoles her 73,364 (TP VI 127); mother lays face close to wounded son and weeps bitterly 74,54 (TP VI 144); prince and minister weeping deeply moved at being reunited after long separation 74,320 (TP VI 163); ivory-carver's daughter strikes go-between on the cheeks with camphor-white hands 75,101 (TP VI 171); pressing three fingers dyed red on heart of go-between 75,111 (TP VI 172); witch makes horrible contortions (*vikāra*) with her face when trying to take away rosary (*akṣa-mālikā*) from ascetic 75,175 (TP VI 176); Rājput rags his garment and thus becomes king's vassal 81,6 (TP VI 209); princess has too great modesty (*hrepaṇa*) for *svayamvara* 83,15f. (TP VII 3); merchant on ship seeing king jump into sea is so afflicted that he wants to commit suicide 86,86 (TP VII 19); at sight of king, mermaid leaves bed out of excitement (*saṃbhrama*) 86,99 (TP VII 20); honouring by directing full-blown lotuses of wide-expanded eyes on someone's feet 86,100 (TP VII 20); princess replies foreign king with mixed feelings of shame, affection and joy 86,105 (TP VII 20); princess in solitary abode feels melancholic (*nirviṇṇā*) 86,108 (TP VII 21); anxiously rolling eyes (*sa-śaṅka-lola-nayana*) (of thief at night) 88,16 (TP VII 36); being of pale hue (*pāṇḍura-cchāya*) from separation from beloved 89,36 (TP VII 42); face cast down through shame for not honouring guest 90,54 (TP VII 52); princess drawing lines on the ground 90,80 (TP VII 54); world is full of people with self-pity (q.v.) 90,140 (TP VII 58); lotuses moved by the wind toward a person and then raised again look like beckoning hands 94,16 (TP VII 88 note 2); social feeling of seven-years-old brahmin boy to offer himself to *brahma-rakṣas* 94,92 (TP VII 93); king embraces hermit's feet 94,38 (TP VII 90); all participants of human sacrifice joined hands (*racitāñjali*) and looked at laughing face of boy to be killed 94,125 (TP VII 96); parents embrace corpse of dead son 97,18 (TP VII 113); old hermit first weeps, then dances (for joy) with gesticulations before entering young brahmin's body 97,33 (TP VII 114); king comes to meet proposed son-in-law bowing humbly (*praśrayāvanata*) 101,166 (TP VII 145); sign (*saṃjñā*) given to steersman to set ship in motion 101,268 (TP VII 152); feast (*kṛtōtsava*) at kings return 101,360 (TP VII 159);

⁶⁵² This is a mark of *kāthaka* as against *Bhārat nāṭyam* dancing style, for, as Dr Katrin Binder (p.c.) kindly informs me, in the former the basic position of the hands is the *pathaka-hasta* with stretched fingers; the thumb lies over the palm so that its top rests under the base of the ring finger. This causes a slightly bent back of the hand. In *Bhārat nāṭyam* the basic position is *tri-pathaka-hasta* where, however, the ring finger is bent. The thumb then moves sideways. The movements are angular; elbows and other joints are stretched which is not done in *kāthaka*. See further on *kāthaka*: Rebling 1981: 199-221. Maharaj 2002 describes the *mudrās* without explanation

king embraced by another and asked after his health (*pr̥ṣṭa-kuśala*) 102,68 (TP VII 167); messenger inquired after his health 102,133 (TP VII 172); some people, biting their lips and wringing their hands together (*danta-daṣṭāuṣṭhā mṛdnantaḥ svān karān karaiḥ*) want to kill insolent, but inviolable messenger 102,147 (TP VII 173); minister points out prince to princess with his finger (? *darśayann agra-pāṇinā*) 103,59 (TP VII 179; OPRC 1074: “*en désignant Mṛgāṅkadatta du doigt*”); princess slowly answers lover, with eyes fixed on the ground (*vasudhā-vinyasta-nayanā*) 103,70 (TP VII 180); embracing (*kaṇṭha-graha*) at meeting 103,177 (TP VII 187); princess dismissing shame and looking at heart with downcast face, as if to tell that its desire was gained 103,183 (TP VII 187); embrace of man met unexpectedly 104,153 (TP VIII 12); lady beckoning with finger at window to king inside to come to her 106,67 (TP VIII 33); female friends embracing (*āśliṣya*) 107,54 (TP VIII 46); *vidyādhari* princesses seem to clothe Naravāhanadatta with the gleams of their eyes in the skin of a black antelope, show anxiety by turning their eyes inwards and express love by placing their hands on their breasts 107,83f. (TP VIII 48f.); nymph whose clothes were taken (after bath) goes with arms crossed in front of her breasts (*sva-hasta-svastika-stanī*) 108,69 (TP VIII 58); angry hero strikes the ground with his hand 108,133 and frowns looking like bow strung by fate for the destruction of his foes 108,134 (TP VIII 64); angry hero presses his hands against each other 108,135 and strikes his arm with his hand and thus seemed to challenge his foe 108,136 (TP VIII 64); asking about someone’s health (*kuśala*) 110,95 (TP VIII 89); milk flowing from mother’s breast at seeing son 110,109 (TP VIII 90); though there was no opportunity of being angry (*a-kopa-kāle ’pi*) the queens had contracted eyebrows and fiery eyes for they were intoxicated 110,130 (TP VIII 91; ORC 1160: “*au moment même où la querelle était imminente ...*”; M II 543: “*die Zeit des Zürnens schien genaht zu sein*”); king feigning anger 111,76 (TP VIII 102); uncle embracing nephew (*āśliṣya cāṅgetaṃ cakāra*) 111,101 (TP VIII 104); accused by king of disobedience his elder brother-in-law weeps with face fixed on the ground 111,78 (TP VIII 102); sign with left hand to wait 112,55 (TP VIII 110); at seeing lovers, two *Gaṇas* interchange glances and smile (*smita-mukhāv anyonyānana-darśināu*) 114,61 (TP VIII 137); ~ of two kings 115,85 (TP VIII 150); prince setting out but often turning back his head to beloved 116,55 (TP VIII 160); Gandharva looks meaningfully at face of Creator (*dhātuḥ sākūtaṃ mukham aikṣata*) 116,85 (TP VIII 162); princess seizing attendant’s hand, looking downcast from shame and addresses her 117,39 (TP VIII 166); princess approaches despondent prince with an affectionate manner (*praśrayôpāgatā*) 117,143 (TP VIII 173); brows curved in anger (*kuṭilatvaṃ bhruvoḥ kope*) 118,11 (TP VIII 178); king remains silent vis-à-vis disobedient son 118,129 (TP VIII 187); old woman messenger asked by imprisoned king how she is (*pr̥ṣṭa-kuśalā*) 118,147 (TP VIII 189); gambler depressed (*khinna*) at Mātaras, etc. refusing to play dice with him 121,96 (TP IX 19); washing almsfood on stone (*bhaikṣyam ambubhiḥ prakṣālya dr̥ṣadi prāpa sa mahā-tāpasa-prathām*) in order to obtain fame as an ascetic 121,158 (TP IX 23); man-hating princess, at seeing disguised man, all at once has hair on body erect (*kaṇṭakitā*) and stands motionless 122,48 (TP IX 37); after long time man greets

his wife as the cloud does the *cātakī* 123,335 (TP IX 66); Vikramāditya obtains Kalinga princess by stratagem (*yukti*) with *vetāla* 124,39; – see also: address; anger; anxiety trauma; *ardha-candra*; *argh(y)a*; beckoning; bewilderment; blessing; boast; chin; compassion; *dhik*; *eka-venī*; etiquette; face; feeling; feet; friendship; front; garland; hair; hospitality; *jīva*; laughing; rolling; melancholy; salutation; shame; sign; suicide; tears

ghana-stanī (not MW) ‘buxom’, said of a nymph 70,70 (TP VI 29: ‘shapely’)

ghaṇṭā, see: bell

ghaṭaḥ kāma-daḥ ‘pitcher that supplies what is desired, cornucopia’ 57,33 (TP V 3); woman (Māyā) puts spiders (= creatures) into ~s symbolizing wombs 70,93 and 112 (TP VI 30-32)

ghee, poured into fire (metaphorically) 24,228 (TP II 187); ~ rubbed on king’s head to remove centipedes 29,144 (TP III 49) relieves head-ache and produces sleep 29,167 (TP III 52); corpse embalmed with heavenly drugs and ~ 45,50 (TP IV 20); meat-curry and ~ as food for guest 54,170 (TP IV 196); oblation of ~ into mouth of corpse 73,307 (TP VI 123); – see further: oil; sacrifice

gift, of half a brahmin’s life to resuscitate *vidyādhara* maiden bitten by a snake 14,80 (TP I 188); ~ of abundant jewels at royal marriage 16,83 (TP II 27); Viṣṇu gives Urvaśī to Purūravas 17,10 (TP II 34); ~ of garments by snake to Nala 56,351 (TP IV 245); complementary (*prābhṛta*)⁶⁵³ ~ to king 66,114 (TP V 187); mendicant daily gives king fruit 75,23 (TP VI 165); Mātāṅga king bestows ~ of musk, garments, meat and spirits to other kings 102,113 (TP VII 170); ~ of poisoned food to dog 75,146 (TP VI 174); Jīmūta vāhana gives his *kalpa-druma* to the world 90,24ff. (TP VII 50f.) and his body to Garuḍa 90,167 (TP VII 60f.), cf. 113,8 (TP VIII 124); ~s bestowed with throwing of grain into marriage fire 103,193 (TP VII 188); ~ of one hundred women at prince’s inauguration 103,219 (TP VII 190); ~s cause all *vidyādhara* chiefs to be bound to emperor with bonds of affection 110,8 (TP VIII 82); ~ of water to the dead 111,59 (TP VIII 101); ~ of *kalpa-taru* and own body by Jīmūtavāhana 113,8 (TP VIII 124); husband’s ~ of only wife to brahmin 113,75 (TP VIII 129); feeding eighteen thousand brahmins by way of ~ to purchase *caṇḍāla*’s daughter (*tanayā-dāna-sūlkena*) 112,194 (TP VIII 121); baksheesh as ~ to doorkeepers 124,192 (TP IX 81); – see also: aloes-wood; *āmalakas*; charity; daughter; donation; dowry; giving; reward; *sāmrājya-śrī*

girding up one’s loins (*parikaram baddhvā*) before jumping into sea 54,102 (TP IV 191); see also: (*ā*)*baddha-kakṣa*; *baddhōttarīyaka*.

Girijāpati = Śiva

Girijāśaṅkarau, see: couple

girl refuses to be married 17,69 (TP II 40); *puruṣa-dveṣiṇī* 42,19 (TP III 260); 43,152 (TP III 291); ~ given away by mother to another than by father⁶⁵⁴ 79,25 (TP VI 201); – see also: husband; *kanyā*; maiden; *pum-dveṣiṇī*; *puruṣa-dveṣiṇī*

⁶⁵³ Also, e.g., Daśakumāracarita 279,2; see also ORC 1563 s.v. *Don*.

⁶⁵⁴ Meyer 1952: 58.

gītaka ('musical composition'), king plays own ~s on lyre in empty temple of Caṇḍikā 69,114 (TP VI 17)

given with own hand as honour (*sva-karārpita*) 14,60 (TP I 187)⁶⁵⁵; – see also: etiquette, hand giving, Nāgārjuna ~ gifts⁶⁵⁶ daily after devotions (*āhāra-samaye*) 41,36 (TP III 254); ~ one hundred *dinārs* 55,10 (TP IV 203); ~ wealth to servants who otherwise wanted to leave 55,23 (TP IV 204); ~ gifts to brahmins 56,203 (TP IV 234); ~ Damayantī as present to other queen 56,328 (TP IV 244); brahmins give fruit of *upoṣaṇā* to *yakṣa* 63,87 (TP V 126); merit~ of daughter (*kanyā-dāna-phala*) 84,23 and 36 (TP VII 6f.); Tārāvaloka ~ away his chariot, horses, sons and lastly his wife to brahmins 113,53ff. (TP VIII 128f.); prisoner cannot give his daughters in marriage 119,17 (TP VIII 194); brahmin tricked (*chalita*) to ~ daughter to Mūladeva 124,159 (TP IX 79); ~ water, see: donation water; – see also: gift; not giving; transfer

giving pledge of royal daughter to king (*pratipanna-sutā-dāna*) 55,93 (TP IV 208); suitor's ~ of monkey to courtesan 57,162 (TP V 12); king's ~ to hero 61,324 (TP V 96); ~ of half of kingdom 65,125 (TP V 164); ~ of woman to visit first lover after her marriage 84,26 (TP VII 6); – cf. *kanyā-sambandha*

glory (*yaśas*) considered white (*pāṇḍu*) 25,228 (TP II 208) and 109,42 (TP VIII 73 note)

glow-worm, see: *kha-dyota*

goat (*chāga*; *vanya-cchagalaka*), fertility elixir (*rasakōttama*) made from he~ flesh 39,7-12 with powder (*cūrṇa-miśritam*; TP III 218f.)⁶⁵⁷; ~ on brahmin's shoulder called dog by rogues 62,66 (TP V 104); rogues eat ~ 62,68 (TP V 104); woman kills ~ with sword and sacrifices it to Śiva, dropping its blood over the *liṅga* and throwing its entrails around it by way of garland, etc. 71,213 (TP VI 51); ~ sold to butcher (*saunika*) 71,273 (TP VI 56); woman brought up on ~'s milk (*ajā-kṣīra-varḍhitā*) 82,36 (TP VI 219); *caṇḍālas* rear exposed child on ~'s milk 112,105 (TP VIII 114); mime (*bhaṇḍa*) in the shape of a divine ~ (*divyaś chāga*) dances before Indra 121,134 (TP IX 21); ~ hit on the head with sticks for refusing to dance 121,140 (TP IX 22); woman's body smells of ~ 82,31 (TP VI 219)⁶⁵⁸

go-between (*gatāgatā*)⁶⁵⁹, ~ not wished for 31,49 (TP III 86); female ascetic as ~ 32,128 (TP III 99) and 65,225 (TP V 172); 75,101 (TP VI 171); – see: Buddhist nun; nurse; *postillon d'amour*; *purohita*; servant; sign

Godāvarī river with seven streams 19,97 (TP II 92f.)⁶⁶⁰

⁶⁵⁵ At Rājat V 16 the donee praises the king giving with his own hand. Cf. Crooke 1906: 187.

⁶⁵⁶ See e.g. Mauss 1970; Gonda 1975: IV 122ff.; Günther 1951; Nath 1987; Michaels 2004: 197ff.; Schwaiger 2011.

⁶⁵⁷ ŚpBr V 2,1,24 identifies the he-goat with Prajāpati, the lord of generation, and ĀpastambaDhS II 6,14,13 says that *bastaś ca śrotriyaś ca strī-kāmatamāv iti*, but I have not found a proper source of, or parallel for, the above passage.

⁶⁵⁸ STh F 647.5.

⁶⁵⁹ On these see, e.g. Schmidt 1904: 156ff.; Jackmuth 2002: 83f.; Bollée 2008a: 17.

⁶⁶⁰ Lüders 1951: 163.

god-built town (*deva-nirmita pura*), of Kāñci 43,60 (TP III 285)
 goddess wants to slay wicked king if hermit approves and heals his wounds 28,34-8 (TP III 22);
 goddess of death (Mārī) entered merchant's house as wife 17,90 (TP II 41)
 goddess of destiny (*bhagavatī bhavitavyatā*), see: destiny
 goddess of fortune (Śrī), clouds of pearls of elephants struck with swords compared to necklace of ~ of battle broken in agitation 103,6 (TP VII 175); (Lakṣmī) 33,8 (TP III 107)
 goddess of prosperity (Lakṣmī), Kauśāmbī as favourite dwelling-place of ~ 9,5 (TP I 94); (Śrī) treacherous as gambling, fickle as a wave, intoxicating as wine 62,164 (TP V 113)
 gods are supremely blessed (*ekānta-sukhino devāḥ*) 1,47 (TP I 6); ~ must be praised (*kṛta-stuti*) and worshipped, and thus enabled grant wishes such as Agni before he could stop Śiva's amorous play 20,79f. (TP II 101); when men had *amṛta*, there would be no difference between ~ and men 41,18 (TP III 253); ~ invited for dinner by Sumeru 50,142 (TP IV 117); ~ as deceivers (*vañcanēpsu*) of Damayanī 56,268 (TP IV 239); speech of ~ never false (*devāḥ ... na hi tad-vacanam mṛṣā*) 114,13 (TP VIII 133); ~ ever nourished by oblations 120,21 (TP IX 3); even ~ fear wicked people (*durjanād devā api ... bibhyati*) 121,95 (TP IX 18); ~ perform austerities (q.v.); – see further names of single gods
 Gokarṇa¹, city in the Deccan (North Karnataka on the Arabian sea)⁶⁶¹ 33,25 (TP III 108);
 Gokarṇa² (name of Śiva), image of ~ on the sea-shore 22,218 (TP II 153)⁶⁶²; worship of ~ at seaside 90,144 (TP VII 59);
*go-karṇa*³, see: cow's ear
 gold (*suvarṇa*),⁶⁶³ Śiva tells three women in dream that the son of one, when waking up, will have under his pillow a lakh of gold pieces 3,22 (TP I 19); ~ throne (*hema-siṃhāsana*)⁶⁶⁴ extracted in excavation (*khāte*) 18,43-48 (TP II 52); king rains ~ (*kanaka*) on subjects 18,50 (TP II 53); brahmin boasts to make ~ out of copper 35,82 (TP III 161); ~ (*svarṇa-leśa*), ship-wrecked man finds ~ on shore 67,63 (TP V 200); two grains of magic rice produce power to spit ~ 108,77 (TP VIII 59); – see also: ant-hill
 gold alms-vessel (*svarṇa-pātra*), snake gives ~ to woman 61,313 (TP V 95)
 Golden city⁶⁶⁵ (Kanakapurī) 24,42 (TP II 173) and 26,5 (TP II 217) et passim; ~ (Kāñcana śṛṅga) of *vidyādhara* king 35,21 (TP III 156) and 59,9 (TP V 26); 35,151 (TP III 167); palace whose tops were resplendent with gold (*sauvarṇa-pura-mastaka-śobhinaḥ abhyantaram ... rāja-sadmanah*) 43,13 (TP III 281: “palace, which was resplendent with seven ranges of golden buildings”; ORC 438: “*la demeure royale dont resplendissent les sommités d'or*”; M I 608: “*Königspalast, der ... aus purem Gold bestand*”)⁶⁶⁶; ~ in 4th *pātāla*

⁶⁶¹ Mani 1975: 293f.

⁶⁶² See further Bollée 2010a: 147 note 82.

⁶⁶³ On gold see Gonda 1991.

⁶⁶⁴ For examples see Jackson: 73 and 196.

⁶⁶⁵ See Verschaeve 1979.

⁶⁶⁶ TP following B read *saptaka* for D: *mastaka*.

45,135 (TP IV 26); ~ in Himālaya (*puram haimam*) 59,9 (TP V 26); ~ in/under sea 86,90 (TP VII 19); Kāñcanapura on Mt Himavat 90,5 (TP VII 49); ~ (Kanakapura) on bank of Ganges inaccessible to Kali 91,3 (TP VII 66); science which produces whatever one desires creates ~ (*sauvarṇa-pura*) 92,37 (TP VII 73);
golden-crested bird, fool takes reflection of ~ for real gold 62,188 (TP V 115); prince cursed by sister to become ~ 65,78 (TP V 160)
golden dishes (*pātra*) with food falling from heaven 43,55 (TP III 284)
golden lotus (*suvarṇa-kamala* [q. v.])⁶⁶⁷ 25,212 (TP II 207); (*hiranyābja*) 54,10 and (*hemāmbuja*) 54,12 (TP IV 184)
golden vilva fruit, Agni brings king ~ as fruit of his tree of valour (*sattva-taru*) 35,69 (TP III 160)
gold figures, see: boy; human statues
goldsmith purifies gold by heating it 61,29 (TP V 70)
gold, ~ sticks (*hema-daṇḍa*) in hands of king's warders 93,5 (TP VII 78); spitting ~ after eating two grains of rice from human sacrifice 108,78 (TP VIII 59); – making ~ from copper, see: alchemy
go-māṃsa 'cow's meat, beef' 26,158 (TP II 228); ~ eaten in famine 27,118 (TP III 9)
gong (*granthi*), see: Buddhist monk; dog
good, doer of ~ will obtain ~⁶⁶⁸ 20,35 (TP II 97f.)
goose/geese see: *haṃsa*
go-rocanā 'yellow orpiment',⁶⁶⁹ wicked woman paints lotus with ~ on *vedi* 71,215 (TP VI 51)
go-śṛṅga, see: horn; hunt(ing)
gossip, see: rumour
gourd⁶⁷⁰ (*karkaṭikā*), after eating ~ man becomes boa constrictor (*aja-gara*) 123,32 (TP IX 45)
go-vāṭa-harmya (not MW) 'cowshed' (q.v.)
govāṭa-vāhana (not MW) 'cow-house as a vehicle' of a witch 20,146 (TP II 108)
graha, cf.: *bhūta* and see: demon; *smara-graha*; *sneha-graha*; *vetāla*
grāha ('crocodile'), hermit maiden seized by ~ and saved by prince 101,236 (TP VII 150)
grain(s) (*tanḍula*), of rice presented by Skanda's servants to traveller do not diminish after consumption 7,21 (TP I 75); ~ (*homa-lāja*) thrown at wedding couple 34,257 (TP III 148); Indra as brahmin throws ~ of sand into the Ganges in order to show *tapas* as senseless to obtain learning 40,16 (TP III 241); three handfuls of ~ (*lāja*) thrown into wedding fire 50,135 (TP IV 116); 51,182 (TP IV 134); ~⁶⁷¹ thrown into the fire is compared to Kāma

⁶⁶⁷ Syed 1990: 631.

⁶⁶⁸ Cf. the English proverb: "what goes around comes around."

⁶⁶⁹ In Baṇa, *Kād.* 17,7 the hems of a royal silk garment have *haṃsas* painted on them with *gorocanā* dye. For this animal orpiment see also Kuv note 123.

⁶⁷⁰ Thus TP but perhaps rather a kind of cucumber just as *karkaṭā*, see MW.

Manobhū's laughter 103,193 (TP VII 188); two ~ of magic rice enable to spit gold 108,78 (TP VIII 59); – see also: bawd; mustard-seeds

grāma, see: three scales

grammar (*vyākaraṇa*),⁶⁷² famous ~ made by Vararuci 2,69f. (TP I 16); Pāṇini obtains new ~ from Indu-śekhara-Śiva 4,22 (TP I 32); its fee (*dakṣiṇā*) of ten million gold pieces 4,93 (TP I 36); king ignorant of ~ 6,117 (TP I 69); ~, gate of all knowledge, learnt in six or twelve years, six months 6,144 (TP I 71);

grāmya 'country bumpkin, paganus' (?), ~s tricked by city wits (*viḍambyante grāmyā nāgarikāḥ*) 124,161 (TP IX 80)

grāmya-kāmuka 'boorish suitor'⁶⁷³ 124,188 (TP IX 81)

grandfather, Prajāpati called ~ 2,12 (TP I 10); ~ by mother's side (*mātā-maha*) decides about marriage of granddaughter 67,51 (TP V 199).

grandson, birth of ~ induces grandparents to go to Ganges and die 22,155 (TP II 148f.); Aniruddha ~ of Hari-Viṣṇu 31,21 (TP III 82)

grant of land, gold, etc. on pupils of Guṇāḍhya 8,36 (TP I 91); ~ of villages, etc. at royal marriage 14,60 (TP I 187); royal ~ resigned (*tyakta-rājāgrahāra*) 20,22 (TP II 96); written ~ (*śāsana*) of a village to a *kāṛpaṭika* 124,62 (TP IX 72); – see also: *agra-hāra*; gift; marriage; present

grantha-lakṣa ('consisting of a hundred thousand couplets'; not MW) 8,20 (TP I 90)

granthi 'gong', see: Buddhist monk; dog

granthi 'knot', see: rosary beads

grass, poisoned to stop military advance 19,81 (TP II 91); ~ as symbol of trifle 28,10 (TP III 18 'worthless straw')⁶⁷⁴; 32,152 (TP III 102); 34,207 (TP III 144); life considered as stubble (*trṇī-kṛta-jivita*) 38,121 (TP III 214); self-restrained man does not care a straw about nymphs sent by Indra to tempt him 45,90 (TP IV 23); 51,205 (TP IV 136); wicked woman, such as one to whom a blade of ~ is a sprout of jewels, falling in love at sight with a blade of ~ (*trṇa-dṛṣṭy-anurāgata*) 52,283 (TP IV 157; ORC 575: "Elle est partie en emmenant un misérable, sans se demander ce qu'il valait réellement, confondant sous l'effet de la passion un brin de paille et une paillette d'or"; MI 805: "Ohne nach einer edlen und tauglichen Sache Verlangen zu verspüren, hat sie irgend etwas Geringes ergriffen und ist davongelaufen. Aus blinder Liebesleidenschaft hält sie gleichsam beim Erspähen eines Grases den Halm für einen Edelsteinsplitter. "); brahmin boy tries flying with wings of ~ and is taken up by *siddha* prince 72,279 (TP VI 89); aged deer reject mouthful of ~ (*śaṣpa-kavala*) 102,52 (TP VII 166); – see also: blade of ~; Buddha; *darbha*; *dūrva*; *kuśa*; *strī-trṇa*

grateful animal motif:⁶⁷⁵ 9,80 (TP I 100 grateful snake gives *viṇā*, etc. to saviour of its life) ; ~

⁶⁷¹ At each handful large gifts are promised.

⁶⁷² See ORC 1574.

⁶⁷³ *Grāmya* can also mean 'venereal disease' (MW).

⁶⁷⁴ Hara 2003: 469.

⁶⁷⁵ STh *B 350ff. See further Rauch upcoming.

of monkey dug up from earth 37,92 (TP III 189); ~ *haṃsa* offers *upakāra* when freed 56,242f. and 250 (TP IV 237); snake bites Nala for his good 56,350 (TP IV 245); ~ of mongoose 64,8ff. (TP V 138f.); ~ of lion 65,70ff. (TP V 160ff.; Buddhist story); ~ of hoopoe 65,83 (TP V 160f.); ~ monkey 123,63ff. (TP IX 47); – see also: ungrateful gratitude, hero obtains magic sword from *yakṣa* out of ~ for ending his curse 10,48 (TP I 109); ~ (*pratyupakriyā*) of *vidyādhara* to king due to help in pre-birth 55, 209 (TP IV 216) grave (*khāta*), human sacrifice into someone's ~ 37,39 (TP III 185)

grdhra, see: kite; vulture(s)

greed⁶⁷⁶ cause of many calamities 24,198 (TP II 183); – see also: bribe; jackal

green⁶⁷⁷, see: bull; hunting; *śyāma*

grey hair, face with ~ (*palita-mlānam ānanam*) like snow-smitten lotus 40,45 (TP III 243; I 121 note); ~ is harbinger of death (*kr̥tānta-dūta*) 103,226 (TP VII 190)

grha 'wife', see: adultery; *para-dāra-grha*

grha-bhāra 'burden of the family', king upholds ~ at his father's death 22,156 (TP II 149)

grhācāra 'rite of hospitality' 57,79 (TP V 7); – see also: etiquette; hospitality

grief (*śucā*), for brothers' death causes death, also of their widows 2,43 (TP I 12); ~ of orphans at being unprotected (*ānāthya-duḥkhitāḥ*) 3,8 (TP I 18); ~ of mother at execution of son 5,100 (TP I 55); heartbreak with ~ (*śucā hṛdayam asphuṭat*) 5,100⁶⁷⁸ and fire of ~ (*śokāgni*) 5,102 (TP I 55); ~ (*saṃtāpavān*) of king at his ignorance of grammar 6,121 (TP I 69); ~ causes abscess (*gulma*) and also makes it burst 15,16 (TP II 2); fire of ~ 15,93 (TP II 9) and *virahānala* 43,186 (TP III 294); poison of ~ (*śoka-viṣa*) 16,106 (TP II 29); ~ of princess at husband's having left her in the night 18,222 (TP II 66f.); seeing wife committing adultery husband is smitten with thunderbolt of ~ (*duḥkhāśani*) 19,27 (TP II 86); fire of ~, terrible like falling of lightning from cloud 25,112 (TP II 199); *vidyādhara* king in his ~ for his cursed daughters goes to the forest 26,61 (TP II 221); ~ for not having obtained joy of battle 27,139 (TP III 11); ~ due to birth of daughter 28,5 (TP III 18) and 46 (TP III 23); ~ at woman friend being married to old king 30,27ff. (TP III 65f.); ~ because of appointment of inauspicious moment 32,20 (TP III 91); ~ of sonlessness 35,27 (TP III 157); ~ at a fallen elephant 36,27 (TP III 171); ~ at not finding jewels 36,78 (TP III 175); darkness of ~ 37,131 (TP III 192)⁶⁷⁹; ~ caused by passion 37,235 (TP III 199); ~ due to lover lost 38,92 (TP III 213); ~ at loosing relative 41,7 (TP III 252); ~ at son's death 41,13 (TP III 253); Nāgārjuna is despondent as not able to prepare *amṛta* for fear of being cursed by Aśvins 41,22f. (TP III 254); out of ~ for his dead minister a king leaves his throne for the forest 41,54 (TP III 256); ~ at news of disappeared husband 42,32 (TP III 261); silent ~ at not obtaining son-producing fruit 42,69 (TP III 264); queen sheds tear like knot of ~ (*duḥkha-granthī*) 43,245 (TP III 298); mother's ~ at loss of son

⁶⁷⁶ Cf. Kuv 64,14-26 (Mette 1991a: 118f.; 2010: 122f.).

⁶⁷⁷ See Hanchett 1988: 291f.

⁶⁷⁸ STh F 1041.1.3.

⁶⁷⁹ STh F 1041.8.2.

46,234 (TP IV 64); ~ at slaughter of kinsmen 47,94 (TP IV 72); ~ at slaughter of army 48,119 (TP IV 82); ~ at death of daughter 52,153 (TP IV 148); out of ~ (*śucā*) at the separation from his wife king is about to leave his body 52,280 (TP IV 157); daughter's ~ at death of brother 53,155 (TP IV 178); ~ of mother for dead children 53,157 (TP IV 179); ~ at unjustified death sentence 54,115 (TP IV 192); ~ at dead son 55,17 (TP IV 203); ~ at sonlessness 55,143 (TP IV 212); ~ of brahmin at not finding lost children 56,68 (TP IV 224); ~ of woman at being alone 56,199 (TP IV 234); ~ at losing magic power 56,230 (TP IV 236); forest-fire of Damayantī's ~ (*duḥkha-davānala*) quenched with tears 56,412 (TP IV 250); ~ feigned at lover's departure 57,107 (TP V 9); man feigned ~ (*kṛtaka-duḥkhita*) 58,30 (TP V 17); king smitten by thunderbolt of ~ (*śokāśani-hata*) 58,39 (TP V 17); ~ at having to wait for marriage 59,20 (TP V 27); ~ at death of lover 59,110 (TP V 34); ~ of separation from bridegroom turns princess mad so that she is cursed by her parents to become Niṣāda maiden 59,155 (TP V 36); mouse grieves at loss of wealth 61,116 (TP V 78); dissatisfaction produces intolerable ~ in both worlds 62,185 (TP V 115); ~ intolerable as a hurricane 64,138 (TP V 150); son at parents' death is distracted with ~ (*śokātura*) 72,198 (TP VI 83); ~ of *yakṣini*-bride about groom who was cursed to become mortal 73,49 (TP VI 104); fatal ~ of mother at son being ruined by gambling 73,204 (TP VI 116); ~ at seeing horses killed by lions 74,101 (TP VI 147); brahmin's ~ (*nirviṇṇa*) at dead family 74,118 (TP VI 148); ~ for loosing friend while swimming across Ganges 74,129 (TP VI 149); parents die of ~ at supposed death of their daughter 75,185 (TP VI 177); ~ (*śoka*) for dead beloved 76,13 (TP VI 180); Durgā takes away ~ (*duḥkha-hāriṇī*) 80,38 (TP VI 207); ~ at seeing king jumping into sea makes merchant wish to commit suicide 86,87 (TP VII 19); brahmin's ~ (*viraha-vyathā*) for abducted wife 87,17 (TP VII 30); father will fall into darkness of ~ (*śokāndhakāra*) at death of son 90,121 (TP VII 57); sonlessness is only ~ of king 93,6 (TP VII 78); ~ is dark 93,12 (TP VII 79); night comes at an end as if out of ~ (*śokād iva kṣiṇābhavat kṣapā*) 95,79 (TP VII 103); fire of ~ (*śoka*) at death of (adulterous) wife 95,84 and 96 (TP VII 103f.); shipwrecked princess falls into sea of ~ (*duḥkhābdhi*) 101,145 (TP VII 144); king in ~ eats little and sleeps on *darbha* grass 101,119 (TP VII 149); ~ of separation from lover 103,26 (TP VII 177); ~ for separation rages in king's bosom like a forest conflagration (*viyoga-davāgni*) 105,10 (TP VIII 22); fire of ~ (*duḥkhāgni*) tortures those who lost relations 111,102 (TP VIII 104); king's ~ about abduction of queen 114,9 (TP VIII 132); Mātaras in ~ (*khinna-mānasāḥ*) over gambling losses 121,89 (TP IX 18); – see also: crest-jewel; depression; heartbreak;

grief overcome by travelling (q.v.)

ground, Siddha princess drawing lines on ~ bashfully (*hrītayā dṛśā*) when being saved by lover 90,80 (TP VII 54); – see further supra: drawing lines

ground scratching, see: scratching the earth

growing like moon, of baby prince 23,87 (TP II 164)

guard(ian)s (*rakṣiṇaḥ*) of executed robber Karpara stupefied by means of sweets with datura

64,77 (TP V 145); Hara-Śiva places basilisks, etc. as ~ (*rakṣaka*) at cave-passage to north

side of Mt Kailāsa 109,69 (TP VIII 75)
 guest, see: hospitality
guhya-cāriṇ (not MW) ‘travelling invisible’, of Asura confidante of Takṣaśilā princess 31,57 (TP III 87)
guhya (attendant of Kubera),⁶⁸⁰ *yakṣa* 56,97 identical with ~ 56,101 gives his *liṅga* away and becomes an eunuch (TP IV 226f.); brahmin reborn as ~ due to being forced to break *upoṣaṇa* (‘fast’) vow 63,76 (TP V 125); ~s as guards at Mt Kailāsa 109,69 (TP VIII 75)
gulikā-kriḍā (‘play at ball’) 42,8 (TP III 259)
gulma, see: abscess
guṇa (‘proper course’), see: six *guṇas*
 Guṇāḍya does not use three languages 6,129 (TP I 58)⁶⁸¹; native of Supraṭiṣṭhita in Pratiṣṭhāna 6,8 and 20 (TP I 60f.); ~ turns Kāṇabhūti’s seven tales in Paiśācī with blood for ink into 700.000 stanzas 8,2 (TP I 89); ~ burns his Bṛhatkathā except one story 8,19 (TP I 90); – see also: (Piśāca) language
*guñjā*⁶⁸² seeds used by Bhillā women for necklace-strings 123,50 (TP IX 46);
guptam ‘secretly’ 32,194 (TP III 106); 37,103 (TP III 190); 38,17 (TP III 207); 45,242 (TP IV 33); 57,101 (TP V 8); 75,97 and 106 (TP VI 171); – see also: gestures; *rahas(i)*; realm; *vijane*;
gupta-yoginī, see: witch
guru,⁶⁸³ pretended ~ knowing the three times (*tri-kāla-jñā*) 19,75 (TP II 90);
guru-dakṣiṇā ‘fee given to spiritual preceptor’, see: fee
guru yoginām, brahmin of the Deccan as ~ 73,103 (TP VI 108 ‘chief of magicians’);
hā Bhadre, wise man (*matimān*) in tattered clothes and begrimed with dust (*jīrṇa-vāsā rajo-lipto*) exclaiming ~ ~ 18,244 (TP II 68)
hā dhig 108,25 (TP VIII 54); *hā dhik* 79,32 (TP VI 202)
hā duḥkham: complaint about destiny of someone’s wife 106,60 and 81 (TP VIII 33f.)⁶⁸⁴;
*hā hā*⁶⁸⁵ 55,197 (TP IV 215); 57,107 (TP V 9); *hā hā dhig* 72,176 (TP VI 81); ~ 72,307 (TP VI 91); 85,12 (TP VII 11); 90,175 (TP VII 61); ~ *hato ’smi* 100,25 (TP VII 130);
Hā tāta, hāmba, ~ ~*āryaputra* 101,148 (TP VII 144); ~ ~ *mṛtā mṛtāsmi* 124,119 (TP IX 76)
hā ... hā ... 56,319 (TP IV 243); 58,39 (TP V 17); 65,151 (TP V 166)
Hāhā-Hūhū-gīta 116,87 (TP VIII 162)⁶⁸⁶

⁶⁸⁰ At 46,199 (TP IV 61) different from *yakṣa*. Zin 2003b: 279 et passim.

⁶⁸¹ Cf. 6,148 (TP I 71).

⁶⁸² See Esposito 2010: 163; Kuv note 162.

⁶⁸³ Gonda 1965a: 229ff.

⁶⁸⁴ On laments see Banerji 1985 where, however, no passages from the KSS have been used.

⁶⁸⁵ Cf. Bailey 2008 II 104; 109.

⁶⁸⁶ Cf. Vdh 130,22 and Bailey 2008: II 104.

hair⁶⁸⁷, new moon in Śiva's blond ~ (*piṅgôttuṅga-jaṭā-jūṭa*) 1,18 (TP I 3)⁶⁸⁸; undoing lock of ~ (*śikhā*) before vow (*pratijñā*) of vengeance 5,118 (TP I 57)⁶⁸⁹; ~ held (*keśa-grahe*) ends curse 10,74 and 79 (TP I 111f.); Śiva as god with matted locks (*dhūr-jaṭi*)⁶⁹⁰ 9,2 (TP I 94); king's ~ stands erect⁶⁹¹ from joy when beholding his son for the first time 10,207 (TP I 120), cf. 107,48 (TP VIII 46); ~ held before cutting off head 18,174 (TP II 63)⁶⁹²; 18,333 (TP II 74); ~ standing on end (*ūrdhva-roma*) at cold ague fit 25,90 (TP II 197); pyre seems to bear on it the chief deity of the Rākṣasas in visible form, with smoke of flames for dishevelled ~⁶⁹³ (*anala-jvālā-dhūma-vyākula-mūrdha-ja*) 25,100 (TP VI II 197); brahmin boy becomes *rākṣasa* with ~ standing on end (*ūrdhva-keśa*) 25,105 (TP II 198); king's ~ stands on end⁶⁹⁴ in joy like thorns 25,220 (TP II 207); long ~ of Good Fortune (*siddheḥ keśa-pāśa ivāgataḥ*) 26,261 (TP II 236); matted locks (*jaṭājūṭa*) of *brahmacāriṇī* 29,52 (TP III 42); Śiva's ~ pulled by Gaurī 35,1 (TP III 155)⁶⁹⁵; prince has ~ of uncle on mother's side shorn off because he wanted to abduct royal ladies⁶⁹⁶ 44,59 (TP IV 5); ~ gleaming on black head of *Asura* Maya like potent herbs on mountain peaks 45,4 (TP IV 17); Kapila-muni with matted locks yellow as flame (*jvālā-kapila-jaṭā-dhara*) 45,371 (TP IV 42); Hṛṣṭaroman ('with hair on end') as proper name 46,38 (TP IV 51); tawny ~ (*kapila-mūrdha-ja*) of *vidyādhara* 48,71 (TP IV 79); ~ of a dog in a lyre 49,19 (TP IV 86) wrongly: "puppy" for *śva-vāla*)⁶⁹⁷; flame as ~ 53,160 (TP IV 179); queen's luxuriant ~ (*kabarī-bhāra*)⁶⁹⁸ likened to tails of *camarīs* 55,200 (TP IV 216); rogue physician claims to know drug producing ~ 61,181 (TP V 83)⁶⁹⁹; ascetics with matted ~ (*jaṭila*) 64,24 (TP V 140); ~ held before attempt to cut off head 72,59 (TP VI 72) and 74,84 (TP VI 146); enchanter's *yajñopavīta* made of ~ (*dhṛta-keśôpavītaka*) 73,283 (TP VI 120);

⁶⁸⁷ See Hildebeitel 1981; Obeyesekere 1981.

⁶⁸⁸ Cf. Riedel 1993: 82f. The association of hair with rays may be as old as AV 14,1,55 where Bṛhaspati is said to do Sūryā's hair before marriage. Hair is Evil (JaimBr 2,369; HiraṇyakeśiGS 1,9,18; Hemacandra, *Triṣaṣṭi* 10,10,51) and therefore must be cut or removed before a new stage of life, such as marriage or becoming an ascetic.

⁶⁸⁹ Hair being *pāpman* (of Prajāpati : JaimBr 2,369, cf. PVB 4,9,22; HiraṇyakeśiGS 1,9,18) and the root of the tree of karman (Hemacandra, *Triṣaṣṭiśālākāpuruṣacaritra* 10,10,51) the undertaker of a vow, in order to be able to perform it, must be without evil, cf. Olivelle 1998: 19f.

⁶⁹⁰ Hildebeitel 1998a: 23f.

⁶⁹¹ Hildebeitel 1998: 145f.

⁶⁹² Thus in Banteay Srei Kṛṣṇa is pictured killing his uncle Kaṃsa in his palace in Mathura (Giteau 1976: 210).

⁶⁹³ Olivelle 1998: 16.

⁶⁹⁴ Hildebeitel 1998: 145f. See also: "horripilation" below.

⁶⁹⁵ On hair pulling in sexual frolocking see also Bāṇa, *Kād.* 10,7 *rateṣu keśa-grahāḥ* and 11,3f. *antaḥpurikā-kuntaleṣu bhaṅgaḥ*.

⁶⁹⁶ The shaving here synecdochically stands for decapitation, if not directly for castration, cf. Olivelle 1998: 28ff. (where various theories are discussed) and 167.

⁶⁹⁷ See Zin 2004: 330f.

⁶⁹⁸ A woman's open hair is her *śakti* 'feminine power' (Keltling 2009: 122).

⁶⁹⁹ Cf. STh J 1062.2.1.

princess trembling with joyful agitation that made her ~ stand on end (*sānanda-pulakôtampa-sādhvasā*) 74,235 (TP VI 157), cf. of a man 81,54 (TP VI 212); flames compared to ~ 78,85 (TP VI 196); ~ (*bāla*) under seven mattresses (*tūlikā*) 82,45 (TP VI 220); woman with ~ like jet (*tārṅṣya-ratnāsita-śīroruhā*) 84,47 (TP VII 8); ~ erect on Jimūtavāhana's body like coat of mail though eaten by Garuḍa 90,165 (TP VII 60); Gaṅgā playfully pulls Śambhu's ~ 93,78 (TP VII 84); *brahma-rākṣasa* with *yajñopavīta* of ~ (*keśa-*) 94,69 (TP VII 91), cf. 99,11 (TP VII 123); ~ of princess stand erect of joy on all her limbs 103,63 (TP VII 179); grey ~ as harbinger of death 103,224 induces king to retire to *tīrtha* 103,229 (TP VII 190f.); ~ on string of *viṇā* 106,25 (TP VIII 30)⁷⁰⁰; one lock (*eka-veṇī*) of queen, tormented by separation, to be loosened by her husband only when he has slain her enemy 106,113 (TP VIII 36)⁷⁰¹; enemy seized by the ~ (*keśeṣu gṛhītvā*) and decapitated 108,109 (TP VIII 62); do, (*keśeṣv ākrṣya*) but decapitation stopped by his sister 109,136f. (TP VIII 80); trees, like hermits, with creepers like matted ~ waving in the wind 110,64 (TP VIII 86); king takes adulterer by the ~ and severs his neck 112,33 (TP VIII 107); old age seizes us by the ~ to hand us over to death 111,69 (TP VIII 101); upstanding ~ of *rākṣasas* becomes yellow as the flames they vomit 116,29 (TP VIII 158); long ~ of princesses resembles snakes made by the Creator to guard their beauty 118,165 (TP VIII 189); laughing man with matted ~ in dream 119,73 and 88 (TP VIII 198f.); princess, overcome by love, remained with ~ on body erect (*kaṅṭakitā*) 122,48 (TP IX 37); brahmin's ~ stands on end due to fright of his wife who devoured his servant 124,98 (TP IX 75); – see also: bald man; *eka-veṇī*; flame; grey hair; hair-style

hair-pulling, queen playfully pulls ~ (*keli-kaca-graha*) of king 85,11 (TP VII 11)⁷⁰²;
 hair-style of Buddhists: rejecting brahmanical lock etc. 27,19 (TP III 2); curly ~ (*keśair arālaiḥ*) of Dānava princess 45,235 (TP IV 33); teacher of dancing, having lost wife and wealth in gambling, mats his hair in a knot (*baddha-jaṭa*) and starts austerities on bank of Ganges 52,295 (TP IV 158); *kārpaṭika* with matted hair 53,12 (TP IV 169); only defeat was the curling in locks of women (*bhaṅgo 'lakeṣu nārīṇām*) 55,27 (TP IV 204); dishevelled curls and locks as signs of sex 74,242 (TP VI 157)⁷⁰³; maiden's hair plaited together after the hermit fashion as symbol of attractivity 94,20 (TP VII 88); Śabara letter-carrier has his hair tied up in a knot behind with a creeper (*latā-tvag-baddha-mūrdhaja*) 101,355 (TP VII 158); wife with one lock (*eka-veṇī*) is weeping for absent husband 106,77 (TP VIII 34)⁷⁰⁴; Takṣasilā queen Madanamañcukā's *eka-veṇī* hair to be loosed at her death by birds⁷⁰⁵ or consumed with fire (*mṛtāyāḥ pakṣibhir vâpi veṇī dāhyâthavâgninā*)

⁷⁰⁰ Cf. 49,19 (TP IV 86).

⁷⁰¹ The reverse in STh M 122.

⁷⁰² Cf. Kād 130,4 where royal women's earrings are ruined by violent hair-pullings: *sa-rabhasa-kaca-graha-cūrṇita-maṇi-karṇa-pūra*.

⁷⁰³ Meyer 1937: I 171 note 2.

⁷⁰⁴ Cf. Daś 196,13.

106,114 (TP VIII 37); hermit with matted ~ (*jaṭābhis*) 108,63 (TP VIII 58) and 110,24 (TP VIII 83); royal ladies with fastenings of their coiffure loosened (*ślatha-dhammilla-bandhanāḥ*) while bathing 108,147 (TP VIII 64); two strands of hair (*keśa-pāśau*) seem like snakes to guard the treasure of the beauty of Daitya maidens 118,165 (TP VIII 189); upstanding hair (*ūrdhva-śiroruhāḥ*) of *vetāla* 121,24 (TP IX 13); – see also: *eka-veṇī*; *Gaṇa*; lock

hālāhala poison,⁷⁰⁶ better to take ~ than trust women 72,255 (TP VI 86);

half-moon (*ardha-candra*), give a person the ~, i.e. fling him out neck and crop 6,59 (TP I 65);

ORC 37: “*qu’on lui baille à la gorge un revers de main en demi-lune*”; M I 53: “*Packt ihn schnell am Halse*”; ~ on Śiva’s head 108,82 (TP VIII 60)

half of kingdom as reward, sonless king gives brahmin ~ 56,134 (TP IV 229)⁷⁰⁷

half of life, brahmin gives ~ to revive bride bitten by snake 14,80 (TP I 188)⁷⁰⁸

halo (*arcis*) radiating from head of brahmin praying at *tīrtha* Puṣkara 45,84 (TP IV 23); – see:

⁷⁰⁵ The queen is granddaughter of Buddhist king Kāliṅgadatta of Takṣaśilā where, according to Strabo, *Geography* XV 1 § 62 quoting Aristobulus, corpses were thrown out to be devoured by vultures (Τῶν δ’ ἐν Ταξίλοις νομίμων καινὰ καὶ ἀήθη λέγει ... καὶ τὸ γούσι ῥίπτεσθαι τὸν τετελευτηκότα); McCrindle 1901: 69. Also in the north, in Uttarakuru, Gigantic storks (*bhāruṇḍa*; see Stache-Rosen 1977; Bollée 2005 § 703; Chojnacki 2008 II note 803), who are often together with vultures and are carrion eaters, pick up corpses and drop them into caves (to devour them), cf. Mbh V 40,15ab *anyo dhanam pretā-gatasya bhūṅkte vayāṃsi cāgniś ca śarīra-dhātūn* (Tiwari 1979: 36ff.) and Kuv 70.1f.

ṚV X 15,14, in NW India that probably is, mentions unspecified non-cremation and AV XVIII 2,35 distinguishes four kinds of obsequies: burial, casting away, burning and elevation (on a tree, platform, etc.). The second is done with Sirimā on an *āmaka-susāna* (see below), the latter with the nun Sundarī on an *aṭṭaka* in Ja II 416,24.

At death, people are usually covered with cloths so that their hair is inaccessible to birds, as shown in 26,78 (TP II 223), 52,150 (TP IV 148) and by Filippi 2005 plates 4f. There are, however, exceptions: according to Mbh I 85,17 a dead person may be cremated, buried or just done away with (*nighṛśyate*), and in Mbh XIII App. 15. 3826 it says that the dead can be burnt on the cremation ground in the South, or be dropped on the ground (*nikṣiped bhūmau śarīram*; Kieffer-Puelz p. c.).

Further, Pāli sources inform us that the former courtesan Sirimā, a prominent person and loyal Buddha devotee dies and the Buddha tells the king that she should not be burnt, but brought to the charnel ground and guarded against crows, etc. for the monks to see (Dhp-a III 106,17ff.). The corpse of the young Queen Damiḷā lies on the *sīvathikā* and is not cremated (Mp I 22,22ff.), etc. At Ja III 523,14 a crow eats the flesh of corpses on the charnel ground which thus are uncovered; at Ja V 302,7 vultures might mix up the beautiful hair of Pabhāvātī amid the charnel ground (*sīvathika-majjhe*; Kieffer-Puelz 1983: 43f. and 28).

Buddhist monks take cemetery-rags (*sosānika*) and make their rag-ropes from them (Vin IV 281; Vism 62); corpses may therefore lie about on which they also meditated. See further also Jain 1984: 283 (Jain’s article “Disposal of the Dead in the Bhagavatī Ārādhanā” was not at my disposal).

In addition, Filippi (p.c.) draws attention to Sītā as *eka-veṇī* in Laṅkā where Rāvaṇa then might correspond to Mānasavega at our place, and to Hildebeitel 1980-1: 198 with parallels from Kālidāsa.

⁷⁰⁶ H. emerged before the *amṛta* from the ocean, when this was churned by *devas* and *Asuras*, and drunk by Śiva. It is said to be made from the root of a plant (MW) or arose first at the churning of the ocean (PWB). Stubbe-Diarra 1995: 8.

⁷⁰⁷ STh Q 112.

⁷⁰⁸ *E 165.

aura (of light); light; *tīrtha*

*haṃsa*⁷⁰⁹ ‘goose’, two golden ~s flying over amid hundreds of white ~s 3,27 address king with articulate voice (*vyakta-vācau*) 3,32 (TP I 20f.); ~ grieves at seeing cloud 6,162 (TP I 72); ~s like gleaming chowries (*prollasaddhaṃsa-cāmara*) in lake 25,12 (TP II 188); wooden ~ robbing royal treasury 43,25ff. (TP III 283); princess in prebirth as *haṃsī* makes nest in sandalwood-tree and gets male offspring 43,154f. (TP III 291); carpenter attaches to strings a couple of wooden ~s (*rañju-yantra-vahaṃ dārumayaṃ haṃsa-yugaṃ*) and makes them steal jewelry (*ābharāṇa*) from the king’s treasury 43,27 (TP III 282f.); ganders are regardless (*niḥsneha*) to offspring and females 43,161 (TP III 292); ascetic, in a pre-birth a ~, crying: “Ah, my goose” (*haṃsī*) at the king’s gate 43,173 (TP III 293); Kāma born as ~ 43,193 (TP III 294); speaking ~, see: human voice; two dice in the form of ~s fly off with Nala’s garment 56,310f. (TP IV 242); celestial ~ caught by Damayantī 56,242f. and Nala and addressing them offers them good turn (*upakāra*) when freed 56,249f. (TP IV 237); celestial ~ as ambassador of Kāma addresses Damayantī with understandable words (*vyaktayā girā*) 56,245 (TP IV 237); two dice in the form of ~s take Nala’s garment 56,311 (TP IV 242); two ~s carry tortoise on a stick (*yaṣṭi*) 60,173 (TP V 56); ~s leave a tank without water 61,118 (TP V 78); rebirth as ~ due to *nidāna* 69,128 (TP VI 18); *haṃsī* hits sleeping monkey who falls on net with *haṃsa*, tears it and thus frees the bird 69,145 (TP VI 19); fowler kills couple of ~s with one arrow 69,152 (TP VI 19); ascetic offers female ~ to Śiva 69,154-6 (TP VI 20); ~ satisfied in lotus-bed ... : stanza sung by bard to prince 71,70 (TP VI 40f.)⁷¹⁰; Siddhas in the shape of ~ 72,186 (TP VI 82); are crows at fault when ~s eat rice ? 75,191 (TP VI 176); ~s like waving chowries (*ullasad dhaṃsa-cāmara*) 108,142 (TP VIII 64); one night, king sees pair of golden ~s attended by a train of *rāja-haṃsas* 114,24 (TP VIII 134); golden ~s offering unfading flowers 114,46 (TP VIII 135); heavenly ~s speak to king in dream 114,48 (TP VIII 136); robbers become golden ~s 114,133 (TP VIII 142); ~s telling story 115,3 (TP VIII 144); – see also: bug

haṃsa-yāna, in chariot drawn by *haṃsas* Brahmā, Indra and Bṛhaspati go to Viṣṇu in Śvetadvīpa 115,101 (TP VIII 151);

hand emerges from Ganges 5,8 (TP I 45); king sprinkles (*abhiṣicya*) princess first queen with his own ~ 6,167 (TP I 73); left ~⁷¹¹ as vulnerable point 11,65 (TP I 127); given with own ~ as honour 14,60 (TP I 187); ~ on heart, see: gestures; ; brahmin widow gives her house to hero with her own ~ (*sva-hastena*) 18,371 (TP II 70); ~ of *vidyādhari* stretched forth from inside pillar to anoint merchant’s back 37,16 (TP III 184); man takes his friend’s love

⁷⁰⁹ ORC 1576 refers to p. 14 note one, p. 1535 that is, for the representation of the *haṃsa*, commonly translated by *oie sauvage*, as “*âme universelle, esprit suprême*” identified with Viṣṇu, but is not in the text. I have changed the swan(s) in TP’s translations into *haṃsa* in view of the confusion of the designations in different texts (Dave 2005: 84ff.). Vogel 1962. See also: date-palms, and further Hensgen 1958: 135.

⁷¹⁰ See also s.v. *āryā* and cf. Meyer 1967.

⁷¹¹ Cf. for classical antiquity Wirth 2010.

by the ~ (*haste gṛhītvā*) and brings her to him 45,210 (TP IV 31); *Asura* prince seizes perspired and trembling (*sa-kheda-vepathu*) ~ of *Asura* princess 45,257 (TP IV 34); Indra seizes Maya by the ~ to propitiate him 45,412 (TP IV 45); Hara-Śiva puts ~ on back (*prṣṭhe karaṃ dattvā*) of Sūryaprabha fallen at his feet and makes him rise up 50,193 (TP IV 120)⁷¹²; general Prabhāsa brings inauguration water with his own ~s 50,203 (TP IV 121); *kṣatriya* with his left ~ seizes lion by the foot, dashes it on the earth and kills it 52,128 (TP IV 147)⁷¹³; angry queen supports downcast face on palm of left ~ 55,124 (TP IV 210); part-*bodhisattva* saves man without ~s and feet from river 65,9 (TP V 154); touch of ~ (*kara-saṃsparśa*) of female ascetic frees prince from curse by hermit 65,232, 237 and 245 (TP V 172f.); the (right) ~ and tongue of thief cut off (*nikṛta-hasta-jihvaḥ*) 60,232 (TP V 61: “cut off the hands”; ORC 690: “ils coupèrent la langue et les mains”; MI 972: “die Hände”), cf. *dakṣiṇaṃ pāṇiṃ* 69,149 (TP VI 19)⁷¹⁴; giving ~ as sign of being colleague (*brahmacārī*) 71,29 (TP VI 38)⁷¹⁵; ~ of Viṣṇu devotee so holy as to be able to cure fever with it 71,122 (TP VI 44)⁷¹⁶; ~ with power to remove disease (*āmaya-hara*) 71,257 (TP VI 54); averting evil spirits by waving ~ round head 73,116 (TP VI 109 with note 1); hero’s ~ wakes up princess by nudging on her shoulder 73,345 (TP VI 125); waves of Ganges compared to uplifted ~s (*taraṅga-hasta*) warning people back 74,113 (TP VI 148); heavenly maiden puts ~ on heart as sign to unknown prince 75,74 (TP VI 169; cf. 107,84 [TP VIII 49])⁷¹⁷; fastidious brahmin stops nose with his left ~ because the loveliest lady of the royal court is smelling of a goat 82,30 (TP VI 219); ~ of delicate queen bruised (*kiṅkita*) by sound of pestle 85,26 (TP VII 11); waves of tank like ~s 86,149 (TP VII 23); Gaurī anoints Jīmūtavāhana with her own ~s 90,188 (TP VII 62); three ~s stretch out for *piṇḍa* at Gayā, one with an iron spike (*lohamayaḥ śaṅku*), one with a colander (*pavitṛaka*) and one with a royal signet ring (*aṅgulīyaḥ su-lakṣaṇaḥ*) 93,88ff. (TP VII 85); sun’s rays as warning ~ not to enter robber forest (*caurāṭavi*) 98,12 (TP VII 117); bridegroom ascends platform, where fire is burning, and seized the ~ (*agrahīt ... pāṇiṃ*) of the princess 103,191 (TP VII 188); trees, agitating their shoots like ~s, (*calat-pallava-pāṇayaḥ ... pādapāḥ*) seemed to say: “we have not seen your beloved” 105,39 (TP VIII 24); *vidyādhari* promises *yakṣas* offerings with her own ~ 105,50 and performs them 57 (TP VIII 24f.); women show love by ~s on breast 107,84 (TP VIII 49 [cf. 75,74 (TP VI 169)]); human ~ (*nṛ-hasta*) in the shape of a red lotus (*rakta-kamala*) given with alms to brahmin 108,24f. (TP VIII 54); after long separation princess takes fisherman lover brought

⁷¹² At Rājāt VII 280 fearful *bhaṭṭa-pāda* men are put at ease by a pseudo-guru when he placed his hand on their heads.

⁷¹³ Acting with the left hand expresses contemptuousness.

⁷¹⁴ See Gonda 1991 VI,1: 41ff. and cf. Wirth 2010: 148ff.

⁷¹⁵ Cf. Wirth 2010: 135.

⁷¹⁶ Laying on of hands is of course common, e.g. Weinreich 1909: 46; HdA 3: 1398ff.; Stemplinger 1948: 100.

⁷¹⁷ According to Bāṇa, *Kādambarī*, 395,6 = ed. Kale 2005: 289,2 she does this because she wants to touch the beloved (Winternitz, *HIL* III [1967]: 408).

by his mother by the ~ and shampoos his withered limbs with her ~ 112,27f. (TP VIII 116); princess gathers fruits and flowers with her own ~s 113,60 (TP VIII 128); hero hurles *rākṣasīs* senseless to earth by a blow from the flat of his ~ (*talāhate*) 116,34 (TP VIII 158) and 56 (TP VIII 160)⁷¹⁸; princess seizes attendant's ~ and addresses her with a face cast down from shame 117,39 (TP VIII 166); – for water thrown over the ~s in donation ceremony see *hastōdaka*; – see also: donation water; finger; gestures; head; healing; hermit boy; left hand; touch of hand

hands formed into a pipe to chant Sāmaveda 6,57 (TP I 64)

hang oneself, woman asks Ḍomba how to ~ 13,100 (TP I 157)

hanging, princess prefers suicide by ~ to entering the fire because of then being mixed up with a strange man (? *para-puruṣa-madhye*) 119,184f. (TP VIII 206: with strange men; ORC 1253: “*auprès d'un homme qui m'est étranger*”; M II 667: “*in dieses Feuer zu gehen, in dem sich fremde Männer befinden*”); – see also: suicide

hangover (lit. ‘severe headache’: *śiraḥ-śūla*) simulated 13,155 (TP I 161)

Hara (Śiva) sports with Gaurī 22,57 (TP II 141); young woman riding on lion to temple of ~ on lake shore 22,79 (TP II 143); ~ fights the *Asura* Bāṇa 27,142 (TP III 12)⁷¹⁹; knowledge (*jñāna*) emerges while one thinks of ~ 37,134 (TP III 192); Vaiśravaṇa-Kubera worships ~ in order to obtain crystal lotus in Mānasa lake 72,39 (TP VI 71); ~ shows himself 73,424 (TP VI 130); king propitiates ~ for a son 83,6 (TP VII 2); Vārāṇasī as ~'s abode 87,3 (TP VII 29); ~ and Gaurī give Naravāhanadatta chariot in lotus form made by Brahmā 107,133 (TP VIII 52); ~ pierces Mt. Kailāsa for emperors to pass 109,72 (TP VIII 75); meditation on ~ (Hara-*dhyāna*) by royals to find out wonder of golden *haṃsas* 114,47 (TP VIII 136); ~ blinds robbers who plundered his temple (*deva-bhuvana*) 114,120 (TP VIII 141); ~ always manifest in Siddhīśvara 115,110 (TP VIII 152); Hari, Brahmā, Devendra and Diviṣadguru (Bṛhaspati) propitiate ~ by severe ascetism 115,116 and ~ seen in *liṅga* promises Candraketu a son as part of himself (*mad-amṣa-sambhava*) 115,124 (TP VIII 152f.);

hāra, see: garland; necklace

hare, horn of ~ 40,21 (TP III 241); wise ~ leads lion to well 60,105f. (TP V 49f.); ingenious (*yuktimān*) ~ sent as ambassador of the moon to elephant king 62,37 (TP V 101)⁷²⁰

harem, intrigue (q.v.); warder as violator of royal ~ executed 71,303 (TP VI 58); – see also: conspiracy

Hari (Viṣṇu) resides in Mathurā 12,128 and 145f. (TP I 143f.); people told to flee to ~ for protection against goddess of pestilence (Mārī) 12,178 (TP I 147 “fly” instead of “flee”); ~'s temple⁷²¹ on the island named Ratnakūṭa 26,3 (TP II 217); ~ as dispeller of transgressions (*agha-hara*) 32,50 (TP III 94); king gives daughter to Naravāhanadatta as sea gave Śrī

⁷¹⁸ STh F 628.1.2.

⁷¹⁹ So also e.g., Mani 1975: 107. Fezas wrongly translates Hara by Viṣṇu (ORC 263 and 1673).

⁷²⁰ STh K 1716.

⁷²¹ The word *pratiṣṭhā* used here is translated in ORC by “statue”.

Lakṣmī to ~ 35,154 (TP III 167); ~ on Garuḍa advises Vikramāditya in dream 38,58 (TP III 210); king considers son Śṛṅgabhuja like incarnation of ~ 39,237 (TP III 235); ~ reclining on Śeṣa on Śvetadvīpa 54,26 (TP IV 186) and 67,96 (TP V 203); **description** 54,31ff. (TP IV 186); ~ sends Nārada to Indra in order to demand back his *apsaras* 54,187 (TP IV 187); ~ dries up sea with fire weapon and makes it restore *ṛiṭṭibha* eggs 60,194 (TP V 57); ~ as endless store of virtues (*an-anta-guṇâugha*) 71,88 (TP VI 42); ~'s temple that dispels calamity (*pāpa-ghnam āśrītāyatanaṃ Hareḥ*) 71,96 (TP VI 42); *tūrtha* Kramasaras arose where ~ in his incarnation as Vāmana had put down his foot 73,95 (TP VI 107); actor representing ~ as a woman 74,36f. (TP VI 143); king praises sea as having cheated ~ out of Śrī by concealing mermaid 86,82 (TP VII 19); ~ rescues the earth 93,4 (TP VII 78); ~ temple that dispels calamity (*pāpa-ghnam āśrītāyatanaṃ Hareḥ*) 71,96 (TP VI 42); king practises asceticism in sanctuary of ~ in Nandigrāma, outside Ayodhyā 103,119 (TP VII 183 where ~ is wrongly rendered as Śiva); Rukmiṇī carried off by ~ after she had been given to king of Cedi 104,126 (TP VIII 10); ~ with *kaustubha* 108,82 (TP VIII 60); ~ as Vāmana makes the earth tremble with his footstep 124,229 (TP IX 84); – often in dreams (see above s.v.); – see also: Mura-jit; Śārngin; Viṣṇu

hariṇâmiṣa ('venison')⁷²² eaten by prince 74,112 (TP VI 148);

hariṇîdrś 'fawn-eyed; MW: doe-eyed' 71,78 (TP VI 41)

Harṣa, King of Kashmir,⁷²³ able to make all mountains (*urvî-bhṛt*) bow before him and to drink up the seven oceans E 10 (TP IX 10)

harṣa-bāṣpa 'tears of joy' 25,66 (TP II 195); – cf. *ānanda-bāṣpa* and see also: gestures; joy

hasta-dīpa 'hand-lamp', prince finds wife's ear-ornament flashing like a ~ 21,85 (TP II 131)

-hastin, see: *-dvīpa*

hastôdaka, see: donation water

hāsya-vibhrama (not MW) 'ridiculous blunder' 43,103 (TP III 288)

Hātakêśvara = Śiva worshipped on 14th day 118,155 (TP VIII 188); – see also: ordeal

hata-supta 'fallen asleep in death' (not MW), of lions killed by hunters 42,3 (TP III 259)

haṭhōpabhoga, see: violation

hating men, – see: daughter; misandry; *puruṣa-dveṣiṇī*

hatred (*virodha*) and affection are genetic due to recalling of pre-birth impressions 23,30 (TP II 159); ~ of woman against men, see: *puruṣa-dveṣiṇī*⁷²⁴

havya-kavya-bhuk 'eater of oblations to gods and ancestors, Agni' (not MW) 18,315 (TP II 73)

hawk (*śyena*), Indra as ~, see: Indra

he lokāḥ "Hear, ye people!" 12,178 (TP I 147)

head, shoes of another carried on ~ for twelve years 6,149 (TP I 71); ~ of king of Pārasīkas (Persians) cut off 19,110 (TP II 94); plunging in the water of the river, remaining a long time ~ downward (as austerity) (*sarīṭ-toye ca sa ciraṃ nimajjyāsīd avāṇ-mukhaḥ*) 24,95 (TP II

⁷²² Bollée 2008a: 12.

⁷²³ Rājāt VII 829. Harṣa reigned from 1063-1089.

⁷²⁴ See also Chojnacki 2008: (I) 352 s.v. *haine du genre masculin*.

176); goddess of destiny (*bhagavati bhavitavyatā*) places her foot on the ~s of all men 26,24 (TP II 218); king's ~ anointed with ghee against centipedes in his ear 29,167 (TP III 52); Creator puts Śiva's order on his head, i.e. obeys him 34,45 (TP III 131, sec: creator); bridegroom must often turn his ~ and look (*pṛṣṭhato viṣitavyam*) for pursuer 39,133 (TP III 227); giving away one's ~ 41,37 (TP III 255); asking for someone's ~ 41,42 (TP III 255); ~ of *rākṣasa* cut off grows again 42,131 (TP III 268); seeing his brother senseless a man wishes to cut off his ~ but is stopped by voice from the air 42,167 (TP III 271); black ~ of *Asura* Maya 45,4 (TP IV 17); heaven is Viṣṇu's ~ 54,33 (TP IV 186); bald man's ~ like a copper pot (*tāmra-kumbha*) 61,48 (TP V 72); idem, 61,180 (TP V 83); snake with three hoods (*tri-phaṇa*) 65,86 and 90 (TP V 161); snake with two heads, a blind one in its tail 63,175 (TP V 134); Mātāṅga king shows himself as slave by putting his ~ on the ground 71,14 (TP VI 37); ~ of Śeṣa, yellow with rays of jewels 72,38 (TP VI 71); covering ~ at night 73,7 (TP VI 100 with note); rams guarding a gate in Pātāla flee when hit on the ~ with a magic stick 73,131f. (TP VI 110); ~ to split in a hundred pieces when no answer is given 75,188 (TP VI 176)⁷²⁵; own ~ cut off as sacrifice to Durgā 78,93 (TP VI 197) and 80,31 (TP VI 206)⁷²⁶; ~s of brother and husband transposed 80,47 (TP VI 207)⁷²⁷; ~ is chief of limbs (*pradhānam ca śiro 'ṅgeṣu*) 80,53 (TP VI 208); severed ~s of warriors fly up to heaven as if to kiss *apsaras* 103,8 (TP VII 175); coronation water poured on ~ of royal couple 103,233 (TP VII 191); ~ split into a hundred pieces at trying to abduct woman against her will 106,133 (TP VIII 38); king cuts off adorned ~ (? *śiro racita-maṇḍanam*) of adulterer 112,31 (TP VIII 107 "oiled and curled head"; ORC 1172 "tête parée d' un bijou".⁷²⁸); prince turning ~ (lit.: neck) back to beloved 116,55 (TP VIII 159); Śiva sits naked with ~ on knee (*jānu-nyasta-kapola*) 121,99); goats refusing to dance are hit on the ~ 121,140 (TP IX 22); ~ of *rākṣasa* split into a hundred pieces after his refusal to give alms to woman 123,189 (TP IX 56); – see also: adulterer; combat; elephant; hair; hand; light; shattered head motif

headache feigned to cover up dog's foot mark with cloth 13,155 (TP I 161); ~ relieved with ghee rubbed on head 29,167 (TP III 52)⁷²⁹; through loss of love ~ feigned (*śiro 'rti-vyapadeśa*) 37,213 (TP III 198); lover suffers severe ~ because of lost unknown loved woman (*śiro- 'rtyātyanta-vṛttayā*⁷³⁰) 104,109 (TP VIII 9)⁷³¹

⁷²⁵ Witzel 1987: 372 but other than the Vedic cases referred there the king might very well be able to answer, yet would not do so for then his head would be shattered.

⁷²⁶ The head is tied by the hair to the chain of the temple bell but illogically falls on the ground when cut off. — Decapitating oneself with a sword or attempts thereat is still practised: in Gujarat: a man tried to do it in 1985 but did not succeed, was brought to a hospital and later also punished (*Fränkischer Tag*, Oct. 24th, 2011) suicide being forbidden by Indian law (Indian Penal Code § 309). – See also: suicide.

⁷²⁷ See e.g. Wilhelm 1978; Courtright 1985: 93f. For another story of transposed heads in South Indian tradition see Doniger O'Flaherty 1976: 351.

⁷²⁸ A reason for head decoration is not given.

⁷²⁹ Because of pretexted headache Queen Dilhā rubs oil on her frightened husband Kalaśa's head (Rājāt VII 332).

headshake (*vārdhaka-kampinā śīrasā*), *tāpasī* prevents suicide with ~ 72,19ff. (TP VI 69)
 healing, of brahmin's fistulous sore (*nāḍī*) by Piśāca with heavenly herbs 28,169 (TP III 33); ~
 of elephant by touch of hand of faithful woman 36,30 (TP III 171)⁷³²; ~ from fever
 71,121 and 125 (TP VI 44f.); ~ heat with fire and the feeling of cold with snow 66,14 (TP
 V 179); ~ of king by *vetāla*'s mustard-seeds 73,312 (TP VI 123); manual ~ of mad
 merchant by ascetic 73,382 (TP VI 128); king's ~ look (*darṣṭi*) for *vetāla*'s eye disease:
similia similibus 123,34⁷³³ (TP IX 45); – see also: *nyasta-mantra*
 health, asking after a person's ~ (*prṣṭa-kuśala*) belongs to etiquette of meeting, greeting and
 reception 103,177 (TP VII 187); 110,95 (TP VIII 89); – see also: gesture; messenger;
 salutation
 hearing, a tale ends curse 2,24 (TP I 10f.); love upon first ~ of woman 51,122 (TP IV 130)⁷³⁴
 heart (*hṛdaya*) of Vararuci struck by Kāma's arrows 4,8 (TP I 31); (*mānasa*) of king stolen by
 sylph 45,204 (TP IV 31); ~ of monkey wanted by wife of dolphin 63,116 (TP V 129)⁷³⁵;
 ears and ~ of donkey wanted by wounded lion 63,130 (TP V 130); woman's ~ stolen
 (*mano muṣitvā*) by brahmin 95,57f. (TP VII 102) and 117,105 (TP VIII 171); she said:
 “the ~ of women is harder than the thunderbolt” 119,181 (TP VIII 205f.; cf. 75,158
 [TP VI 175])
 heartbreak, from grief (*sphuṭitaṃ hṛdayaṃ śucā*) of wives at death of befriended husbands⁷³⁶
 2,43 (TP I 12) and 5,100 (TP I 55); ~ of wife at impalement of husband 10,63 (TP I 111); ~
 from discovered misconduct (*durnaya-vyakti*) 21,94 (TP II 132); queen dies of ~ after
 king's marrying beautiful merchant's daughter 33,72 (TP III 112); afraid of losing chastity
 (*śīla-bhraṃśa-bhayāt*) merchant's wife dies of ~ after king tries to rape her 34,19 (TP III
 129); ~ of mother at son's death 41,57 (TP III 256); ~ from grief for dead brother 53,152
 (TP IV 178); ascetic dies of ~ (*hṛt-sphoṭa*) from beholding the snake Pārāvātākṣa 70,72
 (TP VI 29); ~ from shriek (*rava*) of corpse 73,291 (TP VI 121); death of sister through ~
 at sacrifice of brother 78,74 (TP VI 195); having aggravated king's vice instead of curing it
 minister dies at night of ~ 86,162 (TP VII 25); low water and white mud as signs of broken
 heart of tanks in summer 87,31 (TP VII 31); man dies from ~ with a crack (*tasat-kṛtya*) by

⁷³⁰ For D-text *-vṛddhayā*, see TP VIII 9 note 2.

⁷³¹ In a note Penzer refers to TP VI 71 note 3. Cf. Daś 219.9.

⁷³² Cf. 112,68 (TP VIII 111), where a *caṇḍāla* sylph strikes an infuriated elephant with her hand on its trunk and smites it with her sidelong looks askance (*kare karenāhatya kuṭilais taiḥ kaṭākṣair atādayat*). See also Bollée 2008: 47.

⁷³³ See also: *netra-roga*.

⁷³⁴ See further Bollée 2010a : 150 note 125.

⁷³⁵ STh K 961.1.

⁷³⁶ STh F 1041.1. – As the cardiologist Murray Mittleman and his research team of Harvard Medical School have just discovered the risk of a cardiac infarct within 24 hours of death of a significant person was elevated 21 fold, see <http://circ.ahajournals.org/content/early/2012/01/09/CIRCULATIONAHA111.061770.abstract> (p.c.Christian Weber, Süddeutsche Zeitung of Jan. 10, 2012, p. 16). Nowadays it seems to be more frequent with men than with women, see http://www.actuaries.org.uk/data/assets/pdf_file/0006/128832/Spreeuw_modelling.pdf

sorrow at dead love 95,78 (TP VII 103); young son dies through ~ from grief at loss of his mother's love 106,99 (TP VIII 35); – see also: death

heart-lotus (*hṛt-padma*) torn out and offered to Lakṣmī for son 69,80 (TP VI 14); lotus-like ~ (*hṛt-padma*) of a goat placed on *liṅga* 71,214 (TP VI 51); king tears out ~ (*hṛt-kamala*) and head of wicked hermit and offers them to *vetāla* 99,19 (TP VII 123)

heaven, bodily entry of king into ~ by virtue of part of hermit Vatsa's asceticism 28,90 (TP III 27); ~ becoming red (*piñjara*) indicating it soon being dyed crimson with blood (*raktāruṇa*) 44,134 (TP IV 10); ~ red with blood as when covered with vermilion (*sindūreṇēva kīrṇena ... asṛjāruṇam*) 44,149 (TP IV 11); ~ (as low enjoyment) not desired by wise men 45,113 (TP IV 25); bull of Śiva carries fools holding its tail to ~ 65,185 (TP V 169); stay in ~ can be prolonged indefinitely by *tapas* 72,351 (TP VI 95); in ~ delights can only be seen (*dṛśya-bhoga*), in Kāśmīra, as a second ~, they can be enjoyed (*bhogyā-bhoga*) 73,80 (TP VI 106)⁷³⁷; ~ as woman (? *dyu-vadhū*) 81,17 (TP VI 210, see below under: sun); at sunset ~ places moon on its western quarter like *tilaka* 95,67 (TP VII 102); dharmatic brahmin couple goes to ~ (*divam prāyāt*) 96,6 (TP VII 108); royal in-laws gone to ~ (*śvaśūrau svar-gatau*) 111,57 (TP VIII 101); Indra hit by a mace falls senseless on Vāyu's chariot and is carried to Vāyu's ~ 115,67 (TP VIII 149); – voice from ~ see: voice; – see further also: sun

heavenly maiden, two ~s on throne 17,111 (TP II 43); ~ carries off king in dream 68,6 (TP VI 1); ~ emerges from banyan tree 26,210 (TP II 233); do, from *śiṃśapa* tree and shuts out the mind of an ascetic by a side-long glance of love (*kaṭākṣakṣata-mānasa*) 70,69 (TP VI 29); ~ (*divyākṛtiḥ kanyā*) in lake 75,68 (TP VI 169); ~ resembles a moving lotus lake 81,48 (TP VI 212), et passim; ~ on *kalpa-taru* 86,43 (TP VI 16); two ~s on sandbank in mid-ocean, a white and a dark one 120,105 (TP IX 8) and 121,225 (TP IX 28)⁷³⁸; ~s carry about Indra's son Jayanta as infant 121,236 (TP IX 29); – see also: *apsaras*; beauty; dryad; Nereid; nymph; sylph

heavenly pleasures, see: heaven; pleasures

heel(s), austerities by hanging with ~ upward from tree 32,99 (TP III 97); – see also: Achilles ~

heimatliebe (attachment to one's native country [q.v.]): father-in-law trying to detain son-in-law who is longing for his native land (*sva-deśa-samutsuka*) 18,392 (TP II 79); love more charming than one's native country (*na sasmāra ramyaṃ prema na janma-bhūḥ*) 28,64 (TP III 25); because of ~ (*sva-deśāika-rataḥ*) of Cashmere *pravraj* declines realm of foreign king 66,72 (TP V 183); *janma-bhūmi-vasati-sneha* draws every one 110,139 (TP VIII 92); – see also: disinterest

heir, prince whose kingdom was taken by pretenders flees and enters temple to pass the night 30,80f. (TP III 69); woman ~ is deprived of heritage by relations, and king does not interfere⁷³⁹ 93,9 (TP VII 78); brahmin son as ~ deprived of heritage by relations (*hṛta-vittaḥ*)

⁷³⁷ The second verse quarter: *tridivam sukṛtām kṛte* seems corrupt.

⁷³⁸ Zin 2003b: 223.

- sva-gotra-jaiḥ*) 112,138 (TP VIII 117), cf. *hṛtâgra-hāra* ‘whose royal donation has been taken away’ 114,86 (TP VIII 139)
- heirless king motif, see: son
- hell, pseudo-ascetic’s staying with head downward in river compared to future descent to ~ (*adho-gati*) 24,94 (TP II 176); king sees *rākṣasa* black like darkness and looking like ~ (*pātāla*) embodied in human shape 86,121 (TP VII 21); – see also: *Andha-tāmisra*; *Avīci*
- help, cry for ~ (*mām uddharata bho*) 36,99 (TP III 176); *trāyadhvam!* 71,222 (TP VI 52); *hema-daṇḍa* (not MW), see: gold sticks
- hema-kalaśa* 91,30 (TP VII 68 lacuna)
- hemanta-hastin* see: elephant of winter
- hen-crow defaecates on hermit and is incinerated by his eyes 56,171f. and 175 (TP IV 232)⁷⁴⁰
- hen-cuckoo (*pikī*), see: *pika*
- hen-koel (*kokilā*) distressed with separation from mate (*viraha-klāntā*) sits on mango 111,21 (TP VIII 97);
- hen-maina (*śārikā*) 77,8 (TP VI 183); ~ becomes *apsaras* Tilottamā after curse ends 77,90 (TP VI 189); ~ together with parrot 103,198 (TP VII 188);
- henna⁷⁴¹ (*mendhī*) see Bollée 2008: 50 note 70.
- herald, prince panegyrised by ~s and minstrels (*bandi-māgadhair*) 34,127 (TP III 137); 38,7 and 14 (TP III 206); – see also: bard; minstrel
- Heramba, see: Gaṇeśa.
- herb, magic⁷⁴² healing ~s of a *siddha* Piśāca from Himālaya cure brahmin’s wound 28,169 (TP III 33); ~s dispelling old age, death and fear grow on Himavat plateaux 35,19 (TP III 156); hair of *Asura* Maya gleams like potent ~s on mountain peaks 45,4 (TP IV 17); magic⁷⁴³ ~ (*auśadhayaḥ siddhāḥ*) in Mt Candrapāda cave 46,188 (TP IV 61); seven divine ~s 46,209 (TP IV 62); *haṃsī* restored to life by juice of ~ able to revive the dead (*mṛta-saṃjīva nāuśadhi*) 69,137 (TP VI 18); stocks and ~s (*kāṣṭhāny api tṛṇāny api*) weep with compassion 101,255 (TP VII 152); ~ that shines in the night (*pradoṣa-jvalita*) protects men (from witches) (*rakṣā-mahāuśadhi*) 108,47 (TP VIII 56)⁷⁴⁴
- herdsman, compassion of ~ with lonely woman 29,155 (TP III 51); foolish ~ taken out by rogues 61,19ff. (TP V 69); 68,46 (TP VI 5)
- heretic, female ~ (*pākhaṇḍā*) tells woman to kill her son and offer him to deity 61,290 (TP V

⁷³⁹ At the time of ŚpBr 4.4.2.13 women did not dispose of the heritage (see also Rau 1957: 41f.), but for Kullūka in his commentary on Manu IX 187, the widow stands fourth in the line of heirs, as against Medhātithi, who denies a widow to inherit (Bühler 1886: 367).

⁷⁴⁰ In Haribhadra’s *Maṇipati-Carita* 57 it is a crane and the hermit consumes it with his spiritual fire (Williams 1959: 294).

⁷⁴¹ On henna see further Gode 1961: 347ff.; Kelting 2009: 133f.

⁷⁴² Cf. STh *D 965.

⁷⁴³ I herewith prefer Osier’s translation to the “virtuous herbs” of TP.

⁷⁴⁴ Jackmuth 2002: 79ff.; HdA 3: 1909 and 1920.

94); male ~ (*pākhaṇḍin*), *kāpālika* as ~ 124,16 (TP IX 69)
 heritage, relations take ~ from merchant's son after death of father⁷⁴⁵ 6,29 (TP I 62) and 36,74 (TP III 174); brahmin brothers divide ~ literally in two parts, even cattle and *dāsī* 62,174f. (TP V 114); ~ taken from merchant's widow by relatives as king could not protect her (*rājā-sānāthyād*) 93,9 (TP VII 78 with note 3)⁷⁴⁶; ~ taken from brahmin orphan sons by relatives 96,7 (TP VII 108) and 114,86 (TP VIII 139);
 hermit, see: ascetic; *devarsī*; mendicant
 hero(es) love submission (proverb: *śūrā hi praṇati-priyāḥ*) 19,88 (TP II 91); – see also: ball; battle; bed; body; combat; fifteen; four; Himavat; *kārapāṭika*; muttering; science; sword; thirty-three; wise man; Yama
 heron's young eaten by snake which is then killed by mongoose 60,234 (TP V 61 with note 3)
hima-dīdhiti 'cold-rayed moon', see: moon
 Himavat, **description** of ~ 1,13 (TP I 2); ~ speaking to hermit 62,132 (TP V 110); even heroes cannot reach ~'s top 90,4 (TP VII 49)
 hip(s) (or: loins), husband makes trident mark on ~ of adulterous wife 75,160 (TP VI 175); broad ~ (*jaḡhanābhoga*) of princesses looking like head of the elephant of love 118,164 (TP VIII 189)
hitōpadeśo mūrkhasya kopāyāiva, na śāntaye 'good advice given to a fool does not calm but rather enrages him' 74,74 (TP VI 145);
 hitting, see: brahmin (20,14); miscarriage; daughter (66,139 and 158); dhobi; feet; horse; kick; mother-in-law
 hoarding, excessive ~ (*atisaṃcaya*) condemned 61,105 (TP V 77);
 Holi festival⁷⁴⁷, four men invited for rendez-vous at ~ (*madhūtsava*) 4,35ff. (TP I 33); (*madhumahōtsava*) 20,54 (TP II 99); **23,76ff.** (TP II 163); 35,6 (TP III 155); *vasantōtsava* **54,58** (TP IV 188); 55,107ff. (TP IV 209); 67,48 (TP V 199); 85,6 (TP VII 10); 91,22 (TP VII 67)
homa-lāja, see: grain
 homoeopathy, see: similia similibus
 homosexuality (female), see: lesbianism
 homo viator: buying off assassins brahmin emigrates 3,42 (TP I 22); – see also: mourning tour; pilgrimage; tourism
 honour, signs of, see: *elephant*; *lilā-vajra*; *purohita*; turban; sunshade
 honouring a person by presents of garments, horses, turban, etc. see s.v.; ~ by letting him walk in

⁷⁴⁵ At least in the older period the law of the jungle dominates in heritage (Rau 1957: 45).

⁷⁴⁶ Thus B; D corrects the metre and reads: *tad-dhanaṃ rāja-sānāthyād ākrāntam atha gotra-jaiḥ* 'his (the merchant's) property being taken by his relatives because the king helped them.' ORC 999: "ses parents s'approprèrent ses biens sans que le roi pût s'y opposer"; M II 320: "Die Verwandten rissen unter tatkräftigem Schutz des Königs dessen Vermögen an sich."

⁷⁴⁷ See Anderson 2005: 95-109 (ch. 6); Raghavan 1979: 193-201; Kane 1977 V 2: 237-41 (Holikā); Meyer 1937; <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Holi#References> For an illustration see Jackson 2010: 146f.

front of one (*puraskṛta*) 67,18 (TP V 197)⁷⁴⁸; – see also: etiquette; gestures
 hoopoe, see: *svarṇa-cūla*
 hope, pregnant woman supported by ~ of offspring (*apatyâśā*) as by a friend 34,39 (TP III 130)
 horn(s), of pride (*mada-śṛṅga*) 27,13 (TP III 2); by a charm *yakṣiṇī* produces ~ on forehead of visitors⁷⁴⁹ of Śiva temple and devours them 37,58 (TP III 187)⁷⁵⁰; stupid man called *vṛṣabha* without ~ (*viṣāṇe*) 40,8 (TP III 240); ~s of hare 40,21 (TP III 241); hunt of Bhillas by sounding cow's ~ (*go-śṛṅga*) 59,41 (TP V 29); – see also: cow; evil eye; exorcism; goat; hare
 horny skin, see: *pāruṣya*
 horoscopes, conformity of ~ (*ānukūlya*) (necessary for marriage) 52,141 (TP IV 147); – see also: *janmarkṣa*
 horripilation⁷⁵¹ from joy 10,207 (TP I 120); ~ (*romāñca*) 14,28 (TP I 184); ~ (*ūrdhva-keśa*) in confusion 20,50 (TP II 98); ~ (*ūrdhva-romāḥ*) from cold 25,89 (TP II 197); ~ of *rākṣasa* (*ūrdhva-keśa*) 25,105 (TP II 198); ~ from joy (*sa-kaṇṭhakaiḥ aṅgaiḥ*) 25,220 (TP II 207); 74,235 (TP VI 157); *rājput*'s ~ from erotic passion 81,54 (TP VI 212); *Jimūtavāhana*'s ~ likened to coat of mail 90,165 (TP VII 60); 101,77 (TP VII 139); woman's hairs erect from joy likened to feathers at the end of Kāma's arrows 103,63 (TP VII 179); 107,48 (TP VIII 46); *kaṇṭakitā*, of a princess in love 122,48 (TP IX 37); brahmin's ~ from fright at seeing his wife being a cannibal 124,100 (TP IX 75); – see also: hair
 horse carries off king to forest 18,96 (TP II 56)⁷⁵²; excellent ~ (*hayōttama*) is divine being 18,100 (TP II 56); ~s of Turuṣkas beaten by elephants 19,109 (TP II 93); are ~s of the sun black or white? 22,182 (TP II 150); snakes defile ~s of the sun by spitting poison over them 22,183 (TP II 150); a king should first tame the ~s of the senses (*indriyâśva*) 24,191 (TP III 142); ~ kicks man and flings him into lake 26,82 (TP II 223); ~ carries away king on hunt 32,105 (TP III 97); two witches in form of mares fighting each other 37,162 (TP III 194f.); ~ killed by lion 42,47 (TP III 262); ~s die of thirst at noon 42,98 (TP III 265); stolen ~ 30,101 (TP III 71); ~ *Uccaiḥśravas* smells dead *Asura* to life 46,224 (TP IV 63)⁷⁵³; *Mātali* gives *vidyādhara* prince celestial ~ 59,68 (TP V 31); race between elephant and horses 67,8ff. (TP V 196f.); man gives ~ seven blows daily with stick before his meal 68,56 (TP VI 5); white ~ and magic sword given by *Gaurī* to snake princess (*nāga-kanyā*) *Vijayavatī* 72,47 and 52 (TP VI 72); king gives ~ and sword to princely refugee 72,167

⁷⁴⁸ Cf. *purohita* (Gonda 1975: II 320ff.).

⁷⁴⁹ Thus turning them into animals and avoiding the impression of anthropophagy. In 105,27 (TP VIII 25) meat is offered to *yakṣa*.

⁷⁵⁰ STh D 1375.1.3.

⁷⁵¹ STh F 1041.2.

⁷⁵² Cf. Kuv 27.5. On horses see, e.g. Hein 1989.

⁷⁵³ ORC 503: “U. le ramenait à la vie en lui soufflant dessus.”

(TP VI 81); merchant's ~ white as the moon (*śasâṅka-dhavala*) and with curls of hair on its neck (*rocamāna*) (**description**) 74,77 (TP VI 145)⁷⁵⁴; ~ of endurance (*dhairya*) 74,105 (TP VI 147); battle about ~ between princes 74,81ff. (TP VI 146); king leaves ~ outside (hermitage; *bahiḥ sthāpita-vāhanaḥ*) and enters ... 94,36 (TP VII 89); princess and attendants got up behind men on horse-back 103,73 (TP VII 180); ~ in forbidden palace room kicks hermit into temple of Śiva 108,56 (TP VIII 57); heavenly ~ goes with a wish 118,102 (TP VIII 185); white mare of pure Sindh breed (*su-Saindhavī*) and black Konkan mare 121,278 (TP IX 32); female servant (*ceṭī*) eats mare (*turagī*) 124,99 (TP IX 75); – see also: abduction; curl; king; magic horse
 horse fodder (*ghāsa*), king himself⁷⁵⁵ feeds horse with ~ 42,42 (TP III 262)⁷⁵⁶
 horse sacrifice, see: *āsvamedha*
 horticulture, Durgā gives poor brahmin in Bharukaccha heavenly seed for a beautiful garden (*kāntam udyānam*) and tells him to keep it in good order (*pālyam*) 6,84f. (TP I 66); – see also: garden
 hospitality (*ātithya-sat-kriyā*)⁷⁵⁷ of poor woman 2,50 (TP I 13); brahmin accepts willy nilly ~ in house of other brahmin with dull sons 7,50 (TP I 78); daughter given to king as hospitable entertainment 45,310 (TP IV 37)⁷⁵⁸; ~ only fruitful in this world 47,7 (TP IV 67); 49,202f. (TP IV 98); offering food with meat-curry (*māṃsa-vyañjana*) and ghee 54,170 (TP IV 196); ~ shown by courtesan to king 58,18 (TP V 16); 59,82 (TP V 32); prince is offered full ~ (*arḡha-pātrikṛta*) by *vidyādhari* but of herself 59,138 (TP V 35); ~ of tree-spirit 63,70ff. (TP V 125); Ṭakka miser wants to eat milk rice (*kṣīriṇī*) but stays in bed for fear that some guest (*prāghuṇika*) would come and see him 65,142ff. (TP V 166)⁷⁵⁹; prince entertained with ~ (*sat-kāraiḥ*) 67,20 (TP V 197); prince gives sister to other prince making the duty of hospitality an excuse for doing so (*upacāra-vṛttim ālambya yuktim*) 67,113 (TP V 204; ORC 785: “*prenant comme prétexte les exigences de la courtoisie*”); ~ of hermitage shown by trees with fruit and singing birds 69,117 (TP VI 17); Indra burns forest by *māyā* in order to prevent king to show wayfarers ~ with fruits 72,372f. (TP VI 96); 73,18 (TP VI 101); king refuses ~ of *Asura* maiden 81,84 (TP VI 214); attendant gives royal guest garland with the *arḡhya* as ~ 90,54 (TP VII 53); ~ is obligation of hermit life (*āśramiṇāṃ dharmo*) 94,28 (TP VII 89); robbers give ~ to two *caṇḍālas* and make them their chiefs (*mukhya-caura*) 114,114 (TP VIII 141); ~ (*sat-kāra*) offered to royal

⁷⁵⁴ See also Kuv 23.13ff.

⁷⁵⁵ Negelein 1903: 14. A picture of horse feeding on a Gandhāra relief is in Snead, Doniger & Michell 1989: 110 plate 79, but there will probably be gram in the trough whereas in the above reference grass may be meant.

⁷⁵⁶ Gonda 1985: 139 only gives four Vedic references; Gode 1961: I 193ff. in his many papers on horse food does not mention *ghāsa*.

⁷⁵⁷ See Bornet 2010; Mills 2003: 287f.; Balbir 2001; Jamison 1996. – Hypocrites are excluded from hospitality (Manu iv. 192ff.).

⁷⁵⁸ Cf. STh T 281.

⁷⁵⁹ Balbir 2001: 374.

messenger 120,94 (TP IX 8); 123,247 (TP IX 60; brahmin offers foreign Veda students four months ~ in his house 124,153 (TP IX 79); – see also: etiquette; *grhâcāra*; Kuntī; three objects

hot season, see: summer

hounds used in ravines 21,16 (TP II 126); 27,150 (TP III 12)

house, of Varṣa turned ant-hill by mice 2,49 (TP I 13); old woman in old ~ 3,55 (TP I 22);

householder, stage of ~ best 24,152 (TP II 180)

hr̥dyā, see: fish

hṛtâgra-hāra, see: heir

*hṛt-padma*⁷⁶⁰ (heart-lotus) torn out by king as sacrifice to Lakṣmī 69,80 (TP VI 14);

Hūhū⁷⁶¹ and Hāhā, Indra festival with songs of ~ 116,88 (TP VIII 162)

human existence, object of ~ is salvation through meditation and ascetism for 12 years 73,171 (TP VI 113);

human fat, lamps fed by oil made from ~ (*mahā-taila-jvalad-dīpa*) 73,306 (TP VI 123); – see also: candle

human flesh, king propitiates Caṇḍikā by burnt-offering of his own ~ 11,37 (TP I 125);

sacrifice of ~ 20,51 (TP II 99); woman afraid of eating ~ (*nṛ-māṃsâśana-bhīta*) necessary for witches' spells 20,105 (TP II 103); ~ practice of witches (*mahā-māṃsa-bhojanaṃ ḍākinī-naye*) 20,191 (TP II 112); pyre seems to bear presiding deity of *rākṣasas* in visible form (*nṛ-māṃsa-grāhiṇiṃ sâkṣād iva rakṣo-'dhīdevatām*) devouring ~ 25,100 (TP II 197); evening oblation offered with ~ (*piśita*) left by jackals 25,135 (TP II 201); ~ offered for sale by brahmin on charnel ground at night 25,183 (TP II 205 with note 2); ~ (*mānuṣâṅgaiḥ*) offered to imp of fever-demon (*jvara-ceṭaka*) to make him obliging 71,208 (TP VI 50); king sacrifices heart and head of wicked mendicant to *vetāla* 99,19 (TP VII 123); own ~ sacrificed to *vetāla* 99,50 (TP VII 126)⁷⁶²; gambler sells ~ for shape and power (*rūpa-prabhāvau*) of a *vetāla* 121,53ff. (TP IX 15); brahmin's wife eats husband's servant 124,98 (TP IX 75); – see also: cannibalism; flesh

human sacrifice⁷⁶³ of brahmin prisoner by Śavara chief to Caṇḍikā 10,141 (TP I 116); 13,63 (TP I 154); Durgā asks for ~ 18,163 (TP II 62); ~ by queen 20,51 and 105 (TP II 99 and 103); 20,189 and 208 (TP II 111 and 113); ~ in Durgā temple, but victim saved by brahmin 18,174 (TP II 63) and by Pulindaka 22,65 (TP II 141); ~ of brahmin in Durgā temple 26,144 (TP II 227); ~ to *vetāla* 26,238 (TP II 235); ~ to a dead Turuṣka 37,39 (TP III 185); Lakṣmaṇa takes Rāma's son for a ~ 51,101 (TP IV 129); ~ of brahmin son to Caṇḍikā in order to save king 53,133 (TP IV 177); ~ of man by Bhil to Bhavānī 61,158 (TP V 81); ~ planned to get power over attendant of fever demon (*jvara-ceṭaka*) 71,208 (TP VI 50); ~

⁷⁶⁰ Syed 1990: 658.

⁷⁶¹ Hūhū is a proverbial singer in Hemacandra, *Triṣaṣṭi* VI 2,117.

⁷⁶² Cf. Rājāt 1,133 where king gives of his own flesh to witch.

⁷⁶³ See also below s.v. sacrifice, and ORC 1637; further Crooke 1896: II 167ff.; Kinsley 1986: 145; Mallebrein 1998: 71; Daṇḍin, *Daś* 16,13.

to goddess Caṇḍikā to save king 78,50 (TP VI 194); ~ (*narôpahāra*) of brahmin boy offered by king to *brahma-rakṣasa* on seventh day 94,117 (TP VII 95); king sacrifices head and heart of ascetic to *vetāla* in corpse 99,19 (TP VII 123); ~ to Devī prepared by Pulindas on fourteenth day 101,300 (TP VII 155); hermit cooks child with rice, eats it and is then able to follow his *vidyādhari* wife in the air 108,76 (TP VIII 59); – see also: black magic; Pṛthivī; sacrifice

human statues of gold as automata given by Kubera 38,81 (TP III 212); ~ of wood as automata lifeless by their want of speech 43,11f. (TP III 281); ~ of boy carried around towns, etc. on *karnī-ratha* (q.v.) 94,90 (TP VII 93)

human trafficking, brahmin wants to sell Rāma and Lakṣmaṇa in the market 113,81 (TP VIII 130)

human voice, goose with ~ (*vyaktayā girā*) 56,243 (TP IV 237);

humbleness, performing ones duties with ~ leads to *jyoti* ‘supreme brightness’ 56,190 (TP IV 233); – see also: *nir-ahaṅkāra*

humiliation by queen causes king’s depression 6,126 and 132 (TP I 70); king gives daughter box on the ear by which ~ (*avamāna*) she flees into the forest 66,139f. (TP V 189)

humkāra (‘menacing sound’) made by Śambhu-Śiva 4,24 (TP I 32); ~, made by Viṣṇu 44,152 (TP IV 11); ~, made by Rudra-Śiva against Indra 50,84 (TP IV 113); ~, made against Caṇḍāla by Mahēśvara 112,192 (TP VIII 121)

humour (*hāsyā*), story with ~ 12,77 (TP I 138)

Hūṇas defeated 19,111 (TP II 94)

hunchbacked man (*kubja*), produced by charm 12,51 (TP I 136); attempt to straighten hump of ~ 62,231 (TP V 119)⁷⁶⁴;

hundred,⁷⁶⁵ wives (*patnī-śata*) of king Virabhuja 39,5 (TP III 218); ~ *khārīs* of sesame-seed to be sown outside town 39,116 (TP III 226); living a ~ years 78,51 (TP VI 194); ~ rings taken by adulterous woman from lovers 63,30f. (TP V 122); ~ lovers of a snake goddess 64,157 (TP V 151); king shall live a ~ years after sacrifice of servant’s son 78,51 (TP VI 194); ~ years propitiating Brahmā for son 115,4 (TP VIII 144); ~ villages and golden statue as prize for human sacrifice to *brahma-rākṣasa* 94,94 (TP VII 93f.); Bhilla chief gives daughter to king with ~ camels laden with pearls and musk 123,77 (TP IX 48);

hundred-eight, wings of flying lotus-chariot (*padma-vimāna*) 46,124 (TP IV 57); king worships Lakṣmī daily with ~ white lotuses on a sword in order to get a son 69,78 (TP VI 14);

hundred- thousand gold pieces daily under child’s pillow 3,22 (TP I 19);

hunger, sight of wonderful dolls takes away ~ of princess 29,23 (TP III 40); ~ satisfied by

⁷⁶⁴ See Siegel 1985: 176.

⁷⁶⁵ Hundred and thousand often stand for many, e.g. ṚV IV 30,16 of Indra as *śatā-kratu* ‘hundredfold inventive or resourceful’ (Geldner: “ratreich”), ṚV VI 46,3 *sahasra-muṣka* ‘of a thousand testicles’, and Bāna, *Kād.* 462,7ff. in the description of the old ascetic being bitten thousands of times by kraits when sleeping in empty temples and suffering centuple concussions when falling from trees.

eating seventh cake 62,205 (TP V 116); brahmin couple suffers from burning ~ (*jaṭharâgni*) 73,58 (TP VI 105)

hunter delivers Damayanī from serpent, but fallen in love with her is reduced to ashes 56,326 (TP IV 244); – see also: *palāśa*

hunt(ing) (*mṛgayā*), as royal vice 9,9 (TP I 95)⁷⁶⁶; idem, 11,3 and 10 (TP I 122f.); ~ (*ākhetaka*) 16,6 (TP II 20); **21,11ff.** (TP II 126); ~ with dogs in ravines and with nets in glades 21,16 (TP II 126); Nārada urges king to give up ~ **21,30 (TP II 127)**; ~ elephants for pearls in their heads 22,76 (TP II 142); **21,28ff.** (TP II 127); ~ approved as exercise (*vyāyāma*) for kings 27,146 (TP III 12); ~ with horses, footmen, dogs and nets 27,150 (TP III 12); in the excitement of the ~ (*mṛgayā-rasāt*) king, carried away by his horse, enters hermitage 32,105 (TP III 97); royal ardour for chase (*mṛgayā-rasa*) 35,57 (TP III 159); depiction of ~ **42,3ff.** (TP III 259)⁷⁶⁷; ~ of Bhillas sounding cow's horns 59,41 (TP V 29); king goes ~ for distraction 66,144 (TP V 189) and 69,87 (TP VI 15); ~ boars as means of dispelling distress (*udvega-vinoda*) 94,8 (TP VII 87); hermit Kaṇva enjoins king to stop vice of ~ 94,42 (TP VII 90); king goes out to ~ (*tad-rasâkrṣṭe niragān mṛgayākṛte*) 123,9 (TP IX 43); ~ as royal vice see: vice; – see also: king; *kr̥tānta-kr̥ḍita*

hunting, green ~ -coat (*palāśa-śyāma-kañcuka*) 21,11 (TP II 126)⁷⁶⁸

hurricane (*prabhañjana*) blows like Destiny 25,42 (TP II 192); can one fetter a ~ (*utpāta-vātāli*) with one's arms ? 36,93 (TP III 176); 64,138 (TP V 150); ~ (*sa-sūtkāra-marut*) wrecks ship 101,140 (TP VII 144); do, (*mahān utpāta-māruta*) 101,175 (TP VII 146); – see also: destiny; grief; thunderstorm

husband, do maidens obtain ~s by worshipping Gaṇeśa ? 20,57 (TP II 99); ~ leaves pregnant wife 21,111 (TP II 133)⁷⁶⁹; ~ is refuge of women in both worlds 29,98 (TP III 46) and 39,47 (TP III 221); princess seeking matching ~ 30,13 (TP III 65); father determines ~ for princess 30,26 (TP III 65); as boon Gaurī shows Uṣā ~ in a dream 31,12 (TP III 82); ~ prostituting his wife 43,86 (TP III 287); infidelity to ~ (*bharṭṛ-droha*) strips Anaṅgaprabhā of knowledge (*bhraṣṭa-vidyā*) to fly 52,209 (TP IV 152)⁷⁷⁰; fidelity to ~ leads to wife's knowledge of past, future and present 52,228ff. (TP IV 154); aversion from ~ (*bharṭṛ-*

⁷⁶⁶ At 27,147 (TP III 12) it is said that wild animals desire depopulation of the world and that the king should therefore slay them. The latest case of this royal vice is that of the Spanish king Juan Carlos in Botswana in April 2012 at which elephant safari he broke his hip. – STh R 12.1.

⁷⁶⁷ Cf. STh N 771.

⁷⁶⁸ See Mānasollāsa II 4,1471 (p. 279). Kād 214,7 describes huntsmen (*śva-poṣaka*) as “wearing clothing speckled like the hides of old tigers” (Layne 1991: 113; *jarad-vyāghra-carma-śabala-vasana-kañcuka-dhārin*).

⁷⁶⁹ As in the country nowadays, and thus probably also in the past, pregnancy is a matter of shame and fear of childbirth pollution, when a woman is in labour, her family, especially the male members and even the husband stay away (Jeffery 2008: 100). A delivery is normally attended by a couple of married women from the labouring woman's own compound and neighbouring ones (Jeffery 2008:100). For the position and activity, only at the delivery, of the midwife see Jeffery 2008: 108ff.

⁷⁷⁰ Cf. 52,236 (TP IV 154).

vidveṣa) 52,355 (TP IV 162); effeminate (*klība*) ~ of woman is to be blamed 52,370 (TP IV 164); at night wife sees that ~ is eunuch (*na-puṃsaka*)⁷⁷¹ 56,86 (TP IV 226); woman devoted to ~ has power of discernment (*viññāna-bala*) 56,180 (TP IV 232); wicked wife accuses ~ of killing a Bhilla 61,164 (TP V 82); silly ~ carries wife with paramour on his head 62,115 (TP V 108); woman nicknamed Daśamārikā after death of ten ~s 66,86 (TP V 184)⁷⁷²; princess worships Śauri-Viṣṇu to get ~ 71,201 (TP VI 50); ~ kills wife when asleep, takes her ornaments and leaves 77,45 (TP VI 186); woman causes ~ and brother to change heads 80,47 (TP VI 207); ~ distasteful to wife is as bitter medicine to sick man (*sa-rogasya kaṭu-tiktam auśadham*) 95,9 (TP VII 98); wife with only one lock weeping for absent ~ 106,77 (TP VIII 34); royal ~ gives away only wife 113,75 (TP VIII 129); obtaining ~ by means of austerities 117,179 (TP VIII 176); for women of good family ~ is god (*paramātmā hi patiḥ kulāṅganānām*) 117,173 (TP VIII 176)⁷⁷³; austerities on behalf of imprisoned ~ 118,108 (TP VIII 185); – husband compared to flower, wife to bee, see: bee(s)

husband-killer⁷⁷⁴ (woman throws husband into well) 34,186 (TP III 141); ~ banished 58,77 (TP V 20); intended ~ (*bhartur vadhāiṣiṇī*) 65,16 (TP V 154); 66,97 (TP V 184 ‘eleven-slayer’);

Huta-bhuk, see: Agni

hymn of praise (*stotra*) to Caṇḍikā before suicide 53,165 (TP IV 179), but cf. ~ (*stuti*) to Ambikā-Durgā 78,89 (TP VI 196); ~ to Gaṇeśa 55,162 (TP IV 213); ~ to Viṣṇu Śauri sung by Gandharva princess to *viññā* 106,11 (TP VIII 28); do, by king Naravāhanadatta 106,28 (TP VIII 30);

hypocritical, mother 29,82 (TP III 45); ~ cat with *ahiṃsā* vow 62,51 (TP V 103); ~ (*kūṭa-kuśalā*) wife says to paramour to love her husband best 62,111 (TP V 108); – see also: ascetic; washing

iatromagic, see: *bhū-grha*; medicine; physician

Icarus motif, see: flying

ichneumon, see: mongoose

ichor⁷⁷⁵, elephants raining ~ (*mada*) compared to Vindhya peaks 14,11 (TP I 182); 19,68 (TP II 90); elephants seem to discharge the waters of the Godāvāri sevenfold in the form of ~ 19,97 (TP II 92f.)⁷⁷⁶; wounded hero likened to must elephant stained with ~ (*dānāmbu*)

⁷⁷¹ See ORC 1567.

⁷⁷² Cf. STh *T 172.0.1.

⁷⁷³ Cf. Manu 5,154 and see Doniger O’Flaherty 1980a: 259f.

⁷⁷⁴ See Bollée 2005a § 794. The locus classicus in Sanskrit may be Bāṇa, *Harṣacarita* (Bombay, 1946) 200, 2ff.

⁷⁷⁵ This tar-like sweetish (according to Kurt 1986: 132: bitter), sticky fluid (Edgerton 1931: 34), temporin, contains odorous ketones and aldehydes, see www.wikipedia.org/wiki/Musth and see Kurt 2014: 4.4.

In Greek mythology the blood of the deities is called ichor: ῥέε δ’ ἄμβροτον αἶμα θεοῖο ἰχώρ (Homer, *Iliad* V 339f.).

72,7 (TP VI 67); the water of the celestial Ganges smells of ~ of Indra's elephant 115,146 (TP VIII 154); (*mātaṅga-mada-niṣyanda*) used as *maṇḍana* (decoration)⁷⁷⁷ by Bhilla women 123,50 (TP IX 46 which takes *maṇḍana* wrongly to mean 'perfume', as do ORC 1289 and M II 720: "sinnberaubenden Wohlgeruch" [!])⁷⁷⁸;

ichthyomy (*mātsya-nyāya*), gods introduced the magical name of king out of fear of ~ (that the strong would devour the weak; law of the jungle) 102,63 (TP VII 167)

ignorance, king laughed at and ashamed of his ~ of grammar 6,118 (TP I 70); ~ to be avoided (*a-jñānaṇi hātavyaṇi*) 72,204 (TP VI 83); ~ has to be done away with 72,272 (TP VI 88); ~ laughed at 75,19 (TP VI 165); ~ of prostration pretended 98,70 (TP VII 121)

illiterate porter finds royal bracelet (*kaṭaka*) 57,15 (TP V 2);

illness, see: disease

illuminating power of female beauty, of two heavenly maidens 17,111 (TP II 43)

illusion, Prajāpati's power of ~ substitutes Kalingasenā's son for Rati turned into a mortal maiden 34,42 (TP III 131); ~ makes Kalingasenā's daughter lose recollection of former state 34,94 (TP III 135); ~ of love-sick man that painting is real beloved princess 72,295ff.

⁷⁷⁶ In Kālidāsa, *Ragh* 4.23 ichor issues from seven openings in the body of elephants (Hensgen 1958: 43) or many more (Edgerton 1931: 34 and 81 < *Mātaṅgalilā* IX 5). This poetical or mythological phantasy about ichor was satyriized by Haribhadra in his *Dhuttakkhāṇa* IV 19f. (Krümpelmann 2000: 149). This text ascribes these stanzas to the Mbh, but the reference to this source as an authority for the emergence of a large river from the ichor is odd and must be part of the satire which Krümpelmann may not have been conscious of (for this place I am obliged to Dr Luitgard Soni). According to Kurt (1986: 132) there is only one opening, a slit of one to three cms long, on each side between the eye and the ear.

⁷⁷⁷ As to the rendering of all translations sofar: the ad hoc change of meaning of 'decoration' > 'perfume' may be based on the apparently sweetish smell of the substance of young elephants, but there is no reason for this assumption because Kād. 70,3 mentions a Śabara chieftain who has the ichor of wild elephants as cosmetic (*vanakari-madair aṅga-rāgaḥ*). Moreover, Fred Kurt (p.c.) excludes the use of ichor as perfume. Another black decoration is a bra-like coverlet smeared with black aloe adorning royal women's lofty breasts (*ullasita-kuca-kṛṣṇāguru-paṅka-pattra-latāṅkita-pracchada-paṭam*, Kād 130,4; 137,1), and lines of aloe on the cheeks of a royal baby are compared to ichor at Kād 142,4. If at all, in the 20st century the Bhil women do not use ichor anymore; Koppers, at any rate, does not mention it, at least not in his section on *Frauenschmuck* (Koppers 1948: 101ff.). – To my knowledge, ichor is curiously never mentioned in connection with Gaṇeśa.

⁷⁷⁸ Cf. Bāṇa, *Kād.* 64,8 where the Śabara chieftain's body is smeared with fragrant ichor from the temples of recently slain elephants, so that its odor was that of *saptacchada* blossoms (Layne 1991: 31): *acira-prahata-gajakapola-grhītena saptacchada-parimala-vāhinā kṛṣṇāgaru-paṅktenēva surabhiṇā madena kṛtāṅga-rāgam*. The scent of ichor, which for humans is only strong with bulls in rut (Straube 2013; p.c. Ms A. Suess of Hagenbecks Tierpark, Hamburg), is compared to that of the sap of the *saptacchada* (ditabark, *Alstonia scholaris*) tree (references in Edgerton 1931: 84 < *Mātaṅgalilā* IX 15; Syed 1990: 591f. where the plant's odour is called acrid [*scharf*]), but the ichor of *gandha-gajas* is called sweet-smelling (Bāṇa, *Kād.* 64,8; 319,1). Jackmuth 2002: 196 assumes that elephants are fragrant and therefore receptive which they show through their ichor. This, however, not true; moreover, also elephant cows occasionally show ichor. Anna Esposito (2004: 269) rendered the king's road made fragrant by the ichor of the impetuous elephant Bhadrakapotaka (*ugga-vegena passuda-mada-gandham rāa-maggam karanteṇa maṅgala-hatthiṇā Bhaddaka-vodaṇa*); it may be safer to say that the road smelled after ichor. The name "Little young good one" given the young animal has stuck then for the *mada* appears at obtaining maturity, the age of twelve. Bhaddavatī is the elephant of king Udena in Pali; for young elephants see PED s.v. *potaka*.

(TP VI 90f.); ~ created under water by *iṣṭa-saṃpādini vidyā* 92,50 (TP VII 74); illustration (*dr̥ṣṭānta*), see: comparison; metaphor; poet; simile
 image of Gaṇeśa/Vināyaka carved out of a jewel, found in Mālava 73,325 (TP VI 124); golden ~ of brahmin boy offered as reward for parents giving their son as victim to *brahma-rākṣasa* 94,90ff. (TP VII 93);
 immolation,⁷⁷⁹ of queen (*vahnim āviśat*) due to false report of husband's death 58,38 (TP V 17); – see also: *agni-praveśa*; *kṣīriṇī*; pyre
 immortality, water of ~ guarded by wheel-machine (*cakra-yantra* [q.v.]) 29,47 (TP III 42);
 immunity from death, see: Achilles' heel
 imp of fever demon (*jvara-ceṭaka*) 71,207 (TP VI 50);
 impaled man on stake sits low enough to be hit by shoulder of woman passing in the night 93,13 (TP VII 79)
 impalement, robber put to death by ~ 10,62 (TP I 111)⁷⁸⁰; 18,139 (TP II 60); place of ~ (*sūlādhiropaṇa-sthāna*) 72,194 (TP VI 83); robber ordered to ~ (*sūlāropaṇa*) 88,32 (TP VII 37); 112,168 (TP VIII 120); – see also: heartbreak; sun
 impatience of princess as to wedding day 101,130 (TP VII 143);
 impermanence of things in this world (*bhaṅgure 'smin bhava kasya sthīratā* ?) 111,58 (TP VIII 101)
 impossibility, examples of ~ : *citra-kalpanā*; horn of hare; painting in the sky; sand bridge over the Ganges; writing without letters 40,22 (TP III 241); – see also: ~ motif TP III 250f. and V 64ff.; – wonder
 impotence of Arjuna through curse of spurned Rambhā 33,90 (TP III 114)
 imprisonment (*bandha*), only ~ in city of Kanakapura was the committing of poets' words to leaves (*kavi-girāṃ chedaḥ patreṣu*) 55,27 (TP IV 204, ORC 610: “*on n'y emprisonnait que des fragments de poèmes*”);
 impunity, see: *a-bhaya*
 impurity, see: dirt; flies
 inauguration of queen by king because of affection (*prītyābhiṣicya*) 6,167 (TP I 73); ~ of emperor Sūryaprabha 50,205 and empress 207 (TP IV 121); ~ of Jimūtavāhana *cakra vartin* by Gaurī with her own hand with water from her pitcher (*kalaśāmbudhi*) 90,188f. (TP VII 62); all discernment is washed out of kings when the waters of ~ are poured over them 91,55 (TP VII 70); ~ (*abhiṣeka*)⁷⁸¹ of prince with turban (*paṭṭa*) 103,218 and one hundred women as present 219 (TP VII 190); ~ of king 103,231 with water (*tīrthōdaka*) on his and his wife's head 103,233 (TP VII 191); ~ on Mt R̥ṣabha 110,43 (TP VIII 85); ~ of emperor 110,79ff. and 83 of empress (TP VIII 87f.); ~ as emperor with sprinkling of water 113,88 (TP VIII 130); – see also: coronation; inthronisation
 incantation, see: spell

⁷⁷⁹ Bollée 2008a: 18 note 79.

⁷⁸⁰ STh Q 461.

⁷⁸¹ Gonda 1969: 87ff.

incarnation, of poverty (*rūpinī durgati*), woman as ~ 2,52 (TP I 13); ~ of sorrow (*śucaṃ mūrtimatīm*) 9,62 (TP I 99); ~ of comfort (*mūrtam āśvāsam*) 9,64 (TP I 99); ~ of Kāma (*Kāmadevāvatāra*) 11,78 (TP I 128); ~ of Rati 34,99 (TP III 135) and 110,70 (TP VIII 87); ~ of Buddha (*Sugatāṃśa*) 72,234 (TP VI 85); – see also: Buddha; part-incarnation; visibility

incest (involuntary) of father and daughter 98,51f. (TP VII 119)⁷⁸²

incineration of hen-crow (*bhasmasād abhūt*) by hermit 56,172 (TP IV 232); Nāga incinerates (*bhasmī-cakāra*) wife and traveller 64,158 (TP V 151)

incognito,⁷⁸³ king leaves realm to minister and sets out alone ~ (*guptam*) for maiden 86,67 (TP VII 18); 124,57 (TP IX 72)⁷⁸⁴; – see also: night

incommensality, of brahmin gambler refusing food offered by Pāśupata ascetic 92,34 (TP VII 73); ~ of brahmins refusing food of *cāṇḍāla* 112,180 (TP VIII 120)

inconsistency:⁷⁸⁵ Mṛgāṅkavatī 10,171 calls Śrīdatta her husband (*bhartṛ*) and then she is stated as beloved (*priyā*) whom he marries 180 (TP I 118); 16,42 *tasthau*: does not fit in the story of Kuntū who put the hot food for Durvāsas on her back (in itself a difficult act); *vidyādharas* may not enter land of Siddhas 18,235 (TP II 67), but 18,358 the *vidyādharī* Bhadrā sits on the mountain of the rising sun in the Siddha-dhāman (18,351; TP II 75f.); no female snake kills its partner 34,181 (TP III 141); ichor is not on elephant's trunk (*kara*) 35,2 (TP III 155); when mortals would get *amṛta* there would be no difference between men and gods 41,18 (TP III 253; see: sacrifice); hermit Vālmiki, who knows all by meditation (*praṇidhāna* 51,75), does not know that Sītā took her child with her to bathe and fears it to be carried off by a *śvāpada* 51,87ff. (TP IV 128); disguised king addressed as “*deva*” 58,20 (TP V 16); 67,111 (TP V 204 with note 2); *vīrya* of a *bhṛṅgī* fecundates a (neutre !) *puṣpa* 69,96ff. (TP VI 15); rāja-ḥaṃsas do not nest in a tree 69,129 (TP VI 18); corners of a circle 73,305 (TP VI 123); a man fastens his head with his hear to the bell chain of a temple, cuts off his head which then falls on the ground (*śiraḥ ... chinnaṃ cāpatad bhuvi*; instead of his body) 80,31 (TP VI 206; ORC 929 wrongly but logically translates: “*la tête tranchée, le corps tomba à terre*”; M II 223 correctly but illogically renders: “*(er) band seinen Kopf mit den Haupthaaren am Glockenstrick fest und hieb ihn sich mit jenem Schwert ab. Und das abgetrennte Haupt fiel zur Erde nieder.*”); 81,45 mentions a temple of Kātyāyanī-Durgā which becomes a temple of Pārvatī in 81,75 (TP VI 214); propitiating Śiva for son though karman in pre-birth decides everything 83,8 (TP VII 2); *brahma-rākṣasa* cannot be *daivata* ‘protecting deity’ (ORC 1013: “*divinité gardienne*”) of brahmin boy 94,133 (TP VII 96); brahmin addressed as *bhartr-dāraka* ‘prince’ 104,42 (TP VIII 4); brahmin obtains princes as *dakṣiṇā* for what ? 113,80 (TP VIII 130); fruit given by Śiva in dream to queen and shown next day by harem servant to king 120,42 (TP IX 4); – also

⁷⁸² Rājat VII 278 mentions actual incest of an unscrupulous and fearless guru with his daughter.

⁷⁸³ Gupta 1972: 219.

⁷⁸⁴ See Bollée 2002: 195.

⁷⁸⁵ STh W 186.

see destiny; *karman*; suicide I

incubation, see: dream; Durgā temple; temple of Mahākāla

independence (*sva-tantratā*) reached by *yoga* 45,112 (TP IV 25; ORC 473 ‘*liberté*’)

indīvara ‘blue lotus’, see: eyes

Indra⁷⁸⁶ as hawk persuading Dharma as dove 7,89 (TP I 84); ~ telling story 9,22 (TP I 96f.); ~ predicts birth of daughter in dream 11,76 (TP I 128); ~ as a cat 17,141 (pun on Pkt *majjāo*; TP II 46); ~ oppressed by *Asura Tāraka*⁷⁸⁷ desires son from Śiva to act as general of th gods 20,60 (TP II 100); ~ hits Kārttikeya with *vajra* 20,92 (TP II 102); ~ worships Gaṇeśa 20,98 (TP II 103); ~ curses *apsaras* to become mortal 27,70 (TP III 6); ~ disguised as brahmin 40,20 (TP III 241); ~ as diseased jackal 40,28 (TP III 242); ~ sends Aśvins to Nāgārjuna to stop preparation of *amṛta* 41,17 (TP III 253); message of ~ through Nārada 45,13 (TP IV 18); idem 45,165 (TP IV 28); ~ is given his *Indratva* by Paramêśvara (Śiva) 45,390 (TP IV 43); ~ afraid of being cursed by wives of Maya 45,394 (TP IV 43f.); ~ appeases Kaśyapa 45,395 (TP IV 44); ~ ashamed and fearful 45,401 (TP IV 44); ~ prostrates him self before hermit Kaśyapa 45,413 (TP IV 45); ~ curses brahmin for not rising at his entering 49,192 (TP IV 98); ~ sends treasure 56,166 (TP IV 231); pleased by austerities ~ gives boon to prince 72,225 (TP VI 85); ~ tempts prince by inviting him to paradise 72,228 (TP VI 85); ~ burns down forest by *māyā* and restores it to previous desert (*marū-kṛtam prāg-vattam*) 72,372 (TP VI 96); ~ appears in person, stops suicide of pupil and sprinkles ashes of guru, etc. with *amṛta* 72,390f. (TP VI 98); ~’s throne rocks 113,73 (TP VIII 129); ~ as brahmin asks prince for his wife to prove him 113,74 (TP VIII 129); ~ shows himself in his proper shape (*nija-rūpa-stho bhūtvā*) 113,78 (TP VIII 129); Asura gets boon from Śambhu of slaying ~ in fight 115,49 (TP VIII 147); ~ falls senseless from Airāvaṇa on chariot of Vāyu 115,67 (TP VIII 149); ~ flees with the *devas* to Brahmā’s place (*Brahma-bhavana*) 115,74 (TP VIII 149); ~ announces two sons to sonless king 118,21 and gives him two air-going elephants 118,26 (TP VIII 179)

Indra-jāla ‘enchantment’ 73,367 (TP VI 127)⁷⁸⁸;

Indra-jālin ‘sorcerer’, brahmin able to reanimate dead beings called ~ 83,37 (TP VII 4)

Indra-loka, see: *indu-loka*

indriyāśva (not MW) ‘horse of the senses’, a king should first tame the ~s 24,191 (TP III 142)

Indrōtsava given for birth of princes 11,75 (TP I 128)

indu-loka, Gandharva princess Padmāvatī leaves ‘the world of the moon’ for a temple of Gaurī 116,16 (TP VIII 157⁷⁸⁹; ORC 1213: “*le monde de la lune*”)

⁷⁸⁶ Cf. ORC 1580.

⁷⁸⁷ On Tāraka bei Kālidāsa see Jackmuth 2002: 32; 67f.; 72f.; 139ff.

⁷⁸⁸ The oldest reference to Indra’s net is AV VIII 8,7f. where a sorcerer encircles therewith his enemies with darkness. No description of the net is given. See further Goudriaan 1978: 211ff.

⁷⁸⁹ Thus BD; TP read *Indra-loka*- “the world of Indra”, but see *bhavana ... aindava*, the *janma-bhūmi* of Padmāvatī 117,17 (TP VIII 165).

- inexhaustible pitcher, see: pitcher
- infancy is a sea full of passion for amusement (*kriḍā-rasa*) 28,99 (TP III 27);
- infant prodigy, of five years old son 14,45 (TP I 185); ~ of seven years old willing to sacrifice himself 94,96ff. (TP VII 94); ~ of twelve year old son of Mūladeva 124,203ff. and 210f. (TP IX 83)
- infanticide, see : cannibalism; child; sacrifice
- infidelity, by ~ *vidyādhari* wife loses her magic knowledge (*bhraṣṭa-vidyā*) 52,209 (TP IV 152); 58,65 (TP V 19); ~ of carpenter's wife natural to women (*cāpalaṃ strīṇāṃ saha-jam*) 62,112 (TP V 108)⁷⁹⁰; 64,100 and 104 (TP V 147)
- influence obtained by giving present (*prābhṛta*) 66,114 (TP V 187); – see also: gift; present
- inheritance of vessel, shoes and stick 3,47 (TP I 22)⁷⁹¹
- initiation of boy into *agni-kriyā* (q.v.)
- injuries, unintentional, motif see: garlands (22,138f. [TP II 147])
- innocent man with stolen necklace motif⁷⁹² 10,168 (TP I 117); 54,116ff. (TP IV 192); ~ wife and daughter share Śiva's curse of husband and father 112,193 (TP VIII 121);
- insignia,⁷⁹³ five (not in KSS [TP V 175f.]) or seven (109,23 [TP VIII 71]) ~ (*kakudāni*) of royalty; ~ of rank 24,17 (TP II 171); – see also: *lilā-vajra*
- instability (*a-nityatā*) only stable thing in this world as delusion of Creator (*aiśvaryī māyā*) 5,103 (TP I 55)
- insult (*paribhava*), spitting betel-juice on someone's head is an ~ 70,5f. (TP VI 23)
- intercourse, see: sex
- intronisation (*siṃhāsanāroha*)⁷⁹⁴ by sprinkling water (*abhiṣeka*) 113,88 (TP VIII 130); – see also: coronation; inauguration
- intoxication (*mada-spr̥ś* [not MW]), due to signs of ~ queens show contracted eyebrows and fiery eyes (*sa-bhrū-bhaṅgāruṇēkṣaṇāḥ*) 110,130 (TP VIII 91); – see also: wine
- intrigue, harem ~ of king with attendant (*antaḥpura-cārikā*) 14,66 (TP I 187); 32,123 (TP III 99); 39,24ff. (TP III 219ff.)
- inundation (*mahā-vāri-pūra*) by overflowing river Vipāsā due to monsoon (*prāvṛṣ*) and influx of sea-water (*sāgarāugha*) 74,190f. (TP VI 154)
- invective, see: abuse; *jālma*; *paśu*
- invisibility⁷⁹⁵ by magic (*a-darśanaṃ yukti-balāt*) 12,59 (TP I 137); idem by spell 18,227 (TP II 67); *asurī* travelling invisible (*guhya-cāriṇī*) 31,57 (TP III 87); ointment for discovering invisible *vidyādharas* 48,86 (TP IV 80); ointment (*añjana*) on eyes makes invisible 49,74

⁷⁹⁰ *Così fan tutte*.

⁷⁹¹ Cf. STh D 816.

⁷⁹² See Penzer's note in TP IV 192; STh N 347.

⁷⁹³ Upadhyaya 1947: 77f.; Gonda 1969: 37f.

⁷⁹⁴ Saletore 1943: 171ff., Heesterman 1957.

⁷⁹⁵ Cf. Daś 70,5. For invisibility by smearing collyrium round the eyes see Kuv notes 1770 and 2190; STh *D 1361ff.

and 81 (TP IV 90); 55,147 (TP IV 212); attaining ~ by spell (*vidyā*) of *pratiloma* and *anuloma* 74,133 (TP VI 149); princess alarmed makes herself invisible (*udbhrāntā tiro-bhūya*) 119,111 (TP VIII 201); – see also: aunt; Caṇḍī; Daitya-*kanyā*

invulnerability, son with ~ 115,4 (TP VIII 144); hermit gives king boon of ~ 118,65 (TP VIII 182); – see also: Achilles' heel

iron,⁷⁹⁶ dog's foot (*śunaḥ pādama ayomayam*) branded on forehead of adulterous man 13,142 (TP I 160); balance made of a thousand *palas* of ~ (*ayaḥ-pala-sahasreṇa ghaṭitām tulām*) eaten by mice (*ākhubhir bhakṣita*) 60,238f. (TP V 62)⁷⁹⁷; two ~ (*lohamayāṅga*) rams (*meṣa*), guard gate in Pātāla 73,131 (TP VI 110)

irreligion (*a-dharma*), see: Buddhism

*iṣṭa-devatā*⁷⁹⁸ 'personal deity' worshipped before sea voyage (*arcitābhīṣṭa-devatā*) 81,33 (TP VI 211);

iṣṭa-sampādini vidyā 'science producing whatever one desires' 92,35 (TP VII 73);

iṣṭi 'oblation' made for son as sperma substitute eaten by queens 74,44f. (TP VI 143)

iśvaras like mountains are very rough, firm, uneven, difficult of access 60,38 (TP V 44)

īti-ghna 'averting calamity' 72,61 (TP VI 73 with note 1⁷⁹⁹);

iva for *eva*, reading ~ 16,86 (TP II 28 note 1. BD have *iva*);

ivory carver's (*danta-ghāṭaka*) daughter 75,83 (TP VI 170);

ivory leaf, see: *danta-patra*

ivory throne (*danti-dantāsana*) 102,117 (TP VII 117);

jackal(s) (*śivāḥ*), eating corpse of elephant 12,108 (TP I 141); howling female ~ as harbinger of death (*kṛtānta-dūti*) 29,106 (TP III 46); Indra as diseased ~ (*jambuka*) 40,28 (TP III 242); sheep fleeing from ~ 52,42 (TP IV 141); two ~s as lion's ministers 60,19 (TP V 43); ~ called wise (*prājña*) 60,24 (TP V 43); ~ and drum story to show that one should not be afraid of a mere noise 60,58 (TP V 45f.); greedy ~ killed by self-acting bow 61,104 (TP V 77); ~, lion and ass 63,125ff. (TP V 130); hermit turns female ~ into she-elephant 68,19 (TP VI 2); ~ apes lion 74,270 (TP VI 159); she-~ utters yell (*cakre śabdam*) 121,160 (TP IX 23); 116,3 (TP VIII 156); ~ howling on left hand of traveller is a bad omen 124,108 (TP IX 76);

jāḍya 'coldness', see: pearls

jagad-rakṣamāṇa (not MW) 'protector of the world', said of Vikramāditya 121,19 (TP IX 13)

jagad-yantra (not MW) 'world as machine' 29,43 (TP III 42)

jagan-netra 'eye of the world', moon as ~ 89,5 (TP VII 40)

jagat-kṣobha (not MW) 'upsetting the world system' 115,20 (TP VIII 145)

⁷⁹⁶ Probably because of its black colour, iron has some ominous connotations (Hanchett 1988: 289). Seeligmann 1927: 162.

⁷⁹⁷ Cf. STh J 1531.2.

⁷⁹⁸ Also, e.g. Kuv 43.29 et passim.

⁷⁹⁹ The note states the six calamities to be: excessive rain, drought, rats, locusts, birds and foreign invasion.

- jagat-sthiti* (not MW) ‘constitution of the universe’ is broken up when due to the preparation of *amṛta* there will be neither sacrificer nor receiver of sacrifice 41,18 (TP III 253)⁸⁰⁰
- jagat-tritaya-sundarī*, see: miss universe
- jaghanâbhoga* (not MW) ‘broad hips’ of princesses looking like head of elephant of love 118,164 (TP VIII 189), cf. next and *kandarpa-mātaṅga*
- jaghana-sthala* (not MW) ‘hinder part, buttocks’ 91,31 (TP VII 68 lacuna: ORC 990: “hanches”)
- jahi jahi !* cry (*kalakala*) of armed maidens of man-hating princess 122,38 (TP IX 36); – see also: amazon
- Jāhnavī = Ganges 74,130 (TP VI 149), called after *ṛṣi* Jahnu who, enraged at the haughty Gaṅgā flooding his hermitage, drank her up, but at the request of king Bhagīratha let her out through his ear⁸⁰¹
- Jain monk (*kṣapaṇaka*), Digambara ~ 39,59 (TP III 222 wrongly: ‘Buddhist monk’);
- jala-dāna*, see: *udaka-dāna*
- jāla-kārālaya* (not MW), see: cobweb
- jala-kriḍā*, see: water-game
- jāla-gavākṣa* ‘lattice-window’ of a palace 70,88 (TP VI 30)⁸⁰²
- jala-mānuṣa* (water-spirit), three ~ seize Bhillā king 71,5 (TP VI 36);
- jala-puruṣa* ‘water-spirit’,⁸⁰³ rebirth as ~ due to broken fast (*upoṣaṇa*) 63,60 (TP V 124)
- jālma* ‘fool’ 68,44 (TP VI 5)
- jambu-tree* (Jambolan or black plum tree)⁸⁰⁴, female bee covers flower of ~ with *harṣa-cyūtena vīryeṇa* ‘sperma of joy’ 69,97 (TP VI 15: “tear of joy”; vide infra s. v. *vīrya*); heavenly maiden emerges from *jambu* fruit 69,102 (TP VI 16); its fruits in Pātāla petrify eater and are not to be consumed 73,126f. (TP VI 110); – see also: fruit(s)
- janântikaṃ* (‘in private’) 72,349 (TP VI 95; ORC 848: “à voix basse”); 75,103 (TP VI 171; ORC 903: “en aparté”), cf. *guptaṃ*
- jana-vāda*,⁸⁰⁵ see: rumour
- janma-bhūmi* ‘native country’, the love of dwelling in one’s ~ draws every man 110,139 (TP VIII 92), cf. *heimatliebe*

⁸⁰⁰ This is not true because also deities sacrifice (ŚpBr 5,1,1,2), as “Hindu gods are parodies of men” (Doniger O’Flaherty 1980a: 73) or “Indian gods and goddesses are idealised men and women” (Ambrose 1950: 17), the sense of sacrificing being to enable the receiver to give or do something for the sacrificer: *do ut dare possis*. For Haberman 2013: 184 it is still *do ut des* when he writes: “Ritual gift giving is frequently a process of mutual exchange: something is given with the hope of a reciprocal return.” What a sacrifice is on the religious level kind of resembles ordinary bribing on the mundane and therefore may be so prevalent.

⁸⁰¹ Vettam Mani 1975: 277b (with sources) and 337a.

⁸⁰² Coomaraswamy 1931: 196f.

⁸⁰³ Called *guhya* in 63,77 (TP V 125).

⁸⁰⁴ *Syzygium cumini* (Macmillan 1991: 309 the fruits are about one inch long and slightly sour; Wujastyk 2003-4). Cf. Careri in Sen 1949: 203f. The juice of the fruit has a bluish-red (*nila-pātāla*) colour (Kād 37,11).

⁸⁰⁵ See Hara 1968: 262f.; Bollée 2005: 195.

janma-duḥkha, see: labour

janmani janmani ‘in birth after birth’ 94,121 (TP VII 95); – see: stylistic repetition

janmarkṣa ‘asterism of birth’, astrologers want to know ~ of princess in order to fix date of marriage 32,14 (TP III 91)

janma-taru ‘birth as a tree’ 119,207 (TP VIII 208); – see also: curse 70,32f. (TP VI 26);
Dānava maidens; disguise; Gaṇeśa; tree

japa ‘muttering’, of brahman for two hundred *kalpas* (*divyaṃ varṣa-śata-dvayam*) 45,83 (TP IV 23 “two myriads of years”); – see also: muttering prayers

jāpaka, see: prayer

jar, womb as ~ 70,112 (TP VI 32)⁸⁰⁶; – see also: pitcher(s)

jarā-roga, see: old age

jātaka, see: nativity

jaṭharāgni ‘stomach-fire, digestive fire, burning hunger’ 73,58 (TP VI 105; ORC 855 “*feu de la faim dans son estomac*”)⁸⁰⁷; – see: hunger

jāti-smara ‘remembering pre-births’, of flying white elephant 36,14 (TP III 170); reincarnated part-Bodhisattva with ~ 90,8 (TP VII 49); – see also: pre-birth

jāti-vigraha (not MW) ‘quarrelling with one’s relatives’ 27,22 (TP II 3)

jātu-cit ‘perhaps’ 119,123 (TP VIII 202)

jaws of *yakṣī*, see: mouth

jaya-kuñjara ‘victorious elephant’ (MW) 34,125 (TP III 137)

jaya-stambha (‘pillar of victory’) looking like a *nāga-rāja* 19,91 (TP II 92); – cf. *kīrti-stambha*

jealousy⁸⁰⁸ (*īrṣyā*) makes king condemn brahmin to death 5,15 (TP I 46); ~ of rich neighbours 10,10 (TP I 106); jealous couple receives red lotus (*raktam ambujam*) from Śiva 13,81 (TP I 156); ~ must be avoided (*strī-vairam rakṣaṇīyam*) as seed of calamities 15,134 (TP II 13); ~ of nymph leads to affection for human 17,126 (TP II 44); other queens abandon ~ 18,405 (TP II 80); ~ makes king slash hermit 28,31 (TP III 22); ~ of first queen of new one 32,122 (TP III 99) and 55,120ff. (TP IV 210); ~ excites excessive longing in women 36,134 (TP III 178); other queens’ ~ (*matsara*) of main queen 39,23 (TP III 219); ~ among women 42,65 (TP III 263), 42,161 (TP III 270) and 42,202 (TP III 274)⁸⁰⁹; ~ of wife because husband only loves cares of his duties 45,184 (TP IV 30); 45,265 (TP IV 35); mother advises daughter not to annoy husband by ~ 52,27 (TP IV 140); pilgrimage to wash out ~ 52,239 (TP IV 154); out of ~ Kali, a black man, enters Nala’s body so that he lost his dice play 56,384 (TP IV 248); wife of jealous husband elopes with Bhilla 61,146 (TP V 81); ~ of husband teaches wife to run after other men 61,168 (TP V 82); 63,164 (TP V 133); out of ~ man locks up his wife in a cellar (*bhū-grhe*) 64,129 (TP V 149); ~ (*vaira*)

⁸⁰⁶ Cf. STh T 561.

⁸⁰⁷ See, e. g., Doniger O’Flaherty 1980a: 240.

⁸⁰⁸ Cf. ORC 1581; Kuv 46.1ff.; 125.12-25.

⁸⁰⁹ See Meyer 1952: 222 note 1; Syed 2001: 181.

between two princes 74,50 (TP VI 144); ~ between Lakṣmī and Sarasvatī laid aside in the town of Viśālā 104,23 (TP VIII 2f.); – see also: envy; five fires; foot; king; misfortune; rivalry

jewel(s), offered to sea⁸¹⁰ to prevent shipwreck 18,295 (TP II 72) and 101,183f. (TP VII 147); prince finds ear ornament of his adulterous merchant wife 21,82-4 (TP II 131); ornaments made of false ~s (*kṛtrima-māṅikya*) 24,133 (TP II 179) and 186 (TP II 182); *bhikṣu* daily gives king box with ~ (*ratna*) 38,50 (TP III 209f.) and 75,23ff. (TP VI 165f.); all ~s stem from the Daitya Prabala's body 45,380 (TP IV 42); king gives dependent (*kārpaṭika*) citron with ~ (*ratnair bhṛtaṃ mātuliṅgam*) 53,27 (TP IV 169); magic ~ neutralizes enemy's arms 71,135 (TP VI 45); brahmin hands casket (*bhāṇḍa*) with ~ to princely refugee 74,92 (TP VI 146); ~s of *vidyādhara* emperor 108,138 (TP VIII 64); imperial seven ~s obtained by Naravāhanadatta in hermit Vāmadeva's cave 109,23 (TP VIII 71); ~s do come when thought of (*dhyātōpanata*) 109,84 (TP VIII 76); ~ that confer the power of becoming a *vidyādhara* 119,21 (TP VIII 194); – see also: crest-jewel; elephant; gender-neutral jewelry; necklace; ornament; reward

jewel-lamp (*ratna-dīpa*) shedding a blaze (*tejas*) to protect a baby 23,62 (TP II 161);

jhaḡ 'cry of grief' 66,22 (TP V 179)

jhaṭ ity 'instantly, all at once' 89,67 (TP VII 44)

*jhaṣa*⁸¹¹ killing crane 60,86 (TP V 48);

jihvā-jāla 'web of tongue', rogues spread ~ with hundreds of intricate threads 24,200 (TP II 184; ORC 216: "[*Les gredins sont des pêcheurs qui exercent leur activité sur la terre ferme: leur langue est le filet, [tissé de cent discours dont ils tirent leur substance]*")

Jina among three happy beings, with Sarasvatī and Skanda 51,205 (TP IV 136 with Buddha for Jina; cf. ORC 1421 note 1 on p. 557)

Jina-pūjā-parāyaṇa 'Buddhist devotee' 72,99 (TP VI 76);

jīva ! 'bless you !' (lit.: 'live !' said after someone's sneezing) 28,130 (TP III 30); fool welcomes two evil omens with ~ 124,109 (TP IX 76)

(*jīvan-mukti*, see: emancipation)

jīvita-saṃśaya 'danger of life' 73,362 (TP VI 126);

jñāni-liṅgin [not MW] 'with the appearance of a fortune-teller', a spy 19,83 (TP II 91)

Jonah motif of shipwrecked man swallowed by big fish 25,47 (TP II 192)⁸¹²; brahmin swallowed by large fish in Ganges 74,199 (TP VI 154); fish (*śaphara*) swallows ship with people 123,110 (TP IX 51); large fish swallows woman 123,231 and 238 (TP IX 59f.); journey, gone on the long ~ (*yāto mahā-patham*) = died, out of grief 2,43 (TP I 12); old king and company leave for the great ~ (*mahā-prasthāna*) to the Himālaya 10,217 (TP I 121); rites for auspicious ~ performed by mother 42,83 (TP III 265) and 101,137 (TP VII 143); idem by mother-in-law 43,235 (TP III 297); – see also: mourning tour;

⁸¹⁰ STh V 12.2.

⁸¹¹ Here apparently the same as *makara* in vs 85 and 88f., perhaps m. c.

⁸¹² STh F 911.4.

joy⁸¹³, tears of ~ (*ānanda-bāṣpa*) 10,206 (TP I 120); do, 18,369 (TP II 77); do, 29,3 (TP III 39); do, 69,96 (TP VI 15); ~ of battle 27,139 (TP III 11); delight at the sight of magic dolls takes away appetite of princess 29,23 (TP III 40); hero enters king's palace like ~ incarnate (*pramodo mūrtimān*) 25,221 (TP II 207); a small fortune with enjoyment is better than a great one without ~ 54,210 (TP IV 198); having embraced his friend Śaṅkhadatta went from ~ to ~ (*utsavād utsavam*) 74,197 (TP VI 154); excessive ~ causes death 95,74 (TP VII 103)⁸¹⁴; princess has horripilation from ~ at seeing prince 103,63 (TP VII 179) and 107,48 (TP VIII 46); earth shows ~ at spring by sweating dewy drops 111,4 (TP VIII 94)

judge, inconsiderate ~ executed 72,215 (TP VI 84)

judgement silly 72,212 (TP VI 84 with note 1); see also *dharmāsana*

juggler, woman compared to bunch of peacock feathers of Kāma as ~ (*aindra-jālika*)⁸¹⁵ 30,3 (TP III 64); show of ~ (*Indra-jālōpamāna*), this versatile world is like the show ... 111,87 (TP VIII 103)

jungle, law of, see: ichthyomy

jvālā-liṅga (Śiva's flame emblem)⁸¹⁶ 1,28 (TP I 4)

jvara-ceṭaka (not MW) ('imp / attendant of fever demon') who can remove fever (*jvara-ghna*) 71, 207 (TP VI 50);

jyeṣṭha-tarikā, see: chaperon

jyotī-rasa, kind of gem slab on which Gaṇeśa sits 50,176 (TP IV 119); – see also: Gaṇeśa; slab

kv 121,233 (TP IX 29 with note 2)

Kabandha 102,49 (TP VII 166)⁸¹⁷

kabari-bhāra 'fine head of hair', queen with ~ 55,200 (TP IV 216)

kadalī plant produces daughter from hermit's seed (*vīrya*) fallen on it 32,101 (TP III 97)

Kailāsa⁸¹⁸ boasting of its whiteness 1,16 (TP I 3) and 50,172 (TP IV 118)⁸¹⁹; ~ has eight doors 50,187 (TP IV 119); ~ is Śiva's home 63,54 (TP V 124) and 109,45 (TP VIII 73); ~ as home of *yakṣas* 73,437 (TP VI 131); ~ white like crystal 109,42 (TP VIII 73); formerly the north and south sides of ~ formed different kingdoms 109,61 (TP VIII 74)⁸²⁰; Śiva cleaves ~ and makes cavelike opening in the south to pass to the north 109,66 (TP VIII 75); ~ beautiful with smile of northern quarter 120,16 (TP IX 2)

⁸¹³ See ORC 1565 s.v. Emotions.

⁸¹⁴ STh F 1941.10. – Cfg. German *sich totlachen* 'to kill oneself laughing'.

⁸¹⁵ Cf. Daś 56.3.

⁸¹⁶ In MW name of a sanctuary.

⁸¹⁷ Zin 2003b: 184 note 5.

⁸¹⁸ See Snelling 2006.

⁸¹⁹ Cf. Bāṇa, *Kādambarī* I 16 (Kailāsa is white like crystal, *sphaṭikōpalopana*), and Kale's note 1968: [10].

⁸²⁰ Zin 2003b: 164.

- kaitava-tapas* (not MW) ‘hypocritical asceticism’ 121,157 (TP IX 23; ORC 1273: “*pseudo-ascèse*”)
- kaitava-yukti* (not MW) ‘gambling rules’ 121,96 (TP IX 19)
- kajjala*, see: lamp-black
- kāka-śaṅkin*, see crow
- kāka-vāśita* (not MW) ‘cry of a crow’ 121,169 (TP IX 24)
- kakṣa*, ifc. *ābaddha*-^o
- kakṣyā* ‘zone of a palace’ 38,27 (TP III 208)
- Kāla ‘Death’ and hermit Śveta 72,334 (TP VI 94); ~ throws noose over neck (*gala-kṣipta-pāśaḥ*) of robber Siṃhavikrama when seduced by *divyā stri* 72,348 (TP VI 94)⁸²¹
- kalā*, see: tide
- kālāguru* black Aloeswood⁸²² as perfume for princess’ chamber 74,232 (TP VI 157); ~ in royal chambers 122,19 (TP IX 35)
- kalaha*, see: disputatiousness
- kala-haṃsa* ‘Grey Lag, a kind of goose’,⁸²³ Śiva as ~ in lake Mānasa 35,100 (TP III 163); autumn (*śarat*) vocal with cries of ~ 122,72 (TP IX 72)
- kalakala*, see: noise
- kāla-kambala* ‘black rug’ of a herdsman 64,118 (TP V 148)
- kālakūṭa* poison twin-born with nectar (*sudhā*) 36,95 (TP III 176)
- kāla-megha* ‘black cloud’ (MW) 52,323 (TP IV 160 ‘cloud of doom’)
- Kālāpaka grammar 7,13 (TP I 75)
- Kālārātri, ugly brahmin witch, teaches queen spell of flying 20,106 (TP II 103); ~ enters cowshed with knife drawn (*ākṣṣa-vira-cchurikā*) 20,137 (TP II 106); king bans ~ from entering his kingdom 20,185 (TP II 111); ~ (‘night of destruction’) 74,286 (TP VI 161); ~ created by Viṣṇu to defend *amṛta* against Dānavas is now placed by Śarva-Śiva near the tunnel through Mt Kailāsa to guard it 109,89f. (TP VIII 76)
- kāla-vid* ‘knowing the times’ 50,60 (TP IV 112 ‘possessing tact’; ORC 536 ‘*avec son habituel sens des situations*’)
- Kalaśa, son of ²Ananta, king of Kashmir,⁸²⁴ *tilaka* on the circle of the earth and *an-alika-lagna* E 9 (TP IX 89 with note 1)
- kāla-saṃkarṣiṇī vidyā* ‘life-prolonging science’ appears visibly (*sākṣāt*) and gives brahmin magic sword 68,65 (TP VI 6)
- Kalāvati cursed by Indra, see: curse
- Kali⁸²⁵ enters Nala’s body 56,288 (TP IV 241); ~ issues from Nala’s body as black man

⁸²¹ Some scholars think throttling with a strap was introduced under Western influence (Halbfass 1992: 105 with note 86).

⁸²² McHugh 2012: 169ff.

⁸²³ Thus Dave 2005: 426, translated as *cygne* in ORC 358.

⁸²⁴ Rājat VII 231. Kalaśa reigned from 1063-1089.

56,383 (TP IV 248);

kalpa-kṣaya, see: doomsday

kalpântānala ‘fire of doomsday’ 118,76 (TP VIII 183)

kalpa-taru; *-druma*; *-vrkṣa*, see wishing-tree

kalyāṇi as address of unknown *vidyādhari* by prince 59,8 (TP V 26)

Kāma,⁸²⁶ Manobhū surrounds Śambhu-Śiva’s neck with nooses in the form of Pārvatī’s looks 1,1 (TP I 1); woman is a world-bewildering drug (*jagat-saṃmohanāuśadhi*) of ~ 15,74 (TP II 8); son as portion of ~ 15,130 (TP II 13; cf. 44,9 [TP IV 1]); Urvaśī as weapon (*mohanāstra*) of ~ 17,5 (TP II 34 with note 2); jewelled temple of ~ 18,77 (TP II 55); ~ burnt by Śiva’s anger (*Hara-kopāgni-nirdagdha-smara*) 18,213 (TP II 66)⁸²⁷; ~ born without body in mortals 20,67 (TP II 101); glory to ~ due to whose arrows even the body of Śiva seems to bristle with dense thorns, when embraced by Umā 27,2 (TP III 1); Suṣeṇa created like another ~ to spite Śiva 28,51 (TP III 24); ~ is a juggler (*Indra-jālika*) with a bunch of peacock feathers 30,3 (TP III 64); ~ to be reborn as mortal Naravāhanadatta because of disrespect to Śiva 34,41 (TP III 130), cf. 54,45 (TP IV 187); ~ born as goose 43,195 (TP III 294); king Vatsa born of a part of ~ 44,9 (TP IV 1); ~ made by Śarva-Śiva as born in the mind (*saṃkalpa-janmā*)⁸²⁸ 49,238 (TP IV 101); king of Vatsa created by Śiva as incarnation of ~ 54,45 (TP IV 187); rows of bees as string for ~’s bow 55,109 (TP IV 209); Nala surpassing ~ in beauty who offers his body as burnt-offering in the fire of Śiva’s eye 56,238 (TP IV 237); speaking gander as ambassador of ~ 56,245 (TP IV 237); *Vidyādhara* princess like presiding deity of lake in Kāma’s garden (*Smarōdyāna-vāpī-śobhādhidevatā*) 59,5 (TP V 26); “*Kāma-devo ’ham*” says leper 64,132 (TP V 149); temple (*mandira*) of ~ in Vaiśākha city 67,16 (TP V 197); bow of ~ 72,76 (TP VI 74); merchant’s daughter able to fascinate even ~ (Madana) 91,9 (TP VII 66); mango-cluster with bees compared to bow of ~ 104,6 (TP VIII 1); ~ in temple of the Mātaraś 104,128 (TP VIII 11); ~ *makara-ketu* as destroyer of women (*stri-ghna*)⁸²⁹ 117,65 (TP VIII 168); – see also: aqueous weapon; bow; sweat

kāma-caratva, see: will

kāma-cārin ‘roaming about at will’, said of Kubera Dhanādhipati 38,69 (TP III 211; cf. *kāma-cara* 38,93 said of deities in general);

Kāma-devo ’ham says a leper beloved by a beautiful woman 64,132 (TP V 149); temple (*mandira*) of Kāmadeva in city of Vaiśākha 67,16 (TP V 197)

kāma-dhenu ‘wishing-cow’ 17,135 (TP II 45); ~ produces Sumeru’s food 50,148 (TP IV

⁸²⁵ Gonda 1965: 339.

⁸²⁶ See ORC 1533 s.v. Amour; STh A 475.

⁸²⁷ Jackmuth 2002: 38 discussing Kumārasambhava 3,72, and p. 64f. dealing with Kum. 4.40 and 3,64.

⁸²⁸ ORC 532 “*être d’imagination*”; ‘born from desire’ (MW).

⁸²⁹ At 67,14 (TP V 197) regarding a king women say: “can it be an arrow of desire made by the Creator, in the form of a man, for the sudden complete overthrow of the female heart ?”

117); subjects as king's ~ 72,220 (TP VI 85); – see also: (wishing-) cow
kāma-kalpa-druma ‘wishing tree of love’ 72,27 (TP VI 70)
 Kamalā = Lakṣmī
 Kamalapura, thus read at TP IV 220 for *devakamalapura* (56,4); the town is unidentified
kamalinī ‘lotus’, sun as friend of ~ 121,245 (TP IX 30)
kamaṇḍalu ‘waterpot’ of Gaurī with *amṛta* to resuscitate beings 90,185 (TP VII 62); ~ of
 Creator, *śikhā-ratna* (‘crest-jewel’) sprung from ~, effective magic protection (*mahā-
 prabhāva*) for princess 117,156 (TP VIII 175);
kāma-rūpiṇī ‘changing shape at will’ said of *rākṣasī* 25,196 (TP II 207)
kambu-kaṇṭhī, see: neck
kāminī ‘wife’, one of the seven imperial jewels of the *vidyādharas* 109,22 (TP VIII 71)
kāṃsya-pātrī ‘brass pot’, woman puts barley-meal in ~ 71,268 (TP VI 55)
 Kanakapurī, see: Golden City
 Kāñcanapāta, at the point where the Ganges issues from the hills, where the sacred stream was
 brought down from the table-land of Mt U. by ~, the elephant of the gods, having cleft it [the
 mountain, that is] asunder (*yatra ~ena Jāhnavī deva-dantinā U.-giri-prasthād bhittvā
 samavatāritā*) 3,5 (TP I 18 with note 3⁸³⁰; ORC 13: “à la Porte du Gange, là où l’éléphant
 divin K. fit descendre la rivière du plateau qui couronne le mont U. qu’il avait fendu”)
 Kāñcī, city of ~ with excellences adorns the earth-bride like a girdle 43,20 (TP III 282);
 44,105 (TP IV 8);
kāñcī-nakṣatra-mālāṅka (not MW) ‘with a string of (28) pearls like the (28) constellations’
 91,31 (TP VII 68 lacuna; ORC 990 with note 1473: “(hanches) qu’orne une ceinture à
 vingt-sept (ou vingt-huit) perles”)
kañcuka ‘bodice, bra’ bursting as sign of erotic excitement 74,238 (TP VI 157); bride with
 white ~ (*dhavala-kañcukā*) 104,165 (TP VIII 13); – see also: bra
Kandarpa as beauty model 71,68 (TP VI 40, also with the Jains in Hemacandra, *Triṣaṣṭi* VI
 2,116)
kandarpa-mātaṅga (not MW) ‘elephantlike, i.e. strong, love’ 91,31 (TP VII 68 lacuna; ORC
 990: “éléphant Amour”)
Kandarpa-moha, see: bewilderment
*kanduka-kriḍā*⁸³¹ (not MW), see: game of ball
kañkāla-kiṃnarī [not MW] played by *yakṣiṇī* 37,64 (TP III 187 ‘lute of bones’; ORC 374:
 “instrument fait d’ ossements”)⁸³²
kaṇṭha-graha ‘embracing’ see: gestures
*kaṇṭhāśleṣa*⁸³³ ‘embracing, hugging’ 37,104 (TP III 190), see: gesture

⁸³⁰ Quoting Brockhaus: “wo Śiva die Jāhnavī im goldene Falle von den Gipfeln des Berges U. herabsandte”; M I
 19: “Am Tor der Gaṅgā liegt der heilige Wallfahrtsort K. Auf ihn ließ der Götterelephant K. den himmlischen Fluß
 von den Gipfeln des Berges U. in goldenem Falle herabströmen.”

⁸³¹ Also Daś 209.13.

⁸³² Marcel-Dubois 1941: 166, 171 et passim.

kaṇṭhikā ‘necklace’, *haṃsī* finds ~ and shows it to fisherman (*dāśa*) who had caught her husband in net 69,141 (TP VI 19)

kanyā, Creator made ~ from poison and *amṛta* 39,80 (TP III 223); prince sees ~ in dream who transforms herself in his wife 68,8-11 (TP VI 1f.); – see also: Creator; daughter; *kamaṇḍalu*

kanyā-dāna-phala, see: fruit; giving

kanyakā, see: daughter

kanyā-saṃbandha (not MW) ‘matrimonial alliance of maiden, marrying off’ 17,156 (TP II 47 “giving of a daughter”; ORC 129: “*union avec la fille*”); – see: daughter; negotiation

kāpālika,⁸³⁴ Śaiva ascetic, spies disguised as ~ 19,74 (TP II 90); by a burnt offering (*homa-karman*) and a spell (*mantra*) ~ tries to procure for wife a *yakṣa* princess 121,7 (TP IX 12); *vetāla* devours corpse of ~ (*kapālin*) 121,214 (TP IX 27); ~ kills wife of brahmin with his evil eye, reanimates her by throwing ashes on her burning pyre, flees with her, but is killed by her husband with poisoned arrow 124,6-15 (TP IX 68f.); – see also: heretic

kapilā, see: brown cow

kapittha, see: wood-apple

kārā-grha ‘prison’ resembling hell (*niraya*), king puts rich foreigner out of avarice (*artha-lobha*) into ~ 67,42f. (TP V 199); – see also: *bhū-grha*; prison

karaṇa, see *vicitra-karaṇa*

kara-pallava, see: finger

kari-kareṇū (not MW) ‘female elephant’, gait of ~ compared to that of queen 55,201 (TP IV 216)

Karimaṇḍita forest (*vana*; unidentified), brahmins emigrate from Kāśī to ~ 70,40 (TP VI 27)

karkaṭikā, see: gourd

karma-bīja ‘seed (sown) by one’s deeds’ 86,45 (TP VII 16)

karma-kara (‘hired servant’) in a merchant’s house married to *dāśī* of a brahmin 26,89 (TP III 7)

*karman*⁸³⁵ (‘action and its consequences’) cannot be changed (*kasya prāk-karma kenēha śakyate kartum anyathā*) 72,193 (TP VI 83); ~ to be neutralized by favour?: woman asks of Durgā to get the same husband and brother in future lives 80,40f. (TP VI 207); destiny cannot alter ~ of pre-birth 86,45 (TP VII 16); even the gods cannot alter the influence of ~ 101,199 (TP VII 148); effects of pre-birth actions unavoidable (*kiṃ śakyaṃ pūrva-karmātivartitum?*) 101,296 (TP VII 154); – see also: *nidāna*

karma-taru (not MW) ‘tree of one’s former actions’, from his foetal state onward a man eats the fruit of the ~ 40,109 (TP III 249)

karṇikāra (*Pterospermum acerifolium*)⁸³⁶, bees leave ~ *aṃ* finding it without perfume (*visaurabham*) as good men leave a rich man without character 54,55 (TP IV 188)

⁸³³ Cf. Sivaramamurti 1970: 16.

⁸³⁴ On these skull carrying ascetics who practise black magic see Lorenzen 1972; Dehejia 1986: 90..

⁸³⁵ See, e.g. Doniger O’Flaherty 1981: 182; 1983.

⁸³⁶ Macmillan 1991: 119 “A tree of 36 metres or more ... flowers are yellowish and scented.”

karṇī-ratha ‘a kind of small conveyance on wheels mainly for rich women with supports or handles, an Indian buggy (?)’,⁸³⁷ bride in ~ attacked by elephant 27,168 (TP III 14

⁸³⁷ The oldest western translation attempts may be by Loiseleur Deslongchamps 1839: 187: “char couvert (pour le transport des femmes, suivant quelques-uns: petit char couvert pour la promenade; ou plutôt, une litière portée à épaules d’hommes)” of Amarakoṣa 2,8,52 *karṇī-rathaḥ pravahaṇam ḍayanaṃ ca samaṇ trayam* (the scholiast thinks that a *k.* is called thus because one hears the *ratha* [for the sound of a chariot see Sparreboom 1985: 137 s.v. *kvāṇana*] or because *k.* means ‘shoulder’ as that is near the ear, and the object is carried on the shoulders). The oldest reference is in the Jain canon Nāyā 3 § 46 (= Vivāgasutta 1,2,7 § 34 in P. L. Vaidya’s ed. Poona, 1935), where the courtesan Devadattā moves along by means of a *kaṇṇī-rahā* and Abhayadeva explains this by *pravahaṇa-viśeṣaḥ ... karṇī-ratho hi ṛddhimatām keṣāṃcid eva bhavati*. Banerji 1989: 103 speaks of “covered carriage”. The meaning in PSM is *ek prakār kī śibikā*. Remarkably Pāli has no equivalent of *k.*; Vessantara’s queen travels *paṭicchannayogena* (Ja VI 498,13). In Sa. literature I found Raghuv xiv 13; here Mallinātha explains: *karṇī-rathaḥ stri-yogyo ṛpa-rathaḥ. Karṇī-rathaḥ pravahaṇam ḍayanaṃ ratha-garbhakēti Yādavaḥ*; BKŚS 10,92 (*apaśyam*) *karṇī-ratha-pravahaṇe śibikāṃ ca śivāḥṭim* “I saw ... litters and carts ... and palanquins” (Poddar & Sinha; Renou 1954: 93 renders *k.* by “small vehicle for women”), which shows that *karṇī-ratha* is different from a litter (*śibikā*). For *ḍayana* MW gives the meaning ‘palanquin’. At Rājāt 7,478 a queen leaps from a *k.*, which is called *yugya* in vs 463, on a pyre; at Hemacandra, *Tri*° VI 8,49 a *k.* is made for an Arhat’s statue. Though mostly used by women, at Rājāt 5,219 a dying king orders himself to be carried away in a *k.* which Stein translates as ‘litter’, and at 4,407 a young king is told that his grandfather’s army counted a lakh and a quarter of *karṇīratha*. This sounds rather impractical for an army when the vehicles had no wheels, or, as Grierson thinks (1926: 128, § 148), were four-wheeled. Moreover, their use seems not restricted to rich people then.

Etymologically the compound would mean ‘a conveyance on wheels with handles, supports or “ears”’. Meyer 1952: 267 in his long note 1 remarks that *ratha* is rare as a vehicle for women and gives as examples only Mbh 3,277,39 where Sāvitrī ascends a golden vehicle (*haimaṇ ratham āsthāya*) with her father’s aged counsellors, and 4,21,11 where Kīcaka offers Draupadī a *ratham aśvatārī-yuktam*, a vehicle yoked with she-mules. The former must be a large kind of state carriage, but the latter might be for the woman alone. Our references of *karṇī-ratha* do not indicate who drew them. The earliest pictures of vehicles with noble women are litters without wheels in Ajanta (Schlingloff 1988: 18f., 22f. and 108), and on the western wing of the southern gallery in Angkor Vat a large and clear palanquin with a princess can be seen (Albanese 2011: 96f.; Giteau 1976: 80 where the object is carried by six men). However, because of *-ratha* it should have wheels. This excludes that Kashmiri *katt*, the palanquins the Kashmirian nobles use and which are carried on the shoulders of men, are a corrupted rendering of a Pr. derivative from *karṇīratha* (Stein 1900 I 159 on Rājāt IV 407 < Sachau 1910: 206 [p.c. Patrick Krüger]. *Katt* is not in CDIAL).

Pal 1994: 76 and especially 237, the wrapper on Schubring 2004 and www.herenow4u.net/index.php?id=72813 show the rare, realistic 50 x 60 cm painting on paper of a *samavasaraṇa* from Jaipur, c. 1800, in a private European collection, with many conveyances prominent visitors parked in the outer ring but one. In the centre there are courtesans in full array, or statues; it is not only about transport here, but also about *darshan*. The buggy-like conveyance with two yellow supports, the *karṇa-s* (?), first left to the (Southern, originally Eastern, as for clearness I have turned the picture by 90°) entrance of the *samavasaraṇa*, could fulfil both these qualities the whole looking like a precursor of a rickshaw, unless there is foreign, Moghul or English influence. In the right lower half of the picture, second under the Eastern gate, there is a similar carriage, but with a roof. Like vehicles used by single men and drawn by animals are found in Gujarat or Rajasthan early 17th century (Granoff 2010: 78). Perhaps specimina of *karṇī-ratha* are still found in Indian palace musea such as in the collection of fifty vehicles of H.M. the last Mahārāja of Jaipur. Pratapaditya Pal (p. c.) thinks it would be a reasonable assumption but cannot determine.

For Patrick Krüger the roof supports of the two-wheeled chariot with women in Mathura (Quintanilla 2007: fig. 23 and 231) are bent outwards and may reflect ears, but I think the *karṇīratha* is rather meant as a conveyance for a

“covered palankeen”; ORC 265: “*litière*”); golden image of boy carried around in ~ with proclamation 94,91 (TP VII 93; pwb: ‘*eine Art Sänfte*’ > MW: ‘a kind of litter’, ORC 1010: ‘palanquin’); a female beauty such as a dryad (*vana-śrī ... varâṅganā*) descends from ~ 120,117f. (TP IX 10 “covered chariot”; ORC 1264 “*litière*”)⁸³⁸

karṇōtpala, see: lotus

kārpaṭika ‘foreign dependent on a king, candidate for service’ 24,121 (TP II 178 note); minister as ~ 38,18 (TP III 207); ‘unpaid employee’ 53,2 (TP IV 168 with note)⁸³⁹; Rājput becomes ~ by tearing ragged garment (*karpaṭa*) in front of king 81,7 (TP VI 209); 123,4ff.

single person. – Thévenot 2008: 140ff., Careri in Sen 1949: 160, Deloche 1983 and Gail 1986 do not mention *k.* Gode 1960: II 133f. deals with five types of conveyances for Chinese queens, but does not record Indian ones.

⁸³⁸ In the following stanzas 124, 128 and 132 the word *vahana* is used for the lady’s vehicle.

⁸³⁹ Cf. Rājat 3,161f.

(TP IX 43); ~ turns into boa constrictor after eating gourd / cucumber 123,32 (TP IX 45); Rājput takes vow of ~ 124,53 (TP IX 72); – see also: Rājput

Kārttikeya (Svāmikumāra) in the South sends dream 2,44f. (TP I 12f.); shrine of ~ in the Deccan 3,8 (TP I 18); ~ reveals new grammar to Varṣa 4,92 (TP I 36); Skanda ~ in temple appears to man 7,9 (TP I 74); ~ born six-headed from fire 20,90 (TP II 102); ~ as divine hero on peacock orders dreamer to stay 43,50 (TP III 284); ~ surrounded by inauspicious planets, etc. 50,184 (TP IV 119); ~ propitiated by king for a son sends Gaṇeśa 55,161 (TP IV 213); ~'s temple not to be entered by females 55,174 (TP IV 214); after cursing king, ~ is pleased by his well-turned language 55,177 (TP IV 214); king Mahāsena valiant as ~ 101,43 (TP VII 137)

*kāśā*⁸⁴⁰ (Saccharum spontaneum; symbol of lightness and material of the red sacred thread of the *kṣatriyas*) TP VII 26

kāṣāya, see: Buddhist robe

Kāsmīra, worshipping at holy places of Svayambhū in ~ 51,45 (TP IV 125 wrongly: “named Svayambhū”; MI 767: “*Gehe zu den in Kāsmīra gelegenen Feldern Svayambhu*”); ~ created to prevent mortals from hankering after heaven 63,53 (TP V 123); student of religion (*dhārmika*) going to ~ in order to conquer paṇḍits in dispute (*vāda*) 66,10 (TP V 178); ~ as second heaven 73,79 (TP VI 106); ruled by Kṛṣṇa-devotee (*Kṛṣṇāikāsakta*) 73,87 (TP VI 107); – see also: ²Ananta; pārijāta; Saṃgrāma

kāṣṭha-bhāraka, see: wood-carrier

kāṣṭha-khaṇḍaka ‘mace’ as mark of Rājputs 24,121 (TP II 178)

kāṣṭha-yantra-maya ‘consisting of wooden automata’, golden city with inhabitants ~ 43,10 (TP III 281)

kastūrikā, see: musk

Kāśyapa, his hermitage on Mt Sumeru 45,364 (TP IV 41); ~ of golden appearance and with matted locks yellow as flame 45,371 (TP IV 41f.); ~ appeased by Indra 45,395 (TP IV 44)

kaṭaka, see: *bhārika*

kaṭākṣa ‘sidelong glance’, antelopes likened to ~ of the quarters 21,13 (TP II 126); ~ of love⁸⁴¹ 37,210 (TP III 198) and of a nymph who thus shuts out the thoughts of an ascetic 70,69 (TP VI 29)⁸⁴²; women’s ~ compared to blue lotuses covering the streets 44,74 (TP IV 6); dice are the (loving) ~ of (the goddess of) Ill Luck (Aśrī) 73,76 (TP VI 106); *tiryāṅ-nyasta-dṛṣṭi* 103,61 (TP VII 179); *caṇḍāla* beauty smites elephant with *kuṭalais taiḥ* *kaṭākṣaiḥ* 112,68 (TP VIII 111)⁸⁴³; princess tears out heart of prince with the arrows of her ~ 117,97 (TP VIII 171); – see also: comparison(s); eye

⁸⁴⁰ See Kuv notes 542 and 2087 (symbol of laughing).

⁸⁴¹ In BIS 1124 (< Śṛṅgāraśataka 13) the girl represents a hunter, her brow the bow, her sidelong glances the arrows, and my heart the deer. Hāla 370 does not use *kaḍakkha*, but speaks of glances from a half closed eye. Seligmann 1980: 453 < Plutarch.

⁸⁴² Cf. 90,56 (TP VII 53) *tiryak-prasṭayā paśyantī snigdhayā dṛṣā*.

⁸⁴³ See also: healing.

Kātantra, concise grammar called ~ 7,13 (TP I 75)

kātara-locana ‘squinting eyes’ (mark of male ugliness) 123,164 (TP IX 55)

kathaka, see: story-teller

kathālāpa (not MW) ‘interview, talk, conversation’ 66,116 (TP V 187)

Kathāsaritsāgara, composed by Soma (q.v.) E 13 (TP IX 89)

kaṭi-taṭa ‘the loins, hip’, prince marks intoxicated woman with heated spike on ~ 75,155 (TP VI 175)

Kātyāyana, see: Vararuci

Kātyāyanī, see: Durgā

kauberī-hāsa (not MW) ‘smile of the northern quarter’, Mt Kailāsa beautiful with ~ 120,16 (TP IX 2)

kaumāra-brahmacāriṇī comes to hermitage of princess 66,155 (TP V 190)

kaupīna ‘loincloth’, see: Buddhist monks

Kauśāmbī as (ear-)ornament of the earth 9,4 (TP I 94)⁸⁴⁴; do 30,38 (TP III 66); ~ residence of Lakṣmī, goddess of Prosperity 9,5 (TP I 94; cf. Timirā), and kings of Vatsa 18,64 (TP II 54); queen remains in ~ like a doe that has strayed from the forest 33,2 (TP III 107); ~, making festival, as if scattering red paint with scarlett banners 54,77 (TP IV 189);

kaūśeya ‘silk garment’, merchant woman sitting in window with ~ on 95,17 (TP VII 99)

Kauśika (*vidyādhara-guru*) descending from heaven ends curse 25,258 (TP II 210)

kautuka ‘curiosity’, q.v. and 122,112 (TP IX 42)

Kāverī river crossed into Chola kingdom 19,95 (TP II 92 with note 4)

kāyastha, see: *saṃdhi-vigraha*-°

[*kāya-vyūha*], see: bilocality; body; division of personality

ketaka (Pandanus odoratissimus)⁸⁴⁵ whose (white) sweet-smelling trumpet flowers are compared to the tusks of the monsoon elephant 122,66 (TP IX 38)

ketana ‘house, mansion’, palace of Daitya maidens like the ~ of the Vṛṣṇīs 73,145 (TP VI 111)

kh / c misprint, see: *khaṇḍa-kāpālīka*

khaḍga-siddha ‘magic sword’ 52,173 (TP IV 150)

khādīra-daṇḍa ‘staff of acacia-wood’ as weapon 53,21 (TP IV 169; cf. *laguḍa*)

kha-dyota ‘glow-worm’,⁸⁴⁶ monkeys see ~ and think it to be fire 60,205 (TP V 58 with note)

khaṇḍa-kāpālīka (?) ‘maimed or crippled *k.*’ 121,6 and 13 (TP IX 12f. “hypocritical scoundrel of a *k.*”; ORC 1265: “*minable k.*”⁸⁴⁷; M II 684: “*verkrüppelter Angehöriger der K.-*

⁸⁴⁴ Cf. the description in Kuv. 31,19ff.

⁸⁴⁵ Thus MW; Syed 1990: 230f. quoting, inter alia, Śīsupālavadhā 6,34 where the flower is said to have the form of a crescent (*śaśi-khaṇḍa*); Macmillan 1991: 509; ORC 1590 Pandanus tectorius; Duda 2006: 293f.

⁸⁴⁶ Hensgen 1958: 147.

⁸⁴⁷ This word translates the whole compound *khaṇḍa-kāpālīkādharma*. At vs 13 ORC omits *khaṇḍa*. – If the reading is right the physical sense of maimed or crippled seems better, but this quality does not bear upon the following context where in vs 15 he is called *duṣṭa*, in vs 25 *pāpa*. Shouldn’t we therefore read **caṇḍa-kāpālīka* ‘fierce,

Mischkaste”; MW: ‘inferior k. ascetic’)

khanya-vādin ‘treasure hunter’ (not MW) 34,69 (TP III 133)⁸⁴⁸

khara-karṇaka, see: donkey; ear

khārī, one hundred ~s of sesame-seed (*tila*) to be sown by bridegroom 39,116 (TP III 226)

khāta ‘grave’ (?), four merchants are thrown into the ~ of a Turuṣka 37,39 (TP III 185; ORC 373 “*dans la fosse tombale*”)

khātaka, see: ditch

khaṭvā, see: bedstead

khaṭvāṅga (staff of Śiva and Kālī⁸⁴⁹ like a bed-post with a skull at the top) carried by Pāśupata ascetics 70,3 (TP VI 23); ~ dancing on shoulder of *kāpālika* 124,8 (TP IX 68 with note 1);

khecarī-cakra ‘group of air-flying witches’ 123,199⁸⁵⁰ (TP IX 57)

khecarī-siddhi ‘power of a woman to fly’ 20,105 (TP II 103)

kick, brahmin kicks other brahmin 20,14 (TP II 96)⁸⁵¹; man kicks (*pāda-ghātair atāḍayat*) merchant’s daughter whose passion is then doubled 21,75f. (TP II 131); king gives guard ~ (lit.: hits him with foot) 55,5 (TP IV 202); hermit woken up by king with ~ (*pāda-prahāreṇa*) 56,228 (TP IV 236); man flung by horse with a ~ (*khurāhata*) into a temple of Śiva 108,56 (TP VIII 57); – see also: feet; hitting

kilbiṣa, see: *aḡha*; (offence); *pāpa*; transgression

killut,⁸⁵² see: garment 14,60 (TP I 187)

kiṁnara,⁸⁵³ hunted by king, enters mountain cavern 59,76 (TP V 31)

kiṁnari, see *kaṅkāla-kiṁnari*

kiṁpāka ‘colocynth’ (q.v.)

kiṁśuka (*Butea frondosa*) 104,90 (TP VIII 7 with note 3), cf. *palāśa*

kiṁ tavānena ? ‘what business is that of yours’ ? 72,328 (TP VI 93);

kiṅānkita (not MW) ‘marked by scars, bruised’, of delicate queen’s hands by distant sound of pestle 85,26 (TP VII 11)

king, suddenly dies 4,98 (TP I 37) and is reanimated by magician entering his body 4,99 (TP I 38); brahmin as ~ 5,46 (TP I 50) and 18,403 (TP II 80); ~ fears people’s reproach 5,63 (TP I 52); ~ compared to wind chasing queens like creepers 6,112 (TP I 69); ~ ignorant of grammar and ashamed 6,118 (TP I 69); ~ humiliated by queen 6,117 and 126 (TP I 69f.); ~ exalts queen above all others through affection by sprinkling her with water (*prītyābhiṣicya*)

violent, cruel’ *k.* which would fit better in the story and be a minor conjecture of the *devanāgarī* script ? Moreover, the latter compound is also the name of a teacher in MW.

⁸⁴⁸ See Balbir 1993: 19ff.

⁸⁴⁹ Cf. Rodrigues 2003: 210 and Dallapiccola 2002: 115 (p. c. Prof. Hegewald); see also Pal 2009: 16 (8), 106 and 144. According to Sivaramamurti 1974a: 552 the *khaṭvāṅga* is a club composed of a skull and a thigh bone.

⁸⁵⁰ Cf. 123,212 *yoginī-grāma*. See also Dehejia 1986: 28.

⁸⁵¹ ĀpDhS I 11,31,6 forbids this.

⁸⁵² Yule & Burnell 1968: 483b.

⁸⁵³ See Hopkins 1915:249a; Zin 2003b: 192 note 33 and cf. Smith 2006: 89f.

6,167 (TP I 73)⁸⁵⁴; ~ depending on wise ministers 15,59 (TP II 6); mind of ~s runs towards unlawful objects 17,138 (TP II 45); ~ surrounded by chiefs like polar star by planets (or: a firm man by evil spirits; *dhruvaṃ graha-gaṇā iva*) 18,5 (TP II 49); ~ like cloud (*rāja-jalada*) raining gold on dependents (*anujīviṣu*) 18,50 (TP II 53); ~ carried off by runaway horse to forest 18,96 (TP II 56)⁸⁵⁵; amusement of ~ is fruitful 20,45 (TP II 98); ~ holds queen like cloud holds lightning 24,20 (TP II 171); ~ superintends religion of the people (*dharmānuśāsitrī*) 27,27 (TP III 3)⁸⁵⁶; ~ listens to teaching of *dharmā-pāṭhaka* in (non-Buddhist) *vihāra* 28,45 (TP III 23); ~ slashes hermit out of jealousy 28,31 (TP III 22); (old) ~ white as snow (*hima-śubhra*), as the lotus-bed when linked to the winter 30,30f. (TP III 66); ~ who is feast to the eyes of the world 30,44 (TP III 67); ~ white with age (*jarā-pāṇḍu*) 31,40 (TP III 84); ~ to be kept away from famous beauty 31,63-68 (TP III 87; cf. 32,31 [TP III 92], 33,57 [TP III 111] and especially 91,15f. [TP VII 67]); due to beautiful wife ~ would forget kingdom 33,60 (TP III 111); ~ without fitting wife 33,26 (TP III 109); deity enters ~'s body and makes him speak 34,56 (TP III 132); duties of ~ 34,191ff. (TP III 142f.)⁸⁵⁷; ~ should have *atharvan* as *purohita*⁸⁵⁸ 34,193 (TP III 142); ~ praises Śiva for a son 35,103 (TP III 164); ~ propitiates Viṣṇu to obtain the conquest of the earth and have all kings' daughters as wives 36,11 (TP III 169); ~ leaves realm to ministers and goes out of city secretly 38,17 (TP III 207); out of grief for his dead minister ~ leaves his throne for the forest 41,54 (TP III 256); for ~ the first duty is their physical preservation (*śarīra-mūla*), and counsel is the foundation (*mantri-mūla*) of rule 42,45 (TP III 262); ~ like fire in which he scorches enemies 44,18 (TP IV 2); why ~s have many wives 47,105 (TP IV 73); ~ refuses to eat unless brahmin dances 49,15 (TP IV 86); ~ saved by brahmin from crocodile and snake-bite 49,85 (TP IV 90); ~ is upholder of the castes and stages of life (*varṇāśramāṇām dharmasya rājā ... rakṣitā*) 52,114 (TP IV 146); favour of ~ is fruitful 53,63 (TP IV 172); eulogy of ~ **55,29ff.** (TP IV 204); ~ painted 55,46ff. (TP IV 206); ~ falling at sulking queen's feet and blaming himself 55,130 (TP IV 211); foolish ~ asks physicians for growing drug for his daughter 61,266f. (TP V 91); foolish ~ who had flesh cut from thief 61,284 (TP V 93); elephant puts merchant on his back whom people then anoint ~ 65,25f. (TP V 155)⁸⁵⁹; ~ criticises son for not informing him 67,29 (TP V 198); ~ leaves his city alone on horse at night 69,111 (TP VI 17); as boon, Caṇḍikā has

⁸⁵⁴ This is the reason of the jealousy of the main queen Madanasundarī at 55,119 (TP IV 210).

⁸⁵⁵ STh N 771. Cases of a king carried off alone into the jungle by his run-away horse are not seldom in literature and thus also pictured, e.g. in Cave XVII in Ajanta where the king is then seduced by a lioness in a (rare) case of bestiality (Schlingloff 1988: 102f.). Kings being abducted into the forest are a τόπος also in Western literature, see, e.g., Curtius 1965: 366 and especially Boden 2011, the articles "Wald" (column 436) and "Verirren" (p.c. Albert Gier).

⁸⁵⁶ Cf. our *Cuius regio, eius religio*.

⁸⁵⁷ Anderson 2005: 99f.

⁸⁵⁸ Because the atharvan knows many charms against evil.

⁸⁵⁹ Cf. STh H 171.1 and Mokṣōpāya V 45,36.

sleeping ~ conveyed across sea by attendants 69,115 (TP VI 17); unenterprising (*a-lasa*) ~s perish like snakes arrested by a charm 71,104 (TP VI 43); ~, vanquished in dispute by *bhikṣu*, adopts Buddhism (*Saugataṃ matam*) 72,97f. and builds monasteries for all denominations 72,99 (TP VI 76); ~ criticised by people 74,69 (TP VI 145)⁸⁶⁰; ~ devolves duties to ministers and becomes exclusively addicted to harem, drinking, etc. 74,304 (TP VI 162); ~ with parrot and she-maina 77,6f. (TP VI 183); best ~ is ready to die for the servants by whose lives kings are wont to save their own 78,131 (TP VI 199); ~ as favour of Devī in bodily form 81,104 (TP VI 216); ~ leaves realm to minister and devotes himself to pleasure 86,6 (TP VII 13) and 101,45 (TP VII 137); ~ sets out at night in ascetic disguise 86,70 (TP VII 18); *dharma* of ~ is protecting *dharma* of subjects 89,70 (TP VII 18); eulogy of ~ 91,4ff. (TP VII 66); ~ knower of *śāstras* 91,6 (TP VII 66); ~ is offered merchant beauty, but his brahmins, to protect the kingdom, tell him she has inauspicious marks and so he gives her to his army commander 91,11ff. (TP VII 67)⁸⁶¹; ~s are inflated with arrogance, uncontrollable as elephants (*madā-dhmātā gajā iva nir-aṅkuśāḥ*) 91,54 (TP VII 70); ~ incapable to protect merchant's widow from relations seizing her husband's property 93,9 (TP VII 78)⁸⁶²; Śiva tells sonless ~ in dream of newborn son lying at his gate 93,52 (TP VII 82); ~ called upon by weak being (*durbala*) in danger 94,131 (TP VII 96); ~ establishes son on his throne and retires to forest 101,383 (TP VII 160); five princesses eager to see ~ 107,83 (TP VIII 48); ~ criticised for dallying with wives answers that he does this in order to acquire allies (*bandhu-prāpti*) 108,193f. (TP VIII 68); when ~ is captured, army is broken and flees 109,55 (TP VIII 74)⁸⁶³; ~ asks *loka-pālas* advice 112,135 (TP VIII 116); ~ setting out alone at night to catch robber 112,151 (TP VIII 118); king flying on a bird (*pakṣi-vahana*) 118,68 (TP VIII 182); imprisoned Daitya ~ refuses to marry his daughters to enemy princes and be set free 119,11 (TP VIII 193); ~ heals *kārpaṭika*, who has been transformed in a boa constrictor by eating gourd / cucumber, with sternutatory made of plant extract (*oṣadhī-rasa-nasya*) 123,46 (TP IX 46); Bhillā chief's mansion has high walls with tusks of elephants and tiger skins 123,49 (TP IX 46); fear of ~ (*rāja-bhayena*) prevents brahmin from marrying his ugly son to beautiful wife of another 123,305 (TP IX 64); ~ sets out at night in search of adventures (*vīra-caryā-gata*)⁸⁶⁴ and hears *āryā* recited 124,57 (TP IX 72); – see also: abduction; choosing king; daughter; duty; elephant; forest; grief; hero; horse; hunt(ing); inauguration; *kārpaṭika*; realm; sonless king; vice king guarded by (armed) women: Śak, prelude to II (*rājā*) *bāṇāsana-hastābhir Yavanībhir ... parivṛtaḥ*); Strabo XV,1,56; Gaddhafi of Libya; still in Jogjakarta on the island of Java kingdom, king commits ~ to principal minister 9,15 (TP I 95); witch banned from entering ~

⁸⁶⁰ Cf. Rājāt 6,144.

⁸⁶¹ Anderson 2005: 97f.

⁸⁶² See: heritage supra.

⁸⁶³ Cf. Rājāt V 331 where the army flees when the king is killed.

⁸⁶⁴ Also e.g., Rājāt 7,305.

20,185 (TP II 111); before going to the forest, king makes over his ~ to brahmin 36,109 (TP III 177)⁸⁶⁵; adopting refugee as son king gives away ~ against will of ministers. and leaves for forest 72,175 (TP VI 81f.); younger brother expels elder from ~ 74,25 (TP VI 142); ~ to be guarded by ministers until king returns from pilgrimage 93,72 (TP VII 82); constitutional ~ (*paura-svāmika-rājya*) 113,20 (TP VIII 125); crown-prince does not care for ~ when depending on subjects (*paurâyatta*) 113,48 (TP VIII 127); – see also: realm; throne

Kirāta, a non-Āryan mountain tribe spread all over northern India⁸⁶⁶ and ruled by king 70,19 (TP VI 25)

kīrti-stambha, Gaṇapati throws up his trunk with a swarm of bees like a triumphal pillar with a range of syllables on it 68,1 (TP VI 1); – cf. *jaya-stambha*

kissing ~ on the head (*mūrdhni paricumbya*) 45,366 (TP IV 41)⁸⁶⁷

kissing on the mouth 13,108 (TP I 158)⁸⁶⁸; woman desires to be kissed (*paricumbana-lālasā*) 52,357 (TP IV 163); heads of warriors, cut off, fly up to heaven as if to kiss *apsaras* (*divya-strīr iva cumbitum*) 103,8 (TP VII 175);

kitchen (*sūda-sālā*) 56,394 (TP IV 248)

kitchen-garden (*śāka-vāṭikā*) 72,206 (TP VI 83);

kite (*gr̥dhra*) steals necklace 54,114 (TP IV 192)⁸⁶⁹; plundered merchant finds jewels in ~'s nest 54,128f. (TP IV 193); ~ (*śyena*)⁸⁷⁰ presumably carries off boy 60,244 (TP V 62); saliva of dead snake carried by ~ poisons brahmin's dish of rice 87,44f. (TP VII 32)

knave, see: rogue

knee, dog bites Buddhist monk on ~ 65,135f. (TP V 165); Śiva sits naked with head on ~ 121,99 (TP IX 19)

knowledge or science (*vidyā*), Svāmikumāra gives brahmin (knowledge of) all sciences 2,60 (TP I 15); ~ obtained in the Deccan 6,22 (TP I 61); ~ (*jñāna*) pretended by stupid brahmin 30,100 and 122 (TP III 70f.); ~ without reading is impossible 40,22 (TP III 241); fidelity to husband gives wife ~ of past, future and present 52,228ff. (TP IV 154); four *deva-putras* with ~ of assuming various forms, with ~ of past, present and future, able to measure everything, and to call all deities to their aid 54,17ff. (TP IV 185); *yakṣa* gives brahmins ~ 63,89f. (TP V 125); ~ of antidotes (*viśa-vidyā*) saves brahmin bitten by snake 75,14 (TP VI 165); *vaiśya* with ~ of speech of animals 83,25 (TP VII 3); brahmin acquires ~ of the three times (*tri-kāla-jñāna*) in Śiva temple 108,57 (TP VIII 57); gambler pretends ~ of speech of animals (*ruta-jñā*) 121,163 (TP IX 23); – superhuman ~ of *vidyā-dharas*, see: *vidyā*; – cf. also: ignorance

⁸⁶⁵ Cf. MaitrāyaṇīyaUp 1,2.

⁸⁶⁶ See Saletore 1935: 1ff.; Law 1943: 282ff.; Jackmuth 2002: 80; www.en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kirata_Kingdom

⁸⁶⁷ Cf. Daś 142,8; 197,3; BKŚS 18,69. See Hopkins 1907; Meyer 1952: 183 note 1.

⁸⁶⁸ See Smith 2005.

⁸⁶⁹ Cf. STh B 522.2.

⁸⁷⁰ Hensgen 1958: 133.

koel(s) (*kokila*)⁸⁷¹, sweetly speaking ~ 55,111 (TP IV 209)⁸⁷²; 71,197 (TP VI 50); ~s singing as bards in forest 75,66 (TP VI 168); song of ~ harsh with reproachful utterances of Māra 104,7 (TP VII 1); ~ as warder of Kāma seeing mango-tree stalk 111,6 (TP VIII 94); female ~ on mango tree mute while separated from her mate 111,21 (TP VIII 97)

kolāhala ‘shout of astonishment’ 74,194 (TP VI 154);

Konkan ruled by king Subhaṭa 44,149 (TP IV 11); black ~ mare 121,278 (TP IX 32)

kopa-gr̥ha (‘sulking room’)⁸⁷³ Kuv 12.1

kopāndha ‘blinded with wrath’ (not MW) 106,154 (TP VIII 39)

koṣa-vāri (‘water of ordeal’) 119,35 to be drunk by those affected by the ordeal 39 (TP VIII 195);

koṣa-veśman ‘treasury’, rogue puts box of ornaments in chaplain’s ~ 24,133 (TP II 179); 24,167 (TP II 181)

krait (*kṛṣṇa-sarpa*) not in ant-hill 33,46 (TP III 110); by hermit’s illusive power (*śakti*), ~ bites painted princess unconscious 72,303 (TP VI 91); ~ (*kṛṣṇāhi*), carried by bird of prey, loses poison which drips into brahmin’s rice bowl 87,44 (TP VII 32);

krakaca, see: saw

krama-siddha (not MW), ~*ena mantreṇa* ‘with a regular or relevant spell’ 121,13 (TP IX 13 “by a spell, duly muttered in a circle”; ORC 1265: “*par la formule à efficacité progressive*”; M II 685: “*durch den allmählich, aber unwiderstehlich wirkenden Zauberspruch*”)

kravyâd ‘eating raw flesh’, princesses want to offer their bodies while still alive to *gaṇa* of beings ~s 28,17 (TP III 19), see also: body; flesh-eater

kravya-gandhin ‘smelling of raw flesh’, of an *aśoka* tree in a charnel ground 75,51 (TP VI 167);

kṛcchra-karmôpajivin ‘supporting oneself by menial drudgery’, said of a brahmin woman 21,115 (TP II 134)

krīḍā-hariṇa (not MW) ‘toy-deer’, golden ~ dancing before two beautiful maidens on sandbank 120,107 (TP IX 9)

krīḍā-kṛtaṃ nāma, see: pet name

krīḍālīna (not MW) ‘playful(ly)’, see: bee(s)

kṛśa-pāṇḍura ‘thin and pale’ as the digit of new moon, said of a woman afflicted by separation 106,108 (TP VIII 36)

Kṛṣṇa devotee, king of Cashmere is ~ 73,87 (TP VI 107)

kṛṣṇa-kambala ‘black blanket’ stripped by woman from sick king 29,165 (TP III 52); – see also: black blanket; dream; *kāla-kambala*

kṛṣṇa-turagī (not MW), witch in form of black mare fights other witch in form of bay mare

⁸⁷¹ Hensgen 1958: 140; Dave 2005: 137ff.

⁸⁷² Jackmuth 2002: 127f.

⁸⁷³ Cf. Bhāvadeva, *Pārśvanāthacar.* 7. 42; Hemacandra, *Tri*^o see Johnson 1931-62, s.v. anger-house; Hemavijaya, *Kathāratnākara* 298,19; and *krodhāgāra* in Rām 2,9,22 (Meyer 1952: 494); Bloomfield 1919: 146; Chojnacki 2008 (I), s.v. *boudoir* which word shows that a sulking room was known also in Europe.

(*śoṇa-vaḍavā*) 37,162 (TP III 194)
kṛta-ghna ‘ungrateful’ though long successful will fail at last 56,230 (TP IV 236)
kṛta-kopa, see: anger
 Kṛtānta (‘god of Death’), palace of ~ (*kṛtānta-sadana*) 72,17 (TP VI 69); teeth of angry ~ gnashing 74,283 (TP VI 160); hunt as sport of ~ (°-*kṛīḍita*) 59,44 (TP V 29)
kṛtānta-dūti, see: omen
kṛtrima-putra (‘adoptive son’) as against *aurasa-putra* 73,60 (TP VI 105)
kṛtrima-suta, do, see: adoptive son
 Kṛttikās,⁸⁷⁴ six Pleiades suckle Kumāra 20,88 (TP II 102); ~ as origin (*saṃbhava*) of Skanda 49,239 (TP IV 102)
kṛtyā ‘magic rite’ causing lethal *dāha-jvara* 5,121 (TP I 57)
kṣamā-pāramitā (‘perfection of patience’) 72,259 (TP VI 87);
kṣamasva, see: pardon
kṣaṇa-nāśvara ‘perishing in a moment’ (not MW), of the body 4,133 (TP I 41; ORC 25: “*le corps périt en un instant*”)
kṣapaṇaka ‘Digambara monk’, Śiva in the form of a ~ (*kṛta-kṣapaṇakākṛti*) shows Umā that not even *ṛṣis* possess self-restraint 20,132 (TP II 106: “Buddhist mendicant”; ORC 168: “*moine mendiant*”; M I 240: “*buddhistischer Mönch*”)⁸⁷⁵; ~ with higher knowledge (*jñānin*) 39,59 (TP III 222: “Buddhist mendicant”⁸⁷⁶; ORC 399: “*pénitent*” with note on p. 1398: “*probablement ... un ascète Digambara*”; M I 559: “*jainistischer Bettelmönch*”); ~ as old friend asked meaning of king’s dream 55,137 (TP IV 211: “Buddhist mendicant”; ORC 616: “*moine errant*”; M I 864: “*buddhistischer Mönch*”)⁸⁷⁷;
kṣapitāśeṣa-vayas ‘who has destroyed the strength / youth of unnumerable men’ 102,73 (TP VII 168 “he had seen the death of many ‘secular birds’ [?]”; ORC 1066: “*Il avait déjà fait périr bien des hommes vigoureux*”; M II 416 “*hatte er schon manches Grausame durch den Tod in vielen Schlachten gesehen*”)
kṣatra-dharma, the capturing of wives of besieged enemies by the might of the arm (*bhujārjita*) 54,234 (TP IV 200)
kṣatra-vāda (not MW) ‘discourse or dispute on the *kṣatriya* class’ 72,69 (TP VI 73);
kṣatriya, characteristic of ~s is rescue of distressed 66,16 (TP V 179); ~ king claims to be best sword fighter 83,27 (TP VII 3); ~ woman, *ex-vidyādhari*, cursed to be mortal 52,144 (TP IV 148); ~ cannot be given in marriage to *śūdra* or *vaiśya* 83,35 (TP VII 4); – see

⁸⁷⁴ On these see, e.g. Doniger O’Flaherty 1981: 383.

⁸⁷⁵ Doniger O’Flaherty 1976: 313 states that no Sanskrit text explicitly supports that the *ṛṣis* in this passage were Buddhists, although our text states that Śiva himself took the form of a Buddhist monk (*kṣapaṇaka*) to enter the Pine Forest (*devadaru-vana*) in order to show Pārvatī that even sages are not calm, but apparently she did not check MW for *kṣapaṇaka*.

⁸⁷⁶ Wrongly translated by TP, for in 39,62 he is stated as *nagna-kṣapaṇaka*, ORC 400: “*le pénitent nu*”.

⁸⁷⁷ On divination with the Jains see von Glasenapp 1999: 446ff. Buddhist monks are not allowed to do interpretation of dreams (DīghaN I 9,4) though the Buddha himself traditionally (Bollée 1984: 185) did it.

also: combat; Rājput

kṣattrī ‘royal warder, door-keeper, chamberlain’ receives guests of king in his house 52,106 (TP IV 145); ~ (and close friend) executed as violator of royal harem 71,303 (TP VI 58); ~ gets son⁸⁷⁸ coeval with prince 120,53 (TP IX 5); 122,35 (TP IX 36); ~ builds *matha* 122,73 (TP IX 39); ~ as intermediary between executioners and king 124,126 (TP IX 77);

kṣībate ‘to be intoxicated, made drunk’ 13,10 (TP I 151)

kṣīriṇī ‘milk rice’, foolish Ṭakka prefers immolation to sharing his ~ with a guest 65,142 (TP V 165)

KSS should end with ch. 110 (TP VIII 93 note 2) but 111 starts again with invocation of Gaṇeśa and spring

Kubera residing in Alakā 19,107 (TP II 93)⁸⁷⁹; his son Naḍakūbara, married to Maya’s daughter Somaprabhā 29,16 (TP III 40); ~ curses brahmin-killing *yakṣa* to be born a mortal brahmin 34,77 (TP III 134); ~ Dhanādhipa moving about at will (*kāma-cārī*) 38,69 manifests himself (*prakaṭi-bhūta*) to king 38,70 (TP III 211f.); ~ appearing at being thought of by devotee (*saṃsmṛtōpasthita*) 38,71 (TP III 211); Tejasvatī is his daughter 45,177 (TP IV 29); Dhanādhyakṣa gives *yakṣiṇī* to brahmin 49,187 (TP IV 97); his lake and garden near Kailāsa 51,99 (TP IV 129); ~ curses two *yakṣas* to become brahminy ducks in lake Mānasa 72,43 (TP VI 71);

kukṣi-koṭara (not MW) ‘ocean cavity’, Kamalā-Lakṣmī was in ~ before the ocean was churned 11,80 (TP I 128)

kula-devatā,⁸⁸⁰ Caṇḍikā ~ of merchant woman 95,29 (TP VII 100); ~ of Rājputs 111,45 (TP VIII 99); – see also: death

kuli (not MW; Apte: ‘point’) 53,88 (TP IV 173 ‘atoms of earth’, nano particles)

kuliśāstra (not MW) ‘thunderbolt-weapon’ 116,71 (TP VIII 161)

Kumāra born from Hara’s energy in sacrificial cavity (*vahni-kuṇḍa*) on Mt Meru 20,86 (TP II 102); from ~’s body, when struck by (Indra’s) thunderbolt, the sons Śākha and Viśākha were born 20,91f. (TP II 102); ~ consecrated by Indra as his general 20,95 (TP II 102); – see also: Skanda

kumārī brāhmaṇī ‘brahma-kumārī, perpetual vergin, vestal’ dies as such, but, consumed by fire of love for brahmin, is reborn as courtesan 69,161-3 (TP VI 20)

kumuda ‘white lotus’ miserable without moonlight 26,88 (TP II 223); bees on cluster of ~ at night 84,43 (TP VII 8); pure ~ cluster laughs with the cheerful faces of its open flowers (*hasaty utphulla-vadane viśade kumudākare*) 95,68 (TP VII 102); *kumudvatī* joyfully beholding full moon 119,192 (TP VIII 206);

kumuda-vrata ‘vow of cowering with contracted limbs like a *kumuda* with its petals closed during the day’ adopted by desparate lover 72,287 (TP VI 90 with note 1);

kumudvatī ‘white lotus’ opening under the rays of the moon 73,345 (TP VI 125); 119,192 (TP

⁸⁷⁸ See Bollée 1981: 188f.

⁸⁷⁹ Zin 2003b: 257.

⁸⁸⁰ Also e.g., Kuv 13.29 et passim.

VIII 206)

kuñjara-maṇi ‘pearl in the head of an elephant’ TP II 142 note 1 on 22,76; 116,65 (TP VIII 161); – see also: pearl

Kuntī pleasing Durvāsas as simile for perfect waiting on guest 27,105 (TP III 8); – see also: hospitality

kuśa grass⁸⁸¹ (*Poa cynosuroides*) pricks hermit’s hand 5,133 (TP I 58); *amṛta* placed on bed of ~ 22,196 (TP II 151 with note 3; in vs 195 ~ is called *darbha*); Vālmiki makes for Sītā baby son out of ~ 51,89 (TP IV 128); lying on bed of ~ as penance 52,244 (TP IV 155); Nala and Damayantī lay down on ~ 56,315 (TP IV 243); princess wounded by the spikes of ~ 71,194 (TP VI 50); 98,13 (TP VII 117); sleeping on ~ as a penance 100,49 (TP VII 132) and 101,219 (TP VII 149)

kūsmāṇḍa, kind of spirit (*yakṣa-guhyaka*-~) 46,199 (TP IV 61 [*kumbhāṇḍa*])

kuṭṭīma, see: mosaic

Kuvalayamālā, name of black Konkani mare 121,278 (TP IX 32)

labour (*janma-duḥkha*) [not MW] 52,397 (TP IV 165)

lac, garment of sleeping intruder in *antaḥpura* marked with red ~ (*alakta*) 3,71 (TP I 23); lake with liquid ~ to equal blood 30,46 (TP III 67)

lacuna due to Victorian prudery?, see: *gaja-kumbha*; *hema-kalaśa*

lactation by elderly women for emotional reasons see: milk; www.invitingmiles.com/lactation-without-pregnancy.html etc. in the web; STh T 592. Bollée 2008a: 10 sub breast and 22 sub milk. For ~ by *cāṇḍāla* woman for exposed baby see Rājat 5,76.

ladder, Jacob’s ~, ridges of waves of Ganges seem to make ~ (*sopāna*) for mortals to ascend into heaven 93,77 (TP VII 83)⁸⁸²;

laguḍa ‘club’, *kārpaṭika* standing at main gate with ~ 53,12-4 (TP IV 169; cf. *khādira-daṇḍa* in vs 21)

lāja, see: grain

lake with golden lotuses in Himālaya 25,244 (TP II 209); ~ with liquid lac to equal blood 30,46 (TP III 67); ~ poisoned 37,84 (TP III 189); beryl-coloured⁸⁸³ ~ in *pātāla* 45,130f. (TP IV 26); ~ washing away transgression (*pāpa-hara*) 56,121 (TP IV 228); ~ resembled to Mahābhārata 100,14 (TP VII 129); minister advises king to have ~ for golden *haṃsas* made 114,33 (TP VIII 134); magic ~, transparent, deep and broad like the heart of great men, looking like a material representation of *nirvāṇa* 120,116 (TP IX 9); – see also: *yauvana-dvir-ada*

lakṣaṇa, see: mark(s); sign

Lakṣmī (goddess of beauty and fortune)⁸⁸⁴ 33,8 (TP III 107); ~ as wish-granting creeper

⁸⁸¹ See Gonda 1985: 29ff. and 97ff.

⁸⁸² Cf. Kādambarī (Bombay, 1948) 84,8; STh F 52.

⁸⁸³ This means “crystal-coloured, clear”. Beryl ~ Skt. *vaidūrya*. See Buddruss 1980; Rayanaparikkhā 94 (Sarma 1984: 67f.).

encircling Viṣṇu 54,29 (TP IV 186); ~ worshipped daily with 108 white lotus by king to get son 69,78 (TP VI 14); ~ emerges from sea 86,48 (TP VII 16); rivalry (*vaira*) between ~ and Sarasvatī laid aside in town of Viśālā 104,23 (TP VIII 23); ~ in visible form accompanies consecration water 110,79 (TP VIII 87); ~ appears with lotus in hand and elephant with four tusks 113,91 (TP VIII 130); – see also: (goddess of) fortune; Kamalā *lamba-stanī* ‘with pendulous breasts’ (mark of ugliness) 20,109 (TP II 104)

lament(s),⁸⁸⁵ of brahmin whose wife has been abducted by *vidyādhara* 87,17 (TP VII 30); – see also: *cakrāhva*; call for help; daughter, *hā hā*;

lamp, basket in river with ~ on top 15,38 (TP II 4); sun as ~ of the world (*jagad-dīpa*) 66,166 (TP V 190) and 74,108 (TP VI 147); magician honours corpse with ~s fed by oil from the human body 73,306 (TP VI 123); – see also: oil

lamp-black (*kajjala*), four suitors smeared with ~ and put in trunk 4,53ff. (TP I 34); one side of bawd smeared with ~, the other with vermilion 12,169 (TP I 146); lights in lying-in-chamber seem to heave sighs by discharging ~ 43,149 (TP III 291)

landscape,⁸⁸⁶ see: forest; lake, etc.

language(s), not used by Guṇādhya: Sanskrit, Prakrit and his native dialect 5,129 (TP I 58) and 6,2 (TP I 60); Paiśāca ~ is barbarous (*dhik-Paiśāca-kathā*) 8,15 (TP I 90); Kārttikeya pleased with cursed king’s well-turned ~ 55,177 (TP IV 214)

language of animals: ~ of birds 3,32 (TP I 21) and 26,28 (TP II 219)⁸⁸⁷; superintendent knowing ~ of elephants (*hasti-rūtābhijña*) 13,17 (TP I 151); ~ *mṛga-pakṣiṇām* known by *vaiśya* 52,102 (TP IV 145) and 83,26 (TP VII 3); *haṃsa* telling Nala of its describing him to Damayantī 56,250 (TP IV 237); parrot knowing all *śāstras* 59,159 (TP V 37); *vaiśya* claiming to know ~ 83,26 (TP VII 3); ~ of birds known by five coeval ministers 101,49 (TP VII 137); pseudo-ascetic pretends to understand ~ of animals (*ruta-jña*) 121,163 (TP IX 23); – see also: brown cow; overhearing; speech; voice

language of demons (*bhūta-bhāṣā*: Paiśāci) 8,30 (TP I 91);

language of gestures: hand with five fingers pressed together 5,8 (TP I 45); friend knowing ~ (*iṅgita-jña*) 10,93 (TP I 112)

language of signs used by female lover; robbers, see: sign

Laṅkā made of wood, explanation of ~ 12,136 (TP I 143); built on branch of celestial *kalpa-taru* 12,144 (TP I 144); ~ in jewels 12,194 (TP 149)

lap (*utsaṅga*) 22,107 (TP II 145); *vidyādhari* carries mortal in ~ through the air 37,194 (TP III 197)⁸⁸⁸; lover asleep in ~ (*aṅka-supta*) of *vidyādhari* carried through the air 37,225 (TP III 198); 51,82 (TP IV 127); woman falling on king’s ~ 52,354 (TP IV 162); 52,398 (TP IV 166); king on ~ of beauties takes betel 55,40 (TP IV 205); 120,100 (TP IX 8)

⁸⁸⁴ Cf. ORC 1594.

⁸⁸⁵ See Banerji 1985.

⁸⁸⁶ See ORC 1624 s.v. *paysages*.

⁸⁸⁷ STh B 215ff. See also Kuv 260.14-267.18 and ORC 1618f. s.v. Oiseaux.

⁸⁸⁸ See Quintanilla 2007 Fig. 234f.

lapis lazuli (*rājāvarta*), floor dark with ~ stone 73,339 (TP VI 125); – see also: mosaic
lāsikī ‘nautch-girl’, see: wave
 lasso (*pāśa*), king made prisoner with a ~ 54,223 and 229 (TP IV 199f.)
latā-lāśya (not MW) ‘dance of creepers’ 35,5 (TP III 155)
 Lāṭa in western region 19,103f. (TP II 93); ~ seat of fine arts (*citṛōjjvala-sthiti*) 74,139 (TP VI 150);
 lattice-window, see: *jāla-gavākṣa*; window
 laugh, laugh-and-cry motif 88,43 (TP VII 38); 124,135f. (TP IX 78)⁸⁸⁹; see further: laughing
 laughing,⁸⁹⁰ dead fish ~ 5,16 (TP I 46)⁸⁹¹; brahmin guest greeted with ~ 7,46 (TP I 78); people
 ~ at naked bawd on pillar 12,186 (TP I 148); Purūravas ~ at Rambhā dancing *calita* 17,20
 (TP II 35); ~ at four seducer-merchants with dog’s foot mark 13,190ff. (TP I 164); pupils ~
 at ascetic’s nose and ears being torn off by furious monkey 15,51 (TP II 5); royal court ~ at
 brahmin repeating same words 20,43 (TP II 98); of king ~ at foolish brahmin 24,196 (TP
 II 183); brahmin boy’s ~ at goblins on charnel ground 25,97 (TP II 197); ~ (*sōpahāsayā*)
 at old man 31,42 (TP III 85); ~ (*vihasya*) at *vidyādhara* king 34,221 (TP III 145);
 attendants ~ in their sleeves (*sāntar-hāsāt*) at *rākṣasa* king’s stupid question whether he is
 dead or not 39,184 (TP III 231); Maya ~ at Nārada 45,20 (TP IV 18); angry ~, of Indra
 45,391 (TP IV 43); Prahlāda laughs when Sūryaprabha admits improper action 46,20 (TP
 IV 50); ~ at haughty behaviour 46,168 (TP IV 60); Dānavas ~ at gods to scorn 50,20 (TP
 IV 109); “with the loud laugh” as epitheton of Cāmuṇḍā 52,159 (TP IV 149); king laughs
 at shrewd servant 54,159 (TP IV 195); people ~ at king for coming without reason 56,389
 (TP IV 248); Bhīma ~ to himself (*hṛdī*) 56,414 (TP IV 250) and 60,240 (TP V 62); town
 people ~ at bawd and courtesan’s grief over lost wealth 57,171 (TP V 13); ~ out of
 sorrow⁸⁹² for a parrot 59,56 (TP V 30); hermit ~ at parrot’s knowing all *śāstras* 59,159 (TP
 V 37); ~ at fool burning aloes-wood to charcoal 61,6 (TP V 67); ~ at bald man pelted
 with wood-apples 61,54 (TP V 73); ministers ~ in their sleeves (*antarhasantas*) at foolish
 king 61,218 (TP V 86); even stones (*pāṣāṇa*) ~ at fool 61,246 (TP V 89); public ~ at
 indiscreet people (*niṣprajñās ... lokōpahāsītāḥ*) 62,169 (TP V 113); *yakṣa* ~ at story told
 by his wife 66,27 (TP V 180); stones ~ at wife of eleven dead husbands 66,97 (TP V
 185); miser’s speech makes even stones (*grāvṇaḥ*) laugh 63,162 (TP V 133); people ~ at
 man who looks at his friend’s finger instead of the new moon 64,33 (TP V 241); king ~ at
 adulterous wife carrying maimed man 65,34 (TP V 156); brahmin ~ at people who take
 boy for cat 65,174 (TP V 168); mountain is like ~ with snow 73,159 (TP VI 112f. with
 note 1: smile regarded as white)⁸⁹³; ~ at ignorance 75,19 (TP VI 165); ~ corpse with
vetāla 78,2 (TP VII 191); robber weeping and ~ 88,43 (TP VII 38)⁸⁹⁴; Mūladeva ~ at

⁸⁸⁹ STh *F 1041.11.

⁸⁹⁰ Cf. Chojnacki 2008 (I): 361 s.v. *rire*: Siegel 1987.

⁸⁹¹ STh *D 1318.2.1.

⁸⁹² For the reasons of laughing see ORC 1634 s.v. *rire*. The passage is missing in Siegel 1987.

⁸⁹³ See Kuv note 2087 where the white autumnal flower *kāśa* represents laughing.

brahmin's request for help to get beloved princess 89,24 (TP VII 41); ~ boy as human sacrifice 94,125 (TP VII 96); boy laughs at object accomplished and delusion of those who ought to have protected him 94,136 (TP VII 96); ~ at women without self-restraint 95,38 (TP VII 100); white *kumuda* cluster ~ with the cheerful faces of its opened flowers (*utphulla-vadana*) 95,68 (TP VII 102); Devī curses ~ *gaṇas* to become poor brahmins ..., bob-tailed dogs and birds 114,67f. (TP VIII 137); maiden's limbs, white with sandalwood juice, seem ~ly to say ... 117,108 (TP VIII 171)⁸⁹⁵; pseudo-ascetic ~ at yell of she-jackal 121,161 (TP IX 23); Indra ~ at trick (*māyā*) of gambler 121,186 (TP IX 25); *śakuna-devatā* laughs at foolish traveller who welcomes evil omen 124,109 (TP IX 76); boy ~ at Mūladeva and Śaśin who did not understand his crying in front of a rice-pudding (*paramāṇna*) 124,135f. (TP IX 78); – see also: gesture(s); *loka-hāsyatā*; mountain; stones laughter by king's court at three fickle nobles smeared with soot 4,82 (TP I 36); ~ at question of *rākṣasa* 5,51 (TP I 51); ~ at naked bawd falling from pillar 12,186 (TP I 148); ~ of pupils at false ascetic with nose and ears removed by monkey 15,51 (TP II 5); ~ at king causes laughter's fool⁸⁹⁶ cut off 18,37 (TP II 52); ~ at brahmin repeating words of evening oblation 20,43 (TP II 98); ~ of king' court at duped greedy brahmin 24,196 (TP II 183); ~ at fraudulent brahmin 24,74 (TP II 175); ~ of daughter at silly father 39,183 (TP III 231); *rākṣasa* king is afraid of ~ of people (*loka-hāsa*) 39,193 (TP III 232); ~ at witty remark 40,10 (TP III 240); Indra's angry ~ 45,391 (TP IV 43); *vidyādhara*s' ~ at Sūryaprabha 46,76 (TP IV 54); ~ at furious answer of emperor of *Vidyādhara*s 46,83 (TP IV 54); virtuous woman laughs at angry hermit 56,175 (TP IV 232); ~ at fool who purifies his cotton in fire and burns it 61,31 (TP V 70); ~ at a fool turning vessel upside down to look at leak in the bottom 61,191f. (TP V 84); ~ for ignorance 62,171 (TP V 113) and 207 (TP V 117); ~ at fool 62,224 (TP V 118); two pupils laughed to scorn (*dveṣyōpahāsyau śiṣyau*) 63,173 (TP V 134); people's ~ (*loka-hāsa*) at fool with mouthful of uncooked rice 63,186 (TP V 136); mother-in-law being laughed at by family because of her deceit 74,176 (TP VI 153); ~ of brahmin boy about to be sacrificed to *brahmarākṣasa* 94,124 (TP VII 96); handfuls of parched grain (*lāja*) bride throws into fire compared to ~ of Kāma Manobhū 103,193 (TP VII 188); ~ at man tricked by bawd 108,87 (TP VIII 60); ~ (*parihāsa*) at king by royal ladies 108,158 (TP VIII 65); ~ of sky with falling rain of flowers at birth of child 120,48 (TP IX 4); – see also: cotton; fool

lavaṅga 'clove(-tree), *Syzygium aromaticum*'⁸⁹⁷ 111,15 (TP VIII 96)

lāvanya 'charm, grace, loveliness'⁸⁹⁸, see: beauty

⁸⁹⁴ See Siegel 1987: 48f.

⁸⁹⁵ See Baldissera 2004: 83.

⁸⁹⁶ For the foot as pars pro toto and representing the person see Bollée 2008: 72ff.

⁸⁹⁷ Macmillan 1991: 378f.: "a small conical tree, 8-10 m high".

⁸⁹⁸ According to Jackmuth 2002: 37 *lāvanya* does not pertain solely to the complexion of women, as Kale had argued, but to the regular and charming growth of the members of the body in comparison to the regular growth of the moon.

- lāvanya-jala-dhi* (not MW) ‘sea of beauty’, Śrī emerges from ~ 14,68 (TP I 187)
- lāvanya-nirjhara* (not MW) ‘torrent of beauty’, *divyâkṛtiḥ kanyā* fills tank with ~ 75,68 (TP VI 169)
- law of death, see: mortal(s); ~ of the jungle, see: ichthyonomy
- lead, see: red lead; vermilion
- learning, Valabhī, city of ~ (*vidyā*) 32,43 (TP III 93)
- leaves, loin-cincture of bilva ~ worn by Śabara 101,355 (TP VII 158); betel ~ 104,46 (TP VIII 4), – cutting ~ see: make-up
- leaving family secretly (*a-vidita*) to seek wife 123,158 (TP IX 54); 123,294 (TP IX 64); ~ without telling (*an-āvedya*) followers by night 124,64 (TP IX 73); ~ without telling parents 124,107 (TP IX 76); – see also: king; night
- left, empress sits on ~ side of emperor at coronation 110,76 (TP VIII 87)
- left hand, unguarded spot in ~ of Daitya 11,65 (TP I 127)⁸⁹⁹; angry *apsaras*, looking at husband askance with wrinkled brows, retains (*nivārya*) him with ~ 17,128 (TP II 44); *rākṣasa* extending ~ 18,330 (TP II 74); seizing lion with ~ by a foot 52,128 (TP IV 147); angry queen supports downcast face on palm of ~ 55,124 (TP IV 210); woman-fastidious (*nārī-caṅga*) brahmin stops his nose with ~ in order not to perceive lady’s goat smell 82,31 (TP VI 218); queens sit at ~ of emperor 111,16 (TP VIII 96); sign (*saṃjñā*) with ~ to wait 112,55 (TP VIII 110); – see also: Achilles’ heel
- leg of giant, when stopping ship, cut off 18,304 (TP II 72)⁹⁰⁰; ~ used as hero’s float in ocean 18,310 (TP II 73)⁹⁰¹; Naravāhanadatta seizing ~s (*grhītvâṅghri-yuge*) of Gaurīmuṇḍa whirls him round and dashes him to pieces on a rock 108,112 (TP VIII 62); *vetāla* seizes *kāpālika* by the ~s and dashes him on the earth 121,27 (TP IX 14)
- lekha-hāra(ka)*, see: messenger
- leper⁹⁰² with evil smell calling himself God of Love 64,132 (TP V 149); lonely wife locked up in *bhū-grha* by jealous husband loves ~ 64,135 (TP V 149); – see also: *bhū-grha*
- lesbianism (?): heavenly females associate with mortal ones led by excessive love (*divyā yānti mānuṣībhīr a-sama-snehâhṛtāḥ*) 28,191 (TP III 36); princess diverts herself by marrying her maidens to one another 122,52 (TP IX 37); – see also: Mbh XIII 38,22
- letter of death motif 5,65 (TP I 52)⁹⁰³; 42,88 (TP III 265 and note at 277ff.);
- letter, hand-written ~ of princess (*lekhaṃ sva-hasta-likhitam*) to her father as certificate of life 43,263 (TP III 299); diplomatic ~ of king read out in durbar 44,158 (TP IV 11); do, 74,266f. (TP VI 159); do, about date of marriage committed to messenger 101,121f. (TP VII 142); do, after seal broken (*mudrâkṣepa-prasārīta*) 102,134 (TP VII 172); ~ brought by

⁸⁹⁹ STh T 91.1.

⁹⁰⁰ STh F 531.3.1.2.

⁹⁰¹ Cf. Rājat 3,345ff.

⁹⁰² For Hemacandra’s idea about leprosy see his *Triṣaṣṭī* 10,9,95ff. See also Bollée 2010: 25 notes 111f., Crooke 1972: 305f.

⁹⁰³ STh *K 978 and 1355.

lekha-hastah pumān proves people living 123,330f. (TP IX 66); after eleven years wife sends Rājput husband abroad letter (*ullekha-patirikā*) with *āryā* 124,56 (TP IX 72); disguised wife gives ignorant husband forged ~ (*kūṭa-lekha*) 124,197 (TP IX 82); – see further: letter of death

letter-carrier (*lekha-hāra*), *rākṣasī* disguising as ~ to escape father 39,186 (TP III 231); ~ (*lekha-hāraka*) arrives just before afflicted royal couple wants to enter the fire in front of Śiva temple 101,352 (TP VII 158); Śabara messenger as ~ has his hair tied up in a knot behind with a creeper, is black and wearing a loin-cloth (*kaṭī-nivasana*) of vilva leaves 101,355 (TP VII 158); ~ recompensed (*sat-kṛtya*) 101,360 (TP VII 159); – see also: *lekha-hāra*; messenger

libation at *śrāddha* to in-laws, king gives ~ 111,59 (TP VIII 101)

liberalism, religious ~ of Buddhist kings 72,99 (TP VI 76)

liberality (*tyāga*), see: generosity

liberation, see: emancipation

lie, king healed by ~ that queen had died 17,41 (TP II 37); Jimūtavāhana says to Garuḍa that he is a snake: *nāga evāsmi* 22,234 (TP II 154)⁹⁰⁴; *rākṣasī* speaks falsely (*alika-vādinī*) 25,203 (TP II 206); 71,143 (TP VI 46); 97,37 (TP VII 114); – see also: false information; Pāśupata; physician;

liebestod of righteous king 33,73 (TP III 112); ~ of hermit's son 59,109 (TP V 33)

life, brahmin gives half of his ~ to revive bride bitten by snake 14,80 (TP I 188)⁹⁰⁵; ~ is highest wealth 22,27 (TP II 139); three objects of ~ (*tri-varga*) 24,152 (TP II 180); hermit Ruru gives Menakā half of his ~ 28,88 (TP III 26); princess reanimates fisherman lover with half her ~ 112,142 (TP VIII 117); happy ~ like Indra with Śacī 27,58 (TP III 5); water of ~ (*amṛta-rasa*) 29,57 (TP III 43); *kiṃ jīvitena* ~ is worthless without a certain wife 30,5 (TP III 64); Uṣā remains with loved man as ~ in visible form (*jīvitena mūrtena*) 31,30 (TP III 83); wife loved as one's ~ 35,3 (TP III 155); ~ considered as stubble (*tṛṇi-kṛta-jīvita*) 38,121 (TP III 214); all ~ ends in death according to Vyāsa⁹⁰⁶ 51,27 (TP IV 124); queen dearer than ~ (*prāṇādhikā*) to king 55,105 (TP IV 209) and *jīvitādhikā* 197 (TP IV 216); spirits (*prāṇāḥ*) given up at rising moon because of separation from beloved 59,109 (TP V 33); ~ is without purpose if without good husband 65,229 (TP V 172); Bodhisattva gives ~ for others 72,147 (TP VI 79); brahmin revives boy from ashes by means of charmed dust 76,22 (TP VI 180); brahmin boy offers himself to save the king's ~ 94,100ff. (TP VII 94); Daitya princess feels as if ~ be in her throat (*prāṇāḥ kaṇṭhāgatāḥ*) 112,46 (TP VIII 109); what is the sense of my ~ ? (*jīvitena kiṃ ?*) 112,83 (TP VIII 112); which enjoyments are there in ~ of man which involve separation from

⁹⁰⁴ TP mentions a remark of Dr Brockhaus that *nāga* can also mean “mountaineer” which makes no sense at all here. As the story is Buddhist, Pali & Prakrit *nāga* < *nāyaka* ‘chief, lord, etc.’, fitting Jimūtavāhana, may be taken account of.

⁹⁰⁵ STh *E 165.

⁹⁰⁶ See ORC 1419 note 3 ad p. 547 with ref. to Mbh XI 2,3, etc.

friends hard to bear, and the ... other ills of humanity ? 120,31 (TP IX 3); golden toy-deer (*krīḍā-hariṇa*) possessed of ~ and dancing before two female beauties 120,107 (TP IX 9); parents love foolish son as their ~ (*pitroḥ prāṇa-samo mūrkhah*) 124,104 (TP IX 75); – for: “danger of ~” see: *jīvita-saṃśaya*

life-prolonging charm (*kāla-saṃkarṣiṇī vidyā*) with initiatory rites (*dikṣā-pūrvam*) 68,65 (TP VI 6 with reference to Śaṅkara-*digvijaya* 7,55)⁹⁰⁷; – see also: *siddha-rasāyana*

light radiated by new-born⁹⁰⁸ 23,66 (TP II 161); ~ in lying-in chamber kept burning to protect child 28,4 (TP III 18); 34,48 (TP III 131); 35,112 (TP III 164, see infra: lying-in chamber); ~ radiating from brahmin Kāla’s head sets fire to the three worlds 45,84 (TP IV 23); ~ by *divyā kanyā* at night in wood 68,6-8 (TP VI 1); *vidyādhari* with radiating body like the ~ of the sun 69,169 (TP VI 21); Nārada descends from heaven in aura of ~ 105,82 (TP VIII 27); queen bears boy resembling the sun 118,38 (TP VIII 180); new-born prince radiates chamber like sun does heaven 120,48 (TP IX 4);

lightning brilliant during rain 12,41 (TP I 136); banner like ~ 18,50 (TP II 53); king possesses queen like cloud holds ~ 24,20 (TP II 171); ~ compared to lolling tongue of a *rākṣasa*-like thundercloud 25,41 (TP II 192)⁹⁰⁹; women are fickle like ~ 37,143 (TP III 193); ~ garland 44,179 (TP IV 13); ~ compared to flashing eyes (*jvalad-vidyud-vilocana*)⁹¹⁰ of cloud of doom 52.323 (TP IV 160); who can arrest ~ ? 63,46 (TP V 123); transient as a flash of ~ 66,33 (TP V 180); lion’s claws in a dream like ~ 69,23 (TP VI 10); ~ as autumn’s sword 78,23 (TP VI 192); hair like ~ 94,68 (TP VII 91); ~ striking royal banners as evil omen 116,3 (TP VIII 156); – see also: cloud; rumour; thunderbolt

lilā-vajra, scratching the earth with the handle of a ~ symbol in his hands (*hasta-sthayā ~ muṣṭyā khaṇan kṣitim*) 35,42 (TP III 158; ORC 355: “*creusant la terre à l’aide de l’objet semblable à un foudre qu’il tenait dans sa main*”; M I 499: “*Dort grub er zum puren Zeitvertreib mit dem Griff eines wie ein Donnerkeil aussehenden Werkzeugs die Erde auf*”).⁹¹¹

⁹⁰⁷ <http://ia700503.us.archive.org/27/items/Shankara.Digvijaya.Satika/Shankara.Digvijaya.Satika.pdf> (p.c.Ven. Svāmi Baneśānanda) and Poona 1915 (courtesy of A. Pohlus M.A.). The seventh chapter describes the meeting of Śaṅkara and Vyāsa who by Śiva’s blessing bestows on the former the boon of an extension of his life’s span by sixteen years, but no mantra is given.

⁹⁰⁸ At birth future heroes emit light: the idea of radiating babies at birth may stem from the shining dawn for which see Roesler 1997: 85f.

⁹⁰⁹ Cf. Gonda 1965: 325 < Kauś 66,19 § 3; Rām 7,23,1,74.

⁹¹⁰ STh F 541.1.2.

⁹¹¹ Fezas in ORC 1395 asks: “*une sorte d’arme de poing ?*” which cannot be correct because the subject, a high military official (33 *jayī yuddhāika-sevakah*), was waiting to be admitted, perhaps unarmed, to the king. As *vajra* is a weapon only of gods and heroes, a *lilā-vajra* may be a sports weapon like a *lilā-padma* dignitaries carry playfully in the hand. This can easily become an emblem of rank or dignity such as the marshall’s baton Hermann Göring carried in his left; Vajrapāṇi uses his *vajra* in order to help at the conversion of stubborn people (Zin 2009: 77ff.; p.c. Schlingloff). Like a prefix indicating that the word it is compounded with, c.q. –*vajra*, *lilā* and its synonyms *keli-*, *vilāsa-*, etc., as Slaje (p.c.) points out, do not have their full and originally intended force, but a diminished, qualified or modified one such as for play or leisure; it is not real weapon but only a symbol: just as the pharao’s crook (*hq3*) is emblematic of his power and the gold and silver staffs of old harem attendants of their rank (as in Kād 197,1), the

lilā-vāpī ‘pleasure tank’, queen has *dohada* of bathing in ~ 9,46 (TP I 97)

lilōdyāna-bhū ‘pleasure ground’ of goddess Śrī: city of Vidiśā 71,72 (TP VI 41)

limbs, see: body

lines, drawing ~ on the ground, see: drawing lines

liṅga, ~ as flame (*javālā-liṅga*) of Śiva 1,28 (TP I 4); obscene cake made in ~ form (*piṣṭa-racitaṃ guhya-rūpaṃ jugupsitaṃ*) 2,56 (TP I 13)⁹¹²; ~ played with by Sītā’s sons 51,95 (TP IV 128); *yakṣa* gives boon of ~ to eunuch 56,97 (TP IV 226); *divya-kanyakā* singing before ~ 59,81 (TP V 32); ~ made of sand (*śikatā-Śiva-liṅga*) and maiden in forest garb (*vana-veṣa*) worshipping it 67,65f. (TP V 200); ~ exhibits all Hara’s forms in succession 115,115 (TP VIII 152); Hara Śiva speaks from ~⁹¹³ 115,122 (TP VIII 152); ~ composed of celestial gems, arising from lake and worshipped by beautiful lady with lyre and singing with rapt devotion (*avadhānena*) southern style notes, time and words (*ālambya dakṣiṇaṃ mārgaṃ svara-tāla-padais*) 120,119ff. (TP IX 10)⁹¹⁴; ~ made of *tārṣya-ratna* near which *divya-rūpā vara-striyaḥ* dance with fourfold musical instruments (*vādya*) 123,132 (TP IX 52)

liṅga-tyāga [not MW] ‘giving up one’s genitals’, of a *yakṣa* 56,102 (TP IV 226)

lion, bear terrified by ~ ascends tree 5,81 (TP I 53); boy riding on ~ (ex-*yakṣa*) becomes son of childless king 6,92ff. (TP I 67); ~ becomes man at end of curse 6,96 and 10,47 (TP I 68 and 109) and 22,134 (TP II 147); hero overcomes ~ = *yakṣa* in wrestling and obtains magic sword out of gratitude for ending curse 10,47 (TP I 109); Vindhya hills haunted by ~s 18,96 (TP II 56); maiden riding on ~ 22,79 (TP II 143); ~ of spring (*madhu-kesarī*) tearing to pieces the elephant of female disdain 55,107 (TP IV 209); ~ about to kill king is cut in two by *vidyādhara* 55,204 (TP IV 216); out of fear ~ retires without drinking 60,23 (TP V 43); ~ attacks elephant⁹¹⁵ 60,36 (TP V 44); ~ to eat hare 60,95 (TP V 49 with note); ~ sees his reflection in well, jumps down and is drowned 60,104 (TP V 50); ~ kills and eats camel 60,160 (TP V 54); auto-biography of ~ 65,57ff. (TP V 159f.); sick ~ with jackal as minister 63,125 (TP V 129); ~ with articulate speech and recollection of pre-births 65,56 (TP V 158); ~ puts out tongue at a person in dream (*rasanāṃ mayi āsīd*) and then becomes deformed giant 69,25f. (TP VI 10f.); ~ with ten arms 70,100 (TP VI 31); ~s in reed (*śara*) kill horses 74,97 (TP VI 147); jackal apes ~ (*siṃhāyate*) 74,270 (TP VI 159); ~ of summer with sun as mouth 87,29 (TP VI 31); ~ of spring (*madhu-kesarin*) slaying elephant of winter 91,21 (TP VII 67); four poor brahmins magically create ~ and are killed

lilā-vajra reminds of Indra (cf. Gonda 1975: IV 165). The word seems to be a ἄπαξ λεγόμενον in classical Sanskrit, but occurs in tantric Buddhism for the Absolute, indistructable, and as proper name of teachers. – I regret not having received a reply from the Sanskrit Dictionary in Pune. – See also the note infra on magic staff.

⁹¹² For the use of breads and pastries in the shape of human genitals see also HdA 3: 373ff. s.v. Gebildbrote.

⁹¹³ Perhaps in the shape of a *mukha-liṅga*, for which see, e.g., Liebert 1976: 183.

⁹¹⁴ This passage may illustrate Joseph Campbell’s statement that images are not representations of things but tools for psychic transformation (Osbon 1991: 275). The musician’s performance was splendid so that even *siddhas* etc. were attracted and remained motionless as if painted (vs 122).

⁹¹⁵ Such a scene is pictured e.g. in Snead et al. 1989: 110 plate 79.

- by it 96,41 (TP VII 111);
lion of spring, see: spring
lip(s), queen with trembling ~ in muttering charms (*japa-prasphuritâdharā*) 20,50 (TP II 98);
princess with ~ lovely as the *bandhūka* ‘Pentapetes phoenicea’⁹¹⁶ tree (MW) (*bandhūka-*
manīyāuṣṭhī) 34,231 (TP III 146); ~ of enraged *vidyādhariṣ* trembling 44,53 (TP IV 5);
finger of sun adorns ~ of night 103,215 (TP VII 190)
liquor, see: wine
literacy, see: letter
litter, see: *karṇī-ratha*; palanquin
loca ‘eye’, see: *loka-loca*
locanānanda ‘gladdener of the eyes’: Naravāhanadatta 34,102 (TP III 136)
lock, Buddhists reject brahminical ~ 27,19 (TP III 2); division / separation (TP: “defeat”; only)
of (lit.: in) the curled ~s of women (*bhaṅgo* ‘lakeṣu *nārīṇām*’) 55,26 (TP IV 204; ORC 610:
in Kanakapura “*on n’y séparait que les mèches de cheveux des femmes*”; MI 855: “*Die*
einzigsten Niederungen für die Männer lagen in den Locken der Frauen”)⁹¹⁷; – see also:
eka-venī; hair(-style)
locust (*śalabha*), showers of arrows descend on warriors like ~ on the tender herb 103,5 (TP
VII 175)
Lohajaṅgha disguised as Hari-Viṣṇu on Garuḍa 12,144 (TP I 144f.)
loin(s), see: hip
loin-cincture (or ~ cloth) of bilva leaves worn by dark Śabara messenger 101,355 (TP VII
158); Bhilla women wear peacock-tail skirts 123,50 (TP IX 46)
-*loka* as indicator of plural in *rāja-loka* = *rājānaḥ* 18,26 (TP II 51 “the chiefs”)
loka-hāsana (not MW), see: laughter
loka-hāsyatā ‘laughing-stock to everybody’, man burning aloes-wood to charcoal is ~ 61,6 (TP
V 67), cf. 61,192 (TP V 84)
lokāika-sundarī ‘unique beauty of men, miss world’ 73,251 (TP VI 119); deserted wife
enters Ujjaiyinī dressed as ~ courtesan 124,173 (TP IX 80); – see also: attractivity
stereotype; beauty; courtesan; miss universe; sylph; *trailokya-sundarī*
loka-locana-candrikā ‘moon for the eyes of men’ (said of a princess) 24,22 (TP II 171)
lokānukampin (not MW) ‘full of compassion for men’ said of Jīmūtavāhana 22,25 (TP II
139)
loka-pālas,⁹¹⁸ three ~ called as witnesses 52,52 (TP IV 141); five (!) ~ (Indra, Vāyu, Agni,
Yama and Varuṇa) appear at Damayantī’s *svayamvara*⁹¹⁹ 56,259 and 272 (TP IV 238f.); ~
(in fact: the moon)⁹²⁰ addressed by *pati-vratā* 63,65 (TP V 124); king asks ~ advice 112,135

⁹¹⁶ Syed 1990: 455 with other places.

⁹¹⁷ Cf. 74,242 (TP VI 158) where dishevelled curls or locks (*lulitāḥlaka-keśānta*) are a sign of sex ?

⁹¹⁸ See TP VIII 163 note 1.

⁹¹⁹ In her review of Wessels-Mevissen 2001, Zin 2003a: 503 prompts to study such references in the narrative literature where the gods of the directions appear as a group.

- (TP VIII 116); Indra honours ~ 116,88 (TP VIII 163); – see also: cardinal points; *dig-devatā*; *dik-pāla*; directions;
- loka-loca* (not MW) ‘eyes of the world, of men’ 106,50 (TP VIII 32)
- loka-vāda*, see: rumour
- loka-yātrā* ‘the way of the world’ 6,52 and 60 (TP I 64f.)
- lone son, widow with ~ 6,29ff. (TP I 62); 106,94 (TP VIII 35)
- lone woman 10,71 (TP I 11); ~ abducted in forest 10,131 (TP I 115); ~ attacked by elephant 27,170 (TP III 14); ~ 29,155 (TP III 51); ~ 33,2 (TP III 107); grief of princess at being alone, left by husband in the night 56,199ff. (TP IV 234); Damayantī as ~ 56,325 (TP IV 243); 64,135 (TP V 149); sun stretches out his hand with rays to wipe off tears of lonely princess 71,193 (TP VI 49f.); ~ *vidyādhara* princess feels melancholic, rises up out of the sea and sings of the decrees of fate (*bhavitavyatā*) on a movable wishing tree (*yantra-kalpa-druma*) 86,108 (TP VII 21); king curses daughter to stay ~ (*ekākinī*) 86,139 (TP VII 23); royal couple has only one daughter 98,7 (TP VII 116); – see also: doe; elephant; grief; melancholy; night
- loneliness, see: depression; lone woman; *śūnya-vasati*
- longing, see: pregnancy whim
- long journey, going on the ~ (*mahā-patha*) = to die 2,43 (TP I 12); 30,59 (TP III 68); 61,242 (TP V 88); – see also: *mahā-patha*
- look(s)⁹²¹ of Pārvatī as nooses formed by Kāma (Manobhū) around Śambhu’s neck 1,1 (TP I 1); king struck by ~ of merchant sylph as if she were a female snake (*bhujangī*) 33,65 (TP III 111 “poisonous look”; ORC 324: “voir cette femme pareille à une femelle de serpent fut un poison qui frappa le monarque”) ⁹²²; by angry ~ of hermit ⁹²³ hen-crow is burned to ashes (*kruddho dadarśa tām ... dṛṣṭa-mātrāiva sā tena balākā bhasmasād abhūt*) 56,171f. (TP IV 232); *satī* with angry ~ burns tree 63,41 (TP V 123); ~ (*dṛṣṭi*) of king heals eye-disease of *vetāla* Bhūtaketu 123,34 (TP IX 45); – see also: *dṛg-viṣāhi*; evil eye; Kāma; sidelong glance
- looking, angry wife ~ askance with wrinkled brows (*sācī-kṛta-dṛśā mukhena valita-bhruṇā*) to husband 17,128 (TP II 44); ~ up to the sun as austerity 24,95 (TP II 176 with ref. to I 79 note); ~ back forbidden in Piśāca rite 28,166 (TP III 33)⁹²⁴; beholding someone as the bed of lotus beholds the sun’s splendour 34,101 (TP III 136); ~ back ordered to see (*prṣṭhato vikṣitavyam*) and stop pursuer 39,133 (TP III 227); Śrī conceives son from ascetic abstinent from sex by just ~ at him (*tvad-darśanān mamôṭpannaḥ putraḥ*) 59,95f. (TP V 33); princess in love when returning to palace is often ~ back at her brahmin deliverer from

⁹²⁰ For the connection woman : moon see Varenne 1962: 253.

⁹²¹ See e.g., Michaels 2004: 230ff.

⁹²² Gonda 1969a: 25f.

⁹²³ “The look may, *inter alia*, direct a magic or ritual act ..., transfer will-power ... or co-ordinate mind or intention and action” (Gonda 1965: 237 referring to Seligmann 1922: 453 ?). See also Gonda 1969a: 17.

⁹²⁴ On looking back being forbidden see STh C 331; Crooke 1896: II 57; HdA 8: 1346ff.

frenzy elephant 89,18 (TP VII 41); *caṇḍāla* beauty stops wild elephant with sidelong looks askance (*kuṭilaiḥ kaṭākṣaiḥ*) 112,68 (TP VIII 111); Rudra, etc. ~ at battle of gods and *Asuras* 115,26 (TP VIII 146); *Gandharva* ~ meaningly at the face of the Disposer (*Dhātuḥ sākūtaṃ mukham aikṣata*) 116,85 (TP VIII 162); – see also: eye; head; love; turning back

lotus⁹²⁵, sylph with eyes like blue ~ (*nīla-nīraja*) 4,6 (TP I 30); ~ (*ambu-ja*) opened by boy = Kārttikeya (*Kumāra*) in dream 6,138 (TP I 71); man and wife united like bed of white lotuses with night (*rātryēva kumudākaraḥ*) 10,181 (TP I 119); red ~ (*raktāmbuja*) as chastity index given by Śiva to couple in dream 13,79 (TP I 156)⁹²⁶; faces of curious women on their palaces fill heaven as golden ~ blooming (*hemāmbu-ruha*) in heavenly Ganges 14,19 (TP I 183); queen's body is fragrant as that of the dark ~ (*nīlōtpala*) [q. v.] 16,28 (TP II 22); woman, separated from husband, remains pale like ~ (*padminī*) in the night 16,45 (TP II 25); garlands of eyes resembling blue ~ (*locanēndīvara-srajaḥ*) 18,23 (TP II 51); ~ welcome hero with hum of bees 18,353 (TP II 76); sun friend of ~ 22,77 (TP II 142); golden ~ (*suvarṇa-kamala* [q. v.]) given as present by *rākṣasī* to brahmin son-in-law 25,212 (TP II 207); golden ~ in silver vessel dedicated in Śiva temple resemble glory of king and might of brahmin hero 25,228 (TP II 208); golden ~ of the sky-lake⁹²⁷ (*dyu-saraḥ-svarṇa-kamala*) = sun 25,236 (TP II 208); lake with golden ~ 25,244 (TP II 209); bracelet and necklace of ~ fibres are no relief of inflammation with love 33,166 (TP III 121); looking at someone as the bed of ~ beholds the sun 34,101 (TP III 135f.); golden ~ in fata morgana 29,58 (TP III 43); bed of ~ trampled by elephant has its cluster of black bees dispersed 33,208 (TP III 124); Hari with ~ on his haunch⁹²⁸ (*padmāṅkitōtsaṅga*) advises hero to kill wicked magician 38,58 (TP III 210); five ~ (*padma-pañcaka*) floating down current of river 40,84 (TP III 246); rain dropping from suspended skeleton produces golden ~ 40,103 (TP III 248); hermit bestows on prince in fire-cavity chariot in form of a white ~ (*mahā-padma-vimāna*) with a hundred and eight wings 46,123 (TP IV 57); *liṅga* worshipped with golden ~ from Kubera's lake 51,97f. (TP IV 129); four heavenly men culling golden ~ 54,15 (TP IV 184); brahmin obtains poison-destroying ~ (*utpalaṃ viṣādi-ghnam*) from Nārāyaṇī 56,115ff. (TP IV 228); lake with fragrant ~ 63,11 (TP V 120); king offers his heart-lotus (*hṛt-padma* [q. v.]) on a sword to Lakṣmī for a son and is healed by the deity 69,80 (TP VI 14); ~ falls on Śiva's *liṅga* 69,153 and causes rebirth of gander in royal family 155 (TP VI 19f.)⁹²⁹; at Śaiva sacrifice a ~ with eight leaves (*sāṣṭa-pallava*) is painted with yellow paint (*go-rocanā*) on front of *vedi* 71,215 (TP VI 51); heavenly ~ of

⁹²⁵ See ORC 1596f.; Syed 1990: 620f.; Rau 1954 (did not use KSS); Schmidt 1913; Pandanus Database of Plants: www.iu.ff.cuni.cz/pandanus/database

⁹²⁶ See Norton 1920: 223. Why do we give flowers to the Gods? (McHugh 2012:219f.).

⁹²⁷ According to Lüders 1951: 156 note 10 this the Ganges river.

⁹²⁸ TP III 210: "with his breast marked with a lotus"; ORC 389: "portant sur sa poitrine la marque du lotus." From the lotus (*padma* 'Nelumbium speciosum' [Syed 1990: 658f.]) Brahmā emerges.

⁹²⁹ BIS 6606 „He who with a six-syllabled mantra puts even a single flower on a *liṅga* will not be reborn.“

crystal (*sphāṭikam divyam ambu-jam*) with a thousand leaves in Mānasa lake 72,37 (TP VI 70); maiden like dark ~ 73,196 (TP VI 115); dark lotuses compared to clouds of smoke from the fire of snake-poison 74,212 (TP VI 155); princess puts ~ in her ear as sign to prince that she lives in Karṇōtpala 75,81 (TP VI 170); ~ falls from queen's ear, produces wound on her thigh and makes her faint 85,11 (TP VII 11); ~ as expanded eyes of lake 101,11 (TP VII 134); human hand (*nr-hasta*) in the shape of a red ~ (*rakta-kamala*) given with alms to brahmin 108,24f. (TP VIII 54); *apsaras* conceals man in her ear~ (*karṇōtpala*) and takes him into Indra's palace to see Rambhā dance 121,128 (TP IX 21); eyes like blue ~ see: eyes; – see further also: red lotus

lotus-bed, trampled by elephant⁹³⁰ has cluster of black bees dispersed 33,208 (TP III 124); assembly of learned men compared to ~ 72,74 (TP IV 74); man burning with the fire of love, is rolling on bed of lotus leaves 95,48 (TP VII 101); angry people appear like ~ smitten by the wind 108,130 (TP VIII 63); – see also: rolling

lotus fibre / stalk (*bisa*) eaten 101,13 (TP VII 135);

louse (*yūkkā*) in king's bed 60,126 killed instead of flea (*matkuṇa*) 133 (TP V 52)

love,⁹³¹ man's heart is cleft by stroke of ~'s arrow 4,8 (TP I 31); falling in ~ (*āhṛta-hṛdaya*) (by mere mention) 11,83 (TP I 128) and 42,25 (TP III 261); unrequited ~ burns king to death 15,79 (TP II 8ff.); ~ on first sight of Urvaśī 17,6 (TP II 34)⁹³²; ~ as a creeper 17,73 (TP II 40); man tortured with pain of ~ (*smarārti-vidhura*) 17,74 (TP II 74); ~ of woman spurned 20,120 (TP II 105 and 109 with note on p. 120ff.); ~ more charming than native country 28,64 (TP III 25); ~ as highest joy of the earth (*kāmabhoga-mahābhoga*) 29,53 (TP III 42); falling in ~ by mere description 30,69 (TP III 68 with note); idem, 31,3 (TP III 81)⁹³³; ~ is life as water is life of lotus 33,88 (TP III 113)⁹³⁴; man sets out alone

on journey drawn by noose of ~ (*prema-pāśa*) for woman 37,53 (TP III 186); ~ as a fierce elephant (*madana-vyāla-gaja*) 37,98 (TP III 190); blind with ~ (*kāmāndha*) 37,102 (TP III 190); elephant of ~ (*kāma-kariṇ*) 38,116 (TP III 214); with a look woman is raining ~ (*caḅṣusā prema-varṣiṇī*) 39,81 (TP III 223); queen's ~ of brahmin scorned 49,51 (TP IV 88); women whose ~ is slighted are worse than poison 49,152 (TP IV 95); ~ for offspring is a tenacious feeling 50,75 (TP IV 112); with *śramaṇa*'s words arrows of ~ enter king's ear 51,122 (TP IV 130); princess in ~ with a painting 51,144 (TP IV 132); ~ is brushed off by Sarasvatī, Skanda and Jina like a blade of grass, i.e. something worthless /

⁹³⁰ Syed 1990: 657.

⁹³¹ For a dramatic discussion on the nature of love see Ghurye 1966: 220f.

⁹³² Cf. Andreas Capellanus, *De Amore* (indexed 1277) I 8 “*Ex sola cogitatione [...] passio illa procedit*” quoted after Scharold 2012: 63. – Falling in love at first sight proves that the couple were lovers in a pre-birth (112,110 [TP VIII 115]).

⁹³³ See also Bollée 2010a: 150 note 123.

⁹³⁴ “In Indian poetry love is connected with moistness” (Jackmuth 2002: 166). In KSS this is less clear as Sigmund Freud would have wished.

insignificant 51,205 (TP IV 136); 52,283 (TP IV 157); fever of ~ (*smara-saṃjvara*) 55,63 (TP IV 206); ~ at hearing only 55,74 (TP IV 207); ~ at sight of picture 55,80 (TP IV 208) and 101,77 (TP VII 77); ~ pain (*smarârti*) inflicted on women 55,84 (TP IV 208); ~ as demon (*sneha-graha*) 61,167 (TP V 82); wicked wife falls in ~ with man without hands and feet 65,15 (TP V 154); *vidyâdharî* princess falls in ~ with mortal prince at merely hearing of him 65,228 (TP V 172); girl like a wave of the sea of ~'s arrogance (*Kandarpa-darpâbdhi-laharî*) 67,49 (TP V 199); fire of ~ (*smarâgni*) consumes brahmin woman 69,161 (TP VI 20); tree of ~ (*smara-druma*) growing up and irrigated by streams of passion (*prema-rasa*) in heart of princess at hearing description of prince 71,92 (TP VI 42); moon like ear-ornament made of a shoot of the wishing-tree of ~ (*kâma-kalpadruma*) 72,28 (TP VI 70); ~ as stream (*smarâugha*, of passion) from which woman wants to be saved by lover 74,225 (TP VI 156); signs of being in ~ (*smarâviṣṭa*): trembling limbs and hair erect 81,54 (TP VI 212)⁹³⁵; bewildered by demon of ~ (*smara-graha-vimohita*) 84,15 (TP VII 6); king falls in ~ with mermaid at mere hearing of her (*śrutvâiva ... smara-vaśaḥ*) 86,64 (TP VII 17); fire of ~ (*kâmâgni*) 86,85 (TP VII 19); fever of ~ (*smara-jvara*) consumes king 91,44 (TP VII 69); woman in ~ (*baddha-bhâva*) with brahmin 93,38 (TP VII 81); do, ~ (*kâma-jvara*) 95,25 (TP VII 99); princess falls in ~ with prince from seeing his picture (*citra-paṭa*) 101,125 (TP VII 143); kings disregard ~ of offspring (*apatya-sneha*) in the interest of their kingdom 103,17 (TP VII 176); maiden's look as a messenger of ~ (*prîti-dûtîṃ dr̥ṣaṃ*) 104,31 (TP VIII 3); moon is main friend of ~ 104,112 (TP VIII 9); unlawful ~ is forerunner of fire of hell (*nirayâgni*) 104,119 (TP VIII 10); with hands on breast (*karaiś cōraḥ-sthalârpitaiḥ*) as sign of ~ in women 107,84 (TP VIII 49); fisher in ~ (*smara-vaśa*) with princess 112,114 (TP VIII 115); fire of ~ (*madanânala*) 117,12 (TP VIII 164); shame makes prince conceal fire of ~ 119,3 (TP VIII 193); king falls in ~ with girl in dream 122,30 (TP IX 36); platonic ~, see: looking; – see also: falling in love; fire of love

loved as one's life (*prâṇa-samā*), said of wife 35,3 (TP III 155) et passim; – see also: daughter love at first sight, (*dr̥ṣṭe anurâgiṇî*) of *apsaras* Rambhâ for king 28,68 (TP III 25); do, (*kânta-darśana*) of princess with handsome stranger who consents to meet in retired temple against his will and then flees before out of fear 30,80 (TP III 69); *Asura* woman falls in ~ in a dream 31,12 (TP III 82); ~ at first sight (*âloka-saṃjâta-manmatha*) of brahmin for merchant's daughter 37,101 (TP III 190); do, (*darśana-vaśîkr̥ta*) of *gaṇikâ* for king 38,33 (TP III 208); do, 42,132 makes *râkṣasî* offer herself to prince 142 (TP III 269); idem, of any princess for prince Sûryaprabha 44,41 (TP IV 4); idem, of prince Sûryaprabha for Daitya princess Kalâvatî 45,207 (TP IV 31); do, of king for heavenly maiden in temple (*âyatana*) of Śiva-Svayambhû 51,7 (TP IV 122); princess falls in ~ with king in a picture 51,144 (TP IV 132); *vidyâdharî* falls in ~ with alien king 52,205 (TP IV 152); reciprocal ~ (*anyonya-sâbhilâṣa*) 52,301 (TP IV 158); ~ of king in women 55,32 (TP IV 205); merchant girl is like a wave of the sea of ~'s insolence (*Kandarpa-darpâbdhi-laharî*) 67,49 (TP V 199); ~

⁹³⁵ Kumârasambhava 3,68 compares this with trembling young kadamba flowers (Jackmuth 2002: 60f.).

of merchant for princess (*vaṇik-putrasya dṛṣṭvâiva viveśa hṛdi kanyakā*) 72,286 (TP VI 90); ~ (*hṛta-mānasa*) in *tīrtha* 80,9 (TP VI 204); woman of same family, wealth and occupation (*karman*) fallen in ~ (*darśana-sakta*) with dhobi 80,17 (TP VI 205); princess falls in ~ (*māra-mohitā dṛṣṭvâiva*) with robber to be executed 88,34 (TP VII 37); princess falls in ~ (*dṛṣṭa-mātre*) with brahmin 89,12 (TP VII 41); ~ of princess with Jimūtavāhana 90,46 (TP VII 52); ~ of man with maiden in picture 101,77 (TP VII 139); ~ between brahmin and *kṣatriya* maiden 104,29 (TP VIII 3), cf. ~ (*smara-vaśā*) 104,97 (TP VIII 8); falling in ~ proves bond in pre-birth (*janmāntara-priyatamā cakṣū-rāgōpavarṇitā*) 112,110 (TP VIII 115); princesses fall in ~ (*dṛṣṭyânurāgiṇyau*) 119,9 (TP VIII 193); – see also: (falling in) love; forest-fire; separation

lover, four ~s put off by virtuous woman 4,33f. (TP I 32f.); ~ hoisted in basket into house of unchaste wife 64,100 and 104 (TP V 147); moon as ~ of night (*rajanī-ramaṇa*) 106,50 (TP VIII 31)

love-sick,⁹³⁶ woman becomes ~ (*kāmārtā*) 42,201 (TP III 274); ~ woman flees into Viṣṇu temple which dispels calamity (*pāpa-ghnam āśrityāyatanam Hareḥ*) 71,95 (TP VI 42); ~ man taciturn and averse to food 72,288 (TP VI 90)⁹³⁷; ~ prince compared to *vidyādhara* who lost his *vidyā* 75,77 (TP VI 169); ~ dhobi 80,9 (TP VI 205); ~ (*smara-śarāhata* 81) king praises sea in which nymph has disappeared 86,84ff. (TP VII 18); ~ (*madana-mohita*) brahmin seeing princess gathering flowers 89,9 (TP VII 40); brahmin bitten by snake of passion (*rāga-mahā-vyāla-daṣṭa*) 89,63 (TP VII 44); friend drags off ~ (*madanāviṣṭa*) brahmin home 95,23 (TP VII 99); ~ princess, **description** of 90,60ff. (TP VII 53); princess becomes ~ (*madana-mohita*) by looking at painting 101,108 (TP VII 141); ~ *kṣatriya* maiden 104,54ff. (TP VIII 5); ~ prince treated with snow and sandalwood 117,91 (TP VIII 170); ~ man will die and be released from curse 117,149 (TP VIII 174)

love-sickness,⁹³⁸ lit. ‘bond’ (*nibandhana*) 55,71 (TP IV 207); seventh stage of ~ 89,67 (TP VII 44 with note 2)⁹³⁹; description of ~ of princess 90,65 (TP VII 53) and 101,126ff. (TP VII 143); do, 104,54ff. (TP VIII 5);

loving-sport (*praṇaya-krīḍā*), witch ties string round man’s neck as if in ~ 37,104 (TP III 194)

luck, capriciousness of ~⁹⁴⁰ see: fortune

ludus verborum, see: *majjara*; *mōdakaiḥ*

lulitālaka-keśānta ‘whose curls and locks are dishevelled’ as a sign of sex 74,242 (TP VI 158)

⁹³⁶ Cf. Bollée 2008a: 21 s.v. – The Greek physician Erasistratos of Ceos (305-250 BCE) was the first in literature to decide, from the fast pulse of Antiochos I Soter at the sight of the beautiful Stratonice, that love is a distemper (www.mlhanas.de/Greeks/Erasistratos.htm < Plutarch). In Latin, too, love may be characterized as sickness, e.g. Ovid, *Remedia amoris* 109; 313 et passim (see Index, p. 342 s.v. *aeger amoris* and 348 s.v. *morbus amoris*).

⁹³⁷ Cf. 73, 358 (TP VI 126).

⁹³⁸ STh T 24.1. Bollée 2008a: 21.

⁹³⁹ On the ten stages of love-sickness see TP II 9f. – Also: Schmidt 1904: 94f.; Insler 1988; Chojnacki 2008 (I): 344 s.v. *amour*.

⁹⁴⁰ STh N 100ff. and *N 170ff.

lullaby,⁹⁴¹ praise of Śiva sung as ~ (?) sends brahmin to sleep 52,195 (TP IV 151)
 lust and wrath: two bolts on the door of brahmins' deliverance (*kāma-krodhau viprāṇāṃ mokṣa-dvārārgalāv ubhau*) 20,130 (TP II 106)
 lustration,⁹⁴² of arms (*nīrājana*) 19,67 (TP II 89); ~ of city with oil vessel without spilling it 27,47 and 50 (TP III 4f.), cf. infra: ordeal; ~ (*nagara-bhrama*) of city by king 61,205 (TP V 85); – see also: *pradakṣiṇā*
 lute (*viṇā*) play subdues wild elephants 11,3f. (TP I 122); king with melodious ~ tries to catch mechanical elephant 12,17 (TP I 134); lute of bones (*kaṅkāla-kiṇṇarī*) played by *yakṣiṇī*, and a charm produce horns on ascetic turning him into sacrificial animal and devouring him 37,64ff. (TP III 187f.); ~ out of tune (*viṇā cyutā sthānād*) 34,159 (TP III 139); *deva-kanyakā* plays ~ to praise Śiva 51,6 (TP IV 122)⁹⁴³; – see also: lyre
 lying, physician ~ to patient 15,15 (TP II 2)⁹⁴⁴; brahmin ruined by gambling lies that he has seen Kanakapurī in order to marry princess 24,60 et passim (TP II 174); wicked women spring from ~ speech (*a-satya-vacana*) 49,120 (TP IV 93); queen tells king fictitious tale about intimacy with sick people shown by scratches and bites 66,42 (TP V 181); virtuous woman maltreated by husband tells parents lies to protect her man 77,33f. (TP VI 185); – see also: abscess
 lying-in chamber, illuminated by newly born daughter (*jāta-mātrāiva kānti-dyotita-vāsakā*) 17,66 (TP II 39)⁹⁴⁵; ~ (*jāta-vāsa-gr̥ha*) description 23,61 (TP II 161 and note on 166ff.); ~ with lights on to protect child 23,62 (TP II 161) and idem against evil spirits (*rakṣā-pradīpa*) 28,4 (TP III 18); ~ hung with various arms and protected by conjurers muttering charms 23,62 (TP II 161); ~ illuminated and made red as vermilion by *tejas* of born son 35,112 (TP III 164; MI 505: “*Kaum hatte der Knabe das Licht der Welt erblickt, tauchte er die Wochenstube durch den mit ihm entstandenen Glanz in ein herrliches Purpurroß*”); baby daughter surpassing in splendour the lights in ~ (*jāta-veśman*) and these as it were heaved sighs by discharging lamp-black 43,149 (TP III 291)
 lyre⁹⁴⁶ (*viṇā ... tantrī-nirghoṣa-ramyā śruti-bhāga-vibhājītā*) given by snake Vasunemi to king Udayana out of gratitude for being set free; it is sweet in the sounding of its strings and divided according to the division of the quarter-tones 9,80f. (TP I 100); ~ out of tune (*viṇā cyutā sthānād*) played by queen 34,159 (TP III 139); *kaṅkāla-kinnarī* played by a *yakṣiṇī*

⁹⁴¹ See Bollée 1988:182f. for a Jain lullaby; Graul 1865: 194 mentions a lullaby of Kṛṣṇa (quoted in Glasenapp 1922: 210f.).

⁹⁴² See, e.g. TP I 190f.

⁹⁴³ Cf. ŚatapathaBr 13,1,5,1 “When a man obtains prosperity, the lute is played on him. The lute is a form of Śrī. It is Śrī they confirm on him.”

⁹⁴⁴ For such practices see Müller 2008: 539.

⁹⁴⁵ Bollée 2008a: 10 s.v. For newly born radiating see: daughter; radiating. – Kād 152,6ff. describes a lying-in chamber in more details with a couch suitable for confinement (*garbhōcītaṃ śayana-talam*, 153,4), etc.

⁹⁴⁶ Cf. ORC 1598 (which draws the attention to the (Freudian) role of the lyre in seducing women in 12,64 (TP I 138) and 49,34 (*vallakī*; TP IV 87, Zin 2004: 341 with notes 273-5); Pesch 2009: 73 et passim calls the *viṇā* also ‘harp’; Maten 1973: 37 note.

37,64⁹⁴⁷ (TP III 187); ~ with hair of dog⁹⁴⁸ (*śva-bāla*) inside 49,19 (TP IV 86); queen asks to be taught to play the ~ 49,32 (TP IV 87); king hears singing and heavenly ~ in forest 51,4 (TP IV 122); king plays and sings (*upaviṇayati*) to ~ left in empty Caṇḍikā / Durgā temple 69,113f. (TP VI 17); nereid playing on the ~ (*vallakī*) and singing on karman 86,78f. (TP VII 18); maiden playing on the ~ (*upaviṇayantī*) near Gaurī temple 90,41 (TP VII 51); king Vatsa worships Vṛṣadhvaṅga with his ~ Ghoṣavatī and then commits suicide 111,82 (TP VIII 102); Gandharva princess always sings to the ~ a hymn given her by Śauri = Viṣṇu 106,11 (TP VIII 28); beautiful lady (*varāṅganā*) worships Śiva in *liṅga* and sings to her ~ (*viṇā*) with rapt devotion in southern style 120,117ff. (TP IX 10); – see also: lute

m/y misprint, see: *mukta*

maces (*kāṣṭha-khaṇḍaka*) are mark of Rājputs 24,121 (TP II 178)

machine, see: chariot; doll; elephant;

mada, see: ichor

Madana, see: Kāma

mada-sprś (not MW) ‘beginning intoxication, tipsiness’, see: intoxication

madgu ‘darter or snake-bird’⁹⁴⁹ (?), Mādhava repaired to the house of the chaplain which was the cause of his (the chaplain’s) ruin, as that of the ~ in the trunk of the tree was the cause of its ruin (M. *tasyāivāśīśriyad gṛham vināśa-hetur vāsāya madguḥ skandham taror iva*) 24,132 (TP II 179 translated ~ by ‘mouse’ but in MW it is ‘a diver bird or cormorant; fish; snake’; ORC 212: “*M., tel le plongeon qui cause la destruction de l’arbre dont la fourche l’accueille, élut alors domicile chez le chapelain*” with note on p. 1373 ‘oiseau aquatique’ < Mayrhofer, *EWAi* II 301 ‘ein Wasservogel’ [a kind of aquatic bird]; M I 305: “*lebte M. im Haus des Priesters und entwickelte sich allmählich zur Ursache für dessen Untergang, wie eine Maus, die sich eine Baumwurzel zum Wohnsitz erwählt hat, langsam die Vernichtung des Baumes vorbereitet*”) ⁹⁵⁰

mādhavī flowers,⁹⁵¹ Asura princess resembling cluster of ~ 45,336 (TP IV 39);

madhu, see: wine

madhu-kesarin, see: lion of spring

madhu-māsa-mahōtsava, see: spring feast

⁹⁴⁷ Zin 2004: 338 notes 233f. Pesch 2009: 437 mentions this *viṇā* as a lute in old texts, but does not deal with it. It should be noted that the *kinmarī-viṇā* occurs in the South below the river Vitastā (KSS 37, 54). – The French and English translations of *dūrād* in 37,64 seem to differ.

⁹⁴⁸ Thus certainly correct ORC 520 against TP puppy. – The soundbox of an arched *viṇā* was covered with leather which was laid over it wet and which spanned drying. In order to open it the leather had to be moistened. The brilliant musician could hear the change of sound due to the hair inside. Later the form of the instrument was altered so that a hair could no longer be seen (p.c. from M. Zin).

⁹⁴⁹ Thus Dave 2005. 272ff. A picture of the cormorant-like black water-bird is found in Ali 1979: 2.

⁹⁵⁰ The story behind this metaphor could not be found, but *skandha* does not mean root of a tree, rather the part where the branches begin (MW). The tree may be destroyed by the bird’s droppings.

⁹⁵¹ Syed 1990: 34ff.

madhu-śrī, see: spring

madhūtsava 4,35 (TP I 33); 17,72 (TP II 40); 35,6 (TP III 155); – see also: Holī festival

madhyāhna-savana ‘midday rites or ablutions’, hermit performs ~ 69,167 (TP VI 21)

mādhyamīna-savana = prec. 45,386 (TP IV 43);

madman, playing the ~ (*unmatta-ceṣṭa*) 18,246 (TP II 68); playing mad woman 59,155 (TP V 36)

madness, merchant struck by Pāśupata ascetic’s charmed hand is freed from ~ (*unmāda*) 73,382 (TP VI 128)

magic,⁹⁵² (*yoga*) for breaking chains 12,63 (TP I 137); ~ power (*vidyā-prabhāva*), of *vidyādhari* 18,227 (TP II 67); ~ of witches’ spells (*ḍākinī-mantra-siddhi*) 20,104 (TP II 103) and 187 (TP II 111); ~ (*māyā*) of Asura Maya creates wonderful world (*lokāntaram ... a-pūrvam*) 29,60 (TP III 43); *divyam udyānam* made by ~ (*māyā*) 34,142 (TP III 138); ~ (*māyā-bala*) of wife lets sesame seeds grow 39,120 (TP III 226); entering another’s body by ~ (*yoga-yukti*) 45,60f. (TP IV 21); with ~ due to ruling charnel ground (*mahā-śmaśānādhipatitva-siddha*) 48,122 (TP IV 82); city built by ~ 68,68 (TP VI 6); spared *yakṣa* king gives hero own ring with ~ of averting calamities called *īti* (*īti-ghnaṃ svāṅgulīyakam*) 72,61 (TP VI 73); beautiful daughter wants to be married only to husband knowing ~ (*viññāna*) 79,9 (TP VI 200); hermit with ~ calls to mind science which procures whatever one desires (*vratī siddhaḥ ... iṣṭa-saṃpādinim vidyām*) 92,35 (TP VII 73); four brahmin brothers go out to acquire ~ 96,28 (TP VII 110); sleeping *vidyā dhari*’s ~ of disguising lost 105,62 (TP VIII 25); *vidyādhara* M. brings queen hither and tries to win her to his will by his ~ (*M. mām ihāniya sva-māyayā pravartayitum*)⁹⁵³ (*abhyaicchad*) 106,126 (TP VIII 37; ORC 1115: “M., qui m’avait amenée ici grâce à son pouvoir magique, s’efforça de me faire céder”); by ~ king assumes form of lion 109,130 (TP VIII 79); by ~ mother resuscitates son 109,145 (TP VIII 80); Dānava ladies concealing their bodies (*vigraha*) in trees by ~ (*māyā*) 118,107 (TP VIII 185); black ~ see: black magic; telemagic; – see also: illusion; *māyā*; science; *vidyā*

magic articles: woman gives messenger earth, water, thorns and fire (*mṛttikāṃ toyam kaṅṭhakān agnim*) to throw behind him in order to stop his pursuing brother 39,131 (TP III 227); – see further: barley; bow; chariot; collyrium; crest-jewel; *daṇḍa*; doll; fruit; garments; pearl; pitcher; quiver; ring; shoes; sword; vessel

magic articles motif⁹⁵⁴ TP I 25ff.

magic car (*māyā-yantra-vimāna*), princess of Takṣaśīla travels in ~ 31,56 (TP III 87)

magic circle (*maṇḍala*), queen in ~ is strewn with various coloured powders (*vicitra-varṇakanyasta*) 20,51 (TP II 98f. with Penzer’s note; TP III 201f.); 20,193 (TP II 112); ~ of ashes made by Pāśupata ascetics for protection against *yakṣiṇī* 37,62 (TP III 187); *bhikṣu* makes ~ to destroy king but is decapitated 38,64 (TP III 211); magician puts corpse into ~ marked

⁹⁵² See also ORC 1599.

⁹⁵³ Can *pravartayati* ‘to use, employ’ (MW) > ‘to enjoy’ ?

⁹⁵⁴ See also ORC 1618.

out with powdered human bones, with pitchers with human blood in the corners (of a circle ! *koṇa-nyastâsra-kumbhaka*) and lighted up with lamps fed by oil of human fat (*mahâ-taila-jvala-dîpa*) 73,304-6 (TP VI 123); 75,45 (TP VI 167); *purohita* makes ~ for *brahma-rākṣasa* to appear 94,114 (TP VII 95); ascetic sits in ~ of yellowish powder of bones (*asthi-cūrṇa*) 99,3 (TP VII 122); ascetic throws corpse into ~ 99,10 (TP VII 122); 121,15 (TP IX 13); – see also: dancing

magical city under the Ganges 10,30ff. (TP I 108)

magical conflict motif, see: monkey; ox; plate; shoes

magical cure of animals by king 38,28 (TP III 208)

magic drug (TP VI 62ff.); – see also: barley; bawd; *mahâuśadhi*; mustard

magic fruit, see: fruit

magic horse, visible Gaurī gives snake princess ~ and sword to pass on to hero 72,49 (TP VI 72)

magic gem neutralizes enemy’s arms 71,135 (TP VI 45);

magic ointment for the feet (*pāda-lepa*) to run, *yakṣiṇī* gives *kārpaṭika* ~ 123,19 and 27 (TP IX 44f.)⁹⁵⁵; – see also: ointment; *pāda-lepa*

magic pill (*yoga-gulikā*)⁹⁵⁶, Mūladeva puts ~ in his mouth to turn himself into old brahmin, and a second ~ into that of a young brahmin lover making him a beautiful maiden 89,25 (TP VII 42 and 222f.);

magic plate of Maya 3,47 (TP I 22)

magic ring averting calamities (*iti-ghna*⁹⁵⁷ ... *aṅguliyaka*) 72,61 (TP VI 73);

magic rite (*kṛtyā*), Cāṇakya performs ~ and thereby kills Yogananda with a burning fever in seven days 5,121f. (TP I 57); ~ by *kāpālika* of throwing ashes on funeral pyre and resuscitating brahmin’s wife 124,9 (TP IX 68)

magic science, see: bilocality; *prajñapti*; *vidyā*

magic shoes enable to fly, of Maya 3,47 (TP I 22)

magic skill (*siddhi*) delights army 109,150 (TP VIII 81);

magic staff (*yaṣṭi*), whatever is written with ~ turns out true 3,50 (TP I 22); ~ in shape of a bedstead (*khaṭvâṅga*) dancing on shoulder of *kāpālika* 124,8 (TP IX 68; ORC 1306: “*piet de lit*”)⁹⁵⁸; – see also: *daṇḍa*

magic string, see: thread (TP VI 59ff.)

magic sword, see: magic horse; sword

magic, sympathetic ~ (TP VI 24 note); king proceeds to cut off the head of a male figure he had drawn (*ālekhyā-puruṣa*); that did not sever the neck of a *vetāla*, but made it stream with blood 121,208 (TP IX 27)

⁹⁵⁵ STh *D 1244.

⁹⁵⁶ Cf. Hemacandra, *Triṣaṣṭi* VI 2,118.

⁹⁵⁷ TP translate: “all the calamities”. Did they read *sarvêti-ghna* for NSP text (D): *sann itī-ghna* ?

⁹⁵⁸ Like the Vedic student’s *daṇḍa* the *kāpālika*’s staff may be thought of as representing a *vajra* (Gonda 1975: IV 165) and, as such, inspiration, etc. Thus it is understandable to dance on its owner’s shoulder near his head.

magic vessel, whatever food one wishes to have in ~ is found there immediately 3,50 (TP I 22); – see also: *bhadra-ghaṭa*

magician (*mahā-yogin*), abandons old body (*pūrva-kalevara*) which he throws into ravine after entering body of dead brahmin boy on pyre 97,41 (TP VII 115); – see also: Bhūtivasu

magician and apprentice motif⁹⁵⁹

magnificence, public show of ~,⁹⁶⁰ see king (rides out); curiosity

Mahābhārata, lake compared to ~ 100,14 (TP VII 124)

Mahādevī, drugs of ~ (*mahāuśadha*) 66,39 (TP V 181);

Mahākāla = Hara in Ujjayinī 11,32 (TP I 125); Ujjayinī residence of ~ 27,135 (TP III 11); ~ as a Śiva *liṅga* in the river Sīprā near Ujjayinī 37,6 (TP III 183); ~ orders good witch to free *vidyādhara* maiden 48,127 (TP IV 83); ~ tells brahmins in dream to eat in house of *mātaṅga* who is a *vidyādhara* 112,181f. (TP VIII 121); gambler in ~ temple seeing images of *Mātaras*, *yakṣas*, etc., challenges them to play dice with him and forces them to pay him the gold he won 121,77-87 (TP IX 17f.); ~ invited by gambler declares to sit out of the game 121,93 (TP IX 18); gambler hymns ~ and gets his wish 121,98 (TP IX 18); – see also: Ujjayinī

mahā-jñānin ‘soothsayer’ [MW] 39,42 (TP III 221 ‘astrologer’; ORC 398 ‘*un diseur de bonne aventure*’; MI 557: “*Sterndeuter*”)

mahā-maṭha (not MW) ‘asylum, refuge’ built by king for gamblers 73,263 (TP VI 119)

mahā-māṃsa ‘human flesh’ offered in magic rite 20,51 (TP II 99); ~ eaten by witches in order to obtain magic power 10,105 (TP II 103); ~ (*ṇī-māṃsa*) eaten by witches 20, 191 (TP II 112); gambler offers ~ for sale 121,54 (TP IX 15);

*mahā-patha*⁹⁶¹ ‘long journey’, father goes the ~ = dies 2,43 (TP I 12); old people go ~ 30.59 (TP III 68); – see also: death

mahā-prasthāna = *mahā-patha*, see: journey

mahā-puruṣa seen by man-hating princess in dream 122,81 (TP IX 39);

mahā-siddhi, see: *bodhi*

mahā-taila 99,4 (TP VII 122 ‘human fat’; ORC 1031: “*graisse humaine*”; MW: ‘precious oil’)

mahātodya ‘great drum which accompanies royal dancing’ 71,76 (TP VI 41)

mahattara(ka) ‘chamberlain’ as go-between 31,52 (TP III 86); 32,17f. (TP III 91);

mahāuśadhi ‘potent simple, strong drug’, seven ~s in cave 46,205 (TP IV 62)

mahā-viha-ga, see: vulture(s)

mahā-vratika (Pāśupata ascetic), four ~s 37,54 TP III 186); prince disguised as ~ 70,2 (TP VI 23);

⁹⁵⁹ See Cosquin 1922: 497ff.

⁹⁶⁰ Jackson 2010: 76ff.

⁹⁶¹ Not dealt with in Gonda 1975: IV 323f. though ŚvetUp 3,8 is mentioned with *panthāḥ* in the sense of “the only path which crosses over death.” The *devayānaḥ panthāḥ* is often described as a real road with the sun as gate, Agni, the *pathi-kṛt*, perhaps being the cremation fire. Is the sun gate an indication of the light at the end of the tunnel in near death experience and in Tibetan Buddhism ? See Evans-Wentz 1949: Foreword, p. xxxvii.

Mahāyāna ideas (may my body serve others in every birth: *parāthāya dehaḥ syāt pratijanma me*) 90,152 (TP VII 60);

Mahēśvara = Śiva on bull in dream of king 69, (TP VI 11)

mahout (*hasty-āroha*) bribed by Yaugandharāyaṇa 13,8 (TP I 150); 101,180 (TP VII 146)

maiden (*kanyakā*), two heavenly ~s sitting on *nyagrodha* tree 17,108ff. (TP II 43), cf. 120,105 (TP IX 8f. and 28f.); ~ with two bodies, one living, one dead 26,81 (TP II 223); hermit

turns mouse into ~ by the might of his ascetism (*tapo-balāt*) 62,125 (TP V 109); ~

illuminates the wood at night 68,8 (TP VI 1); heavenly ~ makes Śrī lose all pride in her

beauty (*rūpa-darpa-harā*) 69,110 (TP VI 16); Mūladeva transforms brahmin into ~ by

means of magic pill (*yoga-gulikā*) 89,26 (TP VII 42); ~ (*vara-kanyakā*) playing on lyre near

Gaurī temple 90,41 (TP VII 51); ~ gathering flowers near lake 104,92 (TP VIII 8);

description of beautiful ~ 104,165 (TP VIII 13); ~ strikes trunk of elephant with her

hand (*kare karenāhatya*) 112,68 and swings on her upper garment fastened to the tusks 70

(TP VIII 111); **description** 104,92ff. (TP VIII 8); princess amuses herself by marrying her

~s to one another 122,52 (TP IX 37); – see also: daughter; *femme fatale*; girl; *kanyā*;

kanyakā; *trailokya-sundarī*

maina (myna), see: hen-maina

maintenance, see: alimony

maitrī, see: brotherhood

majjāra ‘cat’ (*marjāra*) and ‘my lover’ (*mad + jāra*) in Apabhraṃśa 17,141 (TP II 46)

makara ‘sea-monster’ swallows brahmin 25,40 (TP II 191); ~ hits ship 54,102 (TP IV

191)⁹⁶²; ~ kills crane 60,89 (TP V 49); mermaids save ship-wrecked couple from mouth of

~s (*makarānana*) 120,112 (TP IX 9)

Makara-ketu, see: Kāma

mā kāṛṣiḥ sāhasaṃ ‘do not act rashly’ 86,87 (TP VII 19); *mā kṛthāḥ sāhasaṃ*, see: *mā*

sāhasaṃ kṛthāḥ

make-up or face-cream line (*pa[t]tra*)⁹⁶³, a lady from whose lotus face sex removed the

⁹⁶² On *m*. see Viennot 1954. Varuṇa has a *m*. for mount (Dallapiccola 2002: 199).

⁹⁶³ *Patra* here is short for *patra-bhaṅga* ‘a decoration consisting in lines or streaks drawn on the face and body with musk and other fragrant substances’ (MW). For *-patra-* against D *-pattra-* see Haebler 1960: 65 note 11. Gode 1961 vol. I wrote several articles on cosmetics but regrettably not on *patra*. Gonda 1968: 240; the abbreviation of the compound shows its frequent use. *Patra-bhaṅga* ‘leaf cutting’ may appear a synonym of *patra-ccheda* ‘act of leaf cutting’ and *patra-cchedya* ‘product and act of cutting a leaf’ for which Haebler (1960: 66) had established this meaning against Böhtlinck. Leaf cutting was one of the 60 *kalās* (Venkatasubbiah 1911 and 1914; Kuv 16.24; 22.4) but not only a pastime of high society; it had a also a practical end in that the leaf cuttings were smeared with a sticky mixture of musk, camphor, etc. and pressed on the face and upper part of the body to serve as (fragrant) decoration (p. c. Proff. Sarma and Zin). A synonym *patra-lekhā* is found in *Rtusaṃhāra* VI 7 where women’s faces with leafy decorations are likened to golden lotuses. Decorations such as on the cheeks of a *yakṣī* (Quinanilla 2007 Fig. 115 < Bharhut, ca. 150 BCE) being unidentifiable, regrettably no picture of a woman thus made up could be found so far, but girls in Birma paint leaves on their cheeks (p.c. Silvia Leibacher of Lotus Travel). We have *tamāla-pattra* as tilak on women’s faces (Rājāt 3,326) and leaves served as ear ornaments (Sivaramamurti 1970: 15 < Raghuvamśa VI 17). – The anthropologist Stephen Huyler was asked in vain, but James McHugh mailed WB that

fragrant ~ (*saṃbhoga-vidalat-patra-mukhâbjā*) 33,208 (TP III 124)⁹⁶⁴; gambler's dayly ~ (*vilepana*)⁹⁶⁵ 37,5 (TP III 183); ~ of sandalwood lotion (*śrī-khaṇḍârdra-vilepana*) 85,21 (TP VII 11) and 104,56 (TP VIII 5); 94,113 (TP VII 95)

makṣikāh, see: flies

Mālava⁹⁶⁶, women shining with twofold beauty 19,99 (TP II 93); charming ~ woman enjoyed by two rogues 24,86 (TP II 176); *vidyādhara* reborn in ~ as disobedient son of brahmin and cursed to be reborn as lion 65,63 (TP V 159); charming ~ woman whom husband loves more than own body 58,80 (TP V 21); festive procession for Gaṇeśa in ~ 73,327 (TP VI 124); brahmin hero from ~ 78,8 (TP VI 191); dark (*śyāmā*) queen from ~ 98,35 (TP VII 118); Rājput's ~ wife desires his return at beginning of spring (Caitra) 111,30f. (TP VIII 98)

Malaya, Mt, home of *Gandharvas* 36,131 (TP III 178)

"male animals are wicked" says maina-hen 77,11 (TP VI 184);

mallikā 'jasmine' 122,65 (TP IX 39)

Mālyavān cursed by Pārvatī to become Guṇāḍhya 1,57-65 (TP I 7); origin of his name 7,111 (TP I 86);

māṃsa-vyañjana 'meat-curry' (not MW) and ghee as guest food 54,170 (TP IV 196)

man (disguised as woman) corrupts harem (*antaḥpura-viplava*) 5,36 (TP I 50); ~ (Agni in the shape of a brahmin) appearing out of fire 17,98 (TP II 42); ~ with sword descending from the air 24,9 (TP II 170); ~ as the appropriate food of *rākṣasas* 39,95 (TP III 224); ~ of heavenly appearance descends into durbar 44,3 (TP IV 1); ~ with elephant's face⁹⁶⁷ opens coral (*vaidruma*) door on Mt Kailāsa to Sūryaprabha 50,175 (TP IV 119); ~ with sword in hand from house composed of jewels is accompanied by *divya-nārī-gaṇa* 56,207f. (TP IV 235); lustrous ~ descends from sky and flies up with dead body of lover 59,111 (TP V 34); beautiful ~ with sword rises from lake 63,18 (TP V 121); ~ with discus and club comes out of painted wall and makes love with queen every night 66,48 and 66 (TP V 181ff.); ~ with pendulous paunch representing Gaṇeśa 70,125 (TP VI 33); minister carried through sky by deformed ~ (*pum̐sātivikṛtena*) who comes when thought of 75,4 (TP VI 164); ~ with matted hair in dream 119,73 and 88 (TP VIII 198f.); – see also: men

to his knowledge the practice of this make-up appears more literary than codified in texts on perfumes. He thinks that the little stamps used for applying *gopi-candana* in some Vaiṣṇava movements may be an echo of this sort of practice, and that henna (q.v. supra) in contemporary Indian perfume culture has replaced agarwood and musk because these are rare and expensive now. Traditional style coloured pastes tend to be saffron and sandalwood these days.

⁹⁶⁴ On the use of cosmetics in general see Cormack 1961: 29f. Tamāla trees issue fragrance of musk (Jayadeva, *Gītagovinda* I 3,4).

⁹⁶⁵ McHugh only talks about *vilepana* as make-up 2012: 137f. and 246, as does Saundarānanda IV 26 (quoted in Zin 2006: 170 note 26) and Mānasollāsa II 3,980ff.

⁹⁶⁶ On the Mālavas see, e.g., Basant 2012 (KSS was not used); Dasgupta 1966; Schmidt 1904: 142; Schmidt 1922: 169f.

⁹⁶⁷ On the *vināyakas* see Courtright 1985: 48f.

man as tree⁹⁶⁸: beauty of prince seems to outdo *kalpa-druma* 71,68 (TP VI 40); brahmin lives with *yakṣiṇī* like banyan-tree with glory of spring 73,27 (TP VI 102); (*su-bhaṭa-pāda-pa*) 108,105 (TP VIII 162); hermit Akampana looking like a great tree 110,24 (TP VIII 83) *māṇava* (not MW in this sense) ‘measure > means?’, see: *svapna-māṇava māñca*, see: cradle
mandâgni ‘with weak digestion’ 54,174 (TP IV 196)⁹⁶⁹
maṇḍala ‘magic circle’ used in enchantments 121,15 (TP IX 13);
maṇḍalârcana ‘circle incantation’ 38,59 (TP III 210)
maṇḍana ‘decoration’, ichor (*mātaṅga-mada-niṣyanda*) used as ~ by Bhilla women 123,50 (TP IX 46; ORC 1289: ‘parfum’)⁹⁷⁰; – *racita*-° 112,31 (TP VIII 107), see: head
maṇḍana-vidhi (not MW) ‘toilet rites, making oneself up’ 44,184 (TP IV 13)
Mandara mountain white as mortar (*sudhā-sita*)⁹⁷¹ 1,16 (TP I 3); ~ wooded and with elephants 19,105 (TP II 93); Śiva loves ~ more than Mt Kailāsa 114,55 (TP VIII 136)
mandāra tree (*Erythrina indica* or *Calotropis gigantea*, coral tree, a paradise tree),⁹⁷² Agni flees on ~ in form of snail (*śambūka-rūpin*) 20,77f. (TP II 101); woman with breasts like clusters of ~ (*mandāra-stabaka-stanī*) 34,231 (TP III 146)⁹⁷³; *liṅga* to be worshipped with ~ flowers and golden lotuses from Kubera’s lake 51,97 (TP IV 128); garland of ~ flowers, used to crown emperor 110,82 (TP VIII 88); ~ trees 111,15 (TP VIII 96); gods shower ~ flowers⁹⁷⁴ at the end of the battle between men and *Asuras* 118,98 (TP VIII 184)
māṇḍya-vyāja ‘simulation of illness’ 24,168 (TP II 181) and 63,102 (TP V 128); – see: sickness feigned
maṅgala ‘ceremony to ensure good fortune’, performed by king before entering palace 18,23 (TP II 51); ~ by queen for daughter on sea voyage 101,137 (TP VII 143); ~ by mother of king setting out 116,10 (TP VIII 157);
maṅgala-gaja (not MW) ‘state elephant’⁹⁷⁵ choosing king 65,25 (TP V 155)
maṅgalôpāyana (not MW) ‘present offered to secure good luck, welcome present’ to king made by feudatories 18,25 (TP II 51)
mango,⁹⁷⁶ (*āmra-phala*) eaten warm or cold 124,143 (TP IX 78f.);

⁹⁶⁸ Cf. German: “*Baum von Mann*”.

⁹⁶⁹ On the stomach fire see e.g. Doniger O’Flaherty 1988: 10; Saletore 1987: I 25.

⁹⁷⁰ At least in the 1970-80ties, when Fred Kurt stayed in South India, tribesmen of e.g. the Kurumba did not perfume themselves with ichor though it was easily available to them on certain trees where elephants had rubbed their head against (p.c. Kurt). See above sub: ichor.

⁹⁷¹ ORC 4: “*l’éclat du nectar*”.

⁹⁷² See Blatter & Millard 1954 plate XIII and pp. 63f.; Cowen 1970: 28ff.; Shakti 1991: 39f.

⁹⁷³ Syed 1990: 436f.

⁹⁷⁴ Text has *-mandara-*. Heroes fallen on the battle field are compared with ~ and their bloody wounds with the red flowers (Syed 1990: 432). The tree is also called *pārijāta*.

⁹⁷⁵ Cf. Pāli *maṅgala-hatthi* (PED).

⁹⁷⁶ Anderson 2005: 54ff. India produces nearly two thirds of the world’s 1.100 varieties of mangos (*Time* July 2, 2012: 48).

mango tree (*āmra-pādapa*; *Mangifera indica*)⁹⁷⁷ with fruits which when eaten cause death 28,126 (TP III 30); *rāja-haṃsas* on ~ 42,228 (TP III 276); blossoming ~s⁹⁷⁸ by way of bows for Kāma 55,108 (TP IV 209); cluster of ~ blossoms with bees 104,6 (TP VIII 1); 111,12 (TP VIII 95); ~s and poisonous trees 124,130 (TP IX 77); – see also: bee(s); bow; koel; *sāśra*

man-hating woman, see: *puruṣa-dveṣiṇī*

Mañibhadra, younger brother of Kubera 121,3 (TP IX 12)

Mañibhadra temple in Tāmraliptī, adulterers brought to ~ 13,165 (TP I 162); M.-temple compared to mouth of death 13,177 (TP I 163);

manifestation, divine: Caṇḍikā *devī* famous for exceeding readiness to manifest herself (*sāṃnidhyôtkarṣa-śālinī*) (to her votaries) 78,50 (TP VI 194);

mānini-māna ‘female disdain, disdainful woman’, elephant of ~ torn to pieces by lion of spring 55,107 (TP IV 209 ‘female coyness’; ORC 614: ‘*dédain des femmes*’)

mañjūṣā, see: trunk

manna motif,⁹⁷⁹ see: rice divine

mano-mṛgā ‘wild animal of the mind’, gaze ... which was like the catching in a frail net of the ~ 22,49 (TP II 140: “deer of the mind”; ORC 187: “*filet qui enserra lentement ce gibier: leurs coeurs*”; M I 267: “*in den Fangnetzen des Herzens gefangenen Gazelle*”; note 2: *mano-mṛgī*)⁹⁸⁰

Manoratha-dāyaka ‘Giver of desires’, name of wishing-tree 22,18 (TP II 138)

mantha-kālābdhi (not MW) ‘ocean at the time of churning’, the refreshing water of a lake is compared to the ~ 100,15 (TP VII 129 “churned see of doom”; ORC 1036: “*océan au moment du barattement*”; M II 372: “*ähnelte der See dem aufgewühlten Meer beim Weltenuntergang*”)

mantra,⁹⁸¹ – see: fire; policy; sayings; spell; statecraft; – ifc. *baddha-°-sūtra*; *ḍākinī-°-siddhi*; *datta-dṛṅ-°*; *moha-°*; *nāga-damana-°*; *nyasta-°*; *utpatana-°*; *vetāla-sādhana-°*; *vidyādi-°*;

mantra-baddha ‘arrested by a charm’, of snakes 71,104 (TP VI 43)

mantrādhirāja ‘sovereign of spells’, a *vetāla* 99,15 (TP VII 122);

mantra-sādhana ‘performance of an incantation’, for which a *bhikṣu* asks the king’s help 75,35 (TP VI 166)

mantra-tantra ‘spells and ceremonies’ for propitiating Śiva learnable from a treatise on Pātāla 73,104 (TP VI 108)

mantra-toya ‘charmed water’, *yoginī* turns transformed buffalo back into brahmin by sprinkling it with ~ 68,51 (TP VI 5)

⁹⁷⁷ Macmillan 1991: 282.

⁹⁷⁸ Upadhyaya 1965: 9.

⁹⁷⁹ STh D 1030.1.1.

⁹⁸⁰ *Mṛga* here may be an abbreviation metri causa of *śākhā-mṛga* for the mind, i.e. thoughts are usually compared to monkeys as, e.g. Saṃyutta-Nikāya II 95. Schlingloff 1964: 86.

⁹⁸¹ Gonda 1975: IV 248ff.; 1988.

mantra-vādin ‘enchanter’ 73,260ff. (TP VI 119f.);
mantra-vidyā ‘magic art’ 33,59 (TP III 111), see: bewilderment
mantrin ‘conjurer’, ~s muttering charms in lying-in chamber 23,63 (TP II 161)
māṇuṣa-vasā ‘human fat’ candle with ~ as means to find hidden treasures 34,70 (TP III 133)
marakatāsana ‘emerald throne’ (not MW) of princess 72,78 (TP VI 75)⁹⁸²
marāṇa-dharman ‘subject to law of death’, said of mortals 41,17 (TP III 253)
marāṇa-nīścaya as protest of citizens against king 12,25 (TP I 135 with note 1 referring to *dharnā*)
māra-śṛṅkhala (not MW; ‘chain of love’) 7,62 (TP I 80)
mare, see: horse
Mārī (Śītalā, goddess of small-pox) said to fall on people 12,178 (TP I 147); ~, goddess of Death, enters merchant’s house as wife 17,90 (TP II 41)
mariage de raison, see: marriage of convenience
maritime traffic, see: voyage
market (*vipaṇi*), dead fish laughs in ~ 5,16 (TP I 46)
mark(s), nightwatchwoman marks garment of sleeping prince with red lac (*alakta*) to facilitate recognition 3,71 (TP I 23); auspicious ~ (*lakṣaṇa*) painted under girdle of queen 5,32 (TP I 49)⁹⁸³; by sprinkling his wives with water king makes them lose the ~ (*tilaka*) on their forehead 6,112 (TP I 69); grateful snake gives king the art of making ~s that never become indistinct 9,81 (TP I 100); woman resembling world-bewildering drug (*jagat-sammohanāuśadhi*) 15,74 (TP II 8); ~s on feet of newborn prince 23,69 (TP II 162); *tilaka* of an emperor 43,169 (TP III 292); *tilaka* of *Asura* princess as beauty ~ 45,234 (TP IV 33); scratches and bites mark intimacy of queen, etc. with sick people 66,42 (TP V 181); *kṣatriya* boy with auspicious ~s made possessed by spirit (*samāviṣṭa*) 70,56 (TP VI 28); ~s of teeth and nails on princess betray lover 74,242 (TP VI 158); prince makes ~ on intoxicated wife’s hip (*kaṭi-taṭa*)⁹⁸⁴ with red-hot iron spike at night 75,155 (TP VI 175); discus-marked footprint (as *cakra-vartin*) ~ of royalty 86,76 (TP VII 18)⁹⁸⁵; baby son with auspicious ~s at king’s gate 93,55 (TP VII 82); – see also: mole; sign;
marks, inauspicious ~ (*durlakṣaṇā*) of maiden 15,36 (TP II 4) and (*kula-kṣaṇā kanyā*) 15,71 (TP II 8); ~ of Kālarātrī 20,108 (TP II 103)⁹⁸⁶; – see also: attractivity stereotype; nose
marriable single woman is like song out of tune (*sthāna-prāpti-vihīnā gītvat kula-kanyakā*), but one married unsuitably is like learning imparted to unsuited man 24,25f. (TP II 172);
marriage⁹⁸⁷ 10,180 (TP I 118; see supra: inconsistencies); presents at royal ~ 14,60 (TP I

⁹⁸² Also Kādambarī 416,3, cf. 413,3.

⁹⁸³ On human marks see Zysk 2014.

⁹⁸⁴ In vs 176 *jaghana-sthala*.

⁹⁸⁵ Bollée 2008: 45.

⁹⁸⁶ It may be remarked that among the inauspicious signs black ears, about which see Zin 2003: 332ff., are not mentioned.

⁹⁸⁷ Cf. ORC 1605f.; Selwyn 1979; STh *T 100-T 199.

187); ~ of merchants 13,73 (TP I 154); ~ with lower-caste (lit.: unequal) woman (*a-tulya-kula-sambandha*) 21,80 (TP II 131)⁹⁸⁸; girl playing with doll as if with child refuses ~ 24,30 (TP II 172); ~ **conditions** expressed by daughter 24,42f. (TP II 173); Śiva marries chaplain's daughter 24,162 (TP II 181); *vidyādhari* refuses ~ 26,63 (TP II 222); princess marries king owing to boon of brahmin 27,105 (TP III 8); ~ of *vidyādhara* king with unwilling *vidyādhari* 26,245 (TP II 235); ~ of daughter more important for hereafter than begetting son 28,50 (TP III 24); ~ of daughter will unite parents 28,69 (TP III 25); **criteria** of ~ : youth, good looks, noble birth, good disposition and wealth, youth being most important, high birth being of subordinate importance 30,29 (TP III 66); Gaurī sends *asurī* dream with *gāndharva* ~ to divine prince whom she misses after waking up at the end of the night 31,12f. (TP III 82; cf. 33,195 [TP III 123]); ~ made by the gods (*saṃbandham deva-nirmitam*) **34,104** (TP III 136)⁹⁸⁹; women throw grain (*homa-lāja*) at ~ 34,257 (TP III 148); bridegroom's ~ condition: obeisance to *rākṣasa* father-in-law 39,98 (TP III 224); misandrous (*puruṣa-dveṣiṇī*) princess refuses ~ 42,19 (TP III 260); idem, 43,152 (TP III 291); union of royal couple resembles ~ of spring creeper and spring festival (*saṃgamo mādhavī-vallī-vasantōtsavayor iva*) 43,218 (TP III 296); ~ causes enmity if not duly performed 44,119 (TP IV 9); prince refuses ~ in order to perform penance 51,29 (TP IV 124); *kṣatriyā* woman refuses ~ to ugly brahmin but is given to him against her will 52,36 (TP IV 140)⁹⁹⁰; ~ refused by *vidyādhari* due to pride on beauty 52,57 (TP IV 142); ~ refused by *vidyādhara* prince proud on beauty (*rūpa-darpāt*) 52,74 (TP IV 143); ~ **conditions** 52,94 (TP IV 144); **forced** ~⁹⁹¹ of princess averse of ugly brahmin 52,113 (TP IV 146); idem, 52,171 (TP IV 150); ~ **criteria** of a woman: man being hero (saving her life), opulent, young, smart and obedient to her orders 52,336 (TP IV 161); ~ first refused and later insatiable appetite for husbands 52,355 (TP IV 162); royal ~ takes seven days 55,103 (TP IV 209); ~ **conditions** 56,247 (TP IV 237) and 79,9 (TP VI 200); ~ by *svayaṃvara* 56,364 (TP IV 247) and 121,219 (TP IX 28); ~ refusal by female friend to marry before her friend has bridegroom 59,124 (TP V 34); ~ between rich old man and young woman averse (*parāṇmukhī*) to him 62,83f. (TP V 106); marrying ten husbands one after another 66,86 (TP V 184); grandfather (*mātā-maha*) decides about ~ of granddaughter 67,51 (TP V 199); *vidyādhari* chooses husband by *gāndharva* ~ 69,90 (TP VI 15); groom arrives for ~ in the evening 71,156 (TP VI 47); ~ **criteria**: *kula*, *artha* and *karman* **80,13** (TP VI 205); ~ only with knower of one *viñāna* 83,18 (TP VII 3); woman swears to return to lover after ~ 84,26 (TP VII 6); ~ to impaled thief 93,23 (TP VII 79); ~ of merchant's daughter in Viśāla with merchant in Tāmralipti 95,7 (TP VII 98); ~ decided by

Kommentar [B1]:

⁹⁸⁸ Cf. Rājat VII 10 where king Saṃgrāma allows his royal dignity to be lowered by unequal matrimonial relations.

⁹⁸⁹ Cf. Manu IX 95.

⁹⁹⁰ Cf. STh T 268.

⁹⁹¹ Also Daś 136.5.

astrologers in three months on the fifth day of the white fortnight of Kārtika 101,119 (TP VII 142); princess would rather die than marry ugly (*virūpa*) husband 103,18 (TP VII 176); ~ ritual 103,190ff. (TP VII 188); ~ night in royal bed-room 103,206 (TP VII 189); ~ preparations 104,160f. (TP VIII 13); ~ day promise being forgotten by *vidyādhari* princess ceremony should be repeated with own-handed offerings to *yakṣas* 105,50 (TP VIII 24); ~ **condition**: Gandharva princess wants husband able to play *vīṇā* and hymn Viṣṇu Śauri in three scales (*grāma*) 106,12 (TP VIII 29); *vidyādhari* marries king in the air by an artifice 106,85 (TP VIII 34); ~ by artifice 106,85 (TP VIII 34); *divyā stri* becomes wife of hermit 108,72 (TP VIII 59); forced ~ (*vivāhyamānā ... an-icchanti balād aham*) 108,169 (TP VIII 66)⁹⁹²; five *vidyādhari*s agree that they want to marry Naravāhanadatta only collectively 108,181 (TP VIII 67); ~ of younger brother before elder is unfitting 118,124 (TP VIII 186)⁹⁹³; ~ of *apsaras* and gambler 121,116 (TP IX 20); queen complains of being married by force 123,3 (TP IX 43); ~ to distant child-wife who is left in father's house 124,92 (TP IX 74); child-wife stays in father's house 124,105 (TP IX 76); – see also: bridegroom; brother; child marriage; class; daughter; *gāndharva*; gift; maiden; merchant; present; rape; *svayaṃvara*

marriage of convenience 15,25 (TP II 3); 16,112 (TP II 30); 37,210f. (TP III 196)

marriage feast, see: feast

marriage thread, heavenly (*divya-kautuka*) 34,251 (TP III 147); 50,133 (TP IV 116);

marriage to tree⁹⁹⁴, not in KSS text, but in TP I 239; STh T 117.5

Marukaccha, w.r. in D for Bharukaccha, see: Bhṛgukaccha

marū-kṛta (not MW) 'turned into a desert, desertified' 72,373 (TP VI 96)

maru-marīci, see: fata morgana

marut 'breeze', loud and fragrant ~ from earth aperture precedes appearance of *Asura Maya* 45,3 (TP IV 17)

mā sāhasaṃ kṛthāḥ ('do not act rashly') 78,102 (TP VI 197); *mā kṛthāḥ sāhasaṃ* 80,44 (TP VI 207); *mā kārṣiḥ sāhasaṃ* 86,87 (TP VII 19); *mā sāhasaṃ kārṣiḥ* 90,76 (TP VII 54); *mā sāhasaṃ* 119,187 (TP VIII 206);

*māṣas*⁹⁹⁵ of gold, eight ~ 6,51 (TP I 64);

masquerade, see: disguise

mast (Persian)⁹⁹⁶, see: must(h)

Mātali (Indra's charioteer) descends from heaven and gives prince horse which makes invincible 59,68 (TP V 31);

mātā-maha 'maternal grandfather' should give away to bridegroom merchant's daughter who

⁹⁹² Cf. Daś 136,5.

⁹⁹³ STh T 131.2.

⁹⁹⁴ See Haberman 2013: 155; Franziera 2010: 14; Anderson 2005: 56f.; Dallapiccola 2002: 57f.; Gupta 1991: 9f.; Crooke 1906: 317f.; Nair 1965; Schmidt 1904: 405ff.

⁹⁹⁵ See e.g., Collins 1974: 170.

⁹⁹⁶ Straube 2013: 2.

had another mother 67,79 (TP V 202)

mātaṅga-muktā ‘pearl in elephant’s head’, see: pearls

Mātaṅga(s) with king Durga-piśāca 71,11 (TP VI 36) and 102,56 (TP VII 166f.); ~ live on southern slope of Vindhyas 102,33 in Karabhagrīva 55 (TP VII 165f.); ~ identical with Bhillas 102,64 (TP VII 167); their king dark like *tamāla* 102,71 (TP VII 167); description of ~ king 102,71ff. (TP VII 167f.)

*Mātaras*⁹⁹⁷ (‘Ladies’ but often wrongly rendered as “Mothers”), ring of ~ (*mātrī-cakra*) sit under a tree at night with their chief Nārāyaṇī and wait for Bhairava with presents (*upahāra*) 56,76 (TP IV 225); Bhairava sports with ~ as *yoginī* 56,106 (TP IV 227); Kāma worshipped on wedding day by bride in temple of ~ (*Mātrī-deva-kula*) 104,128 (TP VIII 11); lover hides behind statues of ~ 104,131 (TP VIII 11); gambler menaces to saw through images (*pratimā*) of ~ 121,86 (TP IX 18); ~ become broken-hearted (*khinna-mānasa*) and Cāmuṇḍā advises them to sit out of gambling 121,89 (TP IX 18); man seeks refuge in empty temple of ~ near river Veṇā 123,207 and prays to them for help 209 (TP IX 58); coven of witches comes from among the ~ and takes brahmin refugee with them through the air 123,215 (TP IX 58);

matchmaker, see: bard; go-between

maṭha (‘religious establishment’) with fools 65,177 (TP V 168); – see also: monastery

Mathurā,⁹⁹⁸ see: Srinivasan 1989

mātrī-cakra ‘ring of Mātaras’ 56,76 (TP IV 225)⁹⁹⁹

matrimonial relations, see: caste; marriage 21,80 (TP II 131)

mātsya-nyāya, see: ichthyomy

matted hair¹⁰⁰⁰: see ascetic(s); creeper(s); disguise; fire; hair; moon; Pāśupata; yellow

mattress (*tūlikā*), see: bed with seven ~es

mātuluṅga-phala, see: citron

maurvikīṅka 118,11 (TP VIII 178), see: *pauruṣya*

Maya(’s) (an Asura) two sons fight for his magic plate, club and shoes 3,47 (TP I 22); his daughter Somaprabhā 28,100 (TP III 27); ~, *Asura* architect, builds Indra’s palace (*sabhā*) 29,12f. (TP III 40); ~ sent by Śiva to teach prince magic sciences 44,29 (TP IV 3); ~ with black head and crimson robe like streams of cinnabar (*ucchalad-dhātu*) emerges from earth aperture 45,4 (TP IV 17, see: cinnabar, supra); ~ recites Sāṅkhya and Yoga doctrine and teaches magic art of entering another body 45,79 (TP IV 22); wife of ~ on a pillar 45,136 (TP IV 27); as boon from Kaśyapa ~ remains unharmed by sickness and old age 45,407

⁹⁹⁷ See note 190; Rodrigues 2003: 200f.; Bhattacharyya 1999; Kinsley 1986: 151ff.; Bhattacharyya 1993; Joshi 1986. According to Vajracharya in Pal 2009: 127, “the Matrika deities originally do not represent earth mothers but atmospheric phenomena. For this reason the mother goddesses are named after rain, thunder, and lightning.” Therefore the designation “Ladies” is better. Known since Mbh these non-aryan deities represent inauspicious village goddesses particularly inimical to small children (Kinsley 1986: 154f.).

⁹⁹⁸ See also: Karashima 315 note 6 on § 40.8.

⁹⁹⁹ Cf. Dehejia 1986: 28.

¹⁰⁰⁰ Olivelle 1998: 23f.

(TP IV 45); ~ propitiated by Indra 45,412 (TP IV 45); ~ makes opening to Pātāla in Kāśmīra 73,107 (TP VI 108);

*māyā*¹⁰⁰¹ ‘delusive power; enchantment’, Pātāliputra, divine city produced by ~ 3,78 (TP I 24); exchange of son for daughter at birth by Creator’s ~ 34,44 (TP III 131); ~ is the woman who causes the wheel with the bees (*cakraṃ sa-bhṛṅgakam*) of mundane existence (*saṃsāarakam*) to revolve 70,89 and 107 (TP VI 30f.); hermit throws ~ over merchant in love with princess on canvas 72,306 (TP VI 91); by ~ Death creates *divyā strī* in order to catch Sindhavikrama 72,341 (TP VI 94); by ~ Indra burns down forest 72,372 (TP VI 96); abduction of queen by ~ 114,7 (TP VIII 132); 120,130 (TP IX 10); 121,223 (TP IX 28); ~ of Viśvakarman 123,135 (TP IX 52); – see also: blame; nymph(s); *prajñapti māyā-kuśala* ‘hypocritical’ (not MW), said of ascetics 32,126 (TP III 99)

māyā-samāhāra ‘concentrated delusion’ (not MW), body is ~ 38,111 (TP III 214)

māyā-yantra-vimāna, see: chariot; magic car

mealtime, see: *āhāra-samaya*; *bhikṣu-velā*

meaningly (*sākūtaṃ*), see: Disposer; gestures; looking

meat¹⁰⁰² (with pepper given to watch dog) 13,125 (TP I 159); [~, ¹⁰⁰³ drink and raiment given to wicked wife 23,37 (TP II 159)]; Sītā’s sons kill deer and eat its ~ 51,95 (TP IV 128); ~ of goat eaten by rogues 62,68 (TP V 104); buffalo eaten by villagers 62,213 (TP V 117); lion feeds *bodhisattva* with ~ of wild animals / deer-meat (*mṛgāmiṣa*) 65,101 (TP V 162); roasted venison (*hariṇāmiṣa*) eaten by prince 74,112 (TP VI 148); *māṃsa-bhāra* (‘mass of ~ as a gift from host to guests’) 102,113 (TP VII 170); ~ (*piśita*) and wine sacrificed to *yakṣas* 105,57 (TP VIII 25); ~ (*mṛga-māṃsa*) eaten by king Naravāhanadatta 107,10 (TP VIII 43); – see also: cat

meat-curry (*māṃsa-vyañjana*) and ghee as guest food 54,170 (TP IV 196);

meat-seller (*māṃsa-vikrayin*), not indulging in self-consciousness (*nir-ahaṃkāra*), humble 56,181-9 (TP IV 233)

mechanical doll ([*sva-*] *māyā-(sad)-yantra-putrikā*) 29,1 and 18 (TP III 39f.)

meddling, being ruined by ~ with what is not one’s business 60,32 (TP V 44);

mediation (*samaya*) 18,139 (TP II 60); 65,228 (TP V 172)

medicine, lady of heavenly beauty (*kanyā divya-paricchadā*) looks as if she were ~ to restore Smara (Kāma) to life 18, 213 (TP II 66); king asks for ~ against sonlessness 39,6 (TP III 218); king stays in *bhū-grha* with “~ against old age” 40,57f. (TP III 244); king asks physicians to prepare ~ (*auśadha-prayoga*) to make his daughter grow 61,266f. (TP V 91); fool drinks ~ to be used as a clyster 64,15 (TP V 139); husband is distasteful to wife as bitter ~ is to sick man 95,8 (TP VII 98); ~ (*oṣadhī-rasanasya*) of natives (Bhillas) used to heal transformation into boa constrictor 123,46 (TP IX 46); – see also: goat; powder

¹⁰⁰¹ See Goudriaan 1978.

¹⁰⁰² See Saletore 1943: 117f.

¹⁰⁰³ *Āhāra* and *anna* (as in 87,27) are translated by TP as ‘meat’ which is nowhere explained.

meditation arising from fire told by goddess Śaraṇyā (Durgā) manifesting her real form to help Vararuci cast off his body 5,140 (TP I 59); fiery ~ (*dhāraṇā*) (to consume guilt with) 52,259 (TP IV 156); four ~s 64,161 (TP V 151); by intent ~ on brahman youth *kumārī brāhmiṇī* is reborn as courtesan 69,163 (TP VI 20); perfection (*dhyāna-pāramitā*) of ~ 72,283 (TP VI 89); hermit starts ~ to avert evil (*duṣṭa-ghnīm abadhṇād yoga-dharaṇām*) 73,135 (TP VI 111); royal couple finds out real state of things by supernatural powers of ~ (*sva-vidyānudhyānād yathā-vṛttam avetya*) 90,157 (TP VII 60); ~ (*dhyāna-sthau*) by two dogs refusing food 114,127 (TP VIII 142)

meeting at sun-rising mountain (*udaya-parvata*) 18,241 (TP II 68); secret ~ in isolated (*vivikta*) temple 30,76 (TP III 69); unexpected ~s (*a-sambhāvyaḥ ... samāgamāḥ*) take place for men in this world 120,8 (TP IX 1)

mekhalā ‘girdle’¹⁰⁰⁴, see: queen

melancholy (*vicintita*) due to ignorance of grammar 6,130 (TP I 70); ~ (*cintā*) childlessness 35,27 and 30 (TP III 157); ~ of lonely woman 86, 108 (TP VII 21); – see also: depression; lone woman

memory, of everything heard only once, Vararuci has ~ 2,37 (TP I 12)¹⁰⁰⁵; austerities produce ~ of pre-births 40,106 (TP III 248); loss of ~ (*naṣṭa-smṛti*) 52,178 (TP IV 150); – see also: pre-birth; recollection; remembering

men, are ever miserable (*manuṣyā nitya-duḥkhitāḥ*) 1,47 (TP I 6); merchant daughter dislikes ~ (*puṁ-dveṣiṇī*) 88,9 (TP VII 35); – see also: misandry; *puruṣa-dveṣiṇī*

mendicant (*pravrajaka*) performing magic rite sitting on corpse 18,152 (TP II 62); ~ mounts shoulder of corpse vitalised by *vetāla* in order to pick up princess for a sacrifice to Durgā 18,156 (TP II 62); Śiva disguises himself as (Digambara) ~ (*kṣapaṇaka*) 20,132 (TP II 106 “Buddhist mendicant”; ORC 168 “*moine mendiant*”; M I 240: “*Gestalt eines buddhistischen Mönches*”); ~¹⁰⁰⁶ in dream gives queen fruit 21,147 (TP II 136); ~ daily bringing gem in box (*samudgagam*) 38,47 (TP III 209), cf. 75,23 (TP VI 165); *yakṣa* gives ~ (*pravraj*) boon of invincibility in disputation, altercation and gambling 66,61 (TP V 82); ~s first fat by being content with alms become thin by dissatisfaction after tasting food with six flavours 62,181f. (TP V 114f.); princess unites herself with (*pravrajā ... saṁgamyā*)¹⁰⁰⁷ ~ 64.90 (TP V 146); king kills wicked ~ with a blow of his sword 99,18 (TP VII 123); – see also: ascetic; hermit; sex

menstruating woman¹⁰⁰⁸ (*kanyā-vrata-sthā*) 26,55 (TP II 221); *rajasvalā* shows to be ~ by placing the impression of three fingers dipped in red dye (*sālakṭakāṅgulī-mudrā-trayaṁ*) on her heart 75,113 (TP VI 172 omits)

¹⁰⁰⁴ Ghurye 1966: 258ff.

¹⁰⁰⁵ This is also a quality of “certain” Jain monks (Schubring § 181 note 4).

¹⁰⁰⁶ Such male figures in dreams of women are generally positive (Abt 1996a: 341 and 388f.).

¹⁰⁰⁷ *Sam* √*GAM* in the sense of ‘to have sex with’ governs the accusative (MW).

¹⁰⁰⁸ Cf. Rājāt VI 270. – On menstruation see Schmidt 1904: 202ff.; Meyer 1952: 225.

menstruation, woman inaccessible for four days monthly and not questionable about it 86,110ff.

(TP VII 21); – see also: period; *rajasvalā*; three fingers

mention, falling in love by mere ~ 11,83 (TP I 128); *vacanair ... apahṛta-mānasā* 22,93 (TP II 143); 30,69 (TP III 68); – see further: love

merchant(s) are greedy of wealth 3,54 (TP I 22); woman disguises herself as ~ (*vaṇig-veṣaṃ cakāra*) 13,179 (TP I 163); ~ caravan attacked by robbers 29,117 (TP III 47); ~ sells wife for horses 43,86ff. (TP III 287); ~ entrusts only son to bawd to learn the tricks of courtesans 57,58 (TP V 5); ~ anointed king 65,26 (TP V 155); shipwrecked ~ finds shipwrecked love in āśram 67,68ff. (TP V 200f.); robbed ~ enters fire with his wife when seeing two *rāja-haṃsas* and by this *nidāna* they are reborn as such 69,128 (TP VI 18); ~ falling in love with a painting of a princess as substitute 72,294 (TP VI 90); ~ daughter dislikes male sex (*pum-dveṣiṇī*) 88,9 (TP VII 35); ~ abducts princess with ship 101,268 (TP VII 152); – see also: daughter ; men; misandry; sea

merit, germ of ~ (*puṇya-bījam*) watered with aspiration (*siktaṃ saṃkalpa-vāriṇā*) bears fruit 27,121 (TP III 10); transfer of ~ 34,89 (TP III 135; 63,87 (TP V 126), 84,23 (TP VII 6) and (*upakṛti*) 123,162 (TP IX 55, see further: transfer); tree of ~ (*puṇya-taru*) 39,78 (TP III 223); deity's pending conception in body of sow due to exhaustion of ~ (*puṇya-kṣaya*) avoided by recourse to Śiva on Indra's advice 53,118 (TP IV 176); transfer of ~ only permanent thing in *saṃsāra* is ~ (*su-kṛta*) acquired by means of this body 94,107 (TP VII 94); revealing own ~s (*su-kṛtôdiraṇa*) makes *cakravartins* fall from their position 113,8 (TP VIII 124);

mermaid (*kanyā*), king gives *āsuri* ~ to *kārpaṭika* as wife 81,105 (TP VI 216); ~ on wishing-tree sings song of karman 86,44f. (TP VII 16) and 77 (TP VII 19); two ~s 120,105ff. (TP IX 8f.) and 121,225 (TP IX 28); do, save people shipwrecked 120,112 (TP IX 9)¹⁰⁰⁹; – see also: *divya-kanyā*

messenger¹⁰¹⁰ of good news given present (*datta-prābhṛtaṃ dūtam*) 17,164 (TP II 48); ~ (of death, she-jackal as ~) 29,106 (TP III 46); ~ of princess choosing king as husband honoured with gold, etc. 31,59 (TP III 87); ~ with letter of death 42,91 (TP III 265); ~ rewarded (*sat-kṛtya*) 44,65 (TP IV 5); 44,158 (TP IV 11); all qualities of ~ (*dūta-guṇa*) **46,135** (TP IV 57); ~ and brahmin must not be slain 46,166 (TP IV 59); feigned ~ of Viṣṇu orders king to make peace with other king 49,76 (TP IV 90); **description**¹⁰¹¹ of brahmin sent as ~ to ask for beloved princess 55,86f. (TP IV 208); speaking gander (*rāja-haṃsa*) caught by Damayantī offers to be ~ of Kāma to Nala 56,242 (TP IV 237); ~ sent to invite for Damayantī's second *svayaṃvara* 56,364 (TP IV 247); *ceṭi* as ~ 56,403 (TP IV 249); ~ with written message (*lekhe likhītvā*) 59,146 (TP V 36); king's ~ sent to prince to make him return 67,27ff. (TP V 198); brahmin sent as ~ 79,11 (TP VI 201); ~ sent with painting to ask for (hand of) princess 101,92f. (TP VII 140); Śabara as ~ with letter (*lekha-hāra*)

¹⁰⁰⁹ Cf. STh R 137.

¹⁰¹⁰ Saletore 1943: 256ff.

¹⁰¹¹ Cf. Kauṭ (Kangle) 1,16,1ff.

101,349 (TP VII 158); do, with hair in a knot tied with a creeper, dark and with loin-cloth of bilva leaves (*kaṭi-nivasanam bilva-patramayam*) 101,355 (TP VII 158); without an army a king has no possibility to send a ~ (*dūta-preṣaṅhāhatā*) 102,96 (TP VII 169); qualities of ~ (*dūta-guṇa*) 102,129 (TP VII 173); king's wrath at ~ inviolable (*a-vadhya*) 102,146 (TP VII 173); ~ with oral message 103,93 (TP VII 181); ~ with letter and oral message (*lekhe dūta-mukhe ca*) 103,147 (TP VII 185); grey harbinger of death seizes king's hair (*palitena kṛtānta-dūtena kaca-grahaḥ kṛtaḥ*) 103,226 (TP VII 190); look from the reverted corner from woman's eye as ~ of love (*prīti-dūti*) 104,31 (TP VIII 3); attendant-messenger gets necklace from prince as reward 117,116 (TP VIII 172); hermit gives pupil, cursed to be a riding animal (*vāmana*, here: a bird), to king as ~ 118,56f. (TP VIII 182); ~ tells king of conquests and is loaded with garments, ornaments and villages 120,75ff. (TP IX 6); ~ with letter in his hand (*lekha-hasta*) 123,330 and (~) with letter (*lekha-hāra*) 334 (TP IX 66); ~ of Vikramāditya (without letter) asks for Kaliṅga king's daughter 124,31 (TP IX 70); – see also: *pratidūta*; reward

metaphor, see: attractivity stereotype; beauty; elephant; ghee; lion; lotus; mind; moon; ocean; sayings; sea; sun; tree

meteor, resplendent woman looks like ~ fallen from cloud 21,72 (TP II 130)

mice (or moles: *mūṣaka*) turn hut into anthill (?¹⁰¹² *Mūṣakaiḥ kṛta-valmikaṃ*) 2,49 (TP I 13; ORC 10: “*Les rats en avaient fait une fourmilière*”; MI 15: “*Mäuse hatten es nahezu in einen Ameisenhaufen verwandelt*”); ~ (*ākhu*) eat particularly sweet iron balance 60,240 (TP V 62)¹⁰¹³; ~ dig holes in Himavat 62,132 (TP V 110); teacher plagued by ~ at night 65,159 (TP V 167); – see also: mouse

Midas, see: donkey

midday, sound of conch at ~ 29,48 (TP III 42); ~ sacrifice or ablution (*mādhyam̐dina-savana*) 45,386 (TP IV 43); 69,167 (TP VI 21); ~ as time for royal bath (*snāna-velā*) announced by warder (*pratihāra*) 86,24 (TP VII 15); – see also: conch

midwife, see: *garbha-grāhikā*

milk, prince and entourage live on ~, etc. in hermitage 70,46 (TP VI 27); woman brought up on goat's ~ 82,36 (TP VI 212); son bathed with ~ flowing from mother's breast at seeing him (*tad-āloka-snuta-stanair*) 110,109 (TP VIII 90)¹⁰¹⁴; 112,105 (TP VIII 114); – see also: lactation

milk-rice, see: *kṣīriṇī*

mind compared to female wild animal (*mano-mṛgī*)¹⁰¹⁵, its catching to the frail net of mutual gaze

¹⁰¹² The anthill must here be meant metaphorically for a small rubble heap. The meaning of *valmika* cannot be found exactly (König 1984: 20). It can stand for anthill and the higher termite hill. As Varṣa is a poor brahmin his hut will have been small and therefore *valmika* was rendered here by anthill.

¹⁰¹³ See STh J 1531.2; Karashima 2012: 97 note 2 on § 12.8. – On rodents' addiction to sugar see Lambert 2011: 66f.

¹⁰¹⁴ Cf. Bollée 2008a: 22. On lactating out of pregnancy see: lactation.

¹⁰¹⁵ Thus TP II 140 note 2; the text reads: *mano-mṛgā-*.

of a couple (*manda-vāgurābandha-saṃnibha*) 22,49 (TP II 140); woman's ~ (*āśaya*) terrible and black like a dark well (*ghana-tāmasaḥ andha-kūpa iva*) 77,72 (TP VI 188); mind-born (*mānasa*)¹⁰¹⁶ son, of Śrī 59,96 (TP V 33); ~ of chaste father 61,250 (TP V 89); Andhaka, ~ of Pārvatī, killed by Śiva 114,80 (TP VIII 138)

ministers,¹⁰¹⁷ king depending on wise ~ 15,59 (TP II 6); ~ approve of king performing *tapas* 19,5 (TP II 84); ~ tested 34,194 (TP III 142f.); realm left to care of ~ 55,155 (TP IV 212) and *mantri-vinyasta-rājya* 81,70 (TP VI 213); wise ~ must penetrate their master's character 60,33 (TP V 44); ~ symbolize kings arms 70,125 (TP VI 33); prince dependent on clever (*mahā-prajña*) ~ 75,103ff. (TP VI 171); young king entrusts realm to ~ and is in harem only 86,7 (TP VII 13); king puts burden of realm into hands of ~ (*hasta-nyasta-rājya-bhara*) 86,70 (TP VII 18); ~ guard kingdom while king is on pilgrimage 93,71 (TP VII 83); ~ guard kingdom while king visits other king 101,215 (TP VII 149); – see also: advice; king; realm

minstrels (*māgadha*), songs of ~ 14,21 (TP I 183); 34,127 (TP III 137); Naravāhanadatta surpasses all ~ 34,171 (TP III 140)¹⁰¹⁸; ~ at marriage 34,262 (TP III 148); – see also: bards; herald; musician

miracle, see *om*

mirror (*pratibimba*), boy shows second father in ~ 14,55 (TP I 186);

misandry¹⁰¹⁹ 42,19 (TP III 260); 88,9 (TP VII 35); – see also: daughter; marriage; *puṃ-dveṣiṇī*; *puṃ-dveṣiṇī*

miscarriage of brahmin woman (*vibhraṣṭa-garbhā*) when kicked by *dhobi* 72,209 (TP VI 84);

miser (*kināśa*), brahmin 24,87 (TP II 176)

misfortune, for whom is the object called woman not the cause of ~s ? (*strī-nāma viṣayo nidānaṃ kasya nāpadām ?*) 15,141 (TP II 14); marriage with (someone from) an unequal family (*a-tulya-kula-sambandha*) is ~ 21,80 (TP II 131); woman is cause of ~ through jealousy 15,141 (TP II 14); when cracks appear ~s multiply (*chidreṣv an-arthā yānti bhūrītām*) 28,181 (TP III 35); – see: class; statecraft;

misogamy (hating marriage), see: daughter; misandry; *puṃ-dveṣiṇī*

misogynous tirade of minister who did not take poisonous drink offered by scorned woman 34,177 (TP III 141);

miss universe 18,85 (TP II 55); *khyāta-rūpā jagat-traye* 31,63 (TP III 87); 32,28 (TP III 92); *lokāika-sundarī* 44,42 (TP IV 4); ~ (*jagat-tritaya-sundarī*) 69,49 (TP VI 12); *trailokya-sundarī* 52,341 (TP IV 162); *sarva-lokāika-sundarī* 66,137 (TP V 188); *lokāika-sundarī* 73,251 (TP VI 119); Naravāhanadatta's queens called ~ (*trailokya-sundarī*) 105,3 (TP VIII 21); do, 108,117 (TP VIII 62); ~, king of Siṃhala's daughter, elects Vikramāditya

¹⁰¹⁶ Mind-born are also the seven ṛṣis (Bhag X 6).

¹⁰¹⁷ Cf. ORC 1609.

¹⁰¹⁸ See Sivaramamurti 1980: 81.

¹⁰¹⁹ Cf. Chojnacki 2008: (I) 352 s.v. *haine du genre masculin*. Misandry is not a quality of some women but thought to be a demon possessing them (122,82 [TP IX 40]).

by *svayaṃ-vara* 121,219 (TP IX 28); ~ (*lokâika-sundarî*) 124,173 (TP IX 80)
mithyā-panḍitā as term of abuse for queen 6,126 (TP I 70)
mlecchas and *Turuṣkas* destroyed near Sindh 19,108f. (TP II 93); ~ are *Asuras* incarnate
(*mleccha-rūpâvatīrṇa*) 99,33 (TP VII 124)¹⁰²⁰ and 120,19 (TP IX 2); *Asuras* slain by Śiva
and Viṣṇu are reborn as ~ 120,19 who cut off the share of the gods of the sacrifices and thus
exhaust the world of the gods 120,21f. (TP IX 2f.)
modaka ‘sweet’¹⁰²¹, only son of prostitute gets ~ every day 106,96 (TP VIII 35)
môdakaiḥ, word play ‘not with water’ and ‘with sweets’ 6,114 (TP I 69)
mode of address, see: address; *ārya-putra*; *bharṭṛ-dāraka*; confidante; *deva*; mother; son
modelling¹⁰²² (*pusta* ?) 34,172 (TP III 140; ORC 344: “*sculpture*”; M I 485: “*Buchkunst*”);
modesty (*hrepaṇa*), princess acts out of ~ 83,15f. (TP VII 3)
moha ‘delusion’, see Prithipaul 1988
moha-mantra, see: spell
mohanâstra (‘bewildering weapon’), of the *apsaras* *Urvaśi* in the hand of *Kāma* 17,5 (TP II
34); ~ used against *Asuras* 118,89 (TP VIII 184);
mohândha-tamasa (not MW) ‘dense darkness of bewilderment’ of brahmin whose wife was
abducted 87,18 (TP VII 30 has “despondency” for *moha*; ORC 962: “*désespoir*”; M II 269:
“*Verwirrung*”)
moha-niśā ‘night > darkness of delusion’ 72,313 (TP VI 92)
mohinî ‘bewildering’ science 46,110 obtained after enduring snake bites for seven days 46,121
(TP IV 56; TP II 212 note: *mohanî* ‘bewitching’)
mokṣa, see: emancipation
*mokṣa-dvāra*¹⁰²³ ‘door of deliverance’, see: lust
¹mole (*lakṣaṇa*) painted under queen’s girdle 5,32 (TP I 49); ~ (*tilaka*) on woman’s nose must
have a counterpart on breast: auspicious marks 49,205 (TP IV 99); –
²mole (*mūṣaka*), see: mice
monarchy against polyarchy 18,136 (TP II 60 with note 1); gods introduced ~ out of fear of
ichthyomy 102,63 (TP VII 167)
monastery (*maṭha*) of brahmins entertaining guests 18,106 (TP II 57); 25,63 (TP II 195); ~ of
Buddhists (*vihāra*) 65,132 (TP V 165), see: *śramaṇa*; 122,62 (TP IX 38); bard (*bandî*)
enters ~ (*maṭha*) to get food 122,73 (TP IX 39); ~ built by *Sūryavatî* of Kashmir (q.v.) for
brahmins of various lands, hospitable even to (fugitive) kings and daily dispelling the distress
of the needy E 5f. (TP IX 88) ; – see also: *maṭha*
money is likened to extracorporeal life to brahmin 33,156 (TP III 120); ~ eaten by monkey and

¹⁰²⁰ As the *Asuras* are the Iranian *ahuras* this may be a vague recollection of the Iranian origin of the *Mlecchas* for which see Halbfass 1992: 107ff. In EWAI s.v. Penzer in his treatment of the *Asuras* in TP I 197ff. does not connect them with *mlecchas*. Mayrhofer rejects an association of the word *mleccha* with a geographical name.

¹⁰²¹ Prakash 1961: 112 et passim.

¹⁰²² Cf. perhaps what is called *daga-maṭṭiya* in the list of *kalās* in Rāyapaseṇiya § 806 (Bollée 2005a: 190f.).

¹⁰²³ In Mbh name of the sun (MW).

vomited 57,139 (TP V 11); wife dear to husband as ~ dear to miser 95,10 (TP VII 98); mongoose¹⁰²⁴ kills snake 60,236 (TP V 61); idem, but is killed itself inconsiderately 64,8-10 (TP V 138)¹⁰²⁵

monk, see: ascetic; Buddhist; Digambara; hermit;

monkey placed into basket adrift on Ganges 15,45 (TP II 5); immoral conduct of false hermit represented as ~ 15,50 (TP II 5); mutual gaze of two youngsters is like catching the ~ of the mind (*mano-mṛgā*)¹⁰²⁶ in a frail net 22,49 (TP II 140 “deer of the mind” with note 2: *mano-mṛgī*); ~s enter wonderful world created by Maya’s *māyā* searching for Sītā 29,61 (TP III 43); eyes of ~ like rubies (*padma-rāgāv akṣiṇī*) 37,88 (TP III 189)¹⁰²⁷; ~ with human voice is transformed brahmin 37,89 (TP III 189) by means of thread around neck 37,116 (TP III 191); ~ with intelligence and articulate speech 37,118 (TP III 191); adulterer turned into ~ 37,130 (TP III 192); ~s thoughtless, imitating others 46,74f. (TP IV 54); ~ devours thousand dinars 57,137 (TP V 11); cruelty to ~ : struck with fist and killed with stick 57,166 (TP V 13); ~ killed by pulling wedge between plank halves 60,31 (TP V 44); ~s kill bird giving them good advice 60,209 (TP V 59)¹⁰²⁸; ~ throws *udumbara* fruits to dolphin (*śiśumāra*) which it eats 63,98 (TP V 128); heart of ~ desired by wife of dolphin 63,116 (TP V 129); ~ (*kapi*) tries to oppress woman who kills it with the help of Ābhīra in exchange for promised sex 64,34-40 (TP V 141); boy scratched by hairy fruit eaters (~s) 64,23 (TP V 140); ~ hit by *rāja-haṃsī*, falls on and tears net with *rāja-haṃsī*’s husband 69,146 (TP VI 19); ~ friend of boar (Bodhisattva) 72,121 (TP VI 78); god Dharma transforms ~ into *muni* 72,149 (TP VI 80); ~ eats fruit with gem 75,27 (TP VI 166); sad ~ points out another path to brahmin in forest and so asks his help to liberate his wife fettered by a mass of creepers 123,56 (TP IX 47); grateful ~ gives brahmin couple fruit that made them no longer liable to old age and disease 123,63ff. (TP IX 47)

monsoon (*prāvṛṣṭ*), in ~ women start making Priapic rolls 2,56 (TP I 13); armies compared to ~ clouds 19,59 (TP II 89); bridegroom adorned by his wife Vidyumālā, as ~ , by the lightning garland 44,179 (TP IV 13); in ~ *rāja-haṃsas* stay near Mānasa lake 69,131 (TP VI 18); *tamāla*-forests in the Deccan are dark like birthplace of ~ (*prāvṛṣo janma-bhūriva*) 73,30 (TP VI 102f.); ~ causes inundation of river Vipāśa 74,190f. (TP VI 154); ~ (*ghanāgama*) bearing a brandished sword of lightning 78,23 (TP VI 192); Rāma stays (in the south) during the ~ (*varṣāḥ*) 107,24 (TP VIII 44); emperor remains ~ (*varṣā-kāla*) in hermitage of Kaśyapa 111,105 (TP VIII 104); emperor spends ~ with twenty-five wives in Kaśyapa’s hermitage 114,4 (TP VIII 132); ~ as an elephant (*prāvṛṣ-kāla-mada-dvipa*) coming down on the forest of heats 122,66 (TP IX 38); – see also: summer

¹⁰²⁴ See Meulenbeld 1974: 480f.

¹⁰²⁵ STh B 331.2 with dog for mongoose.

¹⁰²⁶ See *mano-mṛgā* supra.

¹⁰²⁷ Dreaming of being abducted by a monkey with red eyes leads soon to death (Svapnac 2,84), but v. Negelein does not mention a species. At Kuv 20.8 having red eyes means ferocious.

¹⁰²⁸ See Bollée 1988: 48 where the reference in Harṣakula (Sūyagaḍa ed. Bombay, s. 1936: 119) should be added.

month of spring (*madhu-māsa*), brahmin like ~ with loveliness of the moon free from dew 89,40 (TP VII 43)
 mood, of cheerful (*utsāha-sālin* [not MW]) king 35,95 (TP III 163); – see further: gestures; grief; melancholy; valour
 moon, in upstanding yellow¹⁰²⁹ tufts of Śiva’s matted hair (*piṅgalōttuṅga-jaṭā-jūṭa-gata*) young (? TP “new”; ORC 4: “*nouvelle lune*”)¹⁰³⁰ enjoys touching the eastern mountain yellow in the evening twilight 1,18 (TP I 3); ~ springing from the sea 1,39 (TP I 5); maiden with face like full ~ (*pūrṇa-candra-mukhī*) 4,6 (TP I 30 with note 1¹⁰³¹); princess Śrī looks like presiding goddess of ~ (*candrasya ... adhidevatā*) 7,61 (TP I 80); anxiety clouds heart as a dark spot (*kalaṅka-lekhā*)¹⁰³² does the full ~ 10,182 (TP I 119); king like ~ pleasing to the eyes (*śaśīva locanānando*) 12,24 (TP I 134)¹⁰³³; boy like rising young > waxing ~ (*nūtanēndūdayaḥ*) 13,58 (TP I 153); sea advances to meet rising ~ 16,73 (TP II 27); king sees P. surpassing with the full ~ of her face the circle of the full ~ (*Padmāvatīm antar dadarśa rājā pūrṇa-vaktrēndu-jīta-pūrṇēndu-maṅḍalām*) 16,77 (TP II 27); king sees queen returned from banishment like orb of ~ freed from eclipse 16,105 (TP II 29); night lighted by three ~s 17,111 (TP II 43); pretty women as soldiers of ~ 18,12 (TP II 50); splendour of palace is as that of rising ~ 18,24 (TP II 51); setting ~ comes to ascend pyre of ending night (as of her husband: *gate ’staṃ rajanī-patau citārohāya tad-raśmi-ramyāṃ rātrim ivā*

¹⁰²⁹ See Hopkins 1915 § 44.

¹⁰³⁰ The new moon being invisible *nava* must mean ‘young > waxing’, i.e. visible, but not full here. Śiva is *sārdha-candra* 25,81 (TP II 196); 108,82 (TP VIII 60).

¹⁰³¹ Penzer remarks that this seems hardly complementary from an English point of view (because the English do not like the form which is associated with fat [Polden; Feldhaus, p.c.]), but will be understood by those who have seen the full moon in the East. At any rate the Indian compliment, which Mette (p.c.) thought would base on the connection of cool (cf. *śīta-kara*, *śīta-pāṇi* ‘moon’) with pleasant, actually seems to pertain to the bright radiation, aura, as emerges from 75,129; the designation of the bull Nandi as *candrōjḥvala*, and names such as Kāñcanaprabhā (51,16), and the form, as is shown by 16,75 and 28,102, cf. 9,41 where a princess is *mūrtim ivāindavīm*, see ORC 56 and note 2 on p. 1345. The same is true e.g., in the Arabian Night 740 where a youngster with radiating face like the full moon emerges from the sea, and in no 742 where a baby boy is called Badr Bāsim ‘Smiling full moon’. Indians usually have no round faces (despite the *ānana-maṅḍala* at Kād 185,2) such as have Malayans or East-Asians, and therefore the compliment could refer to something relatively rare, such as a white teint, in the same way as pearls are called cold because they resemble to the white hue of the cold moon (vide infra sub pearl). For a picture of a goddess in Angkor with a round face see Giteau 1976: 171 (plate 103); Albanese 2011: 222. The hue may thus have been the main criterion, just as the colour of a white horse is compared to that of the moon [74,77], and a dark one in proper names such as Kṛṣṇā and Śyāmā(vatī) (p. c. M. Zin). Finally it may be remembered that the moon, present also in their first night, thus is the first husband of all women in RV 10,85,40; see also Varenne 1962: 253.

The western view of a moon face is confirmed by “America’s Finest News Source, the ONION” when in an update of Nov. 14, 2012 it ironically writes: “The Onion is proud to announce that North Korean supreme leader Kim Jong-un, 29, has officially been named the newspaper’s Sexiest Man Alive for the year 2012. With his devastatingly handsome, round face ... (he) is every woman’s dream come true” (www.theonion.com/articles/kim-jongun-). See also Jackmuth 2002: 35ff. for the topos woman : moon.

¹⁰³² Cf. Raghuvamśa XIII 15.

¹⁰³³ Thus, against Hopkins 1915: 44 (p. 90), the moon is not only the type of female loveliness.

gatām) 25,140 (TP II 201); ~ truly beautiful when accompanied by Kārttikā in comparison with Madanamañcukā 34,251 (TP III 147); Rohiṇī dear to ~ 35,23 (TP III 156); new ~ causes high tide (*kalā*) 35,114 (TP III 164); ~ refreshes exhausted partridges 42,148 (TP III 270); princess coming forward to dance compared to the ~ come to the under world out of curiosity 45,233 (TP IV 33); black *Asurī* princess with face like full ~ 45,333 (TP IV 39); face like autumn ~ (*śāradêndu*) 47,107 (TP IV 73); woman longs to drink in man with her eyes, as the female partridge longs to drink the ~ 49,211 (TP IV 99); ~ , angry at his son's death, comes down and fights with killer 50,23 (TP IV 109); *vidyādhari* princess disturbs prince's heart as ~ disturbs heart of sea 51,7 (TP IV 122); daughter growing like digit of ~ 51,22 (TP IV 123); ~ *āryā* as signature verse for Nala 56,358 (TP IV 246); full ~ gladdens the lovely water of the ocean 56,422 (TP IV 251); after seeing *vidyādhari*, prince is disturbed like the sea, when it beholds the orb of the ~ 59,6 (TP V 26); ~ (*soma*) entering pregnant queen's mouth in dream 59,61 (TP V 30); special dish (*kṛsara*)¹⁰³⁴ at change of ~ (*parvan*) 61,99 (TP V 76); hare as ambassador of ~ 62,37 (TP V 101); prince as second ~ without spot on its surface 67,13 (TP V 197); ~ (*śītāmśu*) as ear-ornament (*karṇa-pūra*) on the dark eastern quarter (*vāsava-diś*), made of a shoot from the wishing tree of love 72,27 (TP VI 70)¹⁰³⁵; princess seems like the orb of the autumn ~ lapped in a fragment of a white cloud 73,340 (TP VI 125); horse white as ~ (*śaśāṅka-dhavalā*) 74,77 (TP VI 145); eastern quarter adorns its face with the rising ~ as with a *tilaka* 74,187 (TP VI 154); a woman with a face like a full ~ is shedding forth beauty like beams (*pūrṇāmṛtāmśu-vadanām prasarat-kānti-candrikām ... Rākā-niśām iva*) 75,129 (TP VI 173)¹⁰³⁶; *divyākṛtiḥ kanyā* with face surpassing ~ 75,68 (TP VI 169); female beauty with face like full ~ at midnight (*pūrṇêndu-mukhī*) 82,29 (TP VI 219); cold-rayed ~ (*hima-dīdhiti*) ascends eastern mountain 84,42 (TP VII 7); rays of ~ (*hima-tviṣaḥ karāḥ*) burn delicate queen 85,16f. (TP VII 11); ~ comes out of sea 86,48 (TP VII 16); ~ as eye of the world (*jagan-netra*) 89,5 (TP VII 40); description of ~'s rise **94,57f.** (TP VII 91); at sunset heaven places ~ on its western quarter like *tilaka* on the forehead 95,67 (TP VII 102); ~ as own brother to the curved corner of an angry, long-eyed beauty's eye and as driving hook of the elephant of the mountain of sunrise (Udayācala) 103,204 (TP VII 189); ~ is fire (*candro'gniḥ*) to a lover separated from his beloved 104,75 (TP VIII 6) and 113,75 (TP VIII 129); ~ is main friend of love (*smarāika-suhṛt ... niśā-nātha*) 104,112 (TP VIII 9); ~ as an umbrella (*candrātapatra*) with Gaṇeśa's red trunk as coral handle 105,2 (TP VIII 21); does not the ~, when it is in a state of weakness, spend some time within the circle of the sun ? 106,41 (TP VIII 31); ~ as lover of the night (*rajanī-ramaṇa*) 106,50 (TP VIII 31); ~ looks like face-ornament of nymph of the eastern quarter (*prācī-dig-vadhū-mukha-maṇḍana*) 106,50 (TP VIII 32); half-moon on Śiva's head 108,82 (TP VIII 60); queen resembles night in being moon-faced 110,135 (TP VIII 92); *Gandharva*

¹⁰³⁴ Also ṢaḍvBr V 2 etc., see Om Prakash 1961: 11 et passim (index 331).

¹⁰³⁵ The moon is the main friend of love 104,112 (TP VIII 9).

¹⁰³⁶ In note 1 Penzer refers to Kṣemendra and Bṛhatkathāmañjarī for an expatiation of this theme.

kings go to inviolable (*a-dhṛṣya*) world of the ~ (*soma-loka*) 115,78 (TP VIII 149); do, (*soma-bhuvana*) 115,91 (TP VIII 150); Gandharva princess born on ~ 117,17 (TP VIII 165); divine assembly (*deva-sthāna*) on full ~ day in Caitra (*Caitra-śukla-dina*) 118,17 (TP VIII 179); ~ rose with reddish light (*ālohita-cchaviḥ*), the forest fire of separated lovers 119,166 (TP VIII 204; ORC 1252: “*la lune au teint pourpre se leva, incendie consumant comme une forêt les amants séparés*”; M II 665: “*... ging der Mond in rotem Glanz auf. Er glich einem Feuer, das die Männer ... wie einen Wald verbrennt*”); heavenly maiden with body white like ~ 120,105 (TP IX 9); – see also: act of truth; night; sayings moon-face (*mukhēndu*) 72,32 (TP VI 70); *candra-bimba-vadana* 87,14 (TP VII 30); – see further: face; moon

moon-rays like fiery fingers, moon resembles to lover as with ~ 104,113 (TP VIII 9)

moonstone (*candra-kānta*) dissolves at beholding the moon 29,183 (TP III 53 with note 2); woman with face like ~ 84,48 (TP VII 8); emperor sits on ~ slab in garden 111,16 (TP VIII 96)

morning (*vibhāvarī*), waking up in the ~ after dream 23,10 (TP II 157); drinking spirits in the ~ 40,5 (TP III 240); in the ~ king rises and performs his necessary duties 51,210 (TP IV 136) and 52,30 (TP IV 140); king bathes in the ~ and worships Śiva 54,214 (TP IV 199); *tūrya-śabdāḥ* in the ~ wake princess up 73,360 (TP VI 126); ~ announced by song 103,212 (TP VII 189)¹⁰³⁷; – see also: call of nature; dream; night

mort (hunting shout) (*mṛgayu-grāma-nināda*) 27,151 (TP III 12)

mortal(s), river that cannot be crossed by ~ before border of land of Siddhas 18,350 (TP II 75); *yakṣa* is cursed to become ~ 34,74 (TP III 134); ~ are subject to law of death 41,17 (TP III 253); abduction of *vidyādhari* by ~ 56,174 (TP IV 150); Śrī conceives a mind-born son (*putram mānasam*) from hermit 59,95 (TP V 33); ascetic impregnates *dyu-stri*, cooks her child, eats of it and follows her into the air 108,76 (TP VIII 59); – (re)birth as ~, see: birth; body; curse

mortality, maternal ~ see: death in childbed

mosaic,¹⁰³⁸ pavement of costly ~ (*kuṭṭima*)¹⁰³⁹ in palace 117,14 (TP VIII 165); – see also: terrace

moth (*pataṅga*), how can you, a servant, dare to set yourself up against your master ?

... do you wish to be shrivelled like a moth in the fire of his wrath ? (*tat-pratāpāgnau śalabhāyitum*)¹⁰⁴⁰ 124,34 (TP IX 70)

mother, as mode of address of woman with whom one does not want intimacies 25,141 (TP II 201); ~ performs auspicious rites before son’s departure 42,83 (TP III 265) and (*jananī-kṛta-*

¹⁰³⁷ Also in Veṅīsaṃhāra 2,11 where a queen says: *prabhāta-maṅgala-tūrya-rava-miśreṇa vāra-vilāsini-saṃgīta-śabdena prabodhitāsmi*. At Rājat VIII 2563 the night-watches are announced by kettle-drums (*yāma-tūrya*).

¹⁰³⁸ In Kād. often found (20,3; 22,3; 24,7; 25,1; 30,3; 35,4), other than in KSS, but rarely with details (17,5 *indra-nīla-maṇi-kuṭṭima*; 19,1).

¹⁰³⁹ See Kuv note 202.

¹⁰⁴⁰ For this conventional metaphor see, e.g. Jackmuth 2002: 64ff.; 146 and Hanneder 2005a: 661.

maṅgala) 116,10 (TP VIII 157); ~ of the gods invited to eat in Sumeru's house 50,141 (TP IV 117); ~ of gambler dies of grief 73,204 (TP VI 116); ~ promises daughter to other suitor than father and brother 79,25 (TP VI 201); son tells ~ of being love-sick 80,10 (TP VI 205); king marries daughter with large feet and his son marries dark (*śyāmā*, vs 35) queen, her ~, with small feet 98,51 (TP VII 119); father being alive the ~ lacks authority (to give away daughter) 112,211 (TP VIII 123);

mother-in-law (*śvaśrū*) passes on oral tradition 19,35 (TP II 87); ~ (*rākṣasī*) with flying power 25,214 (TP II 207); ~ eats flesh of daughter-in-law as a she-wolf does of a sheep 29,67 (TP III 43); ~ mistress in the house 29,72 (TP III 44)¹⁰⁴¹; ~ strips, kicks and puts daughter-in-law into cellar (*bhū-geha*) 29,87 (TP III 45)¹⁰⁴²; Asura princess wishes mortal princess a husband's house without ~ and cruel sister-in-law 29,197 (TP III 54f.); ~ receives future son-in-law (*jāmātr-sneha-kātarā*) after his inauguration as *yuva-rāja* magnificently, for she is overpowered with love for him 34,128f. (TP III 137); royal ~ performs rites on behalf of her son-in-law before he departs for his city 35,160 (TP III 168); ~ performs auspicious rites before voyage of son-in-law 43,235 (TP III 297); ~ Kāñcanaprabhā entertains daughter and son-in-law 52,3-23 (TP IV 138f.); auspicious rite performed by bawd (*kuṭṭanī-kṛta-maṅgala*) for suitor of courtesan daughter 57,104 (TP V 8); ~, a witch, releases man from animal condition 68,62 (TP VI 6); wicked ~ is great scold, implacable, passionate (*mahā-raudrā dur-ārādhyātikopānā*) 74,156, makes first daughter-in-law flee the house 74,158ff. and the second one hang herself 74,163 (TP VI 152); ~ exposes herself by deceitful accusation of being hit on the head by daughter-in-law and is ashamed (*vilakṣita*) 74,176 (TP VI 153); queen ~ with magic powers (*siddha-vidyā*) as female protector of king 107,63f. (TP VIII 47)

“Mothers”, see: *Mātaras*

motif,¹⁰⁴³ see: chastity test; crow and palm; death letter; deposit; disguise; doctor knowall; forbidden chamber; grateful animals; heirless king; helpful animals; impossibility; Jonah; laugh-and-cry motif; overhearing; promise to return; shipwreck;

mount of collyrium 51,169 (TP IV 134);

mount, see: conveyance; horse

mountain of Agni or fire, volcano (*Agni-parvata*) 107,109 (TP VIII 50)¹⁰⁴⁴

mountain, of rising sun (*Udaya-parvata*) home of Siddhas 18,241 (TP II 68); idem 18,351 (TP II 75); ~ inaccessible to mortals 18,355 (TP II 76); king ascends his elephant with umbrella just as a lion ascends a ~ with one tree in blossom on it 19,63 (TP II 89); *vidyādhara*s assemble on Mt Rṣabha to worship Śiva 26,65f. (TP II 222); sea as refuge of

¹⁰⁴¹ Cormack 1961: 122. The general attitude towards the mother-in-law is expressed by the dialectal Hindī term of abuse *susrī* < *sasurī* (Jeffery 1961: xi).

¹⁰⁴² Cf. Chojacki 2008 (I): 346 s.v. *belle-mère*.

¹⁰⁴³ See also TP X 38ff.; ORC 1609ff. and Röhl 1989: 173ff.

¹⁰⁴⁴ The only active volcano is a stratovolcano on Barren Island (Andaman Islands) which erupted even in 2013 (Siebert, Simkin and Kimberly).

~s retaining their wings 27,137 (TP III 11); ~ with snow looks like laughing 73,159 (TP VI 112f.); what can wind do against ~ ? 74,105 (TP VI 147); – see also: *añjanâdri*;
 Himavat
 mourning tour¹⁰⁴⁵ 2,43 (TP I 12); ~ of man mourning his wife’s death 10,16 (TP I 107); after death of parents son quits his pregnant wife to go to holy places (*tīrthôddeśāt*) and, blind through sorrow for the loss of his parents, leaves his body 21,111 (TP II 133); king, unable to find his daughter, goes out hunting to distract his mind 66,144 (TP V 189); 93,65f. and 70 (TP VII 83); 94,8 (TP VII 87); 123,20 (TP IX 44); – see also: pilgrimage; tourism
 mouse (*mūṣaka*) as capital lent (*bhāṇḍa-mūlya*) to orphan 6,38 and sold as cat’s meat 6,40 (TP I 63); ~ of gold in exchange for bride 6,48 (TP I 63); ~ dances when seeing cat caught (*baddha*; in noose) 33,115 (TP III 116); ~ frees cat in trap (*pāśa*) 33, 127 (TP III 117); ~ gnaws meshes of net over pigeons asunder and thus frees them 61,70 (TP V 74); crow, ~ and tortoise as friends 61,85 (TP V 75); ~ steals necklace from palace and acquires power from it 61,87 (TP V 75); auto-biography of ~ 61,107ff. (TP V 77f.); ~ frees deer from noose 61,128 (TP V 79); on the strength of his asceticism (*tapo-balāt*) hermit turns ~ (*mūṣikā*) into girl 62,125 (TP V 109); – see also: *ākhu*; darter; *madgu*; mice
 mouth, rinsing ~ before act of truth 16, 117 (TP II 30); flames of fire issue from ~ of *vetāla* 18,165 (TP II 62); in dream moon enters ~ of queen 59,61 (TP V 30); flame issues from ~ of corpse possessed by *vetāla* 73,308 (TP VI 123); king rinses (*ācamya*) ~¹⁰⁴⁶ before addressing *lokapālas* 112,134 (TP VIII 116); *kāpālīka* goes to rinse ~ (*agāt ... ācāntum*) before planned rite 121,16 (TP IX 13); ~ (*mukha*) of *yakṣī* expands with one lip elevated to heaven and the other resting on the earth 123,22 (TP IX 44); – see also: *nāga*
 mouth of death (*mṛtyor mukha*)¹⁰⁴⁷, Mañibhadra’s temple as ~ 13,177 (TP I 163)¹⁰⁴⁸; 18,324 (TP II 74); ~ in form of human sacrifice 22,70 (TP II 142); ~ of submarine fire (*vaḍavā-mukha*) 26,10 (TP II 217); whirlpool of submarine fire is ~ 26,15 (TP II 218) and 139 (TP II 226); Durgā temple whose opening is like the ~ (*mṛtyor ivānana*) with rows of teeth in the form of a line of bells¹⁰⁴⁹ (*ghaṇṭāvalī-danta-māla*) 26,144 (TP II 227 ‘[Death] devouring *tamāla* with projecting teeth’); elephant as ~ 27,180 (TP III 15); wrath of mother-in-law as ~ 29,110 (TP III 47); two halves of plank separated by wedge are like ~ for monkey 60,30 (TP V 44); cave-dwelling of robber as ~ (*mṛtyu-mukha*)¹⁰⁵⁰ 88,23 (TP VII 36); princes saved from crocodile’s (*grāha*) mouth as ~ 101,240 (TP VII 150f.); temple of Ambikā like ~ because of human sacrifice 101,301 (TP VII 155); place of combat as ~ (*kṛtāntasya vadanam*) 103,7 (TP VII 175); – see also: *an-ācānta*; brains; chamber of

¹⁰⁴⁵ See, e.g. Tucker 2009. The German language even has the word *Trauerreise*.

¹⁰⁴⁶ Purification rite, see Kane 1973: II 315f.

¹⁰⁴⁷ Cf. the *rākṣasa* name Yama-daṃṣṭra 18,336 (TP II 74).

¹⁰⁴⁸ Cf. Daś 282,11 *mṛtyu-mukha*.

¹⁰⁴⁹ “Avec ses guirlandes de cloches qui saillaient telles de rangées de dents” (ORC 244). Cf. infra: “temple of Ambikā”.

¹⁰⁵⁰ Also Daś (Bombay, 1940) 282,11.

princess; human sacrifice; Mañibhadra's temple;
 mouth of night is like that of a *rākṣasī*, bright and terrible with rows of teeth in the shape of a twinkling series of lights (*sphurad-dīpāvalī-danta-mālā-bhāsvara-bhīṣaṇa*) 25,238 (TP II 208: “shining and terrible as *tamāla*”; ORC 232: “*la nuit, telle une démonsse, ouvrit une bouche effroyable où les guirlandes des étoiles en scintillant semblaient des dents éclatantes et génèrent la terreur*”)
mṛdaṅga, ‘drum’ of a Ḍomba executioner 13,96 (TP I 157)¹⁰⁵¹
mṛgāmiṣa (not MW) ‘venison’, lion feeds part-*bodhisattva* with ~ 65,101 (TP V 162)
Mṛgāṅka ‘deer-marked > moon’ (?),¹⁰⁵² name of sword given to Śrīdatta to kill crocodiles 10,48 and 51 (TP I 109f.)
mṛta-jāni (not MW) ‘whose wife is dead’ 70,31 (TP VI 26 note 2);
mṛta-saṃjīvanāṣadhi ‘herb able to raise the dead to life’, *rāja-haṃsī* thus revived 69,137 (TP VI 18)
 mud (*saraḥ-paṅka*), elephants sunk into ~ saved by hermit's disciples 68,28 (TP VI 3)
mudrākṣepa ‘removal of a letter seal’ 102,134 (TP VII 172)
mukhāgama (not MW) ‘oral tradition’ 19,35 (TP II 87)
mukha-maṅḍala ‘full-orbed face’ reading of TP VIII 32 in 106,50 *rājani-ramaṇe prāci-dig-vadhū-~e* (ORC 1110: “*son disque, le visage de son épouse orientale*”) for D: *mukha-maṅḍana* (not MW) ‘face decoration’; M II 476: “(*Der Mond*) ... *setzte der Braut, der östlichen Himmelsgegend, einen Schönheitsfleck auf ihre Stirn*”
mukta misprint for *yukta* 56,130 (TP IV 229 note)
muktā-sāra (not MW) ‘necklace of pearls’ from the head of elephants 22,76 (TP II 142 note 1)
 Mūladeva as *siddha guru*, brahmin approaches ~ to get beloved princess 89,21 (TP VII 41); ~ takes princess as wife for his friend Śaśin 89,106 (TP VII 47); stanza of ~ : whoever is not a fool enters a house without a wife waiting ? 98,32 (TP VII 118); ring with name of ~ of Ujjayinī, renowned for cunning (*khyāto dhūrtaḥ*) 124,168f. (TP IX 80); ~ misunderstands story of Bali and becomes slave of his son 124,228 (TP IX 84)
 mummification, see: embalming
mumukṣu-śīla (not MW) ‘characteristic of liberation seekers’ is quietism 66,16 (TP V 179)
 mungoose, see: mongoose
 munificence 35,34 and 49 (TP III 157f.); see also: charity; *dāna*
muni-kanyā (young female ascetic) 67,66 (TP V 200);
muraḥa,¹⁰⁵³ sound of ~ drum announces dance 2,34 (TP I 11); only pressure that of the fingers on the ~ 97,6 (TP VII 112); sound of ~ announces evening spectacle at twilight (*saṃdhyā-prekṣaṇaka*) 123,127ff. (TP IX 52);

¹⁰⁵¹ Dallapiccola 2002: 137; Popley 1996: 120; Ambrose 1950: 29.. Originally a kind of earthen drum and as such still in use in Bengal among the singers of Vaiṣṇava *kīrtana* (Ghosh 1961: II 161 note 1). For a picture see Sivaramamurti 1983: 167 no 232 on a 12th century temple in Halebidu.

¹⁰⁵² Wrong reading for *Mṛtāṅka* ‘sign of death’ ?

¹⁰⁵³ See Sivaramamurti 1956: 147; Bollée 2012a: 204b; Chojnacki 2008: (I) 363 s.v. *tambour*.

Mura-jit (Viṣṇu), *Asuras* killed by disc of ~ 45,374 (TP IV 42);

Murala = Kerala 19,96 (TP II 92 with note 5)

mūrkhā as term of abuse: ‘dumbo, schnook’ 6,117 (TP I 69); 40,78 (TP III 246); 82,14 (TP VI 217)

music, of lute¹⁰⁵⁴ 11,4 (TP I 122f.); king with lute (*ghoṣavati*) teaches princess to sing 12,31f. (TP I 135); stream of lyre ~ purges the ear 49,23 (TP IV 86)¹⁰⁵⁵; ~ of great tabor (*mahā-todya*) beaten to accompany dancing 71,76 (TP VI 41); ~ (*tūrya-śabdāḥ*) in the morning wakes princess up 73,360 (TP VI 126); neighing of white horse compared to ~ of conch (*śuddha-śāṅkhādi-śravaya-niḥsvana*) 74,77 (TP VI 145); animals listen motionless to ~ of *viṇā* played in temple of Gaurī 90, 42 (TP VII 52); *Gandharva* princess sings Viṣṇu-*stuti* to the lyre 106,11 (TP VIII 28); Naravāhanadatta knowing all ~ in the three worlds 106,15 (TP VIII 299); woman splendidly plays and sings southern style (*mārga*) of ~ 120,121 (TP IX 10)¹⁰⁵⁶; – see also: *ānanda-divya-tūrya*; *ātodya-maṅgala*; drum; *kinnarī-viṇā*; lute; lyre; *muraja*; *pīñjaraka*; singing; *viṇā*;

musical instruments, see: *ātodya*; bell; *bherī*; *ḍamaru*; drum; gong; lute; lyre; *mṛdaṅga*; *muraja*; *paṭaha*; *tūrya*; *vādya*; *viṇā*

musician, palace festive with songs of ~ (*māgadha*) 14,21 (TP I 183); treasurer told to give ~ (*gāndharvika*) 2000 *paṇa* as reward 63,158 (TP V 133); – see also: bard; minstrel

music room (*gāndharva-śālā*) in palace 12,31 (TP I 135);

musk¹⁰⁵⁷ (*kastūrikā*), the suitors of a faithful lady are smeared with lampblack, scented with ~¹⁰⁵⁸ and put into a large trunk at night 4,47 (TP I 33); prince, smeared with ~ (*kastūrikānu liptāṅga*), goes out at night in search of adventures 71,22 (TP VI 37); ~ (*mṛga-mada*) as royal present for kings 102,113 (TP VII 170); ~ used as decoration (?) by Bhilla women 123,50 (TP IX 46); wedding present of a hundred camels with pearls and ~ to king 123,77 (TP IX 48);

must(h), see: ichor

mustard-seeds (*sarṣapa*)¹⁰⁵⁹ issuing from corpse’s navel and picked up by mendicant 18,155 (TP II 62); ~ taken from ascetic enable travelling through the air 18,179 (TP II 63); mendicant’s ~ differ from those found on earth 18,199 (TP II 65); *apsaras* give mortal bride ~ to be sown in order to know return path 32,117 (TP III 98) and 182 (TP III 104); with charmed ~ brahmin turns wife into mare 68,55 (TP VI 5); enchanted ~ clear water from dust 70,59 before an oblation 70,67 (TP VI 29)¹⁰⁶⁰; *mahā-tapasvin* scatters ~ to reveal door to Pātāla

¹⁰⁵⁴ On the *viṇā* see, e.g. Pesch 2009:87ff.

¹⁰⁵⁵ Bollée 2010a : 160 note 273.

¹⁰⁵⁶ See Pesch 2009: 42ff.

¹⁰⁵⁷ See also Gode 1961: 476 the references not being very informative; Kuv note 119; McHugh 2012: 318.

¹⁰⁵⁸ The sense of this is not clear.

¹⁰⁵⁹ Brassica juncea, serves to chase spirits and protect against the evil eye (ORC 1611). See also Chojnacki 2008: (I) 357 s.v. *moutarde*.

¹⁰⁶⁰ ORC 806 : “il fit apparaître l’eau sous la poussière en jetant des graines de moutarde enchantées.”

73,117 (TP VI 109); ~ produced in the mouth of a *vetāla* and given to hero as drug to be put on king's head and hands against his *yakṣman* 73,312 (TP VI 123); muttering prayers (*japa*)¹⁰⁶¹ by brahmin sets three-world on fire 45,84 (TP IV 23); *vidyādharas* sacrificing and ~ 46,55 (TP IV 52); *Asura*, etc. heroes sacrificing and ~ obtain magic bows in seven days 46,107 (TP IV 55f.); brahmin's exclusive devotion to ~ (*japa-karmāka-cittatva*) 69,165 (TP VI 20)
myna, see: hen-maina

n / r error, see **nāga-bandha* for *rāga-bandha*

na, prince who never learnt the meaning of the word ~ 113,23 (TP VIII 125)

nabhaḥ-kriḍā (not MW) 'sporting in the air' 22,11 (TP II 138)

nāḍī 'fistulous sore', see: healing

*Nāga*¹⁰⁶² 'snake deity', *gāndharva* marriage of brahmin woman (ex-*apsaras*) with brahmin ~ prince 6,14f. (TP I 61); emerged from tank ~ brings wife and couch out of his mouth and goes to sleep 64,154 but when his wife then embraces a traveller he wakes up and burns both 158 (TP V 151); palace of ~ king (*Nāgêndra-bhavana*) under *śiṃśapa* tree in Vindhya forest 70,58 (TP VI 28); ~ curses man to become blind 74,14 (TP VI 142); ~ king is *Vāsuki* 74,208 (TP VI 155); ~ not to injure crops (*a-sasya-ghātin*) 119,36 (TP VIII 195)

nāga-balā 'Uraria Lagopodioides'¹⁰⁶³ (MW) ?, a medicinal plant with lila or white flowers used in Ayurveda as abortive drug and against bodyache¹⁰⁶⁴ 33,151f. (TP III 120; ORC 1613; *Sida Spinosa* [on which see: www.holisticonline.com/herbal-med/_Herbs/h_sida-spinosa.htm]¹⁰⁶⁵)

**nāga-bandha*¹⁰⁶⁶ 'constriction, twining around by a boa' (*taraṅgōtkṣipta-vikṣipte ~air ivāmbudhau pravahane*) 101,180 (TP VII 146: "[the two vessels, driven to and fro by the waves, as elephants] by elephant-drivers, [wandered about in the sea, as if in the *mêlée* of a battle]"; ORC 1049: "[*Les deux navires, rapprochés puis rejetés par les vagues comme par l'] étreinte d'un serpent [furent ballottés sur l'océan semblable à un champ de bataille]"; M*

¹⁰⁶¹ Padoux 1979.

¹⁰⁶² See also ORC 1613.

¹⁰⁶³ Meulenbeld 1974: 577 designates this as unclear. He deals with the plant under the name of *pr̥śniparṇī* not mentioning *nāgabālā*, and states the assumed synonymy of *U. Lagopodioides* and *U. Lagopoides* DC as incorrect. See also Balbir 1993:18.

¹⁰⁶⁴ Thus Jain 1991:183 (*U. lagopoides*). For pictures, and description as with anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity see: <http://informahealthcare.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13880200490510892?journalCode=phb>

¹⁰⁶⁵ Here *nāgabālā* is at least mentioned and may therefore be the correct meaning. The plant has yellow flowers and the leaves, bruised in water, strained through cloth and administered in the form of a draught, are stated to be demulcent. Jain 1991: 165. Bhisagratna 1963: III Appendix 74 identifies *Nāgabālā* as *Sida spierosa* Graveolens and prescribes it II 519 (Suśruta, *Cikitsa-sthāna* 27,8) against premature old age and senility.

¹⁰⁶⁶ TP utter doubt at their translation which stands only by the addition of "elephants" which is not in the text. The constriction of the snake in the context of ships is odd, too, all the more, because the ships do not come into contact with each other and constriction cannot be the point, therefore. **Nāga-bandha* is a curious hapax legomenon and therefore *rāga-bandha* 'passion' (Raghuvamśa 18,52, etc.), which fits also in battle and may be a small correction in Indian script, appears better.

II 392: “*wie mit Schlangen gefesselt*”; MW: “a snake as a chain or fetter”);
nāga-danta ‘elephant hook, crooked peg’¹⁰⁶⁷, book hung on ~ 76,24 (TP VI 180); – cf.
aṅkuśa
nāga-kany(ak)ā, see: snake princess
nagara-bhrama (not MW), see: ascetic; lustration
*nagarādhipa*¹⁰⁶⁸ (not MW) ‘police chief’ in Ujjain carried off at night and devoured by Asura
 112,29 (TP VIII 107: “head police officer”; ORC 1172: “*chef de police*”; M II 557:
 “Stadthauptmann”)
nagarādhyakṣa ‘city magistrate’, apparent thief brought to ~ 75,168 (TP VI 176)
nāga-rāja Vāsuki worshipped 74,208 (TP VI 155); – see also: *jaya-stambha*
nāgarika,¹⁰⁶⁹ see: *grāmya*
nāga-vallī ‘betel’ 104,46 (TP VIII 4), see: camphor
Nāgī, daughter of Vāsuki, enters king’s bedroom at night without opening the door 55,144 (TP
 IV 212); ~ advises king to propitiate Svāmikumāra (Kārttikeya) for son 55,152 (TP IV 212)
 and enters king’s body to protect him against rain and poisonous snake 55,158 (TP IV 213);
 as female not allowed to enter Kārttikeya’s temple 55,174 (TP IV 214);
nagna-kṣapaṇaka, probably ‘Digambara monk’
 nail marks, earth dented with the edges of hoofs of royal steeds shows ~ as if enjoyed by the king
 18,7 (TP II 49); court ladies with ~ and bites (*nakha-danta-kṣata*) from love play 66,42
 (TP V 181 and note on 193ff.)
 nakedness, of woman in ceremony for Bhairava in order to become witch 20,50 (TP II 98) and
 110 (TP II 104); in magical ritual, see TP II 117ff.¹⁰⁷⁰; ~ of brahmin needed for sacrifice
 to Piśāca at crossroads 28, 165 (TP III 33); Śiva sits naked with head on knee 121,99 (TP
 IX 19); – see also: bawd; covering; *dig-ambara*; *divyā strī*; queen
nakha-śikhā, see: attractivity stereotype (Chojnacki 2008: I 62 note 38).
nakta-bhojī-tva-vādin, false ascetic teaches eating at night 69,67 (TP VI 13)
naktaṃ-carī ‘wanderer of the night’ = *rākṣasī* 116,30 (TP VIII 158)
 Nala surpasses Kāma in beauty 56,238 (TP IV 237); ~ catches goose that asks to be set free
 56,249 (TP IV 237); drunk ~ forgets evening prayer and washing feet 56,288 (TP IV 241);
 ~ loses kingdom in gambling 56,301 (TP IV 242); ~ leaves Damayantī in forest at night
 56,317 (TP IV 243); ~ as moon 56,338 (TP IV 244); ~ as black and deformed cook
 Hrasva-bāhu 56,347 (TP IV 246); ~’s driving excellence 56,370 (TP IV 247); ~ obtains
 dice skill from Ṛtuparṇa 56,381 (TP IV 247);
namas tubhyam ! in praise of Durgā by merchant in chains 37,44 (TP III 186)
 name(s), king confounds ~ (*gotra-skhalita*) of harem attendant with that of queen 14,66 (TP I

¹⁰⁶⁷ See Sivaramamurti 1956: 234.

¹⁰⁶⁸ Perhaps identical with next and Kalidāsa’s *nāgarika* (Saletore 1943: 262).

¹⁰⁶⁹ In Saletore 1943: 262 the *nāgarika* is “one of whose duties appears to have been to look out for offenders against the law.”

¹⁰⁷⁰ Crooke 1919: 248f.

187); Śivas thousand (= unnumerable) ~s 50,181 (TP IV 119), ~ of *apsaras* inquired from their maids 54,75 (TP IV 189); Śiva's 68 ~s destroy transgression and grant all desires 54,215 (TP IV 199); giving child ~ on the eleventh day after its birth 73,67 (TP VI 105); not asking directly a person's ~ 90,49 (TP VII 52); – see also: address; sword
na me doṣaḥ 'it is not my fault' says a woman prostituted by husband 43,90 (TP III 287);
na me 'parādhaḥ 'it is not my fault' 5,117 (TP I 57)
naming brahmin children on the eleventh day 73,67 (TP VI 105); ~ done by father 73,400 (TP VI 129);
Namuci, a Dānava ascetic, drinks smoke (i.e. smokes) for ten thousand years and receives as boon from Brahmā to be proof against iron, stone and wood 46,218 (TP IV 63)¹⁰⁷¹; ~ obtains horse Uccaiṣravas 46,221 (TP IV 63); ~ gives horse U. to Indra 46,231 (TP IV 63); ~ killed by Indra with Ganges foam but reborn as Prabala 46,232 (TP IV 64);
Nandi and Airāvata sporting in the Ganges 115,149 (TP VIII 154)
Nandigrāma sanctuary of Śiva-Hari (*āyatane Hareḥ* !) outside Ayodhyā 103,119 (TP VII 183);
Nandin comforting Naravāhanadatta 107,126 (TP VIII 51);
Nārada's sudden luminous appearance 15,127 (TP II 12); ~ gives king garland from Pārijāta tree and predicts birth of prince 15,129 (TP II 13)¹⁰⁷²; advice by ~ to king 15,146 (TP II 15); ~ sent by Viṣṇu to Śatakratu (Indra) 17,10 (TP II 34f.); ~ with radiant body foretells king future 21,20ff. (TP II 126f.); ~ curses *vidyādhara* for dropping garland on him 22,139 (TP II 147); message of ~ 24,8 (TP II 170); ~ sent by Indra to stop Maya 45,13ff. (TP IV 18); ~ sent by Indra to prevent war 45,163f. (TP IV 28); ~ at the head of *Gandharvas* singing before Viṣṇu 54,25 (TP IV 186); ~ descends from heaven in aura of light, sent by Śiva Śūlin to cheer up (*dhṛty-arthaṃ*) king 105,83 (TP VIII 27);
nara-karaṅkaka 'human skeleton' (? not MW)¹⁰⁷³ hanging in fig tree in front of Śaiva temple 40,90 (TP III 247; ORC 417: "squelette humain"; MI 582: "Gerippe")
Naravāhanadatta reincarnation of Kāma 110,70 (TP VIII 87);
Nārāyaṇa, bathers in water of Pañcatīrthī can become followers of ~ 33,30 (TP III 109);
Nārāyaṇī principal of the "Mothers" 56,76 (TP IV 225); ~ gives female slave (*dāsī*) to brahmin 56,112 (TP IV 227); ~ gives lotus destroying poison to brahmin 56,115 (TP IV 228);
nārī-caṅga (not MW) 'woman-fastidious', brahmin 82,12 and 31 (TP VI 218f.)
Nārikela, sightseeing on ~ 'coconut palm' island 54,49ff. (TP IV 188);
Narmadā shakes waves like twining arms (*vīci-vellad-bhuja-latā*) and gleams white with laughing foam (*vīci-vellad-bhuja-latāṃ vilasat-phena-pāṇḍurām*) 71,2 (TP VI 36)
narmāika-sōdara, see: sayings
nasya,¹⁰⁷⁴ see: *oṣadhī-rasa-nasya*

¹⁰⁷¹ Therefore Indra beat off his head with lead ŚpBr 5,4,1,9f. (Doniger O'Flaherty 1976: 152).

¹⁰⁷² Syed 1990: 434.

¹⁰⁷³ For *karaṅka* MW has 'head, skull'. See also Müller 1925.

¹⁰⁷⁴ See Bollée 2010 note on vs 107.

nationalism, cf. *heimatliebe*

native country (*janma-bhū*), love more charming than ~ 28,64 (TP III 25); wife not interested in ~ 39,166 (TP III 229); ~ (*janma-bhūmi*) dear to beings 52,189 (TP IV 151); (*sva-deśa*) 56,196 (TP IV 234); 66,73 (TP V 183); 67,111 (TP V 204); ~ represented by forest (*vana*) 70,123 (TP VI 33); leaving ~ 87,28 (TP VII 31); 110, 139 (TP VIII 92); – see also: *heimatliebe*

nativity (*jātaka*), man destined by ~ to become robber (*jātaka-nirdiṣṭa-caurya*), genetic thief 72,192 (TP VI 82);

nature, description of, see forest; – call of ~, see: call of nature

nāṭya-prayoga (not MW) ‘dramatic representation’ in court in which Hari-Viṣṇu in the form of a woman carries off the *amṛta* from the Daityas 74,37 (TP VI 143)¹⁰⁷⁵

nāṭyācārya ‘teacher of dancing’ 52,265ff. (TP IV 156)

nāṭya-vedī ‘stage’, royal banquet hall looking like ~ of goddesses of good fortune 110,132 (TP VIII 92)

nāṭya-veśman ‘dance hall’ 52,270 (TP IV 156)

nautch-girls, see: dancing-girl(s); wave

nau-tuli ‘shuttle’ for crossing *bhavāmbudhi* 72,362 (TP VI 96);

navel, Brahmā as bee on lotus growing from Viṣṇu’s ~, see Brahmā; – see also: mustard-seeds

naya-taru (‘tree of policy’) 17,163 (TP II 47)

neck, Kāma surrounds ~ of Śiva with nooses in the form of Pārvatī’s looks 1,1 (TP I 1); female beauty has neck (with three lines) like a shell (*kambu-kaṅṭhī*) 4,7 (TP I 31); magical thread around ~ (*baddha-mantra-sūtra*) transforms man into monkey 37,116 (TP III 191); thread (*sūtraka*) around ~ turns wearer into peacock 71,277 (TP VI 56; cf. 71,55 [TP VI 39]); princess in love departs often turning her ~ 90,87 (TP VII 55); out of fear robber often turns his ~ 112,152 (TP VIII 118); seizing *vetāla* by the ~ (*ardha-candraṃ datvā*) to push him into pit 121,65 (TP IX 16)

necklace,¹⁰⁷⁶ Śiva as wearer of ~ of skulls (*kapāla-mālin*) 1,37 (TP I 5); ~ (*hāra*) hidden in garment leads to false accuse 10,167 (TP I 117); ~ of “elephant pearls” 22,76 (TP II 142 with note 1); ~ as illusion (*māyā*) 28,137 (TP III 31); second ~ of tears 30,27 (TP III 65); ~ of lotus fibres worn by women in love 33,166 (TP III 121); Bhavānī gives bride pearl ~ (*ratnāvalī*) which keeps off hunger, thirst and death 50,137 (TP IV 116); ~ of lotus-fibres (*mṛṅgāla-hāra*) 55,62 (TP IV 206); ~ stolen by kite (*grdhra*) 54,114 (TP IV 192); ~ stolen from palace by mouse 61,87 (TP V 75); mouse acquires strength by looking at ~ 61,88 (TP V 76; ORC 1440 note ad p. 697 remarks that the necklace had magical powers); in prince’s dream pearl ~ (*muktāvalī*)¹⁰⁷⁷ is associated with queen 69,42 (TP VI 11); *rāja-haṃsī* finds ~ (*kaṅṭhikā*) and therewith lures away hunter from her husband caught in net 69,142f. (TP VI 19); river Ganges (*svarga-taraṅgiṇī*) appears as ~ (*hāra-yaṣṭi*) on

¹⁰⁷⁵ Vettam Mani 1975: 32 with puranic references.

¹⁰⁷⁶ For some examples see Jackson 2010: 213ff.

¹⁰⁷⁷ In Jagaddeva I 95 and 114 pearls bring good luck.

Vārāṇasī 75,60 (TP VI 168), cf. 114,17 (TP VIII 133); disguised ascetic's pupil offers stolen ~ for sale in market 75,163 (TP VI 175); attendant puts (pearl) ~ cool as snow (*hāraṃ tuhina-śītaḥ*) on heart of love-sick merchant daughter in order to allay her heat (*tāpōpaśāntaye*) 95,40 (TP VII 101); prince gives his (gender- neutral) ~ as reward to female attendant-messenger 117,116 (TP VIII 172)

necrophagy, see: cannibalism

nectar (*amṛta*),¹⁰⁷⁸ those drinking the ~ of the tale gain prosperity 9,3 (TP I 94); with her look *rākṣasī* rains ~ of love (*prema-rasāsāra-varṣiṇā cakṣuṣā*) 11,49 (TP I 126); Gaurī rains ~ on Jīmūtavāhana 22,246 (TP II 155); preparation of ~ 41,13 and advice to stop its preparation 41,19 (TP III 253); ~ about to be prepared in five days 41,26 (TP III 254); ~ rained into eyes 45,233 (TP IV 33); ~ appearing last at the churning of the ocean was stolen by the gods 46,223 (TP IV 63); king irrigated with ~ (*sparśāmṛta-siktāṅga*) of *vidyādhari*'s touch 52,356 (TP IV 163); Indra sprinkles ~ on ashes and bones of suicide victims and revives them 72,392 (TP VI 98); in dramatic representation (*nāṭya-prayoga*) king sees Hari-Viṣṇu in the form of a woman carry off ~ from Daityas 74,37 (TP VI 143); Gaurī has ~ in her pitcher (*kamaṇḍala*) 90,185 (TP VII 62); ~ for the ear (*śrotrāmṛta*) 94,31 (TP VII 89); – see also: water of immortality; water of life

nectar (*sudhā*) Garuḍa puts vessel of ~ on bed of *kuśa* grass for the snakes but Indra carries it off from there 22,196f. (TP II 151)¹⁰⁷⁹; Kālakūṭa poison is twin-born with ~ 36,95 (TP III 176); rain of ~ 44,21 (TP IV 2); drinking ~ in Rasātala makes one obtain a divine body 45,63 (TP IV 21); ~ in the arms of Garuḍa Sudhāhartṛ 110,126 (TP VIII 91);

negative religion, see: Buddhism

negotiation (*sāman*) 11,16 (TP I 123); ~ termed “matrimonial alliance” (*kanyā-saṃbandha*) 17,156 (TP II 47)

Nereid,¹⁰⁸⁰ see: mermaid

nest, kite's ~ (*gṛdhra-nīḍa*) with ornaments found by merchant 54,128 (TP IV 193)¹⁰⁸¹; ~ of *rāja-haṃsa* in date palm (*kharjūra-pādapa*) 69,129 (TP VI 18)

net (*jāla*), bawd stretches secretly ~ in a well 57,101 (TP V 8); fisherman catches *haṃsas* in ~ which monkey falls on tearing it 69,139-146 (TP VI 19)

netrāgni ‘eye-fire, flaming eye’ (not MW) of Śiva killing Kāma 56,238 (TP IV 237)

netra-pīyūṣa (not MW) ‘nectar as feast to the eyes’, the body of a *vidyādhari* is ~ 35,138 (TP III 166)

netra-roga ‘eye-disease’ of *vetāla* Bhūtaketu healed by look (*dṛṣṭi*) of king 123,34 (TP IX 45)

netrōtsava, see: eyes; feast to the eyes

newborn, see: daughter; radiating

¹⁰⁷⁸ See Thieme 1952: 15ff.

¹⁰⁷⁹ Mbh I 34.

¹⁰⁸⁰ STh F 423.1.

¹⁰⁸¹ STh N 527.

nibandhana, see: love-sickness

nick-name, see: husband (66,86 ~ TP V 184) and pet name; – further see: Hilka 1910: 124.

*nidāna*¹⁰⁸² ‘desire for reward’: for rebirth with same wife before suicide by jumping from hill-side 22,164 (TP II 149); do, of brahmin wife with same husband after death of her two children 53,159 (TP IV 179); ~ of crow to rebirth as owl 62,122 (TP V 109); ~ of couple mentally fixed on *rāja-haṃsas* before suicide are reborn as such birds 69,128 (TP VI 18); a creature receives the form of that which it was contemplating at the moment of death 69,159 (TP VI 20); ~ of *brahma-kumārī* with love of brahmin 69,162 (TP VI 20); ~ as petition to Śiva of brahmin and two wives to be always reborn together 73,418f. (TP VI 130); before throwing herself onto burning pyre, faithful woman wants from Caṇḍī same husband in next birth 78,84f. (TP VI 196); ~ of woman about to hang herself wishes that her dead husband will be her husband also in the next life 80,40f. (TP VI 207; cf. 103,50f. [TP VII 178]); 95,30 (TP VII 100); bride asks Kāma to give her another husband in next birth 104,138 (TP VIII 11); *caṇḍāla* wants princess for wife in next birth 112,99 (TP VIII 113); during suicide by fasting ~ for eating fish makes brahmin be reborn as fisherman 112,140 (TP VIII 117); ~ of woman in front of Kāma’s statue before hanging herself that she may get her lost lover as husband in her next birth 113,134-8 (TP VIII 11); ~ of two *Asura* princesses praying to Agni for a certain husband before entering fire 118,169f. (TP VIII 189f.); – see also: Caṇḍī; prayer

nidhi,¹⁰⁸³ see: nine treasures

nidhy-ālokana and *nidhānālokana* ‘treasure finding’ 61,36 and 39 (TP V 71)¹⁰⁸⁴

night, waking up at close of ~ (*rajanī-kṣaye*) 4,9 (TP I 31); being dazed with the brightness of the sun Piśācas, etc. delight in the ~ 7,35 (TP I 77); king starting secretly by ~ on she-elephant 13,9 (TP I 150); princess is pale with bereavement like a lotus in the ~ 16,45 (TP II 25); *vidyādhari* departing at close of ~ (*rātry-anta-samaye*) 18,238 (TP II 68); ~ comes to ascend pyre of set moon (as of her husband) 25,140 (TP II 201 with note 2); hero meets *rākṣasī* on charnel ground on fourteenth ~ of black fortnight 25,180 (TP II 204); human flesh offered for sale by brahmin on charnel ground at ~ 25,183 (TP II 205); mouth of ~ is like that of a *rākṣasī* 25,238 (TP II 208; see sub “mouth of night” supra); maltreated woman secretly (*guptamī*) leaves city at close of ~ 29,96 (TP III 45f.); setting out at ~ against evil omen 32,45 (TP III 93); ~ as harbinger of *yakṣiṇī* 37,178 (TP III 196); travelling at ~ 42,97 (TP III 265) and 56,195 (TP IV 234); do, of king with Pāśupata ascetic 56,215 (TP IV 235); attack by robbers at ~ 54,126 (TP IV 192); Nala leaves wife in forest at ~ 56,317 (TP IV 243); king leaves alone at ~ 69,111 (TP VI 17); prince in dark garments and smeared with musk leaves alone at ~ 71,22 (TP VI 37); woman sets out secretly at ~ for a deserted temple of Śiva 71,212 (TP VI 51); hero sets out in moon-lit ~ and hears weeping maiden 72,31 (TP VI 70); ~ of delusion (*moha-niśā*) 72,313 (TP VI

¹⁰⁸² See Kane 1977: V 972 and cf. Osier 2007.

¹⁰⁸³ Zin 2003b: 211.

¹⁰⁸⁴ See Balbir 1993: 24.

92); setting out at ~ 73,184 and 193 (TP VI 114f.); do, 73,239 (TP VI 118); king going out sword in hand to charnel ground at ~ 73,280 (TP VI 121); prince and companion riding out at sunset 74,96 (TP VI 147) and, after lions killed horses, walking through forest/wilderness at ~ 74,103 (TP VI 147); man passes ~ impatiently like lotus-flower 74,137 (TP VI 150); king sets out at ~ in ascetic disguise 86,70 (TP VII 18); ~ grudges woman, fair as moonlight, hating her rival charms (*tulya-guṇa-dveṣa*) 87,14 (TP VII 30); 92,29 (TP VII 73); widow flees husband's relations at beginning of ~ (*niśā-mukhe*) 93,11 (TP VII 79); ~ as maiden going to her lover (*abhisārikā*) with a robe of darkness 94,52 (TP VII 91) and 103,203 (TP VII 189); ~ comes at an end as if out of grief (*śokād iva kṣiṇābhavat kṣapā*) 95,79 (TP VII 103); king flees Deccan realm for Mālava to forest with wife and daughter at ~ 98,9ff. (TP VII 116); minister wandering through wilderness (*aṭavī*) by ~ 101,5 (TP VII 134); prince and ministers set out secretly at ~ 103,31 (TP VII 177); general sets out at ~ 103,85 (TP VII 181); ~ has a necklace 103,213 (TP VII 189); finger of sun adorns lip of ~ 103,215 (TP VII 190); couple fleeing one *yojana* at ~ 104,148 (TP VIII 12: three *yojanas*); moon as lover (*rajanī-ramaṇa*) of ~ arises 106,50 (TP VIII 31); flight through the ~ 106,83 (TP VIII 34); witches assault brahmin for three ~s 108,25ff. (TP VIII 54ff.); ~ seems as long as if it consists of one hundred instead of three *yāmās* 109,107 (TP VIII 78); man finds wife dead at end of ~ 111,43 (TP VIII 98); at the end of the ~ (*niśāvasāne*) dreamer sees his father dragged away by dark female in southern direction 111,51 (TP VIII 99); every *nagarādhipa* in Ujjain carried off at ~ by some creature and devoured 112,29 (TP VIII 107); king goes out at ~ and decapitates adulterer (*pāradārika*) 112,30 (TP VIII 107); Caṇḍāla maiden looks like ~ which gives rest to eyes of the world 112,67 (TP VIII 111); robbers plunder town at ~ 114,118 (TP VIII 141); *kārpaṭika* passes ~ in temple 123,21 (TP IX 44); ~ as horrible female ascetic (*raudrī rajanī-tāpasī*) 123,211 (TP IX 58); witches return in last watch of ~ (*paścime yāme*) 123,221 (TP IX 59); – see also: darkness; dream; *dūrvā*;

nīlāmśuka ('black shawl') covering mermaid 86,97 (TP VII 21)

nīlōtpala 'dark Nelumbium'¹⁰⁸⁵, body of queen fragrant as ~ 16,28 (TP II 22); – see: eyes *nimitta*,¹⁰⁸⁶ see: omen

nine treasures (*nidhi*), see: Chojnacki 2008: II note 876; Mette 1973a: 21ff.; Alsdorf, *Literary heritage* in the Goettingen University Library under G 9.

nipples as seals to secure the milk (*stanya-rakṣaṇa-mudrā*) for the child to be born 120,45 (TP IX 4); ~ become dark, see: pregnancy

nir-ahaṅkāra 'humbleness' provides knowledge 56,189 (TP IV 233)

nīrājana, see: lustration of arms

nirmātr 'maker', see Dhātṛ

Nirṛti as goddess of death 50,35 (TP IV 110)

nīrvāṇa, lake (*mahat-sarah*), transparent, deep and broad like a material representation of ~ that

¹⁰⁸⁵ Syed 1990: 627ff.

¹⁰⁸⁶ Gonda 1991: V/1 206ff.

allays the fire of desire (lit.: *tr̥ṣṇā*) 120,116 (TP IX 9);
nir-vr̥ḍa-yantraṇa (not MW) ‘without the restraint of shame’ 68,11 (TP VI 2)
 Niṣāda: non-Aryan tribe living on islands 25,33 (TP II 191); ~ as fishermen 27,124 (TP III 10); ~ princess (= Bhillā) with Veda-knowing parrot 59,24ff. (TP V 28); princess, like mad by separation from bridegroom, is cursed by parents to become ~ maiden 59,155 (TP V 36);
nisarga ‘innate tendency’ of the great, to have mercy upon the wretched 25,116 (TP II 200);
nisarga-niyata (not MW) ‘genetically conditioned’, said of the fickleness of women 19,28 (TP II 86)
nīti-cakṣus (not MW) ‘eye of policy, espionage, intelligence’ 33,180 (TP III 122)
nīti-kalpa-latā, see: wishing-tree
nīti-tattva ‘diplomacy’ 34,211 (TP III 144); 102,22 (TP VII 163), see: science
nīti-tattva-jñā, *nīti-vid*, see: politician; science
niyoga ‘service of *deva-dāsi*’ 12,80 (TP I 139);
*niyoga*¹⁰⁸⁷ ‘sexual relation of wife of elder brother with younger brother’ (~ not in text) 33,40 (TP III 109);
 no, king Tārāvaloka did not learn meaning of ~ (*na-śabdārtha*) 113,23 (TP VIII 125);
 noise (*svana*), of Nala’s wonderful chariot (*āścarya-ratha*) 56,390 (TP IV 248); only cowards (*kātara*) are routed by a mere ~ (*śabda*) 60,54 (TP V 45); ~ of weeping (*rudita-dhvani*) by *nāga-kanyā* in order to draw attention of hero 72,30 (TP VI 70); hand of delicate queen bruised by ~ of pestle (*musala-dhvanī*) 85,23 (TP VII 11); confused ~ (*kalakala*) 122,38 (TP IX 36) and 123,200 (TP IX 57); ~ because of women who heaped up a pyre to enter it 123,320 (TP IX 65); ~ of large fish in river 123,229 (TP IX 59); – see also: anger; drum; lyre; tabor; shriek; *siṃha-nāda*; sound
 non-vegetable food, see: meat; *piśitāśana*; venison
 noon, at ~ the sun stops a *muhūrta* to let dawn (*aruṇa*), his charioteer, bathe and feed the horses 123,12 (TP IX 44)
 noose(s) of Pārvatī’s looks formed by Kāma around Śambhu-Śiva’s neck 1,1 (TP I 1); Domba shows woman how to put head in ~ to hang oneself 13,101 (TP I 157); woman throws ~ of arms (*bhuja-latā-pāśa*) round neck of lover 38,126 (TP III 215); king flings ~ round neck of other king 54,229 (TP IV 200); ~ of Death (Kāla) 72,348 (TP VI 94); kingdom as ~ 73,93 (TP VI 107); woman makes ~ with upper garment to hang herself from *aśoka* tree 95,31 (TP VII 100); lover removes ~ of upper garment from beloved in temple of Kāmadeva 104,142 (TP VIII 11); Varuṇa-weapon produces ~s 118,90 (TP VIII 184); – see also: garment; lasso; *prema-pāśa*; suicide; *vāruṇāstra*
 noose-bearer (*pāśa-hasta*) catches shipwrecked man 56,146 (TP IV 230); – see also: lasso
 North is rich but defiled by intercourse with barbarians (*sphītāpi kauberī mleccha-saṃsarga-garhitā*) 18,58 (TP II 53)
 northern peaks (*uttara-sānavaḥ*) of Mt Kailāsa reddened with evening light 109,94 (TP VIII

¹⁰⁸⁷ See, e.g., Kakar 1989: 13.

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northern quarter, Mt Kailāsa beautiful with smile of ~ (*kauberī-hāsa*) 120,16 (TP IX 2)
 nose, ears and ~ cut off female ascetic itinerant (*pravṛājikā*) 13,160 (TP I 161); king cuts ~
 of impaled robbers on cemetery by night and brings them to brahmins thus becoming their
 head 18,145 (TP II 60) and 151 (TP II 62); ~ of adulterous wife cut off 19,49 (TP II
 88)¹⁰⁸⁸ and 61,166 (TP V 82); flat ~ (*nyañcic-cipita-nāsika*) mark of female ugliness¹⁰⁸⁹
 20,108 (TP II 103); mole on ~ 49,205 (TP IV 99); wicked woman cuts off ~ and ears of
 husband bound to tree 58,99 (TP V 22); ~ of guru cut off and implanted on his wife's
 face 61,16 (TP V 69); women would even eat dirt, if they had no ~s 62,112 (TP V 108); ~
 of adulterous woman bitten of by *vetāla* in corpse of lover 77,68 (TP VI 188) and
daśanaiś chinna-nāsikā bhūtena tat-praviṣṭena 124,117 (TP IX 76); flat ~ (*cipita-*
ghrāṇa) as symbol of male ugliness 123,164 (TP IX 55)
 not-giving, otherwise generous king does not pay *kārpaṭika* 53,6 (TP IV 168); ~ because of
 the sun 54,158 (TP IV 195); 55,15 (TP IV 203); prisoner cannot give daughters in marriage
 199,17 (TP VIII 194)¹⁰⁹⁰
 notice (*cirikā*) hung at the main gate 55,37 (TP IV 205); 71,81 (TP VI 41)
 nouns, see: substantives
ṇ-māṃsa, see: *mahā-māṃsa*
ṇ-paśu 'beast of men', designation of subjects by king 113,49 (TP VIII 127);
ṇtaka, see: actor
 nude (*digambarā*) queen in magic ritual 20,50 (TP II 98 with Penzer's note on p. 117ff.) is
 sprinkled with water, given spells, eats human flesh and becomes witch 110ff. (TP II 108);
 ~ in rite to get help from Piśāca 28,164 (TP III 33); shame for being ~ 73,383 (TP VI
 128); – see also: cannibalism; Digambara; witch
 nudity, see: nakedness
 numeracy, see: *saṃkhyā-jñāna*
 numskull, see: fool
 nun, see: Amarēśa; amazon; ascetic
 nurse (*dhātrī*), beautiful baby girl clings to face of ~ as the candle-flame clings to the wick
 34,98 (TP III 135)¹⁰⁹¹; ladies of the court nursing sick people 66,38 (TP V 181); ~ as
 chaperon 75,94 (TP VI 171);
nyagrodha 'fig-tree, Ficus Indica', see: *divyā strī*; fig-tree; maiden; tree; two *divye kanyake*
nyasta-mantra ('charm-bearing'), Pāśupata ascetic heals madman with his ~ hand 73,381f. (TP
 VI 128);
 nymph(s) (*svarga-vadhū*) dance at a victory feast of Indra 17,19 (TP II 35); heavenly ~ (*divyā*
nārī) emerging from banyan tree¹⁰⁹² 26,210 (TP II 233); ~ (*divya-kanyakā*) singing before

¹⁰⁸⁸ STh Q 451.5ff.

¹⁰⁸⁹ For the snub nose as mark of female ugliness see: bawd.

¹⁰⁹⁰ *Nemo dat quod non habet.*

¹⁰⁹¹ Kumārasambhava 4,30 uses the metaphor of candle and wick for Kāma and Rati (Jackmuth 2002: 154f.).

Śiva's *liṅga* 59,81 (TP V 32); ~ (*divyā strī*) emerging from *śiṃśapā* tree 70,68 (TP VI 29; *āsoka*); by *māyā* Death (*Kāla*) creates ~ and sends her to a robber in order to carry him off 72,341 (TP VI 94); Marubhūti steals clothes of bathing ~ 108,69 (TP VIII 58; cf. 121,111ff. [TP IX 20]); ~ (*dyu-strī*) bears hermit a child and thereby ends her curse 108,74 (TP VIII 59); after dance ~s (*divya-rūpā vara-striyaḥ*) disappear in figures carved on temple pillars 123,132f. as *māyā* of Viśvakarman (TP IX 52); ~ of the eastern quarter, see: *prācī-dig-vadhu*; *pūrva-dig-aṅgana*; – see also: *apsaras*; *divyā kanyā*; heavenly maiden; spell; sylph

oath (*śapatha*)¹⁰⁹³ never to touch wicked sons 7,49 (TP I 78); stepmother asserts to stepson with ~ not to torment him anymore 14,52 (TP I 186); ~ (*grhīta-samaya*) by king in rite involving eating human flesh 20,193 (TP II 112); ~ of travellers to stay together 32,45 (TP III 93f.; cf. below 119,37)¹⁰⁹⁴; queen must swear ~ to stay in city and take care of daughter while king goes to forest with his son 51,42 (TP IV 125); ~ by touching Śiva's feet (*śamāmi pāda-sparśena Dhūrjateḥ*) 66,94 (TP V 185)¹⁰⁹⁵; woman swears ~ (*śapatham satya-vācam babandha*) to return to lover after marriage 84,26 (TP VII 6); ~ sworn by husband not to punish his wife 84,33 (TP VII 7); ~ as confirmation (*sa-śapatham*) of statement 106,142 (TP VIII 39); by ~ (*śapatha*) vassals make themselves sureties 119,37 (TP VIII 195); ~ to return 123,175 (TP IX 55 with ref. to VII 203); – see also: brotherhood; swearing; vow; water of ordeal

obedience of creator to Śiva shown by his placing Śiva's order on his head 34,45 (TP III 131, see: creator); ~ of wife to husband or parents leads to perfection 56,192 (TP IV 233)¹⁰⁹⁶; – see also: disobedience

oblation of rice, milk, etc. (*caru*), purificatory with spells, hermit administers ~ to queen as child-giving substance 9,10 (TP I 95); wife closely knit to husband as ~ (*svāhā*) to fire 69,16 (TP VI 10); ~ (*homa*) with snake-subduing spells (*nāga-damana-mantra*) 70,67 (TP VI 29); magician makes ~ of ghee with ladle and spoon of human bone into mouth of corpse 73,307 (TP VI 123); – see also: *agnihotra*; *agni-kārya*; sacrifice; water oblation
obsequies, see: water-oblation

ocean,¹⁰⁹⁷ as home of marvels (*adbhutālaya*) 26,8 (TP II 217); ~ of milk (*dugdhāmbhas*) churned 46,220 (TP IV 63); man who crossed ~ of curse (*tirṇa-śāpa-mahārṇava*) 67,110 (TP V 204 “~ of separation”); western (*paścimābdhi*) shore of ~ with temple of Caṇḍikā 69,112 (TP VI 17); eastern ~ (*pūrvāmbudhi*) 72,336 (TP VI 94); ~ of existence, see *bhavāmbudhi*; – see also: sea

¹⁰⁹² Cf. Gonda 1965: 339.

¹⁰⁹³ STh *M 100- M 199.

¹⁰⁹⁴ Cf. Rājat 5,422 where an oath of friendship is taken by sacred libation (*pīta-kośa*).

¹⁰⁹⁵ Cf. Bollée 2008: 89.

¹⁰⁹⁶ On obedience see *Mānasollāsa* I § 16; on submissiveness of women Cormack 1961: 77f. and 146.

¹⁰⁹⁷ On the ocean in epic poetry see Hopkins 1900.

odor di femina, see: smell

Oedipus riddle: *kā su-rūpā strī* ? 5,51 (TP I 51)

offence, see: transgression

offering, of one's own flesh to Durgā 11,37 (TP I 125); brahmin ~ *bilva* fruits to Agni 35,56 (TP III 159); ~ of heart and head of wicked mendicant to *vetāla* 99,19 (TP VII 123); ~ of jewels (*ratnair argha*) to the sea 101,178 (TP VII 146); ~ of jewels to sea by prince and five ministers to prevent shipwreck 101,183f. (TP VII 147); combat as ~ to Bhūtas 107,103 (TP VIII 50); golden *haṃsas* make ~ with unfading lotuses 114,42 (TP VIII 135); – see also: filicide; libation

oil, lustration of city (*pura-bhrama*) with ~ not to be spilled 27,48 (TP III 4); what wise man looks for love in courtesans or for ~ in sand ? 57,128 (TP V 10); ~ and ghee are both greasy 61,235 (TP V 88); lamp fed with ~ from human body (*mahā-taila-jvala-dīpa*) 73,306 (TP VI 123);

oil-vessel (*taila-pātra*), leaking ~ 61,190 (TP V 84)

ointment on feet (*pāda-lepa*) enables to find dwelling of snake chief Pārāvātākṣa 70,65 (TP VI 28); ~ enables royal *kārpaṭika* to walk long distance fast 123,19 (TP IX 44)¹⁰⁹⁸ and given to *kārpaṭika* by *yakṣiṇī* 123,27 (TP IX 45); – see also: magic ointment; unguent

old age (*jarā*) reaches king's *karṇa-mūla* and him induces to ascend Himālaya 10,216 (TP I 121); ~ seizes king by chin (*cibuka*) 22,159 (TP II 149); in ~, tip of hermit's ear becomes white 25,14 (TP II 189)¹⁰⁹⁹; Vindhya mountain fruits free from ~ 29,55 (TP III 42); white colour of ~ 30,30 (TP III 66); do, *jarā-pāṇḍu* of king 31,40 (TP III 84); ~ as a woman chooses old king for husband 31,43 (TP III 85); ~ thief of beauty (*saundarya-hāriṇī*) 40,44 (TP III 243); ~ counteracted by stay in *bhū-grha* for eight months 40,49 (TP III 243); king stays in *bhū-grha* with “medicine against ~” 40,57 (TP III 244); elixir (*rasāyana*) against ~ 41,11 and 33 (TP III 253f.)¹¹⁰⁰; ~ about to be stopped by Nāgārjuna in five days with “water of life” (*a-mṛta*) 41,26 (TP III 254); as boon Kaśyapa makes Maya unharmed by ~ and sickness 45,407 (TP IV 45); king retires to Prayāga in ~ 52,386 (TP IV 165); ~ at root of king's ear 52,385 (TP IV 165) and 103,224 (TP VII 190); idem 111,69 (TP VIII 101); ~ caused by want of wealth of youth 61,116 (TP V 78); *Asura* maiden gives king fruit against ~ and death (*jarā-mṛtyu-hara*) 81,108 (TP VI 216)¹¹⁰¹; ~ has seized king by the hair to hand him over to death 111,69 (TP VIII 101); antidotes to ~ and death in country of Mandara 114,54 (TP VIII 136); ~, death and sickness are calamities absent in Siddhīśvara, Hara-Śiva's abode 115,114 (TP VIII 152); king obtains crest-jewel (as a

¹⁰⁹⁸ STh D 1520.26. The Bodhisat goes 30 *yojanas* on foot in one day to Rājagaha (Ja I 66,1). Cf. the Tibetan *rLung sgom* ‘mastery of the currents of energy’ on which see Erhard's definition in 1992: 136 (Lung-Gom), David-Néel 1929: 215f. and Govinda 1980: 133ff.

¹⁰⁹⁹ See Bollée 2010a: 145 note 53.

¹¹⁰⁰ Cf. Devendra on Utt 4,1 (Charpentier 1922: 294) *rasāyaṇaṃ nisevanti maṃsaṃ majja-rasaṃ tahā | bhuñjanti sarasāhāraṃ, jarā tahavi na nassae. //*

¹¹⁰¹ For the motif see STh D 1338.3.2. Baudhāyana-Gṛhya-Śeṣasūtra 3,11 states a rite for conquering death.

talisman) against poison, ~, *rākṣasas* and disease 119,27 (TP VIII 194); ~ as disease (*jarā-roga*) stopped by divine fruit 123,65 (TP IX 47); – see also: antidotes; herb; parents; respect

old brahmin, transformation of Mūladeva into ~ by magic pill (*yoga-gulikā*) 89,25 (TP VII 41f.)

old merchant¹¹⁰² wants to marry young girl averse to him 62,84 (TP V 106)¹¹⁰³; *vidyādhara* prince cursed to become mortal for slaying old men and children with Brahmā weapon 117,151 (TP VIII 174)

old woman (*vṛddhā*), brahmin traveller stays with and is attended by ~ 3,55 (TP I 22); 18,255 (TP II 69); ~ asked by foreigners 43,140f. (TP III 290); ~ dissuades mother to kill son in order to get a second son 61,292 (TP V 94)¹¹⁰⁴; information asked from ~ 64,98 (TP V 147); house of (brahmin) ~ as pension 73,255 (TP VI 119), cf. 75,91 (TP VI 170); ~'s son is a gambler who takes away her clothes 75,95 (TP VI 171); man throws wife and ~, her chaperon (?), into ravine and kills both 77,29 (TP VI 185); ~ weeping with son who is to be eaten by Garuḍa 90,117 (TP VII 57); ~ as harem guardian 105,14 (TP VIII 22); ~ informs king of planned suicide of the harem of his besieged foe 110,6 (TP VIII 82); ~ of harem, Indumatī, sent to imprisoned king 118,140 (TP VIII 187); – see also: garment;

*om*¹¹⁰⁵ recited with heavenly voice (*divyayā girā*) makes brahmin to know the Vedas with the six supplementary sciences 2,78 (TP I 17)

omen, evil ~ (lit. *kṛtānta-dūti* ‘harbinger of death’) of jackal howl (*śabda*) 29,106 (TP III 46), cf. 116,3 below; 31,48 (TP III 86); ~ without counteracting ends in calamity (*avyapohyā-nimittaṃ hi kāryaṃ yat kriyate, tad an-iṣṭāya kalpeta*) 32,41 (TP III 93)¹¹⁰⁶; travelling at night despite evil ~ 32,46ff. (TP III 93f.); delusive ~s (*utpāta-māyā*) displayed by rivals for impediment are dissipated 46,30 (TP IV 51); evil ~ of dog running from left to right, snake appearing on the right, and when left arm and shoulder are throbbing 49,129 (TP IV 93); *mahōtpātas* appear as ~: thunderstorm, earthquake, etc. 107,89f. (TP VIII 49); robber band attacks town disregarding evil ~ (*a-nimitta*) at setting out 114,118 (TP VIII 141), cf. 116,3 (TP VIII 156) when lightning flashes strike banners of army marching out, vultures circle above king’s head, state umbrellas are broken and jackals utter boding howls¹¹⁰⁷; throbbing of a woman’s right eye is an evil ~ 117,141 (TP VIII 173)¹¹⁰⁸; Dānavas ignore ~ (*śakuna*) and go to fight 118,72 (TP VIII 183); partridge appearing on right and she-jackal howling on left hand are bad ~ 124,108 (TP IX 76); deity presiding over (bad) ~ (*śakuna-devatā*) laughs at foolish traveller 124,109 (TP IX 76);

¹¹⁰² See, e.g. Sprockhoff 1979.

¹¹⁰³ Cf. 30,30 (TP III 66).

¹¹⁰⁴ Avadāna 49 (Penzer).

¹¹⁰⁵ TaittUp I 8,1 *Om iti Brahma, om itīdaṃ sarvam*.

¹¹⁰⁶ For an example see 28,130 (TP III 30)

¹¹⁰⁷ Most of these omina are connected with Indra and therefore appear to a king, see ṢaḍviṃśaBr 5,3,1.

¹¹⁰⁸ Also Kādambaṛī 343,2 and 347,3.

omen, lucky (*śubhâgama*): throbbing of man's right eye 51,4 (TP IV 122); citron is ~ (*śakuna*) 53,50 (TP IV 171)

omniscience (*sarvā vidyāḥ*) given by Svāmikumāra Kārttikeya 2,60 (TP I 15); queen has ~ due to fidelity to husband 52,228 (TP IV 154);

one-eyed, boy (*kāṇa-baṭu*) 16,23 (TP II 22); ~ and hunchback brahmin 18,133 (TP II 59)

one finger sign meaning to come near 7,63 (TP I 80)

onehundred and five Dasyus killed 13,40 (TP I 152); ~ women in harem 13,57 (TP I 153)

oneness, until one perceives ~ of Viṣṇu, Śiva and Brahmā, successes of worshipping them separately appear sort-lived 73,170 (TP VI 113);

only daughter, of king (i.e. who had no other offspring: *an-anya-saṃtati*) 52,93 (TP IV 144); ~ (*ekâpatyā*) of bawd 57,85 (TP V 7)

only son 28,114 (TP III 29); 78,71 (TP VI 105); 104,20 (TP VIII 2);¹¹⁰⁹ – see: age; filicide; son

“only” topos: in this city the ~ imprisonment was seen in the committing to paper of the words of poets ... 55,27 (TP IV 204); 91,7 (TP VII 66); 92,11ff. (TP VII 71); 93,5f. (TP VII 78); 97,6f. (TP VII 112); – cf. Kād 10,6ff.; 89,3ff.; 119,2ff.; 125,5ff., etc.

opening (*vivara*) leading to *pātāla*, ~ in Cashmere made by Maya 73,107 (TP VI 108)¹¹¹⁰

oral tradition (*mukhâgama*) descending through mothers-in-law 19,35 (TP II 87)

ordeal,¹¹¹¹ vessel with oil to be carried around city without spilling a drop as royal instruction 27,43 and 53 (TP III 4); ~ (*divya*) of two brothers with man in tree as witness 60,221 (TP V 60; ORC 1439 on p. 690¹¹¹²; MI 971: “... stimmten die beiden Brüder dem Entschluß zu, sich einem Gottesurteil zu unterwerfen”); water of ~ (*koṣa-vāri*) in which the image of Hāṭakésvara has been washed must be drunk 119,35-39 (TP VIII 195 with note 3);

ornament (*ābharāṇa*),¹¹¹³ rank and power (*vibhava*) are to a blockhead like an ~ on a log of wood (*kāṣṭha*) 6,143 (TP I 71); ~ (*vibhūṣaṇa*) lost by adulteress 21,82 (TP II 131); false (*kṛtrima*) ~ 24,178 (TP II 182); Viṭaṅkapura is ~ of the seashore (*vāri-dhes tīra-tilaka*) 25,38 (TP II 191); bewildered princess's ~s warn jingling out the sounds: “This is not the man.” 33,172 (TP III 121); 51,183 (TP IV 134); king takes his ~ from fool who found them 61,27 (TP V 72); exchange of ~s between lovers in order to make certain that they were not dreamers 73,349 (TP VI 126); ~ with the name of the female owner 73,356 (TP VI 126); ~ of woman taken away and offered for sale 75,163 (TP VI 175); ~ with the power of becoming a *vidyādhara* 119,21 (TP VIII 194); – see also: *danta-patra*; ear-ornament; earring; jewel(s); Kauśāmbī; ring

¹¹⁰⁹ Also Bāṇa, *Kād.* 54,3f.

¹¹¹⁰ Cf. STh *F 92.3.

¹¹¹¹ See Kane 1973 III 1053f.; STh D 1394.1. A different water ordeal is described by Johannes Stobaios, *Physica* I 36 (McCrindle 1901: 172).

¹¹¹² Reading *sthāpitāv ā divya-cchedam* for *ā dina-cchedam* (D) gives a better sense and may, therefore, be original, but infringes the metre which, therefore, D will have corrected, as in 93,9, at the expense of the meaning.

¹¹¹³ E.g. Dallapiccola 2002: 147f.

orphan, brahmin ~ grows up with uncle 49,161 (TP IV 96);
oṣadhī-rasa-nasya ‘sternutatory made of plant extract’ heals man who became boa constrictor
 after eating gourd / cucumber 123,46 (TP IX 46)
 outcaste (*patita*) 7,48 (TP I 78)
 overhearing¹¹¹⁴ of Śiva by Puṣpadanta 1,55 (TP I 6); ~ of *rākṣasī* 5,26 (TP I 49); ~ of Piśācas
 and thus learning their language 7,27 (TP I 76); ~ of Brahmā and Śaṅkara-Śiva by Bhūti
 varman 7,34 (TP I 77); ~ of hermit by merchant 15,33 (TP II 4); ~ flying spell 20,139 (TP
 II 107); brahmin ~ conversation (*saṃlāpa*) of birds speaking with human language 26,28
 (TP II 219); ~ of heavenly voices which know to be overheard 28,123-130 (TP III 30); ~
 of *rākṣasī* by woman in tree trunk 29,148 (TP III 50); maid ~ (*dadau dvāri karṇam*)
 brahmin¹¹¹⁵ 30,115 (TP III 72); double ~¹¹¹⁶ 32,38-40 (TP III 93); *brahma-rākṣasa*
 overhears woman 33,102 (TP III 114); ~ of king by *brahma-rākṣasa* 33,104 (TP III 114);
 minister ~ maids in second *pātāla* 45,281 and 287 (TP IV 36); ~ of hermits by mouse
 61,112 (TP V 78); ~ of man inside house by man outside 61,259 (TP V 92); musician ~
 man telling his treasurer to give him two thousand *paṇas* 63,158 (TP V 133); *pravṛtī* ~
yakṣa couple in tree 66,20 (TP V 179); mendicant excuses his ~ 66,55 (TP V 182);
 66,91 (TP V 184f.); king ~ conversation between hermit and pupil 69,176 (TP VI 21);
 boar ~ conversation (*saṃlāpa*) between lion and mate 72,128 (TP VI 78); ~ conversation
 (*kathā*) between elephant and blinded man 74,317 (TP VI 163)¹¹¹⁷; king ~ goddess Earth
 (Pṛthivī) telling his waiter to sacrifice his son for the king 78,51 (TP VI 104); attendant tells
 princess that *mama saṃnidhau* her brother proposed their father to give her in marriage to
 her beloved 90,82 (TP VII 55); Jīmūtavāhana ~ mother and son’s talk while waiting for
 Garuḍa who will eat the latter 90,118 and 127 (TP VII 57f.); *sarveṣv ākarṇayatsu* 105,14
 (TP VIII 22); two *vidyādhara*s ~ the king 108,127 (TP VIII 63); king ~ Asura who tells
 his daughter his only vital point 112,53 (TP VIII 110)
 owl(s) defeat crows in banyan tree at night 62,7 (TP V 98); ~ as inauspicious bird 62,27 (TP
 V 100 with note)¹¹¹⁸; *vetāla* with eyes like an ~ (*ulūkākṣi*) 102,19 (TP VII 163)
 ox, transformation into ~ by magic string around neck 37,153 (TP III 194)¹¹¹⁹; good witch has
 compassion with overloaded ~ 37,155 (TP III 194); man always living on a single ~
 thanks to Devī (Durgā) boon in dream 66,103 (TP V 185)¹¹²⁰; ~ as symbol of *dharma*
 70,118 (TP VI 32); – for ~ as term of abuse see: bull

pacifism pronounced by Kaśyapa’s wife Danu 50,115 (TP IV 115)

¹¹¹⁴ See note 1 in TP I 48; TP II 107 and 219, TP III 60ff. and 151. Bloomfield 1920a.

¹¹¹⁵ Who apparently did not speak Sanskrit.

¹¹¹⁶ *Rākṣasa* overhears woman who overhears other woman.

¹¹¹⁷ OTI B 210.

¹¹¹⁸ STh B 147.1.1.4.

¹¹¹⁹ See TP VI 59ff.; STh D 133.3.

¹¹²⁰ See Brown 1920: 98.

pāda-lepa ‘ointment for the feet’ used by ascetic in order to walk long distances fast 70,65 (TP VI 28); 123,19 (TP IX 44) and 27 (TP IX 45);

pāda-nyāsa ‘placing the foot’ (in dwarf incarnation), *tīrtha* risen from ~ of Hari 73,95 (TP VI 107)

-*pādapa*, see: tree

pade pade ‘gradually; in driblets’ 102,54 (TP VII 166); – see: Agastya; stylistic repetition

padmāṅkitōtsaṅga (epitheton of Hari-Viṣṇu) 38,58 (TP III 210 wrongly: “with his breast marked with a lotus” instead of: ‘with his belly’; ORC 389: “*portant sur sa poitrine la marque du lotus*”; M I 545: “*seine Brust war mit Lotusblüten geschmückt*”)¹¹²¹

padma-rāga-maṇi see: ruby

padmāsana ‘lotus seat’, ascetic sitting in ~ posture 24,96 (TP II 176); 110,23 (TP VIII 83)

padma-vimāna ‘lotus chariot’ of Naravāhanadatta 108,99 (TP VIII 61)

pacan, see: eulogy

pagan, noble,¹¹²² see Śabara 22,65 (TP II 141)

painting wall, pseudo-Viṣṇu emerging from ~, see: man

painter (*citra-kara*) goes with king’s canvas portrait to the latter’s beloved 51,124 (TP IV 131);

~ from Ujjayinī (lit.: the Vidarbhas) advertises himself at palace gate 55,36 and paints king 55,46 (TP IV 205f.); ~ paints princess for lover 72,294 (TP VI 90); female mendicant as ~ 101,74 (TP VII 139); famous ~ (*citra-kr̥t*), enjoying revenues of onehundred villages, paints various girls for king as models of female beauty 122,20 (TP IX 35);

painting, defective ~ of queen 5,32 (TP I 49); ~ a bawd red and black like a Gaṇa 12,169 (TP I 146); ~ of king 55,47ff. (TP IV 206); merchant’s son in love with ~ (*citra-paṭa*) of princess 72,295 (TP VI 90); black snake on ~ 72,302 (TP VI 91); ~ in the sky as example of impossibility [q. v.]; ~ (*citra-kalā*) of *vidyādharīs* 44,52 (TP IV 4); ~ (*paṭeṣu likhitān*) of kings made for *svayaṃvara* 83,14 (TP VII 2); female ascetic makes ~ of beautiful princess 101,74 (TP VII 139); Kātyāyanī asked to paint prince on canvas to test her catching likeness (*sadr̥śālekhya-vijñāna*) 101,79f. (TP VII 139); lonesome Gandharva princess ~ beloved 117,24ff. (TP VIII 165f.)

painting tablet, see: *citra-phalaka*

Paiśāci¹¹²³ language different from three other languages not used by Guṇāḍhya 6,4 (TP I 60);

– see also: seven tales

pākhaṇḍin, see: heretic

pakṣa-pāta ‘flapping of wings, flying; partiality’ (MW), bird whose ~ was as extraordinary as that of fate 26,35 (TP II 219 “exhibiting a strange partiality ... like destiny”; ORC 238 “*dont les ailes donnaient des coups aussi extraordinaires que ceux du sort*”)

pakṣi-vahana (not MW) ‘with a bird as mount, who rides on a bird’, king ~ 118,68 (TP VIII 182)

¹¹²¹ See Duda 2006: 288f.

¹¹²² Cf. Curtius 1965: 249 (*edler Heide*).

¹¹²³ See ORC 1620; Master 1943; Kuv p. 238 with note 807.

pala,¹¹²⁴ iron balance weighs a thousand ~ 60,238 (TP V 62); five ~ of flesh cut from a robber's body 61,284 (TP V 93)

palace (*vāsa-veśman*)¹¹²⁵ with two women burnt to cover up abduction 10,110 (TP I 113) and 16,14 (TP II 21); plot to set fire to queen's ~ (*vāsaka*) 15,21 (TP II 3ff.); city with (white)¹¹²⁶ ~s compared to smile (*saudha-hāsini* [not MW] *puri*) 18,10 (TP II 50); splendour of ~ as that of the sea when the moon is rising 18,24 (TP II 51); due to a spell man flew up into the air with a ~ 20,171 (TP II 110); ~ (*divyaṃ grhaṃ*) of *yakṣi* in fig tree¹¹²⁷ 26,212 (TP II 233); white ~s¹¹²⁸ (*sita-harmya*) in Ujjayinī compared to peaks of Kailāsa 27,136 (TP III 11); Maya builds ~ of Indra (*Vajra-bhṛtaḥ sabhā*) 29,13 (TP III 40); queen put in empty (~) with four halls (*catuḥ-śāla*) to prevent contact with men 36,57 (TP III 173); description of courtesan's ~ (*mandira*) with seven zones (*kaṣṣyā*) **38,20-27** (TP III 208); golden ~ like Mt Meru 43,9 (TP III 281); ~ top white with plaster 73,26 (TP VI 70); white ~ in Vārāṇasī 114,19 (TP VIII 133); ~s in Rasātala with lakes of heavenly wine in their gardens and many stairs of precious stones 118,106 (TP VIII 185); ~ of Indra the gate of which was adorned by the deity's elephant (*surēbha-śobhita-dvāra*) 121,129 (TP IX 21)

palace-gate, see: *siṃha-dvāra*

palanquin, merchant's daughter carried in ~ (*śibikā*) to place of execution of her chosen husband 88,41 (TP VII 38)¹¹²⁹; man disguised as woman put in ~ and brought to house of bride 104,159 (TP VIII 13); king and court travel in ~ made by *vidyādhara* Amitagati 107,77 (TP VIII 48); 110,102 (TP VIII 89); – see also: *karṇi-ratha*

palāśa 'Butea frondosa = monosperma',¹¹³⁰ king clad in vest, dark green as ~ (*milad-vyādhaḥ ~-śyāma-kañcukaḥ*) chases with huntsmen 21,11 (TP II 126); a wishing-tree, in the case of ill-starred men, often becomes a ~ 53,35 (TP IV 170);

palli ('village of Bhillas / Mātāṅgas') 10,135f. (TP I 115); 71,13 (TP VI 37)

palm trees (*kharjūrī*) cut down by foolish villagers to get dates 61,34 (TP V 71)¹¹³¹;

paṇa,¹¹³² half ~ recovered from servant by foolish rich man 61,276 (TP V 92); a traveller

¹¹²⁴ ORC 1621 (ca. 93 grs); Srinivasan 1979: 71 and 107.

¹¹²⁵ ORC 65: '*palais*', but MW translates this as 'bed-chamber'.

¹¹²⁶ The white colour averts evil (Weinreich 1909: 67 note).

¹¹²⁷ Gonda 1965: 339.

¹¹²⁸ See Coomaraswamy 1931: 185.

¹¹²⁹ For a picture of a princess in a palanquin in Angkor see: Albanese 2011: 96f. The present author saw such things in Mandalay still in 1964. See also Yule and Burnell 659ff. under palankeen and 313 under dhooly, doolie. In British times the former was carried by four or six men, the latter, which was lighter and cheaper than a palanquin, by two or four. In Meadows Taylor 1967: 2 a Pathan merchant's wife and son were travelling in a doolie. For a picture see "Post Card of Dhoolie Bearers - Benares" in the Internet.

¹¹³⁰ Macmillan 1991: 102; Jackmuth 2002: 142f.; Upadhyaya 1965: 10.

¹¹³¹ The story corresponds to Avadāna 45 (Penzer).

¹¹³² For the copper coin see Rekhā Jain 1995: 72ff.

buys eight cakes for one ~ 62,204 (TP V 116); stupid physician loses bet of one hundred ~ to cure a hunchback 62,234 (TP V 119); treasurer ordered to give musician (*gāndharvika*) two thousand ~ 63,158 (TP V 133)

pāna ‘wine-party’ 28,121 (TP III 29); king enjoys drinking-bout ~ with queen before sleeping with her 33,13 (TP III 107); ~ is a royal *krīḍā* 34,93 (TP III 135); ~ of king and queen for good luck (*pāna-māṅgala*) after inauspicious dream 36,67 (TP III 174); courtesan spends days with king at ~ 38,33 (TP III 208);

pāna-bhū = *pāna-līlā* 21,10 (TP II 126)

pāna-goṣṭhī ‘drinking-party’ 44,51 (TP IV 4; also Daś 267,8)

pāna-krīḍā (not MW) ‘amusement of drinking’ 44,184 (TP IV 13)

pāna-līlā ‘banquet of wine’ 17,1 (TP II 34); 111,20 (TP VIII 97);

pāna-mada ‘drunkenness’ (not MW), king takes sword from thief asleep due to ~ 56,226 (TP IV 236); Kali enters Nala’s body senseless from ~ 56,288 (TP IV 241)

pānam āsevate ‘to have a drink’ 28,121 (TP III 29); 33,13 (TP III 107)

pāna-supta ‘fallen asleep after drinking’, said of king 28,28 (TP III 22)

pañca-cūḍa ‘with five locks’ left on head of bawd 12,168 (TP I 146)

pañcāgni ‘with three sacrificial fires and two hungry stomach fires’ of couple 73,58 (TP VI 105);

Pañcaśikha, the Gaṇa ~ comes to brahmin when thought of 7,83 (TP I 83)¹¹³³

Pañcatantra begins with KSS chapter 60.

panem et circenses, see: people

panic-seed, see: *priyaṅgu*

Pāṇini as stupid pupil gets new grammar (*vyākaraṇa*) from Indu-śekhara = Śiva 4,20ff. (TP I 32); ~ wins disputation (*vāda*) on grammar on the 8th day 4,24 (TP I 32)

pannagāstra, see: snake-weapon

panting (*śvasan*) *brahma-rākṣasa* 94,115 (TP VII 95)

paṇya-vilāsini, see: poison-damsels; prostitute

pāpa, cf.: *agha* and see: transgression

pāpa as term of abuse for Prajāpati Dakṣa, father of Pārvatī 1,38 (TP I 4); *pāpe*, for the wife of a waterspirit 63,29 (TP V 121)

pāpa-hara ‘removing evil’, ~ lake 56,121 (TP IV 228)¹¹³⁴

parables, see: comparison(s)

para-dāra-grhaṇ kurute ‘to make another’s wife one’s own: to commit adultery’ 105,18 (TP VIII 22)

para-hita ‘the good of others’, only ~ in the *saṃsāra* is real 28,16 (TP III 19)

paramāṇna ‘rice pudding’,¹¹³⁵ boy crying in front of ~ 124,135 (TP IX 78)

¹¹³³ Zin 2003b: 155 note 24.

¹¹³⁴ On the cleansing power of water from transgressions see, e.g., Glasenapp 1922: 44f.

¹¹³⁵ Offered to gods and deceased ancestors (MW). For a recipe see Prakash 1961: 289 sub 86 (rice: milk: ghee = 4: 12: 6).

pāramitā ‘perfection’ 72,218 (TP VI 84); – see further: *kṣamā*-°; *dāna*-°; *dhairya*-°; *dhyāna*-°; *prajñā*-°; *śīla*-°;

paraṃ jyotiḥ ‘supreme brightness’ 56,190 (TP IV 233; ORC 633: “*lumière suprême*”); – cf. emancipation ; *siddhi*

paramour, man supposes wife to have ~ (*upapati*) 14,47 (TP I 185); prince leaves wife with ~ (*kāmuka*) 21,81 (TP II 131); ~ killed by Śavara 32,69 (TP III 95); king’s tolerance of merchant ~ (*prachanna-kāmuka*) 36,97 (TP III 176); *vidyādhari* cursed to become mortal queen and (subsequently) *rākṣasī* with former husband as ~ (*priya*) 42,207 (TP III 274); woman ever taking other ~s (*nava-nava-priya*) 52,296 (TP IV 158); ~ kills husband of adulterous wife and is then killed himself by relatives while the wife is banished 58,75ff. (TP V 20); 62,111 and 115 (TP V 108); 65,40 (TP V 156); warder is secret ~ of queen (*rāja-strī-channa-kāmuka*) 71,33 (TP VI 38); ~ thought to be thief and hanged 77,64 (TP VI 187); princess eloping with ~ 89,99 (TP VII 47); wife leaves sleeping husband and goes to impaled ~ 124,116 (TP IX 76); – see also: adulterer; husband; *para-strī*

Pārasikas (Persians), head of king of ~ cut off by king of Vatsa 19,110 (TP II 94); Nirmūka king of the ~ 122,4 (TP IX 34)

para-strī ‘wife of another’, man with ~ (*naraḥ saha para-striyā*) = adulterer 13,167 (TP I 162)

Pāravatākṣa, chief of snakes obtained sword Vaidūryakānti 70,60 (TP VI 28);

pardon, I beg you ~ ! *kṣamasva* ! 30,106 (TP III 71)

parents, unwittingly eating son 20,208 (TP II 113); as to the old husband they have chosen for her princess says: “what do I care for my ~” (*kiṃ tātena kiṃ ambayā*) 31,4 (TP III 81); prostration before ~ 54,68f. (TP IV 189)¹¹³⁶ et passim; son goes on trading voyage against will of ~ 56,140 (TP IV 230); ~ curse disobedient son 56,150 (TP IV 230); devotion to ~ gives one power of discernment 56,186 (TP IV 233); ~ curse disobedient daughter 59,153 (TP V 36); Yakṣa ~ who deposited their son after birth advise him to go to gamblers’ asylum 73,187f. (TP VI 115); ~ called upon by weak creature (*durbala*) in danger 94,130 (TP VII 96); do, 113,65 (TP VIII 128); king leaves for the forest to practise ascetism without telling ~ 115,13 (TP VIII 145); fool departs to fetch wife without telling ~ 124,107 (TP IX 76);

parihāsa ‘joking at’, royal ladies ~ king 108,158 (TP VIII 65)

pārijāta (coral or paradise tree, Erythrina spp.¹¹³⁷), hermit gives king garland from ~ 15,129 (TP II 13); ~ emerges from sea 86,48 (TP VII 16); female attendant served under ~ with luxuries 117,85 (TP VIII 170); hermit contemplates under ~ 117,128 (TP VIII 172); king Saṃgrāma of Kashmir is a ~ of the Sātavāhana race E 1 (TP IX 87)¹¹³⁸; ~ garland, see: garlands; – see also *mandāra*

pāriṭoṣika ‘reward’ given to messenger 117,116 (TP VIII 172); – see also: fee; reward

¹¹³⁶ TP omit “of his mother” before: Vāsavadattā.

¹¹³⁷ Macmillan 1991: 249.

¹¹³⁸ Syed 1990: 435.

parivartini vidyā ‘science of counteracting’ 46,118, obtained when resisting for three days force of fire 46,121 (TP IV 56)

parivrāt ‘wandering ascetic’, gives brahmin spell for obtaining *yakṣiṇī* 49,179f. (TP IV 97); – cf. *pravrajaka*

parking, see: horse (left outside hermitage)
(parking lot: see figure of *samavasaraṇa* at *karṇī-ratha* above)

parody of judgement 72,212f. (TP VI 84); ~ of *śraddhā* 61,196ff. (TP V 85); ~ of marriage between young wife and rich old man 62,83 (TP 106)

parōpakāra (‘service to others’), see: charity; sayings

parricide, attempt stopped 25,107 (TP II 199); – see also: husband-killer

parrot(s)’ speech cursed by Agni to be inarticulate 20,79 (TP II 101)¹¹³⁹; king warned of angry queen by ~ in cages 55,123 (TP IV 210); Niṣāda princess with ~ in cage wishes to see king 59,24f. (TP V 27f.); ~ knowing four Vedas and is poet 59,29 (TP V 28); ~ fostered by father after mother’s death 59,39 (TP V 29)¹¹⁴⁰; ~ caught (and eaten) by Śabara 59,45 (TP V 29)¹¹⁴¹; ~ in pre-birth *ṛṣi* and therefore remembers the *śāstras* 59,157 (TP V 36); king of ~s remembers pre-births 72,237 (TP VI 86); ~ throws *āmalaka* on his reflection in water taking it to be his wife 72,246 (TP VI 86); royal couple have learned ~ (*śuka*), and hen-*maina* (*śārikā*) 77,6-8 (TP VI 183); ~ becomes *Gandharva* after curse ends 77,89 (TP VI 189); ~ with *maina* (*sārikā*) in court 103,198 (TP VII 188); – see also: *āmalakas*

part-*bodhisattva*, son of merchant is ~ 65,2 and 14 (TP V 153f.); ~ as ascetic draws four beings with articulate speech from a well with a rope made of grass 65,54 (TP V 158); lion feeds ~ with venison (*mṛgāmiṣa*) 65, 101 (TP V 162)

parthenogenesis,¹¹⁴² of centipedes in king’s ear 29.137 (TP III 49); – see also: birth in unusual way

part-incarnation, Naravāhanadatta ~ of Kāma (Kāmāṃśa) 44,9 (TP IV 1); (*avatārāṃśa*) Rāma ~ of Viṣṇu 51,60 (TP IV 126); boar as ~ of Buddha (*Buddhāṃśa-sambhava*) 72,122 (TP VI 78); Indra praises prince as ~ of Buddha (*Sugatāṃśa*) 72,234 (TP VI 85); Vikramāditya is ~ of Maheśvara 99,33 who gives him the magic sword Invincible (Aparājita) 99,37 (TP VII 124) and 115,141 (TP VIII 154); *vidyādhara* prince is ~ of Śiva 115,124 and 130 (TP VIII 153); ~ of Gaurī 115,126 (TP VIII 153); Mahendrāditya is ~ of Śiva and his wife is ~ of Ambikā 120,28 (TP IX 3);

partridge (*cakora*), female ~ can never be satisfied with gazing on the moon 34,102 (TP III 136); moon refreshes ~s when exhausted with severe heat 42,148 (TP III 270); woman longs to drink in man with her eyes, as the female ~ longs to drink the moon 49,211 (TP IV 99); ~ not satisfied by devouring moonlight 51,154 (TP IV 133); looking at a woman(’s face) with the insatiate eye of ~ (looking at moon) 52,351 (TP IV 162); women’s eyes feast

¹¹³⁹ Bāṇa, *Kād.* 27,7.

¹¹⁴⁰ Bāṇa, *Kād.* 54,3.

¹¹⁴¹ Smith 2006: 87.

¹¹⁴² Cf. Smith 1991.

on lovely man like ~s feast on moon rays 77,50 (TP VI 187); emulating ~ (*caḥorāyitum*) 89,41 (TP VII 43); brahmin beholds beautiful merchant daughter as ~ the moonlight 93,45 (TP VII 81); ~ (*kaṣiñjala*) on right hand bad omen for traveller 124,108 (TP IX 76)
pāruṣya ‘horny growth’ on the arm produced by the bowstring (*maurvikināñke bhujē*) 118,11 (TP VIII 178f.)

Pārvatī, Śiva’s *śakti*, incarnation of Nārāyaṇa and Śiva’s wife in a pre-birth 1,32f. (TP I 4); ~ curses Mālyavān to be born as Guṇāḍhya 1,57 (TP I 7); Gaurī = ~ prophesies prince and princess in dream to find each other 65,232f. and 236f. (TP V 172f.); subaqueous temple of ~ 81,75 (TP VI 214)¹¹⁴³; husband taken as fruit of Pārvatī-*sevā* 81,87 (TP VI 214)¹¹⁴⁴; ~ curses five attendants for laughing 114,66 (TP VIII 137); princess dreams of ~ desisting from throwing a garland of lotus around her neck 117,166 (TP VIII 175)

pāśa, see: lasso; noose

passion(s),¹¹⁴⁵ (*riraṃsā*) renewed while beating wife with creepers 58,95 (TP V 22); females are enveloped with a thick cloud of ~ (*bhūri-rajo-bhṛtaḥ*) 72,256 (TP VI 87; ORC 843: “(les femmes) portent en elles une quantité importante d’impuretés faites de passions”; M II 99: “Frauen bringen viel Dunkel der Leidenschaft mit sich. Sie gleichen den gewaltige und ungeheuerliche Wolken mit sich führenden Winden”); lover bitten by snake of ~ (*rāga-mahā-vyāla*) 89,63 (TP VII 44)¹¹⁴⁶; ~s are in the end distasteful (*bhāvān avasāna-nīrasān*) 119,216 (TP VIII 209); – see also: vice

paśu as invective for stupid brahmin 6,63 and 80 (TP I 65f.); ~ as designation of false friend and adulterer 60,5 (TP V 41); two heirs at heritage cut ~ in half 62,175 (TP V 114)

paśu-nibha (? not MW) ‘beastlike’, a prostitute does not care for fee or any ~ men (*na bhāṭyā kāryam asmākaṃ nānyair ~air nṛbhiḥ*) 124,178 (TP IX 81; ORC 1317: “bêtes humaines”)

Pāśupata ascetic¹¹⁴⁷ (*mahā-vratin*) skull-bearing, white with ashes, and with matted hair 25,81 (TP II 196); ~, brahmin, treasure hunter (*nidhānānveṣaṇāyāgāt khanya-vādin*) 34,69 (TP III 133); four ~s disregard warning against *yakṣiṇī* making grow horns on them and devouring them 37,58f. (TP III 186f.); ~ calling *haṃsī* 43,173 (TP III 293); ~ performs nightly rites with king to obtain magic sword which allows flying 56,215 (TP IV 235, cf. 73,278ff. [TP VI 120f.]); robber assumes appearance of ~ 64,67 (TP V 144); minister disguised as Pāśupata ~ (*mahā-vratika*) 69,53 (TP VI 12); prince leaves town secretly disguised as Pāśupata ~ with *khaṭvāṅga*, etc., 70,2 (TP VI 23); ~ with superhuman powers (*siddha-yogin mahāvratā-dhara*) 73,368 (TP VI 127); ~ praising Gaṇeśa 73,376ff. (TP VI 127); ~ heals madman (*unmāda*) by striking him with his charm-bearing (*nyasta-mantra*) hand 73,381f. (TP VI 128); ~ with divine power (*divya-siddhi-bhṛt*) 73,386 (TP

¹¹⁴³ In 81,79 it was a temple of Durgā.

¹¹⁴⁴ Translated by TP as “adoration of Durgā.”

¹¹⁴⁵ See Kuv note 12.

¹¹⁴⁶ “Snake” may mean an indication of extension here as in 10,49 (TP I 109) the site of a city is compared to the snake Ananta. Cf. German *Schlange*.

¹¹⁴⁷ See, e.g. Doniger O’Flaherty 1981: 182f.; Bhatt 2012.

VI 128); ~ with body smeared with ashes, with matted hair and trident 92,31 and whose food is refused by insolvent brahmin gambler 92,34 (TP VII 73); ~ has magic powers (*siddha*) 92,35 (TP VII 73); ~ *yogī* enters corpse of young brahmin on the pyre and tells bystanders the lie that Śiva reanimated him 97,38 (TP VII 114); first weeping then dancing ~ 97,32 (TP VII 114); ~ with supernatural knowledge (*jñānin*) in Śiva-temple 108,35 (TP VIII 55); – see also: ascetic; hermit; *khaṭvāṅga*

Pāśupata weapon sent to king by Śaṅkara-Śiva for his victory, description of ~ (speaking understandably and looking like the fire of doomsday) 118,75ff. (TP VIII 183)

pāśa-rajjū (thus read for D: *pāśu-rajjū*) ‘fetter, noose-rope’ 18,298 (TP II 72)

paṭaha ‘kettledrum’ invites suitors of princess to spend a night with her 18,321 (TP II 73)¹¹⁴⁸; – see also: daybreak; drum; proclamation

pāṭala, see: trumpet-flower

Pātāla¹¹⁴⁹ to be entered in a cavern 45,51 (TP IV 20) or by opening in the water 45,67 (TP IV 22); temple in ~ 45,77 (TP IV 22); nectar (*sudhā-pāna*) drunk in 3rd ~ equips with divine body 45,131f. (TP IV 26); Bali in 3rd ~ 45,151 (TP IV 28); Prahlāda in 4th ~ 45,174 (TP IV 29); Daitya king Amīla in 2nd ~ 45,192 (TP IV 30); Kalāvati in 2nd ~ 45,280 (TP IV 36); Durāroha in the 5th ~ 45,325 (TP IV 38); Sumāya in the 6th ~ 45,332 (TP IV 39); Tantukaccha in the 7th ~ 45,329 (TP IV 39); Sūryaprabha has heavenly enjoyment with princess Sundarī in third ~ 45,337 (TP IV 39); twelve *apsaras* abducted from Indra’s heaven to first ~ 45,354 (TP IV 40); Daityas as kings of seven ~ 50,108 (TP IV 115); ~ residence of Daityas 73,102 (TP VI 108f.; cf. 119,2 et passim); many openings leading to ~ on this earth, a famous one made by Maya in Kaśmīra 73,107 (TP VI 108); ~’s gate guarded by Durgā Śārikā 73,110 (TP VI 108); king and company marching to ~ for five days and nights 73,118 (TP VI 109); thief’s cavern looking like second ~ 88,21 (TP VII 36); dark lake compared to ~ 100,16 (TP VII 129); *āśrama* of Kaśyapa resembles above ground ~ 111,99 (TP VIII 103); prince, portion of Śiva (*Śivāṃśa*), will get earth and ~ into his power 118,21ff. (TP VIII 179); king with divine power (*divya-prabhāva*) can enter ~ and return to earth 123,80f. (TP IX 49)

Pātāla-śāstra, treatise with spells and ceremonies (*mantra-tantra*) to propitiate Śiva Hātakeśana 73,104 (TP VI 108);

Pāṭaliputra capital of king Nanda 2,45 (TP I 12); ~ home of Sarasvatī and Lakṣmī 3,3 (TP I 18); story (*vṛttānta*) of the women of ~ 66,28 (TP V 180: “tricks of the w.”; ORC 767: “*tu as répété l’histoire des femmes*”; M I 1081: “*du hast es wahrlich den Frauen gleichgetan*”); Sarasvatī tutelary deity of ~ 66,30 (TP V 180);

pataṅga-vṛtti (entering the city is rather) ‘temerity, very inconsiderate behaviour’, lit.: conduct of a flying insect (*praveśanam param ~ḥ*)¹¹⁵⁰ 102,25 (TP VII 164 ‘mere chimerical fancy’;

¹¹⁴⁸ The *p.* also marks the half-hour in Bāṇa, *Kād.* 28,2; *dundubhiḥ paṭahas tadvat gambhīreṇa svareṇa śabdena* (*Kād.* 358,21).

¹¹⁴⁹ Cf. ORC 1623.

¹¹⁵⁰ On *pataṅga* see Jackmuth 2002: 65f. and Hanneder 2005a: 661.

ORC 1063: “*se jeter dans la gueule du loup*” explained on p. 1481 as: “*se comporter comme le papillon qui, attiré par la lumière, se précipite dessus et meurt*”; M II 412: “*Darum käme ein gewaltsames Eindringen eher dem Gebaren einer Motte gleich*”)

pāṭhaka, see: reciter

Pāthaspati, see: Varuṇa

patience (*kṣamā*) virtue of brahmins 66,16 (TP V 179); by ~ (*dhairya*) everything is acquired 69,11 (TP VI 9 ‘endurance’); emancipation fruit of ~ (~*ā mokṣa-phalā*) 72,274 (TP VI 89); be patient! (*avalambasva!*) 124,243 (TP IX 85)

*patita*¹¹⁵¹ ‘outcaste’ 7,48 (TP I 78)

pa(t)tra, see: make-up

paunch, big ~ (*pr̥thūdara*) mark of male ugliness 123,164 (TP IX 55); – see: Gaṇeśa (50,177; 70,125)

paura-svāmika-rājya ‘constitutional kingdom’ 113,20 (TP VIII 125)

paurāyatta (not MW) ‘depending on > under the thumb of the subjects’, kind of constitutional of kingdom which crown prince therefore does not care for 113,48 (TP VIII 129)

pauruṣa-pādapa, see: valour, tree of ~

pavement in palace composed of jewels 22,7 (TP II 137)¹¹⁵²; 50,130 (TP IV 116); 117,14 (TP VIII 165)

pavitra, see: colander

pawn, see: *bandha*

payment of servants in natura (cooked rice: *pakvānna*) 27,90 (TP III 7); no ~ for Rājput in king’s service 81,7 (TP VI 209); – see also: *dakṣiṇā*; fee; reward

peacock(s),¹¹⁵³ Skanda’s mount (*vāhana*) 7,13 (TP I 75); raindrops delight ~ afflicted by heat 9,88 (TP I 102)¹¹⁵⁴; arrival of cloud revives ~ 10,84 (TP I 112); citizens behold returning king with bride as ~ behold cloud with lightning 14,18 (TP I 183); with uplifted necks all in court joyfully imitate peafowl (dancing) at coming of rain-clouds 16,121 (TP II 30)¹¹⁵⁵, cf. 110,101 below); Asura daughter’s beauty bewilders three worlds like a bunch of peacock feathers of the juggler Kāma¹¹⁵⁶ 30,3 (TP III 64); divine hero (Kārttikeya) on ~ appears to dreamer 43,50 (TP III 284); ~ dancing at thunderstorm 71,17 (TP VI 37); butcher’s wife (*saunika-bhāryā*) turns man into ~ by binding thread around his neck 71,277 (TP VI 56); charmed ~ as pet (*kriḍanīyaka*) of king’s warder 71,280 (TP VI 56)¹¹⁵⁷; rejoicing like ~ when hearing rain-clouds thunder 110,101 (TP VIII 89); ~ tail

¹¹⁵¹ Bollée 1977: 50.

¹¹⁵² STh F 865.

¹¹⁵³ Hensgen 1958: 138f.

¹¹⁵⁴ See Osier 2010: 123 note 3.

¹¹⁵⁵ See, e.g. Sivaramamurti 1974: 28f.

¹¹⁵⁶ ORC 293 translates: (*cette créature*) *pareille au bouquet de plumes de paon qu’emploient les magiciens au service de l’amour* ([*dṛṣṭvā*] *kāmāindrajālikasyēva picchikām*).

¹¹⁵⁷ Cf. Hensgen 1958: 140.

skirts (*vāsāṃsi barhi-picchāni*) worn by Bhilla women 123,50 (TP IX 46)¹¹⁵⁸
 peahen joyfully beholds new cloud 29,180 (TP III 53);
 pearls in the heads of elephants (*kuñjara-maṇi gaja-muktā*¹¹⁵⁹) 22,76 (TP II 142 with note
 1) and (*mātaṅga-muktā*) 22,88 (TP II 143), 103,6 (TP VII 175) and 116,65 (TP VIII
 161); ~ from nails of elephant-killing lions 27,154 (TP III 13); magic ~ 50,140 (TP IV
 117); coldness found only in ~, (white) sandalwood juice and the moon 92,12 (TP VII
 72)¹¹⁶⁰; – see also: elephant; necklace

¹¹⁵⁸ See Crooke 1919: 1.

¹¹⁵⁹ “[Pearls] originating from the mighty elephants are round, of the size of a myrobalan [2-4,5 cm], and bestow kingdom [upon the wearer]” (Rayaṅaparikkhā 40 > Sarma 1984: 53. “The elephant pearl ... is a pearl-shaped growth found in the elephant’s forehead. Abul Fazl states: “They take out of its (i. e. of an elephant belonging to the *bhadra* class) forehead an excrescence resembling a large pearl, which they call in Hindi *Gaj manik*. Many properties are ascribed to it” (*Ā’in-i Akbarī*, Vol. I, tr. Blochmann, p. 125). I understand that such a pearl from a late royal elephant is displayed in a museum in Kathmandu” (Sarma 1984: 55 < Rayaṅaparikkhā 48). An elephant pearl is “an anomalous growth taking place in the elephant’s tusk due to an injury or a reaction” (R. Sukumar, Centre for Ecological Studies, Indian Institute of Science). – As Lüders 1940: 179ff. proved, *muktā* < Prakrit *muttā* : Sa. *mūrta* ‘coagulated’. A rain drop in a shell condenses to a pearl shell surfacing from the sea and drinking rain drops; the pearl is therefore named *rasōdbhava*. – Gaṇeśa’s real form is the moon (Gaṇeśa-Pur I 13,10) to which pearls are sacred (see previous note). Hensgen 1958: 43f. just touches the matter.

¹¹⁶⁰ Cf. 105,12 (TP VIII 22) where the pearl necklace, sandalwood ointment, the rays of the moon, lotus fibres and leaves cannot alleviate Naravāhanadatta’s torture due to the disappearance of his wife. TP do not give an explanation. The customary reason Indians give, viz that pearls are called cold in literature because found in the sea (*samudra-ja*) cannot be the case, though in his Harṣacarita 250,18 Bāna tells us the myth of the moon’s tears fallen into the sea and drunk by oysters who turned them into pearls (Hara 1999: 168).

(White) sandalwood and the moon are often mentioned together, as, e.g. Jayadeva, *Gītagovinda* IV 1,1 and 9,31; IX 18,59; *candra-kānta* is a word for sandalwood in Lexx (MW). As follows from the references in the note above, the reason of the pearl in this triad of cold things must be the resemblance to the colour (Navaratnaparīkṣā 66) and secondarily the form (idem, 87) of, and therefore its association with the cold-rayed moon (*hima-dīdhiti* 84,42 [TP VII 7]), not the cold sea in which it emerges from the oyster-shell, despite the designation *samudra-ja*. In Kālidāsa, Kum 5,44 the moon is explicitly mentioned as “*Bildspender*” (Jackmuth 2002: 43), i.e. *upamāna*, of jewellery.

With lexicographers *śītala* and *hima* can also mean cold(ness), moon, sandal and pearl (MW). – According to Grīṣma 6 of Kālidāsa’s *Ṛtusaṃhāra* “the female bosom is ointed with (white) sandal and shines with a necklace of cold (or: snow-) white pearls” (*payo-dharās candana-paṅka-carcitās tuṣāra-gaurārpita-hāra-śekharāḥ*), but at Hemanta 2 “the round breasts of bosomy belles are not ornated with beautiful necklaces of pearls resembling snow, jasmine (or: white jasmine, cf. the white lotus, *kumuda*, as friend of the moon [TP III 140 note 2]) and the moon” (*manoharaiś candana-rāga-gauraiś tuṣāra-kundēndu-nibhaiś ca hāraiḥ | vilāsinināṃ stana-śālinināṃ nālaṃ-kriyante stana-maṅḍalāni* ||). Further, in Amaruśataka 140 it says: “This dear pearl necklace fell on your feet. Do pick it up ... and let it adorn your neck. There is no other way to cool your burning heart” (Sarma 2004: 465f.; *muktāhāras tava caraṇa-mūle nipatitaḥ | grhāṇēmaṃ ... vrajatu nija-kantha-praṇayitām ; upāyo nāsti anyas tava hṛdaya-saṃtāpa-śamane*). [WB thanks Professor Sarma for these examples].

In Mokṣōpāya corresponding to Yogavāsiṣṭha (with two minor differences) V 45.37 it says: *tuṣāra-śīśira-sparśais tās taṃ hārir abhūṣayan | śyāmā nava-nadī-pūrir śṛṅgam ivōnnatam* || “These young women (*śyāmā*) adorn him with strings of pearls (which were) ice-cold to the touch just as [dark (*śyāma*)] rainfalls (grace) a looming peak with newly swollen rivers”; “him” is a *śvapaca* just elected king. (I owe this reference to Dr Roland Steiner who also made a [German] translation). – In Agastimata 343 and Navaratnaparīkṣā 172 the pearl is sacred to the moon, and Asura teeth, fallen into the sea, (become) pearls as beautiful as the rays of the full moon (Ratnaparīkṣā 73).

penance, see: austerities; feet;
pencil for painting, see: *dhṛta-varṭin* and Karashima 2012: 140 note 3 on § 18.11
pension, sonless widow obtains quarter of husband's salary from king 73,258 (TP VI 119);
people (*loka*), not knowing of dream ~ will not believe justice of royal proceedings 23,23 (TP II 158); at royal birth festival ~ are smeared with vermilion 23,85 (TP II 164); ~ (*jana*),
prone to calumny of a distinguished person 24,205 (TP II 184); rogue compliments [~]
with presents and pleasures (*dāna-bhogaiḥ*) 66,133 (TP V 188 "keeps complimenting [~]
by entertainments"; ORC 773 "*couvrait tout le monde de cadeaux et de luxes*"); ~ criticize
king 74,69 (TP VI 145); – see also: calumny; *loka*
pepper (*marica*), dog given meat with ~ 13,125 (TP I 159)¹¹⁶¹
perfections (*pāramitā*): charity, chastity, patience, 72,218ff. (TP VI 84ff.); six ~ taught by
Buddha as shuttle (*nau-tuli*) to cross *bhavāmbudhi* 72,362 (TP VI 96); – see: *dāna-*
pāramitā, *dhairya*-°, *dhyanā*-°, *kṣamā*-°, *prajñā*-°, *śīla*-°.
perfume, *vidyādhari* with ~ of blue lotus (*utpala-saurabhā*) 59,4 (TP V 26); lady has
perfumed herself with sandalwood, camphor, black aloes, etc. 82,33 (TP VI 219); ~ (*aṅga-*
rāga), given to Śītā by Anasūyā perfumes the whole forest 107,14 (TP VIII 44); – see also:
bee; fragrance; ichor; *kālāguru*; *mallikā*; *maṇḍana*; musk; smell
period, woman in her ~ (*kanyā-vrata-sthā*) 26,55 (TP II 221 "detained at home by illness";
ORC 239: "*alors que j'avais mes règles*"); *rajasvalā* 75,113 (TP VI 172 omits); – cf.
menstruation
permission, king asking ~ from deity (*tad-abhyanuñātāḥ*; to depart) 107,135 (TP VIII 52)
person depends on body: 119,169f. (TP VIII 205)
personal appearance, see : attributes; *sākṣad*; visibility
perspiration (*kheda*), see: hand
pessimism,¹¹⁶² see: transience
pestilence, goddess of ~, see: Mārī; Sitalā
pestle, hands of queen bruised from hearing ~ pounding rice 85,24 (TP VII 11)¹¹⁶³
pet animal, monkey as ~ (*krīḍā-nibhād*) 37,113 (TP III 191); peacock as ~ (*krīḍanīyaka*)
71,280 (TP VI 56); – see also: parrot
pet name (*krīḍā-kṛtaṃ nāma*) "frog" given by brahmin to his son 30,133 (TP III 73)¹¹⁶⁴

There are eight sources of pearls: elephants, serpents, pearl-oysters, conch-shells, clouds, bamboos, whales and boars (Bṛhatsaṃhitā LXXXI 1, cf. Ratnaparīkṣā 52; Agastimata 83; Navaratnaparīkṣā 58; Johnson, *Tri* I [1931] 254 note 314). "Valuable and lustrous like the Moon is the pearl born from the root of the boar's tusks" (Bṛhatsaṃhitā LXXXI 23). – Sarma 2004: 464 states various articles on pearls.

¹¹⁶¹ Bollée 2006: 41.

¹¹⁶² The Indian idea of suffering of existence does not mean pessimism or weltschmerz but is based on radical reflection of transience (Michaels in Geldner 2006: 116). See also Gonda 1975: IV 302ff.

¹¹⁶³ Cf. STh F 647.8.

phalāsava ‘fruit liquor’ 102,113 (TP VII 170)

phalolatry, see: *liṅga*

philosopher’s stone, see: *cintā-maṇi*; *cintā-ratna*

physician lying to patient 15,15 (TP II 2); patient obeys ~ only if the latter uses convincing speech and gentle words in his treatment (*āturaḥ ... vaśe vaidyasya vartate tv anukūlōktaiḥ sāmñāvācarataḥ kriyām* 31,86 (TP III 89); ~s, questioned by king about patients, prescribed drugs, etc. 33,149 (TP III 120); minister as ~ 39,90 (TP III 224); king asks ~ for artifice (*yukti*) against old age 40,47 (TP III 243; wicked ~ kills sleeping king in underground dungeon 40,61 (TP III 245); ~s should avoid disobedient patient (*duṣṭātura*) 60,119 (TP V 51); rogue ~ claims to know drug to produce hair 61,181 (TP V 83); king loving daughter wants from ~s drug which makes her grow quickly to be married; they conceal the girl for many years and lie to the stupid king of being engaged in procuring the drug from abroad 61,266 (TP V 91); stupid ~ loses bet to cure hunchback 62,234 (TP V 119); – see also: lying; water of immortality

picture, silent like a ~ 6,120 (TP I 69); falling in love with ~ 72,295 (TP VI 90); 101,77 (TP VII 139)¹¹⁶⁵; painter gives king ~ in book 122,26 (TP IX 35)

pictures, without walls (symbolizing making money without capital), mind amazed at ~ 6,50 (TP I 64; M I 53: “*wie kann ein Maler seine Idee verwirklichen, wenn er keine Wand hat, auf die er malt*?”); king praises ~ 55,35 (TP IV 205);

picture gallery (*citra-prāsāda*), king entering ~ 55,34 (TP IV 205)

piety leads to wealth: Boss 1976: 116f. – See, e.g. *nija-dharmārjitānām vināśo nāsti saṃpadām* 19,14 (TP II 85)

pig, rebirth as ~ see: rebirth; Śakra

pigeon(s) (*kapota*)¹¹⁶⁶, Dharma as ~ pursued by Indra as hawk 7,90 (TP I 84); ; ~ (*kapota*, *pārāvata*) caught in net fly up with it (64) to mouse which gnaws meshes asunder and thus frees the birds 61,62-70 (TP V 74)

pika ‘cuckoo’,¹¹⁶⁷ prince equals singing of female ~ (*pikī*) to that of his wife 69,7 (TP VI 9)

pilgrim whose pillow is his arm (*bhujōpadhāna*) 49,226 (TP IV 100), cf. 121,77 (TP IX 17)

pilgrimage, ~ to temple of Durgā under pretext of seeing (*darśana-vyājād*)¹¹⁶⁸ deity 3,38 (TP I 21); ~ because of sorrow for dead wife¹¹⁶⁹ 10,16 (TP I 107; cf. 123,20 below); ~ to

¹¹⁶⁴ One will think of RV VII 103 where brahmins and frogs are compared, or KSS 54,33, where Brahmā on Viṣṇu’s navel lotus is compared to a bee humming the Veda. The nickname shows that the comparison is not used somehow mockingly.

¹¹⁶⁵ Cf. STh T 11. 2.

¹¹⁶⁶ Hensgen 1958: 138.

¹¹⁶⁷ Dave 2006: 128.

¹¹⁶⁸ Lobo in Mallebrein 1998: 9.

¹¹⁶⁹ See Tucker 2009. I thank Professor Tucker (Oxford) for his long p.c., in which he refers to Tibullus’ imagining Delia’s visit to his tomb in Corfú; to the journey of 16th century Portuguese traveller Diogo Pires in his book *Homo viator* (2003: 195-238); to Montaigne’s composition of the *Essais* after the death of his intimate friend Etienne de la Boetie, and his sending me his chapter on this topic in Maes 2009.

Durgā temple out of indignation against wicked wife 23,38 (TP II 159); ~ 33,28 (TP III 109) and *tīrtha-yātrārthaṃ* 33,53 (TP III 111); ~ to Kāśmīra to wash away *brahma-hatyā* 39,35f. (TP III 220)¹¹⁷⁰; ~ to wash off transgression contracted since birth (*prakṣālyājanma-kilbiṣa*) 49,218 (TP IV 100); conditions of ~ **49,224ff.** (TP IV 100); learned *vidyādhari* goes on ~ from one Śiva temple to another 51,23 (TP IV 123); ~ to wash out former crimes 52,239 (TP IV 154); king will recover his wife and son by ~ to Durgā's temple in Vindhya 55,213 (TP IV 217); on a ~ to shrine of Sarasvatī royal court meets with many sick people 66,30 (TP V 180); ministers advise against king's ~, which is exposed to many dangers, to sacred waters 93,67, but he does go 70 and is diverted by beholding various garbs, hearing various languages and by other distractions of travel, seeing all kinds of countries 76 (TP VII 83); a victim of contempt sets out on a ~ to a Durgā temple 108,13 (TP VIII 54); ~ because of loss of / separation from wife (*bhāryā-viyoga* [not MW]) 123,20 (TP IX 44); because of not attaining object of desires man wants to make ~ in order to destroy body 123,250 (TP IX 60)¹¹⁷¹; pretended ~ in order to find husband 124,171 (TP IX 80); – see also: mourning tour; sightseeing

pill, see: magic pill

pillar, of victory, see: *jaya-stambha*; – marble ~ (*śilā-stambha*) representing Kubera's treasure outside Mathurā 34,68 (TP III 133); *vidyādhari* enters ~ of Gaurī to rest 37,9 (TP III 183); Śiva Bhairava emerges from burst ~ in *vidyādhara* court 106,181 (TP VIII 42); – see also: anointing; bawd; bee(s); curse; draughtsman; Gaurī; hand; *jaya-stambha*; Kalāvati; *kīrti-stambha*; laughing; laughter, Maya; nymph(s); *sāla-bhañjikā*; sculptor; Śiva; *stambha-putrikā* Pine Forest (*devadaru-vana*), *ṛṣis* are angry with Śiva in ~ 20,131 (TP II 106)

pīna-tuṅga (not MW) 'full and prominent', of breasts compared to rooftops of palace and frontal lobes of elephant 91,30 (TP VII 68 lacuna; ORC 990: "ses larges seins à la haute pointe"; M II 308: „feste und hohe Brüste“)

piṇḍa, three hands stretch out for ~ sacrificed in well in Gayā by king to his father 93,88 (TP VII 85);

piñjaraka 'unknown musical instrument', princess playing on ~; when her brother takes it away she curses him to become a bird with a golden crest 65,75 (TP V 160, in MW *piñjarika*)¹¹⁷²

piousness shown by washing almsfood 121,158 (TP IX 23)

Piśāca, powerless in the day because dazed by the sun 7,35 (TP I 77); their importunity 28,155 (TP III 32); rite to get help from ~ 28,168 (TP III 33); ~ heals wound with herbs 28,169 (TP III 33); stupid ~ 28,178 (TP III 34); hermit curses *brahma-rākṣasas* to become ~s 114,108 (TP VIII 140);

Piśāca language (*Piśāca-bhāṣā*, *Paiśācī*)¹¹⁷³ 6,4 (TP I 60); ~ learnt by Guṇādhya in Vindhya

¹¹⁷⁰ For transgressions being washable in Hinduism see von Glasenapp 1922: 45.

¹¹⁷¹ Cf. 49,218 (TP IV 100). – Can *piñjara* be an Indian harp like the Birmese one?

¹¹⁷² √*piñj* can mean 'to sound' (MW). *Piñjara* means 'yellow, of a golden colour' (MW).

¹¹⁷³ See note in TP I 92f.; Hinüber, Oskar von, *Das ältere Mittelindisch im Überblick*. Wien, 2001:109ff.

hills 7,27 (TP I 76); ~ called barbarous (*nīrasa*) 8,15 (TP I 90);
piṣitāśana ‘meat-eating, non-vegetarian’, said of brahmins 114,105 (TP VIII 140);
piṣṭa-racita ‘(cake) of flour mixed with molasses’ in *liṅga* (*guhya*) form made at the beginning
of the monsoon¹¹⁷⁴ 2,56 (TP I 13)
pīta-kośa, see: oath
Pitā-maha, *Pumān* called ~ 2,12 (TP I 10)
pitcher(s),¹¹⁷⁵ full ~ (*pūrṇa-kumbha*) in front of gates as breasts of city of Kauśāmbī 18,9 (TP
II 50); ~ of gold found in ant-hill 33,46 (TP III 110)¹¹⁷⁶; inexhaustible ~ of *yakṣas* 57,31
(TP V 3); Gaurī reanimates Jīmūtavāhana with water from her ~ (*kamaṇḍalu*) 90,185 (TP VII
62); breasts compared to two ~s of Kāma’s regal coronation 101,85 (TP VII 140); golden ~ of
breasts (*kuca-kāñcana-kumbha*) of princesses 118,163 (TP VIII 189) gambler and pseudo-
ascetic buries four ~ with wife’s ornaments 121,155 (TP IX 23); – see also: Ambikā;
bhadra-ghaṭa(ka); blood; breast; cornucopia; treasure
*pitṛ-kānana*¹¹⁷⁷ ‘grove of ancestors, charnel ground’ full of Bhūtas 83,3 (TP VII 1); brahmin
seeing dead man lying in the ~ with all his limbs relaxed (*trastāṅgaṃ puruṣaṃ*) is induced to
hang himself 96,14 (TP VII 109)
pity, see: compassion
plagiarism: Guṇāḍhya fearing that *vidyādhara*s may steal his Paisāca poem writes it with his
blood for lack of ink 8,3 (TP I 89); – Rājat 5,160
planets circling around polar star like chiefs around king 18,5 (TP II 49); greedy brahmins
compared to malignant ~, ¹¹⁷⁸ 18,130 (TP II 59); malignant ~ (*a-saumya-graha*) 109,32
(TP VIII 72);
plank (*phalaka*), saves shipwrecked man 25,46 (TP II 192) and 26,122 (TP II 226); – see
also: corpse; death; voyage
plantain-flower (*kadalī*) bears daughter from hermit’s seed (*vīrya*) fallen on it 32,101 (TP III
97);
plantain leaves used for fanning 55,63 (TP IV 206)
plate (*bhājana*) of Maya, magic ~ 3,47 (TP I 22)¹¹⁷⁹; king’s poisoned ~ tested by his dogs
75,146 (TP VI 174); – see also: dish
platonic love, see: conception; looking
play, at ball (*gulikā-kriḍā*) 42,8 (TP III 259); *yakṣas* ~ at king who then is cursed by Kubera’s
son Naḍa-kūbara 73,39 (TP VI 103);

¹¹⁷⁴ For bread baked in phallic shape, Priapic rolls, see Hda 3: 387ff. The use of molasses and honey indicates fertility and magic power.

¹¹⁷⁵ See Dange 1987: 931ff.

¹¹⁷⁶ On gold-digging ants see: ants.

¹¹⁷⁷ Could the original meaning of *pitṛ-kānana* and *pitṛ-vana* be the forest in which corpses were left? See further, e.g. Piano 2005: 1.

¹¹⁷⁸ On these see Underhill 1921: 33.

¹¹⁷⁹ STh *D 1172.1.

pleasure(s) of heaven, not loved by lofty souls (*mahâśayāh*) 45,82 (TP IV 22); ~ of *Asuras* in third *pāṭāla* 45,337 (TP IV 39); ~ see: *divi-ṣad-bhoga*; boon of great ~, see: *bhoga-śrī*;
 pleasure to the ear, see *sukha-śruti*
 pleasure trip, see: pilgrimage (93,76 (TP VII 83)); sightseeing; tourism
 plot to set fire to queen's palace 15,21 (TP II 3)
 plural, see: *-loka*
 poet delighting in illustrations (*dr̥ṣṭānta*), politic queen compared to ~ 27,56 (TP III 5);
 ambiguous phrases of ~ (*kavi-varōkti*) 92,12 (TP VII 72);
 pointing out a person with finger, see: gestures
 poison, prince revives snake-bitten princess with ring neutralizing effect of ~ (*viṣa-ghna*) 10,50 (TP I 110) and 10,97 (TP I 113); bawd seems lump of ~ to young men (*yūnām dṛṣi viṣa-cchaṭā*) 12,79 (TP I 139); ~ of grief 16,106 (TP II 29); ~ put into water and grass 19,84 (TP II 91); ~ offered to man by scorned woman 34,178 (TP III 141); Kālakūṭa ~ is twin-born with nectar 36,96 (TP III 176 with note 1)¹¹⁸⁰; smell betrays lake-water as poisoned 37,86 (TP III 189 and II 276); ~ in king's food 49,38 (TP IV 87); boon joined with a curse compared to nectar mixed with ~ 55,196 (TP IV 215); Nārāyaṇī gives poison-destroying lotus as boon to brahmin 56,115 (TP IV 228); princess kills lover with ~¹¹⁸¹ 64,90 (TP V 146); ORC 745: “*elle empoisonna*”; MI 1051: “*sie vergiftete*”; elephant-keeper swallows ~ because of eloped wife 69,60 (TP VI 13); brahmin couple commits suicide by ~¹¹⁸² 72,214 (TP VI 84); minister liberates brahmin from ~ by knowledge of antidotes (*viṣa-vidyā*) 75,14 (TP VI 165); dog tests minister's poisoned plate and dies 75,146 (TP VI 174); ~ from dead krait drips into brahmin's rice bowl 87,44 (TP VII 32)¹¹⁸³; queen's crest-jewel (as talisman) against ~, etc. (*viṣa-rakṣo-jarā-roga-hara*) 119,26 (TP VIII 194); ~ of separation (*viyoga-viṣa*) from wife 121,150 (TP IX 22); – see also: *hālāhala*
 poison-damsels¹¹⁸⁴ as prostitutes (*viṣa-kanyās ca ... paṇya-vilāsinīh*) sent among enemy's host 19,82 (TP II 91 “as dancing girls”);
 poisoning water, grass, etc. to stop attack 19,80f. (TP II 91)
 poison-tree¹¹⁸⁵ of unrighteousness (*a-dharma-viṣa-vṛkṣa*), does the fruit of the ~ ever ripen sweet ? 90,179 (TP VII 61); ~s of wealth (*dhana-viṣa-druma*) are soon broken by the weight of their own fruit 104,117 (TP VIII 10);
 polar star (*dhruva*), king surrounded by chiefs as ~ by planets 18,5 (TP II 49)¹¹⁸⁶

¹¹⁸⁰ König 1984: 238f.

¹¹⁸¹ For *viṣeṇa* “with poison” TP translate: “in the dead of night” with B reading *niśīthe 'badhid Ghaṭam*.

¹¹⁸² Suicide by poison is often committed with seeds of the Cerbera odollam tree, a species of oleander. People to be executed wear a *vadya-mālā* of oleander (*Nerium odorum*) flowers the sap of which is poisonous (Bollée 2005: 116).

¹¹⁸³ Cf. STh N 332.3.

¹¹⁸⁴ STh F 582.

¹¹⁸⁵ A poison-tree of passion is found in Rājāt 4,26.

¹¹⁸⁶ In reality, no planets are known of the binary polar star.

police chief, see: *nagarâdhipa*

policy¹¹⁸⁷ of ensnaring an enemy by means of a beautiful maiden (*kanyā-ratna*) 11,24 (TP I 124; cf. 33,9 [TP III 107]); ~ (*buddhi*) against assault (*avaskanda*) 12,37 (TP I 135); ~ (*nīti*) compared to Vindhya forest as *durgamā* 12,44 (TP I 136); queen as ~ incarnate (*ākāravatī nīti*) 17,50 (TP II 38); ~ as a blossoming tree (*naya-taru*) 17,163 (TP II 47); as a great plant ~ (*nīti-mahā-vallī*) brings fruit 33,85 (TP III 113); ~ as wishing-tree 34,30 (TP III 130); king asks ministers for survey of ~ (*rāja-niteḥ samuccayam*) 34,189 (TP III 142 with note 2); ~ (diplomacy) before war 46,133 (TP IV 57); ~ (*mantra*) the very foundation of empires 62,16 (TP V 99); ~ ensures success (*siddhir asti buddhitāḥ*) 69,52 (TP VI 12); four expedients (*upāya*) of ~ : conciliation, gifts, division and force (*sāma, dānaṃ ca bhedo daṇḍaḥ*) 102,122 (TP VII 171); royal allying with wives serves acquisition of allies (*bandhu-prāpti-prado ... bhāryā-vyatikaro*) and so is most efficacious method to conquer foes 108,193f. (TP VIII 68); queen consulted (*devyā sahâlocya*) in ~ 118,176 (TP VIII 190) and 119,6 (TP VIII 193); – see also: *mariage de raison*; *rāja-nīti*; statecraft politician (*nīti-tattva-jña*) 102,22 (TP VII 163); *nīti-vid* 102,120 (TP VII 171); *nīti-jña* 110,15 (TP VIII 83);

pollen, heavenly maiden with body of yellow ~ of flowers (*parāṅga-puñja-gaurāṅgī*) 35,12 (TP III 156); yellow (*piśaṅga*) ~ (*puṣpa-reṇu*) 81,63 (VI 213); brown (*kapiśa*) ~ 115,146 (TP VIII 154)

pollution, elephant dies from polluted water 13,33 (TP I 152)¹¹⁸⁸; ~ through looking at “guilty” Sītā 51,73 (TP IV 127); ~ (*agha*) after death of king feared by earth 53,127 (TP IV 176); conversing with female sinner as ~ makes ascetic loose his power 65,53 (TP V 158); by looking at female beauty king washes from his eyes ~ contracted by looking at others 73,149 (TP VI 112); – see also: poison

polyandry (of Draupadī), see note in TP II 16ff., etc.

polyarchy means chaos (*varam ... na vipluta-sarvârthaṃ vibhinna-bahu-nāyakam*) 18,136 (TP II 60)

polygamy, brahmin marries Deccan princess with consent of his first wife (*tac-chradhitāḥ*) 26,186 (TP II 231); ~ embarrasses ladies 45,302 (TP IV 37); ~ of kings justified 47,104ff. (TP IV 73); ~ of brahmin whose mother harasses his two wives 74,162f. (TP VI 152); five princesses want to marry *vidyâdhara* king together 107,85f. (TP VIII 49); – see also: king; puppet; queen; wife

polyptoton¹¹⁸⁹: *agād utsavād utsavam* ‘went from joy to joy’ 74,197 (TP VI 154); *kare kareṇâhatya* ‘striking the tusk with her hand’ 112,68 (TP VIII 111);

polysomaty,¹¹⁹⁰ see: body; division of personality

pomegranate tree (*dāḍīma*), royal treasure buried under ~ 30,120 (TP III 72)

¹¹⁸⁷ See, e.g., ORC 1626; Bhikkhu Pāsādika 2010: 339.

¹¹⁸⁸ Cf. Bollée 2005b: 58f.; 2010: 103 note 546.

¹¹⁸⁹ Gonda 1959: 285ff.

¹¹⁹⁰ For R̥gvedic associations with ~ see Gonda 1965: 215.

poor woman with five sons 21,136f. (TP II 135); word for ~ (*daridra-śabda*) loses meaning 52,380 (TP IV 164) and 93,57 (TP VII 82); ~ man with many sons 61,241 (TP V 88);
 portent, see: omen
 porter, portress, see: doorkeeper
 portion (*aṃśā*), Śiva in *liṅga* promises son as ~ of himself 115,24 (TP VIII 153); Padmāvati is incarnated ~ of Gaurī 115,126 (TP VIII 153); Mukṭāphaladhvaṅga as ~ of Śiva 118,21 (TP VIII 179); king Mahendrāditya ~ of Śiva and his wife is ~ of Ambikā 120,28 (TP IX 3); – see also: *aṃśā*; part-incarnation
 possession¹¹⁹¹, *kṣatriya* boy possessed (*samāviṣṭa*) by hermit 70,57 (TP VI 28); wicked confidante tells mistress lie of having seen her loved prince possessed by demons (*bhūtāviṣṭa*), held / assisted by companions and provided with herbs and a real gem (*ābaddhāuśadhi-san-maṇiḥ*) 71,143 (TP VI 46 “(prince) possessed by a demon, having horns¹¹⁹² on his head, and his attendants were trying to restrain him; besides he had herbs and a talismanic jewel on him”; ORC 818: “(prince) possédé par des démons. Des hommes à ses cotés le maîtrisaient et on lui avait attaché des herbes et une vraie pierre précieuse”; M II 62: “Da erblickte ich einen gebrochenen Mann, der von einem Dämon besessen war. Die ihm zur Seite stehenden bestürzten und verzagten Gefolgsleute versuchten, ihn zu bändigen. Er hatte sich Heilkräuter auf den Leib gelegt und einen Edelstein als Talisman umgebunden.”)
 poster, see: *citra-paṭha*
 postillon d’amour, friend (*vayasya*) sent as ~ 57,77 (TP V 7); servant (*ceṭī*) as ~ 74,220 (TP VI 156); – see also: confidante; go-between; servant
 Potiphar motif 7,57 (TP I 79)¹¹⁹³; 20,120 (TP II 105); 33,40 (TP III 109); 63,34 (TP V 122); – see also: scorned women; woman’s love scorned
 poverty, due to many children 21,136ff. (TP II 135); 61,241 (TP V 88); ~ makes men steal 57,19 (TP V 2); – see also: adoptive son; child; emigration; poor woman
 powder (*cūrṇa*; *dhūli*), see: alchemy; bones; drug; dust; goat; sandal; sword;
 power, mind of rulers is blinded with ~ (*vibhūty-andha*) 17,138 (TP II 45); ~ of a woman to fly (*khecari-siddhi*) 20,105 (TP II 103); queens dance like three royal ~s 34,123 (TP III 137 with note 1) and idem, energy, royal majesty, counsel (*utsāha-prabhutā-mantra*) 34,198 (TP III 143); ascetic ~ (*siddhi*) lost by conversing with female sinner 65,53 (TP V 158); in sleep woman loses magic ~ of disguising 105,62 (TP VIII 25)
 Prabala, Daitya with frame of jewels obtains boon from Durgā 45,381 (TP IV 42);
prabhā-baddha, see aura (of light)
prābhṛta, see: present

¹¹⁹¹ McHugh 2012: 78f. and 139; Jolly 1977: § 94; Ruben 1952: 60ff.

¹¹⁹² In art, demons with horns do not appear before the Moghuls, certainly adopted from pictures of the Rustam saga and earlier in Persia. The demons in the Rustam-figures in the Sogdian Panjikent have nice horns. Whether the horned heads occasionally found in Ajanta belong to demons or to infernal servants is unclear, even when they are looking angrily (p. c. M. Zin).

¹¹⁹³ STh K 2111.

- prachanna-kāmuka* (not MW) ‘paramour’ (q.v.)
prācī-dig-vadhū ‘nymph of the eastern quarter’ 106,50 (TP VIII 32);
pradakṣiṇā ‘circumambulation’ of *aśvattha* tree 20,25 (TP II 96) and ~ around a tree in which Gaṇeśa dwells 100,54 (TP VII 132); 24,145 (TP II 180); ~ of the fire by a newly married couple 34,257 (TP III 148) and 103,192 (TP VII 188); ~ of Śīva and Pārvatī by Nara vāhanadatta 110,57 (TP VIII 86); ~ of Gaurī temple by Mukṭāphaladhvaja 119,105 (TP VIII 200)
pradoṣa-jvalita (not MW) ‘shining in the night’, of herbs (q.v.) 108,47 (TP VIII 56)
pradoṣa-samaye ‘in the evening’ lover visits beloved 74,230 (TP VI 157);
 Pradyumnāstra ‘weapon of Pradyumna = Kāma’, hero’s heart pierced with ~ 50,21 (TP IV 109)
prāghuṇ(ik)a ‘guest’ 65,144 and 150 (TP V 166)¹¹⁹⁴
prāg-jāti, see: pre-birth
 praise¹¹⁹⁵ of Gaṇeśa; Hari; sun, see: prayer
 praise, singing ~ of Śīva as lullaby (q. v.) 52,195 (TP IV 151); ~ of prince by merchant 67,31 (TP V 198); ~ of sea by king 86,84 (TP VII 19), ~ of king 91,4ff. (TP VII 66); – see also: Gaurī; hymn of ~; Mahākāla; Śauri
 Prajāpati sprung from Śīva’s blood 2,12 (TP I 10); – see also: illusion
prajñā ‘wisdom’ of woman prevents outrage (*viplava*) of cowherd 64,41 as it is the principle support of people (*pradhānaṃ loka-vartanam*) 42 (TP V 142)
prajñā-bala ‘power of reason or policy’, hand of princess must be won by ~ 69,46 (TP VI 12)
prajñāna-vāri ‘water of wisdom’ must water tree of valour 96,44 (TP VII 111)
prajñā-pāramitā (‘perfection of wisdom’) 72,318 (TP VI 92); – see also: perfection
prajñapti,¹¹⁹⁶ a *vidyādhara* science named (°-*saṃjñikā*) ‘foreknowledge’ 30,6 (TP III 64); ~ orders princess to visit Svayambhū’s *kṣetrāṇi* in Kashmir 51,51 (TP IV 125); ~ appears visibly and explains evil dream 111,52ff. (TP VIII 100);
 Prajñaptikauśika, the guru of the *vidyādharas*, descends from heaven 25,258 (TP II 210)
prakāśanāstra (not MW) ‘illuminating weapon’ of Prabhāsa 48,45 (TP IV 77)
prakoṣṭhataḥ ‘by the fore-arm’, Pāśupata ascetic takes prince ~ 73,392 (TP VI 128)
prāk-karma, who can change someone’s actions in a pre-birth ? 72,193 (TP VI 83)
Prakṛti springs from Śīva’s blood > *Pumān = Sṛṣṭar* 2,11 (TP I 9);
pralaya, see: doomsday
praṇaya-kriḍā, see: loving-sport
praṇidhāna (‘meditation’) 119,189 (TP VIII 206); ~ 120,6 (TP IX 1)
praṇṛtta, see dancing-girl(s)
prasāda ‘favourable reaction of a deity to praise (*stuti*) of a devotee’ 54,39 (TP IV 187)
prāsāda, see: terrace

¹¹⁹⁴ See Balbir 2001: 374 and 379 note 17.

¹¹⁹⁵ Praise is a verbal gift and so enables the eulogized person to get a boon.

¹¹⁹⁶ See TP II 212 note and Kuv note 2079.

prasthāna-maṅgala ‘auspicious ceremony before setting out’, king performs ~ himself 107,76 (TP VIII 48); – see also: ceremonies

pratāpāgni (not MW), see: fire of wrath

pratāpānala (not MW), see: fire; valour

pratiḍūta ‘counter-ambassador, messenger in return’ 55,95 (TP IV 208)

*prāṭihāra*¹¹⁹⁷ sometimes ‘chamberlain’ better than TP’s ‘warder’ 14,1 (TP I 182; ORC 98 “chambellan”; MI 139: “Türhüter”) et passim; 72,237f. (TP VI 86); 86,24 (TP VII 15); 108,2 (TP VIII 53); ~ often used as messenger (q.v.), e.g. 119,6 (TP VIII 193) and of a female ~ 14 (TP VIII 194); 120,68 (TP IX 6); 124,78 (TP IX 73); – see also: doorkeeper; warder

pratiñā ‘vow’ at which the hairlock on the crown of the head is undone 5,118 (TP I 57)

pratiloma, spell spoken ~ ‘backwards’ enables one to assume any shape 74,134 (TP VI 149; cf. *anuloma*);

Prāṭiśākhya ‘grammatical treatise’, brahmin woman knows ~ 2,38 (TP I 12)

*pratiṣṭhā*¹¹⁹⁸ (‘temple’) for Hari, festival in ~ 26,3 (TP II 217; ORC 236: ‘statue’; MI 338: “Tempel”)

Pratiṣṭhāna on bank of Godāvarī, Trivikramasena’s town 75,21 (TP VI 165);

pratta-yoga (not MW) 45,114 (TP IV 25 ‘communicating the doctrine of mystic contemplation giving supernatural power’, i.e. the Yoga system)

pravāda, see: calumny; rumour; slander

pravrajaka, ‘wandering ascetic’, Viṣṇugupta in Jambu-vana¹¹⁹⁹ in the south, on the banks of river Veṇī, is best ~ 49,176 (TP IV 97); – cf. *parivrāṭ*

pravrajaka-stri ‘female wandering ascetic’ addicted to jugglery etc. (*kuhakādiṣu prayogeṣv abhi yuktyā*) 32,125 (TP III 99 ‘wives of wandering religious mendicants’, ORC 315: ‘ascète mendiante’)

pravrajikā = prec., as instrument for seducing merchant’s wife 13,89 (TP I 156)¹²⁰⁰; 13,160 (TP I 161 ‘female Buddhist ascetic’; ORC 95 ‘nonne’); – see also: go-between

pravṛtta, see dancing-girl(s)

prayer, brahmin muttering ~s (*jāpaka*, ORC 475: “reciteur”) gives king half of its fruit as boon 45,109f. (TP IV 24f.); ~ of Naravāhanadatta to Hari for beneficial attention (*paśyārdayā drśā*) 54,29-38 (TP IV 186f.); ~ to Gaṇeśa 55,162ff. (TP IV 213) and 73,376ff. (TP VI 127); ~ of brahmin to sun (*arka*) 56,28ff. (TP IV 221); ~ of princess to Gaurī to get husband in next life 90,71f. (TP VII 54); ~ of merchant wife to Caṇḍī to get brahmin for husband in next life 95,30 (TP VII 100); ~ of prince Mrgāṅkadatta to Gaṇeśa 100,44 (TP VII 131); ~ of prince to Devī-Durgā 101,302 (TP VII 155); ~ to Gaurī by princess before hanging herself that she may have a certain prince in her next birth when not in this one

¹¹⁹⁷ Saletore 1943: 253.

¹¹⁹⁸ See Gonda 1975 II : 371.

¹¹⁹⁹ Text: Tumbavanam.

¹²⁰⁰ Cf. Daṇḍin, *Daś* 112,6.

103,49 (TP VII 178); princess in love directs ~ to Śiva–Gaurī-pati for husband 117,71 (TP VIII 169); prince addresses ~ to *ṛṣi* that his devotion (*bhakti*) to Śiva and his inclination to fiancée may remain 117,156 (TP VIII 175); princesses pray to Agni that a certain prince will be their husband in their next birth if not in this one 118,172 (TP VIII 190); ~ of princess to Gaurī-Ambikā to be united with lover 119,126 (TP VIII 202); do, to Dhūrjaṭi-Śiva 119,146 (TP VIII 203); burning his present body prince prays to Śiva for return to his former body in order to obtain his love 119,178 (TP VIII 205); ~ of gambler to Bhairava 121,103ff. (TP IX 19); ~ of brahmin to Mātaras for protection 123,215 (TP IX 58); – see also: *nidāna*

pre-birth, *haṃsas* in ~ were crows 3,32 (TP I 20); Vararuci remembers ~ through favour of Vindhyaśini-Durgā 5,127 (TP I 58); horse remembers ~ 18,100 (TP II 57); Jīmūta vāhana remembers ~ (*jāti-smara*) 22,53 (TP II 141) and 90,89 (TP VII 55); hatred and affection are due to always recalling impressions of ~ 23,30 and 51 (TP II 159f.); ~ (*prāg-jāti*) of every individual desired becomes visible in emerald dish found under a banyan in Vārāṇasī 23,42 (TP II 160); suddenly remembered and related ~ brings death 27,83f. (TP III 7); fisherman and king remember ~ as undisciplined brahmin and self-controlled *caṇḍāla* 27,131 (TP III 11); ~ forms friendship of two men 27,190 (TP III 15); idem 28,117 (TP III 29); *asurī not remembering* ~ 29,6 (TP III 39); austerities produce recollection of ~ 40,106 (TP III 248); ~ remembered suddenly 42,196 (TP III 274); ~ remembered 45,124 (TP IV 26); do 52,68 (TP IV 142); ~ remembered after waking up from dream 52,392 (TP IV 165); due to piety (*dharma-vaśāt*) parrot remembers ~ 59,34 (TP V 28); ~ at once remembered at sight of other person 59,172 (TP V 38); ~ remembered because of powerful fasting vow 63,61 (TP V 124); ~ remembered at sight of person 66,176 (TP V 191); remembering ~ caused by *brahmacāra* and death at *tīrtha* 69,164 (TP VI 20); ~ remembered by being addressed by former wives 73,430 (TP VI 131); even gods are unable to alter effect of actions in ~ 101,199 (TP VII 148); influence of ~ 114,30 (TP VIII 134); dogs remember ~ and flee to Śiva for protection 114,124 (TP VIII 141); after circumambulation of Śiva temple king remembers ~ as *vidyādhara* 119,105 (TP VIII 200); – see also: dogs; remembering

pre-birth husband, wife desires ~ (*janmāntarārjitā*) also in this life 25,167 (TP II 204); – see also: prayer

precede, Śacī ~s Prajāpati 116,81 (TP VIII 162)

precious stones, see jewel(s); ornament

precocious child, see: stepmother

prediction by hermit 9,66 (TP I 99); ~ by goddess of Fortune (Śrī) 10,11 (TP I 106); ~ by Viṣṇu 10,43 (TP I 109); ~ by celestial voice 10,214 (TP I 121); idem by Durgā 11,14 (TP I 123); ~ of Indra in dream 11,76 (TP I 128); ~ of wealth by Viṣṇu in dream 12,128 (TP I 143); – see also: curse; dream

pregnancy caused by brahmin Nāga 6,18 (TP I 61); queen oppressed by ~ (*garbha-bharālasā*) 118,37 (TP VIII 180); hermit administers queen oblation (*caru*) with mantras for ~ 9,10

(TP I 95 with note 1); ~ signs¹²⁰¹: rolling eyes [*lola-netra*], palish face, dark nipples 22,2 (TP II 137); pale face, dark breasts 34,32 (TP III 130); rolling eyes, pale face 35,109 (TP III 164); dark nipples (*cūcuka*) as mark of ~ 120,45 (TP IX 4); do, (*sa-garbhâbhūn mecakâgrapayo-dharā*) 124,196 (TP IX 82)

pregnancy dream 23,5 (TP II 157); 35,117 (TP III 164); 59,61 (TP V 30); 120,46 (TP IX 4); – see: dream; pregnancy whim

pregnancy whim (*dohada*)¹²⁰²: wish to bathe in blood 9,46 (TP I 97 with note 3, cf. III 67); ~ of roaming about in the sky, and to hear stories of magicians 22,9ff. (TP II 137); unspecified ~ 34,31 (TP III 130); idem, proclaiming son of noble lineage 35,111 (TP III 164); ~ of queen in a lotus-chariot in the sky since her ~ assumed that form (*tathā-bhūta-vilasat-garbha-dohadā*) 35,117 (TP III 164f.); ~ of three princesses of seeing battle of *Asuras* slain in old time and being conceived again in ~ this being the cause of the ~ 46,27 (TP IV 50); – see also: *dohada*; king; night

pregnant wife left by husband 21,111 (TP II 133)¹²⁰³ whom, when dead, ~ may not follow on pyre 21,112 (TP II 134); *vidyādhara* king leaves mortal ~ 34,36 (TP III 130); ~ queen compared to eastern quarter at sunrise 120,44 dreams of crossing seven seas, etc. 46 (TP IX 4)

prekṣaṇa(ka) (‘spectacle’) in temple 57,74 (TP V 6); ~ of dancing princess in *raṅga-maṇḍapa* 71,77 (TP VI 41)

prema-durlalita (not MW) ‘spoiled by love’ 121,125 (TP IX 21)

prema-pāśa (not MW) ‘noose of love’ 37,53 (TP III 186), see: love

prema-varṣin (not MW) ‘raining love’ with eye 39,81 (TP III 223)

preraṇa, see: *seraṇa*

presence of deity, see: visibility

presence of mind (*pratibhāvatī*) shown by woman to raptor 4,32 (TP I 32)¹²⁰⁴; ~ to *rākṣasa* who wants to devour her husband 123,188 (TP IX 56)¹²⁰⁵

present (*pratigraha*), of eight *māśas* of gold to Sāmaveda singer 6,51 (TP I 64); king gives ~s at marriage 14,60 (TP I 187); royal palace is filled with ~s which feudatories offer to procure good luck (*sāmanta-maṅgalôpāyana*) 18,25 (TP II 51); pretty woman offered to king as ~ 18,79 (TP II 55); ~ of garments 24,113 (TP II 178); ~ of female slaves 43,240 (TP III 297); ~ of daughter as hospitable entertainment (*prāghuṇâtithyaṃ kāryam*) 45,311 (TP

¹²⁰¹ Cf. Schmidt 1904: 487; Lemay 1980: 135 about the 13th century astrologer Leopold of Austria who notices changes of the breast, of the eyes and complexion. In the KSS the most important sign, the absence of the period, is never mentioned, nor is sneezing, the first sign in European mediaeval texts (Kruse 1999: 236f.).

¹²⁰² See Suśruta, Śāriṣṭhāna 3, etc.; Schmidt 1904: 490f.; Bloomfield 1920; Kellersmann 1966: 54 and 58; Gupta 1987: 479; Gélis 1992: 99-101; Kruse 1996: 147 = idem 1999: 131 (unripe, i.e. sour, apples); Abt 1996; ORC 1408 on p. 492 note 4, and 1566 s.v. Envie; Dossi 1998: 90; Mills 2003: 163 (article of Jerome Bauer).

¹²⁰³ In rural regions pregnancy is still a matter of shame, especially for the woman’s natal kin (Jeffery 1989: 72).

¹²⁰⁴ See Baldissera 2004: 90.

¹²⁰⁵ See Baldissera 2004: 89.

IV 37; cf. 45,326 *atithya-hetoḥ*); ~ (*upahāra*) which the ring of the Mātaras (*māṭṭṛ-cakra*) brought with them 56,77 (TP IV 225); complementary ~ (*prābhṛta*) to king 66,114 (TP V 187); ~ of peacock as pet to king's warder 71,279 (TP VI 56); king gives prince beautiful women as ~ 103,219 (TP VI 190); woman makes ~ of fish to princess and obtains a boon 112,122 (TP VIII 115); ~ of crest-jewel to king in order to get his daughters for marriage 119,28ff. (TP VIII 195); 121,224 (TP IX 28); – see also: alms; bribe; corruption; *dakṣiṇā*; donation; fee; gift; marriage; messenger; wedding presents *preta-vāhana* [not MW] 'chariot drawn by ghosts' 48,113 (TP IV 81)
preta-vastra, see: *uṣṇīṣa*
 pretence,¹²⁰⁶ see: anger; disease; distraction; dream; guru; ignorance; knowledge; language of animals; pilgrimage; prince; rape; sleep
 pretended husband 65,29 (TP V 155 and note on TP III 126f.)
 Priapic roll(s), see: cake; monsoon; *piṣṭa-racita*
 pride, of wealth (*dhana-mada*) 18,130 (TP II 59); horns of ~ (*mada-śṛṅga*) 27,13 (TP III 2); great grief experienced through fault of ~ (*ahaṃkāra-doṣa*) 52,86 (TP IV 144); ~ on beauty makes princess dislike husband 52,94 (TP IV 144); man whose body is full of ~ in beauty is cursed to become ugly camel 69,108 (TP VI 16); ~ of Asura (*Asuratvābhimāna*) 119,5 (TP VIII 193); ~ in beauty, see also: daughter; son; Śrī; marriage; – ~ of youth, see: youth
 prince, killed by cook and eaten by his parents 20,207f. (TP II 113); eight years old ~ is instructed together with sons of ministers 27,5f. (TP III 1); ~ as second moon without spot on its surface 67,13 (TP V 197); ~, invisible by spell, visits princess at night 74,231 (TP VI 157); ~ leaves retinue with friend under pretence of hunting 75,88f. (TP VI 170); ~ loves *caṇḍāla* maiden 112,74 (TP VIII 111); – see also: coeval;
 princess preserved in upper story 3,58 (TP I 23); prince awaking sleeping ~ 3,65 (TP I 23) and 86,99 (TP VII 20); ~ abducted in the night by mendicant in order to be sacrificed 18,169f. (TP II 63); ~ rejects brahmin 24,76 and 25,1 (TP II 175 and 188); ~ asleep while husband leaves her 25,239 (TP II 208); ~ sports in palace gardens like a wave of the sea of infancy that is full of the passion for amusement 28,99 (TP III 27); ~ disapproving of every suitor 30,73 (TP III 69)¹²⁰⁷; ~ beholds desired bridegroom as female partridge beholds moon 31,45 (TP III 85); ~ like incarnation of Kāma's magic art (*jagat-moha-mantra-vidyā*) 33,59 (TP III 111); ~ hates men (*puruṣa-dveṣiṇī*) 42,19 (TP III 260); Chinese ~ with charming limbs, yellow as gold, chooses king roaming about for amusement as husband 44,46 (TP IV 4); ~ has sex with one robber and is saved by another 64,46-56 (TP V 143f.); ~ kills her saviour with poison 64,90 (TP V 146)¹²⁰⁸; king slaps daughter who, offended, flees to forest and becomes ascetic 66,139ff. (TP V 189); ~ given to prince under pretext of hospitality 67,113 (TP V 204); simile of dancing ~ who looks like a creeper of

¹²⁰⁶ STh K 2000ff.

¹²⁰⁷ Cf. Kuv 162.11ff.

¹²⁰⁸ TP translates *viṣeṇa* by "in the dead of night" as represents the reading of B: *niśithe*.

the tree of love 71,74 (TP VI 41); hero approaches sleeping ~ 73,337 who pours forth rays of beauty 340 (TP VI 125); ~ solicits (*anunāthati*) prince through confidante 74,224 (TP VI 156); ~ charming as the presiding goddess of the garden of the gods (*Śrīr iva nāndanī*) 101,69 (TP VII 139); war because of ~ 103,16 (TP VII 176); ~ would rather die than marry ugly husband 103,18 (TP VII 176); ~ saved from wild elephant by *caṇḍāla* with whom she falls in love 112,93 (TP VIII 113); ~ wants to share lot (*gati*) of cursed fiancé but is refused 117,152 (TP VIII 174); Dhātṛ astonished at beauty of ~ whose *nirmātr* he was 123,106 (TP IX 50); – chamber of ~ see: chamber; – see further also: beauty; *pumdvēṣiṇī* prison (*bhū-gr̥ha*) of the womb 29,110 (TP III 47)¹²⁰⁹; leaves as ~ of words (*bandhaḥ kavi-girām chedaḥ patreṣu*) 55,27 (TP IV 204); ~ (*kārā-gr̥ha*) like hell 67,42 (TP V 199); Śabarā bring prince and minister to ~ (*kārā-gr̥ha*) 101,289 (TP VII 154); ~ full of vermin, cobwebs and snake-skins 101,290 (TP VII 154); ~ compared to birthplace of hells (*nirayāṇām utpatti-dhāman*) 101,292 (TP VII 154); – see also: *bhū-gr̥ha*; *kārā-gr̥ha* prisoner(s), brahmin ~ praises sun 56,28ff. (TP IV 221f.); voice orders ~ to put burning wheel on head of fellow ~ 56,159 (TP IV 231); ~s (*bandhana-stha*) released at royal wedding 101,380 (TP VII 160 with note 2)¹²¹⁰; ~ cannot give his daughters in marriage 119,17 (TP VIII 194); – see further: human sacrifice; lasso

prīti-dūti (not MW) ‘messenger of love’, look from reverted corner of woman’s eye as ~ 104,31 (TP VIII 3)

private (*viḥane*) delivering of message 24,118 (TP II 178); two men sitting in ~ in empty temple 27,152 (TP III 12); king tells tale in ~ (*vivikte*), i.e. amid queens and ministers 44,16 (TP IV 2); ~ communication of *bhikṣu* with king 75,35 (TP VI 166); pseudo-ascetic addresses city magistrate in ~ (*viḥanaṃ kṛtvā*) 75,172 (TP VI 176; ORC 907: “*faisant faire le vide autour de lui*”; M II 191: “*führte den Stadthauptmann beiseite*”); *ekānte* 90,17 (TP VII 49); – see also: *guptam*; *rahas(i)*

priyaṅgu ‘callicarpa macrophylla; Panicum Italicum, Setaria italica, panic-seed, foxtail millet’,¹²¹¹ woman dark as ~ (°-*śyāmalā*) 47,109 (TP IV 73) = 121,226 (TP IX 28); 120,105 (TP IX 8)

procession, festive (*yātrōtsava*) for Hari on the 12th day of the white fortnight of Āṣāḍha 26,4 (TP II 217); prince goes on (sightseeing ?) ~ to a garden (*yātrāyām udyānaṃ sa ... yayau*) 34,174 (TP III 140: “on a pilgrimage”; M I 485: “*gelegentlich einer Reise ...*”); ~ of idols (*deva-yātrā*) 67,38 (TP V 198); ~ (*yātrōtsava*) for Gaṇeśa assembling all Mālava 73,327 (TP VI 124); ~ for the Nāga-king Vāsuki in Lāṭa (**description**) 74,208 (TP VI 155); ~ in

¹²⁰⁹ See below: womb.

¹²¹⁰ Cf. STh P 14.1.

¹²¹¹ For Kālidāsa, however, *priyaṅgu* outshines women’s arms (Ṛtus. III 18) and pales like a girl parted from her lover (*p. priya-viprayuktā vipāṇḍutām yāti vilāsinīva*, Ṛtus. IV 10). This would fit Foxtail millet, whereas the KSS references would favour the identification with Callicarpa macrophylla which has purple flowers. See Gopal 2008: 12 (p.c. Kieffer-Pülz); <http://venetiaansell.wordpress.com/2010/02/28/the-priyangu-creeper/> and <http://encyclopedia2.thefreedictionary.com/Panicum+italicum> Further ascriptions in Kuv note 6.

spring 89,6 (TP VII 40); *madhûdyāna-yātrā* 89,39 (TP VII 42)
 proclamation, by drum (*sa-paṭahaṃ*) 18,321 (TP II 73); 24,50 (TP II 173); idem 73,262 (TP VI 119) and 357 (TP VI 126); ~ on walls of Brahma's egg 90,192 (TP VII 62)
 procrastination (*kālahāra*) serves to avert inauspicious measure 31,75 (TP III 88);
 promise of Garuḍa to never again eat snakes 90,195 (TP VII 62); ~ of king is kept (*devena pratipannaṃ cet satyaṃ, pālitaṃ eva tat*) 119,29 (TP VIII 195); ~ to return motif 25,213 (TP II 207); do, by oath (*śapatha*) TP VII 203 with ref. to III 33; 123,175 (TP IX 55); reciprocal ~s (*anyonyaṃ pratijñāte*) of Mūladeva and his wife 124,164 (TP IX 80); – see also: return on promise
 proof, tale as ~ 5,58 (TP I 51) et passim; wife's ~ of chastity 63,41 (TP V 123); – see further: Namuci
 property, private ~ of princess of Ujjain 103,184 (TP VII 187)
 propitiation of deities by penance, of Śiva by Brahmā and Nārāyaṇa (Viṣṇu) 1,29 (TP I 4); ~ of Śrī by Kālanemi 10,10 (TP I 106); ~ of Agni 18,110 (TP II 58); ~ of Śambhu (Śiva) 19,3 (TP II 84); idem by Bāna 27,142 (TP III 12); ~ of Agni for son 27,164 (TP III 13); ~ of Śiva 30,10 (TP III 64); ~ of Gaurī by Uṣā for a husband 31,11 (TP III 81); ~ of Agni with offer of bilva fruits (*bilva-homa*) 35,61 (TP III 159); ~ of Viṣṇu 36,11 (TP III 169); ~ of white elephant Śīta-raśmi by feeding brahmins 36,22 (TP III 170)¹²¹²; ~ of Bhavānī = Gaurī by fasting and sleeping on *darbha* grass for a son 42,56 (TP III 263); ~ of Ambikā = Durgā for help 42,104 (TP III 266); spell for ~ of god Svāmikumāra (Skanda) 49,237 and 241 (TP IV 101f.); ~ of Śiva to obtain supreme felicity (*paramam padam*) 51,29 (TP IV 124); ~ of Śiva who then appears in dream and tells future 52,389 TP IV 165); ~ of Durgā 54,163 (TP IV 195) and 54,208 (TP IV 198); ~ of Kārttikeya to obtain son 55,156 (TP IV 213); ~ of *yakṣa* to obtain genitals for eunuch 56,97 (TP IV 226); ~ of Śiva for a son 57,55 (TP V 5); ~ of Śiva is favoured by son 59,60 (TP V 30); ~ of Devī (Durgā) by sacrifice of oneself (*ātmōpahāra*) 72,19 (TP VI 69); ~ Tryambaka-Śiva, who appears in vivo (*sākṣāt*), for knowledge and a wife 73,105; ~ of Śārikā-Durgā by means of many praises (*stuti-śataih*) 73,110 (TP VI 108f.); unable to ~ of Kālarātri by praise, emperor offers to sacrifice his head as appeasement 109,103 (TP VIII 77)
 prosperity, maiden remains unmarried in her father's house like Kamalā-Lakṣmī, the goddess of ~, in the cavity of the ocean (*kukṣi-koṭara*) before it was churned 11,80 (TP I 128); valourous brahmin lives some nights with princess (his wife) as if with goddess of ~ 18,345 (TP II 75); ~ (Śrī) of kings is like a courtesan (*veśyā*), ~ of merchants is like a woman of good family 21,56 (TP II 129); ~ flickers like candle in the wind 22,40 (TP II 140); ~ in questionable, but courageous deeds 27,208 (TP III 17); goddess of ~ is ever treacherous as gambling, fickle as a wave, intoxicating as wine 62,164 (TP V 113); city of Vidiśā is pleasure-ground of Śrī 71,72 (TP VI 41), cf. 120,10 (TP IX 2); ~ is result of virtue (*dharma-mūlā hi saṃpadaḥ*) 72,156 (TP VI 80); – see also: churning; courage; flesh; goddess of ~; Kamalā; Lakṣmī

¹²¹² Thus text; TP has Śvetaraśmi.

prostration (*praṇāma*), mendicant (*bhikṣu*) tells king to make ~ with eight limbs 99,15 (TP VII 123); – see also: prostration

prostitute, poison damsels (*viṣa-kanyā*) sent as ~s (*paṇya-vilāsini*) into enemy's host 19,82 (TP II 91); *yakṣa* princess as ~ 26,216 (TP II 233); brahmin prostitutes himself for 500 dinars 93,42 (TP VII 81); poor young widow living as ~ on her physical beauty (*rūpa-śālīnī*) 106,94f. (TP VIII 35); ~'s fee (*bhāṭi*) 124,177f. (TP IX 81); – see also: courtesan

prostitution, sacred,¹²¹³ see below *vāra-vilāsini*, and note in TP I 231ff.; husband prostitutes his wife 43,86 (TP III 287);

prostration with eight limbs 98,69 (TP VII 120f.); 99,15 (TP VII 123); – see also: ignorance; parents; prostration

protest of citizens against king by *maraṇa-niścaya* 12,25 (TP I 135); ~ against seclusion of women (*strīṇāṃ rakṣā-niyantraṇa*) 36,6 (TP III 169); ~ against crown prince's giving away of state elephant to brahmins 113,42 (TP VIII 127); – see also: suicide

protocol: sitting in due order (*yathôcitam*) at state dinner 102,115 (TP VII 171); ~ at feast¹²¹⁴ 107,60 (TP VIII 47); welcome at court according to merit (*yathârham*) 108,8 (TP VIII 53);

proud, king ~, because of physical beauty, is cursed to become ugly camel 69,108 (TP VI 16)

proverbial saying,¹²¹⁵ see: amusement; bees; candle; foot; forest; geese; heroes; *hitôpadeśo*; horse; instability; king (unenterprising ~); misfortune; righteous; salt; **sayings**; selfprotection; snake; sun; undertaking; ungrateful men; wealth;

Pṛthivī, the earth goddess, tells waiter at royal gate to sacrifice his son to Caṇḍikā in order to save the king's life 78,51 (TP VI 104)¹²¹⁶

prudence, a man who displays ~ (*kṛta-prajña*) is never harmed; even with animals ~ produces success, not valour (*śreyase, na parākramah*) 60,10 (TP V 41)

pseudo-ascetic, female ~ gives prince magic jewel (*maṇi*) 71,130 and 135 (TP VI 45); ~ male pretends to be meditating and muttering (*kaitava-tapaḥ kṛtaka-dhyāna-japyavān*) 121,157 (TP IX 23); do, laughs at yelling she-jackal 121,161 (TP IX 23);

psycho-somatic abscess due to wounded honour not curable by medicine 15,14f. (TP II 2); – see also: abscess

puberty of unmarried daughter, see: daughter

public interest, see: *sarva-sattvârtha*

public relations, see: bards

pūjā 'religious service', see Jina-°.

Pulindaka as ally of king of Vatsa 14,10 (TP I 182)¹²¹⁷

Pulindas in Vindhya range 12,45 (TP I 136); ~ called *taskara* in 22,62 (TP II 141)

¹²¹³ Syed 2009.

¹²¹⁴ Cf. 110,120 (TP VIII 91).

¹²¹⁵ See especially Stembach 1990.

¹²¹⁶ For the relation between earth and king see 53,114 (TP IV 175).

¹²¹⁷ Zin 2003b: 203.

Pumān springs from egg 2,11 (TP I 9); = Brahmā, whose head was cut off by Śiva 2,13 (TP I 10); – see also: Dhātṛ; Disposer

pum-dveṣiṇī ‘hating men’, misogynist woman 88,9 (TP VII 35; opp.: *stri-dveṣin*); – see also: *puruṣa-dveṣiṇī*

Puṇḍara-viṣaya (Paṇḍra) = Bengal 86,27 (TP VII 15)

punishment, curse of mortal rebirth as ~ for jealousy 36,119 (TP III 177); do, for pride in beauty 52,58 (TP IV 142); ~ of cutting off hands and tongue of thief and his banishment 60,232 (TP V 61)¹²¹⁸; ~ of brothers who cut female slave in two 62,176f. (TP V 114); right hand cut off as ~ for assumed theft of necklace 69,149 (TP VI 19); city guards hang supposed thief at night 77,64 (TP VI 187f.); – see also: adultery; banishment; capital ~ ; *caura-yātanā*; confiscation; curse; disobedience; envy; pride

puns, see ORC 1582f.

puṇya-kṣaya (not MW) ‘exhaustion of merit’, see: merit

puṇya-taru, see: tree of merit

pupil(s), two envious ~ 63,164 (TP V 133); ~ refuses to carry stick and water-vessel (*danḍa-kunḍikā*) of guru 97,30 (TP VII 114); hermit’s ~ curses *vidyādhara* prince to mortal rebirth 117,136 (TP VIII 173)

puppet (*dāru-putrikā*), brahmin has two ~s made and marries one as a third wife 74,165 (TP VI 152)

pura-bhrama, see: oil

Purāri = Śiva, Ujjain residence of ~ 120,9 (TP IX 2);

pardah (*striṇām rakṣā*), see: protest; seclusion of women

purifying, see: transgression

pūrṇa-kumbha ‘full pitcher, vase of plenty’, ~s in front of city gate compared to breasts 18,9 (TP II 50); – see also: breasts; cornucopia

pūrṇa-ṣāḍguṇya-mūrti ‘(Viṣṇu’s) shape is full aggregate of the six kingly measures’ 54,31 (TP IV 186)

purohita has sunshade and elephant as signs of honour 18,125 (TP II 59); ~ is spoken of as miser because he withholds (*āskandin*) half of the fee of brahmins 24,87 (TP II 176); skilful ~ in Arthaśāstra is Atharva-vedin 34,193 (TP III 142); – see further: brahmin(s); cow; garment; magic circle

Purūravas and Urvaśī 17,4f. (TP II 34); P. appeasing Viṣṇu to end curse 17,29 (TP II 36)

puruṣa ‘figure of a man’, king asks Kubera for five indestructible golden ~s whose limbs when cut off grow again as before 38,81 (TP III 212)

puruṣa-dveṣa-durgraha, see: demon; -*durgraha*

puruṣa-dveṣiṇī ‘misandrous’ princess 42,19 (TP III 260); ~ because of remembering pre-birth 43,152 (TP III 291)¹²¹⁹; ~ princess has all men killed by armed maidens 122,40 (TP IX 36); – see also: misandry; *pum-dveṣiṇī*; – opp.: *nārī-caṅga* (q.v.)

¹²¹⁸ Saletore 1943: 284ff.

¹²¹⁹ This motif also in the Arabian Night 719f. of the princess Hayāt en-Nufūs.

puruṣa-medha ‘human sacrifice’, gods ask Prabala’s body for ~ 46,238 (TP IV 64f.); – see also: human sacrifice

puruṣârtha ‘object of human existence’, the wise should always pursue ~ (the unity of Brahmā, Viṣṇu and Śiva, to be obtained by meditation and austerities) 73,169 (TP VI 113)

pūrva-dig-aṅgana ‘for whom the nymph of the eastern quarter’ 84,12 (TP VII 7)

pūrva-karma-taru, from his state of foetus (*ā garbhād*) one eats the fruit of the tree of his former actions 40,109 (TP III 249)

pūrvāmbudhi, see: ocean; Śveta

pūrva-pakṣa (‘first argument in a dispute’) 72,79 (TP VI 75)

Puṣkara wins in gambling against his brother Nala 56,305 (TP IV 242);

Puṣpadanta cursed by Pārvaṭī to become Vararuci Kātyāyana 1,55 (TP I 6f.)

puṣpa-reṇu ‘pollen of flowers’, gardeners find man in love bewildered, with body covered with yellow (*piśaṅga*) ~ as if with the fires of separation 81,63 (TP VI 213); – see also: pollen

pusta, see: modelling

putrīyêṣṭi (‘sacrifice to procure a son’) 13,58 (TP I 153)

pyre (*citā*) with patron deity of Rākṣasas in visible form on it, with the smoke of flames for dishevelled hair (25,99ff. (TP II 197); 53,160 (TP IV 177); merchant widow of impaled robber ascending ~ 88,44 (TP VII 38)¹²²⁰; *kāpālika* quenches burning ~ with ashes and resuscitates dead brahmin woman 124,9 (TP IX 68)

python (*aja-gara*), royal *kārpaṭika* eats gourd (*karkaṭikā*) and becomes ~ 123,32 (TP IX 45)

qualities, physical, queens with extraordinary ~ (*niḥsāmānya-vapur-guṇa*) 85,4 (TP VII 10)

quarrel between thief and *rākṣasa* over two cows of brahmin 62,93 (TP V 107); ~ between two heads of snake 63,176 (TP V 135);

quarreling, see: disputatiousness

quarrelsome wife 23,35 (TP II 159)

quarter, see: *dig-bandha*; ear-ornament; eastern ~; elephants of the ~s; heaven; *kauberi-hāsa*; northern ~; *prācī-dig-vadhu*; *vāsava-diś*; pregnant; southern ~; western ~

queen is painted with *tilaka* under girdle (*mekhalā-pade*) 5,32 (TP I 49); ~ pregnant from stranger 5,60 (TP I 52); ~s compared to (slim) creepers (*latā*), see: forehead; ~ knowing grammar (*śabda-śāstra-vid*) mocks at king 6,118 (TP I 69); ~ compared to second goddess of royal fortune (*nṛpa-śrī*) 14,20 (TP I 183); report of ~ burnt 15,103 (TP II 11)¹²²¹; ~ said to be dead as means to cure king 15,15 (TP II 2) and 16,51ff. (TP II 25); idem 17,41 (TP II 37); ~s drinking spirits as enjoyment 18,27 (TP II 51); naked ~ engaged in sacrificing human flesh 20,51 (TP II 99)¹²²²; king possesses ~ like cloud holds lightning 24,20 (TP II 171); politic and well-conducted ~ is such an ornament to king as language is to a poet 27,56 (TP III 5); far advanced in pregnancy, ~ resembles the East in which the pale

¹²²⁰ STh T 211.2.

¹²²¹ Cf. 10,113 (TP I 114) of a princess.

¹²²² See Dehejia 1986: 15f.; Crooke 1919: 248.

streak of the young moon is about to rise 28,2 (TP III 18), cf. 120,44 (TP IX 4); ~ dies of broken heart after king marries also a merchant beauty 33,72 (TP III 112); king with eight thousand¹²²³ ~s 36,21 (TP III 170); king leaves intoxicated ~ 36,68 (TP III 174); ~ without equal in beauty in the three worlds 49,6 (TP IV 85); ~ speaks Apabhraṃśa 55,125f. (TP IV 210f.); ~ in dream represented by necklace¹²²⁴ 55,139 (TP IV 211); ~'s illicit love of sick man 66,40 (TP V 181); two ~s suddenly die 73,405 (TP VI 129); king with two ~s 74,45 (TP VI 143); king with three ~s 85,5 (TP VII 10); ~ wounded by lotus falling from her ear 85,11 (TP VII 11); ~ burnt by moon rays 85,17 (TP VII 11); hands of ~ bruised after hearing pestle pounding rice 85,24 (TP VII 11); dark (*śyāmā*) ~ 98,35 (TP VII 118); dark ~ from Mālava (vs 6 and 35) with small feet becomes wife of prince and her daughter with large feet wife of king 98,51f. (TP VII 119); ~ compared to night in being moon-faced 110,135 (TP VIII 92); ~ in character like the Ganges (*Gaṅgā-sama-sthiti*) 113,18 (TP VIII 125); ~ consulted (*ālocya samaṃ devyā*) in policy 119,6 (TP VIII 193); pregnant ~ likened to eastern quarter at sunrise 120,44 (TP IX 4; cf. 28,2 above)

question, *vetāla* asks Trivikramasena ~ 75,186 (TP VI 176) et passim;
quicksilver (*pārada*) can be fixed; not so a woman's heart 37,232 (TP III 199);
quiver, snake becomes magic ~ (*tūṇa-ratna*) 46,77 (TP IV 54)¹²²⁵

r/s mistake in writing, see Mette 1973a: 21 note 76 *ratta* for *satta*.

racita-maṇḍana (not MW) 'decorated', see: adulterer

radiating light,¹²²⁶ *kanyā* 17,66 (TP II 39); *divyā kanyā* ~ at night 68,8 (TP VI 1); newborn son ~ 115,130 (TP VIII 153); – see also: attractivity stereotype (illuminating power of female beauty); halo; light; lying-in chamber; maiden

rāga-bandha, thus read at 101,180 for **nāga-bandha* ?

rahas 'in private', speaking ~ 13,179 (TP I 163)¹²²⁷; 28,177 (TP III 34); 29,28 (TP III 41); 30,20 (TP III 65); 34,62 (TP III 133); 35,79 (TP III 161); 37,151 (TP III 193); 38,128 (TP III 215); 39,162 (TP III 229); 43,84 (TP III 287); 43,166 (TP III 292); 45,288 (TP IV 36); 46,225 (TP IV 63); 51,24 (TP IV 123); 58,34 (TP V 17); 60,73 (TP V 47); 71,127 (TP VI 45); 74,224 (TP VI 156); 75,78 (TP VI 169); 94,88 (TP VII 93); 104,53 (TP VIII 5); 123,160 (TP IX 54); – see also: *guptam*; leaving; *rahasi*; *vijane*

rahasi (of Śiva's sex with Umā) 20,72 (TP II 101); ~ having heard story 25,298 (TP II 213); ~ of making love 33,41 (TP III 110; see: *niyoga*); 61,174 (TP V 83); 103,16 (TP VII 176)

rahasya-jñā 'confidante', false ~ sent out to check prince wants to have him herself 71,127

¹²²³ Thousand, like hundred, often stands for a plethora, very many, see infra: hundred.

¹²²⁴ This is understandable when one has seen Indian royal necklaces (vide supra s.v.).

¹²²⁵ STh D 1092.1.

¹²²⁶ Cf. in western literature Curtius 1965: 334f.

¹²²⁷ Cf. Karashima 2012: 307f.

(TP VI 45)

rahasya-dhāriṇī ‘confidante’ 58,123 (TP V 24);

rain, of flowers (*puṣpa-vṛṣṭi*) falls, when Garuḍa ate Jīmūtavāhana 22,225 (TP II 154); queen is ~ of nectar to the eyes (*dr̥ṣṭi-sudhā-vṛṣṭi*) of ship-wrecked man 36,85 (TP III 175); torrential (*a-cchinna-dhārā*) ~ 72,123 (TP VI 78)¹²²⁸; ~ of arrows (*śara-varṣa*) 118,68 (TP VIII 182); acclamation of the gods with a ~ of flowers (*puṣpa-vṛṣa*) 118,89 and, at the end of battle, (*mandāra*¹²²⁹-*vṛṣṭi*) 118,98 (TP VIII 184)

rainy season, see: monsoon

rāja-darśana ‘auspicious viewing of a king’, women’s curiosity of ~ 18,11ff. (TP II 50); – see also: *darśana*

*rāja-haṃsa*¹²³⁰, mango-trees at lake with ~s with soft cries on them 42,228 (TP III 276: “on it the swans sang sweetly”; ORC 437: “*le cri raucque des oies sauvages*”; MI 607: “... *lieben die Königsschwäne ihren summenden gesang ertönen*”); ~ caught by Damayanī in her robe offers to be ambassador to Nala 56,242 (TP IV 237), ~ couple with nest in wild datepalm (*kharjūra-pādape nīḍa-sthitau*)¹²³¹ 69,129 (TP VI 18); *-haṃsī* strikes monkey in tree so that it falls on net and tears this with her captured husband in it who is thus freed 69,146 (TP VI 19);

rāja-jalada (not MW), see: king

rāja-mārga ‘king’s highway’ decorated at coronation 103,235 (TP VII 191)

rajani-rākṣasā (not MW), awful (*ghorā*) ‘night as a female demon’ 98,1 (TP VII 116)

rāja-nīti ‘policy’, to prove his ministers king asks for summary of ~ **34,189 (TP III 142)**

rājarṣi, Gaurī curses ~ to become female who then fell in love with Buddha 89,86 (TP VII 46)

**rāja-santra*, see: almshouse

rāja-śrī ‘fortune of kings’ ever bounding away like a doe 21,99 (TP II 132)

rajasvalā ‘menstruating woman’¹²³² 75,113 (in TP VI 172 omitted);

rājāvarta ‘lapis lazuli’, floor with ~ stone 73,339 (TP VI 125)

Rājput from Deccan, robber disguised as ~ 24,148 (TP II 180); ~ becomes king’s vassal

(*kārpaṭika*) by ragging his garment (*karpaṭa*) 81,6f. (TP VI 209); ~ living on proceeds of village 111,24 (TP VIII 97); ~ from Deccan with 500 clan members 124,52 (TP IX 72);

– see also: *āmalakas*; Deccan; garment; *kārpaṭika*

rājya-pāśa (not MW) ‘kingdom as noose’ 73,93 (TP VI 107);

rājya-sukha ‘happiness of royalty’, old king retires after enjoying ~ 52,383 (TP IV 164)

¹²²⁸ STh F 962.

¹²²⁹ The coral tree (*Erythrina indica*), one of the five heavenly trees.

¹²³⁰ From Dave’s 2005: 436ff. observations it is unclear which kind of bird is meant here. Important is his remark on p. 441: “it is perhaps true to say that poets ... have striven in their compositions more after general effect and word symphony than faithfulness to Nature.”

¹²³¹ According to Dave 2005 ch. 84 *rāja-haṃsa* is used for various waterbirds but these nest on the ground.

¹²³² See Meyer 1952: 225.

rakṣa rakṣa mām ! 52,31 (TP IV 140)

*rākṣasa*¹²³³ discovers riddle 5,23 (TP I 48); ~ comes when thought of (*dhyātāgata*) 5,47 (TP I 50)¹²³⁴ and 18,341 (TP II 75); ~ asks about best-looking woman in city 5,51 (TP I 51); ~s active only at night 7,30 (TP I 76f.), cf. 116,30 *nakṭamcarī*; ~ with heavenly insight (*divya-dṛṣṭi*) 7,31 (TP I 76); ~ without power in the day because dazed by the sun 7,35 (TP I 77); ~ do not attack vegetarians (*a-māṃsa-bhakṣa*) 7,37 (TP I 78); ~ < Daitya when asleep, but boar when wake 11,55f. (TP I 126); two ~s contemplating brahmin from afar, remembering their defeat by Rāma 12,118 (TP I 142)¹²³⁵; ~'s right arm cut off 18,282 (TP II 71); ~ carrying man on shoulder 18,349 (TP II 75); riding a ~ as on a chariot 18,388 (TP II 78); black thunder-cloud like a roaring ~, its tongue compared to lightning 25,41 (TP II 191f.); becoming initiated into practices of ~s by eating brains from funeral pyre (*śmaśāna-vahninā nakṭamcarī-siddhir*) 25,104 (TP II 198); ~ becomes brahmin again 25,256 (TP II 210); ~ in the shape of a crane (*baka*) destroys cities 39,60 (TP III 222); humans¹²³⁶ as appropriate food of ~ 39,95 (TP III 224); head of ~ king cut off grows again but does not do so anymore after being divided 42,133ff. (TP III 268); ~ driven away by brahmin reciting charm for destroying ~s (*rakṣo-ghna-jāpin* [not MW]) 62,97 (TP V 107); disputatiousness (or: noise, *kalaha*)¹²³⁷ characteristic of ~s 66,16 (TP V 179); ~ as black as darkness (*tamaḥ-śyāma*)¹²³⁸ and looking like hell incarnate (*sākāra*) 86,121 (TP VII 21); king takes ~ by the hair to slay him 112,31 (TP VIII 108); ~ rushing to battle of gods and *Asuras* for the corpses of the fallen 116,28 (TP VIII 158); ~ menaces to devour brahmin but leaves him on his promise to return 123,173 (TP IX 55); ~ curses and kills himself for not giving Keśaṭa as alms to his wife 123,189 (TP IX 56); ~ as *pratīhāra* of Rājput chief 124,78 (TP IX 73); – see also: thundercloud

rākṣasa marriage¹²³⁹: brahmin marries *rākṣasī* 25,208 (TP II 206); bridegroom's marriage condition: obedience to *rākṣasa* father-in-law 39,98 (TP III 224)

rākṣasī, genius of hunting is like a ~, defiled with dust (*dhūmra*)¹²⁴⁰ (?), with upstanding hair, etc. (**description**) 21,29 (TP II 127); ~ queen able to change form (*kāma-rūpiṇī*) 25,196 (TP II 206); brahmin marries ~ 25,208 (TP II 206); ~ with two sons asks Bhairava for food and is offered king with centipedes in his head 29,132 (TP III 49); entering lying-in chamber at night ~ with sword carries off child from queen 55,189f. (TP IV 215); woman

¹²³³ See also ORC 1631.

¹²³⁴ Cf. *pumṣātivikṛta* 75,4 (TP VI 164).

¹²³⁵ Cf. 102,51 (TP VII 166)

¹²³⁶ When *rākṣasas* avoid vegetarians, as said in 7,37 (TP I 78), the people actually eaten must be non-vegetarians.

¹²³⁷ Cf. 62,96 (TP V 107)

¹²³⁸ Cf. *megha-malina* in vs 126.

¹²³⁹ See, e.g., Minoru Hara 1974.

¹²⁴⁰ Thus TP for *dhūmra* (Tawney may have read *dhūli*); ORC 177 has “gris”, cf. *dhūmra-keśa* ‘dark-haired’ (MW), but in 116,29 (TP VIII 158) *rākṣasas* have yellow hair.

- disappears as soon as seen, like a ~ 78,113 (TP VI 198); awful night as ~ (*rajani-rākṣasī*) 98,1 (TP VII 116); **description** of ~ , with upstanding yellow hair (*piṅgôrdhva-mūrdhaja*), etc. 116,29 (TP VIII 158);
- rakta-kamala* ‘red lotus’, man’s hand passed off for ~, given to begging brahmin as alms 108,26 (TP VIII 54)
- rakta-mālyānulepana* Mbh 3,264,65d; 10,8,64b, see: garland (73,305)
- raktāmbuja*, see. two red lotuses
- raktāvadāta* (not MW) ‘red and white’, of a woman captivating the eyes as soon as seen 47,109 (TP IV 73)
- ram, two iron ~s (*meṣa*) guarding a gate in Pātāla flee after being hit on the head with a charmed wand (*daṇḍena nyasta-mantreṇa*) 73,131 (TP VI 110);
- Rāma abandoned Sītā because of rumour (*jana-vāda*) 86,13 (TP VII 14)
- Rāmāyaṇa-pāṭhaka* at court 55,142 (TP IV 211)
- Rāmāyaṇa-vṛttānta* 107,12 (TP VIII 43)
- Rambhā, Indra appoints *apsaras* ~ as wife of mortal king 28,93 (TP III 27); ~ dancing, see: dance; ~ singing with Nārada, see: concert
- raṇa-dīkṣā*, see: combat
- raṅga-maṇḍapa* (royal theatre, dancing hall) 71,75 (TP VI 41);
- rank, insignia of ~ (*pada*) 24,17 (TP II 171); ascetic gets ~ of *vidyādhara* 26,230 (TP II 234); – see also: *lilā-vajra*
- raṇōtsava* (not MW), see: feast
- rape, Kālarātri pretends ~ 20,121f. (TP II 105); princess threatens to kill herself when raped 34,9 (TP III 128); woman spurned complains that she was raped 63,34 (TP V 122); wicked princess says to be raped (*dhvaṃsitā*) 64,89 (TP V 146); ~ causes death by curse 105,71 (TP VIII 26); ~ of queen 106,129 (TP VIII 38, see: blood); queen complains of being married by force (*parinītā ... balāt*) 123,3 (TP IX 43)
- rasakōttama*, see: fertility elixir
- rasāyana* ‘elixir for long life’ smeared on minister’s neck against strokes of sword 41,33 (TP III 254)
- rash act(s), attendant advises king against ~ (*alaṃ sāhasena*) 42,24 (TP III 260); ~ destroy person in both worlds 64,13 (TP V 139); fool drinks clyster (*vasti*) instead of using it orally 64,15 (TP V 139); – see also: *mā kārṣiḥ sāhasam*; *mā sāhasaṃ kṛthāḥ*; mongoose
- rata-lālasa* (not MW) ‘ardently desirous of sex’, said of a queen 52,270 (omitted in TP IV 156)
- Rati, Kāma’s wife, changed into mortal maiden 34,44 (TP III 131);
- ratna-dīpa*, see: jewel-lamp
- ratnāni*, see: insignia
- ratna-Vināyaka* [not MW] ‘image of Gaṇeśa made of a jewel’ 73,325 (TP VI 124)
- rātry-abhisārikā*¹²⁴¹ (not MW) ‘nymph of night’ veiling her shape in a black robe of darkness 94,52 (TP VII 91; ORC 1008: “nuit telle une femme qui va au rendez-vous”; M II 333: “die

¹²⁴¹ The word may not be a compound though its recurrence makes it plausible.

Mädchen, die zur Nachtzeit zum Stelldichein gingen”) and 103,203 (TP VII 189; ORC 1082: „*la nuit vint à son rendez-vous*“; M II 439: „*zog die buhlende Nacht in ihrem vergnüglichen schwarzen Gewand der Dunkelheit heran*“)

rat(t)an palm (*vetasī*), pitcher with treasures buried in forest under ~ (*vetasī-tale*) 121,162 (TP IX 23)

rava, see: shriek

ravine (*śvabhra*), wicked wife plots to kill husband in ~ 65,17ff. (TP V 154f.); after entering body of young brahmin, magician throws his old body (*pūrva-kalevara*) into ~ 97,41 (TP VII 115)

rays, of sun compared to hand¹²⁴² 29,126 (TP III 48); ~ stretched out (*prasārīta-kara*) 71,193 (TP VI 50); princess is pouring forth ~ of beauty 73,341 (TP VI 125); *kumudvatī* opens under the ~ of the moon 73,345 (TP VI 125); lovesick man is smitten on his bed by the ~ of the moon (*candra-pādāhato*) 84,14 (TP VII 6); sensitive queen burnt by ~ of moon 85,16ff. (TP VII 11); the sun stretching forth its first ~, like a warning hand, to dissuade ... 98,12 (TP VII 117); – see also: attractivity; beauty; eye; seeing

reading, knowledge without ~ impossible 40,22 (TP III 241)

realm, king devolves care of ~ on ministers to enjoy pleasures 11,2 (TP I 122) and 21,3 (TP II 125); wealth is compared to root of tree of ~ 19,51 (TP II 88); ~ likened to grass 22,44 (TP II 140); *vidyādhara* king gives brahmin hero, his son-in-law, his ~ and his magic sciences, and makes him king 26,281 (TP II 238); crime of “destroyer of the ~ (*deśa-dūṣaka*)” 27, 29 (TP III 3); ~ as tree (*rājya-śākhin*) watered with ambrosia of minister’s counsel 33,163 (TP III 121); ~ left to ministers by king who secretly goes to city of enemy 38,17f. (TP III 207); as king remains fixed on queen he entrusts ~ on minister 52,264 (TP IV 156); king gives ~ to son 52,368 (TP IV 163); king commits ~ to ministers in order to go to sole of Svāmikumāra’s feet 55,155 (TP IV 213); sonless king gives brahmin his daughter and half his ~ 56,134 (TP IV 229); king leaves ~ to minister in order to go and seek his wife 71,244 (TP VI 54); ~ of Rāma without sickness and famine 72,92 (TP VI 76); ~ as noose (*rājya-pāśa*) 73,93 (TP VI 107); ~ given to king’s younger brother (*anuja*) 73,94 (TP VI 107); ~ entrusted to ministers, king and vassal embark ship 81,70 (TP VI 213); king leaves care of ~ to chief minister 86,6-9 (TP VII 13f.); do, 86,70 (TP VII 18); king devolves ~ upon minister and retires into harem 89,4 (TP VII 40); ministers guard ~ while king is on pilgrimage 93,71 (TP VII 83); king flees ~ at night 98,9 (TP VII 116); king leaves weight of ~ to minister and devotes himself to pleasure 101,45 (TP VII 137); king entrusts ~ to ministers and visits with queen other king 101,215 (TP VII 149); king with grey hair abandons ~ 103,229 (TP VII 191); two divisions of the *vidyādhara* ~ 107,65 (TP VIII 47); extension of ~ of Vikramāditya 120,76f. (TP IX 6); – see also: king; ministers

reanimation, see: resuscitation

¹²⁴² Cf. the famous picture of Echnaton and his wife Nofretete under the sun in Tell el-Amarna (Schulz & Seidel 2004: 221 and 338; Schloegl 2006: 234f.)

rebirth¹²⁴³ with same wife 3,20 (TP I 19); 4,10 (TP I 31); ~ of human as *vidyādhara* with re collection of pre-births (*smṛta-jāti*) 22,58 (TP II 141); ~ of *vidyādhari* as mortal 26,169 (TP II 230); ~ of servant in royal family 27,99 (TP III 8); Nāgārjuna not to be reborn attains Buddhalike status (*Buddha-samāṇi gatim*) 41.53 (TP III 256); *deva-putra* foresees ~ as a pig in seven days (*saptāhāt sūkari-garbhe saṃbhavaṃ cāikṣatātmanah*) 53,118 but six days of meditation on Śambhu saves him therefrom 53,125 (TP IV 176); ~ of *ṛṣi* and wife as parrot and wild sow 59,157f. (TP V 36f.); ~ as bird 69,158 (TP VI 20); ~ of inconsiderate judge as animal for making brahmin couple take poison 72,215 (TP VI 84); ~ with same body from belly of fish 74,207 (TP VI 155); – see also: remembering
 recitation of *om* syllable, see: *om*
 reciter (*pāṭhaka*) of the Rāmāyaṇa 55,142 (TP IV 211);
 reckless act, see: act
 recollection, see: remembering
 red as mark of anger and passion,¹²⁴⁴ see: eyes
 red face of bride from heat and smoke of marriage fire 103,192 (TP VII 188)
 red lead (*sindūra*),¹²⁴⁵ bawd's body painted half lamp-black, half ~, the colour of Śiva's Gaṇas 12,169 (TP I 146); *tilaka* of ~ on head of naked queen at sacrifice 20,50 (TP II 98); particles of ~ flying from Gaṇeṣa's trunk 24,1 (TP II 170); – see also: *sindūra*
 red lotus (*raktāmbuja*), Śiva gives ~ to couple which will show unfaithfulness during separation 13,79 (TP I 156); housewife gives beggar ~ (*rakta-kamala*) with alms 108,24 (TP VIII 54)
 red lower lip, of newborn prince, long like a leaf (*raktāyatādhara-dala*) 23,69 (TP II 162)
 red powder, see: *kuṅkum*
 red cotton or cloth banners (*dhvaja-raktāṃśuka-*) 18,9 (TP II 49); ~ on Durgā temple compared to tongue of Death 22,63 (TP II 141)¹²⁴⁶; ~ on palace, seeming to fling red dye to one another 23,78 (TP II 163); city of Kausāmbī with ~ 54,77 (TP IV 189)

¹²⁴³ See also ORC 1633 s.v. *Renaissance*. STh E 601. – Doniger O'Flaherty 1983, Part I; Bronkhorst 2007: 52ff. and 72ff. considers karma and rebirth concepts to be native to Greater-Magadha and to be non-Vedic (pp. 142ff.). Rebirth proper actually fits only in Hinduism and Jainism, because these know of a permanent soul. As in Buddhism there is no such *ātman*, but instead the illusion of a person, *aham*, gradually arising in a firm, material body, this illusion also dies with that body. Its karman (thoughts, words and deeds of a life), however, pass on in *saṃsāra* and (with a *gandharva* as kind of catalysator ?) become the basis of a new body plus illusion of person. Thus there is actually no rebirth proper, but one more birth from another mother in new surroundings which create a new illusion on the basis of the former karman. Advaitins such as Nisargadatta therefore “totally discards the concept of re-birth as sheer nonsense” (Balsekar 1982: 123ff.).

¹²⁴⁴ Lüders 1940: 419f.; Hanchett 1988: 286f. who remarks that “the individual colour red seems to have a different significance in north and south India. In the north, the colour red is generally auspicious. ... In Karnataka, the colour red is good in the vermilion-mark, but otherwise used it is a wild and difficult colour, sometimes good but often dangerous” (because associated with blood). – “Red is associated very directly with *śakti* by the Hindu” (Abbott 1932: 281).

¹²⁴⁵ On red lead or vermilion see Feldhaus 1995: 244; Bollée 2010a.

¹²⁴⁶ Cf. von Duhn 1906.

- red (*piñjara*) sky due to approaching *vidyādhara*-army 44,134 (TP IV 10);
- red, rosa ~ (*rāga*), love's proper hue,¹²⁴⁷ is the harbinger of eclipse to the courtesan as to the evening twilight (*doṣāgra-dūto rāgo hi veśyā-pāścima-saṃdhyayoḥ*) 57,62 (TP V 6; ORC 651 with note on p. 1437¹²⁴⁸: “*l’embrasement annonce la nuit: cela vaut pour le soir – comme pour la courtisane*”; MI 915: “*Die rote Liebesleidenschaft ist für eine Hetäre der Vorbote des Untergangs, wie die Abendröte das Vorzeichen für den Untergang der Sonne ist*”)
- red unguent, emperor adorned with ~ (*aruṇenāṅga-rāgeṇa*) 110,81 (TP VIII 87);
- red as vermilion, citizens and sun ~ (*sindūra-piṅgala*) at the end of a festival day¹²⁴⁹ 18,122 (TP II 58); 35,112 (TP III 164)
- red, wind from Malaya mountain, ~ with pollen of flowers (*puṣpa-reṇu-piśaṅgo Malayānila-pāvakaḥ*) 71,198 (TP VI 50);
- reflection in water,¹²⁵⁰ see: lion; parrot
- refuge, sea as ~ of mountains 27,137 (TP III 11)
- refugee, king gives horse and sword to princely ~ 72,167 (TP VI 81); brahmin ~ 108,47 (TP VIII 56); – see also: economic refugee
- regalia, see: insignia
- regicide, see: tunnel
- reincarnation, see: rebirth
- relations (relatives), refuse to fight ~ 22,41f. (TP II 140); king expelled by ~ (*gotraja*) goes to father-in-law 58,110 (TP V 23); – see also: daughter (93,11 [TP VII 79]); Deccan (52,96 [TP IV 144]); emigration (20,21 [TP II 96]); envy (22,37 [TP II 139]); expulsion; fire; forest (98,8ff. [TP VII 116f.]); heritage; *jāti-vigraha*; paramour (58,75ff. [TP V 20])
- releasing prisoners at royal wedding feast (*mocita-bandhana-sthaṃ mahōtsavaṃ*) 101,380 (TP VII 160)
- religion (*dharma*) is not confined to one form, a transcendent (*lokōttara*) ~ differs from one that embraces the universe (*sārva-laukika*) 27,21 (TP III 3)
- religious festival (*yātrōtsava*), world's beauty is short-lived like a ~ 66,33 (TP V 180); 89,6 (TP VII 40); – see also: procession; spring
- remarriage of widowed queen 98,54 (TP VII 119); – see also: eleven; widower; woman who killed eleven husbands
- remembering, things heard only once 2,37 (TP I 12)¹²⁵¹ and *sakṛcchruta-dhara* 2,61 (TP I 15f.); Jīmūtavāhana is ~ pre-births (*jāti-smara*) 22,53 (TP II 141); idem at rebirth 22,166

¹²⁴⁷ For red as an auspicious colour with respect to procreation and marriage see, e.g. Daniel 1983: 88f.

¹²⁴⁸ Refers to the double pun of *rāga* which signifies ‘glow’ as well as ‘red colour’ and ‘love, passion’, and *doṣā* / *doṣa* meaning ‘night’ or ‘fault, bad consequence’.

¹²⁴⁹ TP, in a note, thinks that “probably the people sprinkled one another with red powder, as at the Holi festival.” The consequence of the use of alcohol seems to be a more likely assumption.

¹²⁵⁰ STh *J 1791ff.

¹²⁵¹ See above: memory.

(TP II 149); three *vidyādhara* princesses ~ pre-birth, supplemented with divine insight, despite curse to become mortal 26,60 (TP II 221); sudden (*a-kāṇḍe*) ~ of pre-birth by queen 27,83 (TP III 7); ~ pre-birth and telling it causes death 27,83 (TP III 7); reciprocal ~ of pre-birth by royal couple 27,85 (TP III 7); fisherman ~ pre-birth as undisciplined brahmin suffers misery 27,131 (TP III 11); **not** ~ pre-birth 29,6 (TP III 39); white elephant, a cursed *Gandharva*, remembers pre-birth 36,14 (TP III 170); cursed *Gandharvas* remember pre-birth and abandon body 36,129f. (TP III 178); prince suddenly ~ pre-birth after waking up from sleep and telling his father 42,197 (TP III 274); princess ~ pre-births (*jāti-smarā*) is a *puruṣa-dveṣiṇī* 43,152ff. (TP III 291); whoever does not die of his own free will, and is born in another womb does not remember anything, as his memory is destroyed by old age 45,59f. (TP IV 21); ~ all, when entering another's body by magic 45,60f. (TP IV 21); ~ birth (*smṛta-jāti*) at information by *vidyādhara* Smara abandons his body in the water of Prayāga 52,405 (TP IV 166); hermit tells story thus causing parrot to remember pre-birth 59,57 (TP V 30); king ~ former birth enters former (*vidyādhara*) body which falls from heaven 59,176 (TP V 38); after telling history cursed *vidyādhari* remembers former birth 66,175 (TP V 191); Jīmūtavāhana ~ pre-births 90,89 (TP VII 55); Caṇḍāla chiefs turn into bob-tailed dogs ~ their pre-births 114,123 (TP VIII 141); ~ pre-birth (q.v.) remorse (“*aham evāparādhyāmi*”) of king for grieving queen 16,115 (TP II 30); king dies of ~ after trying to rape merchant's wife, who died of fear to lose her chastity 34,20 (TP III 129); – see also: *anutāpa*

repetition, see: stylistic repetition

reply, see: answer

report, king rewards scouts for ~ 12,9 (TP I 133); false ~ (*mithyā pravādaḥ*) of king's death 15,98 (TP II 10); ~ of queen burnt (*devī-dāha-pravāda*) 15,103 (TP II 11); ministers telling king ~ of inauspiciousness of merchant sylph 91,16 (TP VII 67); – see also: calumny; lying; rumour; slander

reproach, king's fear of ~ 5,63 (TP I 52); ~ (*mithyā-vādinī*) of Gaurī by devotee 90,183 (TP VII 61); ~ of Devī followed by curse 114,69 (TP VIII 137); – see also: criticism

resolution accomplishes everything 60,163 (TP V 55)

respect for the aged,¹²⁵² see: parents

resuscitation, of robbers by *vetālas* 18,149 (TP II 61); ~ of snakes by Garuḍa 22,245 (TP II 155); ~ of *Asura* by smelling 46,224 (TP IV 63); ~ of dead woman by brahmin 52,104 (TP IV 145) as an unlawful art (*vikarman*) 52,113 (TP IV 146); ~ by being sprinkled with charmed water with Cāmuṇḍā-spell 52,158 (TP IV 149)¹²⁵³; ~ of beloved by spell, Ganges water, asceticism 76,34f. (TP VI 181); brahmin is knower of ~ of dead beings (*jantūn mṛtān*) 83,29f. (TP VII 4); Bhairava revives robber husband to faithful wife 88,51 (TP VII 38); ~ of Jīmūtavāhana by Gaurī sprinkling him with nectar from her pitcher (*kamaṇḍalu*) 90,185 (TP VII 62); Caṇḍī revives woman and two men 95,89 (TP VII 104),

¹²⁵² Cf. Rājāt 1,293.

¹²⁵³ STh E 50ff.

cf. 111,45 (TP VIII 99); *kāpālīka* revives woman on pyre by throwing ashes on the flames 124,9 (TP IX 68); – see also: adulterer
 return, king's ~ to his previous Dānava body embalmed in Pātāla 45,50 (TP IV 20);
 return on promise, of *yakṣiṇī* to ascetic 37,81 (TP III 189); ~ of woman to lover motif¹²⁵⁴
 84,26 (TP VII 6) and 50 (TP VII 8); ~ of brahmin to *rākṣasa* 123,173 and 184 (TP IX 56)
 Revā river, king crosses ~ for Ujjayinī 19,98 (TP II 93)
 revenge (*pratikriyā*), god Svāmikumāra (Skanda) propitiated to obtain ~ 49,232ff. (TP IV 101); ~ on slayers of sons 50,75 (TP IV 112); ~ feared by gamblers 121,35 (TP IX 14)
 revolt of subjects against king 113,42-5 (TP VIII 127)¹²⁵⁵; – see also: protest; subjects; suicide
 reward, king ~s minister for communicating him all sciences 6,166 (TP I 72); rejoiced (*pāritoṣika*) king gives scouts a lakh of gold pieces for a report 12,9 (TP I 133); mother asks for ~ for giving birth to daughter (*sutā-phala*) 12,163 (TP I 146); cursed *apsaras* live as wives of good men as ~ for acts of devotion and charity (*yāga-pradāna-*) 17,133 (TP II 45); necklace as ~ given to female messenger 117,116 (TP VIII 172); ~ of garments, ornaments and villages for reporting conquest 120,80 (TP IX 7); – see also: bard; *bhadra-kṛt*; *bhāṭi*; charity; fee; messenger
rex puer (*Nandasya tanayo bālo*) 4,106 (TP I 39)¹²⁵⁶
 rhetoric valued: king speaks correctly Sanskrit (*ācāṣṭa ... samyak-saṃskṛtayā girā*) and the court is delighted (*pramudita*) to witness that 7,2 (TP I 74); Damayantī thinks *divya-haṃsa* a polished speaker (*satyābhibhāṣin*) 56,246 (TP IV 237)
 rhinoceroses (*khaḍga*) in wilderness 101,282 (TP VII 153)¹²⁵⁷
 rice, divine ~ as food for journey does not diminish 7,21 (TP I 75); two handfuls of ~ (*tanḍula-muṣṭī*) thrown at cross-roads (*catuṣ-patha*) to conciliate Piśāca 28,166 (TP III 33); living on ~ in the husk (*a-sūdrāna*; *śuṣkāna*) symbolizes virtue 33,134 (TP III 118); minister eats two grains of magic ~ from human sacrifice which can produce gold 108,78 (TP VIII 59f. with long note 3); – see also: gold; poison
 riches come and go like a cloud out of season 33,141 (TP III 119); ~ pass away like an autumn cloud 96,24 (TP VII 109)
 riddle,¹²⁵⁸ of hand in Ganges 5,8 (TP I 45); escaping death by solving ~ of the best-looking woman asked by *rākṣasa* 5,51 (TP I 51); ~ of man coming out of painted wall 66,65 (TP V 183); ~ of *vetāla* solved by king Trivikramasena 75,186 et passim (TP VI 177 etc.); – see also: Oedipus riddle
 right eye, man's ~ throbbing is auspicious omen 67,68 (TP V 200); ~ throbbing is inauspicious for a woman 117,141 (TP VIII 173)

¹²⁵⁴ Cf. Bollée 2006a: 33.

¹²⁵⁵ Cf. *janapada-kopa* in Daś 164.12.

¹²⁵⁶ See Bollée 2008a: 27 note 127; Rājat 1,76 and 80ff.; 5,290 and 449; 6,115 et passim.

¹²⁵⁷ Kuv 27.31 states rhinos to be in the Vindhya forest; see also Kuv note 339.

¹²⁵⁸ See ORC 1566 s.v. Enigmes.

righteous (*śubha-kṛt*) people do not sink (proverb) 56,232 (TP IV 236);
 righteousness (*dharma*), bull (*vṛṣa*) as symbol of ~ 70,108 (TP VI 31f.)
 right arm (*bhuja*), *rākṣasa* extends ~ into dark room which a hero then cuts off 18,281ff. (TP II 71)¹²⁵⁹; ~ hand (*dakṣiṇaṃ pāṇim*) cut off for thieving 69,149 (TP VI 19)¹²⁶⁰
 ring, destroying effect of poison, see: poison; ~ given by *vidyādhari* as reminder to husband 18,238 (TP II 68); ~ (*ratnāṅguliyaka*) put into water pitcher for *vidyādhari* 18,361 (TP II 76); Nereid had rings from onehundred lovers 63,30 (TP V 122); *yakṣa* king gives hero ~ with power of averting *iti* calamities 72,61 (TP VI 73 with note 1); brahmin asks king's evil-removing (*sarva-doṣa-ghna*) ~ against *brahma-rākṣasa* 72,159 (TP VI 80); Mūladeva puts his ~ on finger of sleeping bride and leaves 124,168 (TP IX 80)
 rinsing mouth (*ācamya*)¹²⁶¹ before act of truth 16,117 (TP II 30); ~ forbidden (*an-ācānta*) in Piśāca rite 28,165 (TP III 33); ~ before eating 87,42 (TP VII 32); ~ before receiving charm 92,62 (TP VII 75); ~ of royal devotee of Trilocana before addressing *lokapālas* for advice 112,134 (TP VIII 116); ~ before rite with corpse 121,16 (TP IX 13)– see also: mouth
 rite to get help from Piśāca 28,164 (TP III 33); funeral ~s (*saṃskāra*) by king for daughter 52,167 (TP IV 149); king worships Lakṣmī daily with 108 white lotuses for a son 69,78 (TP VI 14); incantation to get control over an imp of the fever demon (*jvara-cetaka*) 71,207 (TP VI 50)
 rivalry in royal harem 32,123 (TP III 99)¹²⁶²; – see also: envy; jealousy; Lakṣmī
 rival wives bring many false accusations 32,191 (TP III 106)
 river, of the gods (*sura-sindhu*, i.e. Ganges)¹²⁶³ 18,62 (TP II 54); ~ Śītodā, impassable for mortals 18,350 (TP II 75)¹²⁶⁴; who can restrain a furious ~ and a passionate woman ? 36,8 (TP III 169); male and female ~s provide coronation water 50,203 (TP IV 121); women like ~s drown man who falls into their power 52,288 (TP IV 157); woman becomes faithful as ~s at rest in bosom of sea (*sāgara-varmaṇi*) 52,362 (TP IV 163); wife escapes from jealous husband like ~ breaks a dam 61,147 (TP V 81); ~ Vitastā in Cashmere repels transgression (*kalmaṣa*) with its waves as if they were hands 73,83 (TP VI 107); ~ Vipāśā flowing backwards 74,190 (TP VI 154);
rLung sgom, see: ointment
 road (*mārga*) dividing into two; left ~ to be taken to empty town 124,71f. (TP IX 73); – see also: *catuṣ-patha*
 roaming, hero is ~ about at night 72,30 (TP VI 70); – see also: king; night
 robber(s) (*caura*)¹²⁶⁵, man led off as ~ about to be executed 10,170 (TP I 118); impaled ~

¹²⁵⁹ The right arm follows from 18,330 (TP II 74).

¹²⁶⁰ Cf. Wirth 2010: 148f.

¹²⁶¹ Vasu 1918: 13f.

¹²⁶² STh T 257.2; Syed 2001: 181.

¹²⁶³ Lüders 1951: 679.

¹²⁶⁴ STh F 141.1.

tenanted by *vetālas* 18,149 (TP II 61); two rogues (*dhūrtau*) as ~ 24,82 (TP II 175); old age as ~ of beauty (*saundarya-hāriṇī*) 40,44 (TP III 243); man found in temple with royal necklace thought to be ~ 54,110 (TP IV 191); ~ falls into sea at night and perishes 54,117 (TP IV 192); ~ attack at night 54,126 (TP IV 192); one of two ~s breaks into chamber (*vāsa-veśma*) of princess 64,44 and, bewildered with love and wine, falls asleep 49 (TP V 142); genetic ~ (*jātaka-nirdiṣṭa-caurya*) 72,192 (TP VI 82)¹²⁶⁶; ~ in Siṃhaladvīpa 72,319 (TP VI 92); genetic ~, when old, worships only Citragupta 72,324 (TP VI 93); ~ gives his wife to Citragupta 72,330 (TP VI 93); ~ boss (*caura-camū-patī*), brahmin only by name 73,206 (TP VI 116); ~ makes hole in house wall (*saṅghim bhittvā*) 77,58 (TP VI 187); ~ follows adulterous wife, sees her nose bitten off by *vetāla* in corpse of lover and later informs king thus saving husband from execution 77,61-88 (TP VI 187-9); man on his way at night hung as ~ (*caura-buddyā pāśa-kaṇṭhaṃ mṛtaṃ*) 77,64 (TP VI 188); ~ made chief magistrate of town (*purādhyakṣa*) 77,88 (TP VI 189); generous ~ let go faithful bride who promised to visit him 84,57 (TP VII 8); ~ lives in underground cavern in forest 88,20 (TP VII 36); merchant's daughter falls in love with ~ to be executed (*māra-mohitā*) 88,34 (TP VII 37); ~ weeps and laughs when impaled 88,43 (TP VII 38); marriage of dying ~ 93,23 (TP VII 79); at sea a roaring cloud suddenly arises as if a ~ 101,140 (TP VII 143); Mātāṅgas as ~s of caravans 102,58 (TP VII 166); king as ~ whose vices make him unbearable 112,156 (TP VIII 118f.; see supra: *durbhara*); home of ~ in underground excavation (*veśma kṣmā-tale khāta-nirmitam*) like city of Nāgas 112,158f. (TP VIII 119); ~ led off to place of execution (*vadhya-bhūmi*) 112,164 (TP VIII 119); attempt to buy ~ free from execution fails 112,168 (TP VIII 120); *caṇḍālas* thought ~s cut off nose and ears but set free by other ~s as guests on Senānī (Kārttikeya) feast 114,111-115 (TP VIII 141); ~s plunder Śaivaite town (*Śaiva-kṣetram puram*) at night 114,118 (TP VIII 141); ~ become bob-tailed (*puccha-vinā-kṛta*) dogs 114,123 (TP VIII 141); – see also: *bhakṣya-kośalikā*; incognito; Kāla; king; thug(s); wall

robber gang (*caura-senā*) killing and plundering caravan in wood at night 54,124 (TP IV 192); ~ (*caura-camū*) 73,206 (TP VI 116; ORC 864: “*cohorte de brigands*”); – see also: thug(s) robe, see: garment

rocamāna ‘curl of hair on a horse’s neck’ (auspicious sign on a horse)¹²⁶⁷ 74,78 (TP VI 145); – see also: *āvarta*; curl; horse

rock of execution (*vadhya-śilā-tala*), awful, as the bed where the play (of life) ends (*kṛtānta-lilā-paryāṅka-raudra*) [?] 90,143 (TP VII 59; ORC 984: “*le lit où la Mort se joue des êtres vivants*”; M II 300: “*das Ruhebett, das dem Todesgott zu seinen vergnüglichen Spielen dient*”)

rock-weapon (*śailāstra*) 116,71 (TP VIII 161)

rogôpaśānti (not MW) ‘cure’ 24,168 (TP II 181)

rogues, two ~ in Ratnapura 24,82 (TP II 175); 124,131ff. (TP IX 77ff.); – see also:

¹²⁶⁵ See Saletore 1943: 284ff.; Fezas 1990.

¹²⁶⁶ STh J 1179.4.

¹²⁶⁷ See above s.v. *āvarta*.

physician

Rohiṇī, *nakṣatra* (and wife), dear to the moon 35,23 (TP III 156);

Rohiṇī tree resembling the Vedas in that many birds are in its branches just as brahmins in those of the Vedic tradition 59,37 (TP V 28)

rolling, on the ground as love symptom¹²⁶⁸ (*luloṭha dharāṇau*) 7,66 (TP I 81); ~ of a dog 61,212 (TP V 86); ~ of charmed peacock at feet of prince in order to show string round its neck 71,54 (TP VI 39); ~ of love-sick woman on bed 89,34 (TP VII 42) and 95,25 (TP VII 99); brahmin ~ about on bed of lotus leaves 95,48 (TP VII 101); ~ of a woman in love 117,106 (TP VIII 171); 121,150 (TP IX 22); – see also: bed; gestures

roomal (*pāśā*),¹²⁶⁹ Kāla (like a thug ?) throws ~ over neck of man (*gala-kṣipta-pāśā*) 72,348 (TP VI 94)

root of ear, see: ear; ~ of eye, see: eye (90,43 [TP VII 52])

root of tree of realm; ~ of tree of vice; – see: tree

rope (*rajju*), man pulled into queen’s apartment by the window with a ~ 58,124 (TP V 24); ~ of grass 65,19 (TP V 155) and 65,54 (TP V 158); ~ with seat to leave palace through window 75,119 (TP VI 172)

rosary beads (*akṣa-mālikā*) compared to transgressions 24,102 (TP II 177); ~ seem knots (*granthi*) marking ages of owner’s life and resting on his ear 25,15 (TP II 189); ~ and water vessel of hermit 28,78 (TP III 26); *brahmacāriṇī* with ~ 29,52 (TP III 42); ~ (*akṣa-sūtra*) of female Hindu ascetic 71,130 (TP VI 45); drunk witch tries to take away ascetic’s ~ (*akṣa-mālikā*) 75,175 (TP VI 176); queen Dhanavatī wearing ~ (*akṣa-sūtra*) 107,63 (TP VIII 47); pseudo-ascetic with ~ 121,154 (TP IX 23);

rotting in the Ganges (*śirṇo Gaṅgā-jale*), (corpse of) *cāṇḍāla* ~ 27,128 (TP III 10);

royal banquet, see: drinking bout; food

rubies, eyes of a monkey like two ~ (*padma-rāga-maṇī*) 37,87 (TP III 189)

rudīta-dhvani ‘noise of weeping’ 72,30 (TP VI 70)

Rudra, sacrifice to ~ to be preceded by *aśvamedha* 45,18 (TP IV 18); royal sacrifice to ~ at night 45,41 (TP IV 19), ~ and others looking at battle between gods and *Asuras* 115,26 (TP VIII 146)

ruṅṇa ‘broken, infirm, diseased’, false confidante tells mistress lie of having seen loved prince ~ 71,143 (TP VI 46: “crouching”; ORC 818 “*brisé*”; M II 62: “*gebrochen*”)

Rukmiṇī as dear to Viṣṇu as Madanasundarī to Kanakavarṣa 55,105 (TP IV 209); ~ as main woman cherished by Kṛṣṇa 68,5 (TP VI 1);

rumour,¹²⁷⁰ slanderous, of ascetic eating children (*arbhaka*) 24,209 (TP II 185); ~ spreads from ear to ear (*karṇa-paramparām pravādo ... yayau*) 24,212 (TP II 185)¹²⁷¹; ~ (*prasiddham gīyate*) 39,29 (TP III 220); ~ (*pravāda*) 39,52 (TP III 221); ~ terrible as stroke of lightning

¹²⁶⁸ Cf. Amaru 33.

¹²⁶⁹ For a picture see Wagner 2007: 104 and 115.

¹²⁷⁰ Cf. Bollée 2008a: 27.

¹²⁷¹ See also Bollée 2010a: 152.

(*vidyun-nīpātôgrā vārtā*) 67,54 (TP V 199); ~ (*jana-vāda*) 86,11 and *loka-vāda*¹²⁷² 86,13 (TP VII 14); *pāramparyeṇa śrutāni* 119,123 (TP VIII 202)
rūpābdhi (not MW) ‘sea of beauty’ 57,75 (TP V 7); – see: sea
rūpa-prabhāvau ‘shape and power’, a *vetāla* gives his ~ to a gambler 121,55 (TP IX 16)

s/m misprint (*sati* for *mati*) 18,47 (TP II 53 note 2)

s- for *pr-* ? see: *seraṇa*. For the old confusion of *p* and *s* see Norman 1969: 134 on Thag 49.

Śabara¹²⁷³ (cf. Śavara) lives by dancing snakes 9,76 (TP I 100); ~ in Vindhya 10,134-141 (TP I 115); ~ compassionate 22,65 (TP II 141); ~ searches elephant pearls in wood 22,87 (TP II 143); ~ kills paramour 32,69 (TP III 95); ~ takes sleeping king to Durgā’s temple as victim 55,221 (TP IV 217); ~s fetter brahmin in search of water in wilderness 56,23 (TP IV 221); old ~ climbs tree and catches parrots, etc. 59,45 (TP V 29); water spirits seize ~ king after bath 71,5 (TP VI 36); ~ women dance at royal reunion feast 101,347 (TP VII 158); black ~ letter-carrier wears loin-cloth (*kaṭī-nivasana*) of bilva leaves 101,355 (TP VII 158); ~ adorned with peacock feathers and elephant tusks, clothed in tiger skins and living on deer meat 102,61 (TP VII 167)¹²⁷⁴; **description** of ~ **102,61** (TP VII 167)¹²⁷⁵; ~ identical with *caṇḍāla* 112,80 (TP VIII 112); ~ (Bhilla) dwelling (*sadana*) with high walls of elephant tusks 123,49f. (TP IX 46); – see also: Bhilla; Mātāṅga

sabhā, see: court

sabhya ‘croupier’, gambler makes himself ~ in Mahākāla temple playing dice against Mātaras, etc. 121,80 (TP IX 17f.)

sacred thread, see: *upanayana*

sacrifice to procure prince (*putrīyêṣṭi*) 13,58 (TP I 153); ~ to waterspirits with jewels 18,295 (TP II 72); ~ of blood, spirits and human flesh 20,51 (TP II 99); human ~ before Caṇḍikā 26,144 (TP II 227); by ~ of bilva fruit Agni is enabled to give king a golden one back 35,68f. (TP III 160); human ~ to someone’s grave 37,39 (TP III 185); ~ (*bali*) to Rudra at night 45,41 (TP IV 19); time of midday ~ (*mādhyam̐dina-savana-samaya*) 45,386 (TP IV 43); ~ with lotuses and ghee produces cloud raining black snakes 46,91 (TP IV 55); wandering hermit (*parivrāt*) performs ~ in charnel ground in order to get *yakṣiṇi* in his power (*yakṣiṇi-siddhaye*) 49,163 (TP IV 96); human ~ (*upahāra*) to Durgā / Caṇḍikā 53,131f. (TP IV 177) and 72,402 (TP VI 99); ~ of *haṃsa* to Hara / Śiva 69,156 (TP VI 20); ~ of goat to Śiva, see: goat; ~ of life by Bodhisattva 72,380 (TP VI 97); ~ (*iṣṭi*) as sperma substitute on behalf of a king to get a son 74,43ff. (TP VI 143); *brahma-rākṣasa* demands ~ of seven year old brahmin boy 94,78 (TP VII 92); human ~ (*narôpahāra*)¹²⁷⁶ 94,117 (TP VII 95); ~

¹²⁷² Cf. Daś 95.9 and Bollée 1977: 122.

¹²⁷³ See Kuv note 146, and for pictures in Ajanta: Zin 2003: II 202ff.; Zin 1999; Saletore 1935: 38ff.

¹²⁷⁴ Zin 2003b: 202.

¹²⁷⁵ A Śabara chief is described in Bāṇa, *Kād.* 64,1ff.

¹²⁷⁶ Human sacrifices still occur occasionally. Thus, according to the *Times of India* of Aug. 18th, 2010, parents in Dahelikushepa village, Sitapur dist. (80 kms north of Lucknow) killed their four year old daughter Kanni in a *pūjā* in

of human teeth and flesh to *vetāla* in corpse 99,13f. (TP VII 123); human ~ to the sea to prevent shipwreck 101,183f. (TP VII 147); human ~ for Bhagavatī sought by Pulindas in forest 101,283f. (TP VII 153); ~ of ministers to Devī by Pulindas 101,297 (TP VII 155); ~ of wine and meat (*madya-piśita*) to *yakṣas* 105,57 (TP VIII 25); ~ of water to dead parents 111,88 (TP VIII 103); ~ impeded by *Asuras* 118,50 (TP VIII 181); ~ by brahmins satiates deities (*brāhmaṇair hutam agnau havis tṛptyai devâukasām*) 120,21 (TP IX 3); – see also: penance; Śivi

sadana, see: dwelling

ṣāḍ-guṇya ‘group of six acts or measures of royal policy’ 54,31 (TP IV 186)

sādhu sādhu ‘bravo, bravo’ 108,113 (TP VIII 62)

sad-yoginī [not MW] ‘good witch’ 48,122 (TP IV 82)

-*sāgara* in the sense of a collective suffix, see: *Kathā-sarit-°*; *sattva-°*; *śoka-°*

*sa-guḍa*¹²⁷⁷ ‘with molasses, sugared’ 2,56 (TP I 13)

sāhasa-bhūmi (not MW) ‘benchmark of violence, etc.’ 124,102 (TP IX 75);

śailāstra, see: (rock-)weapon

Śaiva-gaṇas in Vārāṇasī 114,19 (TP VIII 133)

Śākala town in Madra country 44,17 (TP IV 2)

śākāśin (not MW) ‘eating vegetables, vegetarian’, said of a *muni* 5,133 (TP I 58 where note 2 is wrong)

śāka-vāṭikā (‘vegetable-garden’) 72,206 (TP VI 83)

śākhā, ¹branch; ²technical term of dance¹²⁷⁸ 100,18 (TP VII 129)

sakhī (‘female friend, confidante’) as helper in many private situations such as go-between, etc.

31,1 (TP III 81)¹²⁷⁹; man invited by ~ 77,53 (TP VI 187); – see also: confidante

sakhī-bhartr ‘friend’s husband’ ought never to be seen (by a woman) 29,66 (TP III 43)

sakhyād (D w.r. for B *saṃkhyād* ?), see: *sākṣyād*

śākinī ‘female demon attendant on Durgā’, witch 37,170 (TP III 195)¹²⁸⁰; *daivāt* (brahmin) wife becomes ~ 68,37 (TP VI 4; ORC 788: “*elle avait obtenu les pouvoirs magiques d’une sorcière*”); 71,269 (TP VI 55)

Śakra looking angrily 45,388 (TP IV 43); ~ refers *deva-putra* to Śiva to prevent his rebirth as a pig 53,122f. (TP IV 176); ~ promises king Merudhvaja son who is a portion of Śiva (*Śivâṃśa*) 118,21 (TP VIII 179); ~ curses the *apsaras* Kalāvati to become mortal 121,119 and 122 (TP IX 20);

sākṣād, anyaiḥ ~ *ahanyata* “others smote them in open fight” 121,257 (TP IX 31 with

order to obtain wealth; in Yadgir (North Karnataka) villagers saved a thirteen year old boy from being sacrificed by his family to Yellamma (do of Nov. 13, 2010), but a two year old boy in Bhilai (Chattisgarh) was less fortunate (do of Nov. 25th).

¹²⁷⁷ Also Mṛcchak. 8,13 in Karmarkar’s ed. (Poona, 1950).

¹²⁷⁸ Sundaram 1979: 751f.

¹²⁷⁹ See Baldissera 2004: 91.

¹²⁸⁰ Also: Daś 234.5.

- note)¹²⁸¹; – see also: appearance; attributes; visibility
- śakti*, king smiting enemy with ~ (*āhatya śaktyā*) 54,223 (TP IV 199 ‘iron spear’¹²⁸²; ORC 607: ‘*coup d’épée*’; M I 851: “*verletzte seinen Gegner an der Stirn mit drei Geschossen*” [?])
- śakti-hasta* ‘spear-handed; name of Skanda’ 7,6 (TP I 74)
- saktu-bhāṇḍa* (not MW) (‘barley-meal bin’) 71,268ff. (TP VI 55);
- śakuna* ‘omen’, *Asuras* ignore ~ 118,72 (TP VIII 183)¹²⁸³
- śakuna-devatā* (‘deity presiding over omen’) laughs at foolish traveller who welcomes bad omen 124,109 (TP IX 76)
- śākūtaṃ*, see Disposer; gestures
- sāla* for *śāla* tree (*Vatica robusta* [MW])¹²⁸⁴, *Piśāca* in stature like ~ 2,5 (TP I 9)
- sāla-bhañjikā*,¹²⁸⁵ Indra curses *apsaras* to become ~ on a temple-pillar in Nāgapura for bringing mortal husband in ear-lotus to heaven 121,145 (TP IX 22); ~ weeps when seeing husband 121,175 (TP IX 24);
- sale, of boys, see: child (113,81 (TP VIII 130); human trafficking; ~ of human flesh (q.v.); ~ of wife for horses 43,86ff. (TP III 287)
- saliva, see: kite
- śālmali* (‘red silk cotton tree, *Bombax Malabaricum*’),¹²⁸⁶ crow living in ~ 61,58 (TP V 73); image of Gaṇeśa carved in ~ 71,59 (TP VI 40); ~ hollow as dark hiding place feared and avoided by princess’s accomplice 71,163 (TP VI 47);
- salt, fool eats ~ (*lavāna*) 61,42 (TP V 72); miserly Ṭakka couple eat barley-meal without ~ 65,141 (TP V 165)¹²⁸⁷; ouch, who has rubbed ~ into my wounds ? (proverb used by impaled man hit by woman at night: *āḥ, kṣate kṣāram etan me kṣiptaṃ kena ?*) 93,14 (TP VII 79)
- salutation¹²⁸⁸ implies asking after health (*kuśala*) 102,68 (TP VII 167); 102,133 (TP VII 172); 103,177 (TP VII 187); 110,95 (VIII 89)
- salvation,¹²⁸⁹ see: *siddhi*

¹²⁸¹ TP read with B *saṃkhyād* which they think ought to be *sākṣād* and appear to translate the latter. ORC 1278: “*L’armée ennemie fut battue ... par nos soldats en collaboration avec les autres*” (derivation not explained); M II 705 unclear.

¹²⁸² See Whitaker 2000 : 108 note 18.

¹²⁸³ See also Chojnacki 2008 (I) 360 s.v. *présage*.

¹²⁸⁴ Kuv note 195 *shorea robusta*, a big tree with hard, termite resistant wood, evergreen leaves and yellow flowers.

¹²⁸⁵ Cf. 123,133 *stamba-stha-putrikā*. For the woman and tree motif see Pisharoti 1935 with illustrations.

¹²⁸⁶ This ugly and thorny tree, the seat of *Garuḍa*, can become as tall as 40 meters and has red flowers and cotton-wool filled fruits; its fast-growing, weak wood can be worked easily, but is not very durable. Because of the thorns it features in hells where inhabitants have to embrace it, see Syed 1990: 540ff. with various depictions in literature such as Kād. 50,7ff. (46,8ff. in Kale’s ed. 2005); Macmillan 1991: 467f.

¹²⁸⁷ Cf. Jones 1912: 371.

¹²⁸⁸ Hopkins 1930-32.

¹²⁸⁹ STh *V 520ff.

salvation from sea, see: ship-wrecked man

sāman, see: negotiation

sāmanta, see: feudal chief

samarāṇava ‘sea of war’ (not MW) swelled high 115,28 (TP VIII 146)

samāśvasya (not MW) ‘having encouraged’ 25,101 (TP II 197)

Sāmaveda¹²⁹⁰ chanters in city of Supraṭiṣṭhita 6,25 (TP I 62); ~ chanted on pipe made by the hands 6,57 (TP I 64); ~ chanters are home of timidity, boorishness and ill temper (*bhaya-kārkaśya-kopānām grhaṇi*) 18,108 (TP II 57)¹²⁹¹;

*samaya*¹²⁹² ‘agreement’ between king and Pāśupata to enter opening in the earth and get sword 56,216 (TP IV 235); ~ ‘rule, law’ of celestials is to return to their own place at the end of a curse 86,144 (TP VII 23)

sambandhin ‘being a marriage connection’ 15,25 (TP II 3); see: *mariage de raison*

śambara, see: women 37,170 (TP III 195)

śambūka, see: snail

Śambhu = Śiva¹²⁹³ gives boon of knowledge (*vidyāḥ*) 7,55 (TP I 79); six days of meditation on ~ save *devaputra* from rebirth as a pig 53,125 (TP IV 176); may third eye of ~ protect you ! 57,2 (TP V 1); ~ gives boon of birth as *Gandharva* 74,27f. (TP VI 142); ~ protects Ujjain against *vetālas* 102,20 (TP VII 162); ~ propitiated with penance gives boon 115,86 (TP VIII 150); harem maid (*antaḥpura-ceṭikā*) shows king fruit ~ gave queen in dream 120,42 (TP IX 4);

saṃdhi-vigraha-kāyastha ‘secretary of Foreign Affairs’ 42,91 (TP III 265)

saṃdhyāgni-hotra-mantra ‘words spoken at evening oblation to Agni’: I am a “*yakṣa*” 20,36 (TP II 27)

saṃdhyā-prekṣaṇaka (not MW) ‘evening spectacle’ in temple 123,129 (TP IX 52)

saṃgīta, see: concert

Samgrāma, king of Kashmir of Sātavāhana race¹²⁹⁴ E 1 (TP IX 87)

saṃgrāma-kāla (not MW), see: destruction, demon of ~

saṃhṛta-viśva-kaṇṭaka ‘having destroyed all enemies’ 116,91 (TP VIII 163 ‘... the plague of the universe’; ORC 1217: “*qui avait repoussé les ennemies de l’univers*”; M II 619: “*nach seinem Sieg über den Stachel und Feind der ganzen Welt*”)

śamī (*Prosopis spicigera* Lin. = *cineraria*)¹²⁹⁵ at the windows of a lying-in-chamber (protects against the evil eye)¹²⁹⁶ 23,61 (TP II 161)

¹²⁹⁰ The most important Veda in Bhag X 22.

¹²⁹¹ Bollée 2010a : 154 note 180.

¹²⁹² Cf. Mette 1991.

¹²⁹³ In Kālidāsa the name Śambhu stresses the erotic side of Śiva’s character (Jackmuth 2002: 46).

¹²⁹⁴ Rājāt VI 368. Samgrāma reigned from 1003-1028.

¹²⁹⁵ TP: *Mimosa suma*. Macmillan 1991: 521; Syed 1990: 524ff. with quotation of KauśikaS 35,8 expressing the necessity of *śamī* wood at the *punī-savana* in order to obtain a son.

saṃkhyā-jñāna (not MW) ‘knowledge of reckoning, calculation’ = *akṣa-jñāna*, king Ṛtupaṇṇa wants to trade his ~ for Nala’s skill in chariot-driving 56,378-381 (TP IV 247f. ‘skill in numbers’; ORC 643: “*habileté au jeu*”; MI 904: “*die Kunst des Würfelspiels*”)

saṃlekhanā, see death, by starvation

sampling in advance, merchant ~ prince’s food 28,118 (TP III 29); – see also: dog; plate

saṃrāj ‘universal emperor’ 73,329 (TP VI 124); 122,5 (TP IX 34);

sāmrājya ‘realm’, Śiva says to Sūryaprabha: “you will obtain the realm of all the sky-goers four times as large (as your present one ?)” (*prāptavyam ... tvayā hītaś catur-guṇam ~ṃ ... a-śeṣāṇāṃ dyu-cāriṇām*) 50,100 (TP IV 114: “you are destined to receive the fourfold sovereignty of all the sky-goers”; ORC 538: “*tu obtiendras un royaume quatre fois plus grand, celui de tous les êtres célestes ...*”; MI 753: “*die vierfache Oberherrschaft*”)¹²⁹⁷

sāmrājya-śrī ‘imperial dignity’ obtained by generosity (*dāna-prabhāva*) 113,92 (TP VIII 130)

saṃsāra as Buddhist notion 72,314 (TP VI 92); ~ is a *Gandharva-nagara* 97,13 (TP VII 113); see also *bhavāmbudhi*

*saṃsāra-cakra*¹²⁹⁸ ‘wheel of mundane existence’, Māyā causes ~ to revolve 70,107 (TP VI 31)

saṃskāra ‘works in a former birth’, great souls easily attain the supreme goal gained in pre-births its accomplishment being effected by abundant ~ (*a-kleśa-labhyā bhavanti uttamāthā mahātmānām janmāntarārjitāḥ sphāra-saṃskārākṣipta-siddhayaḥ*) 7,19 (TP I 75 n. 3; “the highest matters are easily acquired by great-souled ones, having been learnt in a former birth, the real truth of them being recalled by their powerful memories”; ORC 45: “*pour les magnanimes, il n’y a aucune difficulté à apprendre les sujets les plus relevés, qu’ils ont appris dans une existence antérieure et qu’ils savent saisir par l’ampleur de leur mémoire*”); king performs ‘obsequies’ (ORC 168: “*la toilette rituelle*”) for his dead daughter 52,167 (TP IV 149)

samudraka (not MW) ‘box’ (with jewel given by mendicant to king) 38,47 (TP III 209)

saṃvid, see: conspiracy

sand, Indra as brahmin throws ~ into Ganges to show *tapas* as useless to obtain knowledge 40,16 (TP III 241); what wise man looks for love in courtesans or for oil in ~ 57,128 (TP V 10); pot of ~ (*sikatā-pātra*) given to brahmin instead of food 72,87 (TP VI 75); ~ (*pāṃsavas*) as bed for gambling victim 73,77 (TP VI 106);

sandal-powder, see: body

sandal tree (*candana-pādapa*; *Santalum album*)¹²⁹⁹, *haṃsī* makes nest in ~ and has male offspring 43,154f. (TP III 291); ~ one of the jewels of an emperor, addresses the latter with

¹²⁹⁶ Thus ORC 1639. Abbott 1974: 316 only says that *bhūts* haunt trees such as the *śamī* and this would keep them from the new-born child, but (p. 319) “the power of trees enables many evils besides that of the evil eye to be transferred to them in the distress of man.” The *Śamī* tree, *Prosopis spicigera*, is called auspicious in Gonda 1985: 39.

¹²⁹⁷ No translation is explained.

¹²⁹⁸ Zin & Schlingloff 1998.

¹²⁹⁹ See, e.g. en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sandalwood.

bodiless voice (*girā ... a-śarīrayā*) 108,198 and 205 (TP VIII 68), cf. 109,23 (TP VIII 71);
 sandal-water removes faint 69,10 (TP VI 9; see also note in TP VII 105f.); 85,29 (TP VII 11); 95,48 (TP VIII 101);
 sandalwood (*śrikhaṇḍa*),¹³⁰⁰ body (*aṅka*) of lover is cool as ~ for a woman 31,23 (TP III 83 'bosom' for 'body'); does ~ profit a shivering man (*kiṃ candanena*¹³⁰¹ *śītāloh*)? 66,35 (TP V 180: "What does the cold moon ..."; ORC 768: "A-t-on besoin de santal quand on a froid?"; MI 1082: "Was nützt der Mond dem Frierenden?")¹³⁰²; ~ as lady's perfume 82,33 (TP VI 219); moon comforts man with rays cool as ~ (*candana*) 87,15 (TP VII 30); contact with brahmin's body makes princess feel as if anointed with ~ 89,44 (TP VII 43); lovesick princess treated with ~ 90,62 (TP VII 53); coldness (*jādyā*) found only in pearls, ~ juice and the moon 92,12 (TP VII 72); ladies are white with ~ paste in the hot season 95,17 (TP VII 99 with note on p. 105ff.); 117,108 (TP VIII 171)
 sandbank in mid-ocean with two beauties 120,105 (TP IX 8f.)
saṇḍha 'eunuch', in letter to father princess complains of having been given to ~ 56,87 (TP IV 226)
sandhyâgñihotra 'evening oblation to Agni' 20,34 (TP II 97)
ṣaḍ-guṇya 'six measures of royal foreign policy' 54,31 (TP IV 186 with note 3)
sa-nīraṅgī '(woman) wearing a veil' 71,167 (TP VI 48 "fair-hued maid"¹³⁰³; ORC 820 "*elle portait une voile*"; M II 64 unclear)
 Śaṅkara (Śiva), propitiated, gives son 65,216 (TP V 171); do, 67,37 (TP V 198); ~, in heaven destroys robber's offences (*kilbiṣa*) 72,359 (TP VI 95); expelled prince propitiates ~ 74,26 (see further: Śambhu; TP VI 142); ~ gives information 107,67 (TP VIII 47); emperor Naravāhanadatta has seen the giver of boons 110,56 (TP VIII 86) and beheld ~ face to face (*sākṣāt-kṛtya*) 110,96 (TP VIII 89)
 Sāṅkhya and Yoga doctrines recited by Maya in Pātāla temple 45,79 (TP IV 22);
saṅkhyād, see: *sakhyād*
 **santra*, *sattra* 'house' 122,63 (TP IX 38 'relief-house'; ORC 1283: "*réfectoire*"); – for compounds see: almshouse
śapatha, see: oath
śaphara 'large fish',¹³⁰⁴ swallows ship 123,110 (TP IX 51); – see also: fish; Potiphar motif
saptacchada, see: ichor
śarabha,¹³⁰⁵ fallen bodies of ~s show like fruit (of creepers) 42,5 (TP III 259; ORC 423: "*les*

¹³⁰⁰ See McHugh 2012: 182ff.; Kuv notes 126 and 201; Macmillan 1991: 261 (up to 20 m high tree); Gode 1961: 314-46.

¹³⁰¹ Thus D; B reads *śaśaṅkena* which lecture is adopted by TP and Mehlig.

¹³⁰² McHugh 2012: 207f.

¹³⁰³ TP follow the reading of B: *upayeme sa gaurāṅgīm*.

¹³⁰⁴ In the dictionaries wrongly given as either a small fish or a carp.

¹³⁰⁵ See Bollée 2008: 99 note 427; Hensgen 1958: 35 (p.c. Esposito).

corps affaissés des cerfs en étaient les fruits”); king strips mountainlike ~s of their wings 94,11 (TP VII 88);

Śaraṇyā (Durgā), see: meditation

saras ‘lake’, one of the seven imperial jewels of the *vidyādhara*s 109,23 (TP VIII 71)

Sarasvatī (river > goddess) appears in dream in white garments¹³⁰⁶ 4,9 (TP I 31); ~ dwells in Vararuci’s frame 4,11 (TP I 31); minister dreams of ~ visible in white garments entering mouth of king¹³⁰⁷ 6,139 (TP I 71) and 7,9 (TP I 74); man, blind through grief for the loss of his parents, abandoned his body in the ~ (~-*pūre*) 21,111 (TP II 133 “abandoned the body in fire purified by the goddess S.”¹³⁰⁸; ORC 182 “*aux flots de la Sarasvatī*”; MI 260: “*in den Fluten des Flusses S.*”); ~ with Skanda and Jina as one of three happy beings 51,205 (TP IV 136)¹³⁰⁹; as patron goddess of music ~ gives king making music with his ladies long applause from heaven (~ *tasya dadau priyābhiś cira*¹³¹⁰-*saṁstavaṁ varam*) 54,241 (TP IV 201 “gave him and his beloved ones high commendation”)¹³¹¹; brahmin wife distinguished for modesty (*vinayōjjvalā*) and a third beside ~ and Lakṣmī 56,5 (TP IV 220); on 13th day of white fortnight four ladies visit temple of ~ as protecting deity of Pāṭaliputra 66,30 (TP V 180); Śrī and ~ frequent Kaśmīra as if vying with each other for pre-eminence there 73,81 (TP VI 106); ~ taking form as speech 104,3 (TP VIII 1)¹³¹²; in Śobhāvātī in Kaliṅga, Lakṣmī and ~ (fortune and learning) gave up their enmity (*mukta-vairayoḥ*) 104,23 (TP VIII 2); ~ is wife (and daughter)¹³¹³ of Brahmā 106,24 (TP VIII 29); – see also: Śrī *śārikā* ‘hen-maina’ owned by queen 77,8 (TP VI 183);

śarīra-mūla (not MW) ‘based in a body > person’, of king 42,45 (TP III 262)

Śārṅgin (Viṣṇu), Ayodhyā, capital of ~ incarnate as Rāma 88,3 (TP VII 35)

sarpa-sattra ‘snake sacrifice’ by Janamejaya¹³¹⁴ 30,41 (TP III 66)

Śarva (Śiva) worshipped by *vidyādhara* princess 86,132 (TP VII 22);

Śarvāṇī Devī (Durgā) bestows rank of *Vidyādhara* king on brahmin hero 26,251 (TP II 236);

sarva-sattvārtha ‘the good of the community, public interest’, seven-years-old brahmin boy sought who will offer himself for ~ to a *brahma-rākṣasa* 94,92 (TP VII 93)

¹³⁰⁶ Cf. Mani 1975: 696 under 7), Kinsley 1986: 55ff.

¹³⁰⁷ Cf. BrahmāṇḍaPur 43 < Mani 1975: 695: “Brahmā ordained that Sarasvatī should stay on the tip of everyone’s tongue.”

¹³⁰⁸ Reading with B *śokenāgnau* instead of D *śokenāndho*.

¹³⁰⁹ See ORC 1421 with note on 557. The mention of Sarasvatī here is unclear. The story of Sarasvatī’s warding off Brahmā’s advances as given by Mani 1975: 696 from MatsyaPur (no ref.) could not be verified.

¹³¹⁰ Thus D for B *saha* which latter lecture Mehlig seems to follow; his rendering is free.

¹³¹¹ ORC 608: “*lui permit de vivre longtemps dans la plus grande harmonie avec ses chères épouses*”. This rendering is also grammatically correct but for Somadeva Sarasvatī is the patron of music, not of familial harmony.

¹³¹² Cf. *flux de paroles* Bollée 2012: 95.

¹³¹³ For the Monists, the couple represents consciousness and matter, the duality of parenthood principle without which no creation can take place (Balsekar 1990: 66).

¹³¹⁴ Vogel 1926: 69ff.

śāsana, see: grant

śaṣpa-kavala (not MW) ‘mouthful of grass’, aged deer reject ~ 102,52 (TP VII 166)

sāśra ‘mango’ ? 71,216 (TP VI 51); – see also supra: mango

Śāstras in bodily form come to see battle 47,47 (TP IV 70)

sāsūyaṃ ‘scornfully’, *apsaras* Rambhā speaks ~ to laughing mortal 17,21 (TP II 35

“sarcastically”; ORC 121: “*courroucée*”; M I 172: “*recht ungehalten*”)

śata-padī, see: centipede

ṣaṭ-caraṇāyate ‘to act like a bee’ 54,33 (TP IV 186 with note 4)

ṣaṭha ‘fool, blockhead’ as term of abuse used by lion for hare 60,99 (TP V 50: ‘scoundrel’;

ORC 683: “*coquin*”)

*satī*¹³¹⁵ of wife after execution of minister-husband 5,100 (TP I 54); ~ of Śātānīka’s queen

9,17 (TP I 95); ~ of brahmin wife on husband’s pyre 27,165 (TP III 13); ~ of merchant

daughter / queen 33,73 (TP III 112); ~ of ex-*yakṣiṇī* 34,89 (TP III 135); brahmin ~ after

husband’s death 49,160 (TP IV 96 with note); ~ of queen Śāśilekhā 58,38 (TP V 17); ~ of

unfaithful, yet firmly resolved, merchant wife though her attendants tried to dissuade her

58,65 (TP V 19);

satī-dhura ‘female virtue’, see: Arundhatī

satī-tejas (not MW; ‘wifely fidelity’) 56,326 (TP IV 243)

sat-kāra, see: hospitality

sattva-sāgara (not MW) ‘sea of valour’ 58,115 (TP V 23)

sattva-taru (not MW) ‘tree of valour’, princess expecting husband like ~ 18,368 (TP II 77);

Agni brings king golden bilva fruit as fruit of his ~ 35,69 (TP III 160)

satya, see: truth

satyābhibhaṣin (not MW) see: rhetoric

satyân-ṛta ‘half truth half falsehood’ as brahmin’s answer 104,208 (TP VIII 16);

saudha-hāsin (not MW), see: palace

saugata-mata ‘buddhist Dharma’ rich in the merit of benefiting the creatures 72,98 (TP VI

76);

saunika-bhāryā, see: butcher’s wife

saurabha, see: fragrance

Śaurī = Viṣṇu, ex-*Asura* Maya flees to ~ for protection 29,12 (TP III 40 where Ś. is wrongly

rendered by Śīva); princess worships Śaurī-Viṣṇu to get husband 71,201 (TP VI 50); hymn

to ~ 106,11 (TP VIII 28);

Śavara, see: Śabara

śava-rakta ‘blood of corpses’ 73,153 (TP VI 112);

sa-vigraha, see: attributes

Sāvitrī, *vidyādhari* queen with rosary and skin of black antelope like an incarnation of ~ 107,63f.

(TP VIII 47)

saw (*krakaca*), gambler threatens images of Mātaras, etc. with ~ with points sharp as Yama’s

¹³¹⁵ Hansen 1992: 15ff.

eye teeth 121,86 (TP IX 18);
 sayings:¹³¹⁶ how can the ungrateful prosper ? (*kṛta-ghnānām śivaṃ kutaḥ*) 3,44 (TP I 22); to
 the wise character is wealth (*śīlaṃ hi viduṣāṃ dhanam*) 5,98 (TP I 54); all things are
 unstable (*sarvam ... cañcalam*) 5,126 (TP I 58); fancies of women are ever inconstant
 (*strīṇām cañcalās citta-vṛttayaḥ*) 7,57 (TP I 79); youth is twin brother to mirth (*narmāika-
 sôdara*) 12,56 (TP I 137); the timid are ever unreflecting (*nirvimarśā hi bhīravah*) 15,39
 (TP II 4); the words of wise men must be done/followed (*kartavyam hi satām vacaḥ*)
 15,111 (TP II 11 “ the mind of good men is ever fixed upon duty”; ORC 111: “*ne faut-il pas
 suivre les avis des gens de bien ?*”); the principal element of sound statecraft is averting of
 misfortune (*mukhyam aṅgaṃ hi mantrasya vinipāta-pratikriyā*) 15,113 (TP II 11); jealousy
 is seed of calamities (*strī-vairam ... bijam āpadām*) 15,134 (TP II 13); to whom is not the
 attractive object called woman the cause of misfortune ? (*strī-nāma viṣayo nidānam kasya
 nāpadām ?*) 15,141 (TP II 14); humility is unfailing characteristic of good women (*vinayo
 hi satī-vratam*) 17,56 (TP II 38); avoiding society of a wife (who is like the goddess of death
 incarnated) is a vow as difficult as standing on sword’s edge 17,91 (TP II 41); honouring
 gods and brahmins is considered wishing-cow of the good 17,134 (TP II 45); the mind of
 kings runs towards unlawful objects (*a-viṣaye*) 17,138 (TP II 45); excellent horses are
 divine beings (*daivatam hi hayôttamaḥ*) 18,100 (TP II 57); men of firm mind rightly treat
 with contempt men of little soul (*alpa-bhāveṣu dhīrāṇām avajñāiva hi śobhate*) 18,131 (TP
 II 59); a situation without ruler, so that prosperity merely depends on fate, is better than one
 with many discordant rulers (*varam hi daivâyattâika-vṛddhi-sthānam a-nāyakam*) 18,136
 (TP II 60); courage merits command 18,140 (TP II 60); the course of fate cannot be barred
 18,267 (TP II 70); ungrateful men blinded by desire of gain cannot see a benefit 18,308 (TP
 II 72); if courage fails, even a small calamity cannot be overcome 18,309 (TP II 73); even
 destiny takes the part of men of distinguished valour 18,311 (TP II 73); who that has tasted
 heavenly joys can take pleasures in any other ? 18,346 (TP II 75); what will not women do
 when mastered by affection ? 18,381 (TP II 78); for a proud man death is preferable to ex-
 hibiting poverty to relatives 19,22 (TP II 86); how can man, deprived of wealth, ... hope to
 retain a woman’s affections (*strīṣu kā kathā*) ? Women have fickleness implanted in their
 nature like flashes of lightning (*nisarga-niyatam vāsām vidyutām iva cāpalam*) 19,28 (TP II
 86); wealth is the root of the tree of empire (*mūlam rājya-taror dhanam*) 19,51 (TP II 88);
 fates protect one who is destined to be prosperous 20,19 (TP II 96); of resolute men, perse-
 verance is increased by misfortune 20,31 (TP II 97); who does good will obtain good 20,35
 and 212 (TP II 97 and 114); without worshipping Gaṇeśa there is no success in this world
 20,58 (TP II 100) and 100 (TP II 103); Smara-Kāma makes ugly people his laughing-
 stocks 20,119 (TP II 105); terrible is compliance with women (*dhig aho kaṣṭhām strīṣv
 anurodhitām*) 20,197 (TP II 112); a ball thrown against a wall rebounds frequently 20,213
 (TP II 115); how can a female crow leave the male crow to take pleasure in a koel ? 21,80
 (TP II 131); hearts of women are as hard as adamant in daring transgression, but soft as a

¹³¹⁶ Sternbach 1990.

flower when they are afraid 21,97 (TP II 132); fortune of kings (*rāja-śrī*) is ever bounding away like a doe 21,99 (TP II 132f.); terrible is the spite of women against each other (*kaṣṭā hi strīṇām anyā-sahiṣṇutā*) 22,184 (TP II 151); what other fruit but ridicule can there be for the over-greedy ? 22,200 (TP II 152); the destruction of a pearl (*muktā-maṇi*) for the sake of a piece of glass is never becoming 22,216 (TP II 153); men of resolution never leave unfinished an undertaking they have begun 22,234 (TP II 154); those who follow evil courses easily contract guilt 22,239 (TP II 155); a bribe (*upapradāna*) is the main specific for attracting the covetous 24,119 (TP II 178); greed causes many calamities 24,198 (TP II 183); meeting a relative in a foreign land is like a fountain in the desert 25,70 (TP II 195); to have mercy on the wretched is a natural quality (*nisarga*) of the great 25,116 (TP II 200); who can calculate the caprices (*vilāsa*) of fate or the waves of the sea ? 26,18 (TP II 218); who can resist the awful goddess of destiny (*bhagavatī ... bhavitavyatā*), who ever places her foot on the head of all men 26,24 (TP II 218); men are generally inclined to do that which is forbidden 26,76 (TP II 222); who knows what is the nature of destiny ? 26,90 (TP II 224); great-hearted feel pity even for their enemies when they are terrified 26,248 (TP II 235); religion is not confined to one form (*eka-rūpatā*); a transcendent (*lokōttarah ... sārva-laukikah*) religion differs from one that embraces the whole world 27,21 (TP III 3); tree of good deeds produces glorious fruit to the righteous 27,99 (TP III 8); good fortune is the result of virtue (*bhavanti bhadraṇi dharmād*) 27,106 (TP III 8); prosperity follows on courage (*sattvam anudhāvanti sampadaḥ*) 27,134 (TP III 11); what boy does not become self-willed if not kept in order by some superior ? 27,166 (TP III 13); a passionate woman like a female snake will never neglect vengeance 27,187 (TP III 15); the heart of creatures recognises friendships formed in a pre-birth 27,190 (TP III 15); a son, being embodied joy, is far superior to a daughter, that is but a lump of grief 28,6 (TP III 18); giving wealth (*artha-pradāna*) in this world is great asceticism 28,9 (TP III 18); only the good of others (*para-hita*) in the *saṃsāra* is said to be real 28,16 (TP III 19); love is more charming than one's native country (*ramyaṃ prema, na janma-bhūh*) 28,64 (TP III 25); intimacy in a pre-birth quickly knits friendship 28,117 (TP III 29); children of kings slay their guides and disregard benefits, like infuriated elephants 28,152 (TP III 32); when cracks appear, misfortunes multiply (*yac chidreṣv an-arthā yānti bhūritām*) 28,181 (TP III 35); (a woman) ought never see a friend's husband (*sakhī-bhartā*) 29,67 (TP III 43); a bride in the power of a treacherous mother-in-law is in difficult position (*kaṣṭā sthiti*) 29,74 (TP III 44); who is not deceived by the hypocritically affectionate speeches of a mother ? 29,82 (TP III 45); a husband is the only refuge of virtuous women in this world and the next 29,98 (TP III 46); the soul can distinguish friends from enemies (*vetty ātmāiva hitāhitam*) 29,163 (TP III 52); a frog is unable of relishing fibres of red lotuses 30,78 (TP III 69); Fate watches to ensure the objects of auspicious persons, as good servants of their masters, when the latter are not on the look-out 30,91 (TP III 70); the wise are tested in difficulty, even as heroes are tested in fight 31,93 (TP III 89); celestials when asleep assume their own form 32,28 (TP III 92); any business undertaken without first counteracting evil omen (*a-vyapohyānimittam*) will end in calamity 32,41 (TP III 93); giving advice to a fool is like beautifying ordure (*saṃskāro*

'*vaskarasyêva tiraskara-karo*) 32,54 (TP III 94); a single wise man fallen among many fools is like a lotus in the path of the waves 32,55 (TP III 55); the forest is like straw (*ṛṇa*) to a sylvan fire fanned by the wind 32,152 (TP III 102); even clever women are deceived by the tales of an impostor 32,166 (TP III 103); kings are the appointed prey of rogues (*dhūrtair bhojyā batêśvarāḥ*) 32,189 (TP III 106); men, bewildered by the speeches of wicked women, do not know the difference between truth and falsehood 33,42 (TP III 110); man who is free from anger has gained heaven 33,51 (TP III 110); your love is my life, even as the water is of the lotus 33,88 (TP III 113); the upright come to love even their enemies in their neighbourhood 33,122 (TP III 117); circumstances sometimes make an enemy a friend, but not for ever 33,128 (TP III 117); wisdom is in every exigency the best, not valour 33,132 (TP III 118); riches come and go like a cloud out of season 33,141 (TP III 119); intellect always obtains supremacy, triumphing over valour (*sarvadā buddheḥ prādhānyam jita-pauruṣam*) 33,158 (TP III 120); marriage is made by the gods 34,104 (TP III 136); seeing into one's lord's soul is the surest way of winning him (*hṛdayānupraveśo hi prabhoh saṁvānaṁ param*) 34,169 (TP III 140); a good servant is not admitted to an ignorant king as husbandman cannot get at a crop of rice enclosed with a palisade 34,203 (TP III 143); it is better to emerge in the world as an old tree or a stone than as a poor man given to the vice of generosity 35,36 (TP III 157); discernment and reflection are the main things in governing a kingdom 34,213 (TP III 144); in this world successes quickly befall those of fierce spirit (*tīvra-sattva*) 35,76 (TP III 161); who can restrain a furious river and a passionate woman ? 36,8 (TP III 169); royal dignity is an ever-exacting wife (*nitya-sniḡdhā hi rājatā*) 36,68 (TP III 174); where there are these five fires: feminine nature, intoxication, privacy, a man and the absence of restraint, what chance is there for the stubble of character (*śīla-ṛṇa*) ? 36,87 (TP III 175); can one fetter a whirlwind (*utpāta-vātāli*) with one's arms ? 36,93 (TP III 176); nothing in this world is difficult to the enterprising (*adhyavasāyinām*) 37,29 (TP III 185); females, like prosperous circumstances, are never faithful to anyone 37,142 (TP III 193); effort for a woman is like colocynth fruit 37,145 (TP III 193); when two are of one mind what more does secret love require ? 37,211 (TP III 198); even the Disposer cannot overstep destiny (*bhavitavyam hi dhātrāpi na śakyam ativartitum*) 37,236 (TP III 199), cf. 40,31 (TP III 242); success (*siddhayaḥ*) is easily obtained when the obstacles to it are swept away by the aid of a hero 38,55 (TP III 210); which true *kṣatriya* would wish to conquer in an unfair combat (*a-dharma-yuddha*) ? 38,133 (TP III 215); wonderful indeed are the results of our deeds in a pre-birth (*citrāiva gatiḥ prāktana-karmaṇām*) 39,159 (TP III 229); the only vengeance the great make use of against their enemies is compassion 39,229 (TP III 234); who can overstep the lot prescribed by destiny ? (*ko daiva-likhitam bhogaṁ laṅghyet ?*) 40,31 (TP III 242); everything depends upon the power of actions in a former life 40,41 (TP III 243); fools intent on objects of sense cannot endure reflection 40,51 (TP III 244); from his foetal state onward a man eats the fruit of the tree of his former actions (*ā garbhāj jantur aśnāti pūrva-karma-taroḥ phalam*) 40,109 (TP III 249: "from his birth"; ORC 418: "à partir de sa naissance", MI 583: "von Geburt an"); grief produced by the loss of dear relatives is hard to bear ! Why did not the Creator make men

exempt from old age and death ? 41,7 (TP III 252); lust of sovereign sway is cruel and overcomes one's affection for one's friends 41,40 (TP III 255); who, when blinded by passion, distinguishes between right and wrong ? (*ko hi mārḡam a-mārḡam vā vyasanāndho nirikṣate*) 43,29 (TP III 283); how can an evil deed done in spite of good advice bring pleasure to anyone ? 43,39 (TP III 283); good men derive satisfaction from breaking off their connection with the bad 43,128 (TP III 290); mortals who possess courage can obtain all powers (*mṛtyā hi sattvādhyāḥ sarva-siddhy-adhikāriṇaḥ*) 45,22 (TP IV 18); fire does not of itself burn so fiercely as when fanned by a breeze 46,12 (TP VI 49); of what avail is a candle in the face of the sun (*kaḥ pradīpo raveḥ puraḥ*) ? 46,114 (TP IV 56); terrible is the thirst of enjoyment carried away by which even gods do not shrink from infamous conduct 46,233 (TP IV 64); noble men do not turn their backs on a suppliant, but bestow on him even their lives 46,239 (TP IV 65); how can servants refuse the request of an importunate lord ? 49,16 (TP IV 86); a lovely woman, the rising of the moon, and the fifth note of a lute delight the happy but afflict the miserable 49,215 (TP IV 100); mud thrown at the heaven falls upon the head of the thrower 49,220 (TP IV 100); love for one's offspring (*suta-sneha*) is a feeling hard to lay aside 50,75 (TP IV 112); a man of reputation prefers the sorrow of separation to ill-repute 51,70 (TP IV 127); who can escape from the shadow of his own head, or the course of destiny ? 52,211 (TP IV 152); whom does not association with persons of virtuous conduct benefit ? 52,238 (TP IV 154); one who has conquered anger conquers this whole world 52,240 (TP IV 154); fickle is the mind of women 52,277 (TP IV 157); dispensations of destiny are irremediable 52,332 (TP IV 161); brave men do not submit to insult on account of a woman 52,360 (TP IV 163); after becoming queen of mortal king, *vidyādhari* roamed no more, but remained faithful to him, as rivers are at rest in the bosom of the sea 52,362 (TP IV 163); fortune of victory is fickle in fight (*jaya-śrīś capalā raṇe*) 52,375 (TP IV 164); fortune ever enriches a rich man (*pūrayati pūrṇam ... Lakṣmīḥ*), as all the streams replenish the sea, but she never even comes within the range of the eyes of the poor 53,32 (TP IV 170 "replenishes the full man"; ORC 584: "comme les rivières qui s'assemblent dans l'océan ... Fortune comble le comblé ..." MI 819: "Die Glücksgöttin labt immer nur den Satten, wie die Fluten der Flüsse stets das Meer anfüllen ..."); a wishing-tree, in the case of ill-starred men, often becomes a *palāśa* ('cruel') tree 53,35 (TP IV 170 with note); how can the attendance on a grateful king be void of fruit ? 53,79 (TP IV 173); the wise who aim at a goal do not discover themselves out of season (*kurvanti a-kāle 'bhivyaktim na kāryāpekṣiṇo budhāḥ*) 56,133 (TP IV 229); poverty makes men steal, and whoever gave up what he had found ? 57,19 (TP V 2); when men are cursed by destiny, even the wealth they obtain is lost 57,24 (TP V 2); the creator (*vedhas*) has made the courtesan to steal wealth and life of rich young men 57,57 (TP V 5); wealth gives us religion and love, consideration and renown 57,70 (TP V 6); treacherous games of a bawd are not to be fathomed even by Providence (*a-tarkyā kuṭṭāni-kūṭa-racanā hi vidher api*) 57,115 (TP V 9); which wise man looks for love in courtesans or for oil in sand ? 57,128 (TP V 10); the hearts of courtesans are fathomless 58,54 (TP V 18); often men blinded by affection (*snehāndha*) do not discover the wickedness of their wives 58,61 (TP V

19); women are like flies that leave camphor and haste to dirt 58,136 (TP V 24); water breaks a bridge, secret whisperings (*karṇe-japa*) friendship, counsel is ruined by garrulity 60,54 (TP V 45); prudence (*prajñā*) is power 60,91 (TP V 49); he is truly brave who does not become bewildered even in the time of calamity (*so dhīro, yo na saṃmoham āpat-kāle 'pi gacchati*) 60,96 (TP V 49); he who discards the advice of the good, but listens to the advice of the bad, soon falls into calamity 60,121 (TP V 51); people must follow good advice (*hitōpadeśa*), otherwise they will be ruined 60,167 (TP V 55); wealth obtained by oppression of subjects, friendship obtained by deceit, and a lady-love gained by violence, will not remain long 60,203 (TP V 58); to a virtuous man no country is foreign; a man who is content cannot be unhappy; for the man of endurance calamity does not exist; there is nothing impossible to the enterprising 61,121 (TP V 78); a wise man should guard his wife without showing jealousy (*īrṣyām a-prakāśya*) 61,168 (TP V 82); man must not reveal a secret to a woman 61,169 (TP V 82); subjection to bad women is pernicious 61,308 (TP V 95); who is not grieved when he has involved himself in a dangerous quarrel by a mere speech ? 62,59 (TP V 103); οἱ πολλοί prevail in this world (*bahavo hi jayantīha*) 62,61 (TP V 104); women would even eat dirt (*a-medhyaṃ*), if they had no noses 62,112 (TP V 108); every creature is such as he is made by the Creator 62,124 (TP V 109); goddess Śrī is ever treacherous as gambling, fickle as a wave, intoxicating as wine 62,164 (TP V 113); the indiscreet are always ruined 62,169 (TP V 113); a wise man desiring happiness should establish his mind in contentment, for dissatisfaction produces grief in both worlds 62,185 (TP V 115); will not a person possessed by a demon eat his own flesh ? 63,118 (TP V 129); the man who is poor in wealth lives, but the man who is poor in intellect (*dhī-daridra*) does not live 64,42 (TP V 142); women in a house are a snare ... so life in the forest is to be preferred 64,108 (TP V 148); women are like torrents flowing in a ravine, capricious, beautiful at a distance, prone to turbidness, as difficult to guard as such rivers are to drink 64,149 (TP V 150); if it is impossible to guard one's wife by enclosing her in one's own body, how can one keep her safe in a house ? 64,159 (TP V 151); woman's heart being full of hate, indiscriminating, prone to the base is difficult to fathom 65,42 (TP V 156); association with fools brings no prosperity to anyone 65,212 (TP V 171); this world is wavering as a wave of the sea, transient as a flash of lightning, and its beauty is short-lived like that of a religious festival. ... Only the virtuous person can be said truly to live. What is the use of giving to the rich ? What does the cold moon profit a shivering man, or what is the use of a cloud when winter has arrived ? 66,33ff. (TP V 180f.); kings, who know times and seasons, bend like canes, if it is expedient to do so (*bhajanti vaitasiṃ vṛttim rājānaḥ kāla-vedinaḥ*) 69,73 (TP VI 14); unenterprising kings perish like snakes arrested by a charm 71,104 (TP VI 43); who knows the mysterious ways of a woman's heart, any more than those of Destiny (*strī-cittasyēva daivasya ko veti gahanāṃ gatim*) 71,236 (TP VI 53); association with the great produces great profit 72,150 (TP VI 80); prosperity is the result of virtue (*dharma-mūlā hi sampadaḥ*) 72,156 (TP VI 80); who is able to alter prebirth actions ? 72,193 (TP VI 83); people obscured by the darkness of ignorance ... and not setting the lamp of sound treatises in front of them, surely stumble 72,216 (TP VI 84); females being, like the winds, very

changeable, and enveloped with a thick cloud of passion, defile those walking in the right path 72,256 (TP VI 87); seed of benefits (*su-kṛta-bīja*), sown in good soil, produces abundant fruit 73,322 (TP VI 124); destruction is ever impending over those whose minds are captivated by objects of sense 72,348 (TP VI 95); good advice given to a fool does not calm but enrages him 74,74 (TP VI 145); wind cannot do anything against a mountain (*vāto 'dret iva kiṃ kuryāt ?*) 74,105 (TP VI 147); what is the use of the greatness of great ones, if they do not stop the sufferings of their neighbour as soon as they hear of them ? 74,124 (TP VI 149); who can deprive the fire of its quality to burn ? (*dahanâmatā*) 74,160 (TP VI 152); the way of fate is inscrutable (*vidher a-cintyâiva gatih*) 74,205 (TP VI 155); jackal apes lion (*siṃhâyate srgālo*) 74,270 (TP VI 159); the spirit (*citta*) of heroes is a gem harder (*a-khaṇḍita*) than (lit.: unbreakable compared to) diamond 75,56 (TP VI 168); princes should never hesitate about following the advice of an excellent minister 75,159 (TP VI 175); are crows at fault when *haṃsas* eat rice ? 75,191 (TP VI 176); association with wicked people is root of tree of vice (*vyasana-vṛkṣasya mūlam durjana-saṃgatih*) 77,18 (TP VI 184); mind of women is terrible (*āśayaḥ strīṇāṃ bhīṣaṇaḥ*) 77,72 (TP VI 188); does the bee delight in a lotus on which another bee has settled ? 84,24 (TP VII 6); whatever seed of works a man has sown in a former life, of that he eats the fruit; for even fate cannot alter what has been done in a previous existence (song of a *divya-kanyakā*) 86,45 (TP VII 16); service to others (*parōpakāra*) is the only permanent thing in *saṃsāra* 90,20 (TP VII 50); does the fruit of the poison-tree of unrighteousness (*a-dharma-viṣa-vṛkṣa*) ever ripen sweet ? 90,179 (TP VII 61); how can great men leave off an enterprise they have begun, even though it be difficult ? 91,61 (TP VII 70); bad women (*ku-striyaḥ*) are a calamity to their family 95,81 (TP VII 103); wife fitting to husband as oblation to fire 96,5 (TP VII 108); Destiny performs everything 96,13 (TP VII 109); if Destiny is adverse, one cannot even die 96,22 (TP VII 109); riches pass away like autumn cloud (*arthānām śarad-bhra-calā gatih*) 96,24 (TP VII 109); a householder's home without wife is empty 98,31 (TP VII 118); what is the lotus-bed without the goose 101,107 (TP VII 141); it is the part of a brave man to display unbroken firmness in calamity, and freedom from arrogance in success, and never to abandon fortitude 101,37 (TP VII 136); who can decide the course of destiny difficult to know ? 101,196 (TP VII 148); even the gods cannot change the influence of karman 101,199 (TP VII 148); even in the most grievous hour of calamity (*āpat-kāle*) the wise do not give up their fortitude 101,272 (TP VII 153); effects of pre-birth actions are unavoidable (*kiṃ śakyam pūrva-karmāti vartitum ?*) 101,296 (TP VII 154); course of destiny is strange 101,298 (TP VII 155); those who have lost their wealth die daily, other than those who have lost their breath 101,342 (TP VII 157)¹³¹⁷; kings disregard love for offspring (*apatya-sneha*) altogether when the interests of their kingdoms are at stake 103,17 (TP VII 176); even Vāsuki¹³¹⁸ has no tongue able to describe the beauty of that prince

¹³¹⁷ This seems to be the Indian equivalent of the German proverb: *Lieber ein Ende mit Schrecken als ein Schrecken ohne Ende* 'rather a calamitous end than an endless calamity' (Messinger 2002: 951 s.v. *Schrecken*).

¹³¹⁸ The king of snakes with a thousand tongues.

103,22 (TP VII 176); war that involves a great waste of human life is worst of all political measures 103,30 (TP VII 177); only a steady (*a-viklava*) person reaches his desire 104,66 (TP VIII 5); propitious fate brings about unexpected results 104,194 (TP VIII 15); women do not endure wounding of affections (*praṇaya-khaṇḍana*) 105,31 (TP VIII 23); does not the moon when it is in a weak state, spend some time within the circle of the sun ? 106,41 (TP VIII 31 with note; ORC 1109: “*la lune ne retarde-t-elle pas son heure quand elle disparaît dans le disque du soleil ?*”; M II 475: “*Verschiebt nicht auch der Mond seine Zeit, wenn er in der Bahn der Sonne erschöpft und in seiner Kraft vermindert ist ?*”); destiny decides (*prabhu*) 106,57 (TP VIII 32); all actions of heavenly beings have important end in view (*saṃkalpâika-pradhāna*) 106,85 (TP VIII 34); even fate cannot comprehend the principle that makes men fall into happiness or misery 108,51 (TP VIII 57); even stones melt when fate is propitious 108,92 (TP VIII 61); pride goes before a fall (*pravartamāno hy utsekād a-sādhye paribhūyate*) 110,16 (TP VIII 83); fortunate are those who live to see their offspring elevate their race 110,100 (TP VIII 89); those who are exclusively devoted to the service of another do not care for their own family 111,39 (TP VIII 98); what is permanent in this transient world ? (*bhaṅgure ’smiṇ bhava kasya sthiraṭā ?*)¹³¹⁹ 111,58 (TP VIII 101); this versatile world, that perishes in a moment, is like the show of a juggler (*Indra-jālôpamāna*) 111,87 (TP VIII 103); how can a crow and a female royal *haṃsa* ever unite ? 112,96 (TP VIII 113); there are always disguised celestials on earth (*pracchannā divyāḥ sadā bhuvi*) 112,109 (TP VIII 114); destiny does not consider the feasibility of a union 112,114 (TP VIII 115); father is to maidens a divinity procuring all happiness 116,20 (TP VIII 157); for women of good family the husband is their god (*paramâtmā hi patiḥ kulâṅganānām*) 117,173 (TP VIII 176); there is nothing that austerities cannot accomplish 117,174 (TP VIII 176); promise given by king is kept (*devena pratipannaṃ cet satyaṃ, pālitaṃ eva tat*) 119,29 (TP VIII 195); unexpected meetings occur for men in this world (*a-sambhāvyaṃ nṛṇāṃ bhavantiha samāgamāḥ*) 120,8 (TP IX 1); a virtuous woman is invincible by strangers (*satī parâ-dhṛṣyā*) 120,10 (TP IX 2); recklessness and disregard of all ties are ingrained in the nature of gamblers 121,71 (TP IX 17); even gods fear wicked people (*durjanād devā apy ... bibhyati*) 121,95 (TP IX 18); – see also: sea schadenfreude, seeing king’s ~ minister dies of heart attack at night 86,162 (TP VII 24) science(s) (*vidyā*), ~ dispelling snake poison 10,95 (TP I 113); Kārttikeya gives brahmin knowledge of all ~s 2,60 (TP I 15); reciting *oṃ* brahmin obtains the Vedas with the six supplementary ~s 2,78 (TP I 17); acquiring ~ in the Deccan (*Dakṣiṇāpatha*) 6,22 (TP I 61); minister communicates all ~s to king and is rewarded 6,166 (TP I 72); 7,59 (TP I 79); *vidyādharī* gives up ~s (*siddhi*; *vidyāḥ*) at leaving with mortal husband for Ujjayinī 18,375-7 (TP II 78); ~ of the *vidyādharas* 25,260 (TP II 210) and 113,95 (TP VIII 131); ~ called *prajñapti* ‘foreknowledge’ 30,6 (TP III 64); Naravāhanadatta chosen master (*bhartṛ*; TP: “bridegroom”; ORC 344: “*māitre*”; M I 485: “*Brāutigam*”) of ~ 34,173 (TP III 140); political ~ (*nīti-tattva*) 34,211 (TP III 144); two ~s of flying up and

¹³¹⁹ Cf. 111,66 *ālokya cāsthiraṃ sarvaṃ*.

descending 37,201 (TP III 197); ~ consulted about missing husband 42,34 (TP III 261); maiden telling prince she is an incarnate (*rūpinī*) ~ called Māyāvātī 42,38f. (TP III 261); “bewildering ~” (*mohinī vidyā*)¹³²⁰ of king Caṇḍadaṇḍa¹³²¹ of the bamboo wood 46,110 (TP IV 56); ~s of bewildering and counteracting (*parivartinī*) known by Yājñavalkya 46,121 (TP IV 56); ~ producing food and drink 52,193 (TP IV 151); by adultery *vidyā dhari* looses ~ (*vidyā-bhraṣṭā*) of flying 52,209 (TP IV 152); *vidyādhara* princess obtains ~ from Gaurī 59,15 (TP V 27); ~s given by *yakṣa* to two brahmins 63,81 (TP V 125); king bestows knowledge of the ~s on only son 65,74 (TP V 160); princess well taught in all ~ 72,66 (TP VI 73); ~ of flying up into the air leaves *vidyādhari* 86,158 (TP VII 24); ~ which provides whatever one desires (*iṣṭa-saṃpādinī vidyā*) 92,35 to be taught under water 50 (TP VII 73f.); Pāsupata ascetic teaches his ~ to brahmin 92,59 (TP VII 75); ~ taught to unfit person is lost by teacher and pupil 92,56 (TP VII 75); four *vijñānas* to resuscitate animal 96,31ff. (TP VII 110); prince knowing principles of policy / diplomacy (*nīti-tattva-jñā*) 102,22 (TP VII 163); refused by brother, daughter obtains ~ with difficulty from father 105,67f. (TP VIII 25); person put in the protection (lit.: hand) of a ~ (*vidyā-hasta*) 105,89 (TP VIII 27); ~s must be restored¹³²² (*prasādhayitum*) 105,91 (TP VIII 27); ~ of recollection 106,141 (TP VIII 39); ~ of Gaurī 107,105 (TP VIII 50); visible (*rūpinī*) ~ comforting heroes 107,111 (TP VIII 50f.); Śiva appears in person to Naravāhanadatta and grants him the most transcendent ~ 107,129f. (TP VIII 52); ~ of Gaurī subject to Naravāhanadatta 107,132 (TP VIII 52); all ~s present themselves to a prince in visible form (*sa-vigraha*) and ask him for his orders 107,134 (TP VIII 52); visible ~ brings back ministers 108,13 (TP VIII 53); ~s destroyed by crossing Hara’s residence (*Harāspadasya ... laṅghana*) = Mt. Kailāsa 109,45 and 63 (TP VIII 73f.); by ~ king divides himself into many forms¹³²³ and sleeps with all queens 110,134 (TP VIII 92); ~ called *p.* (*vidyā prajñapti-nāma*) presents itself visibly and explains dream 111,52ff. (TP VIII 100); ~ of gods never false 114,13 (TP VIII 133); – see also: bilocality; magic power; *oṃ*

scorned women: teacher’s wife affects to be scorned 20,119ff. (TP II 105); 33,40 (TP III 109); scorned queen slanders virtuous brahmin 49,97 (TP IV 91); – see also: Potiphar motif

scratching of the earth, by royal horse 18,7 (TP II 49)¹³²⁴; ~ by bashful princess 90,80 (TP VII 54)¹³²⁵; – see also: drawing lines; *līlā-vajra*

scream (*nāda*) of witches on charnel ground at night 18,147 (TP II 60); by the shrill whistling of the loose bark (*tāra-cīra-cītkāra*) of the creepers of its parched body a forest appears to ~ (*rodinī*) 73,240 (TP VI 118); – see also: shriek

¹³²⁰ TP II 212 note: *mohani* ‘bewitching’.

¹³²¹ Thus D followed by ORC and M. TP: Chandradatta < B: Candradatta.

¹³²² As the science is *jyeṣṭhavy-atikramaṇa-durbalitā*; TP render ‘appease’ as if from *prasādayitum*.

¹³²³ The *vidyā* which changes the form is called *śemuṣī* (Hemacandra, *Triṣaṣṭi* VII 2,291)

¹³²⁴ Also e.g. Kād 179,5 *kṣiti-talam utkhāta-*.

¹³²⁵ Cf. Hemavijaya, *Kathāratnākara* 19,1.

sculptor (*rūpa-kṛt*), draughtsman and ~ decorate pillar with image of Gaurī 37,8 (TP III 183) sea, Śrī issuing from ~ of beauty (*lāvanya-jala-dhi*) 14,68 (TP I 187); ~ propitiated with jewels 18,295 (TP II 72); looking like mountain with wings a banyan-tree emerges from ~ 26,9f. (TP II 217); who can calculate the caprices of Fate or the waves of the ~ (*vidher vilāsān abdhēs ca taraṅgān ko hi tarkayet ?*) 26,18 (TP II 218); ~ as refuge of mountains that retain their wings 27,137 (TP III 11); princess sports like wave of the ~ of infancy (*śaiśavāmbudhi*)¹³²⁶ that is full of the passion for amusement 28,99 (TP III 27); ~ disturbed when moon rounds off its digits 34,163 (TP III 140); ~ gives Śrī-Lakṣmī to Hari-Viṣṇu compared to father giving daughter to husband 35,154 (TP III 167); moon disturbs heart of ~ 51,7 (TP IV 122); ~ calm like a man whose wrath is appeased 52,330 (TP IV 161); *apsaras* sprung from ~ of milk (*kṣīrōda*) 54,40 (TP IV 187); dancing-girl (*lāsikī*) dances like a wave of the ~ of beauty (*rūpābdhi*) 57,75 (TP V 7); king as ~ of valour (*sattva-sāgara*) 58,115 (TP V 23); ~ disturbed when seeing the moon 59,6 (TP V 26); ~ as mine of jewels 59,59 (TP V 30); ~ dried up by Viṣṇu's fire-weapon (*āgneyāstra*) restores *tiṭṭibha* eggs 60,194 (TP V 57); merchant girl like a wave of the ~ of love's arrogance (*Kandarpa-darpābdhi-lahari*) 67,49 (TP V 199); ~ of despondency (*śoka-sāgara*) 67,56 (TP V 199); in a dream Śiva drops from his right eye a tear which becomes a ~. The dreamer drank up that ~ in a human skull stained with blood and immediately awakes 69,38ff. (TP VI 11); Rājput plunging into the ~¹³²⁷ after shipwreck and emerging in splendored city 81,43 (TP VI 212); ~ praised by love-sick king because of mermaid 86,84 (TP VII 19); ~ of physical existence (*bhavāmbudhi*) is transient (*cañcala*) 90,18 (TP VII 50); ~ of calamity (*viplavāmbhodhi*) 91,4 (TP VII 66); Agastya vomits up *pade pade* the ~ he swallowed 102,54 (TP VII 166); ~ of war (*samarāṛṇava*) 115,28 (TP VIII 146); ~ of battle (*āhavāṛṇava*) 116,67 (TP VIII 161); ~s and mountains (*abdhayaḥ kula-śailās ca*) will change at doomsday (*pralaye*), not so royal promises 119,16 (TP VIII 194), cf. 119,29 (TP VIII 195); – ~ of vice, see: dice; separation; substantives instead of augmentative suffixes

sea-monster, see: *makara*

seasons, all ~ present at the same time 81,98 (TP VI 215); activity of king during ~ 122,17-19 (TP IX 35); – king of ~: see spring

seat with rope to leave palace, go-between uses ~ (*pīṭhikāṃ baddhāmbana-rajjukāṃ*) through window (*gavākṣeṇa*) 75,119 (TP VI 172)

seclusion of women social custom or folly of jealousy (*nīti-mātram ... strīṇāṃ rakṣā-nīyantra ṇam irṣā-kṛto mohah*) 36,6f. (TP III 169);

secret, Śiva tells Rati ~ 21,32 (TP II 128); ~ revealed by man made drunk (*kṣibatāṃ nītvā*)

¹³²⁶ Words for elephant, sea, tree etc., often serve as kind of augmentative suffixes on which see, e.g. Grandi 2011 and Matisoff 1991 (indications kindly sent me by Professor Nicola Grandi, of Bologna). These suffixes seem to have even collective value. For the sea as a measure of time cf. *vār-rāśī* in Guṇabhadra's *Pārśvacaritam* 41 (Bollée 2008b: 10).

¹³²⁷ The sea, just as the tank in vs 57, functions as amniotic fluid.

- 57,8 (TP V 1); ~ not to be revealed to woman 61,169 (TP V 82; cf. Kuv 237.1);
 courtesan tells ~ to bawd 61,174 (TP V 83); ~ of Buddhist Dharma 72,366 (TP VI 96);
 – see also: *guptam*; private; *rahas(i)*; *vijane*
- seduction (*pralobhana*),¹³²⁸ Tilottamā sent for ~ of Asuras 15,138 (TP II 14)¹³²⁹; *apsaras*
 seduces *vidyādhara* which angers Śakra 27,61 (TP III 5); by *māyā* Death (*kāla*) creates
 nymph to seduce (*vaśī-cakre*) Simhavikrama with her wealth of beauty 72,341 (TP VI 94);
 – see also: Tilottamā
- seed, Devī gives brahmin heavenly ~ for glorious garden in Pratiṣṭhāna 6,84 (TP I 66); ~ one
 sows becomes fruit one reaps 17,148 (TP II 46); fire becomes pregnant with Śiva's ~ 20,84
 (TP II 102); ~ (*vīrya*) of hermit inflamed by *apsaras* Menakā falls on plantain-flower
 (*kadalī-garbha*) 32,101 (TP III 97); ~ of benefits, sown in good soil, produces abundant
 fruit 73,322 (TP VI 124); – see also: garden; *guñjā*; heavenly seed; horticulture; *kadalī*;
 magic seed; mustard-seeds; panic-seeds; sesame-seeds; *su-kṛta-bīja*
- seeing off person as far as the border of the hermitage 10,208 (TP I 121); do, 52,387 (TP IV
 165); 56,305 (TP IV 242); ~ up to a well 57,105 (TP V 8); ~ friend a long way 73,4 (TP
 VI 100), cf. 110,145 (TP VIII 93); ~ at frontier by court of king on pilgrimage 93,74 (TP
 VII 83); ascetics ~ royal couple as far as the limits of the hermitage 94,49 (TP VII 90);
 citizens of Kauśāmbī see off old king to Mt Kalañjara 111,81 (TP VIII 102: Kālīñjara); –
 see also: frontier
- seeing as receiving rays sent out by someone else, see: princess who in sleep pours forth rays of
 beauty 73,340 (TP VI 125); – see also: eye
- self-consciousness is impediment to knowledge (*jñāna-vighnam ahaṅkāram*) 56,189 (TP IV
 233)
- self-immolation, see: suicide; suttee
- self-pity, the world is full of people with ~ (*jaḡat pūrṇaṃ svātma-mātrānukampibhiḥ*) 90,140
 (TP VII 58)
- self-protection, even animals understand ~ (*svārtho rakṣaṇīyaḥ*) 33,80 and 104 (TP III 113f.)
- self-sacrifice of Jimūtavāhana 22,222 (TP II 153); 90,146 (TP VII 59); ~ of brahmin boy for
 the benefit of others in birth after birth (*janmani janmani*) 94,121 (TP VII 95); – see also:
 social feeling; stylistic repetition
- selling meat, man living by ~ (*māṃsa-vikraya-jīvin*) 56,181 (TP IV 232); she-goat sold to ~
 71,273 (TP VI 56)
- selling one's wife is a crime (*dāra-vikraya-duṣkṛtam*) 43,103 (TP III 288); – see further: wife
 Senānī = Kārttikeya, Śiva's son worshipped on the eighth day of the month 114,115 (TP VIII
 141)
- sensitivity, marvelous,¹³³⁰ see: bed with seven mattresses; fastidiousness; smelling; sound
 sentence contraction¹³³¹: in 91,57 (TP VII 70) ?, see: sun

¹³²⁸ STh *K 1300ff.

¹³²⁹ Zin 2003b: 156 note 31.

¹³³⁰ STh F 647.9.

separation (*viyoga*), from love 9,34 (TP I 96)¹³³²; do, 17,9 (TP II 34); do, reduces brahmin to skin and bone (*tvag-asthi*) 52,44 (TP IV 141); do, 59,109 (TP V 33); ~ from husband leads to death 15,90 (TP II 9) and 69,96 (TP VI 15); fire of ~ (*viprayogâgni*) 25,265 (TP II 210); four days of ~ (*viraha*)¹³³³ as if they were four years 54,79 (TP IV 189); Apabhraṃśa *āryā* about ~ 55,125f. (TP IV 210f.); king tossed with wind of ~ 55,206 (TP IV 216); ocean of ~ (*viṣayogârṇava*) 71,255 (TP VI 54); fire of ~ (*viyogâṇala*) 87,20 (TP VII 30) and (*virahâṇala*) 89,48 (TP VII 43) and 106,110 (TP VIII 36); princess tortured by ~ (*virahâturā*) 101,132 (TP VII 143); defilement of ~ (*viraha-mālīnya*) to be washed off by tears 101,336 (TP VII 157); Mārīca brings about ~ of Rāma and Sītā Vaidehī 102,53 (TP VII 166); grief of ~ from lover 103,26 (TP VII 177); do, (*viraha-saṃtapta*) 104,4 (TP VIII 1); ~ from night makes moon in the morning pale of grief (*rajanī-viraha-dhvasta-kāntir indur*) 105,7 (TP VIII 21); ~ (*viyoga*) from beloved rages like forest fire in lover's bosom 105,10 (TP VIII 22; cf. 111,40 below); ~ from daughter confuses mother like *vidyādhari* having lost magic power 105,13 (TP VIII 22); night of ~ (*viraha-doṣā*) 108,121 (TP VIII 63); ~ from beloved in spring hard to bear (*preyo-viyogas ... duḥsahaḥ*), even animals ... **111,20** (TP VIII 97); wife dies due to ~ from husband, as if consumed by the forest-fire of love 111,40 (TP VIII 98); in spring, fire of ~ is intolerable (*duḥsaho virahâṇalaḥ*) to all creatures 111,47 (TP VIII 99); prince tortured by fire of ~ (*viyogâgni*) from Caṇḍāla maiden 112,84 (TP VIII 111); fisher-boy dies of ~ from princess 112,132 (TP VIII 116); Devī is distracted with sorrow of ~ and angry (*viraha-sôdvegā kruddhā*) 114,64 (TP VIII 137); princess goes into garden to alleviate fire of ~ 117,19 (TP VIII 165)¹³³⁴; prince tortured with ~ 117,93 (TP VIII 170); husband hit by poison of ~ (*viyoga-viṣa*) from wife 121,150 (TP IX 22); fire of ~ from wife 123,149 (TP IX 54); *seraṇa*, questionable reading at 112,153 (TP VIII 118 takes *seraṇa* from √ *si*, and thinks *preraṇa* would make a kind of sense).¹³³⁵

serpent, see: snake

serpent-weapon (*nāgâstra*) repelled with the weapon of Garuḍa 116,71 (TP VIII 161); ~ produces snakes repelled by Garuḍa-weapon from which Garuḍa birds emerge 118,81 (TP VIII 183)

serpent-worship¹³³⁶ 34,188 (TP III 142);

¹³³¹ Gonda 1959: 397ff.

¹³³² For parallels see, e.g. Chojnacki 2008 (I): 344 s.v. *amoureuse*.

¹³³³ Doniger O'Flaherty 1980a: 122ff.

¹³³⁴ At 104,75 (TP VIII 6) a garden is a prison (*udyānaṃ bandhanam*) for a lovesick person.

¹³³⁵ ORC 1180: "(*son épée hors du fourreau émettait des rayons, comme autant de cordes*) en mouvement." 1502: *seraṇa* < *sa* + *iraṇa*; M II 568: "Man konnte ihn durch die Lichtstrahlen, die von seinem gezückten blanken Schwert ausgingen, gut sehen. Und diese Strahlen glichen wahrlich vorausgeschickten Seilen, mit deren Hilfe er offenbar die Edelsteine, die man Sterne nennt, stehlen wollte".

¹³³⁶ See Vogel 1926. In Europe serpent cult is still extant in the village of Cocullo in Italy, near Ovid's native town of Sulmona east of Rome. The cult is a christianized form of the ancient worship of the Italic healing goddess Angitia by the Marsi tribe whose magicians were famous for miraculous snake-bite cures. The rites are now yearly

servant(s), alien ~ are easily corrupted (*bheda-saha*) 32,174 (TP III 104); being ~ (*para-sevā*) is a miserable condition 36,74 (TP III 174); *ceṭī* sent by Damayantī to look for Nala 56,391 (TP IV 248); prying for one's own gratification is not the duty of a ~ (*sevaka*) 60,35 (TP V 44); ~s leave a master who does not support them 61,118 (TP V 78); ~ turns oil-vessel upside down to look at leak in bottom 61,190 (TP V 84); foolish ~ tastes *āmalakas* 61,297 (TP V 94); *dāsī* at heritage cut in two 62,176 (TP V 114); ~ takes care of shop door (*vipaṇī-dvāra*) 62,209 (TP V 117); ~ disguised as bride 64,71 (TP V 145); princess makes ~s drunk with wine in order to be able to escape to forest 66,141 (TP V 189); faithless female ~ 71,152ff. (TP VI 46f.); ~ as *postillon d'amour* 74,220ff. (TP VI 156f.); Deccan Rājput becomes king's *kārpaṭika* but is not rewarded for years 81,7ff. (TP VI 209); ~ are bound to preserve their masters 91,53 (TP VII 70); Vidyādhara ~ 110,142 (TP VIII 93); harem maid (*antaḥpura-ceṭikā*) 120,42 (TP IX 4); ~ abducts his master's beloved in order to marry her himself 123,257 (TP IX 61); Śeṣa, head of ~, yellow with rays of jewels 72,38 (TP VI 71); – see also: crystal lotus sesame-seed, onehundred *khārī* of ~ (*tila*) to be sown 39,116 (TP III 226); ~ gathered by ants 39,123 (TP III 227)¹³³⁷; fool roasts and sows ~ 61,8 (TP V 68); dog defiles ~s for meal 61,106 (TP V 77);

setu-bandha 'building a bridge' (to Śrīlāṅkā) 19,5 (TP II 84)

seven blows daily with stick on mare 68,56 (TP VI 5);

seven brahmins rivalling to be chief 18,130 (TP II 59); 27, 109 (TP III 9); ~ fools 32,44 (TP III 93);

seven continents, see: seven *dvīpas*

seven days (of disputation on grammar) 4,23 (TP I 32); fever causes death after ~s 5,123 (TP I 57); death after ~ in famine 27,120 (TP III 10); magic bows obtained from lake Mānasa in ~ 46,107 (TP IV 56); dwelling for ~ in serpent lake in order to obtain sciences 46,120 (TP IV 56); Kanakavarṣa's ~ of remaining in city of father-in-law after wedding 55,103 (TP IV 209); ~ of Nala's stay with father-in-law 56,284 (TP IV 241); ~ of disputation 72,95f. (TP VI 76); king asks *vidyādhari* wife to stay for ~ 86,146 (TP VII 23); ~ days' feast of king's inauguration 103,235 (TP VII 191); king stays ~ after marriage with Bhilla chief's daughter 123,78 (TP IX 48);

seven divine (*divyāḥ*) herbs in cave of Mt Candrapāda 46,209 (TP IV 62);

seven *dvīpas* of the world 120,29 (TP IX 3); 123,107 (TP IX 50)

seven hells, see: seven *pātālas*

seven herbs 46,209f. (TP IV 62), see: *mahāuṣadhi*

seven heroes 74,253 (TP VI 158);

seven imperial jewels of *vidyādharas* 109,23 (TP VII 71)¹³³⁸

performed in May for San Domenico by "Serpari" who wind non-poisonous snakes around their body (Hammond & Scullard 1970 s.v. Marsi). – STh V 1.3.1.

¹³³⁷ König 1984: 36.

seven *koṭis*, see: seventy million
seven mattresses, fastidious brahmin sleeps on ~ 82,38 (TP VI 219)
seven oceans, king Harṣa of Kashmir is able to drink up the ~ E 10 (TP IX 89)
seven palm-trees (*tāla*) cleft by one arrow 107,21 (TP VIII 44);
seven *pātālas* 45,161 (TP IV 28; also Kuv. 143,23);
seven princesses, commit suicide 28,17 and 43 (TP III 19 and 23); ~ choose same prince for husband 44,41ff. (TP IV 4); – see further also: hair-style
seven-rayed (*saptârçih*) god (Agni) 35,69 (TP III 160);
seven *ṛṣis* (*maharṣi*) ask Naravāhanadatta to tell the story of his life 27,4 (TP III 1)¹³³⁹
seven seas, crossing ~ as pregnancy dream 120,46 (TP IX 4)
seven stories, see: seven tales
seven streams, see Godāvārī
seven syllables, spell of ~ 74,133 (TP VI 149)
seven tales, Kātyāyana relates ~ in seven hundred thousand verses to Kāṇabhūti 2,26 (TP I 11); ~ in Paisācī by Kāṇabhūti 8,1 (TP I 89)
seventh cake (*pūpaka*), only ~ satisfies hunger 62,205 (TP V 116)¹³⁴⁰
seventh day, marching on ~ 46,9 (TP IV 49); Maya and company leave *pātāla* on ~ 46,29 (TP IV 50); marriage on ~ 79,18 (TP VI 201); brahmin boy to be sacrificed to *brahma-rākṣasa* on ~ 94,78 (TP VII 92);
seventh stage of love-sickness (*madanāvasthā*) 89,67 (TP VII 44)
seventy million = seven *koṭis* of *vidyādharas* in Kauśāmbī 110,93 (TP VIII 89);
seven vessels with treasure of brahmin 24,87 (TP II 176)
seven Vidyādharas, wonderful adventures of ~ 1,51 (TP I 6);
seven year old brahmin boy, *brahma-rākṣasa* demands sacrifice of ~ 94,78 (TP VII 92);
seven zones of a palace 38,27 (TP III 208);
sex¹, Ābhīra wants ~, see Ābhīra; *apsaras* desires ~ with mortal 17,129ff. (TP II 44); kettle-drum invites to ~ with princess in the evening 18,321 (TP II 73); ~ of Śiva with Umā 20,72 (TP II 101); delight such as ~ is a baseless fabric of a dream (*svapna-vibhrama*) 28,15 (TP III 19); ~ (*su-rata*) of ardently desirous (*rata-lālasā*) queen with dancing teacher 52,270f. (TP IV 156); ~ (*tam ... aramsta*) of housewife with merchant 58,59 (TP V 19); princess has ~ with one robber and is saved by another 64,46-56 (TP V 143f.); brahmin wife has ~ (*tena sākam sā śayanam yayau*) with cowherd 68,43 (TP VI 4); brahmin is paid 500 dinars for ~ 93,42 (TP VII 81); **description** 103,208-211 (omitted in TP VII 189); *āśliṣṭau dampatī ... ekatām iva jagmatuḥ* 106,110 (TP VIII 36); king divides himself into many forms and sleeps with all queens 110,134 (TP VIII 92); – see also:

¹³³⁸ Viz. lake, sandalwood-tree, elephant, sword, moonlight, wife and the destroying charm. They are pictured on a pillar in Jaggayyapeta (Andhra Pradesh; first century B.C.E) e.g. in Dallapiccola 2002: 48.

¹³³⁹ Description of these celestial ascetics with golden bark garments, etc. in Kumārasambhava 6,6 (Jackmuth 2002: 90ff.)

¹³⁴⁰ STh J 2213.3.

bilocality; cohabitation; copulation; disguise; division of personality; fee; hospitality; transformation

sex²: brahmin is fastidious about women (*nārī-caṅga* [not MW]) 82,12 (TP VI 218)

sex-changing pill as boon from Viṣṇu 89,95 (TP VII 47)¹³⁴¹

shadow (*chāyā*),¹³⁴² five gods assume ~ at Damayantī's *svayaṃvara* 56,271 (TP IV 239)

shame, contest between ~ and curiosity in eye of princess when woken up by unknown king 3,66 (TP I 23); ~ of king due to false jealousy 5,97 (TP I 54); ~ (*vriḍā*) of queen at having endured separation when she heard of the attachment of another woman to her husband 17,31 (TP II 36); ~ of prince, expelled from his kingdom, to ask help of his father-in-law 21,70 (TP II 130); woman's ~ disregarded by eagerness (*autsukyâgaṇita-trapā*) 37,103 (TP III 190); woman's face cast down for ~ at discovered adultery 37,230 (TP III 199); minister bows down with ~ (*trapā-nata*) before prince 40,37 (TP III 243); discovered woman doubts between ~ and jealousy 45,265 (TP IV 35); maidens shocked and ashamed at being collectively married to same husband 45,301f. (TP IV 37); ~ at telling story 56,79 (TP IV 225); with face downcast from ~ daughter has friend ask father about marriage 65,250 (TP V 174); heavenly maiden dismisses ~ (*nirvriḍa-yantraṇam*) and offers herself to king who marries her the *gāndharva* way 68,13 (TP VI 2); brahmin's ~ for improper garments (*anucitāmbara*) 73,74 (TP VI 106); ~ for being reduced low by gambling (*dyūta-durgata*) 73,180 (TP VI 114); princess's ~ for wearing masculine decorations 73,363f. (TP VI 127); ~ for being naked (*dig-ambara*) 73,383 (TP VI 128); ~ of mother-in-law at being laughed at by family because of her deceit 74,176 (TP VI 153); ~ of dissipation (*daurgatya-lajjā*) due to gambling, etc. 77,19 (TP VI 184); ~ of king at not paying dependent 81,24 (TP VI 210); princess too modest for *svayaṃvara* 83,17ff. (TP VII 3); with ~ woman tells husband adventure 84,34 (TP VII 7); Siddha princess ashamed when blamed for not honouring guest 90,54 (TP VII 52); ~ of adulterous couple after their revival by Caṇḍī 95,90f. (TP VII 104); ~ of princess at stopped suicide attempt 103,55 (TP VII 179); lover addresses beloved to dispel her ~ (*tyājayan hriyam*) 103,64 (TP VII 179); out of ~ brahmin maiden flings son by Agni in the street 112,104 (TP VIII 113); ~ (*lajjā-nata-mukhī*) at being in presence of strange man 116,40 (TP VIII 159); ~ makes a prince conceal fire of love 119,3 (TP VIII 193); ~ of twelve year old boy of ignoring his father 124,204 (TP IX 82); – see also: *ābhāva-lajjā*

shape, see: form

shattered head motif¹³⁴³: *vetāla* threatens king that his head will split in a hundred pieces if he does not tell him the truth about his doubt, though he knows it 75,186ff. (TP VI 177) et passim; 106,133 (TP VIII 38)

shaving, see: hair

shawl, see: roomal

¹³⁴¹ Esposito 2013: 511 and Doniger O'Flaherty 1980: 378 under: sex, change of.

¹³⁴² Malamoud 1989: 241ff.

¹³⁴³ See Insler 1990.

she-elephant (*kariṇī*) being harnessed utters cry 13,17 (TP I 151); (*kareṇukā*) carrying queens 18,6 (TP II 49); ~ flings monkey into ant-hill mud 37,132 (TP III 192); ~ carries queen 55,233 (TP IV 218); hermit turns she-jackal into ~ 68,19 (TP VI 2)

sheep fleeing from jackal, fugitive woman compared to ~ (*jambukād avikêva*) 52,42 (TP IV 141)

she-goat (*chāgī*), witch turned into ~ by eating charmed barley-meal and is sold to butcher 71,273 (TP VI 56)

she-jackal, hermit turns ~ (*śṛgālikā*) into she-elephant 68,19 (TP VI 2); ~ (*śivā*) yells (*cakre śabdaṃ*) when king wishes to depart in the evening 121,160 (TP IX 23); ~ howling on left hand bad omen 124,108 (TP IX 76); – see also: messenger of death; omen

she-partridge (*cakori*) beholds moon like woman her beloved 31,45 (TP III 85); woman be-
holding man as ~ longs to drink the moon 49,211 (TP IV 99);

sheth (*vaṇiṇ-nivaha-nāyaka*) obtains daughter by propitiating deities 88,5 (TP VII 35)

ship stopped in mid-ocean by giant's leg 18,303 (TP II 72)¹³⁴⁴; ~ whirled around by wind like head of mast elephant 36,82 (TP III 175); ~ struck by *makara* breaks up 54,102 (TP IV 191); 67,60 (TP V 200); *bhavāmbudhi* to be crossed on shuttle (*nau-tuli*) 72,362 (TP VI 96); ~ drawn to gold banner half-way to Laṅkā 81,37 (TP VI 211); ~ compared to elephant, waves to passions (? *rāga-bandha* [q. v.]) 101,180 (TP VII 146); ~ near Suvarṇadvīpa swallowed by large fish (*śaphareṇa*)¹³⁴⁵ 123,110 (TP IX 51);

ship-wrecked man 36,85 (TP III 175); ~ saved by spar (*kāṣṭa*) like an arm extended by Creator 67,62 (TP V 200); ~ finds himself in golden city and does not see sea anymore 81,43 (TP VI 212)

shipwreck motif¹³⁴⁶ 25,45 (TP II 192); 36,83 (TP III 175); 52,324 (TP IV 161); 54,87 and 102 (TP IV 190f.); 56,143 (TP IV 230); 67,55 and 60 (TP V 199f.); (*bhagna-vahana*) 67,105 (TP V 203); 81,42 (TP VI 212); ~ 101,141f. (TP VII 144); 120,111 (TP IX 9);

shock, see: bewilderment

shoes , magic ~ (*pāduke*) of Maya enable to fly and are fought for by his two sons 3,49 (TP I 22)¹³⁴⁷; minister will carry ~¹³⁴⁸ of Guṇāḍhya on his head for twelve years 6,149 (TP I 71); mango wood (*cūta-pādapa*) ~ of Śiva Dhūrjaṭi slipped off 67,97 (TP V 203);

shower (*dhārā*), makes elephant's skin contract 12,110 (TP I 141)

showing off (*pradarśayan*), king ~ horse to queen 18,91 (TP II 56); ocean like hero's valour ~ impetuosity 18,389 (TP II 79)

shriek (*rava*) of corpse causes heartbreak (*hṛt-sphoṭa*) and death of carrier 73,291 (TP VI 121); Śibi gives his own flesh to Indra as hawk 7,94 (TP I 84)¹³⁴⁹

¹³⁴⁴ STh F 531.3.1.2.

¹³⁴⁵ The reference in MW is wrongly given as ccxxiii 10. – STh F 911.4.1.

¹³⁴⁶ See, e.g., Schlingloff 1982: 51f.

¹³⁴⁷ See Bollée 2008: 48; Sartori 1894. The work “*Fuß and Schuh im Volksglauben*” by G.A. Gerhards, mentioned by Weinreich 1909: 69 note 3 as being in preparation, could not be found.

¹³⁴⁸ Shoes here represent the person thus honoured, see Bollée 2008: 94.

sick, ladies of the court each take care of a ~ person asking for medicine and fall in love with them 66,38 (TP V 181); – see also: pilgrimage (66,30 (TP V 180))

sickness feigned (*māndya-vyāja*) 24,168 (TP II 181) and 32,153 (TP III 102); king pretends headache (*śiro 'rti-vyapadeśa*) 33,148 (TP III 120); – see also: disease; pretence

siddhāñjana ‘magic collyrium’ used to see people invisible by magic power (*māyā*) 48,86 (TP IV 80)

Siddha(s),¹³⁵⁰ attend with *gaṇas* and *vidyādharas* upon Śiva 1,17 (TP I 3); land of ~ 18,234f. (TP II 67 with ref. to I 204) cannot be entered by *vidyādharas* nor by *rākṣasas* 18,351 (TP II 75); ~ gives smart brahmin in heaven spell to descend to earth 20,179 (TP II 111); Jimūtavāhana cares for his father in a hermitage of the ~ 22,46 (TP II 140); ~ Piśāca 28,169 (TP III 33); ~ā, *apsaras* or *vidyādhari*? 28,190 (TP III 36), cf. 94,25 (TP VII 89) and 103,24 (TP VII 176); 36,116 (TP III 177); ~ curses *Gandharvas* to become mortals 36,118 (TP III 177); imperial princess carried off by ~ 44,43 (TP IV 4); two ~s flying in the shape of *haṃsas* 72,186 (TP VI 82); prince of ~ flying 72,278 (TP VI 89); ~s applaud from heaven at death of warrior 74,296 (TP VI 161); king of ~s resides on Mt Malaya 90,39 (TP VII 51); domain of ~s (*siddha-kṣetra*) 107,6 (TP VIII 43); do, 107,80 (TP VIII 48); ~ sing praises of king 107,136 (TP VIII 72); all emperors have their inauguration on Mt Rṣabha as the land of the ~s¹³⁵¹ 110,46 (TP VIII 85 with note 2); ~ princess performs penance to get desired husband and curses woman who laughs at her 117,177ff. (TP VIII 176)¹³⁵²; ~s announce princess to have lord of seven continents for husband 123,107 (TP IX 50)

Siddha-dhāman = mountain of rising sun 18,350 (TP II 75);

siddhāñjana (not MW) ‘magic collyrium or unguent’ enables to see people invisible by magic 48,86 (TP IV 80; ORC 516: “*onguent efficace*”)

siddha-rasāyana ‘possessing a life-prolonging elixir’, a minister ~ and who knows the use of all herbs (*sarvāuśadhi-yukti-jñā*) makes himself and his king long-lived 41,11 (TP III 253); – cf. *kāla-saṃkarṣiṇī vidyā*

siddha-saktu (not MW), see: charmed barley-meal

siddha-tāpasī ‘female ascetic with supernatural power’ 65,223 (TP V 172)

siddha-yoginī ‘good witch’ 37,161 (TP III 194); ~ teaches couple life-prolonging science (*kāla-saṃkarṣiṇī vidyā*) 68,64 (TP VI 6 with note)

siddhi ‘magic power’ of witches’ spells 20,104 (TP II 103); ‘good fortune (?)’, (magic) sword as long as the tuft of ~ (*keśa-pāśa ivāyataḥ*) 26,261 (TP II 236; ORC 251: ‘*Réussite*’); ~ (‘supernatural power’?)¹³⁵³, by yoga brahmin reaches independence and ~ (*sva-tantratām*

¹³⁴⁹ Cf. Oberlies 2009.

¹³⁵⁰ Cf. ORC 1644; Zin 2003b: 165.

¹³⁵¹ TP: “for it is a holy place”; ORC 1155: “car c’est un lieu pour les *siddha*.”

¹³⁵² See Baldissera 2004: 83.

¹³⁵³ On these see e.g. Varenne 1966: 264f., but is not rather ‘final emancipation, being delivered from *saṃsāra*’ meant? ORC 473: *pouvoirs magiques*.

yogāt siddhiṃ) 45,112 (TP IV 25); ascetic looses ~ by talking to wicked woman 65,52f. (TP V 158); after living in Pātāla a long time with a Daitya maiden a king attains ~ ('salvation') 73,176 (TP VI 114); *gaṇas* carry hero by means of their ~ to Haṃsadvīpa 73,336 (TP VI 125); man wants to sacrifice himself to Durgā in order to obtain ~ 80,29 (TP VI 206); – see also: Buddha-like status; emancipation; *paraṃ jyotiḥ*

Siddhīśvara, Hara's abode, in ~ old age, death, etc. are absent, and animals and plants are of gold 115,114 (TP VIII 152)

Siddhōdaka, a *tīrtha* called 'holy water', king performs ablution at ~ 119,81 and 91 (TP VIII 199)

siddho varṇa-samāmnāyaḥ 'the traditional doctrine of letters'.¹³⁵⁴ *sūtra* pronounced by Skanda 7,10 (TP I 75)

sidelong glance, see: *kaṭākṣa*¹³⁵⁵

sight, ~ of person causes remembrance of pre-birth 66,176 (TP V 191); Bhilla king compares ~ of the feet of other monarch with perfect fruit (*pūrṇaṃ phalam*) = benefit or luck 123,72 (TP IX 48); – see also: *darśana*; first sight; love at first sight

sightseeing, by royals 35,158 (TP III 168); ~ of town by four heroes 52,117 (TP IV 146); ~ on Nārikela 'coconut palm' island 54,49ff (TP IV 188); ~ of prince in Lāṭa looking for friend 74,140 (TP VI 150); ~ beauty of city (*nagara-śriyam*) by Naravāhanadatta 106,33 (TP VIII 30); attendant of Gandharva princess is ~ in Vidyādhara city 117,81f. (TP VIII 169); – see also: pilgrimage; tourism

sign(s), candle falling out of hand: ~ (*lakṣaṇa*) of hidden treasure 34,70f. (TP III 133); ~ of recognition (*abhiññāna*) 39,107 (TP III 225); ~ of *rākṣasī* sister allows prince to kill her brother 42,132 (TP III 269); distinguishing ~ (*tilaka*) of emperor of *vidyādhara*s 43,169 (TP III 292); ~ (*saṃjñā*) language of communication between robbers 64,52f. (TP V 143f.)¹³⁵⁶; auspicious ~s on horse¹³⁵⁷ 74,77f. (TP VI 145); *kanyā* gives ~s to prince 75,72 (TP VI 169 [see also: *danta-patra*])¹³⁵⁸; Padmāvātī giving ~ by hitting old go-between 75,101 (TP VI 171); discus-marked footprint ~ of royalty 86,76 (TP VII 18); low water and white mud as ~s of broken heart of tanks 87,31 (TP VII 31); ~ with left hand to wait 112,55 (TP VIII 110); – see: one finger; two fingers; three fingers; five fingers; language of gestures; mark(s); omen

sikatā-pātra 'pot with sand' (not MW), king gives ~ to importunately begging brahmin 72, (TP VI 75)

śikhā, see: hair

¹³⁵⁴ Abhyankar 1961: 386; ORC 44 with note 3 on p. 1341: "transmission énumérative des phonèmes" < Renou 1957: 4 (*akṣara*).

¹³⁵⁵ The image is not always clear to us as in Amaru I where Durgā is prayed to protect the poet with her sidelong glance.

¹³⁵⁶ See Lüders 1940: 483ff.

¹³⁵⁷ See Caland 2010.

¹³⁵⁸ STh T 42.1.

śikhā-ratna (not MW) ‘crest-jewel,’ efficient (*mahā-prabhāva*) because sprung from waterpot (*kamaṇḍalu*) of Disposer 117,156 (TP VIII 174f.)¹³⁵⁹

śīla, see: characteristic

śīlā-bhāva ‘stone-nature’ of Ahalyā due to Gautama’s curse 17,143 (TP II 46 with note 3)

śīla-pāramitā ‘perfection of chastity’ 72,236 and 259 (TP VI 86f.);

śīla-tṛṇa (not MW) ‘stubble of character’ 36,87 (TP III 175; ORC 367: “*un brin de vertu*”; M I 517: “*Welche Kunde gibt es schon dort über das Gras, das da ‘edle und fromme Sinnesart’ heißt*”)

silence, of king through grief 6,120 (TP I 69); vow of ~ (*saṃkṛta-mauna*) 6,159 (TP I 72); idem, *maunatva* 7,23 (TP I 76); ~ practised by woman who considers herself Viṣṇu’s wife and therefore should not speak to mortals 12,158 (TP I 145); after getting alms from a merchant beauty ascetic breaks vow of ~ 15,33 (TP II 4); ~ as difficult as standing on edge of sword (*asi-dhārām iva*)¹³⁶⁰ 17,91 (TP II 41); princess silences¹³⁶¹, i.e. beats opponents in dispute 72,67 (TP VI 73) and is subsequently beaten herself 72,80 (TP VI 75); ~ of deities means their agreement to play dice with gambler 121,81f. (TP IX 18)

silk, white woven ~ (*sita-paṭṭa*), see: bed; *kauśeya*

silk cotton tree, see *śālmali*

silver vessel in temple of Śiva 25,228 (TP II 208)

śimantōnnayana,¹³⁶² principal mountains marked by Gaṇeśa with a line like ~ 21,1 (TP II 125)

śiṃha-dvāra ‘lion’s gate, main gate of palace’, Pāśupata ascetic at ~ 43,173 (TP III 293);

kārpaṭika standing at ~ with club (*laguḍa*) 53,12 (TP IV 169); 55,37 (TP IV 205); 71,81

(TP VI 41); 78,24 (TP VI 192); child exposed at ~ 93,51 (TP VII 81); – see also: notice

śiṃha-nāda ‘war-cry’, *vidyādharas* utter ~ 107,94 (TP VIII 49)

śiṃhāsana, lion throne, jewelled ~ (*ratna-°*) 18,44 (TP II 52)¹³⁶³; – see also: throne

śiṃhāyate srgālo 74,270 (TP VI 159 ‘jackal apes lion’);

simile (*dr̥ṣṭānta*), see: comparison(s); poet; proverb; sayings

similia similibus, drug made of flesh of wild goat for fructifying queens 39,7 (TP III 218);

quenching heat with fire 66,14 (TP V 179); ~ of weeping deer with weeping king in forest

66,148 (TP V 189)¹³⁶⁴; healing ~ 123,34 (TP IX 34); – see also: *vanyac-chagalika*

śiṃśapā tree (*Dalbergia sisso*¹³⁶⁵), snake palace under ~ 70,58 (TP VI 28 and ORC 805

translate “*aśoka tree*”)¹³⁶⁶; corpse under ~ 73,285f. (TP VI 121); Trivikramasena asked to

¹³⁵⁹ This waterpot may be filled with *amṛta*, just as that of Gaurī, see supra s.v. *kamaṇḍalu*.

¹³⁶⁰ Text wrongly: *āsīdhāram*.

¹³⁶¹ If one cannot answer one is silent in order to avoid the consequence that one’s head bursts (Witzel 1987: 372).

¹³⁶² See Gonda 1975 IV: 186-206; Bollée 2010a.

¹³⁶³ Saletore 1943: 176f. For examples see the throne of the Mahārāja of Mewar (Jackson 2010:166) and that of the Mahārāja of Patiala (Jackson 2010: 227).

¹³⁶⁴ Jātaka parallels ???

¹³⁶⁵ Macmillan 1991: 243 “fast-growing, large, upright tree.”

bring corpse hanging on ~ which smells after (spoilt) raw flesh (*kravya-gandhin*) and looks like a Bhūt 75,51 (TP VI 167) et passim;

sin¹³⁶⁷, see: transgression

sindūra ‘blood-red’, see: TP II 23 note; red lead; vermilion

sindūra-tilaka, queen with vermilion *tilaka* 20,50 (TP II 98)

singing peasant has discovered the essence of religion (*sāraṃ dharmasya*) 33,34 (TP III 109):

“highest virtue”; ORC 322: “*l’essentiel du dharma*”; M I 454: “*den wahren Kern der Tugend*”); Gandharvas ~ before Viṣṇu 36,115 (TP III 177); Vidyādhari ~ praise of Śiva sends husband to sleep 52,195 (TP IV 151); Gandharva princess wants only husband able to ~ perfectly in three scales (*tribhir grāmaiḥ*) song in praise of Viṣṇu 106,12 (TP VIII 29); lady in lake worships *līṅga* ~ southern style in notes, time and words (*ālambya dakṣiṇaṃ mārḡaṃ svara-tāla-pādaiḥ*) splendidly 120,121¹³⁶⁸ (TP IX 10); at the end of the evening spectacle (*saṃdhyā-prekṣaṇaka*) in a Śiva temple the singers disappear into the figures of men painted on the walls 123,133f. (TP IX 52)

single alms-offering, vow of accepting only a ~ (? *eka-bhikṣā-vrata*)¹³⁶⁹ 71,137 (TP VI 45):

“she had vowed an exclusive devotion to the life of a beggar”; ORC 818: “*qu’elle avait pour voeu d’être seulement mendiante*”; M II 62: “*Gelübde, ein Bettlerinnenleben zu führen*”);

single combat (*dvandva-yuddha*) between kings for power 38,132 (TP III 215); (for woman) 43,120 (TP III 289); 47,56 (TP IV 70); ~ 48,117 (TP IV 82); 49,87 (TP IV 90); 50,8 (TP IV 108); 50,63 (TP IV 112); ~ between gods and Asuras 115,29 (TP VIII 146); – see also: battle

single parent, widow raises lone son by menial drudgery 6,29ff. (TP I 62); parrot father as ~ 59,30 (TP V 29)

śirīṣa flower,¹³⁷⁰ queen (*mahiṣī*) delicate as ~ 6,113 (TP I 69); do, of a princess, like a matchless arrow, of five flowers, appointed by Smara for the conquest of the world 34,232 (TP III 146); do, (of Vaiṣṇavite princess) 71,118 (TP VI 44); do, 101,156 (TP VII 145); do, 117,113 (TP VIII 172);

śiro-’rti ‘headache’, man having lost his beloved in panic develops severe ~ 104,109 (TP VIII 9), see: disease

sister dies of heartbreak (*hṛt-sphota*) when brother is sacrificed 78,74 (TP VI 195);

¹³⁶⁶ As the text continues with dusty water on which couples of *haṃsas* swim, *śiṃśapā-taru* is incorrect or something is lost.

¹³⁶⁷ The Christian-biased word “sin” is actually unsuited to corresponding Indian notions; misbehaviour, transgression or misdemeanour may be better.

¹³⁶⁸ As to this the musician Ludwig Pesch writes me that the south-Indian music, as against its northern counterpart, possesses a wide repertoire of bi- and tripartite *kunstlieds* with longer texts (*kīrti* and *kīrtana*; see Pesch 2009: 270). Vocal and instrumental elements in the South blend more and singers adopt marks of *viṇā* style the reverse occurring also. Another, modern, mark of the southern style is the frequent imitation of the vocal part by the accompanying tune, mostly only with a short delay. We do not know exactly if this was the case in former ages, too.

¹³⁶⁹ Cf. Pāli *eka-bhikkhā*.

¹³⁷⁰ Acacia Sirissa Buch. Syed 1990: 579ff. has many more examples from literature and pictures from Bhārhuṭ on p. 586ff.; Jackmuth 2002: 121ff.

śiśumāra, see: dolphin

Śītā on wall painting (*citra-bhitti*) in Magadha palace 16,27 (TP II 22)

śīta-jvara, see: fever

Śītodā, river that cannot be crossed by humans 18,234 (TP II 67) and 350 (TP II 75);

Śiva¹³⁷¹ not invited to Prajāpati's sacrifice because of wearing chain of skulls 1,36 (TP I 4); ~ quarrels with Pārvatī¹³⁷² 1,43 (TP I 5); ~ telling stories as Creator by dropping blood from his thigh into the universal water, blood which then becomes the cosmic egg 2,10ff. (TP I 9ff.); his (Vibhu's) sweat as Kāma's water weapon (*vāruṇāstra*) 9,1 (TP I 94); ~ in dream gives lotus to couple 13,79 (TP I 156); ~ becomes four-faced to look at Tilottamā 15,137 (TP II 14)¹³⁷³; ~ predicting future in dream 19,10 (TP II 85)¹³⁷⁴; Gaurī obtains ~ as three-eyed (*try-ambaka*) husband 20,61 (TP II 100); ~ has hundreds of years sex with Umā 20,73 (TP II 101); ~ engaged in severe and long austerities 20,61 (TP II 100); ~ tells Rati secret 21,32 (TP II 128); ~ appears himself and predicts son in dream 21,143 (TP II 136); ~ curses *vidyādhara* to mortal birth 22,57 (TP II 141); ~ promises in dream husband to woman 22,122 (TP II 146); ~ worshipped by *vidyādhara*s on 14th (white ?) fortnight 26,65 (TP II 222); ~ tells *rākṣasī* to eat dead king's flesh 29,139 (TP III 49); ~ propitiated (*tuṣṭa*) tells *viyādhara* king to assume form of king of Vatsa and marry by the *gāndharva* ceremony mortal beauty wanted by the latter 30,12 (TP III 64); two people are inseparable like ~ and Pārvatī 31,32 (TP III 83); ~ curses *apsaras* to mortal rebirth 34,35 (TP III 130); ~ orders Kāma's wife Rati to be reborn outside a mortal womb (*a-yoni-jā*) 34,42 (TP III 131); ~'s voice heard from heaven deciding that Kāma is to be reincarnated as Naravāhanadatta 34, 243 TP III 146; cf. 120,26 where ~ decides that Mālyavat should incarnate as Vikramāditya [TP IX 3]); sonless king propitiating ~ 35,94 as cause of world's creation, preservation and destruction (*jagat-sarga-sthiti-saṃhāra-hetu*) who assumes the eight special forms of ether &c. (*vyomādi-bheda-bhinnāṣṭa-mūrti*) **35,99** (TP III 163); ~ androgyne, creating the universe by a wish (*icchā-nirmita-viśva*)¹³⁷⁵ and appears in dream promising son **35,102f.** (TP III 163f.); ~ predicts daughter in dream 43,145 (TP III 291); ~ as *kala-haṃsa* on lake Mānasa 35,100 (TP III 163); ~ sends *Asura* Maya to teach magic sciences 44,29 (TP IV 3); message of ~ (Śambhu) through Nandin 45,43 (TP IV 20); ~ orders good witch to free *vidyādhara* maiden 48,127 (TP IV 83); ~ orders gods and *Asuras* to eat Sumeru's ever satisfying food 50,144 (TP IV 117); ~'s thousand names 50,181 (TP IV 119); Sūryaprabha sees ~ with three eyes on throne 50,190 (TP IV 120); ~ orders *Gaṇa* to bring Sūryaprabha to Mt Rṣabha for coronation 50,197 (TP IV 120); temple of ~ Svayambhū with maiden playing the lyre 51,5 (TP IV 122); image of ~ in Sundarapura 52,15 (TP IV 139); maiden singing praise of ~ as kind of lullaby 52,195 (TP IV 151); ~ appears in double dream and

¹³⁷¹ See ORC 1646f. and O'Flaherty 1973.

¹³⁷² See O'Flaherty 1973: 224f.

¹³⁷³ See O'Flaherty 1973: 84 and 248f.

¹³⁷⁴ Bollée 2010a: 151 note 19,10.

¹³⁷⁵ Cf. 2,10f. (TP I 9).

tells future

52,390 (TP IV 165); refuge to ~ (Śambhu) avoids Suprabha's conception in sow body due to exhaustion of merit 53,124 (TP IV 176); innocent man condemned to death seeks Śiva's protection 54,115 (TP IV 192); propitiated ~ gives a son 59,60 (TP V 30); third eye of ~ 57,2 (TP V 1); Śambhu instructs two people in dreams about the future 59,168 and 171f. (TP V 37f.); Hara's bull (*Hara-vṛṣa*; Nandi) tearing up ant-hills with his horns 60,17 (TP V 42); king with five daughters gets son from Hara 65,73 (TP V 160); Hara predicts two sons to king 66,170ff. (TP V 191); son of merchant as result of propitiation of Śaṅkara (*Śaṅkarārādhanaṅjita*) 67,37 (TP V 198); mango-wooden shoes of ~ Dhūrjaṭi 67,97 (TP V 203); king worships Hara daily to get a wife 69,84 (TP VI 14); hermit sacrifices *haṃsa* to Śiva 69,154 (TP VI 20); ~ does not lead "all the gods" as do Brahmā and Viṣṇu 72,396 (TP VI 98); ~ appears to hermit and shows him door to Pātāla in Kaśmīra 73,107 (TP VI 108); ~ (Hara) propitiated for husband 73,423 (TP VI 130); ~ gives *darshan* 73,424 (TP VI 130); king propitiates Hara for son at the bank of the river Mandākinī 83,8 (TP VII 2); temple of ~ in *Puṇḍra-viṣaya* (Puṇḍra = Bengal) near sea 86,27 (TP VII 15); Vārāṇasī ~'s abode (*Hara-nivāsa*) 87,3 (TP VII 29); ~ (Bhairava) invisibly present on charnel ground speaks from the air and gives woman two boons 88,47ff. (TP VII 38); Gaurī and Gaṅgā are the two wives dear to Hara (*Hara-kāntāḥ*) 90,3 (TP VII 49); ~ resides in Ujjayinī 92,9 (TP VII 71); ~ (Hara) tells mother and grandmother in dream to expose new-born son at royal gate 93,49 (TP VII 81); ~ (Vṛṣadhvaṅja) in dream tells king of new-born son exposed at his gate 93,52 (TP VII 82); ~ appears visibly (*sākṣād abhūt*) to king Trivikramasena and tells him to be a portion of himself 99,31ff. (TP VII 124); ~ Bhagavān appears as Bhairava and threatens *vidyādhara* Mānasavega with sword 106,127 (TP VIII 38); ~ Bhairava, black as antimony (*añjana-nibha*), emerges from pillar filling the sky and hiding the sun 106,182 (TP VIII 42)¹³⁷⁶; ~ pleased gives *darshan* 107,129 (TP VIII 52); Śiva Vṛṣabhadhvaṅja visited by Naravāhanadatta 110,53 (TP VIII 85); ~'s temple plundered by robbers 114,119 (TP VIII 141); ~ promises son as boon to Vidyādhara prince 115,118 (TP VIII 152); do, 120,25 and 37 (TP IX 3f.); ministers obtain same dream as king of Śiva's promise 120,41 (TP IX 4); king and ministers make ~ in Benares their refuge 120,60 (TP IX 5)¹³⁷⁷; – see also: Bhagavān, *Bhagavat-sāyujya*, Girijāpati, Hara, Śaṅkara, Śambhu, Śarva, Śrīkaṅṭha; Vṛṣa(bha)-dhvaṅja

Śivāṃśa 'portion of Śiva', prince, ~ shall get earth and Pātāla into his power 118,21ff. (TP VIII 179)

Śivi offered his flesh for protection seeker¹³⁷⁸ 62,100 (TP V 107)

six Buddhist perfections (*ṣaṭka-pāramitā*) 72,362 (TP VI 96)

six calamities (for peasants), see: *īti-ghna*

¹³⁷⁶ In 107,5 this emergence of Śiva is declared a delusion of Prabhāvatī by means of her magic science.

¹³⁷⁷ ORC 1516 note on p. 1261 "le roi et son entourage vont donc pratiquer en un lieu sacré une ascèse qui pourra aller jusqu'à un suicide rituel."

¹³⁷⁸ Cf. Ohnuma 2007: 26ff. (Gift of the body genre).

- six days of meditation on Śambhu prevents *devaputra* from rebirth as pig 53,125 (TP IV 176)
- six faces, deity with ~ (Kārtikeya) 6,167 (TP I 73); boy (Kumāra) born with ~ drinks from the breasts of the six Kṛttikās 20,87f. (TP II 102)
- six faults, see: six human faults
- six fires, see: five fires
- six flavours (*rasa*) 45,230 (TP IV 32); mendicants become slim by eating food with ~ 62,181 (TP V 114); king gives food-fastidious brahmin food with ~ 82,19 (TP VI 218);
- six gamblers besieged by brahmin prince 74,178f. (TP VI 153)
- six *guṇas* ‘political measures (of peace, war, march, halt, stratagem and recourse to the protection of a mightier king)’ 23,93 (TP II 165 with note; ORC 1368 ad 204 note 2 refers to Kauṭilya VII,1,6)¹³⁷⁹; ~ (‘proper courses’) 34,200 (TP III 143 note); Viṣṇu’s shape is the full aggregate of the ~ 54,31 (TP IV 186)
- six Kṛttikās (Pleiades) suckle boy Kumāra with six mouths 20,88 (TP II 102)
- six human faults 20,134 (TP II 106)
- six months, auspicious moment in ~ 32,5 (TP III 90); if in ~ heavenly man should not visit courtesan she vows to enter the fire 38,113 (TP III 214)
- six nights, after ~ prince remembers dream of seeing emaciated celestial maiden in Śiva temple and a laughing hermit 119,70f. (TP VIII 198);
- six *pāramitā*, see supra: six Buddhist perfections
- sixteen princes 46,36 (TP IV 51);
- sixteen¹³⁸⁰ year old brahmin sets out for Valabhī to acquire learning 32,43 (TP III 93); ~ boy becomes crown prince 44,24 (TP IV 2); death of ~ princess 52,172 (TP IV 150); ~ only brahmin son dies of fever 97,11 (TP VII 113);
- sixth day, on ~ poor merchant finds treasure 54,88 (TP IV 190); on ~ king Bhūnandana and hermits cross infernal Ganges and worship Śiva 73,119ff. (TP VI 110);
- sixth fire created by destiny (*vidhi*) 101,286 (TP VII 154);
- sixth night, on ~ after birth of prince terrible woman enters lying-in chamber through bolted door, takes child and plunges with it in tank followed by queen when night ends 55,190ff. (TP IV 215)
- sixth weapon of Kāma, *kṣatriya* beauty as ~ 104,28 (TP VIII 3);
- sixty-eight parts of the body, Śiva’s names referring to ~ 54,215 (TP IV 199 with note 1); reciting 68 names of Gaṇeśa, corresponding to so many parts of the body, removes fear of harm by king, thieves, etc., 55,166 (TP IV 213)
- sixty thousand *yojanas* distant Aniruddha, in Dvāravatī 31,22 (TP III 82);
- sixty *yojanas*, house ~ away 28,188 (TP III 35);
- six years for learning grammar 6,145 (TP I 71)
- Skanda¹³⁸¹ gives Śarvavarman sight (*darśana*) of himself 7,9f. and speaks *sūtra* with six mouths

¹³⁷⁹ Cf. Manu vii 160ff.

¹³⁸⁰ As formulistic number STh Z 71.10. Gonda 1965a: 115ff.

- (TP I 74 leaving out *ṣaḍbhir ānana-pañkajaiḥ*); Sarasvatī, ~ and Jina as three happy (*dhanya*) beings 51,205 (TP IV 136 renders Jina by Buddha); – see also: Kārttikeya; Kumāra; Svāmikumāra
- skeleton, human ~ (*nara-karaṅkaka*) hanging in fig tree (*vaṭa*) 40,90 (TP III 247); corpse (*śava*) hanging in *śiṃśapa* tree 75,50f. (TP VI 167) et passim; Kālī as wearer of ~s (*kaṅkālinī*) 78,91 (TP VI 197)
- skin, queens with skintight bathing clothes (*aṅgaiḥ saktâmbara-vyakta-vibhāgaiḥ*) pelt king with water 6,111 (TP I 69; cf. *aṅga-lagnârdra-vāsasaḥ* 108,147 [TP VIII 64]); ~ of black antelope with charm (*sa-mantram ... kṣṇa-mṛgâjinam*) protects king against stinging bees 73,173 (TP VI 114); ass in panther's ~ 62,19 (TP V 99); (~) white with sandalwood ointment 95,17 (TP VI 99); – horny ~ see: *pāruṣya*
- skull, world (*rodasī* 'heaven and earth') resembles skull 2,15 (TP I 10); necklace of ~s (*karaṅka-mālā*) round neck of bawd 12,169 (TP I 146); ~ on pyre split by boy who gets brains into his mouth and thus becomes *rākṣasa* 25,103 (TP II 198); in dream king drinks sea in human ~ (*nr-kapāla*) and awakes 69,39 (TP VI 11); – see also: destiny; forehead
- skull-bearing (*kapāla-mālī*), Śiva 1,37 (TP I 5) and 2,14 (TP I 10)¹³⁸²; spies assuming the vows of ~ worshippers of Śiva 19,74 (TP II 90); ~ ascetic (*kapālin*) 25,82 (TP II 196); ~ Kālī 78,91 (TP VI 197)
- sky (*diśaḥ*) see: directions
- slab, Gaṇeśa sitting on *jyoti-rasa* ~ 50,176 (TP IV 119); prince waking up on ~ of *tārksya* 68,7 (TP VI 1); emperor sitting on ~ of moonstone (*candra-kānta-śilā-tala*) 111,16 (TP VIII 96)
- slander (*pravāda*) of the people made Rāma leave Sītā 34,236 (TP III 146); slighted queen ~s virtuous brahmin 49,97 (TP IV 91); because of ~ of the people Rāma left Sītā in the forest 51,70 (TP IV 127); – see also: calumny; report; rumour
- ślatha-dhammilla-bandhana*, see: hair-style
- slave(s), with wrappers bound around their heads, see: *ābaddha-śāṭaka*; female ~s as presents 43,234 and 240 (TP III 297); ~s wash dust of journey from king 18,113 (TP II 58); king loving a female ~ 57,52 (TP V 5); female ~ divided in two parts by brahmin brothers 62,176 (TP V 114); Mātāṅga king shows himself as ~ by putting his head on the ground 71,14 (TP VI 37); Vidyādhara ~, see: *dyu-cara-viṣṭi*
- slavery, money paid to king for redemption (*dāsyā-mukti*) of merchants from ~ 13,193 (TP I 164); Kadrū, mother of the snakes, makes Vinatā, mother of Garuḍa, a slave 90,97 (TP VII 55)
- slave trade, see: human trafficking
- sleep (*svāpa*), divine beings assume own form in ~ 32,30 (TP III 92)¹³⁸³; *vidyādhara* power of changing form suspended during ~ 33,177f. (TP III 122); wicked queen speaking in ~ while

¹³⁸¹ See ORC 1647; Rangarajan 2010.

¹³⁸² Doniger O'Flaherty 1976: 278f.

¹³⁸³ STh D 796.

drunk 39,207 (TP III 233); feigned ~ (*vyāja-supta*) 45,190 and 199 (TP IV 30f.); idem 46,174 and (*vyāja-nidrā*) 46,191 (TP IV 60f.); ~ (*nidrā*) refreshes the three worlds 61,330 (TP V 97); thinking of loved beauty prevents ~ as a goddess (*Nidrā*) to take possession of thinker 67,23 (TP V 197); ~ pretended (*alika-supta*) by unfaithful wife 77,57 (TP VI 187); ~ takes away all grief (*sarva-duḥkha-harā*) 104,189 (TP VIII 15)

sleeping (*suptavān*) with, see: cohabitation; sex

Sleeping Beauty,¹³⁸⁴ see: awaking princess; princess; Snow White

sleeplessness of princess out of terror (*a-nidrāiva bhītā*) 18,191 (TP II 64); ~ from anxiety 20,32 (TP II 97); ~ by mental fixation on desire 25,72 (TP II 195); ~ (*a-nidra*) due to doubt 27,33 (TP III 3); ~ due to impatience and anxiety 31,96 (TP III 89); ~ (*unnidra*) through absence of wife 37,216 (TP III 198); ~ because of worry about separation from beloved 38,78 (TP III 212) and 43,66 (TP III 285); goddess of sleep did not come to king (*Nidrā ... nāyayau*) 45,183 (TP IV 29); ~ of women due to admiration for man's beauty 45,296 (TP IV 37); ~ of king when hearing of many *vidyādhari*s given him in marriage 45,308 (TP IV 37); sleepless hero sees wonderful maiden enter chamber and feigns sleep 46,173f. (TP IV 60); ~ for grief at fallen kinsmen and for military discussions 47,95 (TP IV 73); ~ out of eagerness for battle and reason for story telling 49,2 (TP IV 85); ~ through separation from bride 51,116 (TP IV 130); ~ due to grief 55,144 (TP IV 212); sleepless wanderer 56,76 (TP IV 225); ~ of prince due to love of slave-girl 57,52 (TP V 5); 67,23 (TP V 197); ~ (*vinidratā*) of love-sick woman 71,96 (TP VI 42); ~ (*vinidro niśi*) of love-sick man 72,287 (TP VI 90); idem (*svāpaṃ jahau*) 73,359 (TP VI 126); princess is *vīta-nidrā* because brave kings are daily slain for her sake in battle 103,35 (TP VII 177); ~ of king seeing two golden *haṃsas* flying over at night 114,24 (TP VIII 134); ~ of prince due to fever of love 118,195 (TP VIII 191); ~ of brahmin due to fear of witches 123,200 (TP IX 57); – see also: story

slighted women, see: scorned women

Smara = Kāma; – see also: beauty

smara-bāṇa, see: arrow

smara-druma (not MW) ‘passion as large, strong, etc. as a tree’ 71,92 (TP VI 42)

smara-dvipa (not MW) ‘love as large, strong, etc. as an elephant’ 118,64 (TP VIII 189)

smara-graha, see: demon

smara-jvara ‘fever of love’ 17,77 (TP II 40); 73,358 (TP VI 126); 101,88 (TP VII 140); 118,195 (TP VIII 191)

smara-prekṣaṇaka (not MW) 114,64 (TP VIII 137 “to look lovingly”, note 1 “it may possibly mean: acted a love drama”; ORC 1196 “[ils offrent] le spectacle de leur amour”; 1508:

“qu’ils échangent des regards amoureux”; similarly M II 589);

smara-taru (not MW) ‘love as large as a tree’ 71,77 (TP VI 41)

smara-śara-jvara ‘fever produced by the arrows of love’ 117,95 (TP VIII 170)

smarāugha (not MW) (‘love as a stream’) 74,225 (TP VI 156);

¹³⁸⁴ Cf. Daś 128,9.

smell, conception by ~ of human sacrifice 13,64 (TP I 154); good body ~ (*śarīra-su-rabha*) of queen fragrant as *nīlōtpala* 16,28 (TP II 22)¹³⁸⁵; ~ of lake water betrays its being poisoned 37,86 (TP III 189); ~ of lotus frees boy from poison 56,129 (TP IV 229); *vidyādhari* with ~ of blue lotus (*utpala-saurabhā*) 59,4 (TP V 26); evil ~ of leper 64,131 (TP V 149); evil ~ (*visra*) of man emerged from fish stomach is as if washed off by tears of discoverer 74,196 (TP VI 154); sylph smells of goat 82,31 (TP VI 219)¹³⁸⁶; elephant driven furious by ~ of other elephant 89,14 (TP VII 41); – see also: body odour; elephant; fragrance; goat; ichor; perfume; poison; sweat

smelling, Namuci's horse Uccaiḥśravas reanimates dead *Asuras* by ~ them 46,224 (TP IV 63); ~ the head, see: kissing on the head; sniff-kiss

smile, white palaces as ~ of city 18,10 (TP II 50)¹³⁸⁷; goddess with ~ like a flower (*kusuma-smitā*) 81,48 (TP VI 212); Mt Kailāsa beautiful with ~ of northern quarter (*kauberī-hāsa*) 120,16 (TP IX 2); – cf. laughter

smiling, *yakṣa* leaves ~, being unable to prevent king from making gold out of copper 35,88 (TP III 162); king passing night ~ (*rātriṃ smayamāno nināya*)¹³⁸⁸ 53,189 (TP IV 181);

smoke, brahmin feeding only on ~, i.e. smoking (*dhūma-pa*) as austerity 7,53 (TP I 79)¹³⁸⁹; brides eyes red with ~ from marriage fire 14,30 (TP I 184); ~ reddens eyes 21,122 (TP II 134); dishevelled hair of flesh-eating *rākṣasa* on burning pyre compared to ~ 25,100 (TP II 197); princess compared to fire free from ~ (*vidhūma iva pāvakaḥ*) 28,77 (TP III 26); Namuci drinking ~, i.e. smoking, as an ascetic practice 46,218 (TP IV 63); black ~ of king's valour to be increased by sighs of enemies' widows¹³⁹⁰ 59,31 (TP V 28); ~ introduced in tree trunk kills man in it 60,230 (TP V 61); blue lotuses compared to ~ from the fire of snake poison 74,212 (TP VI 155); tears produced by contact with ~ (*dhūmāsaṅge*) 93,5 (TP VII 78); sighs of love-sick woman compared to ~ from fire of love 95,59 (TP VII 102); *vetāla* gratified by ~ (*dhūpa*) proceeding from burnt human eyes 99,14 (TP VII 123); after long fasting ~ rises from head of strict ascetic and Śiva-Śambhu manifests himself 115,48 (TP VIII 147);

smṛtāyāta, see: coming when thought of

snail (*śambūka*), Agni flees on *mandara* tree in form of ~ 20,77f. (TP II 101)

snake(s),¹³⁹¹ Śabara lives on dancing ~ (*bhujaṅgaṃ khelayan*) 9,76 (TP I 100); grateful ~

¹³⁸⁵ On the *odor di femina* see Schmidt 1904: 263. The lotus smell is given off by the *padmini* among the four types of women. – For a king's body odour see Rājat 2,122.

¹³⁸⁶ STh F 647.5.

¹³⁸⁷ See Chojnacki 2008: II note 2087.

¹³⁸⁸ The reason of his smiling, if the text is correct, is not given: in the previous sentence the king is thinking how to thank a brahmin who was prepared to sacrifice for him also his own life after that of his family; then smiling is no understandable reaction.

¹³⁸⁹ On smoking see Prakash 1961: 255ff.; Dallapiccola 2002: 65f.; Gode ???

¹³⁹⁰ This is a *śloka* recited by a parrot. The widows of the enemy kings apparently are no *satīs*.

¹³⁹¹ Cf. Hensgen 1958: 142ff.

speaking and giving lute with quarter-tone (*śruti-bhāga-vibhājita*) strings to saviour of its life 9,80 (TP I 100)¹³⁹²; city (i.e. its size) likened to ~ Ananta emerged from the earth 10,49 (TP I 109); colubrid¹³⁹³ (*duṇḍubha*) speaking with human voice: “~s and colubrids are different” 14,83f. (TP I 189); open white lotus is like the uplifted hoods of the ~ Śeṣa 19,73 (TP II 90); ~s spit venom over sun’s horses 22,183 (TP II 150); tongue of ~ split (*pāṭita-jihva*) 22,200 (TP II 152)¹³⁹⁴; Garuḍa devours ~s 22,201 (TP II 152); ~s revived after Garuḍa’s sprinkling *amṛta* along the seashore 22,248 (TP II 156); king dies struck by poisonous look (*dr̥ṣṭi-viṣa*) > laming stare of minister’s wife as by a female ~ 33,65 (TP III 111); woman slaying husband like female ~ (*bhujagī*) 34,181 (TP III 141) and 58,78 (TP V 20)¹³⁹⁵; ~ worshipped in snake-grove (*nāga-vana*) 34,188 (TP III 142)¹³⁹⁶; women unreliable like ~s 37,143 (TP III 193); ~ emerged at sacrifice to Agni becomes magic quiver (*tūṇa-ratna*) 46,77 (TP IV 54); black ~s turn into bow and bow-string 46,92f. (TP IV 55); ~ appearing on the right is evil omen 49,129 (TP IV 93); *nāgī* aunt protecting king advises him to propitiate Svāmikumāra for obtaining a son 55,152 (TP IV 212); enormous ~ rises from ground hole and hisses *vidyādhara*s away who try to seize it 56,63f. (TP IV 53); ~ seized becomes quiver 56,77 (TP IV 54); snake bites Nala and gives him fire-bleached garments (*agni-śaucākhyam vastra-yugam*) 56,351 (TP IV 245); woman in love with another man kills husband like a ~ (*anya-rakta-cittā strī-bhujangī hantī*) 58,78 (TP V 20); ~ eats heron’s (*baka*) young and is killed by mongoose 60,234 (TP V 61 with note 3); out of fear of Garuḍa in the form of a man ~ (*nāga*) flees to courtesan, but is found out and eaten 61,173ff. (TP V 82); ~ swallows brahmin and gives vessel of gold to his wife for alms 61,313 (TP V 95); *vidyādhara* king becomes ~ due to curse by Gotama 61,319 (TP V 96); in order to ride a ~ himself frog-king lets ~ eat his subjects 62,161 (TP V 112); ~ with two heads, one in its tail 63,175 (TP V 134); mongoose kills ~ near child and is rashly killed itself by its father 64,8 (TP V 138f.)¹³⁹⁷; ~ (*nāga*) in human shape bringing couch and woman out of his mouth 64,156 and spitting fire burns two people to ashes 158 (TP V 151); auto-biography of ~ 65,84ff. (TP V 161); ~ with three hoods fixed by spell 65,86 (TP V 161); ascetic cursed to be ~ with three hoods (*phaṇa*) coils around king 65,122 (TP V 164); entering unsuspected the house of a confiding man a wicked woman does not bring prosperity, any more than a female ~ entering a secluded place (? *kakṣāntara-praviṣṭēva bhujagī*)¹³⁹⁸ 68,49 (TP VI 5); ~ put in elephant’s ear kills it 69,69f. (TP VI 13); camel approaches (?) two ~s entwined about in

¹³⁹² Cf. STh B 211.14.

¹³⁹³ ORC 102 ‘*couleuvre*’; TP: ‘watersnake’; MW has: a kind of lizard.

¹³⁹⁴ See e.g. Stubbe-Diarra 1995: 73.

¹³⁹⁵ No female snake kills its partner like certain spiders do.

¹³⁹⁶ See, e.g. Haberman 2013 : 86.

¹³⁹⁷ See OTI 1958: B 331.

¹³⁹⁸ M II 21: “*Gleicht sie etwa nicht einer in einen Schlupfwinkel eingedrungenen Schlange ?*” TP renders *kakṣā* by „women’s apartments”, ORC 789 by “*gynécée*” which meanings are not in MW.

copulation 69,87 (TP VI 15; see s.v. camel supra); ~ with magic sword Vaidūryakānti 70,60 (TP VI 28); ~ curses prince and ministers to become blind and deaf for helping ascetic 70,75 (TP VI 29); ~ with white and black mouth symbolizing time (or, with TP, ORC 808 and M II 48: death)¹³⁹⁹ with good and evil fortune 70,92 and 111 (TP VI 30 and 32); unenterprising kings perish like ~ arrested by a charm (*mantra-baddha*) 71,104 (TP VI 43); black ~ painted on canvas near figure of painter's beloved as if to protect her 72,302 (TP VI 91); sword black as a ~ with slough cast 86,123 (TP VII 22), cf. 109,20 (TP VIII 71) where a king sees a sword looking like a mighty ~; dead ~ carried by kite poisons brahmin's food 87,43 (TP VII 32)¹⁴⁰⁰; Vāsuki offers Garuḍa one ~ every day at the southern sea (*dakṣiṇōda-dhi*) 90,101 (TP VII 56); ~s eaten by Garuḍa are revived by Gaurī 90,196 (TP VII 62)¹⁴⁰¹; thief's underground home with beautiful women and many jewels likened to city of ~ (*bhujāṅga-nagara*) 112,159 (TP VIII 119); – see also: krait snake-bite¹⁴⁰², sleeping queen of sonless king dies from ~ 6,90 (TP I 67) and is reanimated by antidotal (*viṣa-ghna*, 95) ring (*aṅgulīyaka*) put on her finger 10,97 (TP I 113); brahmin's bride bitten by ~ 14,80 (TP I 189) and 28,87 (TP III 26); 49,85 (TP IV 90); boy bitten by ~ is saved by smelling magic lotus 56,129 (TP IV 229); ~ bites Nala at his tenth step (*daśa*) in front of his forehead making him shrink, become deformed and black, and gives him two “fire-bleached” magic garments for recovering his natural shape 56,347-351 (TP IV 245); brahmin bitten by ~ wants to drown himself but is saved by toxicological knowledge (*viṣa-vidyā*) of Vikramakesarin 75,12ff. (TP VI 165); lover bitten by snake of passion (*rāga-mahā-vyāla*) 89,63 (TP VII 44); – see also: snake; woman snake charmer (*jīvāmi bhujagaṃ khelayan*) 9,76f. (TP I 100); ~ called for against snake poison (*viṣa-mantri*) 87,49 (TP VII 32) snake-cult 34,188 (TP III 142)¹⁴⁰³ snake-king bites Nala for his good 56,350 (TP IV 245) snake-princess (*nāga-kanyā*) receives white horse and sword from Gaurī 72,52 (TP VI 72); snake sacrifice (*sarpa-sattra*) by Janamejaya 30,41 (TP III 66); snake-skins (*nirmoka*) in holes in prison-walls 101,290 (TP VII 154); snake-weapon (*pannagāstra*) of *Asura* king 118,80 (TP VIII 183); *snāna-mṛttikā* (not MW) ‘(perfumed) bathing earth’ (as soap substitute), stuck on horns of deer coming with hermit boy 101,19 (TP VII 135)¹⁴⁰⁴ *snāna-velā* (not MW) ‘bathing time’, at midday warder announces ~ to king 86,24 (TP VII 14)¹⁴⁰⁵

¹³⁹⁹ Parallels ???

¹⁴⁰⁰ Cf. STh N 332.3.

¹⁴⁰¹ On birds and snakes see Doniger O'Flaherty 1981: 26 sub 30.

¹⁴⁰² As healing substances against snake-bite the Buddha is said to have recommended for monks a decoction of faeces, urine, ashes and clay (Karashima 2012: 157f. note 3 on § 18.53).

¹⁴⁰³ See König 1984: 223ff.

¹⁴⁰⁴ Cf. Bāṇa, *Kād.* 79.6 *snāna-mṛd.* Not in Gode's article on soap in Gode III 1969: 150ff.

snāna-yātrôtsava ‘bathing festival’ 104,86 (TP VIII 6)
 snare (*vyāja*), enemy minister lays ~ in the path of king Vatsa by poisoning water, grass, etc.
 19,80f. (TP II 91); women in a house are a ~ (*nibandhana*) 64,108 (TP V 148); – see
 further also: *pāśa*
snāyu-śeṣa (not MW), see: disease
 sneezing a hundred times 28,129f. (TP III 30 and Appendix I); – see also: *jīva* !
sneha-graha (not MW) ‘demon of love’ 61,167 (TP V 82)
sneha-śālin (not MW) ‘full of oil; full of affection’ 28,4 (TP III 18 note 2; II 166ff.)
 sniff-kiss,¹⁴⁰⁶ see: kissing on the head
 snow, fire feeling like ~ 92,76 (TP VII 76)
 Snow White, see: princess
 soap-substitute, see: *snāna-mṛttikā*
 social feeling, see: compassion; gestures; *para-hita*; *sarva-sattvārtha*
 social system offended (prince loves *cāṇḍāla* maiden) 112,74 (TP VIII 111)¹⁴⁰⁷; (princess
 loves *cāṇḍāla*) 112,93 (TP VIII 113); – see also: class; marriage
 soil, see: scratching
śoka-kanda (not MW) ‘lump of grief’, see: daughter
śokākṛānta (not MW) ‘shocked’ at seeing copulating snakes being eaten by camel 69,87 (TP
 VI 15)
śoka-sāgara, see: depression, sea of ~
 sole(s) of Svāmikumāra = Kārttikeya’s foot worshipped 2,60 (TP I 15); 55,155 (TP IV 212);
 ~ of Durgā 42,172 (TP III 271)
 solitude, *vidyādhara* king curses daughter to staying alone (*ekākinī*) 86,139 (TP VII 23)
 solstice, see: winter ~
 Soma, son of Rāma, by which brahmin author the summary of the Bṛhatkathā’s essence
 (*Bṛhatkathāyāḥ sārasya ... saṃgrahaḥ*), i.e. Kathāsaritsāgara was made E 12 (TP IX 89)
somaka ‘of the Somaka country’ (?) 72,191 (TP VI 82: ‘of the race of Soma’; ORC 839: “(*je suis ...*) *du pays de Somaka*”; M II 93: “(*ich gehöre dem*) *Geschlecht des Somaka (an)*”)
soma-loka, ‘world of the moon’, lords of Gandharvas go to the inviolable (*a-dhṛṣya*) ~ 115,78
 (TP VIII 149)
soma-prabhā ‘moonlight’ delightful to *cakoras* 114,22 (TP VIII 134)
 son,¹⁴⁰⁸ desire for ~ by heirless king 9,8ff. (TP I 95); ~ produced by sacrifice to procure ~
 (*putrīyêṣṭi*) 13,58 (TP I 153)¹⁴⁰⁹; single ~ immolated to get other sons by harem becoming

¹⁴⁰⁵ In Bāṇa, *Kād.* 28,2 the midday conch (*madhyāhna-saṅkha*) announces the king’s bathing time. The conch is of course a (sea-)water product.

¹⁴⁰⁶ Cf. Daṇḍin, *Daś* 39,8 etc. (see Bollée 2008a: 28 s.v. smelling); McHugh 2012: 13.

¹⁴⁰⁷ At *Kād.* 24,5 king Śūdraka regrets he cannot have sex with a Mātāṅga girl.

¹⁴⁰⁸ See ORC 1565f. s.v. *Enfant*; Michaels 2004: 100ff. for the different, Indian, relation of son to parents; Bollée 2008a: 9 note 27.

¹⁴⁰⁹ Cf. STh J 2067.1.

pregnant at the smell of its sacrifice 13,64 (TP I 154); ~ predicted by Śiva 19,7 (TP II 85) and 21,35 (TP II 128); many ~s are the effect of many pre-birth offences 21,138 (TP II 135); ~ given by Śiva in the form of a fruit in a dream 21,144 (TP II 136); ~ stopped from killing father 25,108 (TP II 199); a ~, being embodied joy, is far superior to a daughter, who is but a lump of grief 28,6 (TP III 18); ~s eat father like crabs 28,48 (TP III 23); begetting ~ less important for the hereafter than marriage of daughter 28,50 (TP III 24); only ~ 28,114 (TP III 29); ~ promised by Śiva 35,104 (TP III 164); ~ grows like new moon fills out with digits and causes tide 35,114 (TP III 164); ~ as second self of father 49,194 (TP IV 98); ~ made of *kuśa* grass by Vālmiki for Sītā 51,92 (TP IV 128); ~ to be sacrificed to Caṇḍikā-Durgā in order to save king 53,133 (TP IV 177); ~ obtained by propitiating Svāmikumāra-Kārttikeyya 55,170-2 (TP IV 212); parents curse disobedient ~ 56,150 (TP IV 230)¹⁴¹⁰; ~ of less than 16 years taught courtesans' skill 57,66 (TP V 6); Śrī conceives mind-born ~ by looking at chaste ascetic 59,95f. (TP V 33), cf. mind-born ~ of chaste father 61,250 (TP V 89)¹⁴¹¹; ~ killed by fool 61,242 (TP V 88); ~ killed by wicked astrologer as a deceitful display of skill 61,256 (TP V 90); sons banished by remarried father 65,3f. (TP V 154); *vidyādhara* father curses disobedient ~ to become mortal 65,60 (TP V 159); brahmin father curses disobedient ~ to become lion 65,63 (TP V 159); king desiring ~ worships Lakṣmī daily with 108 white lotus 69,78 (TP VI 14); brahmin's ~ seized by *brahma-rākṣasa* 72,153 (TP VI 80); depression because of having no ~ 73,28 (TP VI 102); ~ predicted by Agni in dream 73,59f. (TP VI 105); parents put ~ for adoption on pitcher with gold 73,62 (*hema-kumbha* 73,65; TP VI 105); king has brahmins sacrifice for ~ 74,42 (TP VI 143); wicked ~ as gambler robs his mother's garments 75,95 (TP VI 171); ~less king propitiates Śiva 83,8 (TP VII 2); Bhairava gives ~less merchant one hundred ~s and revives robber husband as boon to faithful wife 88,49f. (TP VII 38); king obtains ~ from wishing tree 90,8 (TP VII 49); only ~ (*kulāikatanta*) Śāṅkhacūḍa to be eaten by Garuḍa 90,120 (TP VII 57); ~lessness as only grief of king 93,6 (TP VII 78); dying thief without ~ thinks that, when he marries, his wife's ~ (*putraṃ kṣetra-jam*) of what ever father will be his 93,21 (TP VII 79); only ~ of a hundred wishes (*manoratha-śatair*) 97,9 dies with sixteen years of fever 97,11 (TP VII 112f.); ~ marries mother 98,54 (TP VII 119); ~less king 101,379 (TP VII 160); only ~ born from brahmin parents in middle life (*vayasi madhyame*) 104,20 (TP VIII 2); only ~ of prostitute gets sweet (*modaka*) every day 106,96 (TP VIII 35); ~ of Agni and brahmin maiden (*Pāvaka-sūnu*) reared by *caṇḍālas* 112,108 (TP VIII 114); ~ born of father whose youth had gone (*yauvanāpagame*) 113,21 (TP VIII 125); brahmin asks for and obtains little ~s from father 113,61 (TP VIII 128); ~less Daitya king propitiates Brahmā at Ganges for one hundred years and obtains an invulnerable ~ 15,4 (TP VIII 144); Śiva promises ~ as boon to Gandharva king 115,86 (TP VIII 150); anxiety of ~less king 118,13 (TP VIII 179); ~s older than father 123,52 (TP IX 46); brahmin ~ is fool (*mūrkhā*) 124,104 (TP IX 76); – sacrifice

¹⁴¹⁰ See Boss 1976: 107.

¹⁴¹¹ Doniger O'Flaherty 1981: 67.

of one ~ to get another cf. 13,63 (TP I 154)
śoṇa-vaḍavā (not MW), see: *kṛṣṇa-turagī*
 song, unmarried maiden of good family is like ~ without tune (*sthāna-prāpti-vihinā gītvat kula-kanyakā*) 24,25 (TP II 172; ORC 206: “*un chant discordant*”; M I 296: “*Gesang mit falscher Einstimmung*”); ~ (*āryā*) in Prākṛit sung by sulking queen 55,125f. (TP IV 210); singing *divya-kanyā* in front of *līṅga* 59,81 (TP V 32); mermaid on wishing-tree sings ~ on truth of karman doctrine 86,44f. (TP VII 16); morning ~ for prince 103,212ff. (TP VII 189); ~s pierce the ear of man separated from his beloved like needles (*gītāni śruti-sūcayāḥ*) 104,75 (TP VIII 6); ~ of Hāhā and Hūhū 116,87 (TP VIII 162);
 son-in-law appointed successor of sonless king 72,90 (TP VI 75)
 sonless king propitiates Ambikā 42,56 (TP III 263); ~ brahmin minister begs brahmin foundling children from *vaiśya* 56,44 (TP IV 222f.); ~ man¹⁴¹² does not reach the (heavenly) worlds (*aśnute lokān*) 93,21 (TP VII 79 “does not inherit worlds of bliss”)¹⁴¹³; Vṛṣa-dhvaja (Śiva) orders ~ king, who is tormented with anxiety to get a son (*suta-cintātura*), in a dream to pick up child at palace gate 93,52 (TP VII 82), cf. 118,13 (TP VIII 179);
 sonlessness causes charity (in the expectation to be given then son in turn ?) 35,34 (TP III 157); – see also: generosity
sopāna, see: ladder; stairs
 sorrow, see: grief; suicide
 soul, second, external to the body (*prāṇān iva bahiś-carān*)¹⁴¹⁴, compared to the money of a brahmin miser 33,156 (TP III 120); – see also: *antar-ātman*
 sound (*śabda*), the might of creatures is proportionate to the ~ they utter 60,51 (TP V 45); ~ of machines (*yantra*) is terrible 60,55 (TP V 45); ~ of pestle (*musala-dhvani*) causes bruises on hands of delicate queen 85,23-6 (TP VII 11); – see also: anger; drum; jackal; lyre; noise; omen; labor
 south, king goes alone to the ~ to fetch corpse from *śiṃśapā* tree 75,49f. (TP VI 167)
 southern district 110,97 (TP VIII 89)
 southern quarter, region, see: *dakṣiṇa-dik*, *-patha*; *dakṣiṇā āśā*; Deccan; quarter
 southern sea (*dakṣiṇôdadhi*), see: *nāga*
 southern style of singing (*dakṣiṇaṃ mārgaṃ svāra-tāla-pādaiḥ*)¹⁴¹⁵ 120,121 (TP IX 10; cf. 123,132 [TP IX 52]);
 sow (*sūkarī*), rebirth as ~ 53,119 prevented by Śiva’s favour 125 (TP IV 176)
 speaking after birth, said of baby daughter 17,66 (TP II 39); by ~ to sinful woman Bodhisattva loses power 65,100 (TP V 162)

¹⁴¹² See, e.g. ORC 1565 s.v. *Enfant*.

¹⁴¹³ ORC 1000: “*on n’ accède pas aux séjours célestes.*” – Cf. AitBr 7,13 *nāputrasya loko ’stīti; tat sarve paśavo viduḥ*.

¹⁴¹⁴ Cf. STh *E 710ff.

¹⁴¹⁵ See Pesch 2009: 42ff.

speaking animals: boar and elephant 123,121 (TP IX 51); – see also: snake
speaking birds,¹⁴¹⁶ see also: language; parrot;
speaking tree, see: wishing tree
spectacle (*prekṣaṇakam*) in temple 57,74 (TP V 6); evening ~ in Śiva temple 123,129 (TP IX 52)
spectators, gods as ~ of battle 50,2 (TP IV 108), 109,51 and 122 (TP VIII 74 and 79);
Brahmā, Rudra, etc. as ~ of battle 115,26 (TP VIII 146); do, of Śarva, Śauri and Pitāmaha 116,68 (TP VIII 161); Rudra and Indra as ~ of battle between *Asuras* and men 118,74 (TP VIII 183);
speech, goddess of ~, see Sarasvatī; Vāc
speech (*gir*) of Prajāpati Dakṣa is like a poisoned needle (*viṣa-sūcikā*) piercing Pārvatī's ear 1,37 (TP I 5)¹⁴¹⁷; ~ not restrained by women 1,52 (TP I 6); inarticulate ~ (*an-abhivyakta-vāca*) of frogs, (*jihvā-viparyāsa*) parrots and elephants 20,77-79 (TP II 101); ~ of wishing-tree promising son's birth 22,20 (TP II 138); who is not deceived by the hypocritically affectionate ~es (*vākya*) of a mother ? 29,82 (TP III 45); king should try ~ of ministers 34,195 (TP III 143); monkey with intelligence and articulate ~ (*prājñō 'pi vyakta-vāg*) 37,118 (TP III 191); king hears wicked queen's ~ in her sleep 39,209 (TP III 233); king utters feigned ~ (*kṛtakam abhyadāt*) 39,232 (TP III 234); golden city with wooden automata as inhabitants lacking ~ as sign of life (*nirjīva iti vāg-virahāt*) 43,11 (TP III 281); prince enrages *vidyādhara* females with sportive, sarcastic ~ (*narma-vaktrōkti*) 44,52 (TP IV 4); ~ of enraged *vidyādhara* females, the syllables of which falter on their trembling lips 44,53 (TP IV 5); head wives address king with playfully sarcastic, sweet, affectionate and bashful turns of speech (*sa-narma-vaktra-madhura-snigdha-mugdhair vacaḥ-kramaiḥ*) 50,162 (TP IV 118); hypocritical (*kṛtrima*) ~ of adulterous wife 62,113 (TP V 108); articulate ~ of animals¹⁴¹⁸ 65,55 (TP V 158); king hears ~ of two Siddhas in the shape of *haṃsas* 72,186 (TP VI 82); elephant speaks *vyaktayā girā* to blind man 74,6 (TP VI 141), cf. 123,121 (TP IX 51); Deccan *vaiśya* knowing ~ of animals and birds 83,26 (TP VII 3); man is smitten by wife's thunderbolt of ~ (*vaco-vajra-pāta*) 84,39 (TP VII 7); (~ as fluid) brahmins ears are filled with nectar of ~ of princess 89,49 (TP VII 43), cf. 106,27 (TP VIII 30); ministers understanding cries of birds 101,49 (TP VII 137); flowers of ~ (*vāk-puṣpa*) 109,98 (TP VIII 77); ~ from heaven calls upon king to perform his coronation as emperor on Mt Rṣabha 110,47 (TP VIII 85); king asks *lokapālas* about his duty 112,135 (TP VIII 116); – see also: speaking; voice
spell(s)¹⁴¹⁹ to produce dreams (*svapna-māṇavaka*) 6,137 (TP I 70) and 72,103 (TP VI 76); ~ for breaking through walls and rending fetters 12,42 (TP I 136); ~ to alter shape 12,50 (TP I 136); idem (*yogaṃ rūpa-vivartanam*) 16,10 (TP II 20); minister gives king ~ to conquer

¹⁴¹⁶ STh B 210ff.

¹⁴¹⁷ See further Bollée 2010a : 152 note 158.

¹⁴¹⁸ ORC 879; Penzer's note in TP II 107f. and IV 145 note.

¹⁴¹⁹ Cf. ORC 1605.

woman which ~ were attached to strings of her lute 12,64 (TP I 138); ~ to propitiate Agni (*Agner ārādhana*) 17,97 (TP II 42); brahmin gives merchant ~ to keep nymph (*divyā strī*) 17,120ff. (TP II 43f.); ~ of *vidyādhari* to make invisible 18,227 (TP II 67); ~ to drive away *rākṣasas* (*rakṣo-ghna*) 20,138 (TP II 106); ~ enabling (witches) to fly (*utpatana-mantra*) overheard 20,140f. (TP II 107); ~ forgotten (*śruta-vismṛtam*)¹⁴²⁰ 20,159 (TP II 109); ~ to return to earth given by *siddha* 20,178 (TP II 111); minister gives queen ~ for sporting in the air (*nabhaḥ-kriḍā*) 22,11f. (TP II 138); ~ muttered by hermit 26,198 (TP II 232); ~ pronounced by *yakṣiṇī* dancing outside magic circle produces horns on forehead of ascetics 37,58 (TP III 187); ~ (*mantra-prayoga*) to turn man into ape 37,110 (TP III 191); ~ to return to embalmed previous body 45,50f. (TP IV 20); sound expressed by *anu svāra* (*nādo bindu-pathāśritaḥ*) becomes ~ of force in magic sciences (*vidyādi-mantratām eti*) 46,116 (TP IV 56); ~ to counteract poison 49,41 (TP IV 88) and 69,60 (TP VI 13)¹⁴²¹; Buddhist monk gives brahmin spell for obtaining *yakṣiṇī* 49,180 (TP IV 97); ~ to propitiate Svāmikumāra-Skanda 49,237 (TP IV 101); ~ with *āryā* spoken over water asking Cāmuṇḍā's help to resuscitate woman 52,158 (TP IV 149); ~ to propitiate *yakṣa* to give boon 56,94 (TP IV 226); ~ for destroying *rākṣasas* 62,97 (TP V 107); ~ of miser makes even stone (*grāvan*) laugh 63,162 (TP V 133); Caṇḍikā gives robber bewildering ~ (*moha-mantra*) 64,81 (TP V 146); life-prolonging ~ (*kāla-saṃkarṣiṇī vidyā*) 68,65 (TP VI 6); ~ makes cobra creep into bamboo 69,69 (TP VI 13); ~ (*abhicāra*) of son against father 70,10 (TP VI 23); hermit knows many ~s (*nānā-mantrāugha-siddhimān*) 70,55 (TP VI 28); oblation with snake-subduing (*nāga-damana*) ~ for conquering earthquakes, etc. 70,67 (TP VI 29); heavenly nymph mutters ~ causing infatuation 70,69 (TP VI 29); unenterprising kings perish like snakes arrested by a ~ (*mantra-baddha*) 71,104 (TP VI 43); ~ of controlling attendant of fever demon 71,207 (TP VI 50); ~ depicted on eight lotus leaves 71,216 (TP VI 51); ~ to grow barley 71,266 (TP VI 55); ~ to get *yakṣiṇī* into one's power 73,25 (TP VI 102); ~ in Pātālaśāstra to propitiate Śiva 73,104 (TP VI 108); gate opens when guarding rams are hit on their head with charmed (*nyasta-mantra*) *daṇḍa* 73,132 (TP VI 110f.); charmed (*sa-mantra*) black antelope skin averts bees 73,173 (TP VI 114); Gaṅgā gives brahmin ~ (*vidyā*) of seven syllables for visibility, utterable as *pratiloma* and *anuloma* 74,133ff. (TP VI 149); idem 74,230 and 234 (TP VI 157); brahmin gives ~ to master Vetālas (*vetāla-sādhana-mantra*) 75,16 (TP VI 165); ascetic heats prongs of his trident with a ~ and marks a witch on the loins (*jaghana-sthala*) 75,176 (TP VI 176); reanimating ~, recited from book and pronounced over dust thrown over ashes to raise the dead 76,21 (TP VI 180); ascetic steals book with reanimating ~ 76,25 (TP VI 180); ~ given to unfit person is lost also to teacher 92,86 (TP VII 77); *vetāla* as sovereign of ~s (*mantrādhirāja*) 99,25 (TP VII 122); ~ against poisonous snake bite 99,47 (TP VII 126); *kāpālīka* tries to enchant *yakṣa* princess with a regular (*krama-siddha*) ~ muttered in a circle 121,13 (TP IX 13); ~ (*śakti*) able to keep off witches 123,226 (TP IX 59); ~ will

¹⁴²⁰ Text: -vismṛtam.

¹⁴²¹ Cf. Kathākośa (Hoffmann 1974) 249,24 *viṣāpahāra-mantra*.

- bestow good fortune (*vidhiḥ śreyo vidhāsyati*) 123,226 (TP IX 59); – see also: *datta-dṛi-mantra*; oblation; *siddhi*
- sperma substitute, see: sacrifice (*iṣṭi*)
- sphuraḍ-ḍamarukā-rava* (the *kāpālika* came there with ...) ‘with rebounding noise of drum’ 124,8 (TP IX 68: “the booming drum in his hand”, ORC 1306: “*il battait son tambour*”; M II 745: “*in seinen Händen trug er eine dröhnende Trommel*”)
- spiders, bees turned into ~ 70,90 (TP VI 30); ~ entering a hollow coral rod (*daṇḍaṃ suṣira-vaidrumam*) 70,96 (TP VI 31)
- spies, see: spy
- spirits, see: wine
- spitting betel, see: betel
- splendour, celestial ~ (*divyā vibhūti*) of emperor 110,122 (TP VIII 91)
- split person, see: boy; heritage
- spoiled, see: *prema-durlalita*
- sporting in gardens is like a wave of the sea of infancy (*laharī śaiśavāmbudheḥ*) 28,99 (TP III 27);
- spot, see: mole
- spring, princess looking like beauty of ~ in bodily form (*sākṣād iva madhu-śrī*) 10,88 (TP I 112)¹⁴²²; concert (*saṃgīta*) held by singing *kinnarīs*, koels and bees in honour of ~ as king of seasons (*ṛtu-rājā*) 54,56 (TP IV 188)¹⁴²³; ~ refreshes female cuckoo (*madhuḥ pika-vadhūm iva*) 56,196 (TP IV 234); description of pomp of ~ 71,197ff. (TP VI 50); (brahmin) united (*yuktaḥ*) with *siddhā* is like a banyan with ~ (*madhu*) 73,27 (TP VI 102); ~ procession festival (*madhu-māse yātrōtsava*) 89,6 (TP VII 40); lover compared to (deity of) ~ retired to the forest through disgust at the burning of the body of Kāma 90,47 (TP VII 52); lion of ~ (*madhu-kesarī*) slays elephant of winter (*hemanta-hastin*) 91,20f. (TP VII 67); let ~ flower be united to ~ (said of princely couple: *yujyatām madhunā ... mādhavi latā*) 101,103 (TP VII 141); **description** 111,18ff. (TP VIII 97)¹⁴²⁴; in the season of ~, the fire of separation is intolerable to all creatures 111,47 (TP VIII 99); in the absence of Hara-Śiva Devī is troubled by the advent of ~ (*madhu-prāpti-sōdvegā*) 114,58 (TP VIII 136); at ~ King Vikramāditya marries 122,8 (TP IX 34);
- spring festival (*madhūtsava*), in the first watch of night of the ~ all citizens are excited 4,35 (TP I 33); *vasanta-samayōtsava*, king goes with harem in heavenly garden at ~ 6,108 (TP I 68) and 85,6 (TP VII 10); (*madhu-māsa-mahōtsava*) 10, 87 (TP I 112); woman on the roof looking at ~ 17,72 (TP II 40); – see also: Holī
- spurned women, see: scorned women
- spy (*cāra*), spies assuming the vows of skull-bearing Śaiva mendicants (*dhṛta-kāpālika-vrata*) 19,74 (TP II 90); ~ with signature verse discovers Nala disguised as cook (*sūda*) 56,356

¹⁴²² Jackmuth 2002: 99ff.

¹⁴²³ Cf. STh H 641.1; Jackmuth 2002: 63.

¹⁴²⁴ Cf. Ṛtusamhāra VI.

(TP IV 247); ~ reports of queen's death 58,37 (TP V 17); woman in ascetic disguise acts as ~ 71,130 (TP VI 45); spies sent to princess' chamber discover lover 74,243ff. (TP VI 158); brahmin spies disguised as ascetics 103,12 (TP VII 176); confidante of princess spies out prince in enemy camp 103,21ff. (TP VII 176)

*śrāddha*¹⁴²⁵ 'regular ceremony for the benefit of the ancestors' (MW) on 13th day 5,112 (TP I 56); parody of ~ 61,196ff. (TP V 85); king performs ~ in Prayāga 93,80 and Gayā 93,87 (TP VII 84); – see also: obsequies

śramaṇa, Buddhist merchant honours ~s 27,18 (TP III 2); brahmin makes friends with ~s who teach him *upoṣaṇa* vow 63,75 (TP V 125); ~ bitten by dog sounds gong of *vihāra* 65,132 (TP V 165)

śravaṇa-mūla, old age reaches root of king's ear 103,224 (TP VII 190)

śravaṇa-phala 'fruit of hearing' (not MW) of the Vetāla-pañcaviṃśati-kathā, which frees from *pāpa*, given to king Trivikramasena 99,22 and 27 (TP VII 123f.); last stanza of ch. 124 *śramāpanoda* 'dispelling of weariness' (not MW) of husband as wife's duty, "who will attend on you to remove your weariness?" (*kas te ~āya paricaryāṃ kariṣyati ?*) 56,320 (TP IV 243; ORC 640: "Qui s'occupera de te délasser?")

śṛgālī (female jackal) turned into she-elephant 68,17ff. (TP VI 2)

Śrī (goddess of Fortune) propitiated by burnt-offerings (*homa*) appears in vivo (*sākṣād*) 10,9 (TP I 106); ~ dwells in the *nagarī* of Timirā, ihrem *mandira* 17,33 (TP II 36); king as vessel (*bhājanam*) of ~ 34,205 (TP III 144); ~ imprisoned in king's treasury (*koṣa*) 43,21 (TP III 282); ~ by auspicious viewing (*darśana*) of celibate hermit gives him spiritual son (*putram mānasam*) 59,95ff. (TP V 33); when the fickle ~ places her feet at the same time upon two exalted persons she will abandon one of the two 60,118 (TP V 51); divine woman taking the pride of beauty of ~ (*āpnuhi divyāṃ rūpa-darpa-harāṃ Śrīyaḥ*) 69,110 (TP VI 16); city of Vidiśā as pleasure-ground of ~ 71,72 (TP VI 40); – see also: *dyūta-lilā*; (goddess of) Fortune

Śrīkaṇṭha (Śiva), Vilāsapura home of ~ 40,42 (TP III 243)

śrīvṛkṣa 'curl of hair on an excellent horse's chest'¹⁴²⁶ 18,88 (TP II 56)

śṛṅga-māṃsa (not MW) 'flesh in the horns' (?), physician gives sonless queen (aphrodisiacum for women in the shape of) a powder mix made of ~ of a wild he-goat (*śṛṅga-māṃsataḥ ... cūrṇa-miśraṃ*) 39,17 (TP III 219 "fleshy part of the horns"; ORC 397: "la chair contenue dans les cornes"; M I 555: "aus dem Knochenmark der Hörner ein Elixier")

śrotra-dāruṇa (not MW) 'terrible to the ears', opp. of *śruti-sukha* (q.v) 104,64 (TP VIII 5)

śrotrāmṛta, see: nectar

śruti 'quarter tone' lute with ~ (*śruti-bhāga-vibhājita*) strings 9,80 (TP I 100); princess joins notes (*svara*) to ~s, like Sarasvatī 106,24 (TP VIII 29);

śruti-sukha 'pleasure to the ears,' musician gives short ~ 63,161 (TP V 133); – for the opp. see: *śrotra-dāruṇa*

¹⁴²⁵ Hanchett 1988: 220f. illustrates the foods on leaves for ancestor meals. On *śrāddha* see Gonda 1980: 441ff.

¹⁴²⁶ See Caland 2010.

staff of acacia wood (*khādira-daṇḍa*) as weapon 53,21 (TP IV 169; cf. *laguḍa* in vs 15);
stag party, see: bachelor's party
stair(s) (*sopāna*), in a palace garden in the Rasātalas (hells) 118,106 (TP VIII 185)
stambha-putrikā 'maiden carved on the pillars of a temple' weeping 121,179 (TP IX 25); ~
of extraordinary beauty 123,136 (TP IX 53); 124,27 (TP IX 70);
*stambha-stha-putrikā*¹⁴²⁷ 123,133 (TP IX 52); 124,26 (TP IX 70);
stana-taṭa 'banks of breasts' 27,65 (TP III 6); – cf. Amaru 55 and 61
stanza, see: *āryā*; *gāthā*
starvation, see: death; suicide
statecraft (*mantra*), main element of ~ is averting misfortune (*mukhyam aṅgaṃ mantrasya
vinipāta-pratikriyā*) 15,113 (TP II 11); – see also: policy
stealing, ~ horse (*vāhana*, cf. 103 *haya-caura*) 30,101 (TP III 71); prince ~ ornaments from
princess 75,160 (TP VI 175); *vidyādhara* prince ~ brahmin wife 87,9 (TP VII 29);
Marubhūti ~ garments of bathing nymph in order to get information about his master
108,68 (TP VIII 58); 121,112 (TP IX 20); – see also: robber
stepmother, see: *apara-mātar*
sternutatory made of plant extract (*oṣadī-rasa-nasya*) turns boa into man 123,46 (TP IX 46)
stick, magic ~ (*yaṣṭi*), whatever is written (*likhyate*) with ~ turns out true 3,47 (TP I 22); –
see also: *daṇḍa*; gold stick; pupil
stiffness of bosoms in Ujjayinī 92,11 (TP VII 71)
stolen, garments ~ from bathing *apsaras*¹⁴²⁸, see: garment; stealing
stomach, of fish compared to womb 25,52 (TP II 193); Viṣṇu's ~ is egg of Brahmā 54,33 (TP
IV 186); ~ of fish (*minōdara*) 74,196 (TP VI 154); man emerges from killed elephant's ~
123,87 and couple from boar's ~ 123,90 (TP IX 49); – see also: paunch
stomach-fire, see: *jaṭharāgni*
stones (*pāṣāṇa*) laughing at fool 61,246 (TP V 89); ~ (*grāvan*) laughing at miser's speech
63,162 (TP V 133); even ~ melt when fate is propitious 108,92 (TP VIII 61); rain of ~ in
combat 116,74 (TP VIII 162); – see also: laughing
storm, furious ~ (*pracaṇḍaś ca prabhañjanaḥ*) blows like Destiny whirling up light objects and
hurling down heavy 25,42 (TP II 192); hit by mighty ~ (*vāyunā balinā*) ship (*yāna-pātra*)
sinks 52,324 (TP IV 161); – see also: wind
story, Kāṇabhūti writes ~ with his own blood in the forest 8,3 (TP I 89); ~ unbearable as
venom in one's breast (*vytāntaṃ vakṣaḥ-stha-viṣa-duḥsaham*) 19,47 (TP II 88); hermit asks
pupils to tell odd ~ (*a-pūrvam ikṣitaṃ kiṃcic chrutaṃ*) 66,3 (TP V 178)¹⁴²⁹;— stories,
see: tale(s)
storyteller (*kathaka*) 10,2 (TP I 106); 12,76 (TP I 138); 68,16 (TP VI 2)
straw, see: grass

¹⁴²⁷ Cf. *śāla-bhañjikā*.

¹⁴²⁸ STh K 1335; T 56.3.

¹⁴²⁹ Cf. Daś 124.3. In her book *Number Our Days* (1978) Barbara Myerhoff styled the Indian as *homo narrans*.

stream of water (*jalâughah*) in dream means battle 46,143 (TP IV 58)¹⁴³⁰
streets (*rathyā*), ~ irrigated with sandelwood water 44,74 (TP IV 6); out of shame brahmin
maiden flings Agni's baby in the ~ 112,104 (TP VIII 113);
stri-citta ('a woman's mind'), who knows mysterious way of ~ ? 71,236 (TP VI 53);
stri-ghna, Kāma as killer of women 117,65 (TP VIII 168)
string(s) of dry cow's sinew (*tantrī*) bitten off and fastened to lyre by *vidyādhari* cause her
mortal rebirth in a fisher family 26,170 (TP II 230)¹⁴³¹; magic ~ around neck (*kaṇṭha-sūtra*)
turns man into ape 37,137 (TP III 191)¹⁴³²; Bhavānī gives bride a ~ of jewels that
preserve youth 50,139 (TP IV 117); king removes ~ around neck of peacock which then
turns into king's minister 71,56 (TP VI 40);
stri-tṛṇa (not MW) 'woman, valueless as a straw'¹⁴³³ 21,81 (TP II 131)
strongroom (*koṣa-veśman*) of *purohita* for deposits 24,133 (TP II 179)
stupid, villager ~ as an animal 61,27 (TP V 70); ~ bald man believes in drug producing hair
61,181 (TP V 83); ~ servant tastes *āmalakas* 61,296f. (TP V 94); – see also: hospitality
stupidity connected with muddling one's head with the Vedas 6,62 (TP I 65)
stuti, see: hymn of praise
stylistic repetition,¹⁴³⁴ see: *janmani janmani*; *pade pade*
subaqueous palace 86,91 and 94 (TP VI 19f.); submarine fire
śubhāgama (not MW), see: omen
subjects, king like cloud raining gold on dependents (*anujīviṣu*) 18,50 (TP II 53); ~ (*prajāḥ*)
are king's cows of plenty 72,220 (TP VI 85); (*paurāḥ*) tell king to take back state elephant
given away by his son or to set up another king 113,45 (TP VIII 127); ~ as human animals
(*ṅṛ-paśu*) 113,49 (TP VIII 127)
submarine fire (*vaḍavā*)¹⁴³⁵ 26,10 (TP II 217); lord of the fishermen (*dāśa-pati*) falls into
mouth of ~ 26,137ff. (TP II 227)
substantives instead of augmentative suffixes, see: elephant; fire; forest; lion; ocean; sea; snake;
tree; wheel; wishing-tree
substitute burned to conceal king 15,99 (TP II 10); – see also: palace burnt; – prince killed as
~ for victim of human sacrifice 20,207 (TP II 113)
substitution of children in the mother's womb by *māyā* of deities 34,44 (TP III 131) and 65
(TP III 133); 110,71 (TP VIII 87)¹⁴³⁶
success (*ṛddhi*), see: *a-dharma*; – see also: destiny

¹⁴³⁰ Cf. *āhavārṇava* 'sea of battle' 116,67 (TP VIII 161), etc.

¹⁴³¹ Fishermen are low-caste, sons of female slaves (*dāsyāḥ sutāḥ*), as killers of living beings (*prāṇi-ghātinah*) 27,125f. (TP III 10).

¹⁴³² STh D 585. On the magical power of strings see Weinrich 1909: 97 ("Bindezauber"); Zachariae 1977: 529.

¹⁴³³ Cf. Bāṇa, *Kād.* 13,4 *tṛṇam iva straiṇam*.

¹⁴³⁴ Gonda 1959: 324ff.

¹⁴³⁵ See Saletore 1936; Doniger O'Flaherty 1973: 286f.

¹⁴³⁶ For this motif see Bollée 2005: ???

Sudarśana, Viṣṇu's weapon¹⁴³⁷ 50,55 (TP IV 111)

śuddhānta-vidhvamsin (not MW) 'violator of the royal harem' 71,303 (TP VI 58)

Sudhāhartṛ, see: Garuḍa; nectar

sudhā-varṣa 'rain of nectar' in king's ear 44,21 (TP IV 2)¹⁴³⁸

śūdra weaver (of five garments daily) 52,99 (TP IV 144) and as suitor from Deccan of Ujjain princess 83,22 (TP VII 3)

suffering (*duḥkha*), see: grief

Sugata = Buddha, even ~ has no compassion to one of small pre-birth karma 117,32 (TP VIII 166); even ~ would loose his self-restraint (*saṃyama*) if loved by beautiful princess 117,75 (TP VIII 169);

Sugatāṃśa, see: *Buddhāṃśa*; incarnation

*Sugatāśa*¹⁴³⁹ (not MW) 'who wishes to become a Buddha' (? Probably w.r.) 72,234 (TP VI 85 'incarnation of Buddha'; omitted in ORC 841; M II 97: "*Teil des Buddha*"), cf. 237

Sugatāṃśa-ja;

suicide¹⁴⁴⁰ [I: as such or committed] ~ of seven princesses on charnel ground who then reach highest beatitude (*saṃsiddhi paramā*) 28,43 (TP III 23); ~ of female goose into sea 43,164 (TP III 292); ; ~s (*ātma-ghātin*) suffer in next world more than here 49,227 (TP IV 101), cf. 96,20; ~ of woman on pyre with husband's permission because of her children's death 53,160 (TP IV 179); ~ of couple by entering fire after attack by robbers 69,128 (TP VI 18); brahmin couple commit ~ by poison because they were distressed (*saṃtāpa*) 72,214 (TP VI 84: "because of wrong judgement"; ORC 840: "*Dans leur désarroi devant ce verdict*"; M II 95: "*aus Kummer und Schmerz über dieses Urteil*"; ~ in fire (*vahni*) of old brahmin and two wives 73,418 (TP VI 130); prince as ~ by jumping into Ganges 74,34 (TP VI 143); wife harassed by mother-in-law hangs herself 74,163 (TP VI 152); man commits ~ in order to obtain salvation (*siddhi*) from Devī by cutting off his head with a sword followed by his brother-in-law; the heads though fastened to the chain of the temple bell fall on the ground 80,29ff. (TP VI 206)¹⁴⁴¹; ~ of *senāpati* by entering fire out of

¹⁴³⁷ Whitaker 2000: 90.

¹⁴³⁸ Bollée 2010a : 160 note 273.

¹⁴³⁹ *Sugata* + *āśā* or *āśa* stands for *aṃśa* (see BHSD 109 s.v.).

¹⁴⁴⁰ See, e.g., Mayer 2010; Chapple 1993 and Hansen 1992: 19. Suicide in India is beyond the world average presently every four minutes a person dying thus, mostly in the South (*Economic Times* of Jan. 16th, 2011). The number of younger males is about twice as high as that of females. – The many cases here in the KSS are divided into unspecified mentions, threats and accounts of ways of suicide. Distinguishing between planning and threatening was not always clear.

¹⁴⁴¹ See above under: inconsistencies. A man who tried the same in a temple in Gujarat in 1985 was hospitalized and faced prosecution (*Fränkischer Tag* German newspaper of Oct. 24th, 1985), suicide being forbidden by law (Indian Penal Code, 1860 § 309: "Whoever attempts to commit suicide and does any act towards the commission of such offence, shall be punished with simple imprisonment for term which may extend to one year [or with fine, or with both] "). In the most relevant case as far as Jainism is concerned, Nikhil Soni v. Union of India and Ors. AIR (2006) Raj 7414, the petitioner invoked the right to life enshrined in Art. 21 of the Constitution, alleging *sallekhanā*

bhakti to king 91,45 (TP VII 69); by ~ one only gains pains of hell (*nārakaṃ duḥkham ātma-tyāgena vāñchasi*) 96,20 (TP VII 109)¹⁴⁴²; ~ as offense of cowards / bad people (*pāpaṃ kā-puruṣōcitam*) 101,21 (TP VII 135); brahmin orphan commits ~ with his wife by fasting on bank of Ganges due to being robbed of wealth by relatives 112,139 (TP VIII 117); ~ of merchant's daughter by entering the fire with corpse of beloved robber 112,169 (TP VIII 120); ~ of desperate lover by fire 119,178 (TP VIII 205); – see also: *aśoka* tree suicide [II: planned but given up or prevented] ~ decided by poor brahmin to propitiate Durgā, but goddess stops him 6,81 (TP I 66); ~ (*ātmānaṃ hanmi*) attempt in Durgā shrine hindered 6,82 (TP I 66); idem 6,156 (TP I 72); king's thought of ~ overcome by reflexion 16,51 (TP II 25); ~ of pregnant widow not allowed 21,112 (TP II 134); offended queens resolved on ~ unless ... 33,79 (TP III 113); determination to commit ~ by starvation at *tīrtha* by depressed brahmin 33,142 (TP III 119); king prevents brahmin's ~ 33,147 (TP III 119f.); threat of princess with ~ before feared violation 34,9 (TP III 128); merchant dissuaded from ~ by ascending pyre by other merchant 36,79f. (TP III 175); courtesan ready to commit ~ because grieved at separation from lover 38,92 (TP III 213); vow of ~ of grieved woman by entering fire 38,95 (TP III 213); threat of ~ to get back golden arrow and prevent banishment 39,72 (TP III 223); daughter's ~ in case of father's refusal of husband 39,94 (TP III 224); ~ planned out of grief 41,52 (TP III 255); ~ decided upon by grieving women 42,165 but refused by brother who offers instead his own head as sacrifice which is turned down by voice of Durgā 42,173 (TP III 271); brahmin refuses to be ~ (*ātma-ghātin*) 45,93 (TP IV 23); king intends ~ out of grief over lost wife but is comforted by minister 52,280 (TP IV 157); ~ planned by penance 52,342 (TP IV 162); ~ by cutting off own head prevented by bodiless voice 53,176 (TP IV 180); bawd and courtesan daughter are near ~ (*prāṇa-tyāgōdyata*) for grief over lost wealth 57,169 (TP V 12); ~ by fire planned 59,110 (TP V 34); crow wishes for firewood to commit ~ 62,121 (TP V 109); elephant-keeper swallows poison because of eloped wife, but the poison is counteracted and he is revived by false ascetics with a spell 69,60 (TP VI 13); ~ planned but given up by sober reason 71,187 (TP VI 49); ~ (*ātmōpahāra*) in temple of Devī due to separation from beloved woman and planned by sword in order to propitiate Durgā, but prevented by compassionate *tāpasī* with headshake (*vārdhaka-kampinā śīrasā*) 72,19ff. (TP VI 69); ~ by entering fire (*agni-praveśa*) planned by king deprived of kingdom but he is adopted by other king 72,171 (TP VI 81); hermit king dissuades man, unhappy at death of parents, from committing ~ (*ātma-vadha*) by hanging himself (*udbandhana*) 72,189f. (TP VI 82)¹⁴⁴³; thief plans ~ (*deha-vyayōnmukha*) but is consoled by heavenly nymph 72,198 (TP VI 83); man on the point of ~ out of disappointment consoled by royal sage 72,201 (TP VI 83); ~ of love-sick merchant from tree top prevented by hermit bearing him up in his

to be a social evil that should be considered to be hit by the ambit of Section 309 IPC (p. c. Mr Satyanarayan Hegde with thanks).

¹⁴⁴² But by dying of one's own free will (*svātantrya*) one retains memory of pre-birth 45,60 (TP IV 21).

¹⁴⁴³ Cf. Rājat 3,423ff.

hands 72,308f. (TP VI 91); man's ~ by yielding up breath (*prāṇōtkrānti*) stopped by Indra 72,390 (TP VI 98); ~ planned but stopped by *yakṣa* 73,18 (TP VI 101); ~ decided but prevented by hermit 73,169ff. (TP VI 113); ~ decided but stopped by Gaṅgā 74,132 (TP VI 149); ~ of snake-bitten brahmin prevented by spell 75,14 (TP VI 165); ~ by cutting off own head prevented by Durgā (*mā sāhasaṃ kṛthāḥ*) 78,102 (TP VI 197); Devī stops young woman from committing ~ by hanging 80,44 (TP VI 207); ~ prevented by heavenly voice 86,87 (TP VII 19); ~ by noose of upper garment bound to branch of *aśoka* tree but is stopped by voice of goddess 90,73 (TP VII 54); ~ planned if object not reached 92,5 (TP VII 71); ~ of merchant woman by hanging, planned but stopped by friend 95,33 (TP VII 100); breaking of rope stops ~ of brahmin by hanging 96,17 (TP VII 109); out of sorrow, king plans ~ by throwing himself into a lake but is prevented by bodiless voice 100,35 (TP VII 130); ministers unable to bear separation from prince consider ~ (*dehattyāga*) 101,15 (TP VII 135); king and queen bent on ~ but dissuaded by ministers 101,211 (TP VII 148f.); ~ (*maraṇōdyama*) of king prevented by ministers 101,215 (TP VII 149); intention to ~ from grief by hanging from *aśoka* tree 103,42 stopped by attendants 103,54 (TP VII 178f.); disappointed at beloved princess being given to *kṣatriya*, brahmin tries ~ by hanging from banyan tree but is prevented by someone cutting noose 104,71ff. (TP VIII 6); ~ of woman by hanging in front of statue of Kāma in temple of Mātara prevented by lover 104,139ff. (TP VIII 11); ~ attempt by hanging stopped by personified Gāyatrī 105,29 (TP VIII 23); wives of conquered kings dissuaded from ~ by entering fire 110,7 (TP VIII 82); ~ of king and company by hurling from cliff after worshipping Vṛṣadhvaja (Śiva) with his lyre Ghosavatī, but saved by fiery chariot (*vimānena bhāsvareṇa*) 111,82 (TP VIII 102); unhappy minister plans ~ by jumping from from a precipice (*prapātataḥ*) but is saved by hermit 108,16f. (TP VIII 54); king of Bhūts dissuades man from ascending pyre 108,91 (TP VIII 61); ~ planned but dissuaded by hermit 108,66 (TP VIII 58); ~ planned to appease Kālarātrī who stops it 109,103f. (TP VIII 78f.); king and company hurl themselves from cliff, are caught by fiery chariot and brought to heaven 111,83 (TP VIII 102); disappointed at separation from princess, *caṇḍāla* prepares ~ in fire but is stopped by Agni Pāvaka 112,99 (TP VIII 113); ~ threat by princess if Śiva would not give her a certain husband 117,72 (TP VIII 169); ~ of Daitya queen and two daughters stopped by eastern *cakravartin* Merudhvaja 118,183 (TP VIII 191); ~ of desperate princess by hanging from *aśoka* planned, but stopped by hermit 119,187 (TP VIII 206); wishing for ~ due to separation from beloved and being abroad (*para-deśa-ga*) king is comforted by hermit Kaṇva 120,5 (TP IX 1); ~ planned by pilgrimage to destroy body 123,250 (TP IX 60); brahmin's beauty captivates two women besides his bride and so all three want to enter fire in his absence 123,317 (TP IX 65); – see also: blackmail; *dharnā*

suicide¹⁴⁴⁴ [III: threatened] blackmail with ~ 10,103 (TP I 113); ~ (*maraṇa-niścaya*) as

¹⁴⁴⁴ The power of self-willed suicide can convert death into a symbolic triumph over self-limitations (Bech 1983: 79).

protest of citizens against king 12,25 (TP I 135); mendicant desiring boon from Durgā threatens her with ~ 18,161 (TP II 62); ~ threatened by queen in order to compel husband to perform magic rites 20,192 (TP II 112); ~ of king by cutting off own head if Agni is not satisfied with vilva fruit offered 35,68 (TP III 160) and 36,28 (TP III 171); king threatens ~ if other king does not come to marry his abducted daughter 44,110 (TP IV 8); ~ announced by spurned queen unless minister does her will 49,56 (TP IV 88); *dehattyāgam* threatened 49,218 (TP IV 100); *dharnā* for not obtaining bride wanted 52,37 (TP IV 140); brahmin's threat to cut off head 52,162 (TP IV 149); ~ threat by entering fire 55,6 (TP IV 203); Candrasvāmin wants ~ by austerities on bank of river Ganges if he does not find his children 56,71 (TP IV 225); woman threatens ~ by biting tongue in two 89,78 (TP VII 45); son threatens father with ~ 98,33 (TP VII 118); ~ threat in fire by princess when she does not get husband within six months 122,89 (TP IX 40); – see also: *dharnā* suicides (*ātma-ghātin*) suffer more in the next world than here 49,227 (TP IV 101); suitors, four ~ of princess 52,96 (TP IV 144); ~ from Deccan 83,20 (TP VII 3); – see also: address; ascetic; ashes; beauty; bone(s); cremation; Deccan; depression; *dhanyāsmi*; dispute; four; garland; giving pledge; *grāmya-kāmuka*; lamp-black; mother(-in-law); musk; princess; three (fingers); three suitors; warder; youth;

śuka 'parrot', Niṣāda princess with ~ in cage at door of assembly hall of king Sumanas 59,25ff. (TP V 26ff.)¹⁴⁴⁵; king of ~ remembers pre-births, but has a foolish warder enslaved to his passions (*rāgi-mūrkhah pratihārah*) 72,237f. (TP VI 86)

sūkara, rebirth as ~ ('pig') escaped by Śiva's favour 53,125 (TP IV 176)

su-kṛta, see: merit

su-kṛta-pādapa 'tree of good deeds' produces glorious fruit to the righteous 27,99 (TP III 8)

śūla-kara (not MW), see: trident

śūlāropaṇa 'impalement', q.v.; – see also: heartbreak;

Śūlin, Śiva ~ sends Nārada to cheer up (*dhṛty-arthaṃ*) king 105,83 (TP VIII 27); sulking of Pārvatī 1,43 (TP I 5)¹⁴⁴⁶; ~ of queen out of jealousy 55,120ff. (TP IV 210); – see also: *kopa-gr̥ha*

sulking room, see boudoir; *kopa-gr̥ha*

summer (*grīṣmartu*) represented as *bhīmaḥ kesarī* 87,29 (TP VII 31)¹⁴⁴⁷; *gharma-kāla* impedes travelling 95,12 (TP VII 99);

sun with seven horses 18,103 (TP II 57); ~ is friend of lotuses (*ab-ja*) 22,77 (TP II 142); sun's horses, discussion on their colour, black or white, between Kadrū and Vinatā 22,182 (TP II 150); looking into the ~ (*arkābhimukha*) as if showing that one should be impaled 24,95 (TP II 176); ~ on western mountain stretches forth rays like fingers as if saying: "Wait patiently one night" 29,126 (TP III 48); ~ as lamp of the three worlds 30,144 (TP III 74), 66,166

¹⁴⁴⁵ For the story cf. Kād. 25,1ff.

¹⁴⁴⁶ This scene is perhaps depicted in the Elephanta cave, see Rau 1978: 222. On sulking see e.g. Schmidt 1904: 95f.; Meyer 1952: 494; Amaru 94ff.; Hāla 522f., 896, etc.; Jackmuth 2002: 70.

¹⁴⁴⁷ This characterisation is not found in Ṛtusamhāra I.

(TP V 190) and 74,108 (TP VI 147); when ~ has risen other luminaries give no light (proverb) 45,29 (TP IV 19); Gaṇeśa bright as twelve ~s 50,177 (TP IV 119) and 100,46 (TP VII 131); ~ prevents king from giving something to *kṣatriya* servant 54,155 (TP IV 195 with reference to II 81ff.); brahmin prisoner praises ~ identifying it with Viṣṇu, Śiva and Prajāpati 56,28ff. (TP IV 221f.); following the example of the ~ the great ones, after suffering a decline, rise again 56,418 (TP IV 250); ~ as flaming eye of the world 59,51 (TP V 29); maiden's body gleams as if she were the light of the ~ come to visit the wood out of curiosity 69,169 (TP VI 21); ~ as friend of the virtuous (*guṇi-bāndhava*) stretches out fingers (lit.: hand) of his rays to wipe off tears of lonely princess 71,193 (TP VI 49f.); ~ hears Bodhisatta teaching and assumes the hue of sunset like orange monk's robe (*kāṣāya*) 72,364 (TP VI 96); ~ is centre-jewel of heaven as a jewel in the mid of the girdle of an *apsaras* (*dyu-vadhū*) 81,17 (TP VI 210: "sky-bride"; ORC 932: "*Le soleil – placé au centre de la voûte céleste comme un joyau au milieu de la ceinture d'une jeune femme*–"; M II 227: "*Sonne, dieses Mitteljuwel auf dem Gürtel der Himmelsbraut*")¹⁴⁴⁸; ~ as mouth of summer-lion (*griṣmartu-kesarin*) with rays for mane 87,29 (TP VII 31); 94,51 (TP VII 90f.); ~ in love with twilight departs together with the day 95,67 (TP VII 102); ~'s rays like warning hand 98,12 (TP VII 117); ~ as wicked king (*duṣṭa-pāla iva tīkṣṇa-karaḥ*) 104,202 (TP VIII 16); ~ as friend of the *kamalinī* 121,245 (TP IX 30); at noon ~ waits a *muhūrta* in order to let dawn (*aruṇa*), his charioteer, loosen the horses to bathe and feed 123,12 (TP IX 44); – see also: *bhānu*; eclipse; hand

sunrise, see: mountain

sunset, a fickle woman is like ~ momentarily aglow for everyone 52,285 (TP IV 157); sun assumes hue of ~ as a Buddhist monk's robe¹⁴⁴⁹ and enters the cavern of the western mountain 72,364 (TP VI 96); at ~ heaven places moon on its western quarter like a *tilaka* 95,67 (TP VII 102); – see also: Gaṇeśa

sunshade,¹⁴⁵⁰ king with white ~ (*sītenātapatreṇa*) 18,4 (TP II 49); idem 18,71 (TP II 55); ~ and elephant given to brahmin as sign of honour 18,125 (TP II 59); idem (*sita-cchatra*) after becoming king 18,403 (TP II 80); king ascends elephant with ~ 19,63 (TP II 89); defeated king of Kāmarūpa without ~ (*apacchattreṇa śirasā*) 19,113 (TP II 94); brahmin honoured with ~ for assumed divination 30,137 (TP III 73); ~ as mark on feet of *vidyādhara* king 33,178 (TP III 122); ~ and chowrie (*chattra-cāmara*) as signs of a bird

¹⁴⁴⁸ As the sky is masculine in Sanskrit there appears to be here a kind of ellipsis or sentence contraction. For a possible representation of the sky as a cow ṚV I 134,4 could be adduced where the Maruts are said to be born from the udders (*vakṣāṇābhyaḥ*) of the sky. The new translation by Witzel et al. renders: "Für dich (Vāyu) soll die saftig milchende Kuh alle Güter als Milch geben. Du erzeugtest die Maruts *aus den Bäuchen* des Himmels" (2007: 251; italics are mine); p. 697 explains the *Bäuche* as clouds, as did Geldner for the *Euter*. Mehlig's version of our passage apparently makes the sun a jewel on the girdle of the earth, who is the *Himmelsbraut*. – On ellipsis see Gonda 1960.

¹⁴⁴⁹ At Daś 122.4 the colour of sunset is likened to Viṣṇu's yellow robe.

¹⁴⁵⁰ See Penzer's Appendix II in TP II 263-72; Saletore 1943: 177ff. A Pali tradition states that the royal sunshade has a deity as its protector (Ja VI 370,17; Sīhalavattuppakaraṇa 28,19 *rañño chattamhi devatā*).

king 62,25 (TP V 100); two *haṃsas* shelter under a lotus by way of a ~ 69,150 (TP VI 19), cf. 25,12 (TP II 188); (royal) ~ keeps off kings from sunshine as well as from truth (*ātapatreṇa satyaṃ ca sūryâloko nivāryate*) 91,57 (TP VII 70); circle of the earth ruled under one ~ (*ekātapatra*) 103,239 (TP VII 192); broken state ~s (*mahā-cchattra*) as bad omen 116,3 (TP VIII 156); king's ~ white as own glory 118,194 (TP VIII 191); sunspot, see: *tikṣṇâṃśu-bimba*

sūnya-vasati 'solitary abode', *vidyādhara* princess in ~ feels melancholic (*nirviṇṇā*) 86,108 (TP VII 21)

Supratika cursed by Kuvera to become the Piśāca Kāṇabhūti 1,59 (TP I 7); *surā*,¹⁴⁵¹ see: wine

Surabhi, the first cow 28,191 (TP III 36); brahmin's brown cow is incarnation of ~ 108,29 (TP VIII 55)

sūrpa-karṇa 'with ears like a winnowing-fan',¹⁴⁵² epithet of Gaṇeśa 55,165 (TP IV 213 wrongly: 'basket-eared'; ORC 617: "oreilles en éventails"; MI 867: "Wannenähnliche Ohren-Besitzer")

surroundings, natural ~ influence character of people 102,103 (TP VII 170);

Sūryavatī, queen of Kalaśa of Kashmir and great builder of monasteries, etc. E 4ff. (TP IX 88)

sūryôparāga (not MW) 'eclipse of the sun' enables king to give wealth to *kṣatriya* 54,156 (TP IV 195)

śuṣka-taru, -*vrkṣa* see: tree 70,25ff. (TP VI 25)

suspicion, brahmin's ~ of his wife's adultery dismissed 14,56 (TP I 186)

su-svādu 'delicious', said of fruit 123,30 (TP IX 45)

sutā-phala (not MW) 'reward for (giving birth to) daughter' 12,163 (TP I 146)

sūt-kāra 'whistling' (*sa-°-marut* 'hurricane') 101,140 (TP VII 144);

suttee,¹⁴⁵³ 5,100 (TP I 54)¹⁴⁵⁴; *yakṣa* wife as ~ 34,89 (TP III 135); brahmin ~ 68,36 (TP VI 4) and 73,71 (TP VI 106); 72,197 (TP VI 83); 96,6 (TP VII 108); ~ of queen after king's death 111,56 (TP VIII 100)

suvarṇa-kamala (not MW) 'golden Nelumbium' 25,212 (TP II 207), see also: golden lotus

Suvāsakumāra, hermit coming on when thought of (*cintitôpasthita*) 46,44 (TP IV 52);

śva-bāla 'hair of dog' in lyre 49,19 (TP IV 86 wrongly: "puppy")¹⁴⁵⁵

svairam 71,129 (TP VI 45 "acting in accordance with her own will only");

Svāmikumāra = Skanda, general of the gods, when worshipped gives all *vidyāḥ* 2,60 (TP I 15); ~ visited in the Deccan by brahmins grieved at their being unprotected 3,8 (TP I 18); ~ , propitiated, gives treasury 49,237-245 (TP IV 101f.); king Kanakavarṣa worships ~ to get son but is rained upon without ceasing¹⁴⁵⁶ by ~ 55,156ff. (TP IV 213); ~ sends Heramba-

¹⁴⁵¹ Müller 2008: 460 note 87 states that there is no evidence of distillation in India before Islamic times.

¹⁴⁵² Cf. the epithet *cala-karṇânilôddhūta* in 44,1.

¹⁴⁵³ See Diodorus Siculus XIX 30.

¹⁴⁵⁴ STh P 16.4.1.

¹⁴⁵⁵ Cf. 106,25.

Gaṇeśa to impede king 55,158 (TP IV 213)¹⁴⁵⁷; ~, propitiated, promises king a son as boon 55,172 (TP IV 214); pleased by *sūkta* and *su-bhāṣita* ~ ends curse 55,179f. (TP IV 214) – see also: Kārttikeya, Kumāra, Skanda

svapna-māṇava ‘charm effecting the realisation of a dream (MW)’; ‘dream as measure > “means of prospecting the far past”’ (Osier)¹⁴⁵⁸ a *bhikṣu* tells a king 72,103 (TP VI 76 ‘charm for producing dreams’; M II “Zauber, der Träume erzeugt”) and 152 (TP VI 80 “charm for obtaining a dream”)

svapna-māṇavaka 6,137 (TP I 70 “charm to produce a dream”; ORC 42: “*charme producteur de songes*”; M I 60: “*Traumbild*”)¹⁴⁵⁹

svarṇa-cūla (‘Sultan Tit’),¹⁴⁶⁰ prince cursed to become ~ with golden crest 65,78 but released after service in return 65,83 (TP V 160f. “hoopoe”)

svarṇa-rūpaka ‘gold coin’, 78,13 (TP VI 192)¹⁴⁶¹

svasti (‘happiness’) at end of its curse bird wishes Bodhisattva ~ 65,106 (TP V 163): cf. *siddhi*

svasti-kāra ‘blessing’ 25,53 (TP II 194)

sva-tantratā, see: independence

sva-tantravat (‘wilful’) behaviour of *apsaras* who forgets going to Indra’s feast 27,63 (TP III 5)

svātantrya ‘free will’, dying of one’s own ~ retains memory of pre-birth 45,60 (TP IV 21)

śva-vāla ‘dog’s hair’ 49,19 (TP IV 86 wrongly: ‘puppy’; ORC 520: ‘*poil de chien*’)

Svayambhū temple of Śiva 51,5 (TP IV 122 with note); his *kṣetrāṇi* in Kashmir 51,45 (TP IV 125); 52,15 (TP IV 138); Svayambhuvau (‘self-existent deities’): Śiva and Viṣṇu 63,54 (TP V 123)

svayaṃvara ‘marriage by choice’, *vidyādhara* princess gives herself to mortal hero because of

¹⁴⁵⁶ Svāmikumāra’s heavy reaction is unexplained and can only be due to fate. It was predestinated (vs. 153f.) and cannot be caused by the *nāgī* Ratnaprabhā’s presence in Kanakavarṣa’s body though just as Kumāra S. has certain gynaeophobous aspects (women are not admitted in his temple [55,174 = TP IV 214]). On Skanda see, e.g. Saletore 1984: 1360ff. and Dange 1987: 1366ff.

¹⁴⁵⁷ Deities who can do good such as Gaṇeśa *vighna-jit* (55,169), can also cause the opposite: *vighnēśvara* (168).

¹⁴⁵⁸ Osier 2009: 270f. quoting A. M. Esnoul as “*rêve provoqué*” states that the translations given are rather interpretations of a difficult syntagm. The dream being retrospective and not premonitory he proposes as a new and word-to-word translation “dream of the Infinitesimal”. – Oniromantics is characterised as a bad livelihood practised by non-Buddhists (Dīghanikāya I 9,4).

¹⁴⁵⁹ See ORC 1340 at p. 42 note 2. PWB: “Traumbube, Bezeichnung eines bestimmten Zaubers, der eintreffende Träume bewirkt” (“dream-boy”, designation of a charm effecting the realisation of dreams [MW]). Just as *soma* or liquor was drunk to produce an appropriate drugged state I could imagine *māṇava* to be no spell, but something taken. Perhaps *māṇava* is an old error for *mānaka* which besides ‘measure’ can mean ‘spirituous liquor’. The *-ṇ-* in *māṇava* may be secondary.

¹⁴⁶⁰ Thus Dave 2005: 22 where the place is discussed. ORC 755: *huppe d’or*. MW has: “probably Blue Jay or Indian Roller.”

¹⁴⁶¹ Lüders 1940: 478.

his handsome form (*vapuṣ*) 26,64 (TP II 222); fishermen princess gives herself to brahmin hero 26,154 (TP II 228); *yakṣa* princess gives herself to brahmin hero 26,217 (TP II 234); beautiful princess throws garland of blue lotuses of her eyes over smart hermit and thus selects him as her husband 28,79 (TP III 26); princess makes unknown prince her self-chosen husband in retired (*vivikta*, 76) temple at night 30,82 (TP III 69); princess puts necklace on her head as token of choice at ~ 39,113 (cf. 107; TP III 225); ~ of Damayantī 56,256ff. (TP IV 238) and 56,366 (TP IV 247); ~ of *cāṇḍāla-kanyakā* 61,213 (TP V 86); eye (*dṛṣṭi*) of princess compared to garland of blue lotuses she threw on man and so chose him as her husband 67,22 (TP V 197); (*divya-strī*) chooses husband by ~ and marries him by *gāndharva* ritual 68,14 (TP VI 2); father offers *vātsalyāt* ~ to daughter who refuses out of modesty (*hrepaṇāt*) 83,15f. (TP VII 3); *trailokya-sundarī* chooses husband 121,219 (TP IX 28); – see also: beauty; gestures

svedāmbu ‘sweat water’, may the ~ of Śīva-Vibhu, fresh from the embrace of Gaurī, which Kāma uses against the fire of Śīva’s eye, protect you 9,1 (TP I 94)

Śveta, hermit, due to whom Śīva consumes Kāla¹⁴⁶² 72,334 (TP VI 94); ~ stays beyond River Taraṅgiṇī at the other side of the eastern ocean (*pāre pūrvāmbudheḥ*) 72,336 (TP VI 94);

Śveta-dvīpa as Viṣṇu’s home 63,54 (TP V 124);

swearing with face turned eastward and after rinsing mouth 16,117 (TP II 30); – see also: act of truth; oath

sweat, see: *svedāmbu*

sweet, prostitute promising son a ~, see: *modaka*

swing of doubt (*vicāra-dolā*) 9,87 (TP I 102); *caṇḍāla* maiden makes ~ with upper garment fastened to elephants tusks 112,70 (TP VIII 111)¹⁴⁶³

swinging, father slaps disobedient *vidyādhari* daughter fond of ~ (*dola*) 66,138 (TP V 189 with note 1); *caṇḍāla* maiden touches wild elephant’s trunk and is ~ between its tusks 112,70 (TP VIII 111);

swoon (*moha*), see: faint

sword, magic ~ named Mrgāṅka given hero to keep off crocodiles in Ganges 10,51 (TP I 110); magical ~ given by Caṇḍikā = Durgā 11,38 (TP I 125)¹⁴⁶⁴; ~ given by Agni comes on thought 18,116 (TP II 58) and 278 (TP II 71); king’s agile ~ (*khaḍga-latā*) as the smoke of the fire of his valour (*pratāpānala-dhūmika*) 19,104 (TP II 93; ORC 159: “*son sabre courbe affectait désormais la forme arrondie des volutes de la fumée du feu de sa gloire*”; M I 228: “*Sein einem Schlinggewachs ähnelndes Schwert entsprach gewiß dem Rauch des Feuers seiner Glut und Macht*”); ~ dark-blue as the sky (*vyoma-śyāmala-nistrimśa*) 26,234 (TP II 234); embryo removed turns into ~ 26,259 (TP II 236) and enables carrier to fly

¹⁴⁶² For this story see Doniger 1993: 64f.

¹⁴⁶³ On the magico-ritual meaning of swinging see Gonda 1975 IV: 409ff.; Raghavan 1979: 12f., 74 and 129f. According to Meyer 1937: II 264 swinging generates growth (“*wachstumerzeugend*”).

¹⁴⁶⁴ See TP II 106 note 4; Rodrigues 2003: 129 and 211ff.; Kinsley 1986: 109f.

26,268 (TP II 237)¹⁴⁶⁵; ~ like long hair of good fortune (*siddheḥ keśa-pāśa iva*) 26,261 (TP II 236); ~ smeared with magic powder (*cūrṇa*) in order to cut through neck strengthened by *rasāyana* 41,50 (TP III 255); Devī-Durgā in dream gives ~ to prince 42,118 (TP III 267); ~ like philosopher's stone (*cintā-ratna*) 42,145 (TP III 270); fire-dimmed (TP; *kalankita* 'stained' [MW])¹⁴⁶⁶ ~ 42,164 (TP III 271); ~s red with blood falling on heroes' heads 44,147 (TP IV 10); ugly mortal with magic ~ (*khaḍga-siddha*) to become husband of princess 52,173 (TP IV 150); magic ~ given by Durgā enabling holder to fly when it is in his hand 52,183 (TP IV 149f.); king obtains from *Asura* maiden ~ which enables flying (*kha-gati-dāyin*) 56,218f. (TP IV 235); ~-blades waving to and fro appear like tongues of Death (*kṛtānta-rasanā*) 50,5 (TP IV 108); man with ~ (*khaḍgī*) arising from lake 63,18 (TP V 121); *siddha-yoginī* gives brahmin ~ 68,66 (TP VI 6)¹⁴⁶⁷; snake chief (*nāga-vara*) Pārāvātākṣa obtained ~ Vaidūryakānti, whose possessor will become chief of Siddhas 70,60f. (TP VI 28); prince sets out at night, ~ in hand 71,23 (TP VI 37); ~ given by Gaurī to *nāga-kanyā* 72,47 (TP VI 72); Daitya maiden gives king ~ called *A-parājita* 81,108 (TP VI 216); royal ~ black as a snake with slough cast (*nirmoka-mukta*) 86,123 (TP VII 22), cf. *khaḍgam ahindrābhaṃ* 109,20 (TP VIII 71); Śiva gives ~ *A-parājita* to king Trivikramasena to become *vidyādhara* king 99,37 (TP VII 124); ~-jewel (*khaḍga-ratna*)¹⁴⁶⁸ obtained by Naravāhanadatta 109,21 (TP VIII 71); Caṇḍī propitiated gives king her own ~ 112,27 (TP VIII 107); Śiva Girijā-pati gives Muktāphalaketu the ~ *Aparājita* 115,143 (TP VIII 154); dead boar touched on the neck becomes celestial ~ 123,96f. (TP IX 50) swordmanship, *kṣatriya* boasts of proficiency in ~ (*khaḍga-vidyā-vijñāna*) 83,28 (TP VII 3); *śyāmā* 'green',¹⁴⁶⁹ *asurī* ~ as *dūrvā*-grass stalk and with full moon face 45,333 (TP IV 39); ~ queen from Mālava 98,35 (TP VII 118); beauty ~ as panic seed (*priyaṅgu*) 120,105 (TP IX 8); – see also: black; *dūrvā*

syandana 'chariot' 11,45 (TP I 126; ORC 74: "cheval"; MI 105: "Wagen")

śyena, see: kite

sylph, see *gāndharva* marriage; heart; king; look(s); lotus; smell

sylvan deity, see: forest deity

sympathetic magic: Vikramāditya cuts off the head of a man (drawn on the ground) instead of that of a *brahma-rākṣasa* whose neck then streams with blood (*sruta-śonita*) 121,208 (TP IX 27); ~ of cutting off a hand of a man drawn which makes the hand of a *vetāla* fall severed 121,213 (TP IX 27)

synaesthesia: royal family drunk in by the eyes of the citizens 10,211 (TP I 121); 34,99 (TP III 135); ; body of *vidyādhari* is like nectar to the eyes 35,138 (TP III 166); 49,211 (TP IV 99); *gandhāndha* 104,101 (TP VIII 8 "driven mad by the smell"; ORC 1093: "fou

¹⁴⁶⁵ Zin 2003b: 167 note 41.

¹⁴⁶⁶ The sword had magical properties (*māhātmya*) which it seems to have lost by its lying in the fire (vs 163).

¹⁴⁶⁷ Zin 2003b: 168 note 43.

¹⁴⁶⁸ Cf. Kuv 251.27; 252.18. Chojnacki 2008: I 350 (*épée magique*)

¹⁴⁶⁹ Zin 2003b: 148.

furieux à cause de l'odeur"); *vāk-puṣpa* 109,98 (TP VIII 77); – see also: *netra-pīyūṣa*; speech

t / r alternation¹⁴⁷⁰ see: Bhūrivasu

tabor (*mahā-todya*) beaten to accompany dancing 71,76 (TP VI 41); ~ noise (*muraḥa-dhvani*) 2,34 (TP I 11);

tail, grammatical treatise called Kālāpaka after the ~ (*kalāpa*) of the peacock, the *vāhana* of Sarasvatī 7,13 (TP I 75); ~ of *camarī* 55,200 (TP IV 216); to lash the ~ (*lāṅgūlam āsphālayati*), said of an angry lion 60,101 (TP V 50); ~ of snake with head 63,175 (TP V 134); fool holding bull's ~ ascends heaven 65,185 (TP V 169); bob-tailed dogs 114,68 (TP VIII 137); Bhilla women wearing skirt of peacock ~s 123,50 (TP IX 46)

Tājika, kind of barbarians in the northern regions, inhabitant of modern Tajikistan 37,36 (TP III 185)¹⁴⁷¹

Ṭakka,¹⁴⁷² miser eating no salt 65,141 (TP V 166);

Takṣaśīlā, Buddhist city on the banks of the Vitastā with many palaces 27,10 (TP III 2); princess of ~ travels by magic car (*māyā-yantra-vimāna*) 31,56 (TP III 87); – see also: *eka-veṇī*

tāla 'Borassus flabellifer, Palmyra-palm, fan-palm',¹⁴⁷³ Rāma cleaves seven ~s with one arrow 107,21 (TP VIII 44)

talāhata, see: hand

tale, laughable ~ of bawd on pillar 12,186ff. (TP I 148); amusing: ~ (*sukhôn mukha*) 51,200 (TP IV 136), et passim; after hearing ~s prince is able to sleep 61,330 (TP V 97)); *vetāla* tells king ~ to amuse (*vinodāya*) him 76,5 (TP VI 179, but the following story is not amusing and irony cannot be assumed¹⁴⁷⁴); 79,4 (TP VI 200);

tale(s) explaining etymology of name Sātavāhana 6,105 (TP I 68); idem, of Puṣpadanta 7,68 (TP I 82); ~ of Kandarpa 20,64 (TP II 100); – see also: story

tale, false (*mṛṣā*) 71,138 (TP VI 46); ~ told for one's good 72,240 (TP VI 86)¹⁴⁷⁵; tale, as illustration 72,22 (TP VI 69); *tathā cāitāṃ kathāṃ śṛṇu* 15,10 (TP II 1); idem 15,62 (TP II 6); idem *tathā cātra kathāṃ śṛṇu* 15,96 (TP II 10), etc.; ~ composed by Hara-Śiva 7,113 (TP I 86); prince gone to sleep without telling his ~ is cursed 28,124 (TP III 30); ~ invented (*mithyāiva*) 66,24 (TP V 180); queen tells king fictitious ~ (*kṛtakam*) 66,47 (TP V 181); wonderful (*a-pūrvā*) ~ related by prince 68,16 (TP VI 2) and princess 68,32

¹⁴⁷⁰ Cf. Sā(t)iputra and Sāriputra in Isibhās 38,2; *āṭi*, *āḍi*, *āri* in Dave 2005: 353.

¹⁴⁷¹ According to ORC 1655 rather a general designation for foreigners than a specific people. M I 524 takes them to be Persians.

¹⁴⁷² Perhaps an equivalent of Bāhika, a people in Panjab, reputed for its avarice (ORC 1655). See Saletore 1984: 1426f.

¹⁴⁷³ The fan-palm is considered as a measure of height (MW), see Macmillan 1991: 404 (20-25 m high).

¹⁴⁷⁴ See 98,73 (TP VII 121), 99,22 (TP VII 123) and 107,12 (TP VIII 43).

¹⁴⁷⁵ Cf. the falsehood told a king by his physicians in 15,15 (TP II 2).

(TP VI 4); ~ told for consolation (*a-kheda*) 77,4 (TP VI 183); ~ illustrating faults of males (*puṃ-doṣa*) 77,15 (TP VI 184); man disguised as woman tells ~ about sage disguised as woman to sleepless princess 89,84 (TP VII 46); whosoever shall read or hear even a *śloka* of the twenty-five ~ of a vampire shall be freed from his curse 99,28 (TP VII 124); ~ told by Kaṇva 101,40 (TP VII 136); Naravāhanadatta occupies himself in telling ~ 114,6 (TP VIII 132); agreement about telling marvellous ~ in exchange for bedstead (*khaṭvā*) 124,216ff. (TP IX 83); ~ related by Śiva, see there; ~ told by Indra (q.v.); – see also: *dhik-kathā*; story

tale as proof (*tathā cātra kathām śṛṇu*) 5,58 (TP I 51); 69,46 (TP VI 12); do, 69,77 (TP VI 14); do, 71,66 (TP VI 40); do, 75,21 (TP VI 165) and (*tathā kathā*) 77,47 (TP VI 186); talisman, see: crest-jewel

talking to bad woman lets hermit loose his ascetic power (*tapah-śakti*) 65,52f. (TP V 158)

“talking cure” of desperate husband by relatives 87,22 (TP VII 30); – see also: lovesick *tamāla*,¹⁴⁷⁶ ‘garcinia morella’, dark ~ forests on the confines of the southern region 73,30 (TP VI 102)¹⁴⁷⁷; (dark) ~ trees looking like nights in the rainy season when the clouds collect, and contrasted with white Arjuna trees 102,3f. (TP VII 162); Mātāṅga king dark as a ~ tree 102,71 (TP VII 167); boar black as a ~ tree 123,8 (TP IX 43);

tamāla-pattra, see: make-up

tamo-’stra ‘weapon of darkness’ 116,71 (TP VIII 161)¹⁴⁷⁸

tāmra-kumbha ‘copper pot’, bald man’s head like a ~ 61,48 (TP V 72)

Tāmraliptī inhabited by honourable men (*ārya-juṣṭa*) 77,51 (TP VI 187)

tanayā-dāna-śulka, see: gift

*tāṇḍava*¹⁴⁷⁹ (dance) of Bhairava in the company of witches 56,106 (TP V 227)

tank (*saras*), built for two *haṃsas* 3,30 (TP I 21); *dohada* of princess to bathe in ~ (*vāpī*) with blood 9,46 (TP I 97); builder of ~ rewarded in next life according to Dharma śāstra¹⁴⁸⁰ 65,178 (TP V 168); ~ with wine, blood and fat of corpses in Pātāla 73,153 (TP VI 112); plunging in ~ (*vāpikā*) makes Rājput dependent emerge in garden 81,58¹⁴⁸¹ (TP VI 213) and *vāpī* 81,109 (TP VI 216); king jumps with his *vidyādhari* love into ~ that served as a magic gate (*yantra-dvāra-*) to world of men 86,150f. (TP VII 24); king has ~ made for *haṃsas* 114,36 (TP VIII 135)

tantrī ‘string’, king sprinkles ~s of lute 49,21 (TP IV 86)

tantric rites to revive a person with an *āryā* to Cāmuṇḍā 52,159 (TP IV 149)

tapah-śakti, see: conversation; talking

¹⁴⁷⁶ See Kuv note 195; “a small tree with evergreen leaves. It produces tears or grains of Indian gamboge” (Macmillan 1991: 455f.).

¹⁴⁷⁷ Cf. Kuv note 331.

¹⁴⁷⁸ Cf. *tamasā* (Dikshitar 1987: 120) which, however, is not adduced with this meaning in MW.

¹⁴⁷⁹ Sundaram 1979: 752f.

¹⁴⁸⁰ Not found in Manu.

¹⁴⁸¹ The tank seems to have the function of amniotic water, just as the sea in vs 43.

tapah-sukha, see: asceticism

tapas produces customary right to stay in heaven 72,359 (TP VI 95)¹⁴⁸²; – see also: austerities

tāpasī, see: ascetic

tapasvini,¹⁴⁸³ see: ascetic; hermit

tāpiccha (*Garcinia xanthochymus*; Egg tree)¹⁴⁸⁴ looks like smoke of Kāma's burnt body 104,90 (TP VIII 7)

tapo-vana, famine ends when prince enters ~ 72,224 (TP VI 85); *vidyādhari* queen recovers lost *vidyā* in ~ 107,52 (TP VIII 46)

Tārā, Buddhist deity 27,12 (TP III 2); for *--vara* (not MW) see: Buddha

Tāraka, see: Indra

taraṅga-hasta 'wavelike hands' 74,113 (TP VI 148);

Taraṅgiṇī river beyond the eastern ocean 72,336 (TP VI 94);

tāra-tūrya 'shrill kettledrum' (?) 109,152 (TP VIII 81 with note 2; ORC 1152: '*sons perçants des instruments*'); M II 532: "*Pauken und Trommeln*")

tarjanī, see: forefinger

tārṅśya-ratna 'dark gem'¹⁴⁸⁵, prince waking up on slab of ~ 68,7 (TP VI 1); woman with hair like ~ 84,47 (TP VII 8); tips of wings of golden *haṁsas* are of ~ 114,40 (TP VIII 135 "emerald", with note 2; ORC 1194 "*joyaux*"; M II 587: "*aus herrlichen Edelsteinen*"); slab of in garden of *Vidyādhara* king's city of Candrapura 117,85 (TP VIII 170); *liṅga* of ~ worshipped 123,131 (TP IX 52 with note)

-taru, see: tree; – cpds see: *karma-°*; *kalpa-°*; *janma-°*; *dharma-°*; *naya-°*; *punya-°*; *sattva-°*; *śiṁśapa-°*; *smara-°*

tārunya-vāta (not MW) 'wind of youth > juvenile tempestuousness' 57,75 (TP V 7)

ṭasat-kṛtya 'with a crack', man dies from heartbreak 95,78 (TP VII 103)

teacher, of royal dancing (*nāṭyācārya*) 52,265f. (TP IV 156); ~ with two jealous pupils 63,164 (TP V 133); – see also: *guru*

team-work by a group of women 4,47 (TP I 33)¹⁴⁸⁶

teardrop, *añjana*-like black ~s look like bees 95,60 (TP VII 102); ~ from Mahēśvara-Śiva's right eye becomes sea 69,38 (TP VI 11)

tears of joy (*harṣa-bāṣpa*) 18,369 (TP II 77); do, 25,66 (TP II 195) and 253 (TP II 209); do, (*ānandāśru*) 29,3 (TP III 39); father's ~ at coronation of son as *yuva-rāja* 34,102 (TP III 136); 69,96 (TP VI 15); ~ as second necklace 30,27 (TP III 65); ~ rise (*udaśru*) to royal wife's eyes when not seeing husband 34,165 (TP III 140); ~ through disillusion at woman's unfaithfulness 37,231 (TP III 199); at seeing son queen sheds ~ like knot of pain (*duḥkha-*

¹⁴⁸² As this *tapas* tries to bypass the *karman* law it is a root of corruption. See also Brown 1920 and Babb 1983: 178.

¹⁴⁸³ See Hara 1978; Hansen 1992: 6ff..

¹⁴⁸⁴ Macmillan 1991: 301 a symmetrical bushy tree, up to 10 m high, with large and leathery leaves.

¹⁴⁸⁵ Also *Agastīya Ratnaparīkṣā* 81, 98 and *Maṇimāhātmya* 57.

¹⁴⁸⁶ See Baldissera 2004: 90f.

granthī) 43,245 (TP III 298); ~ quench forest-fire of grief 56,412 (TP IV 250); ~ drop from Śiva's right eye becomes sea 69,38 (TP VI 11); crocodile ~ 71,172 (TP VI 48); dew drops as ~ of heaven moved with compassion 71,192 (TP VI 49); ~ staining moon-like face 72,32 (TP VI 70); king gazes with ~ (*harṣāsrūṇā*) of joy on beautiful lady 73,149 (TP VI 112); ~ only produced by contact with smoke (*dhūmāsaṅge*) 93,5 (TP VII 78); ~ of love-sick woman black as collyrium and looking like bees attracted by the fragrance of her lotus-like face 95,60 (TP VII 102);

teeth, woman drops flower from ~ as a message 7,68 (TP I 82); projecting ~ (*dantura*)¹⁴⁸⁷ mark of female ugliness (of Kālarātrī) 20,108 (TP II 104); Asurī dancer Mahallikā with pointed (eye) ~ (*daśanaiḥ śikharaiḥ*) 45,235 (TP IV 33); long ~ are ugly 57,60 (TP V 5); idem, of male ugliness 123,164 (TP IX 55); line of bells like ~ on Durgā temple 26,144 (TP II 227); ~ of king, sharp as edge of thunderbolt 32,162 (TP III 103); pointed eye ~ of Dānava princess as beauty mark (*daśanaiḥ śikharaiḥ*) 45,235 (TP IV 33)¹⁴⁸⁸; fighting with ~ after arms cut off 48,110 (TP IV 81); gnashing ~ of angry *Kṛtānta* 74,283 (TP VI 160); human ~ (*nara-danta*) sacrificed to *vetāla* in corpse 99,13 (TP VII 123); Bhairava's ~ shine like cranes flying in a long row (*danta-prabhā-vitata-paṅkti-patad-balāka*) 106,182 (TP VIII 42); saw sharp as Yama's ~ 121,86 (TP IX 18); – see also:

Yama

tejah-puñjākṛti, see: flame

*tejas*¹⁴⁸⁹ 'majesty' of a king 58,17 (TP V 16); ~ of newborn *Vidyādhara* prince 115,130 (TP VIII 153); – see also: *satī-tejas*

tejasvin 'energetic', ~ men advance like blazing forest fires (*dāvānala*) 110.14 (TP VIII 83), cf. 71,104 (TP VI 43); – see also: Agastya

telemagic, see: black magic

temple, meet in isolated ~ (*deva.-kulaṃ viviktam*) 30,76 (TP III 69); king of Cedi founds ~ for his glory 34,10f. (TP III 128); spectacle (*prekṣaṇaka*) in ~ 57,74 (TP V 6); merchant builds ~ (*devatā-grha*) with timber 60,27 (TP V 43); ~ with *liṅga* and beautiful hermit maiden 101,225 (TP VII 149); ~ built at wrong place and time (*a-sthāne ku-muhūrte ca*) 121,178 (TP IX 25); – see also: Durgā temple; empty temple

temple of Ambikā, its bells like range of teeth to which heads of human sacrifices cling 101,300 (TP VII 155); ~ like mouth of Death (*mṛtyu-mukha*) 101,301 (TP VII 155)

temple of Caṇḍikā / Durgā, the temple of the horrible ~, the interior of which was enlarged, as it continually swallowed many lives, is like the mouth of Death whose projecting rows of teeth are like its rows of bells (*bhaya-kṛc-Caṇḍikā-grham śāsvat-kavalitāneka-jīvaṃ pravitatôdaram khacad-ghaṅṭāvalī –danta-mālaṃ mṛtyor ivānanam*) 26,144 (TP II 227: "horrible temple of C."; ORC 244: "Le ventre de ce temple était gonflé à force d'engérer continuellement d'innombrables êtres vivants et, avec ses guirlandes de cloches qui sallaient

¹⁴⁸⁷ Drinking *surā* leads to black teeth (Manu XI 49; YājñavalkyaDhŚ III 209).

¹⁴⁸⁸ Cf. Sītā's teeth in Rām 3,46,18.

¹⁴⁸⁹ See Vogel 1930; Magnone 1990; Ray 2007.

telles des rangées de dents, on eût dit la gueule de la Mort"; MI 348: "Tempel der furchterregenden Göttin Durgā, deren Bauch von den immer wieder verzehrten vielen Lebewesen aufgebläht war. Sie glich dem Maul des Todes, dessen Zahnreihen einer Reihe funkelnder Glocken ähnelten."¹⁴⁹⁰; empty ~ (*śūnya ... gr̥ha*) where king finds *vīṇā* and sings to it for the goddess 69,113f. (TP VI 17); submarine ~ of Devī-Durgā 81,45 (TP VI 212); ~s (*sura-mandirāṇi*) built on the bank of the Vitastā by Sūryavatī, queen of Kashmir E 7 (TP IX 88)

temple of Devī outside charnel ground (*śmaśāna-bāhyaṃ*) 18,125 (TP II 67)

temple of Gaṇeśa with statue found at sea shore (*jala-dhes tīrāt*), and supported by a thousand villages 73,325ff. (TP VI 124 'on the border of a tank'; ORC 870: "au bord de l'océan"; M II 140: "am Gestade des Meeres")

temple of Gaurī (*Gaury-āyatana*) in Śobhāvātī 80,5 (TP VI 204);

temple of Hari (Viṣṇu) on the isle of Ratnakūṭa 26,3 (TP II 217); do, dispelling calamity (*pāpa-ghna*) 71,95 (TP VI 43)

temple of Kāma in Vaiśākha city 67,16 (TP V 197);

temple of Kātyāyanī, empty (*śūnya*), medicant enters ~ 18,158 (TP II 62)

temple of king Narasiṃha in Nāgapura with *sāla-bhañjikā* 121,145 (TP IX 22);

temple of Mahākāla-Śiva, brahmins perform *tapas* in ~ 112,180 and Śiva appears to them in a dream 182 (TP VIII 120)

temple of "Mothers", see: empty temple; "Mothers"

temple of Pārvatī (*Pārvaty-āyatana*) named Meghavana 116,13 (TP VIII 157);

temple of Śambhava (Śiva) in forest 39,126 (TP III 227)¹⁴⁹¹

temple of Sarasvatī, royalty and entourage go to ~ 66,30 (TP V 180)

temple of Śiva, under water 10,30 (TP I 108); ~ in distant town 25,128 (TP II 200); ~ on a river bank with fig tree 40,89 (TP III 247); deserted ~ with one *liṅga* (*śūnyâika-liṅgaṃ Śivâlayam*) anointed / doused with goat's blood 71,212 (TP VI 51);

temple of Svāmikumāra / Kārttikeya in Deccan 3,8 (TP I 18); 6,159 (TP I 72)

temple of Vibhu (Śiva) with Pārvatī to the left and Vināyaka to the right of Vibhu 39,153 (TP III 229)

temple of *yakṣa* Mañibhadra in Tāmraliptī 13,165 (TP I 162)

temporin, see: ichor

temptation of self-restrained man by Indra with heavenly nymphs 45,89f. (TP IV 23)

ten days wandering in forest 52,220 (TP IV 153)

ten cardinal points conquered 72,91 (TP VI 75);

ten fingers, nurse hit with ~ by other woman 75,104 (TP VI 171);

tension between father and daughter ; ~ between father and son ; ~ between in-laws, see: father; mother-in-law

¹⁴⁹⁰ On the wrong translation by TP here, (and 25,238 [TP II 208]), due to false analysis of the compound and not asking why the small *tamāla* tree should be terrible, see TP II 227 note 2.

¹⁴⁹¹ The same as Vibhu's temple in 39,153 (TP III 229)

- ten-slayer (*daśa-mārikā*) as nickname of a tenfold husband-killer 66,86 (TP V 184);
- ten stages of love-sickness TP II 9 note 2. Cf. also 89,67 (TP VII 44) and Chojnacki 2008 (I): 344 s.v. *amour*.
- ten steps of Nala 56,345f. (TP IV 245)
- ten years long Trivikramasena daily receives fruit from mendicant 75,23 (TP VI 166); *rājput* lives ~ on fruits 81,23 (TP VI 210)
- ten *yojanas*, king's horse traverses ~ 94,14 (TP VII 88);
- terrace, jewelled ~s (*vicitra-ratna-prāsāda*) in the fourth *pātāla* 45,339 (TP IV 39; ORC 485: “*demeures*”); – see also: mosaic
- test, of brahmin's knowledge by king 30,131 (TP III 73); ~ of courtesan's love by king's assumed death 58,29 (TP V 17); ~ of three fastidious brahmins 82,18ff. (TP VI 218ff.); king wishes to ~ prince singing to the lyre 106,21 (TP VIII 29)
- theatre, royal (*raṅga-maṇḍapa*) 71,75 (TP VI 41);
- theft, capital sentence (*vadhe ... ādiṣṭe*) for presumed ~ 54,115 (TP IV 192); ~ of two fruits from brahmin causes him to curse his son 70,32f. (TP VI 26)
- thief, see: robber; – genetic ~ see: nativity
- thigh, as Creator Śiva drops from his ~ blood into universal water (*jalamayam jagat*) 2,10 (TP I 9)
- third day, king to die on ~ 53,115 (TP IV 176); 78,44 (TP VI 194);
- third person, story told in ~ (*ātmānam anyavat*) 27,3 (TP III 1)
- thirteenth day of going without food, brahmin is fed on ~ 52,224 (TP IV 153)
- thirty-three heroes slain 47,93 (TP IV 72)
- thought, coming on¹⁴⁹² ~ (*cintitôpasthita*) 5,18 (TP I 47) and 6,163 (TP I 72); (*dhyāta-mātrâgata*) 5,45 (TP I 50); idem (*smṛtamātrâgata*) 7,83 (TP I 83); idem of sword 18,116 (TP II 58); idem (*saṃsmṛtôpasthita*) of Kubera-Vaiśravaṇa 38,80 (TP III 212); idem of *pum̐sâtivikṛta* 75,4 (TP VI 164); Amartya-guru comes to Indra when ~ of 115,92 (TP VIII 150); – see also: coming
- thousand, granddaughters of Bali, king of Daityas 10,39 (TP I 108); Śiva's germ, developed after a ~ years, becomes boy with six faces, Kārttikeya 20,87 (TP II 102); ~ arms of Bāṇa cut off by Viṣṇu 27,142f. (TP III 12); brahmin hides ~ dinars in forest 33,136 (TP III 119); king cursed to pass one year long as a ~ *yugas* without queen 55,197 (TP IV 216); ~ dinars recompense for bawd teaching skill of courtesans 57,67 (TP V 6); ~ villages given as support of Gaṇeśa temple 73,327 (TP VI 124); ~ faces and mouths of Vāsuki 90,107 (TP VII 56); thief offers a ~ pieces of gold (*kāñcana*) to mother for daughter to be married to him 93,19 (TP VII 79); idem to be given to new-born son who is to be put at king's door 93,49 (TP VII 81); king meditates on Śiva living for a ~ years on fruits only 115,45 (TP VIII 147)
- thousand eyes¹⁴⁹³, Indra will have a thousand *divya-stri* on his body, which will become ~ when

¹⁴⁹² See Penzer's note in TP I 50 and TP II 58.

¹⁴⁹³ See Doniger O'Flaherty 1981: 84.

he sees Tilottamā, because Gautama cursed him for his adultery with Ahalyā 17,144f. (TP II 46)

thread bound around his neck turns man into monkey 37,110 (TP III 191); do, into ox 37,153 (TP III 194); ~ into peacock 71,276f. (TP VI 56); magician wears brahmanical ~ of hair (*dhṛta-keśōpavītaka*) 73,283 (TP VI 121); – sacred ~ see: *upanayana*

three arms (dagger, sword and shield) 78,10 (TP VI 191);

three, brahmin daughters 3,10 (TP I 19); ~ brahmin sons 3,6 (TP I 18f.); ~ fickle nobles smeared with soot (*kajjala*) 4,47-60 (TP I 33f.); ~ brahmin brothers 33,36 (TP III 109); ~ suitors 76,8 (TP VI 179)

three cold things: pearls, sandalwood and the moon 92,12 (TP VII 72); – see also: pearl

three couples (humans; water vessel and pitcher; broom and brazier; *yugma-tritaya*) 27,91 (TP III 7)

three days,¹⁴⁹⁴ performing austerities for ~ amidst fire in order to obtain bewildering power 46,120 (TP IV 56); prince waits ~ (*try-ahē gate*) for princess being accessible (due to her menstruation) 75,114 (TP VI 172); king stays ~ days in Vārāṇasī fasting and worshipping Śiva Vṛṣadhvaṅga 93,84 (TP VII 84)¹⁴⁹⁵

three eyes of Śiva, Gaurī obtains the three-eyed (*try-ambaka*) Śiva as husband 20,61 (TP II 100); ~ of Gaṇeśa 50,177 (TP IV 119); ~ of Śiva 50,190 (TP IV 120); 57,2 (TP V 1); *Try-akṣa* 109,74 (TP VIII 75); *deva-deva tri-locana* 112,135 (TP VIII 116)

three fastidious (*taruṇa*; in vs 11 *caṅga*) sons fetch turtle for brahmin's sacrifice 82,4ff. (TP VI 217); – see also: turtle ; three wives

three faults of women: flightiness, recklessness and love for congregation of witches¹⁴⁹⁶ 37,170 (TP III 195);

three fingers, go-between struck by woman with ~ red with dye on heart indicating three nights of menstruation on which she cannot receive suitor 75,113 (TP VI 172)¹⁴⁹⁷;

three fish in a lake near a river (*nady-antahsthe hrade*) 60,178 (TP V 56)

three or four, days sightseeing 54,60 (TP IV 188); ~ armed men 69,56 (TP VI 12);

three hands stretch out for *piṇḍa* in well of Gayā (*Gayā-kūpa*) 93,88 (TP VII 85); – see also: hand

three handfuls of rice as alms given to crows, guest and oneself 24,101 (TP II 177)

three happy beings (*dhanyāḥ*): Sarasvatī, Skanda and Jina 51,205 (TP IV 136)

three heads, snake with ~ 65,86 (TP V 161)¹⁴⁹⁸

¹⁴⁹⁴ In Kuv 15.5 the goddess Śrī remarks to a king worshipping her for a son: “Après trois nuits seulement ! Voilà un ascète bien impatient” .

¹⁴⁹⁵ TP translates *bhogair nijōcitaiḥ* by “with various meat-offerings.”

¹⁴⁹⁶ ORC 380: “la pratique de la magie ou de la sorcellerie”; M I 535: “die Flatterhaftigkeit, die Rücksichtslosigkeit und das Verlangen nach einer Versammlung mit Hexen”. Text: *śambara* ‘sorcery, magic’ (MW).

¹⁴⁹⁷ The heart is the seat of the lymph chyle (*rasa*) ... which is transformed into the catamenial flow in women (*Tasya [rasasya] hṛdayaṃ sthānaṃ ... rasād eva striyā raktam rajaḥ-saṃjñam pravartate* [Suśruta, *Sūtrasthāna* 14, 1-7]).

- three hundred *yojanas* 123,18 (TP IX 44);
 three kinds of fruit (*tri-phalā*) 70,43 (TP VI 27 with note 1);
 three lakhs of gold pieces 82,46 (TP VI 220)
 three languages forsaken by Guṇāḍya 5,129 (TP I 58); Sanskrit, Prakrit and vernacular
 taught in six months 6,146 (TP I 71)
 three lines on neck (*kambu-kaṇṭhī*) of female beauty 4,7 (TP I 31)
 three moons, night with ~ (*tri-candrêva yāminī*) 17,111 (TP II 43)
 three, prince grows up with ~ coeval ministers' sons 120,54 (TP IX 5)
 three nights' fast to propitiate Śiva for son 19,6 (TP II 85); idem 21,143 (TP II 136); do,
 35,103 (TP III 164); princess not accessible for ~ (due to menstruation) 75,113 (TP VI
 172); fights with witches for ~ 108,40ff. (TP VIII 55f.)
 three objects of life (*tri-varga*), married householder obtains ~ (of life) performing homage to
 gods, *pitaras*, and guests (as hospitality) 24,152 (TP II 180 with note specifying *tri-varga*
 as by virtue, wealth and pleasure: *dharma*, *artha* and *kāma*)
 three powers (*śakti*) of king: *prabhutva*, *mantra*, *utsāha* 34,123 (TP III 137); 34,198 (TP III
 143);
 three queens, see: three wives
 three robbers impaled and vitalised by *vetālas* 18,149 (TP II 61)
 three scales (*grāma*), Viṣṇu-stuti in ~ 106,12 (TP VIII 29);
 three sons die after birth of daughter who is therefore called Trimārikā 66,80 (TP V 184)
 three suitors, maiden promised to ~ 79,28 (TP VI 202)
 three times, knowledge of ~ acquired in Śiva temple 108,57 (TP VIII 57);
 three waterspirits (*jala-mānuṣa*) seize Bhilla king after bath 71,5 (TP VI 36);
 three wives, of king Naravāhanadatta 43,275 (TP III 300); ~ of prince Sūryaprabha 45,177
 (TP IV 29); ~ sensitive wives of king Dharmadhvaḥja 85,3 (TP VII 10, cf. three fastidious
 sons [supra]);
 three women, voices of ~ in the air 28,123 (TP III 30)
 three worlds, Bhavānī as mother of ~ 1,14 (TP I 2); ultimate beauty in ~ (*trailokya-sundarī*)
 11,39 (TP I 125); beauty queen of ~¹⁴⁹⁹ (Kaliṅgasenā) 31,63 (TP III 87) and 32,28 (TP
 III 92); ~ set on fire by light from brahmin's head 45,85 (TP IV 23); Kumudāvātī, beauty of
 the ~ 45,328 (TP IV 39); queen without equal in beauty in ~ 49,6 (TP IV 85); Ayodhyā
 famous in the ~ (*bhuvana-traya*) 69,15 (TP VI 10); chief beauty of ~ (*jagat-tritaya-*
sundarī) 69,49 (TP VI 12); merchant's daughter as *trailokya-ratna* 91,11 (TP VII 67);
 Naravāhanadatta knows all music in the ~ 106,15 (TP VIII 29); 121,219 (TP IX 28); –
 see also: *trailokya-sundarī*
 three wrinkles (*vali-traya*) like waves as sign of female beauty 84,7 (TP VII 5); ~ (*tri-valī-*)
 116,35 (TP VIII 158);
 three *yāmā* 'watch', satisfied hero's night long as if consisting of a hundred watchess instead

¹⁴⁹⁸ Cf. STh B 15.1.2.4.

¹⁴⁹⁹ A *façon de parler* for a beauty who surpasses all others (ORC 1659 s.v. *trois mondes*).

- of ~ 109,107 (TP VIII 78)
- throbbing, of the right eye heralds arrival of beloved woman 22,106 (TP II 144 with note 1; cf. 51,4 [TP IV 122])¹⁵⁰⁰; ~ of man's left arm and shoulder is evil omen 49,129 (TP IV 93; ~ of princess' right eye as evil omen 117,141 (TP VIII 173)
- throne, jewelled ~ (*ratna-siṃhāsana*) found in forest and guarded by *yakṣa* 18,44 (TP II 52); ~ of ivory (*danti-dantāsana*) 102,117 (TP VII 171); – see also: gold; *siṃhāsana*
- thug(s),¹⁵⁰¹ chief of a gang of ~ (? *caura-camū-pati* [not MW]) 73,206 (TP VI 116); Death (Kāla) like a ~ (?) leads robber with roomal thrown round his neck (*gala-kṣipta-pāśa*) to Yama-*sabhā* 72,348f. (TP VI 95); – see further: death; robber(s)
- thumb, divine Bālakhilyas the size of a ~ are engaged in austerities under bough of wishing-tree of paradise 12,142 (TP I 144)
- thunder (*megheṣu garjatsu*), peacocks begin to dance at ~ 71,17 (TP VI 37)
- thunderbolt, sword is to king what ~ is to Indra 11,43 (TP I 126); king smitten by ~ of grief (*śokāśani*) 58,39 (TP V 17); prince dreams of lion with claws terrible as ~ (*vajrôgrana-khara*) 69,23 (TP VI 10); man is smitten by wife's speech as if by down-lighting ~ (*vaco-vajra-pātena*) 84,39 (TP VII 7); bewildered king is as if struck by a (*vajrâhata iva*) 105,80 (TP VIII 26); the female is harder than the ~ 119,181 (TP VIII 205f.); – cf. lightning
- thundercloud, black ~ with rumbling thunder at sea is like a roaring *rākṣasa* 25,41 (TP II 191)
- thunderstorm (*vāyur mahā-raudrah*) 107,89 (TP VIII 49);
- tide (*kalā*),¹⁵⁰² 34,163 (TP III 140 with note one); the boy grew by degrees ... as the new moon fills out with digits and causes the sea to rise 35,114 (TP III 164; ORC 359: “*Comme la lune, cause de la croissance des marées, grandit chaque jour un doigt, cet enfant ... grandit*”; M I 505: “... *wie der zunehmende Mond mit seinen Strahlen nach und nach immer voller wird, um das Wachstum und Gedeihen des Meeres zu mehren*”);
- tiger-skins as wall decoration (*vyāghra-cchada-cchavi*) of Śabara dwellings 123,49 (TP IX 46)¹⁵⁰³
- tikṣṇāṃśu-bimba* ‘sun's disk’, spot defiles the ~ 90,141 (TP VII 59: “disk of the moon”; ORC 984: “*une tache souille le disque du soleil*”; M II 300: “*wie ein Fleck die Sonnenscheibe nicht besudeln kann*”)
- tilaka* ‘birthmark, mole > distinguishing sign’¹⁵⁰⁴, missing ~ of queen under girdle and painted on canvas angers king 5,32 (TP I 49); ‘spangle’ (?) 16,31 (TP II 22 with note 3: “The reference must be to the *ṭiklī*, or spangles worn by Hindu women, and not merely to the *tilaka*,

¹⁵⁰⁰ STh D 1812.5.2.1.

¹⁵⁰¹ See Dundas 1995; Van Woerkens 1995; Wagner 2007; ORC 1546 s.v. Bhilla. Thugs are reported first by Hsüan-tsang in the 7th cent. CE (Bowker 1997: 966).

¹⁵⁰² See e.g., Collins 1974: 171ff.

¹⁵⁰³ Living beings are travellers in the forest of *saṃsāra* (*saṃsāra-vana*) and as such are liable to be killed by the servants of Yama with a *pāśa*.

¹⁵⁰⁴ The meanings given in Jackmuth 2002: 103 must be extended.

or caste marks”; ORC 115: “*Vāsavadattā lui fit des tilaka*”; MI 162: “*V. malte ihr frisch bleibende Schönheitsflecken auf die Stirn*”; ~ of future *cakravartin* of *vidyādhara*s 43,169 (TP III 292); king Kalaśa of Kashmir was a ~ on the circle of the earth E 9 TP IX 88); – see also: comparison; forehead; moon, queen; red lead; *sindūra-tilaka*; western quarter
 Tilottamā curses king to be separated from his love for fourteen years 9,33 (TP I 96); ~ created by Viśvakarman 15,136 (TP II 14); ~ sent to seduce (*pralobhanāya*) two *Asuras* 15,138 (TP II 14)¹⁵⁰⁵; creator made ~ by taking an atom (< sesam seed: *tila*) from all noblest beings 27,66 (TP III 6), cf. 87,5 (TP VII 29); beautiful princess Damayantī said to be the ~ of the earth 56,251 (TP IV 297); as *maina*’s curse is finished she becomes ~ 77,90 (TP VI 189); Disposer (*vidhi*) makes priceless beauty after getting experience with ~ 87,5 (TP VII 29); *Daitya* maidens superior in beauty to ~ 118,167 (TP VIII 189), cf. 120,102 (TP IX 8);
 time,¹⁵⁰⁶ ~ past does not return 40,54 (TP III 244); ~ conquered (*vijita-kāla*) by brahmin Kāla muttering prayers (*japād a-viramaṃś ca saḥ*) 45,95f. (TP IV 24); *kālaṃ nayati* ‘to spend > kill the ~’ 101,162 (TP VII 145); due to fidelity to husband wife knows past, present and future 52,230 (TP IV 154); though mortal, brahmin knows the three ~s (*tri-kāla-jñāna*) 108,57 (TP VIII 57); warder as incarnation of ~ 124,189 (TP IX 81); time indicated by drum (q.v.; morning of new day) and conch (q.v.); – see also: evening; midday; night; twilight
 Timirā, unidentified residence city of the goddess of Prosperity (Śrī) 17,33 (TP II 36);
 tipsiness (*mada-sprś*), see: intoxication
tīrtha, halo appears on head of brahmin praying at Puškara ~ 45,83 (TP IV 23); old king retires to ~ due to the perishability of the body and then one should not remain in one’s house 52,384 (TP IV 165)¹⁵⁰⁷; death at ~ causes remembering pre-birth in next birth 69,164 (TP VI 20); ~ arisen from *pāda-nyāsa* of Hari/Viṣṇu (as Vāmana) 73,95 (TP VI 107); ~s have everlasting purity (*nitya-śuddha*) 86,21 (TP VII 14); brahmin visiting ~ to wash away transgressions (*kṣapayāmy agha-saṃcayam*) 87,25 (TP VII 31); *yakṣī* gives *kārpaṭika* ointment for the feet to travel to all ~s 123,27 (TP IX 45)
tīrtha-yātrāpadeśa ‘pretext of a pilgrimage’ 86,14 (TP VII 14)
ṭiṭṭibha ‘lapwing, plover’,¹⁵⁰⁸ couple 60,164 (TP V 55); Viṣṇu restores ~ eggs from the sea 60,194 (TP V 57);
todya ‘tabor (TP), kind of cymbal (MW)’, princess dancing to the music of a big ~ 71,76 (TP VI 41)
 toe-nails (*pāda-nakhâgra*) of Mahêśvara are reflected in crest-jewels (*cūḍā-maṇi*) of *devas* and *Asuras* kneeling before him 1,20 (TP I 3)
 tongue of man bitten off by woman in tree 13,108 (TP I 158)¹⁵⁰⁹; red banner on Caṇḍikā

¹⁵⁰⁵ Doniger O’Flaherty 1981: 84.

¹⁵⁰⁶ See, e.g. Balslev 1983

¹⁵⁰⁷ Cf. MaitrUp 1,2 *Bṛhadratho vai nāma rājā*, etc.

¹⁵⁰⁸ Dave 2005: 357ff.

temple resembles ~ of Death (*kṛtāntasya jihvā*) 22,63 (TP II 141); ~ of snakes split (*pāṭita-jihvā*) by lecking of *amṛta* 22,200 (TP II 152)¹⁵¹⁰; ~ of rogues is web (*jihvā-jāla*) with intricate threads 24,200 (TP II 184); black cloud with rumbling thunder resembles a roaring *rākṣasa* with flickering lightning as his rolling ~ 25,41 (TP II 192); ~ of *rākṣasa*, when swallowing / enjoying¹⁵¹¹ brains, quivers like flames 25,106 (TP II 199); sword-blades drinking blood and waving to and fro are like ~ of Death 50,5 (TP IV 108); ~ and hands of thief cut off 60,232 (TP V 61)¹⁵¹²; ~ (*rasanā*) of lion in dream cut off and used as bridge to cross river 69,25 (TP VI 10); pyres with lolling ~ of fire (*javā-vilola-rasana*) 92,1 (TP VII 71)

tonsure, see: hair

tooth, saw as sharp as the points of Yama's teeth (*Yama-daṃṣṭrâgra-tikṣṇa*) 121,86 (TP IX 18)

tortoise, see: turtle

touch of hand of female ascetic will release *vidyādhara* from curse 65,232 (TP V 172); ~ of princess's hand removes fever 71,122 (TP VI 44) and 205 (TP VI 50); by ~ Dharma transforms boar into *munindra* 72,145 (TP VI 78); ~ resembles nectarlike fluid, see nectar (*amṛta*); Caṇḍāla maiden stops elephant by striking his trunk with her hand 112,68 (TP VIII 111); princess comforts fisher-boy by ~ and shampoos his limbs with her cool hand 112,127 (TP VIII 116); – see also: boar; hand; Pāśupata ascetic

tourism, religious, see: pilgrimage; minister advises king to go to Lāvānaka for the sake of defending it and for his own enjoyment (*rakṣā-hetoś ca vinodāya ca*) 15,125 (TP II 12); ~ to behold seaside woods 22,177 (TP II 150); ~ in vow to see Golden city in order to marry princess 25,4f. (TP II 188); royal procession (*yātrā*) to garden 34,174 (TP III 140 'pilgrimage'); ~ to see temples in celestial gardens and lakes 35,158 (TP III 168); wandering about in town out of curiosity 43,138 (TP III 290) and 52,117 (TP IV 146); seeing city, gardens and many wonderful sights 52,4-10 (TP IV 138); deities show Naravāhanadatta around Nārikela island 54,49 (TP IV 187); ~ of hermit and male companion on pleasure journey 59,99 (TP V 33); prince is carried in arms of *vidyādhara* to see *vidyādhara* world out of curiosity 59,127 (TP V 35); sight-seeing country of Kirātas by prince and companions, travelling from Ayodhyā to Ujjayinī 70,47 (TP VI 27); royal couple roaming about out of curiosity finds snake bones 90,94 (TP VII 55); king's pilgrimage to Ganges as ~ when he is diverted by various garbs, languages and countries **93,76** (TP VII 83)¹⁵¹³; brahmin on ~ reaches lake Śaṅkahrada sacred to *nāga*-king 104,84 (TP VIII 7); king goes out to see beauty of town (*nagara-śrī*) 106,33 (TP VIII 30); *vidyādhari* on nightly flight shows king from the sky the earth like a *vedikā*, rivers like snakes and

¹⁵⁰⁹ See Baldissera 2004: 89.

¹⁵¹⁰ Vogel 1926: 53.

¹⁵¹¹ Cf. proper name of Lambajihva of a *rākṣasa* 25, 196 (TP II 206).

¹⁵¹² STh Q 451.4.

¹⁵¹³ Pilgrimage and education are also combined in Germany as is shown by a signboard on the motorway A 7: *Volkersberg Wallfahrt und Bildung*. Volkersberg is a place near Wuerzburg in Bavaria.

mountains like ant-hills¹⁵¹⁴ 106,86 (TP VIII 34); sudden arrival of king as if to take a look at the city (*a-kasmāt puraṃ draṣṭum ivāgatam*) 108,160 (TP VIII 65); 117,17ff. (TP VIII 165); *kutra ca kiṃ dr̥ṣṭaṃ kautukaṃ* 120,82 (TP IX 7); – see also: amusement; pleasure trip
 toxicological knowledge (*viṣa-vidyā*) saves brahmin 75,14 (TP VI 165)
 toy(s), white elephant as ~ 36,120 (TP III 177); clay horses, chariots and elephants 113,68 (TP VIII 129)¹⁵¹⁵
 toy-deer, two mermaids make living golden ~ (*krīḍā-hariṇa-potaka*) dance before them 120,107 (TP IX 9)
 track, woman can go back home to *āśram* from royal palace following sown ~ of mustard seeds (*sarṣapa*) 32,117 (TP III 98) and 182 (TP III 104)¹⁵¹⁶; hero follows ~ of drops of blood of *rākṣasa* 39,76 (TP III 223)
 trade, see: slave ~
 tradition, brahmin ~ is that life, son and wife must be sacrificed to protect the king 78,128 (TP VI 199)
 traffic, maritime ~, see: voyage
 trafficking in human beings, see human trafficking
 tragedy of love-sick king who is gradually consumed by fever of love 91,44 (TP VII 69)
trailokya-ratna ‘pearl of the three worlds’, merchant’s daughter as ~ 91,11 (TP VII 67)
trailokya-sundarī ‘most beautiful lady of the three worlds’, a Daitya maiden 11,39 (TP I 125); 30,64 (TP III 68); 52,341 (TP IV 162); ~ to be married 108,117 (TP VIII 62); ~ chooses own husband 121,219 (TP IX 28); – see also: miss universe
 transfer of merit¹⁵¹⁷, *yakṣa*’s wife burnt herself with his mortal body and his offences were wiped away by her sufferings 34,89 (TP III 135)
 transformation combat motif, see: bee; horse; witch; TP III 203ff.
 transformation¹⁵¹⁸ into fruits, see: tree; ~ into other beings, see: *apsaras*; bee; boar; buffalo; disguise; dog; elephant; *Gandharva*; horse; jackal; lion; maiden; monkey; old brahmin; *rājarṣi*; touch of hand; *vidyāharī*; wife; *yakṣiṇī*;
 transgression, Garuḍa wants to enter the fire to purify himself from ~ (*pāpa-śuddhaye*) of starting to eat Jīmūtavāhana 22,241 (TP II 155 “guilt”); ~ (*kilbiṣa*) contracted since birth (*ājanma-kilbiṣa*) 49,218 (TP IV 100); bodily ~ (*pāpaṃ kāyikaṃ*) is to be avoided 56,114 (TP IV 228); king pays off minor ~ by giving away twice ten crores of gold 72,106ff. (TP VI 77); burnt up by propitiating Śaṅkara / Śiva 72,359 (TP VI 95); Citragupta blots out ~ (*agha*) from birch bark register (*bhūrja*) 72,360 (TP VI 95); ~s (*agha*) washed away with water from *tīrthas* 87,25 (TP VII 31);

¹⁵¹⁴ König 1984: 83.

¹⁵¹⁵ See Dongerkery 1954.

¹⁵¹⁶ Cf. STh R 135.

¹⁵¹⁷ See ORC 1548 s.v. Bouddhisme; Michaels 2004: 178f., 208. Transfer of merit occurs already in Mbh 5,120.

¹⁵¹⁸ See further ORC 1610. Doniger O’Flaherty 1980a: 67ff., 93ff. Ninck 1921: 166f. quoting Ludwig Klages thinks the transformation belief emerges from dreaming in which phenomena use to change restlessly.

transience of everything 111,58 (TP VIII 101)

transmigration, see: rebirth

transport, nocturnal ~ on shoulder of *rākṣasa* 18,156 and 349 (TP II 62 and 75) and by *Gaṇas* 73,336 (TP VI 125); ~ of corpse with *vetāla* by king 75,57 (TP VI 168) et passim; ~ of man on shoulder of *yakṣiṇī* 37,182 but in the daytime he is carried in her lap (*tad-utsaṅge*) vs. 194 (TP III 196f.); *vetāla* carries man on his shoulder through the air 99,54 (TP VII 126); – see further: chariot; flying; *karnī-ratha*; palanquin; science(s); ship;

travelling; turtle; visibility

transposition of noses 61,16 (TP V 69); ~ of heads 80,47 (TP VI 207)¹⁵¹⁹

Trauerreise, see: mourning tour

trauma, see: anxiety trauma

travelling by air, transmission of knowledge of ~ (*utpatanīm vidyām ... avataraṇīm*) by *yakṣī* to male companion 37,201 (TP III 197) and (*vyoma-gamaṇī vidyā*) 59,106 (TP V 33); ~ of a *vidyādhara* 37,204 (TP III 197); ~ by holding tail of heavenly bull 65,185 (TP V 169); ~ of minister on shoulder of deformed man 75,4 (TP VI 164);

travelling by day over lake, of *Sītā* carried in the lap of the Earth goddess 51,82 (TP IV 127); ~ in autumn 122,72 (TP IX 38)

travelling by night, of king 22,99 (TP II 144) and 56,195 (TP IV 234); ~ of brahmin youths 32,45 (TP III 93); ~ of princes and minister in the *Vindhya* forest 42,97 (TP III 265); woman sets out ~ with husband and severed head of *Bhilla* 61,163 (TP V 82); of tricked princess ~ in forest 71, (TP VI 49); ~ of a refugee 73,184 (TP VI 114); ~ of prince as *persona non grata* 74,91 and 103 (TP VI 146f.); widow and daughter flee dead husband's relatives 93,11 (TP VII 79); minister ~ through *aṭavī* 101,5 (TP VII 134); couple flees ~ 104,200 (TP VIII 16); – see also: night

travelling by sea, see: voyage

treasure under boy's pillow (lit.: at his head, *śīrṣānte*) in the morning 3,22 (TP I 19); ~ buried¹⁵²⁰ in forest and guarded by *yakṣa* 18,41 (TP II 52); 19,15 (TP II 85) referring to four jars of gold buried 19,33 (TP II 87)¹⁵²¹; hidden ~ shown by *Durgā* in dream 23,40 (TP II 159)¹⁵²²; buried in garden under pomegranate-tree 30,120 (TP III 72); ~ of 1000 dinars buried in forest 33,137 (TP III 119); ~ hidden outside *Mathurā* and guarded by *yakṣa* 34,68 (TP III 133); *Pāśupata* brahmin makes business of exhuming ~ with candle made of human fat (*mānuṣa-vasā-dīpa*) falling out of hand 34,69f. (TP III 133); ~ in *Citrakūṭa* 35,37 (TP III 157f.); second ~ in copper vessel (*tāmra-kumbhi*) found in royal garden and dug up with a *lilā-vajra* 35,42 (TP III 158); ~ found in garden (*ārāma*) 54,89 (TP IV 190); ~ found by fool who decorates his wife with wrong ornaments 61,26 (TP V 70); – see also: pitcher; sign

¹⁵¹⁹ Courtright 2001: 94.

¹⁵²⁰ See Balbir 1993.

¹⁵²¹ Cf. Daś 39.16.

¹⁵²² Cf. STh X 12.

treasure-finder, hands and feet of ~ cut off 33,48 (TP III 110); 35,37 (TP III 157); ~ blinded 61,37f. (TP V 71);
 treasure-hunter, Pāsupata brahmin as ~ 34,69 (TP III 133)
 treasurer (*bhāṇḍāgārika*) ordered to give musician money 63,158 (TP V 133)
 treasury (*kośa*) empty 23,81 (TP II 164); – see also: *kośa-veśman*
 tree¹⁵²³, of policy (*naya-taru*) 17,163 (TP II 47)¹⁵²⁴; ~ of valour (*sattva-taru*) 18,368 (TP II 77) and (*pauruṣa-pādapa*) 96,44 (TP VII 111); wealth is root of ~ of empire (*rājya-taru*) 19,51 (TP II 88); magic banyan ~ (*vaṭa-taru*) like mountain with wings emerging from ocean 26,9 (TP II 217); *divyā nārī* emerges from *vaṭa* ~ 26,205 (TP II 233)¹⁵²⁵; ~ of good deeds (*sukṛt-pādapa*) 27,99 (TP III 8); ~ of virtue (*dharma-taru*) 27,132 (TP III 11); hollow ~ 29,115 (TP III 47); woman in trunk of ~ (*koṭara-sthitā*) overhears *rākṣasī* 29,148 (TP III 50); minister's counsel waters with nectar the ~ of empire (*amṛta-seko manro rājya-śākinah*) 33,163 (TP III 121); ~ of valour (*sattva-taru*) 35,69 (TP III 160); ~ of merit (*puṇya-taru*) 39,78 (TP III 223); from his foetal state onward one eats the fruit of the ~ of his former actions (*pūrva-karma-taru*) 40,109 (TP III 249); ~ of enmity (*vaira-pādapa*) 42,77 (TP III 264); in Śiva's abode ~s ever bear flowers and fruit 50,189 (TP IV 120); Nala counting leaves of ~ 56,380 (TP IV 247f.); man in ~ as witness of theft of treasure 60,225 (TP V 60); cutting down of date palms (*kharjūrī-chedana*) punished by king 61,35 (TP V 71)¹⁵²⁶; man emerges from ~ 63,73 (TP V 125); men staying the night in ~ 64,153 (TP V 151)¹⁵²⁷; ~ of existence (*bhava-pādapa*) 66,18 (TP V 179); dry ~ (*śuṣka-vṛkṣa*) growing leaves and fruit at night 70,26 (TP VI 25); dry ~ becomes brahmin¹⁵²⁸ 70,29 (TP VI 26); father curses son to become dry ~ 70,34 (TP VI 26); princess looks like a creeper of the ~ of love (*smara-taru*) 71,77 and (*smara-druma*) 71,92 (TP VI 41f.)¹⁵²⁹; tricked princess wants to kill herself in the ashes of a *śālmālī* ~, burnt for her, and thus pay her debt to it (*bhaviṣyāmy āṇṇā*¹⁵³⁰ *taroh*) 71,185 (TP VI 49); brahmin lives with *yakṣiṇī* like banyan-tree with glory of spring 73,27 (TP VI 102); two heavenly women emerge from *nyagrodha* ~¹⁵³¹ 73,412 (TP VI 130); golden city (*hemayaṃ puram*) inside ~ 73,414 (TP VI 130); *aśoka* ~ in charnel ground smelling of raw flesh (*kravya-gandhin*) 75,51 (TP VI 167); association with wicked people is root of ~ of vice 77,18 (TP VI 184); wonderful ~ agitated by the wind looked like Śaṅkara dancing, and has fruits that transform men into

¹⁵²³ See: substantives instead of augmentative suffixes (supra) and ORC 1536.

¹⁵²⁴ Cf. Daś (Bombay 1940) 278,7 *naya-vanaspati*.

¹⁵²⁵ Gonda 1965: 339.

¹⁵²⁶ Cf. STh J 2126.1.

¹⁵²⁷ Against TP the word *suptam* belongs to the second half of vs. 153.

¹⁵²⁸ Crooke 1911: 196f.

¹⁵²⁹ Cf. Kumārasambhava 3,39 (Jackmuth 2002: 75f.).

¹⁵³⁰ The D-text has *āṇṇā* (*metrī causā*).

¹⁵³¹ Cf. OCD s.v. tree.

fruits 100,18-23 (TP VII 130); wonderful ~ is residence of Gaṇapati (Gaṇeśa) who curses those eating its fruit 100,39 (TP VII 131); ~ s compared to ascetics with arms / branches aloft 101,27 (TP VII 136); hermitage ~s ask for alms 101,28 (TP VII 136); ~ of Gaṇeśa Vighnajt worshipped (*natvā Vighnajit-drumaṃ*) 102,2 (TP VII 162)¹⁵³²; at royal marriage even ~s had garments and gems fastened to them,¹⁵³³ and looked like earthly wishing ~s 103,199 (TP VII 188); clump of ~s like Kāma's body burnt by Śiva's eye 104,91 (TP VIII 7); poison-tree of wealth (*dhana-viṣa-druma*) 104,117 (TP VIII 10); warriors like ~s marked for the axe 108,105 (TP VIII 62); hermit Akampana looking like a great ~ (*mahā-druma*) 110,24 (TP VIII 83), cf. 113,86 (TP VIII 130); ~s of gold in Siddhīśvara 115,114 (TP VIII 152); ~ produces flowers of different kinds 117,82 (TP VIII 170); Dānava maidens concealing their forms in ~s by means of magic (*taruṣv antar māyā-cchādita-vigrahāḥ*) 118,107 (TP VIII 185); prince has gathered the fruit of the ~ of his birth (*janmataru*) 119,207 (TP VIII 208); – dancing ~s, see: dancing; – see also: *arjuna*; *aśoka*; *aśvattha*; *bilva*; disguise; fig tree; five trees; *jambu*; *kalpa*; *mandāra*; mango; merit; *nyagrodha*; palm tree; *pārijāta*; realm; *uḍumbara*; wishing tree; tree-spirit (dryad), hospitality of ~ 63,70ff. (TP V 125) tree worship of *aśvattha* 20,26 (TP II 96f.)¹⁵³⁴; 26,205 (TP II 233) tribute (*kara*), elephants presented as royal ~ (*kari-kṛta*) 19,114 (TP II 94); earth as ~ 42,196 (TP III 274); – see also: *antaḥpura* trident, queen dreams of ~-bearing (*śūlin*) god Śiva 23,21 (TP II 158); ivory-carver's daughter marked on the loins (*jaghana-sthala*)¹⁵³⁵ with heated ~ of angry Śaiva ascetic 75,157-160 (TP VI 175); idem 75,176 (TP VI 176); goddess Durgā who has a ~ in her hand (*śūla-karā*) 78,90 (TP VI 196: “trident-bearing”; ORC 921: “*déesse au trident*”; M II 212: “*Göttin mit dem Spies in der Hand*”)¹⁵³⁶ Trigartā, garland-city (*mauli-maṇḍana-mālikā ... su-mano-guṇa-gumphitā*) strung with virtues as with flowers, on the head of the earth-bride (*vasudhā-vadhu*) 73,21 (TP VI 102 note 2: it also means: “the virtues of good or learned men”; ORC 853: “*terre, tressée avec les qualités des hommes bienveillants qui l'habitent*”; M II 114: “*(Stadt) ist wahrlich ein Kranz, der das Haupt der Braut, welche die Erde ist, schmückt. Denn sie ist umwunden mit Blumen, Vorzügen und Tugenden.*”)¹⁵³⁷

¹⁵³² Haberman 2013 does not mention a tree especially dedicated to Gaṇeśa, but writes (p. 55): “I visited a banana tree shrine in the small temple compound of a Kali temple in Rishikesh, for the banana tree is also linked to the goddess Kali. ... at its base ... several Shiva lingas and images of Ganesha had been placed. Because of the fluid nature of the religious ideas associated with the trees in India, the identity of the god or goddess connected with a particular tree is not firmly set; a single species can be identified with more than one god or goddess.”

¹⁵³³ Haberman 2013: 157.

¹⁵³⁴ Haberman 2013: 49; Pande 1965: 36f.

¹⁵³⁵ In vs 155 *kaṭi-taṭa*, 160 *jaghana*.

¹⁵³⁶ Cf. Daś 281.24 where it is Bhavānī with the trident.

¹⁵³⁷ Cf. Daś 218.1.

tri-kāla-jñā, see: *guru*

Trimārikā, daughter named ~ because three sons die after her birth 66,80 (TP V 184)

Tri-patha-gā,¹⁵³⁸ ‘flowing in three courses > worlds’, epithet of Gangā 4,30 (TP I 32)

tri-phalāḥ, see fruit

tri-varga, see: three objects

tṛṇa, see: forest; grass; sayings; *śīla-tṛṇa*

Trojan horse as mechanical elephant (*yantra-hastin*), see: elephant; warriors

trumpet-flowers (*pāṭala*)¹⁵³⁹ blooming ~ 122,65 (TP IX 38)

trunk (*mañjūṣā*), three suitors of married woman put in ~ at night 4,56ff. (TP I 34); servants who kept rain off the clothes- ~ (*petā*) 62,195 (TP V 116)

truth (*satya*), royal parasol keeps off from sunshine as well as from ~ 91,57 (TP VII 70);

gods speak ~ (said of Gaurī: *na me mithyā vacaḥ*) 90,185 (TP VII 61); – see also: act of truth

try-akṣa ‘with three eyes; with three dice’ 121,104 (TP IX 19)

try-ambaka, see: Śiva

tsunami causes shipwrecked princess to be thrown into forest / wilderness (*atyuccenōrmiṇā prāpaṇaṃ vane*) 101,144 (TP VII 144);

tūlikā-caṅga, see: bed

Tumbavana, place in the south 49,175 (TP IV 97 reading Jambuvana against D)

Tumburu,¹⁵⁴⁰ dancing teacher, curses Purūravas to separation from Urvaśī 17,23 (TP II 35); his daughter Maṅgalāvātī 45,177 (TP IV 29);

tunnel (*surāṅgā*) dug to underground dungeon, and king in it killed 40,61 (TP III 245; see note 2 in TP V 142)¹⁵⁴¹; ~ (*guhā*) through Mt Kailāsa, see: cave

turban of honour (*paṭṭa*) 12,190 (TP I 148)¹⁵⁴²; 14,33 (TP I 184); 29,193 (TP III 54); ~ of *vidyādhara* emperor 50,206 (TP IV 121); ~ for heroic brahmin 53,191 (TP IV 181); ~ to warder and general 54,233 (TP IV 200); ~ given to queen 55,237 (TP IV 218); magician on charnel ground wears ~ made of garments of the dead (*preta-vastra-kṛtōṣṇīṣa*) 73,283 (TP VI 121); ~ put on at inauguration 103,218 (TP VII 190);

turning the neck (*valita-kandhara*) and looking back for pursuing *rākṣasa* 39,133 (TP III 227); woman in *āśram* going away ~ back to look with loving eye to lover 67,71 (TP V 201); princess in love departs often ~ 90,87 (TP VII 55); robber ~ out of fear 112,152 (TP VIII 118); *vidyādhara* prince ~ (*valita-grīvaṃ paśyan*) to his *Gandharva* bride when leaving for battle 116,55 (TP VIII 160); – see also: looking

turtle (*kacchapa*) in sea as Garuḍa’s food 12,140 (TP I 144); ~ (*kūrma*) carried on stick

¹⁵³⁸ Lüders 1951: 686.

¹⁵³⁹ *Brugmansia suaveolens* (Macmillan 1991: 122; not in McHugh 2012)

¹⁵⁴⁰ Tumburu, together with Hā Hā and Hū Hū, worships Hari in GaṇPur II 9,2. As a *Gandharva* (q.v.) Tumburu (!) is a proverbial lute player in Hemacandra, *Triṣaṣṭi* VI 2,117.

¹⁵⁴¹ Cf. Daś 34.12.

¹⁵⁴² Gonda 1969: 37.

(*yaṣṭi*) by two *haṃsas* 60,172 (TP V 56 and note 3)¹⁵⁴³; crow, mouse and ~ as friends 61,85 (TP V 75); three sons fetch marine ~ for brahmin's sacrifice 82,6 (TP VI 217)¹⁵⁴⁴
 Turuṣkas (Turks), cavalry of ~ subdued by elephants of king of Vatsa 19,109 (TP II 93);
tūrya-kolāhala (not MW) 'loud sound of musical instruments' 54,83 (TP IV 190 "great noise of drums"; ORC 599: "grands battements de tambour"; MI 839: "Lärm eines verworrenen und von Trommeln begleiteten Geschreis")¹⁵⁴⁵
 tusks (*daṃṣṭra*), of Brahma-rākṣasas 94,70 (TP VII 91f.); 114,107 (TP VIII 140); ~ of elephants as wall decoration (*danti-dantacitōttuṅga-bhitti*) in Śabara dwellings 123,49 (TP IX 46)
 tutelary deity (*daivata*) of a town,¹⁵⁴⁶ Sarasvatī as ~ 66,30 (TP V 180); deluded *brahma-rākṣaka*, ~ of brahmin boy, wants to eat him 94,133 (TP VII 96);
 twelfth¹⁵⁴⁷ day of the month, on ~ king dreams of unison with Daitya maiden, but waking up does not see her¹⁵⁴⁸ 73,88 (TP VI 107);
 twelfth white fortnight of Āṣāḍha, festival for Hari on ~ in Ratnakūṭa 26,4 (TP II 217)
 twelve, on the number twelve see Spellman 1962 and Sternbach 1962.
 twelve *apsaras*, companions of Mahallikā, abducted from Indra's heaven to first *pātāla* 45,346 (TP IV 40); Maya saves ~ *apsaras* (queens) from 4th *pātāla* 46,18 (TP IV 50);
 twelve days fast, after king's ~ two heavenly *haṃsas* speak to him understandably (*vyaktvā vācā*) in his dream 114,48 (TP VIII 136); ~ of *vidyādhara* prince to propitiate Bhagavān Śiva who gives him the sword Invincible (*A-parājita*) 115,141 (TP VIII 154); ~ by two princesses to blackmail Śiva for a husband 119,62 (TP VIII 198);
 twelve festival days at obtaining son 93,58 (TP VII 82);
 twelve suns, Gaṇeśa's brightness blazing forth like ~¹⁵⁴⁹ 50,177 (TP IV 119) and 100,46 (TP VII 130)
 twelve Veda branches (*śākha*) 49,156 (TP IV 95);
 twelve wives of Prabala 46,243 (TP IV 65)
 twelve years' drought 5,72 (TP I 52)¹⁵⁵⁰; learning grammar in twelve years 6,144 (TP I 71); shoes carried on head for ~ 6,149 (TP I 71); ~ search for treacherous Pāsupata ascetic

¹⁵⁴³ Penzer supposes the Kacchapa Jātaka to be the source of this story. On tortoises see Patyal 1995; Desai 2009.

¹⁵⁴⁴ The turtle is dedicated to and the *vāhana* (animal symbol) of Varuṇa. It plays a role in the Agnicayana where it is inserted in the layers of the fire altar (Meyer 1937: III 223ff.; Krick 1982: 115). – According to the English newspaper Daily Mail of No. 26th 2011 thousands of turtles are presently sacrificed to Kālī at Dīvālī in Bengal (dailymail.co.uk/.../100.000-turtles-sacrificed-ritual-slaughter-celebrate-Hindu-festival.html). Turtle sacrifices are performed also in the Hinduist Indonesian island of Bali.

¹⁵⁴⁵ Chojnacki 2008: I 364 notes "trompette" for *tūrya*.

¹⁵⁴⁶ Also Daś 99.5 (*nagara-devatā*) and cf. Ferri 2010 for the Roman idea of a tutelary divinity.

¹⁵⁴⁷ See also Sternbach 1962.

¹⁵⁴⁸ Cf. RV place < Bollée ??? Träume

¹⁵⁴⁹ As will appear at the destruction of the world (ORC 1479 on 1038 note 1 for which no source is given).

¹⁵⁵⁰ See drought (supra), Daś 218.3 and Bollée 2010: 33 note 169.

- 56,224 (TP IV 236); ~ of asceticism 73,99 (TP VI 108) and 73,171 (TP VI 113); ~ of *kārpāṭika* to king Vikramāditya 124,54 (TP IX 72); ~ old son accused of not knowing his father 124,204 (TP IX 82: “being bastard”);
- twenty-fifth day, single combats on ~ 116,69 (TP VIII 161)
- twenty-first, on ~ day Asuras rout the gods 115,60 (TP VIII 148);
- twenty-five tales, see: tale
- twilight, sun, in love with ~, departs together with the day 95,67 (TP VII 102); nymphs (*vara-striyaḥ*) always dancing in Śiva temple at both ~s 123,135 (TP IX 52); – see also: evening
- twin sons, queen bears ~ 113,32 (TP VIII 126)¹⁵⁵¹
- two Aśvins¹⁵⁵² as messengers of Indra to Nāgārjuna 41,15 (TP III 253)
- two brahmin sons (elder one stupid, younger wise) 20,8 (TP II 95); 25,75 (TP II 196); ~ young brahmins 104,11 (TP VIII 2); ~ born in father’s middle age (*vayasi madhyame*) 114,84 (TP VIII 138)
- two brothers, (elder stupid) 2,55 (TP I 13); ~ *Asuras* 15,135 (TP II 13); ~ carpenters 43,22 (TP III 282); ~ of whom the younger deceives the elder as to a treasure near a tree, is found out and banished 60,232 (TP V 61); ~ elder spendthrift, younger economic 61,301f. (TP V 95); ~ divide heritage literally 62,173 (TP V 114); ~ donated to brahmin 113,62f. (TP VIII 128) and offered for sale 113,81 (TP VIII 130);
- two Buddhist monks (*śramaṇau*) in Pratiṣṭhāna 51,118 (TP IV 130)
- two cows, brahmin gets ~ as charity which thief and *rākṣasa* want to carry off 62,91 (TP V 107)
- two daughters of *Asura* Maya 29,15 (TP III 40);
- two districts (*vedy-ardha*) of *vidyādhara* territory 107,65 (TP VIII 47);
- two *divya-kanyake* sit on *nyagrodha* stem at night 17,111 (TP II 43)
- two elephants, air-going ~ given by Śakra 118,24 (TP VIII 179);
- two fathers, ill-treated stepson tells his father : “*dvau mama tātau staḥ*” thus suggesting his stepmother is unfaithful 14,46 (TP I 185)
- two fingers shown 5,12 (TP I 45)
- two friends 38,4 (TP III 206)
- two garments as presents for *purohita* 24,113 (TP II 178); – see also: present; reward
- two goddesses, Diti and Danu, mothers of the *Asuras* in Kaśyapas hermitage, visited 45,363 (TP IV 41);
- two golden *haṃsas* flying over palace at night, king sees ~ looking like two golden lotuses 114,24 (TP VIII 134); ~ appear to king in dream 114,48 (TP VIII 136); – see also: golden lotuses
- two grains of rice from *pāka-bhāṇḍa* in which child was cooked causes a man to spit gold 108,77 (TP VIII 59)
- two *haṃsa* (*haṃsa-yuga*) made of wood with flying mechanism with strings 43,25 (TP III

¹⁵⁵¹ STh T 587.

¹⁵⁵² Gonda 1974: 42ff.

- 282); ~ hold stick with tortoise 60,172f. (TP V 56)
- two heads, snake with ~ 63,175 (TP V 134);
- two hundred *yojanas*, chariot going ~ 43,44 (TP III 284); ~ *varṣa* of years of muttering prayers at Puṣkara *tīrtha* produces immense light at brahmin's (*mahā-dvija*) head which sets the three worlds on fire 45,84 (TP IV 23)
- two maidens, a dark and a white one, on sandbank in sea 120,105 (TP IX 8) and 121,225f. (TP IX 28); ~ in cave of *kāpālika* 124,17 (TP IX 69)
- two men deliberating in empty (*śūnya*) temple 27,152 (TP III 12f.)
- two mermaids, a dark and a white one on a sandbank in mid ocean 120,105 (TP IX 8)
- two months, execution after ~ 27,30 (TP III 3)
- two moons 101,69ff. (TP VII 139)
- two princesses (*rāja-kanye*) suddenly appearing in forest 123,103 (TP IX 50)
- two pupils of Guṇāḍhya 8,16 (TP I 90); ~ each washing one foot of teacher 63,164 (TP V 133);
- two queens follow king 19,71 (TP II 90); 42,54 (TP III 263); ~ suddenly die 73,405 (TP VI 129); 74,45 (TP VI 143);
- two *rākṣasīs* abducting *Gandharva* maiden from lake 116,28f. (TP VIII 158);
- two red lotuses (*raktāmbuja*), deity in dream gives to couple ~ 13.79 (TP I 156)
- two robbers about to rob brahmin miser in Ujjayinī 24,86 (TP II 175f.); ~ enter bedchamber of princess who then has sex (*rantvā*) with one of them 64,46 (TP V 143)
- two snakes entwined in sex about to be eaten (?) by camel (q.v.) 69,87 (TP VI 15);
- two sons and one daughter of brahmin 6,9 (TP I 60)
- two spells (*mantra-prayoga*), witch with ~ 37,110 (TP III 191);
- two thieves, see: two robbers
- two thousand dinars, quarrel about ~ by two brothers 60,220 (TP V 60)
- two or three days, of marching 14,15 (TP I 183); ~ of coma of insolvent brahmin gambler 92,21 (TP VII 72); after ~ of love-sickness merchant woman considers suicide 95,26 (TP VII 100); after ~ sailing 101,175 (TP VII 146)
- two or three months, after ~ brahmin meets prince 70,78 (TP VI 29)
- two or three steps and words of an infant prince 23,88 (TP II 165)
- two *vidyādharas* as spies 108,125 (TP VIII 63)
- two wives, of prince 42,187 (TP III 273) and 42,202 (TP III 274) and 72,83 (TP VI 74); ~ emerge from mouth¹⁵⁵³ of heavenly man from lake 63,20 (TP V 121); ~ of brahmin 63,56 (TP V 124); idem 73,399 and 417 (TP VI 129f.) and 123,273 (TP IX 62) ; ~ of Hara 90,3 (TP VII 49)
- two women gathering flowers 26,38 (TP II 220)
- two wonders 33,28 (TP III 109);
- two wooden geese robbing royal treasury 43,28 (TP III 283)
- two worlds, grief produces dissatisfaction in both worlds 62,185 (TP V 115)

¹⁵⁵³ Thus TP; text reads: *sukhād*.

- Uccaiḥśravas, Namuci's horse 46,221 (TP IV 63); ~ resuscitates the dead 50,119 (TP IV 115); ~ unyoked from sun's chariot begets royal mare 123,13 (TP IX 44)
- udaka-dāna* festival¹⁵⁵⁴ 112,25 (TP VIII 106); do (*jala-dāna*), 112,60 (TP VIII 110) and 112,78 (TP VIII 111); – see also: donation water
- udārākṛti* (not MW) 'noble appearance' 59,82 (TP V 32)
- Udayācala 'mountain of sunrise', Garuḍa leaves pregnant queen on ~ where she bears a son who therefore is called Udayana 30,47 (TP III 67); moon as driving hook of the elephant of the ~ 103,204 (TP VII 189); – see also: sunrise
- Udayana,¹⁵⁵⁵ birth of ~, the later king of Vatsa 30,47 (TP III 67)
- udghāta* 'hint, suggestion, allusion', by ~ warder remembers (affair) 71,295 (TP VI 57 with note 2)
- udghoṣa-dinḍima* 'warning drum' giving notice to all virtuous high-born women (*kula-yoṣtitaḥ*) to retire, when the king rides out 91,23 (TP VII 67; ORC 990: "*Des tambours accompagnaient une proclamation invitant toutes les dames de la ville à se tenir à l'écart, la vue de la beauté du roi pouvant mettre leur vertu en péril*"; M II 308: "*Eine Trommel verkündete laut warnend, daß sich die tugendhaften Frauen zurückziehen sollten, um ihren vorauszusehenden und wahrscheinlichen Untergang beim Anblick seiner Schönheit zu entgehen.*")
- udghoṣaka* 'man making a proclamation' 94,98 (TP VII 94)
- udrikta-manmatha*, (not MW) (nymph of night) 'overflowing with love' 94,52 (TP VII 91; see supra: *rātry-abhisārikā*)
- udumbara* 'figus racemosa Wall.'¹⁵⁵⁶, its fruits eaten by monkey and dolphin 63,97f. (TP V 127 'porpoise' instead of 'dolphin'; ORC 733: "*dauphin*")
- udyāna-latā-grha* (not MW) 'arbour of creepers in royal garden', king marries princess by *gāndharva* ceremony in ~ 14,69 (TP I 187: 'summer-house'; ORC 101: "*tonnelle de jardin*"; M I 144: "*Gartenhaus*")
- ugliness stereotype, of man 12,51 (TP I 137); ~ by misshapen figure and ugly face (*vikṛto vikaṭānanaḥ*) with large mouth 52,77 (TP IV 143); brahmin as embodiment of ugliness (*agraṇīr*) *virūpānām* **123,163f.** (TP IX 55 "projecting teeth, a flat nose, dark colour, squinting eyes, big belly, crooked feet and ears like winnowing baskets"); – see also: eyes; face
- ugliness stereotype of woman: ~ of brahmin female (Kālarātrī) with flat nose **20,108f.** (TP II 103f.); ~ of bawd 57,60 (TP V 5)¹⁵⁵⁷
- ugra-pratāpa*, see: valour

¹⁵⁵⁴ Kane 1973: IV 218ff.

¹⁵⁵⁵ Zin 1990 and 1998.

¹⁵⁵⁶ Meulenbeld 1974: 528f.

¹⁵⁵⁷ Cf. e.g. Gaṇeśapurāna II 7,13f. where Virajā is depicted.

Ujjayinī, ornament of the earth, with its white palaces laughs to scorn Amarāvati 11,31f. (TP I 124f.); king crossing river Revā for ~ 19,98 (TP II 93); ~ town in Avanti and residence of Śiva Mahākāla (**description**) 27,135 (TP III 11)¹⁵⁵⁸; ~ built by the gods, limitless as the body of Śiva (...); its names in previous *yugas* 83,5f. (TP VII 1); ~ residence of Śiva¹⁵⁵⁹ inferior only to Bhogavatī and Amarāvati (**description**) 92,10ff. (TP VII 71); **description** 102,10ff. (TP VII 163); Śambhu protects ~ against *vetālas* 102,20 (TP VII 163); ~ is like a faithful (*satī*) woman, resort of Śrī like a lotus plant, rich in *dharma* like the heart of the good (*dhīriva satām*) and like the earth full of many wonderful sights 120,10 (TP IX 2)

Umā worships Gaṇeśa 20,84 (TP II 102); ~ in dream announces future son to be devoted to *dharma* 51,17 (TP IV 123);

umbrella, see: sunshade

uncle on mother's side, head of ~ shorn¹⁵⁶⁰ to ward him off at the abduction of princesses 44,59 (TP IV 5)

unconscious (*mūrchita*), Indra falls ~ on chariot of wind-god 115,67 (TP VIII 149)

undertaking begun is to be completed 22,234 (TP II 154)

underworld, journey into Pātāla 45,51 (TP IV 20); palace in second ~ with body of giant 45,115f. (TP IV 25); Asura prince invites guests in his fifth ~ 45,325 (TP IV 38); idem in seventh ~ 45,329 (TP IV 39); opening to ~ in Kāśmīra made by Maya 73,107 (TP VI 108); – see also: *Pātāla-śāstra*

unemployed brahmin steals horse in order to show himself as the finder 30,92-101 (TP III 70f.)

unfaithfulness, see: infidelity

ungrateful, prince ~ towards bear who saved him from lion 5,86f. (TP I 53)¹⁵⁶¹; ~ men blinded by greed cannot see benefit (proverb: *kṛta-ghnā dhana-lobhāndhā nōpakārēkṣaṇa-kṣamāḥ*) 18,308 (TP II 72); ~ (*kṛta-ghna*) though long successful will fail at last 56,230 (TP IV 236); apparently ~ snake bites Nala 56,347ff. (TP IV 245); ~ brahmin rashly kills mongoose which guarding the brahmin's son killed a snake 64,10 (TP V 139); ~ woman and grateful animals 65,54ff. (TP V 158ff.)

unguent, see: *aṅga-rāga*; *siddhāñjana*

unity, see: oneness

universe becomes water (*jalamayam jagat*) in which Śiva drops blood from his thigh 2,10 (TP I 9); ~ is broken up when, due to the preparation of *amṛta*, there will be no difference between gods and men 41,18 (TP III 253); – Miss ~ see: **Miss**

unmāda, see: madness

Unmādinī, beautiful merchant daughter offered to king 91,8 (TP VII 66)¹⁵⁶²

¹⁵⁵⁸ Cf. Daś 8.2; Kādambarī (Bombay, 1948) 109,3–116,3.

¹⁵⁵⁹ Cf. 120,9 *purāri-vasatiḥ* (TP IX 2)

¹⁵⁶⁰ ORC 1405 note 2 ad 458 “*hors de certains rites, le fait de raser la tête de quelqu'un est un traitement injurieux et humiliant.*”

¹⁵⁶¹ STh W 154.8; Rājat 5,310f.

¹⁵⁶² Anderson 2005: 97ff.

unmatta-ceṣṭa (not MW) ‘behaving like a madman’ 18,246 (TP II 68); – see also: madness
unnatural birth¹⁵⁶³ 34,81 and 90 (TP III 134f.); Mātāṅga born to brahmin maiden by Agni
112,103f. (TP VIII 113)
unnatural conception (q. v.)
unrighteousness (*a-dharma*), donkey (*khara*) symbolical of ~ 70,118 (TP VI 32)
untouchability of *caṇḍālas*: *na taiḥ saṃkaro mama says vidyādhara* 112,196 (TP VIII 121)
upakāra ‘service in return’ ends curse 65,64 and 81 and 93 (TP V 159ff.)
upalakṣaṇa ‘mark, sign’ (where something has been buried)¹⁵⁶⁴ 33,144 (TP III 119)
upanayana ‘sacred thread’¹⁵⁶⁵, investiture with ~, of a hermit 59,98 (TP V 33); ~ of a
brahmin 104,20 (TP VIII 2); 114,85 (TP VIII 139); 118,49 (TP VIII 181); ~ of a prince
120,55 (TP IX 5)
upamāna, see: comparison(s)
upāya ‘politic device’ 20,2 (TP II 95); – see also: four *upāyas*
upoṣaṇa ‘fast’¹⁵⁶⁶, in the scriptures of the *bhikṣus* broken shortly before its completion by
brahmin with one of his wives in the fourth watch of the night, leaving his recollection of pre-
births 63,57 (TP V 124); *śramaṇas* teach brahmin ~ 63,76 (TP V 125); brahmins give fruit
of ~ to *yakṣa* (~-*vratam yakṣa-puṇyāya cakratuḥ*) 63,87 (TP V 126); ~ involves
truthfulness, circumambulating statues of deities, eating when *śramaṇas* do, restraint of mind
and patience 63,82 (TP V 126);
ūrdhva-pāda ‘heels-up’, *muni* practising penance ~ is excited by Menakā 32,99 (TP III 97)
Uriah letter, see: letter of death
Urvaśī, see: Purūravas
urvī-bhṛt ‘mountain’, see: Harṣa
uṣṇīṣa (‘turban’) made of garments of corpses (*preta-vastra*) 73,282 (TP VI 121);
utpala ‘Egyptian blue lotus, *Nymphaea caerulea* Sav.’, good smell of ~ 59,4 (TP V 26; cf.
16,28 [TP II 22])
utpāta-māruta, see: hurricane; tsunami
utpāta-māyā (not MW) ‘delusive omen’, displayed by rivals for impediment but dissipated
46,30 (TP IV 51)
utsāha-śālin (not MW) ‘cheerful’, said of a king 35,95 (TP III 163)
utsava-tūrya (not MW) ‘festal musical instrument’ 103,197 (TP VII 188)
Utsthala, an island of Niṣāda aboriginals in the ocean 25,39 (TP II 191)
uttamārtha (not MW; Pāli *uttam’-attha*) ‘supreme goal, *mokṣa*’ 7,19 (TP I 75)
uttaṅga-nāsika (not MW) ‘high-nosed’ guru 61,15 (TP V 69)
Uttara, mountain in Kāmpilya country 25,23 (TP II 190)

¹⁵⁶³ See Doniger O’Flaherty 1973: 377 20ea.

¹⁵⁶⁴ See Balbir 1993: 18 showing that the translation of TP is false. Cf. 61,38 *bhū-lakṣaṇa* ‘indication of treasure in the earth’ (TP V 71).

¹⁵⁶⁵ Brockington 1981.

¹⁵⁶⁶ Leads to rebirth as deity in heaven (63,77; TP V 125). See e.g. Wadley 1983.

uttarâyaṇa ‘winter solstice’ 104,152 (TP VIII 12 with note and 19f.; Underhill 1921: 30f.)

v / n, misprint of *v* for *n* (*vidārya* for *nivārya*) 17,128 (TP II 44 note 2)

Vāc as the lamp illuminating countless objects 1,3 (TP I 1);

vaco-vajra, see: speech

vaddhā to be read for *baddhvā* 77,33 (TP VI 185);

vadhâhata (not MW) ‘near dead, half-dead’ king calls to mind magic science 107,105 (TP VIII 50; ORC 1125: “*frappé à mort*”; M II 497: “*dem Tode nahe*”)

vadhya-bhū (not MW) ‘place of execution’, thief led to ~ with drum beaten 112,166 (TP VIII 119); see also: *diṇḍima*; execution, place of

vādi-muṇḍa-mudgarikā (‘hammer for disputing *bhikṣus*’) 72,97 (TP VI 76 ‘hammer of shavelings’; ORC 833: “*véritable marteau pour les têtes rasées des débatteurs*”; similarly M II 84);

vādya ‘musical instrument’, of four kinds¹⁵⁶⁷ (*catur-vidha*) 123,132 (TP IX 52)

vāhana ‘mount of deities’, see: peacock; vehicle

vāhani-bhūya ‘become a mount’, said of birds who carry Gandharva princess 117,21 (TP VIII 165)

*vahni-kunḍa*¹⁵⁶⁸ ‘fire-cavity’, entering ~ to obtain *mohini* power 46,121f. (TP IV 57)

vahni-pradakṣiṇa (not MW) ‘circumambulation of the fire at wedding’ 14,30 (TP I 184)¹⁵⁶⁹; – see also: *agni-pradakṣiṇa*; fire

Vaidūryakānti sword from the war of the gods and Asuras 70,61 (TP VI 28);

Vaiśākha, unidentified city with Kāma temple 67,16 (TP V 197)

Vaiśravaṇa-Kubera wants crystal lotus in lake Mānasa and starts worshipping Hara-Śiva 72,39 (TP VI 71 “Viṣṇu” for Hara)

Vaiśya knowing language of animals 52,102 (TP IV 145); 83,26 (TP VII 3)

-*vajra*, see: *lilā-vajra*; *vaco-vajra*

vajra-vyūha, see: battle-arrangement

vāk-puṣpa ‘flowery speech’ 109,98 (TP VIII 98);

vakrōkti ‘hint, indirect expression, allusion’ 55,130 (TP IV 211)

Valabhī city of learning 32,43 (TP III 93)

Vālakhilya, see: Bāla-

valgulikā (‘box’ [MW]) of a female ascetic for a painting 101,74 (TP VII 139 ‘bag’; ORC 1043: “*coffret*”; M I 383: “*Kasten*”);

valita-kandhara, see: turning neck

valkala, see: garment

¹⁵⁶⁷ “Regular musical instruments are of four kinds, such as stringed (*tata*), covered (*avanaddha*), solid (*ghana*) and hollow (*suṣira*) [Ghosh 1961: 1 < Nāṭyaśāstra 28,1 *tataṃ cāivāvanaddhaṃ ca ghaṇaṃ suṣiram eva ca / catur-vidhaṃ tu vijñeyam ātodyaṃ lakṣaṇānvitam //*].” Also Rāyapaseṇiya § 192.

¹⁵⁶⁸ See Karashima 2012: 135 sub § 18.4: note 2.

¹⁵⁶⁹ Bachelard 1949, ch. IV.

vallakī ‘kind of lute, often mentioned together with the *vīṇā*’ [MW] 49,33f.¹⁵⁷⁰ (TP IV 87); 86,78 (TP VII 18)

valour, men of distinguished ~ (*sattva-śālin*) 18,311 (TP II 73); ~ of hero 18,389 (TP II 79); ~ of king 59,31 (TP V 28); fire of ~ (*pratāpānala*) 19,104 (TP II 93) and (*ugra-pratāpa*) 101,43 (TP VII 137); wisdom is in every exigency the best, not ~ (*pauruṣa*) 33,132 (TP III 118); intellect always obtains supremacy, triumphing over ~ 33,158 (TP III 120); tree of ~ (*sattva-taru*) 35,69 (TP III 160) and (*pauruṣa-pādapa*) **96,44** (TP VII 111); black smoke of king’s ~ increased by sighs of widows of enemies 59,31 (TP V 28); even with animals prudence produces success, not ~ (*parākrama*) 60,10 (TP V 41); brahmin beauty wants only husband with ~ (*śura*), knowledge or magic power 79,9 (TP VI 200f.); king as binding-post of elephant of ~ (*śaurya-kariṇ*) 94,6 (TP VII 87)

Vāmadeva, old hermit and depository of imperial jewels 109,11 (TP VIII 70)

vampire: wife as witch sucks sleeping husband’s entrails, coprophagous wife 32,156f. (TP III 102)¹⁵⁷¹; – see also: *vetāla*

vana-devatā, see: forest deity¹⁵⁷²

vana-śrī ‘dryad’ 120,117 (TP IX 10); – see dryad; forest deity; *karṇī-ratha*

vaṇiṇ-nivaha-nāyaka (‘dean of a guild, sheth’) 88,5 (TP VII 35)

vanyac-chagalaka ‘wild goat’, drug made of flesh of ~ as means to fructify queens of sonless king 39,7 (TP III 218)

varaṇa-mālā ‘garland of election’ at a *svayaṃvara* 56,277 (TP IV 239)

Vārāṇasī as town of Śiva (*Purāri-vasatī*) resembles Mt Kailās plateau 75,59 and Ganges appears as necklace on its neck 75,60 (TP VI 168); ~ *Hara-nivāsa-bhū* 87,3 (TP VII 29); ~ bestows emancipation 114,18 (TP VIII 133);

varāṅga ‘vulva’, Indra’s body covered with ~s due to Gautama’s curse 17,147 (TP II 46)¹⁵⁷³

Vararuci sent dream by Durgā 2,3 (TP I 9); ~ makes famous grammar 2,70 (TP I 16); becomes minister 4,117 (TP I 40)

vāra-vilāsini ‘*devadāsī*’¹⁵⁷⁴ 12,78 (TP I 138)

Vardhamāna, a city¹⁵⁷⁵ (now: Burdwan ca 60 miles north-west of Calcutta ?) 24,19 (TP II 171); idem north of Vindhya hills 25,5 (TP II 188); ~ ruled by Vīrabhuja 39,3 (TP III 218);

varṇa, see: class

varṇa-vartī ‘tablet for painting and colour-pencils’, princess brings over ~ by magic 117,24 (TP VIII 165; ORC 1219: “*une tablette à peindre et des pâtes de couleurs*”); similarly M II

¹⁵⁷⁰ See Zin 2004: 341f. who takes it to be a leather covered string instrument of lutelike shape and held on the lap.

¹⁵⁷¹ STh *E 251.

¹⁵⁷² See also Chojnacki 2008: (I) 350 s.v. *divinité*.

¹⁵⁷³ Cf. O’Flaherty 1980: 310.

¹⁵⁷⁴ See: en.wikipedia.org/wiki/devadasi with literature. Dallpiccola 2002: 57f.

¹⁵⁷⁵ See Hampana 2010: 154f. quoting Hiralal Jain who identifies V. with Badaṇāvara in Madhya Pradesh which seems more plausible than Bengal.

621; MW: ‘pencil’)
varṇi-veṣa (not MW) ‘disguised as a member of a caste’ 24,91 (TP II 176); – see also:
 ascetic
 Varṣa, stupid brahmin 2,54 (TP I 13); asked about fee for new grammar 4,93 (TP I 36);
vāri-koṣa,¹⁵⁷⁶ see: water of ordeal
 Varuṇa Pāthaspati sports in the sea 108,146 (TP VIII 64)
vāruṇāstra ‘Varuṇa-weapon’ produces nooses 118,90 (TP VIII 184)
vāsaka ‘bed-room’, newly-weds enter ~ 45,317 (TP IV 38)
vasanta-mahôtsava, *vasanta-samayôtsava* see: festival of spring
vāsava-diś ‘the eastern quarter’, moon rising like ear-ornament on the darkness of ~ 72,27 (TP VI 70)
vasâsava (not MW) ‘fatty fluid’, Daitya maiden offers ~ to king which he refuses 73,154
 (TP VI 112);
vasna ‘skin’ (MW: Lexx.) 108,69 (TP VIII 58)¹⁵⁷⁷
 vassals bound by oath (*śapatha*) 119,37ff. (TP VIII 195)
vasti (clyster), see: rash act
vastū-karoti (not MW) ‘to give bail’ 60,225 (TP V 60)
 Vāsuki, king of snakes, curses king Gandhamālin 72,35 (TP VI 70); ~ curses man to become
 blind 74,14 (TP VI 142); *yātrôtsava* for ~ 74,208 (TP VI 155); temple (*ketana*) 209 and
 lake (*hrada*) sacred to ~ 74, 211 (TP VI 155); ~ offers daily his own subjects and has a
 thousand faces 90,107f. (TP VII 56); 90,101 (TP VII 56); 90, 107 (TP VII 56); ~ does
 not have a tongue able to describe a prince’s beauty 103,22 (TP VII 176)
vaṭa-taru ‘banyan tree’, see: fig-tree; tree
vāta-yantra-vimāna ‘chariot with pneumatic contrivance, with wings (?)’¹⁵⁷⁸ 43,38 and 44 (TP
 III 283f.)
vātena kṣubhita ‘crazy, mad’ 94.103 (TZP VII 94)¹⁵⁷⁹
vayasi madhyame, brahmins born ~ (in their father’s middle age) 104,20 (TP VIII 2); 114,84
 (TP VIII 138);
vayaśya ‘coeval’ (q. v.)
 Veda(s), stupidity is engrained in people who muddle their head with the ~s (*dhārâdhirūḍhaṃ
 jāḍyaṃ veda-jaḍe jane*) 6,62 (TP I 65); ~ Gāyatrī, etc. in bodily form (*mūrta*) 47,47 (TP
 IV 70); twelve ~ recensions 49,155 (TP IV 95); bees humming Brahmā representing the
 four ~s in *śleṣa* (*Brahmā te ... svādhyāyôdyan*) 54,32 (TP IV 186; ORC 1424 note 4 on p.
 596); parrot knows the four ~ (*catur-veda-dhara*) 59,28 (TP V 28); *brahma-rākṣasa*
 reciting the Veda (*adhyayanam paṭan*) 94,115 (TP VII 95); – see also: four ~
vedi, as marriage-altar 45,312 (TP IV 38) and 69,179 (TP VI 21); two parts of ~ 50,99 (TP

¹⁵⁷⁶ See Gonda 1968.

¹⁵⁷⁷ Read: *hṛta-vastrârâdra-vasnâ ca* ‘whose skin was wet because her garments were taken away.’

¹⁵⁷⁸ Cf. 46,124 (TP IV 57).

¹⁵⁷⁹ Jolly 1977: § 94. For references to insanity caused by wind see Meyer 1902: 241 note.

IV 114); northern half ~ 50,209 (TP IV 121); front of ~ smeared with goat's blood and sandal wood for sacrifice to Śiva 71,215 (TP VI 51); at the wedding of a Siṃhala princess her eldest brother puts mass of jewels on ~ 122,12 (TP IX 34 'marriage-altar'); 123,216 (read: *vedī* for *vedo*; TP IX 58);
 vegetarian(s) (*śākāśin*) hermit 5,135 (TP I 58); ~s not attacked by *rākṣasas*, *yakṣas* and *piśācas* 7,37 (TP I 78)
 vehicle, celestial ~ going with a wish (*divya-kāmaga-vāhana*) 118,102 (TP VIII 185)
velatio capitis, see: covering the head
 velocity of riding animals, dispute about ~ 67,7 (TP V 196);
 venison, see: *hariṇāmiṣa*; meat; *mṛgāmiṣa*; part-*bodhisattva*
veṇu-vanêśvara 'king of the bamboo wood', owns the bewildering science (*mohinī vidyā*) 46,109f. (TP IV 56)
 vermilion¹⁵⁸⁰ (*sindūra*), woman painted black and ~ in order to look like a *gaṇa* 12,169 (TP I 146); sun red as ~ 18,122 (TP II 58); ~ on ears of royal elephant 19,68 (TP II 90); ~ on forehead (*sthūla-sindūra-tilaka*) of naked queen at magical rite 20,50 (TP II 98)¹⁵⁸¹; after birth of prince lying-in chamber is made red as ~ 35,112 (TP III 164; ORC 359: "*la chambre natale que l'on eût crue rougie par du vermillon*"; MI 505: "*Kaum hatte der Knabe das Licht der Welt erblickt, tauchte er die Wochenstube durch den mit ihm entstandenen Glanz in ein herrliches Purpurrot*")¹⁵⁸²; heaven red with blood as if with ~ 44,149 (TP IV 11); city of Kauśāmbī scatters ~ with its waving red banners 54,77 (TP IV 189); ~ on Gaṇeśa's trunk 57,1 (TP V 1); ~ on cheeks of mad elephant 72,7 (TP VI 67); ~ colour of festive city decoration compared to red glow of citizen's affection 103,170 (TP VII 186); red colour (*nava-sindūra-samujjala*) of moon when making itself driving-hook of the elephant of the eastern mountain 103,204 (TP VII 189, ORC 1082: "*orange feu*")¹⁵⁸³; ~ on Gaṇeśa Vighna jit's cheeks 111,1 (TP VIII 94)
 vernacular language, see: three languages
 vessel, magic ~ (*bhājana*) fills with desired food 3,50 (TP I 22); hot ~ burns woman's back 16,41 (TP II 24); full ~ (*pūrṇa-pātra*) auspicious 23,84 (TP II 164); king puts golden lotus on silver ~ in temple of Śiva 25,228 (TP II 208) and 25,294 (TP II 212); ~ with oil to be carried around city without spilling a drop as royal instruction of merchant's son in

¹⁵⁸⁰ See TP II 22 note 3 and Bollée 2010a; Chojnacki 2008: I 365 s.v. *vermillon*; Meyer 1952: 128. – The smear of vermilion in the hair of married women originally represents the blood of defloration and the colour thus means blood-red. It is curious, therefore, to see it used as the colour of the lying-in chamber in 35,112 following the birth of a prince which illuminates it, unless the mother's blood is meant, and especially of the moon in 103,204, when it perhaps pertains to the blood of the elephant on the hook. For Crooke (1906: 319) the marking with vermilion is a survival of the original blood-covenant entered into by the pair. This does not explain why the bridegroom is not marked in the same way. Jones 1912: 470.

¹⁵⁸¹ Cf. Pal 2009: 96. The red *tilaka* is not a sign of *iṣṭa-devatā* (Hertel 1903: 31 note 2).

¹⁵⁸² No one gives an explanation of this curious phenomenon; a profusion of the mother's blood seems to be meant.

¹⁵⁸³ On the fluctuating perception of colours in India after the example of red see Müller 2008: 456 notes 65f.

the doctrine of salvation (*mokṣôpadeśa*) 27,43 and 53 (TP III 4); snake gives brahmin lady ~ of gold for alms 61,313 (TP V 95); prince gives begging brahmin ~ with sand (*sikatā-pātra*) 72,85 (TP VI 75); – see also: pitcher

vetāla ‘ghoul, corpse-animating spirit’, burning ground in Ujjayinī tenanted by ~s 12,48 (TP I 136); ~ breathing fire 18,147 (TP II 61); ~ propitiated by human sacrifice (*ṅṛ-māṃsa-bali*) 26,238 (TP II 235); king sees in dream ~ with body made of limbs of many animals¹⁵⁸⁴ who flies up with him and drops him into sea 55,135 (TP IV 211); raising ~ (*vetālôttthāpana*) disagreeable to coward (*alpa-sattva*) 73,165 (TP VI 113); ~ able to end king’s *yakṣman / ruja* 73,261 (TP VI 119); evoking (*āhvāna*) ~ on 14th of black fortnight 73,277f. (TP VI 120); ritual of evoking ~ 73,305ff. (TP VI 123); ~ swallows enchanter (*sādhaka*) and gives hero mustard seeds from his mouth 73,309-311 (TP VI 123); spell to master ~ 75,16 (TP VI 165); all wishes (*abhīṣṭam sarvam*) obtainable from ~ 75,19 (TP VI 165); ~ cries out when its corpse is dropped from tree 75,52 (TP VI 167); ~ carried in corpse on shoulder of king 75,57 et passim (TP VI 168ff.); ~ in corpse of lover bites off nose of adulterous woman 77,68 (TP VI 188); ~ laughs at the king’s inability to answer his question 98,61 (TP VII 120); **rare description** of ~ with black complexion, ears of an ass, with face of an elephant, neck like a camel, etc. **102,19** (TP VII 163)¹⁵⁸⁵, cf. 55,135 (TP IV 211) and VI 139 where it is characterised as mischievous goblin and Deccan Guardian; ~ with flaming eyes and upstanding hair ordered to kill and eat *kāpālika* 121,25 (TP IX 13); ~ enters corpse in magic circle of worship (*arcā-maṇḍala-sthita*) 121,26 (TP IX 14); gambler pushes ~ into pit to be devoured by two *brahma-rākṣasas* 121,65 (TP IX 16); – see also: demon

vetasa-vṛtti ‘pliant as canes’, said of women 44,49 (TP IV 4); – see also: women

vetasī ‘rat(t)an palm’, pitcher with jewels buried under a ~ 121,162 (TP IX 23); – see also: rat(t)an

vetra-hasta ‘with a wand in his hand’, epithet of the hereditary warder (*pratihāra*) of the emperor of the *vidyādharas* 108,2 (TP VIII 53)

vibhavāḥ (‘rank and power’) are to a blockhead like ornaments on a log of wood 6,143 (TP I 71)

vibhūti, see: splendour

vibudha ‘sage’ attending on Saṃgrāma, king of Kashmir, and ‘god’ in the comparison of Kashmir with Nandana, Indra’s paradise E 1 (TP IX 87)

vicāra-dolā (not MW) ‘swing of doubt’ 9,87 (TP I 102)

vice of drinking (*pāna*): king drinks *surā* 11,5 (TP I 122); ~ of drinking destroys people’s intellect and leads to poverty 57,48 (TP V 5); ~ of king 74,304 (TP VI 162);

vice of gambling 19,18 (TP II 86); 26,197 (TP II 231); studied brahmin becomes devoted to ~ (*dyūtāika-vyasana*) 92,14 (TP VII 72); – see also: dice

vice of hunting¹⁵⁸⁶ 9,9 (TP I 95); 11,3 and 10 (TP I 123, see also 124 note); *gaja-bandha-rasā*

¹⁵⁸⁴ Representations of this kind are found in Moghul painting (p. c. Hegewald).

¹⁵⁸⁵ There are apparently no representations of *vetālas* known (M. Zin, p. c.).

sakta- 12,6 (TP I 133 “passionately fond of elephant-catching”); *mṛgayā* 15,8 (TP II 1);
 Kaṇva enjoins king to abandon ~ 94,42 (TP VII 90)
 vice of prodigality (*tyāgâika-vyasana*) 35,36 (TP III 157); ~ of crown prince who gives away
 state elephant, etc. 113,41ff. (TP VIII 127f.); – see also: egg of Brahmā
 vices (*vyasana*), royal¹⁵⁸⁷ 11,25 (TP I 124 with note); forest boundless as ~ 12,15 (TP I 134);
strī-madya-mṛgayā 15,8 (TP II 1); 18,78 (TP II 55 addiction to queen); exclusive devotion
 to ~ condemned 27,148 (TP III 12); ~ (vicious passion for women) will increase if
 thwarted 31,67 (TP III 87); addiction to pleasure with queen 40,43 (TP III 243); king
 Vikramatūṅga not addicted to ~ 53,87 (TP IV 173); king Nala indulges in various ~ after
 Kali had entered his body 56,290ff. (TP IV 241); king’s exclusive addiction to harem
 74,303 (TP VI 162); king becomes devoted to pleasure only (*sukhâika-sakta*) and stays in
 harem 86,6f. (TP VII 13); – see also: dice; gambling; hunting
vicitra-karaṇa,¹⁵⁸⁸ (princess skilled in dance) of / with various movements 57,81 (TP V 7)
vīci-vellad-bhuja-latā, see: Narmadā; wave
 Victorian hypocrisy of TP, see: betel (55,40 [TP VI 205]); *gaja-kumbha*; *hema-kalaśa*;
 menstruating woman; *rajasvalā*; *rata-lālasā*; sex (103,208-11 omitted in TP VII 189)
 victory (*jaya* !) exclaimed by hero in praise of Durgā 78,90 (TP VI 196); ~ shout to king by
 messenger 120,72 (TP IX 6); – pillar of ~ see: *jaya-stambha*; *kīrti-stambha*
 Vidarbha, famous painter from ~ 55,36 (TP IV 205: ‘Ujjayinī’)
vidhi, see: destiny; Disposer
vidhvamsinī (*vidyā*), science of destroying, one of the seven imperial jewels of the *vidyādharas*
 109,22 (TP VIII 71)
vidhvastatā (‘ruin’) as wife of gambling victim 73,77 (TP VI 106);
 Vidiśā,¹⁵⁸⁹ city and pleasure-ground (*lilôdyāna-bhū*) of Śrī 71,72 (TP VI 41);
vidruma-sad-daṇḍa (not MW) “bright coral tube”, viz the orb of the sun 70,117 (TP VI 32)
 Vidūṣaka, name of virtuous brahmin 18,109 (TP II 58); for his story cf. that of Trivikramasena
vidvat-sabhā, see: assembly
vidyā (‘magic science’) of *vidyādharas*, chariot made by ~ 35,117 (TP III 164); 35,121 (TP
 III 165); ~ of flying up and descending 37,201 (TP III 197); ~ incarnated as the girl Māyā
 vatī 42,38 (TP III 261); becoming mortal through loss (*bhramśa*) of ~ 52,176 (TP IV 150);
 ~ which produces whatever one desires (*iṣṭa-sampādini*) appears when called to mind by
 Pāśupata ascetic 92,35 (TP VII 73); *vidyādhari* queen recovers lost ~ in *tapo-vana* 107,52
 (TP VIII 46); all ~s are destroyed by crossing Mt Kailāsa 109,45 (TP VIII 73); king put in
 power of ~ (*vidyā-haste*) 120,4 (TP IX 1); – see also: *mohinī*; *prajñapti*; science; spell

¹⁵⁸⁶ Cf. ORC 1553 s.v. Chasse, and 1666. The killing of animals for pleasure was already forbidden by Aśoka in his fifth pillar edict (see new translation by Chl. Werba in Kratochvil 2012: 171f.)

¹⁵⁸⁷ Cf. Manu VII 47f.

¹⁵⁸⁸ According to Sundaram 1979: 757 *karaṇa* is a technical term for the 108 combinations of bodily movement and disposition of hands and legs.

¹⁵⁸⁹ Cf. Bāṇa, *Kād.* 11,6ff.

*vidyādhara(s)*¹⁵⁹⁰ as thieves 8,3 (TP I 89); ~ cannot invade the land of the Siddhas 18,234 (TP II 67)¹⁵⁹¹; ~ Jīmūtavāhana remembers pre-births 22,53 (TP II 141); merchant flings himself from hill-side and is reborn as ~ 22,165f. (TP II 149); Naravāhanadatta, though mortal, will be *cakravartin* of ~s 24,5 (TP II 170) and 44,11 (TP IV 1); ~ rank how obtained? 24,14 (TP II 171); insignia of rank (*pada*) of ~ (*vidyā-khaḍga-mālā*, etc.) by propitiating Śaṅkara (Śiva) 24,17 (TP II 171); Prajñaptikauśika as guru of the ~s descends from heaven 25,258 (TP II 210); due to curse ~s are reborn as *rākṣasas* 25,259 (TP II 210); two ~s fall in love with hermits' daughters 25,283 (TP II 211); ~ king with four daughters 26,54 (TP II 221); ~ king goes to the forest in his grief for three cursed daughters 26,61 (TP II 221); most excellent ~s assemble on Mt Rṣabha on 14th day of lunar fortnight to worship Hara Śiva 26,65f. (TP II 222); ascetic wants to become ~ 26,202 (TP II 233); ascetic wants and gets human sacrifice of embryo to get the rank of ~ 26,230ff. (TP II 234); brahmin becomes king of ~s 26,281 (TP II 238); *apsaras* seduces ~, which angers Śakra 27,61 and 64 (TP III 5f.); ~ power of changing form is suspended during sleep 33,177f. (TP III 122); ~ explains that he must go off when mortal child has been born 34,34 (TP III 130); yellow bodies of ~s 35,20 (TP III 156); ~ king descends in king Vatsa's durbar 44,6 (TP IV 1); ~s grow hostile to their future lord 34,225 (TP III 145); Puṣkarāvati is city of ~ 37,146 (TP III 193); one ~ dark as blue water-lily (*kuvalaya-śyāma*), from Mercury 48,69 (TP IV 79); one ~ very dark with tawny hair (*kṛṣṇa-kṛṣṇaḥ kapila-mūrdha-jah*), from Saturn¹⁵⁹² 48,71 (TP IV 79); black ~ 48,82 (TP IV 79); magic collyrium (*siddhāñjana*) applied against invisible ~ 48,86 (TP IV 80); water produced in ~ king's hollow hand and sprinkled on ground of courtyard creates wedding altar 51,220 (TP IV 137); ~s perceive by *vidyā-prabhāva* ('divine knowledge') 55,212 (TP IV 217); ~ carries man home at end of his curse 56,166f. (TP IV 231); ~ king cursed to be a serpent 61,319 (TP V 96); ~ king curses disobedient son to be reborn as a brahmin 65,60 and then as a foolish lion 65 (TP V 159); ~ king gets five daughters and, by Hara-Śiva's favour, one son 65,73 (TP V 160); ~ prince seizes his sister's *piñjaraka* (musical instrument) and is cursed to become bird with golden crest 65,78 (TP V 160); at the end of its curse a golden-crested bird becomes a ~ prince 65,107 (TP V 163); prince is *avatāra* of ~ 66,171 (TP V 191); are shooting stars the army of the ~s? 66,189 (TP V 192); lovesick prince compared to ~ without *vidyā* 75,77 (TP VI 169), cf. 104,106 (TP VIII 9); Śrī turns brahmin couple into ~s with charm that materializes as magic sword 68,66f. (TP VI 6); ~ abandons daughter 86,107 (TP VII 20); ~ abducts sleeping brahmin woman 87,9 (TP VII 29); man who lost his love out of sight has a void in his heart like a ~ who lost his magic power (*vibhraṣṭa-vidya*) 104,106 (TP

¹⁵⁹⁰ On v. see, e.g. Zin 2003b: 163ff.; 2002: 143 note 2; Grafe 2001; Hardy 1990: 132 note 2; ORC 1667; Sternbach 1980: 44 note 3.

¹⁵⁹¹ Zin 2003b: 165 note 15.

¹⁵⁹² On Saturn see von Negelein 1928: 245.

VIII 9); ~ king becomes yellow by adoring Agni (*Agny-ārādhana-piṅgala*) 106,73 (TP VIII 33); court of the ~ (*dharmārthā sabhā*) 106,157 (TP VIII 40); ~s are a deceitful race (*māyī vidyādhara-jano*) 107,37 (TP VIII 45); queen merits respect from ~ 107,64 (TP VIII 47); two divisions of ~ territory:¹⁵⁹³ north and south of Mt Kailāsa 107,65 (TP VIII 47); ~ army dense as a cloud at the end of a *kalpa* 107,95 (TP VIII 49); five ~ maidens agree to marry the same king 108,181 (TP VIII 67); Jīmūtavāhana *cakravartin* of ~s 113,7 (TP VIII 124); – see also:

comedium; court; *vidyādhari*

vidyādhara-guru 25,258, see: Kauśika

vidyādhari cursed to become female elephant 13,35 (TP I 152); ~ offers herself (*kuru pāṇi-grahaṃ mama*) to mortal hero 18,219 (TP II 66) and 26,67 (TP II 222)¹⁵⁹⁴; ~ roaming about at will (*kāma-caratvād*) 18,216 (TP II 66); magic science of ~ 18,227 (TP II 67); ~ cannot go to land of Siddhas (*siddha-kṣetra*) 18,234 (TP II 67); ~ princess curious about brahmin 26,50 (TP II 221); ~ on mount of rising sun 18,358 (TP II 76); hermit curses three ~ princesses to become mortals 26,58 (TP II 221); ~ reborn as *yakṣi* due to curse 26,227 (TP II 234); the bodies of four ~ princesses remain in their cities when by a curse they are reborn mortals 26,267 (TP II 237); body of ~ is like nectar to the eyes (*netra-pīyūṣaṃ*) 35,138 (TP III 166); ~ enters Gaurī pillar 37,11 and rubs man's back 37,15 (TP III 183f.); ~ with mortal husband 37,205 marries also a *vidyādhara* 211 (TP III 197f.); ~ cursed to become mortal queen 42,207 (TP III 274); ~s descending from heaven; **description** 59,2ff. (TP V 26); ~ as a potent medicine to revive Kāma 59,6 (TP V 26); ~ is born after five brothers as boon from Gaurī 59,12 (TP V 26); Pārvatī tells ~ in dream that the curse of her beloved will end and he will become a *vidyādhara* again by the touch of the hand of a female ascetic 65,237 (TP V 173); ~ becomes beautiful mortal due to curse and is fond of swinging 66,138 (TP V 188); ~ chooses husband by *gāndharva* marriage and is therefore cursed by her father to separation 69,90 (TP VI 15); king marries ~ by *gāndharva* form 86,113 (TP VII 21); ~ married to king of Aṅga cannot return to heaven 86,160 (TP VII 24); pretty only daughter is fallen ~ 93,8 (TP VII 78); ~ gives *yakṣas* liquor, meat, etc. (*madya-piśitādi*) 105,57 (TP VIII 25); ~ must leave husband temporarily to appease her sciences 105,91 (TP VIII 27); ~ shows face at king's window at night 106,61 (TP VIII 32); by magic ~ gives king her own shape and disappears 106,121 (TP VIII 37); ~s assemble by sound of drum (*bherī-mahā-śabda*) 106,163 (TP VIII 40); ~ with white body and garment (*sitātma-vastra*) 107,39 (TP VIII 46); ~ queen with rosary and skin of black antelope like an incarnation of Bhagavatī-Durgā or Sāvitrī 107,63f. (TP VIII 47); with the gleams of their eyes ~ maidens seem to clothe their emperor in the skin of a black antelope 107,83 (TP VIII 48); ascetic lives with ~ 108,73 (TP VIII 59); emperor bestows sciences on his wives and so makes them ~s 108,122 (TP

¹⁵⁹³ Cf. 110,12.

¹⁵⁹⁴ Cf. Baldissera 2004: 81.

VIII 63); – see also: curiosity
vidyā-hasta (not MW) ‘protection of a science’, person put in ~ 105,89 (TP VIII 27)
vidyānudhyāna (not MW) ‘looking into ... with the help of (supernatural) knowledge’ 90,157 (TP VII 60), see: meditation
vidyā-svayaṃvara-vṛta ‘chosen bridegroom of science’ 34,173 (TP III 140)
Vighnajit-druma ‘tree of Gaṇeśa’ 102,2 (TP VII 162)¹⁵⁹⁵
Vighnajit, Vighnêśvara, see: Gaṇeśa
vihāra, see: *ambo-vihāra*; Buddhist temple; monastery
vijanaṃ ‘private(ly)’ 74,87 (TP VI 146); 75,35 (TP VI 166);
vijane ‘private(ly)’ 24,218 (TP II 178); 29,8 (TP III 39); 49,212 (TP IV 99); 52,270 (TP IV 156); 57,155 (TP V 12); – see also: *rahas(i)*
Vijaya in Kāśmīr sacred to Śiva 66,5 (TP V 178)¹⁵⁹⁶;
vijñāna, see: magic power; science
vijñāna-bala ‘power of discernment’, see: *bharṭṛ-bhakti*
vijñānin ‘possessing magic power’, brahmin beauty wants only husband who is a hero, learned, or ~ 79,9 (TP VI 200), cf. *vijñāna* 14 (TP VI 201)
vijñapti ‘request’ to king 66,114 (TP V 187)
vikarman ‘unlawful art’ see: reanimation
Vikrama story, cf. Vidūṣaka
vikṛti ‘apparition’ 25,150 (TP II 202 note 2)
villager, robber assumes appearance of drunken ~ (*matta-grāmīṇa*) 64,72 (TP V 145)
village(s), Śavara ~ 10,138 (TP I 115); ~ oppressed by brahmin owners like malignant planets 18,130 (TP II 59); ~ of robbers 22,68 (TP II 141) and 114,110 (TP VIII 140)); – see also: *Bhilla-palli*; grant; hundred villages; *palli*; Rājput; reward; thousand ~s
vilva fruits of gold will come out of a brahmin’s fire-cavity (*kuṇḍataḥ*) when Agni-Ānala is pleased 35,61 (TP III 159)
Vimalapura,¹⁵⁹⁷ city of Mandaradeva 110,2 (TP VIII 82);
vimāna, see: *Bhūtāsana*; (lotus-)chariot;
vimānādhideva, see: chariot
vimanas, see: depression
vimāna-sādhana (not MW) ‘the art of providing oneself with magic chariots’ 44,36 (TP IV 3)
viṇā, see: lute; lyre
vinaya, see: courtesy
Vināyaka (Gaṇeśa) 20,55 (TP II 99); prince worships ~ before departure 70,17 (TP VI 25); ~ appears as man with pendulous paunch (*lambôdara-rūpin*)¹⁵⁹⁸ 70,125 (TP VI 33); 73,116 (TP VI 109); Naravāhanadatta propitiates ~ with austerities 107,124 (TP VIII 51)

¹⁵⁹⁵ Cf. 100,37 (TP VII 131) and 102,92 (TP VII 169) where an unspecified tree with fruits is mentioned.

¹⁵⁹⁶ See Gonda 1968: 234.

¹⁵⁹⁷ A city of this name is mentioned in Sheth & Balbir 2010: 29 and 77.

¹⁵⁹⁸ E. g. Dallapiccola 2002: 80.

vinayôjjvala (not MW) 56,5 (TP IV 220 ‘distinguished for modesty’); see Sarasvatī Vindhya, Vararuci visits shrine of Devī-Durgā in ~ mountains¹⁵⁹⁹ 2,2 (TP I 9); mechanical elephant (*yantra-hastin*) with concealed warriors placed in ~ forest 12,4 (TP I 133); countries between ~ and Himālaya mountains are considered most excellent 18,61 (TP II 54); lions in impassible forest of the ~ hills 18,96 (TP II 56)¹⁶⁰⁰; its peaks compared to elephants 12,8 (TP I 133) and 19,93 (TP II 92); forest of ~ range 25,6 (TP II 188); subterranean palace in ~ built by Maya 29,14 (TP III 40); two princes err in ~ forest 42,97 (TP III 265); distracted by love king enters ~ forest 55,199 (TP IV 216); residence of *rākṣasa* in ~ 79,35 (TP VI 202); king loses kingdom and flees at night to ~ forest 98,10 (TP VII 116); ~ mountain lofty as soul of prince Mrgāṅkadatta 102,41 (TP VII 165); with firm and black body Mātaṅga king is like second ~ range 102,71 (TP VII 167) and 102,103 (TP VII 170); Durgā resident in ~ 102,72 (TP VII 167); – see also: Ambikā; Bhils; Durgā; Pulinda; Śabara

Vindhya-vāsini, see: Durgā

violation¹⁶⁰¹ (*haṭhōpabhoga*) of women causes death by curse 30,9 (TP III 64) and 105,71 (TP VIII 26); princess says she will commit suicide when raped 34,9 (TP III 128); merchant wife suffers heartbreak after ~ by king 34,19 (TP III 129); woman spurned complains that she was raped 63,34 (TP V 122); – see also: rape; suicide

violator, of another’s wife (*-dāra-dhvaṃsa-kārin*) 113,10 (TP VIII 124); – of the harem, see: *śuddhānta-vidhvaṃsin*

violence against maiden causes father’s curse 52,249 (TP IV 155); maiden betrothed to another fears ~ (*balāt-kāra-bhayākulā*) by lover 84,22 (TP VII 6); *vidyādhara* applies ~ against abducted princess (*abhyaicchad bhāyayan krūra-karmabhiḥ*) 106,126 (TP VIII 37); – see also: daughter; disobedience

vipañcī ‘the Indian lute’¹⁶⁰² 49,20 (TP IV 86)

vipaṇi, see: market

viparītāṅghri ‘with feet turned the wrong way’¹⁶⁰³ said of *yakṣas* 73,245 (VP VI 118); *viparīta-vidhi* ‘operator of wrong decisions’ (reading of D) ~ *e vidhe* ! 71,252 (TP VI 54 [with note] reading *viparīta-nidhe vidhe* “Destiny, source of untoward events”; ORC 824: “*destinée aux injonctions contraires à mes voeux*” apparently following D; M II 71: “*du widerwilliges und grausames Schicksal*”)

vīra-caryā ‘adventures’, prince sets out at night in search of ~ 71,23 (TP VI 37); – see also: night

viraha-kleśa (not MW) ‘sorrow of separation’ 51,70 (TP IV 127)

¹⁵⁹⁹ Near Mirzāpur (TP I 9 note 1). – Cf. ORC 1670f.

¹⁶⁰⁰ For a description see Kuv note 337.

¹⁶⁰¹ Meyer 1952 index s.v. rape.

¹⁶⁰² See Pesch 2009: 164 with modern picture; Zin 2004: 328ff., especially 331.

¹⁶⁰³ Bollée 2008: 101 note 451. Demons and pregnant women have feet urned backward (*paścāt prapadāni*, AV VIII 6,15.

viraha-jvāla (not MW) ‘burning separation’ 122,70 (TP IX 38)
viraha-doṣā (not MW) ‘night of separation’ 108,121 (TP VIII 63);
viraha-mālīnya, see: separation
vīra-vetāla (not MW) ‘heroic *vetāla*’, ~-*sādhana* 55,208 (TP IV 216 “making a goblin my servant”; similarly M I 870; ORC 620: “*soumettant un chef des vetāla*”);
virginity, vow of *brahmacāriṇī* 29,15 (TP III 40); ~ (*kanyakā-bhāva*) of princess lost beguiled by *vidyādhara* 33,209 (TP III 124)
vīrya (‘sperma’), *vidyādhari*, transformed into female bee (*bhṛṅgī*), bedewes jambu flower with ~ of joy (TP: “tear of joy”; M II 31: “*Freudenträne*”) (*harṣa-cyutena vīryeṇa*; due to seeing her husband) 69,97 (TP VI 15)¹⁶⁰⁴
viṣa-cchaṭā ‘lump of poison,’ see: bawd
viṣa-lālā (not MW) ‘poisonous saliva’ of a snake, see: kite
viṣa-mantriṇ, see: snake charmer
viṣa-vedanā ‘poison-agony’ (not MW), courtesan considers life a ~ 38,111 (TP III 214); ~ of a brahmin after eating rice poisoned by saliva of snake 87,46 (TP VII 32); – see: kite
viṣa-vidyā ‘knowledge of antidotes’, minister saves snake-bitten brahmin from suicide due to his ~ 75,14 (TP VI 165)
viṣa-sūcikā ‘poisoned needle’, speech like a ~ to the ear 1,37 (TP I 5)
viṣayogārṇava ‘ocean of separation’ 71,255 (TP VI 54)
visibility of deity:¹⁶⁰⁵ *sākṣāt sāvī devī Caṇḍī tam abhyadhāt* 11,37 (TP I 125); *Devī pratyakṣya tām yayau* 26,251 (TP II 236); Sītā is taken by the earth goddess personally (*āvīr-bhūtayā Bhuvā*) in her lap and brought to the other side of a lake 51,82 (TP IV 127); Śiva appears in terrible form 106,127 (TP VIII 37); ~ of Agni (q.v.); – see also: *agnya-agāra*; attributes; *Caṇḍī*; *sākṣād*
visibility, corporeal ~ of science 107,111 (TP VIII 50); – see also: *prajñāpti*; *vidyā*
Viṣṇu¹⁶⁰⁶ in dream predicts wealth 12,128 (TP I 143); Lohajaṅgha riding just as ~ on Garuḍa 12,147 (TP I 144); offering of white flowers to ~ 24,97 (TP II 176); ~ propitiated by king of Ratnakūṭa 36,11 (TP III 169); ~ appears in bodily form (*sākṣād ādideśa*) to penitent 36,12 (TP III 169); two *Gandharvas* sing for Bhagavan (Viṣṇu) 36,115 (TP III 177); ~ with threatening sound (*huṃ-kāra*) stops killing enemy and saves votary 44,152 (TP IV 11); Viṣṇu’s foot is the earth, heaven his head, the cardinal points his ears, sun and moon his eyes, his stomach is the egg of Brahmā 54,33 (TP IV 186); ~ is without form and support 54,37 (TP IV 187); ~ orders Nārada to bring *apsaras* back from Indra 54,40 (TP IV 187);

¹⁶⁰⁴ ORC 796: “*de la sécrétion née de sa joie elle arrosa ... cette fleur*” explaining this on p. 1459 by “*de genre masculin en sanskrit, l’abeille est donc conçue comme un être mâle*”. In vs 96, however, it says *bhṛṅgī-vapur vidhāya* which form she only leaves after having see her spouse in vs. 97f. *Vīrya* cannot mean ‘sperm of women’, as the French translation of Mme Besnard seems to suggest, the secretion in the vagina before copulation, that is, because this has no influence on the foetus (Jolly 1977: 61) and because *puspa* is neutre. The picture is slightly false.

¹⁶⁰⁵ For the matter of the body of the deities see Oberlies 2006.

¹⁶⁰⁶ See also ORC 1672f.

~ as boar 54,220 (TP IV 199); ~ dries up the sea with fire 60,194 (TP V 57); king believes queen's lies that she is visited every night by ~ as a trick (*māyām āśaṅkya vaiṣṇavīm*) 66,50 (TP V 182); ~ in a dream tells man the cause of fever and healing by the (right) hand of princess devotee of ~ 71,121 (TP VI 44); devotion to ~ in order to regain lover 71,201 (TP VI 50); word of Viṣṇu (*vaco Vaiṣṇavam*) made known to men (in dream) will not have been spoken in vain 71,235 (TP VI 53); Kuvera worships ~ to get a crystal lotus in the Mānasa lake 72,39 (TP VI 71); after worshipping ~ dream is had of Daitya-*kanyā* approaching 73,88 (TP VI 107); Brahmā, ~ and Śiva as mountain peaks in Kāśmīra 73,96 (TP VI 108); boon from ~ (*Vaiṣṇavo ... prasādaḥ*): gender-changing pill 89,95 (TP VII 47); ~ as Nṛ-siṃha 103,4 (TP VII 175); ~ sends aid seeking deities to Śiva 115,108 (TP VIII 151f.); – see also: Hari; Śauri

viṣḍḍha-vahni (?; not MW) for *viṣa + ūḍha + vahni*, cf. *viṣāgni*, *viṣānala* ‘after resisting burning poison’ 46,121 (TP IV 56 reading *soḍhāhidanśasya*: “when he had endured the bite of the snakes”); similarly ORC 497 and M I 691)

visphoṭa ‘blister’, rays of moon cause ~ on body of delicate queen 85,18 (TP VII 11)

visual clusters, see: gestures

vivāda, see: dispute

vivāhōtsava, see: marriage feast

voice (*Sarasvatī*)¹⁶⁰⁷ from heaven stating that a boy just born will be able to remember all he has heard once 2,68 (TP I 16); ~ explains birth of son 6,20 (TP I 61); idem 9,70 (TP I 100); announces end of curse 9,88f. (TP I 102); ~ stops suicide and predicts future 10,57 (TP I 110); ~ predicts future 10,214 (TP I 121); idem (Durgā) 11,14 (TP I 123); heavenly ~ tells king that his Daitya wife will bear an incarnation of Kāma as son who will become king of the *vidyādhara*s 11,78 (TP I 128; cf. 23,73 below); ~ announcing Mārī Sitalā to fall from pillar upon people 12,178 (TP I 147); ~ explaining acts 13,35 (TP I 152) and 18,180 (TP II 63); ~ commands brahmin to give half of his life to beloved bitten by snake 14,80 (TP I 188); divine ~ predicts future 15,27 (TP II 3); heavenly ~ confirms wife's fidelity 16,119 (TP II 30); ~ of Durgā asking for human sacrifice 18,163 (TP II 62); ~ of *vidyādhari* commanding hero to return to Durgā temple 18,177 (TP II 63f., cf. 66); ~ of Agni predicting hero's future 18,312 (TP II 73); ~ of *yakṣa* in fig tree 20,32 (TP II 97); heavenly ~ of Durgā stopping suicide 22,67 (TP II 142); ~ declares that ministers will crush the enemies of the future *cakravartin* 23,58f. (TP II 161); ~ stating that prince born is incarnation (*avatāra*) of Kāma and will become king of *vidyādhara*s 23,73 (TP II 163); ~ stops son from killing father 25,108 (TP II 199); ~ (*gir*) of impaled man begging for water 25,129ff. (TP II 201); ~ instructs queen in dream to give daughter to pre-birth husband 25,167 (TP II 204); ~ enjoins brahmin to perform Caesarean and remove embryo (*garbham vipātaya*!) 26,257 (TP II 236); confirmation (*evam asti*) from ~ 28,91 (TP III 27); four ~s pronouncing curse 28,124ff. (TP III 30); ~ predicting future 30,55 (TP III 67); ~ of Śiva making king of Vatsa speak (*iśvara-codita*) 34,51 (TP III 132); king hears ~ from heaven

¹⁶⁰⁷ Cf. Chojnacki 2008: (I) 366 s.v. *voir*; STh F 966.

34,57 (TP III 132); ~ commanding ministers to accomplish all things prosperously for prince 34,118 (TP III 137); ~ of Śiva explaining future 34,242 (TP III 146); ~ of visible Jātavedas-Agni 35,70 (TP III 160); ~ of Gaurī predicting the future husband of the newly born daughter 35,118 (TP III 165); bodiless heavenly ~ announces that fallen elephant would rise only if touched by faithful woman 36,29 (TP III 171); ~ of Kubera appearing and offering boon 38,68f. (TP III 211); ~ (of Śiva) speaking through king 34,56 (TP III 132); ~ ordering to propitiate Devī-Durgā 42,168ff. (TP III 271); princess with sweet ~ (*mañju-bhāṣiṇī*) 44,48 (TP IV 4); ~ warning to protect queens carried off by *vidyādhara*s 45,70ff. (TP IV 22); ~ forbids kings to commit suicide through grief at their wives' abduction 46,6 (TP IV 49); ~ orders Sūryaprabha to accept magic quiver (*tūṅga-ratna*) 46,78 (TP IV 54), and bow and string 46,95 (TP IV 55); ~ orders Sūryaprabha to enter flying chariot 46,125ff. (TP IV 57); ~ confirms power of seven herbs 46,209f. (TP IV 62); ~ announces future daughter to be wife of emperor 51,21 (TP IV 123); ~ of Loka pāla confirming woman's statement 52,54 (TP IV 141); ~ stopping brahmin's suicide 52,162 (TP IV 149); ~ (of Durgā) applauding human sacrifice 53,170 (TP IV 178); ~ stops suicide and gives boon 53,177 (TP IV 180); ~ (of Śiva) explains man's innocence 54,116 (TP IV 192); ~ (of Śiva) encouraging fight 54,216 (TP IV 199); ~ deciding name of child 56,6f. (TP IV 220); ~ (of sun or Viṣṇu) announcing brahmin prisoner that he will not be put to death 56,34f. (TP IV 222); ~ ordering prisoner to place burning wheel on head of fellow prisoner 56,159 (TP IV 231); ~ explains to Nala that the geese who took his garment are dice 56,311 (TP IV 242); ~ stops planned suicide of *vidyādhari* 59,113 (TP V 34); ~ (of water spirit) invites two brahmins to be his guests 63,70 (TP V 125); saintly woman's (*bhagavatī*) refreshing ~ compared to cloudless rain (*an-abhra-vṛṣṭi*) 67,88 (TP V 202); ~ from heaven foretells destiny of daughter at birth 68,70 (TP VI 6); ~ (of Śiva) from heaven foretelling the fulfilment of desires 69,85 (TP VI 14); ~ of two *yakṣas* from heaven (*vācaṃ divaḥ*) addressing gambler 73,191 (TP VI 115); ~ (*bhārati divaḥ*) predicting famous son 74,48 (TP VI 143); ~ (of goddess Caṇḍikā) 78,72 (TP VI 195) and, stopping suicide of king, 78,101 (TP VI 197); ~ *mā kṛthāḥ sāhasaṃ* of Durgā 80,44 (TP VI 207); ~ (of Śiva) from heaven (*giraṃ divaḥ*) promises birth of son and daughter 83,9f. (TP VII 2); ~ of a nereid singing about karman and fate (*daiva*) 86,79f. (TP VII 18f.); ~ of Śarva-Śiva unnoticeable in the air (*an-ālakṣya-mūrtau Śarve nabhaḥ-sthite*) 88,52 (TP VII 38); ~ of *kalpa-vṛkṣa* from heaven 90,28 (TP VII 51); ~ of Gaurī tells suicidal Siddha princess not to act recklessly and promises her a husband 90,76 (TP VII 54); ~ from air stops Mṛgāṅkadatta from jumping into lake 100,36 (TP VII 131); ~ of Gaurī announces husband to princess 103,55 (TP VII 178); divine ~ announces husband 106,38 (TP VIII 30); cow with articulate ~ (*vyaktayā girā*) addressing man 108,34 (TP VIII 55); heavenly ~ (*divyā vāk*) announces that only emperor can bathe in lake in Himālaya 108,145 (TP VIII 64); ~ (Sarasvatī) announces birth of emperor of *vidyādhara*s 109,78 (TP VIII 76); ~ from heaven (*vāk ... divaḥ*) 109,88 (TP VIII 76); Naravāhanadatta urged by *divyayā vācā* to go to Mt. Ṛṣabha for inauguration 110,47 (TP VIII 85); ~ from heaven (*gaganād a-śarirā sarasvatī*) declares Madanamañcukā to be incarnation of Rati and Nara

vāhanadatta the same of Kāma 110,69f. (TP VIII 87); heavenly ~ informs king about his daughter 112,136 (TP VIII 116f.); two heavenly *haṃsas* speak with articulate ~ to king in dream 114,48 (TP VIII 136); ~ from the air (*ākāśād ... Sarasvatī*) tells Vāyu to carry senseless Indra out of the fight 115,69 (TP VIII 149); at birth of son ~ from heaven (*bhāratī divaḥ*) announces his name 115,132 (TP VIII 153), cf. vs 138; gardeners in the form of birds speak with articulate ~ (*su-vyakta-vacana*) 117,84 (TP VIII 170); ~ from *garbha-gr̥ha* of Śiva temple tells fallen *vidyādhara* prince that he will not suffer in the womb (*na hi te garbha-vāsa-kleśo bhaviṣyati*) and in his life as mortal 118,3 (TP VIII 178); ~ from heaven (*vāg divaḥ*) enjoining gods to go home (*sva-padāni*) 119,211 (TP VIII 208); ~ of unseen omen deity (*nigūdhā śakuna-devatā*) from the air stops execution 124,124 (TP IX 77);– see also: speech

vow¹⁶⁰⁸ (*mahā-vrata*) of Śiva (unspecified) after beheading Brahmā 2,14 (TP I 10); ~ (*pratijñā*) with undoing of hair lock 5,118 (TP I 57); brahmin with ~ of silence (*maunī*) makes heavenly garden with temple 6,74 (TP I 66); sonless king takes ~ of perpetual celibacy (*brahmacarya-vrata*) 6,90 (TP I 67); minister observes ~ of silence (*kr̥ta-mauna*) 6,159 (TP I 72); do, (*maunatva*) 7,23 (TP I 76); vow of rigid fast to propitiate Śiva 13,77 (TP I 156); ascetic breaks his ~ of silence 15,35 (TP II 4)¹⁶⁰⁹; ~ difficult as that of standing on edge of sword (*asi-dhāram iva vratam*) 17,91 (TP II 41); brahmin's ~ to see the Golden City (Kanakapurī) 25,2ff. (TP II 188); Asura woman with ~ of virginity (*brahma-cāriṇī*) in her father's house 29,15 (TP III 40); ~ to conquer enemies 38,8 (TP III 206); ~ for six months as difficult as standing on sword edge to please Kubera 49,186 (TP IV 97); king about to go to forest makes queen take ~ (*śapatha*) to stay in town and care for unmarried daughter 51,42 (TP IV 125)¹⁶¹⁰; ~ confirms wife's words 52,52 (TP IV 141); ~ (*pratijñā*) of Kali and Dvāpara to separate Nala and Damayantī 56,283 (TP IV 240f. with note); ~ (*niyama*) of fasting (*upoṣaṇa*) broken prematurely with wicked wife in the fourth watch of the night ends remembering pre-birth 63,57ff. (TP V 124); ~ of chastity causes remembering pre-birth in next life 69,164 (TP VI 20); ~ of single alms-offering (*eka-bhikṣā-vrata*) 71, 137 (TP VI 45); ~ to imitate partridge, see *cakora-vrata*; – see also: *kumuda-vrata*; oath; single alms-offering

voyage,¹⁶¹¹ hero sets out on ship which is stopped in mid-sea by sleeping giant's leg; he cuts off leg and uses it as saving plank 18,293ff. (TP II 72); brahmin joins merchant on his ship and is wrecked and swallowed by *makara* 25,40 (TP II 191); brahmin and fisher king set out for Ratnakūṭa island in mid-sea 26,7 (TP II 217); brahmin youths set out at night without knowledge of parents 32,45 (TP III 93); merchants to Suvarṇadvīpa wrecked in mid-ocean after five days; one survives on plank 36,81 (TP III 175); merchant and love start on ship, are wrecked and merchant is saved by another ship 52,327 (TP IV 161); merchant travelling

¹⁶⁰⁸ On vows in general see Kane 1974 vol.V: 1-462.

¹⁶⁰⁹ Balbir 2001: 389f.

¹⁶¹⁰ Cf. STh *M100-M 199.

¹⁶¹¹ Cf. ORC 1675 and OCD s.v. travel.

over the sea is shipwrecked but saves himself on corpse to Suvarṇadvīpa 54,100-4 (IV 191); against his parents' advice a merchant goes to Suvarṇadvīpa, is wrecked and thrown on shore where he is brought away by black man with noose 56,140-6 (TP IV 230); merchant daughter shipped to Ceylon to marry prince; ship is wrecked and no one is saved 67,53 (TP V 199); prince sets out for Ceylon, is shipwrecked and saved by holding spar 67,58 (TP V 200); ambassador prince boards ship to Ceylon to ask for princess' hand 81,33 (TP VI 211); king and merchant board ship for Suvarṇadvīpa when in mid-sea maiden emerges from sea and starts singing 86,37ff. and 76f. (TP VII 16-8); princess travels on sea to lover 101,139 (TP VII 143); wicked merchant accepts princely couple as passengers and has the ship leave with the princess before the prince could board it 101,267 (TP VII 152); messengers board ship from island 120,103 (TP IX 8); a bard crosses the sea and reaches a city in the centre of an island (*dr̥ṣṭam mayā ... mahā-puram ... uttīrya vāridhiṃ dvīpa-madhyagam*) 122,79 (TP IX 39; "sea that separates the *dvīpas*"; ORC 1284: "*elle (la cité) se trouve au milieu d'une île*"; M II 713: "*ich gelangte auf eine mitten im Ozean liegende Insel und sah die große Stadt*"); brahmins cross river Narmadā 123,170 (TP IX 55); – see also: shipwreck voyeur, king as ~ 55,118 (TP IV 210); – see also: curiosity
vraṇa-paṭṭaka 'wound plaster, bandage on a wound' 28,159 (TP III 32)
vṛddha-pathika 'old traveller' 71,261 (TP VI 55);
 Vṛṣabha-dhvaja (Śiva) while playing dice with Devī 110,55 is visited by Naravāhanadatta 110,53 (TP VIII 86);
 Vṛṣadhvaja (Śiva) in dream tells king of newborn son deposited at his gate 93,52 (TP VII 82); king stays three days in Benares worshipping Śiva ~ 93,84 (TP VII 84);
vṛṣṭair (D) misread for *vṛkṣair* 28,65 (TP II 25 note 1)
vṛtta-prāṇōdgama (not MW) 'who had resigned, at the rising of the moon, the nectar of his life' 59,109 (TP V 33)
 vulture(s),¹⁶¹² cries of ~ (*gr̥dhra*) in charnel ground 18,147 (TP II 60); in the evening brahmin sees big birds (*mahā-vihaga*)¹⁶¹³ like ~s in banyan tree 26,26f. (TP II 219); ~ carries brahmin on its back 26,36 (TP II 219); ~ (*gr̥dhra*) circling overhead are an evil omen 116,3 (TP VIII 156)
 vulva as eye, see: ascetic 17,143ff. (TP II 46); curse; Indra;
 vulva as wound see: wound (28,178 [TP III 34])
vyādhi, see: abscess
vyāja-kheda 'feigned weariness (MW), affected unhappiness' 49,97 (TP IV 91)

¹⁶¹² See Hensgen 1958: 133. Vultures are in danger of being exterminated today by eating animals, especially kine (a *go-susāna* is already mentioned in Ja II 50,26), who have been treated with Diclofenac which they do not tolerate, but measures are undertaken for their recovery (www.nytimes.com/2012/11/30/world/asia/cultivating-vultures from the New York Times and www.wired.com/wiredsciences/2011/05/indian-vulture-recovery by Brandon Keim). I thank Dr Mrs Petra Kieffer-Puelz for this information.

¹⁶¹³ These birds may be *bhāruṇḍa* birds, Gigantic Storks, for which see supra sub hair-style the note on 106,114 (TP VIII 37). For the story cf. Tawney 1895: 163f.; Hoffmann 1974: 395ff.

vyāñjana, see: curry; meat-curry

vyasana, see: vice

vyoma-gamanī vidyā ‘knowledge of travelling in the air’ 59,106 (TP V 33)

vyoman ‘ether’, one of eight special forms assumed by Śiva 35,99 (TP III 163 with note 2)

wager, see: bet

waist of a princess can be spanned with the hand, a very bow of Kāma 74,217 (TP VI 156)¹⁶¹⁴;
beauty’s ~ is like (the middle part of a) thunderbolt (*vajra-madhyā*) 84,48 (TP VII 8:
“diamond”; ORC 946: “*ta ceinture est un diamant*” [sic])¹⁶¹⁵; Gandharva princess as torrent
river of the elixir of beauty, with a ~ charming with three wavelike wrinkles 116,35 (TP
VIII 158)

waking up, with a dream at the night’s end¹⁶¹⁶ (*rajanī-kṣaye*) 35,106 (TP III 164); (*prayātā
vibhāvarī*) 69,40 (TP VI 11); do, 71,124 (TP VI 45); hero ~ princess by nudging on her
shoulder 73,345 (TP VI 125);

wall(s) of gold (*sauvarṇa-bhitti*), palace with ~ 26,44 (TP II 220); thief makes hole (*saṃdhi*)
in palace ~ and enters bed-chamber of princess 64,43 (TP V 142f.), cf. 77,58 (TP VI
187); man with discus and mace emerges from painted ~ 66,66 (TP V 183); war because
of princess 103,16 (TP VII 176)¹⁶¹⁷; worst of political measures (*upāyeṣu jaghanyo*) 103,30
(TP VII 177);

war chariot, see: ass

war-cry, see: *siṃha-nāda*

warder, female¹⁶¹⁸ 36,3 (TP III 169); 52,47 (TP IV 141); 119,14 (TP VIII 194); – see also:
doorkeeper; *prātihāra* and -ī

warder, male (*pratihāra*) sent by one king to another 13,48 (TP I 153); 14,1 (TP I 182), 21,38
(TP II 128), etc.; announces royal bathing time (*snāna-velā*) at midday 86,24 (TP VII
14)¹⁶¹⁹; brahmin ~ at palace gate, khilladar 120,14 (TP IX 2); ~ (*kṣattr*) consoles army
123,83 (TP IX 49); (*dvāra-pāla*) 124,187 (TP IX 81); suitor abused by ~ in the shape of
time (*kālenēva rūpiṇā*) 124,189 (TP IX 81 “who seemed like an incarnation of untimeli-
ness”; ORC 1317: “*qu’ on aurait pris pour le Temps incarné*”; M II 761: “*Türwächter,
welcher der leibhaftigen, über alles herrschenden und von niemand abhängigen Zeit glich*”);
~s (*dvāḥ-stha*) propitiated at every door with presents 124,192 (TP IX 81); – see also:
doorkeeper; *kṣatr*; *prātihāra*; *śuka*

warriors, concealed in mechanical elephant 12,5 (TP I 133); ~ compared to trees marked for
the axe 108,105 (TP VIII 62); – see also: head

¹⁶¹⁴ See Müller-Jung 2007 and Singh et al. 2006.

¹⁶¹⁵ The woman may have been thought of as a *śāla-bhañjikā* statue.

¹⁶¹⁶ Signal of a dream that will come true at once (Jagaddeva, *Svapnacintāmaṇi* 1,17).

¹⁶¹⁷ Cf. STh T 104.

¹⁶¹⁸ Saletore 1943: 254f.

¹⁶¹⁹ Cf. Saletore 1943: 253f.

washing, of man by woman servant 39,111 (TP III 225); Nala forgets ~ his feet (*a-kṣālitāṅghrika*) so that Kali can enter into his body 56,288f. (TP IV 241); brahmin washes hands and feet, and rinses his mouth before eating 87,42 (TP VII 32); hypocritical ascetic ~ food with water on a stone (*dṛṣad*) as sign of great holiness¹⁶²⁰ 121,158 (TP IX 23); – see also: feet;

washing the head: Bollée 2009a 83.

watch, hero reaches forest when morning ~ (at nine o'clock) has passed (*prātaḥ-prahare gate*) 10,115 (TP I 114); man falls from heaven in fourth (last) ~ (*turye yāme khād bhraṣṭa-puruṣa*) 123,200 (TP IX 57)

watchman, chants (*yāmikaḥ puruṣo jagau*): “young men obtain the fruit of their birth when they wake up the sleeping one ...” 3,64 (TP I 23); ~ banished for interruption of king’s dream 122,31 (TP IX 36)

water, Kāma’s weapon of ~ (*vāruṇāstra*) 14,29 (TP I 184); universe became ~ at end of *kalpa* 2,10 (TP I 9); king shows queen great affection by sprinkling her with ~ (*prītyābhiṣicya*) 6,167 (TP I 73: “anointing her”; ORC 44: “*le roi éleva la reine considérablement audessus des reines, en lui dispensant en personne une amicale aspersion lustrale*”; M I 63: “*überhäufte sie mit Liebe*”); if dead Daitya is not yearly satisfied with an oblation of ~, five ministers will die 11,72 (TP I 127); polluted¹⁶²¹ ~ causes elephant’s death 13,33 (TP I 152); shouts compared to ~ of the ocean overflowing out of due time 18,2 (TP II 49); ~ poisoned to stop attack 19,84 (TP II 91); Kālārātri sprinkles princess with ~ (*abhiṣicya*), gives her spells, etc. and makes her a witch 20,111 (TP II 104); wine with rosy glow (or: passion) compared to ~ of royal coronation in empire of love 21,7 (TP II 125); hermit Agryatapās, sprinkled with ~, curses three Vidyādhara princesses to become mortals 26,57 (TP II 221); *cakra-yantra* guards ~ of immortality (*amṛta*) 29,48 (TP III 42); ~ of Pañcatīrthī enabling bathers to become followers of Nārāyaṇa 33,30 (TP III 109); at anointing *yuva-rāja* first comes the ~ of his father’s tears of joy, and then the ~ of holy bathing places 34,108 (TP III 136); smell betrays ~ of lake as poisoned (*viṣākta*) 37,86 (TP III 189); rain ~ dripping from skeleton and skull (*asthi-karaṅka*) of corpse hung from banyan becomes gold lotus when fallen into *tīrtha* 40,93f. (TP III 247f.); stream of ~ (*jalāugha*) in dream means battle 46,143 (TP IV 58); coronation ~ 50,203 (TP IV 121); ~ produced in hollow of *vidyādhara*’s hand produces wedding altar 51,220 (TP IV 137); ~ of life sprinkled on corpse with spell (*abhimantritais toyaiḥ*) for reviving it 52,158 (TP IV 149)¹⁶²²; is ~ found in Fata Morgana? 57,91 (TP V 8); ~ thrown into the face for reanimation 59,54 (TP V 30); do not water the tree of existence with the ~ of controversial conceit (*hetu-vādābhimānāmbu-seka*) 66,18 (TP V 179); all discernment is washed out of kings when the ~s of inauguration are poured over them 91,55 (TP VII 70); ~ of wisdom

¹⁶²⁰ Cf. Mette 2010: 135.

¹⁶²¹ On water pollution see, e.g., Bollée 2005b: 58f.

¹⁶²² Cf. the magic water with which black stones are charmed back into heroes in the Arabian night no 756 (Littman 1953: V 193).

(*prajñāna-vāri*) must water tree of valour (*pauruṣa-pādapa*) 96,44 (TP VII 111); ~ of holy places poured on the head of royal couple at coronation 103,233 (TP VII 191); king performs asceticism in ~ during the winter 115,45 (TP VIII 147); – see also: consecration water; coronation; donation water; inauguration;

water-bubble, *saṃsāra* is frail like ~ (*vāri-budbuda-bhaṅgura*) 97,13 (TP VII 113);

water-game¹⁶²³ (*jala-kriḍā*) 55,115 (TP IV 210); ~ of Damayantī 56,241 (TP IV 237); (*jala-keli*) 67,90 (TP V 202);

water-giving festival, see: water-oblation

water-lilies, see: enemies; eyes; *vidyādharas*

water-oblation to the dead, king gives ~ (*dadau jalam*) at funeral rite of in-laws¹⁶²⁴ 111,59 (TP VIII 101); do, to dead parents 111,89 (TP VIII 103); if no yearly ~ is given to dead Asura, five of king's ministers will die 112,57 (TP VIII 110); – see further: *ambu-dānōtsava*; festival; *jala-dāna*; *udaka-dāna*; water of immortality

water of coronation, Gaurī anoints Jīmūtavāhana with her own hand emperor over the Vidyā dharas and sprinkles him with ~ from her pitcher 90,188f. (TP VII 62)

water of giving, see: donation water

water of immortality (*amṛta*), Nāgārjuna preparing ~ 41,13 (TP III 253) and burying it in the earth five days before its being finished 41,25f. (TP III 254); ~ fills pots by Nalas magic 56,395 (TP IV 248); Gaurī, visible, sprinkles Jīmūtavāhana with ~ 90,185 (TP VII 61)

water of life (*amṛta-rasa*) motif¹⁶²⁵ 29,57 (TP III 43); TP VI 98 note 1; – see also: *amṛta*; libation; water-giving festival; water of immortality

water of ordeal¹⁶²⁶ in which the image of Hāṭakēśvara has been washed (*Hāṭakēśvara-sambandhi-koṣa-vāri-*), to be drunk by vassals as surety 119,35 and 39 (TP VIII 195)

water of presents, see: donation water

water of wisdom, by ~ the tree of valour bears fruit (*prajñāna-vāriṇā ... phalati ... pauruṣa-pādapaḥ*) 96,44 (TP VII 111)

water-pot, Gaurī sprinkles Jīmūtavāhana with water from her pitcher (*kalaśāmbudhi*) 90,189 (TP VII 62); (*kamaṇḍalu*), crest-jewel very effective because sprung from Disposer's ~ 117,156 (TP VIII 175)

water-spirits,¹⁶²⁷ sacrifice to ~ in order to calm down wild sea 18,295 (TP II 72); ~ (*puruṣaḥ ... jala-vāsi*; *jala-puruṣa*) rising from lake 63,14-60 (TP V 121); ~ (*jala-mānuṣāḥ*) rise up from Narmadā river and are killed 71,5 (TP VI 36); – see also: mermaid

water vessels in front of gates symbolizing city's breasts (*pūrṇa-kumbha-kuca-dvaya*) 18,9 (TP II 50)¹⁶²⁸; – see also: pitcher

¹⁶²³ See Vātsyāy 35.

¹⁶²⁴ See also 11,72 (TP I 127) [supra under “water”], Śak III 11 (water with sesame-seed) and, e.g. Michaels 2004: 136.

¹⁶²⁵ On the religious meaning of water, not only in the cultic worship in ancient Egypt, see Kleibl 2013.

¹⁶²⁶ STh H 222ff. Saletore 1943: ???

¹⁶²⁷ See Aarne-Thompson 1932-5: 64-78 (F 420) and Thompson 1958: 182.

wave, nautch-girl (*lāsikī*) dances like a ~ of the sea of beauty 57,75 (TP V 7), cf. 104,165 (TP VIII 13); goddess Śrī is fickle as a ~ (*vārivicīva capalā*) 62,164 (TP V 113); merchant daughter like a ~ of the sea of love's insolence (*Kandarpa-darpābdhi-laharī*) 67,49 (TP V 199); Narmadā shakes her ~s like twining arms (*vici-vellad-bhuja-latā*) 71,2 (TP VI 36); ~s as hands repelling transgression (*kalmaṣa*) 73,83 (TP VI 107); ~ uplifted like hands seem to warn crossing person back 74,113 (TP VI 148);

way to *āśram* in forest found back by woman, see: track

wealth, who can hide ~ from women ? 1,51 (TP I 6); Pāṭaliputra home of ~ and learning 3,78 (TP I 24); for the wise character is ~ 5,98 (TP I 54); ~ acquired through a dead mouse 6,36ff. (TP I 63); pride of ~ 18,130 (TP II 59); ~ seized instead of capital punishment 18,387 (TP II 78)¹⁶²⁹; ~ is root of tree of realm 19,49 (TP II 88); giving ~ (*artha-da*) is said to give life, for life depends on ~ 28,9 (TP III 18); ~ like unseasonable cloud, comes and goes 33,141 (TP III 119); fortune of enjoyment better than that of ~ 54,205f. (TP IV 198); everyone is valued on account of his ~ (*dhanena pūjyate sarvaḥ*) 57,61 (TP V 5); ~ (*artha*) gives us religion and love (*dharma-kāmau*), consideration and renown 57,70 (TP V 6); ~ is youth to creatures (*artha hi yauvanaṃ puṃsām*) 61,116 (TP V 78); ~ given by *yakṣa* as boon 63,90 (TP V 126); acquiring ~ to give it away 67,39 (TP V 198); heavenly nymph fascinates man with her ~ of beauty (*lāvaṇya-sampad*) 72,342 (TP VI 94); poison-trees of ~ (*dhana-viṣa-druma*) 104,117 (TP VIII 10); – see also: beauty; confiscation
 weapon, maiden looking like ~ of Kāma, but no arrow 4,3 (TP I 30); Vibhu-Śiva's sweat (*svedāmbu*) as Kāma's water ~ 9,1 (TP I 94); nervous bride, bathed in perspiration, appears as if struck by Kāma's bow with the arrow of confusion / fascination, and the ~s of wind and water (*su-saṃmohana-vāyavya-vāruṇāstra*) 14,29 (TP I 184)¹⁶³⁰; *apsaras* Urvaśī as stupefying weapon (*mohanāstra*) in the hands of Kāma 17,5 (TP II 34); illuminating ~ (*prakāśanāstra*) 48,45 and ~ of fire (*mahāstram āgneyaṃ*) of Prabhāsa 48,46 (TP IV 77)¹⁶³¹; ~ of Śiva Paśupati 50,54 (TP IV 111)¹⁶³² does not hurt children, old men and fugitives 115,35 (TP VIII 146); Sudarśana, ~ of Hari-Viṣṇu 50,55 (TP IV 111)¹⁶³³; ~ of Brahmā cannot be repelled except by the ~ of Paśupati 115,20f. (TP VIII 145)¹⁶³⁴; various ~ (of darkness, of the sun, of cold, of heat, etc.)¹⁶³⁵ 116,71 (TP VIII 161);

¹⁶²⁸ For the association of jars and pitchers with breasts see also: breasts

¹⁶²⁹ Saletore 1943: 283.

¹⁶³⁰ TP refers in note 2 to Bhāvabhūti's *Uttararāmacarita* VI 5f., where the water and wind weapons are mentioned.

¹⁶³¹ Divine weapons are best understood as „God-given inner potencies and spiritual forces available to man, rather than physical instruments of destruction“ (Mehta 1990: 268f. in Whitaker 2000: 88); they are weapons forged from the *tejas* (fiery energy) of various gods (Whitaker, loc. cit. and 91).

¹⁶³² Cf. its description (of a destroying fire which does not attack children, old men or fugitives) 115,35 (TP VIII 146) and 118,76ff. (**description**; TP VIII 183).

¹⁶³³ Begley 1973.

¹⁶³⁴ On the neutralisation of divine weapons see Whitaker 2000: 93f.: greater *tejas* repels or absorbs weaker *tejas*.

Muktāphaladhvaja, a portion of Śiva, will obtain ~ of Paśupati 118,81 (TP VIII 183); – see also: *añjalika*; *ayo-daṇḍa*; *Brahmāstra*; *garuḍāstra*; *khādira-daṇḍa*; *laguḍa*; lasso; *mohanāstra*; *pannagāstra*; *pāśupata*; *Pradyumnāstra*; *śakti*; *Sudarśana*, *vāruṇāstra*

weaving, art of ~ unfading garlands 9,81 (TP I 100)

webs (*jāla*) of white and black spiders between wholesome and poisonous flowers 70,90 (TP VI 30); – see also: cobwebs

wedding altar, water in *vidyādhara* king’s hollow hand sprinkled on courtyard becomes ~ 51,220 (TP IV 37); – see also: *vedi*

wedding, groom arrives in the evening (*sāyam*) for ~ 71,156 (TP VI 47); – see also: marriage

wedding present, of horses, gold, camels, etc. 44,131f. (TP IV 9); 103,194 (TP VII 188); chariot as ~ to king, see: chariot; *vedi*

wedding ring, woman with a hundred ~s 63,31 (TP V 122 with ref. to Arabian Nights)

weeping Daitya princess 10,36 (TP I 108); ~ bitch due to being given meat with pepper dust 13,126 (TP I 159); ~ woman near impaled man 25,138 (TP II 201); ~ dancer like a bed of white lotuses (*kumudvatī*), wet with dew at the hour of dawn 34,165 (TP III 140); ~ deer in forest seeing ~ king and daughter after long separation 66,148 (TP V 189); noise of ~ (*rudita-dhvani*) 72,30 (TP VI 70); ~ earth 78,40 (TP VI 193); first ~ then dancing, of Pāśupata ascetic before entering corpse of young brahmin on pyre 97,32f. (TP VII 114); ~ woman wearing the form of the image on a pillar 121,175 (TP IX 24)

well, wife throws husband who killed her paramour into ~ 34,186 (TP III 141)¹⁶³⁶; net in ~ catches courtesan feigning grief at lover’s departure 57,106 (TP V 9); foolish lion throws himself on his reflection into ~ 60,105 (TP V 50); bird falling into ~ is drawn out 65,80ff. (TP V 160ff.); wise man atones for his fault like a man who digs a ~ 66,134 (TP V 188); while brahmin was offering *piṇḍa* to his father in the ~ of Gayā (*Gayā-kūpa*) three hands rose out of it to take the cake 93,88 (TP VII 85)

West is not honoured as being the cause of the setting of the sun 18,59 (TP II 53)

western gate of city crowded with bridegroom’s attendants 71,163 (TP VI 47)

western mountain, sun on ~ (*asta-śikhara*) stretches forth rays like fingers 29,126 (TP III 48); ~ sea (*aparāmbho-dhi*) with Hamsadvīpa 73,329 (TP VI 124);

western quarter (*saṃdhyā*), heaven puts moon on ~ like *tilaka* on forehead 95,67 (TP VII 102)

wheel, good woman turns ~ of virtues (*guṇa-cakra-pracodini*) 34,180 (TP III 141: “urging on a host of virtues”; ORC 345: “*capable de mettre en branle la roue des vertus*”; M I 485: “*treibt das Rad der Tugenden und löblichen Eigenschaften vor sich her*”); man with burning iron ~ (*lauhena cakreṇa*) on head in hell as parents’ curse for disobedience 56,148 (TP IV 230)¹⁶³⁷; woman (Māyā) turning ~ of mundane existence 70,89 and *saṃsāra-cakra*¹⁶³⁸

¹⁶³⁵ These *muktāmukta* weapons are discussed by Hopkins 1915: 123f. (§ 67) whom Date wrongly quotes 1929: 28, together with Oppert 1880: 30.

¹⁶³⁶ Cf. Daś 219.11.

107 (TP VI 30f.); – see also: voice
wheel machine (*cakra-yantra*) guarding water of immortality (*amṛta*) 29,47 (TP III 42);
white¹⁶³⁹, man stays united with newly-wedded *yakṣī* as a bed of ~ lotuses (*kumudâkara*; ORC
69: *le lotus de nuit*) with the night 10,181 (TP I 119); chowries fan (*śukla-cāmara-vijitām*)
divine maiden on throne in fig tree 17,109 (TP II 43); ~ is beautiful 104,165 (TP VIII
13); ~ colour of glory 109,42 (TP VIII 73 note); – see further: elephant; flowers; glory;
horse; laughing; mountain; old age; palace; Sarasvatī; umbrella;
who are we ? (*vayaṃ ca ke*) 45,56 (TP IV 20)
wickedness of men or women, see: dispute; men; women
widow¹⁶⁴⁰ deprived of possessions by relations raises lone son by menial drudgery (*kṛcchra-*
karmāṇi) 6,29-31 (TP I 62); ~ queen remarries prince 98,54 (TP VII 119); poor young ~
with lone son, living as prostitute (*rūpa-śālīnī*) 106,94 (TP VIII 35); – see also: single
parent
widow-burning, see: suttee
widower, remarried banishes sons with first wife 65,4 (TP V 154)
wife, brahman with two wives 14,38 (TP I 184); *senāpati* designates his ~ as slave and offers
her to the king 15,76 (TP II 8); five brothers share one ~ 15,132 (TP II 13); bride refuses
to be treated as ~, lit. being bedded (*śayyâ rohaṇa-varjana*) 17,84 (TP II 41); Rati and Prīti
are wives of Kāma 18,27 (TP II 51); man sees ~ committing adultery (*bhāryām anya-*
gāminīm) 19,27 (TP II 86); pregnant (*dhṛta-garbhā*) ~ abandoned 21,111 (TP II 133); evil
~ like she-crow (*kākīva*) 23,27 (TP II 158 with “she-wolf” for “she-crow”); shrewish
(*śathā*) and quarrelsome ~ continually pesters husband for money 23,35f. (TP II 159); ~
ascends (*citârohāya*) the funeral pyre of impaled husband at night 25,140 (TP II 201
[“worships”] with note 2)¹⁶⁴¹; jealousy of rival ~ 32,123 (TP III 99); ~ as witch sucks
sleeping husband’s entrails 32,156f. (TP III 102); rival wives bring many false accusations
32,191 (TP III 106); king without fitting ~ 33,26 (TP III 109); unfaithful ~ pushes
husband, who killed adulterer, into well 34,186 (TP III 141); ~ not interested in native
country 39,166 (TP III 229); ~ as incarnate success (*rūpavatyârtha-siddhyā*) of husband
39,244 (TP III 235); ~ sold for horses and garments 43,77 (TP III 287); selling one’s ~ is
a crime 43,103 (TP III 288); twelve head wives (*mukhya-bhāryā*) of hero Prabhāsa 46,243
(TP IV 65); why kings have many wives 47,104ff. (TP IV 73); ~ loved as own life (*prāṇa-*
samā) 49,6 (TP IV 85); earth as king’s ~ 53,114 (TP IV 175)¹⁶⁴²; ~ removes husband’s
weariness (*śramâpanoda*) 56,320 (TP IV 243); ~’s father wants to see daughter 58,81 (TP

¹⁶³⁷ Penzer refers to Pañcatantra V 3, but cf. e.g. the Pāli Jātaka nos 369 and 439. See further Grey 1994: 250ff.
and Klaus 1983 (p. c. Adelheid Mette who also kindly lent me her copy of this M.A. thesis).

¹⁶³⁸ See Zin & Schlingloff 1998.

¹⁶³⁹ See Hanchett 1988: 290f.

¹⁶⁴⁰ Kane 1974: II 583ff.

¹⁶⁴¹ ORC 227: “venue monter sur le bûcher.”

¹⁶⁴² Manu ???

V 21); flogging contemptuous ~ renews husband's passion 58,94f. (TP V 21); ~ hides husband in cave 61,155 (TP V 81); faithless ~ falsely accusing her husband of murdering a Bhilla has her ears and nose cut off 61,164ff. (TP V 82); faithless ~ is present at her own *śrāddha* 61,199f. (TP V 85); young ~ averse to old husband embraces him out of fear of a burglar 62,84f. (TP V 106); silly carpenter carries adulterous ~ (*jāyā*) on his head 62,115 (TP V 108); two wives emerge from mouth of celestial husband 63,20 (TP V 121); ~ stupefied with drink does not recognize husband 64,105 (TP V 147); vicious ~ of absent brahmin loves cowherd 64,115 (TP V 148); lonely ~ of absent merchant, locked up in *bhū-grha* by jealous husband, gives herself to leper 64,135 (TP V 149); ungrateful ~ wants to kill husband 65,16 (TP V 154); adulterous ~ carries maimed paramour¹⁶⁴³ 65,28, is mutilated, branded and banished 65,40 (TP V 155f.); ~ dies when husband is cursed 65,244 (TP V 173); *yakṣa* wife in tree pretends to be dead (*mṛta-kalpaṃ kṛtvā*) when struck with a garland of flowers 66,22 (TP V 179); with charmed mustard seeds brahmin transforms ~ into mare 68,55 (TP VI 5); ~ and husband closely connected as oblation to the fire (*anuraktā vahner iva svāhā*)¹⁶⁴⁴ 69,16 (TP VI 10); robber gives his ~ to Citragupta 72,330 (TP VI 93); *yakṣiṇī* ~ called *jñānini* 73,52 (TP VI 104); ruin (*vidhvastatā*) is gambler's ~ 73,77 (TP VI 106); brahmin with two wives 73,417 (TP VI 130); king with two wives 74,24 (TP VI 142); one ~ flees mother-in-law 74,161, a second ~ hangs herself 74,163 (TP VI 152); wicked man kills and robs sleeping ~ 77,45 (TP VI 186); captured wives of enemies wave chowries for victor 78,6 (TP VI 191); corpse animated by *vetāla* bites off nose of faithless ~ 77,68 (TP VI 188); king with three sensitive wives 85,3 (TP VII 10); wise ~ Medhāvati 86,14 (TP VII 14); brahmin ~ abducted at night by *vidyādhara* prince 87,9 (TP VII 29); prince's dearest wish (*ekā cintā ... hṛdi*) is suitable ~ 94,7 (TP VII 87); ~ fitting (*anurūpā*) husband is as the oblation to the fire 96,5 (TP VII 108) and 97,9 (TP VII 112); home of a householder is empty without a ~ 98,31 (TP VII 118); prince without suitable ~ 101,50 (TP VII 137); ~ of Brahmā, designation of Sarasvatī 106,24 (TP VIII 29); ~ as one of the seven jewels of a *cakravartin* 109,22 (TP VIII 71); woman destined to become one's ~ again by a pre-birth connection (*pūrva-saṃbandha-nirmitā*) 112,171 (TP VIII 120); ~ and daughter of wicked *vidyādhara* share curse 112,193 (TP VIII 121); ~ has no authority as witness when husband is alive 112,211 (TP VIII 123); prince donates only ~ to brahmin = Indra 113,75 (TP VIII 129); ~ performs penance on behalf of husband for success in war 116,16 (TP VIII 157); merchant's ~ disappears from sleeping husband at night 123,146 (TP IX 53), cf. 87,8f. (TP VII 29); brahmin ~ leaves sleeping husband in order to go and embrace paramour, an impaled thief 124,116 (TP IX 76); repudiated ~ see: alimony; – see further: adulteress; bridegroom; polygamy; woman

wilderness, see: forest; night; rhinoceros; Śabara; tsunami

will, what cannot Śiva's ~ (*īśvarêcchā*) effect? 9,60 (TP I 99); *vidyādhari* roaming about at

¹⁶⁴³ Cf. Daś 219,11.

¹⁶⁴⁴ The comparison goes wrong for the fire is masculine.

~ (*kāma-caratvād*) 18,216 (TP II 66); cf. *kāma-cāriṇ*
 wind, Kāma's weapon of ~ (*vāyavya- ... astra*) 14,29 (TP I 184); ~ whirls ship like head of
mast elephant 36,82 (TP III 175)¹⁶⁴⁵; violent ~ like *mast* elephant with rain drops as ichor
 55,188 (TP IV 215); king tossed with ~ of separation (*virahānala*) 55,206 (TP IV 216); ~
 (*tārūnya-vāta*) of youth 57,75 (TP V 7); ~ conspires with hermit's curse 67,101 (TP V
 203); dancing princess looking like a creeper of the tree of love agitated by the ~ of youth
 (*yauvanānila*) 71,77 (TP VI 41); ~ from Malaya mountain, yellow with the pollen of
 flowers (*puṣpa-reṇu-piśaṅga*) 71,198 (TP VI 50) and 104,8 (TP VIII 1); females are
 changeful like the ~s (*vātyā ivāticapalāḥ*) 72,256 (TP VI 87); what can ~ do against
 mountain ? 74,105 (TP VI 147); ~s in hot season laden with fragrance of jasmine and
 trumpet-flower (*mallikā-pāṭalā-moda-medurā marutaḥ*) 95,13 (TP VII 99); ~ (*pavana*)
 falls after kings and ministers jump overboard 101,186 (TP VII 147);- see also:
 comparison(s); crazy; destiny; forehead; king
 window(s),¹⁶⁴⁶ king with magic shoes enters *antaḥpura* of sleeping princess by ~ (*vātāyana*)
 3,62 (TP I 23); round ~ as eyes (*gavākṣōtphulla-locanā*) of a city 18,9 (TP II 49); wife
 standing at ~ (*vātāyanāgra-sthā*)¹⁶⁴⁷ captivated by male passer-by 58,120 (TP V 23); man
 enters royal harem at night by the ~ (*vātāyana-pathena*) being pulled up with a rope
 (*rajjūtksipta*) 58,124 (TP V 24); minister looks into palace in cave through lattice-- (*jāla-*
gavākṣa) 70,88 (TP VI 80); thoughtless king stays devoted to latticed ~s (*rajyati sma ca*
nīścinto jāla-vātāyaneṣu) (of *antaḥpura*) instead of to the affairs of kingdom 86,8 (TP VII
 13); - see also: *arka*; basket; beckoning; cave; face; garment; *kaūśeya*; rope; *śamī*
 wine (*madya*),¹⁶⁴⁸ drugging mahout with ~ 13,10 (TP I 150); ~ (*surā*) drunk by king 11,5 (TP
 I 122); idem 28,121 (*pāna*; TP III 29); to be intoxicated with ~ (*madyena kṣibate*) 13,10
 (TP I 151); ~ with *dhattūra* 13,142 (TP I 160); king addicted to ~ 14,89 (TP I 189); idem
strī-madya-mṛgayāyakta 15,8 (TP II 1); idem **21,6ff.** (*mada, madhu, ārakta-sura-*; TP II
 125); heavenly ~ (*āsava*) 17,114 (TP II 43); king drinks spirits to counteract evil dream
 (*rājā pratighnan duḥ-svapnaṃ siṣeve pāna-maṅgalam*) 36,67 (TP III 174); ~ as chief ally
 of lust 36,92 (TP III 175); queen intoxicated by ~ (*atipāyitā*) 39,207 (TP III 233); ~ party
 at rising moon (*candrōdaye pānaṃ*) 28,121 (TP III 29); wicked queen drugged with ~
 (*madyam atipāyitā*) so that she talks in her sleep and betrays her misbehaviour 39,207 (TP
 III 233); ~ drunk (*pitāsava*) after betel 43,64 (TP III 285); ~ or water for the latter part of
 the night (*apara-rātra*) 54,200 (TP IV 198); goddess Śrī is intoxicating as ~ (*madirēva*
vimohinī) 62,164 (TP V 113); king refuses to drink mixture of ~ and fat of corpses offered
 by Asurī maiden 73,154 (TP VI 112); ~ is the life of intoxication by which Kāma lives
 (*pānaṃ madasya Kandarpa-jīvitasyāpi jīvitam*) 85,9 (TP VII 10); ~s (*madhūni*) red as
bimba lips of queens who tasted them before the king 85,10 (TP VII 10)¹⁶⁴⁹; ~ offered to

¹⁶⁴⁵ See on winds: The Imperial Gazetteer of India, Atlas 1931 map 8.

¹⁶⁴⁶ Coomaraswamy 1931: 195ff.

¹⁶⁴⁷ On *vātāyana* see Karashima 2012: 208 note 1 on § 25.1.

¹⁶⁴⁸ Wine in India is grown from Punjab up to Tamil Nadu.

yakṣas 105,57 (TP VIII 25); king drinks ~ with queen at her wish 106,52 (TP VIII 32); ~ (*madhu*) drinking at festival of victory 109,152 (TP VIII 81; ORC 1152: “*du vin*” : M II 532: “*Branntwein*”); ~ snaps the fetters of shame binding the ladies of the harem (*avarodha-strī-lajjā-nigaḍa-bhedī*) 110,127 (TP VIII 91); ~ as essence of love’s life and ally of merriment (*smara-jīvita-sarvasyaṃ vilāsa-sacivaṃ madhu*) 110,127 (TP VIII 91); ~ causes contracted eyebrows and fiery eyes of the queens 110,130 (TP VIII 91); king drinking ~ (*āpānaṃ sevamāno*) 111,18 (TP VIII 97); lakes of heavenly ~ (*divyāsava-bhṛta*) in gardens of Rasātala palaces 118,106 (TP VIII 185); ~ party, see: *āpāna-goṣṭhī*; (*āpāna-līla*); combat; *pāna*

wings, of mountains, clouds of dust from an army make Indra fear of ~ 14,13 (TP I 182); elephant sinks in mud like mountain that has fallen due to its ~ having been cut off by (Indra’s) thunderbolt 68,23 (TP VI 3); fastening ~ of grass to his sides stupid brahmin tries to fly 72,279 (TP VI 89)¹⁶⁵⁰; sea as refuge of mountains that retain their ~ (*sapakṣa-kṣmā-bhṛd-āśraya*) 86,83 (TP VII 19)

winking (*nimeṣa*) of eyes as mark of mortality 104,95 (TP VIII 8)¹⁶⁵¹

winter, elephant of ~ (*hemanta-hastin*) slain by lion of spring 91,20f. (TP VII 67); ~ solstice (*uttarāyaṇa*) 104,152 (TP VIII 12)¹⁶⁵²

winter solstice (*uttarāyana*), bathing in the Ganges on ~ 104,152 (TP VIII 12 and 19f.)

wisdom, water of ~ 96,44 (TP VII 111); – see also: sayings

wise man (*jñānī*) consoles desperate princess 18,228 (TP II 67); ~ men are tested in difficulty as heroes are tested in fight 31,94 (TP III 89); single ~ man fallen among fools is like a lotus fallen on the waves 32,55 (TP III 94); ~ man does not look for oil in sand 57,128 (TP V 10)

wise woman gets back husband 124,236 (TP IX 85)

wishing-cow (*kāma-dhenu*) of the good: honouring the deities and brahmins 17,134 (TP II 45); ~ produces Sumeru’s food 50,141 (TP IV 117); devotion (*bhakti*) to parents is ~ of plenty 56,170 (TP IV 232)

wishing-pot, see: cornucopia; *ghaṭa*

wishing-stone, see: *cintā-maṇi*; *cintā-ratna*

wishing-tree (*kalpa-vṛkṣa*),¹⁶⁵³ slopes of Mt Kailāsa are made of branches of ~ 1,66 (TP I 8); Garuda perching on ~ in order to eat elephant and tortoise from sea 12,141 (TP I 144); speaking ~ (*kalpa-druma*) called “Manoratha-dāyaka” asked for son 22,18ff. (TP II 138); ~ asked for relief from poverty for all poor 22,30 (TP II 139); ~ of policy (*nīti-kalpa-latā*) 34,30 (TP III 130); ~ in the case of ill-starred (*a-bhavya*) men often becomes a *palāśa*-tree 53,35 (TP IV 170; ORC 584: “*Pour les infortunés, même l’arbre à désirs peut perdre ses*

¹⁶⁴⁹ In love play wine is passed on from mouth to mouth (Raghuvamśa 8,68 (Jackmuth 2002: 117).

¹⁶⁵⁰ STh *F 1021.1.

¹⁶⁵¹ Penzer refers to TP IV 239. See also 28,61 (TP III 24).

¹⁶⁵² Penzer points out in a note the wrong translation ‘summer solstice’ in the dictionaries. See TP VIII 19f.

¹⁶⁵³ See, e.g., ORC 1536.

feuilles” with note on p. 1423; MI 819: “*Der Wunschbaum verwandelt sich wahrlich für Menschen, die unter einem bösem Stern stehen, meistens in welchem Laub*”); king as ~ (*kalpa-pādapa*) 67,10 (TP V 196); prince admirable as to outdo Skanda, Kandarpa and ~ 71,68 (TP VI 40); moon like an ear-ornament made of a shoot of ~ of love (*kāma-kalpa-druma*) 72,27 (TP VI 70); king is ~ of suppliants 72,159 (TP VI 80); king is called subjects’ ~ 72,177 (TP VI 81) and 220 (TP VI 85); prince by austerities becomes ~ as boon from Indra 72,223 (TP VI 85); sitting on ~ rising out of sea mermaid sings to the music of a lute (*vallakī-vādyā*) on the seed of former karman to be eaten as fruit in this life 86,41 and 43f. (TP VII 16); do, 86,77 (TP VII 19); ~ grants *vidyādhara* king part *avatāra* of Bodhisatta as son with pre-birth memory (*jāti-smara*) 90,7f. (TP VII 49; cf. 72,234 [TP VI 85]); at royal wedding even trees had garments and gems fastened to them making them look like earthly ~s 103,199 (TP VII 188)¹⁶⁵⁴; – movable ~, see *yantra-kalpadruma*; – see further: *pārijāta*

witch(es),¹⁶⁵⁵ screams of ~ (*ḍākinī-nāda*) in charnel ground at night 18,147 (TP II 60); magic power of ~’s spells (*ḍākinī-mantra-siddhi*) due to eating human flesh 20,104f. (TP II 103); Kālarātri sports with her coven (*ḍākanī-cakra*) in charnel ground 20,142 (TP II 108); wife as ~ sucks sleeping husband’s entrails 32,156f. (TP III 102); “wife is a ~” 32,156 and 173 (TP III 102 and 104); barber’s wife declared ~ 32,169 (TP III 103); friend of adulterous woman is ~ (*yoginī*) 37,109 (TP III 191); ~ (*yoginī*) with two spells (*mantra-prayoga*) 37,109f. (TP III 191); brahmin woman is secretly a ~ 37,150 (TP III 193); ~ turns man with string round his neck into ox 37,153 (TP III 194)¹⁶⁵⁶; evil ~ turns into black mare to slay good ~ (*siddha-yoginī*) in the form of bay mare 37,162 (TP III 194)¹⁶⁵⁷; two ~s become different horses and fight 37,162f. (TP III 194); good ~ (*sad-yoginī*) 48,122 (TP IV 82); Bhairava sporting with ~es (*akṛḍad yoginī-sakhaḥ*) 56,106 (TP IV 227); (brahmin) wife becomes ~ by fate (*daivāt ... śākinī-siddhi-saṃvarā*) 68,37 (TP VI 4); ~ (*ḍākinī*) turns husband into buffalo throwing magic dust in his face 68,44f. (TP VI 5); good ~ (*yoginī*) turns buffalo back into man by means of charmed water 68,51 (TP VI 5)¹⁶⁵⁸; ~ mentions imp of fever-demon (*jvara-ceṭaka*) who has the power of removing fever 71,207 (TP VI 50); ~ sows barley in her house 71,266 (TP VI 55); coven of ~es (*yoginī-cakra*) in charnel ground at night 75,173 (TP VI 176); drunk ~ tries to take away ascetic’s rosary 75,175 (TP VI 176); ~ gives man’s hand looking like red lotus to brahmin beggar 108,26 (TP VIII 54); ~es harrass brahmin protected by brown cow 108,32 (TP VIII 55); rescue of brahmin from ~es 108,41 (TP VII 55); in fight between ~es brahmin escapes to deserted country 108,44 (TP VIII 56); ~es appear because Kālarātri is not worshipped 109,96 (TP

¹⁶⁵⁴ For wrapping sacred trees with cotton string as a common feature of tree worship see Haberman 2013: 185.

¹⁶⁵⁵ On witches see Crooke 1896: II 259ff.; R.N. Saletore 1981: 109ff.; Dehejia 1986: 13ff.; Stubbe-Diarra 1995: 28; Dallapiccola 2002: 210; STh G 200-299. – Cf. HdA ???

¹⁶⁵⁶ STh *G 263.

¹⁶⁵⁷ Doniger ???

¹⁶⁵⁸ On water and transformation in classical antiquity see Ninck 1921: 138ff. and cf. 156 quoting 1001 night.

VIII 77); ~es after fight with other ~es drop brahmin from air 123,222 (TP IX 59); ~es save young wife in forest and bring her to father-in-law 123,285 (TP IX 63); – see also: cannibalism; *gupta-yoginī*; nude; *rakta-kamala*; *sad-yoginī*; *sākinī*; *siddha-yoginī*; *yogēśvarī*; witness (*sākṣi*), fire as ~ for *a-droha-pratyaya* 16,84 (TP II 28); Śiva as ~ for husband’s statement against his wife 23,21 (TP II 158); *loka-pālas* invoked as ~es 52,52 (TP IV 141); tree invoked as ~ of thief of *dīnārs* 60,222 (TP V 60); ministers as ~es (*antara-stha*) of king’s promise to give half his realm to *Bodhisattva* for relieving him from snake 65,125 (TP V 164); ~es to agreement 124,231 (TP IX 84)

woman,¹⁶⁵⁹ virtuous ~ (*satī*) made king’s sister 4,82ff. (TP I 36); any ~ is good-looking to the man who admires her 5,51 (TP I 51)¹⁶⁶⁰; ~ bitten by snake 6,90 (TP I 67) and revived by magic ring 10,97 (TP I 113); brahmin seizes ~ diving in Ganges by the hair and follows her underwater to Śiva temple 10,29f. (TP I 108); ~ compared to night 10,181 (TP I 119); pretty merchant ~ spurned by king has resentment (*antarjāta-vimānanā*) 15,72 (TP II 8); ~ as world-bewildering drug of Kāma 15,74 (TP II 8); to whom is not the attractive object called ~ the cause of misfortune ? (*strī-nāma viṣayo nidānaṃ kasya nāpadām*) 15,141 (TP II 14); immortal ~, who gives up her celestial rank (*tyakta-divya-sthiti*), desires sex (*mām upehi* !) with mortal 17,129-132 (TP II 44); pretty ~ offered as present to king 18,79 (TP II 55); ~ abandoned while asleep 18,222 (TP II 66); idem 18,289 (TP II 71); adulterous ~ 19,30 (TP II 86); in a palace ~ representing Māyā turns a wheel with bees 70,89 (TP VI 30); adulterous ~ kicked by alien at night which doubles her passion (*dvi-guṇī-bhūta-rāgā*) 21,75f. (TP II 131); ~ worthless as a straw (*strī-tṛṇa*) 21,81 (TP II 131); ~ riding on lion like moon digit on lap of autumn cloud 22,107 (TP II 145); ~ refuses to be married 24,30 (TP II 172); ~ remembering pre-birth 24,232 (TP II 187); heavenly ~ emerges from tree 26,210 (TP II 233); passionate (*vikāritā*) ~ compared to snake¹⁶⁶¹ (*bhujagīva*) 27,187 (TP III 15); killing ~ is wicked deed 32,33 (TP III 92); ~ kills sleeping husband and accuses travellers 32,77 (TP III 95); weeping ~ compared to bed of white lotuses, wet with dew 34,165 (TP III 140); ~ is nectar and poison 34,178 (TP III 141); ~ is like lotus-bed with alligator concealed in it 34,179 (TP III 141); wicked ~ slaying husband is like female snake 34,181 (TP III 141); do, 58,78 (TP V 20); passionate ~ and furious river (*mattā nadī ca nārī ca*) cannot be restrained 36,8 (TP III 169); faithful merchant ~ heals sick elephant by touch of hand 36,39 (TP III 172); how can a ~ addicted to wine, the chief ally of lust, be faithful ? 36,92 (TP III 175); ~ cannot be guarded by force 36,133 (TP III 178); effort for a ~ is like colocynth fruit, bitter in its after-taste 37,145 (TP III 193); heart of ~ is a tangled maze (*strī-cittaṃ hy atidurgamam*) 37,149 (TP III 193); three faults of ~: flightiness, recklessness and love for congregation of witches¹⁶⁶² 37,170 (TP III 195); ~ ever desires fresh men as female bee wanders from flower to flower

¹⁶⁵⁹ See, e.g., Roesler & Soni 2004.

¹⁶⁶⁰ Cf. our “beauty is in the eye of the beholder.”

¹⁶⁶¹ Cf. Bollée 2009: 23,20 (Kuṇārajātaka).

¹⁶⁶² ORC 380: “la pratique de la magie ou de la sorcellerie”. Text: *śambara* ‘magic, sorcellery’ (MW).

37,174 (TP III 195); ~ as a mixture of ambrosia and poison 39,80 (TP III 223); ~ hating men 42,19 (TP III 260); ~ is like fortune incarnate 43,93 (TP III 287); no one ~ possesses all good qualities 47,105 (TP IV 73); good qualities of ~ 47,107ff. (TP IV 73f.); ~ given away by her father against her will 49,216 (TP IV 100); fickle ~ is like sunset, momentarily aglow for everyone 52,285, and like human life 52,287 (TP IV 157); wise man never falls into power of rivers or ~ 52,288 (TP IV 157); conquered queen as king's banner of victory 54,238 (TP IV 201); deformed ~ (*vikṛtā stri*) in dream snatches king's crest-jewel from his head 55,133 (TP IV 211)¹⁶⁶³; *nāgī* entering king's bedroom without opening door 55,144 (TP IV 212); ~ with sword enters lying-in chamber through bolted door and steals baby 55,189 (TP IV 215); virtuous ~ has great power of discernment (*vijñāna-bala*) 56,180 (TP IV 232); *vidyādhari* offers herself as wife to prince 59,138 (TP V 35); women would even eat dirt if they had no noses 62,112 (TP V 108); female water spirit offers herself (*mām bhajasva* !) to brahmin 63,28 (TP V 121); ~ carries maimed man on her back 64,28 (TP V 155)¹⁶⁶⁴; ~ avoids outrage by monkey and cowherd 64,41 (TP V 142); ~ carries cripple on back 65,28 (TP V 155)¹⁶⁶⁵; ~ mind difficult to fathom 65,42 (TP V 156); by talking to servant ~ Bodhisattva loses his power to procure fruits etc. 65,100 (TP V 162); ~ with eleven husbands 66,97 (TP V 185); wicked ~ compared to snake (*bhujagī*) 68,49 (TP VI 5); ~ (Māyā) causes to revolve wheel of mundane existence with bees 70,89 (TP VI 30f.); who knows the mysterious way of a ~'s mind (*stri-citta*) as of destiny ? 71,236 (TP VI 53); divine (*divyā stri*) picks up suicide candidate in wood 72,199 (TP VI 83); unison with ~ is like banyan with spring (*viṭapīva madhu-śriyā*) 73,27 (TP VI 102); ~ beaming beauty 75,129 (TP VI 173); ~'s mind is terrible 77,72 (TP VI 188); ~ (the earth) weeping at night 78,32 (TP VI 193); ~ as incarnation of Rati (*Kāmāṃśasyāvatīrṇā*) 105,34 (TP VIII 23); king sees heavenly female descending from the sky with her daughter, like the lightning with the rain in a cloudless atmosphere 106,34 (TP VIII 30); ~ white as the moon 120,105 (TP IX 9); princess as present (*prhṛta*) to emperor 108,162 (TP VIII 66); life saved in war by ~ is worthless 109,141 (TP VIII 80); man and ~ issue from belly of elephant 123,90 (TP IX 49); ~ does not receive alms 123,187 (TP IX 56); ~ (*aṅganā*) issues from belly of fish 123,231 (TP IX 59); ~ returns to life by ashes being thrown on her pyre 124,9 (TP IX 68f.); – see also: earth; disguise; *femme savante*; maiden; misfortune; moon; *pum-dveṣiṇī*; *puruṣa-dveṣiṇī*; quicksilver; women
 woman's love scorned 10,77 (TP I 112 and note in IV 104ff.)¹⁶⁶⁶; idem, 20,123f. (TP II 120ff. and see also: Potiphar motif); Rambhā rejected by Arjuna 33,90 (TP III 113); ~ (merchant's wife rejected by Gomukha) tries to kill the latter with a poisoned drink 34,175

¹⁶⁶³ In evil dreams of kings often a deformed or black woman takes something from him or even drags him off, see, e.g. Bollée 1984: 176f.

¹⁶⁶⁴ Cf. Daś 234.16.

¹⁶⁶⁵ Cf. Kuṇḍ 21 (Bollée 1967: 119 and 132); Daṇḍin, *Daś* 234,16.

¹⁶⁶⁶ STh T 71.

(TP III 140); women whose love is slighted are worse than poison 49,152 (TP IV 95); ~ spurned complains to husband that she was raped 63,34 (TP V 122)¹⁶⁶⁷;
 woman-murder, offence of ~ (*stri-hatyā-pātaka*) 32,143 (TP III 102); – see also: women
 (made drunk)
 womb,¹⁶⁶⁸ man emerges alive from belly (of fish) cut open, having endured a second wonderful [stay in the] womb (*pāṭitasyōdarāj jīvan ... anubhūtāparāścarya-garbha-vāso viniryayau*) 25,52 (TP II 193); ~ as prison 29,110 (TP III 47); ~ typified by jar (*ghaṭaka-rūpa*) 70,112 (TP VI 32)¹⁶⁶⁹; fallen *vidyādhara* prince hears voice in Śiva’s temple: “You shall not endure misery in the ~ (*garbha-vāsa-kleśa*)¹⁶⁷⁰ and in your mortal existence” 118,3 (TP VIII 178);
 women¹⁶⁷¹ do not restrain speech 1,52 (TP I 6); fancies of ~ are ever inconstant (*strīṇām cañcalāś citta-vṛttayaḥ*) 7,57 (TP I 79)¹⁶⁷²; two ~ made drunk and burnt in palace 10,113 (TP I 114); ~ staring at king entering city 16,75 (TP II 27); ~ whose husbands are still alive (*pativatī*) busy in chamber prepared for marriage ceremony 16,76 (TP II 27); celestial ~ as reward for good deeds (*su-kṛtaiḥ śubha-karmaṇām divyāḥ ... nāryas*) 17,133 (TP II 44); ~ carrying water in golden pitchers (*kāñcana-ghaṭāḥ*) 18,356 (TP II 76); hearts of ~ are hard as adamant in daring transgression, but soft as a flower when afraid 21,97 (TP II 132); ~ of different rank (*bhinna-jāti*) in pre-birth 23,48 (TP II 160); ~ bestow themselves on men out of affection 27,201 (TP III 16); deities protect good ~ devoted to husband (*bhartr-eka-bhaktānām ... devatā eva sādhvīnām trāṇam āpadi kurvate*) 29,122 (TP III 47); ~ in love regard neither height nor depth in front of them, as a horse urged on by his rider does not fear the sword-edge 31,39 (TP III 84); good ~ do not visit house of a friend’s husband 32,193 (TP III 106); ~ kept away from beautiful king when riding out 33,57 (TP III 111); ~ representing the sciences (*vidyāḥ*), entering a crown prince 34,155 (TP III 139); ~ are created as imitation of recklessness (*sr̥ṣṭam sāhasam tad-anu striyaḥ*) 34,177 (TP III

¹⁶⁶⁷ For the Potiphar motif see s.v. supra.

¹⁶⁶⁸ Suffering in the womb is drastically depicted by Buddhaghosa, *Vism* 500,4ff.: “(One) is born in the belly in a position that is below the receptacle for undigested food (stomach), above the receptacle for digested food (rectum), between the belly-lining and the back-bone, which is very cramped, quite dark, pervaded by very fetid draughts redolent of various smells of ordure, and exceptionally loathsome. And on being reborn there, for ten months he undergoes excessive suffering, being cooked like a pudding in a bag by the heat produced in the mother’s womb, and steamed like a dumpling of dough, with no bending, stretching, and so on” (Ñānamoli 1956: 569). Mahānisiṅha 5,10,114ff.; Vasudevahiṇḍi 10,9f. (*jahā kūvo, tahā gabbha-vāso*) and Hemacandra, *Par.* III 268 compare the womb to a dunghole (*kūpa-vāsa*).

¹⁶⁶⁹ Dallapiccola 2002: 120 s. v. *kumbha*.

¹⁶⁷⁰ Cf. Rājat 5,201. – See further Dossi 1998: 79ff.

¹⁶⁷¹ As early as the RV “Females are defined by a patriarchal and misogynist tradition that characterizes them as fickle or even dangerous and values them for their subservience, sexuality, and reproductivity. Ritual participants reinforce such values as men can fulfil their ritual and social responsibilities only by being married and having sons” (Whitaker 2011: 30). As recent history informs us this attitude does not appear to have changed very much in the past millennia.

¹⁶⁷² On the fickleness of women see Mbh 1963: XIII 38,11ff. especially 24 (see Bollée 1967: 118).

141); protest against seclusion of ~ (*strīṇām rakṣā-nīyantraṇam*) 36,6 (TP III 169); like prosperous circumstances ~ are never faithful; like the evening, they display a short-lived passion; their hearts are crooked like the channels of rivers; like snakes they are not to be relied on; like lightning they are fickle 37,142f. (TP III 193); ~ have three faults: flightiness, recklessness and (a connection with) female demon attendants on Durgā, and magic (*cāpalaṃ sāhasikatā śākinī-śambara-*) 37,170f. (TP III 195 “a love for the congregation of witches”; M I 535 similar; ORC 380: “*pratique de la magie ou de la sorcellerie*”); for ~ the husband is chief refuge in this world and in the next (*ihāmutra nārīṇām paramā gatiḥ patiḥ*) 39,47 (TP III 221); ~ pliant as canes (*vetasa-vṛtti*) 44,49 (TP IV 4); ~ as wedding present 44,78 (TP IV 6); ~ as war booty 45,70 (TP IV 22); women always talk about matters involving themselves and others (? *strīṇām na sa kṣaṇo, yatra na kathā sva-parāśrayā* [?]¹⁶⁷³) 47,97 (TP IV 73 with note 1: “there is no occasion on which women are not irrelevant in their talk”; ORC 510: “*pour les femmes il n’est pas de moment où les conversations ne soient pas de mise.*”; M I 710: “*für die Frauen gibt es nun einmal keine Gelegenheit, bei welcher sie das Gespräch nicht auch auf die eigene Sache lenken.*”); **ethnic catalogue** of ~ 47,106 (TP IV 73); there is nothing which women will not let out when they are met together in social intercourse and their minds are interested in the course of conversation (*prasaṅga-militāḥ kathā-prasara-sakta-cittā mithas tad asti na kim apy aho yad iha nōdvamanti striyaḥ*) 47,120 (TP IV 74); wicked ~ have sprung from lying speech (*a-satya-vacanam*) 49,120 (TP IV 93); ~ whose love is slighted are worse than poison 49,152 (TP IV 95); fickle is the mind of ~ 52,277 (TP IV 157); ~ never to be trusted 58,56 (TP V 18); ~ are like flies that leave camphor and haste to dirt 58,136 (TP V 24); ~ would eat dirt if they had no noses 62,112 (TP V 108); ~ in a house are a snare (*nibandhanam*; proverb ?) 64,108 (TP V 148); ~ like torrents that flow in a ravine 64,149 (TP V 150)¹⁶⁷⁴; of Pāṭaliputra, tricks of ~ 66,28 (TP V 180); ~ are weak (or clever ? *peśala*) 72,70 (TP VI 74; ORC 832: “*faible*”; M II 82: “*mit lieblichen und zarten Frauen*”); ~ are changeful like winds (*vātyā ivāti capalāḥ*) and enveloped with a cloud of passion 72,256 (TP VI 87); two ~ of celestial appearance (*divya-rūpe striyau*) issue from fig tree 73,412 (TP VI 130, cf. 118,12 [TP VIII 185]); mind of ~ is terrible (*āśayaḥ strīṇām bhīṣaṇaḥ*) 77,72 (TP VI 188); ~ have to retire (*apasārayitum*, ORC 990 “*se tenir à l’écart (la vue de la beauté du roi pouvant mettre leur vertu en péril*”; similarly M II 308) when king rides out at spring festival 91,23 (TP VII 67)¹⁶⁷⁵; bad ~ are a grievous affliction, and

¹⁶⁷³ In the note TP discusses the reading of the last two words of the text (*sv-aparāśrayā* ?) but wrongly cites D which reads the same. In view of 47,120 one may divide *sva-parāśrayā* but the meaning would not differ very much. As to 77,72 one may even think of reading *-āśayā*.

¹⁶⁷⁴ See Feldhaus 1995.

¹⁶⁷⁵ Anderson 2005: 99 with note 9 on p. 108 where it is supposed that the sight of the attractive king might be too much for women to bear. In vs 15, however, the brahmins think that the king should be protected against the female beauty because he would otherwise no longer care for the realm (cf. 86,8 [TP VII 13]). At 18,16 (TP II 50) women hang out of the windows to see the king, but in vs 23 respectable women (*kula-yoṣitaḥ*) apparently should be

a source of calamity to their family 95,81 (TP VII 103); curious urban ~ (*paura-nāri*) 103,178 (TP VII 187); one hundred ~ as present given to prince at inauguration 103,219 (TP VII 190); ~ do not endure wounding of affections (*praṇaya-khaṇḍana*) 105,31 (TP VIII 23); Kāma as destroyer of ~ (*strī-ghna*) 117,65 (TP VIII 168); emperor Merudhvaja takes pleasure in virtuous deeds, not in ~ (*ratim dharmā-caryāsu śraddadhe nāṅganāsu*) 118,12 (TP VIII 179); Dānava ~ concealing by magic their form within trees 118,107 (TP VIII 185, cf. 73,412 [TP VI 130]); ~ are unreliable and full of daring wickedness (lit.: fit committers of violence: *nāsti viśvāsaḥ strīṣu sāhasa-bhūmiṣu*) 124,102 (TP IX 75; ORC 1312: “... *femmes qui sont l’effronterie incarnée*”); Mūladeva speaks up for the existence of good ~ with a story 124,129 (TP IX 77); – ~ deposited, see: deposit; – ~, Divine or Great, see: Mātaras; scorned ~ q.v.; – see also: present

wonder (*citra*), of grains not diminishing after consumption 7,21 (TP I 75); ~ (*āścarya*) of Agni changing a bilva fruit offered by a king meditating with soul of firm valour (*ḍṛḍha-sattvena cetasā*) into a golden one from his tree of valour (*sattva-taru*) 35,66 (TP III 160); ~ of golden lotuses emerging from rain drops that touched a human skeleton 40,94 (TP III 248); ~ of golden *haṃsas* offering unfading flowers 114,46 (TP VIII 135)

wood, dearth of ~ due to heavy rains 6,46 (TP I 63); rank and power are to a blockhead like ornaments on a log of ~ 6,142 (TP I 71); Somaprabhā brings friend basket with mechanical dolls of wood with magic properties (*māyā-sad-yantra-putrikām karaṇḍikām*) 29,2 (TP III 39); automata made of ~ (*kāṣṭha-yantramaya*) 43,22 (TP III 282); ~en puppets (*yantramayo ... janaḥ*) created in order to have company 43,58 (TP III 285); – see also: forest

wood-apples (*kapittha*)¹⁶⁷⁶ thrown on bald man’s head 61,50 (TP V 72)

wood-carrier (*kāṣṭha-bhāraka*) 57,26 (TP V 3)

woodcutter, *rākṣasī* disguises as ~ 39,175 (TP III 230)¹⁶⁷⁷

word, see: speech; voice; – ~play, see: *daśa*; *mōdakaiḥ*

world-egg created from Śiva’s thigh blood 2,10 (TP I 10)

world, Puruṣa-Brahmā creates ~ and becomes proud 2,13 (TP I 10); ~ as skull (*kapālātma jagad*) in Śiva’s hand 2,15 (TP I 10); ~ under dominion of delusion (*moha*) 22,240 (TP II 155); ~ unreal (*a-sāraṃ viśvam etat*) 28,15 (TP III 19); ~ as machine (*jagad-yantra*) consists of five elements 29,43 (TP III 42); most beautiful lady of the three ~s 30,64 (TP III 68) and 31,63 (TP III 87); do, 32,28 (TP III 92) and 52,341 (TP IV 162); ~ painted in colour (*varṇa-vartibhiḥ*) for Uṣā by Citralekhā to recognize future husband dreamt of 31,18f. (TP III 82); brahmin’s boon allows king access to all ~s the brahmin himself obtaining ~ of the gods called Śiva’s 45,111 (TP IV 25); sun as flaming eye of the ~

protected against the greedy eyes of the king (and probably his entourage). See also 58,120 (TP V 23) and Kuv 73.9ff. and 185,5ff., especially 187,5.

¹⁶⁷⁶ ORC 1588 *Feronia limonia*; Macmillan 1949: 247 (figure) and 257 *Feronia elephantum* (not in 1991 edition which has *Limonia acidissima* on p. 303 instead). The globular or ovoid fruit is of the size of a large cricket ball. It has a hard shell and its bitter-sweet pulp is used for a cooling drink and in medicine.

¹⁶⁷⁷ STh 1816.2.

59,51 (TP V 29f., cf. 89,5 [TP VII 40]); people who keep in mind their interest in both ~s (*loka-dvaya-hitâiṣiṇaḥ*) 60,2 (TP V 41); grief produces dissatisfaction in both ~s 62,185 (TP V 115); ~ (*jīva-loka*) is wavering as a wave of the sea, transient as a flash of lightning and its beauty is short-lived like that of a religious festival 66,33 (TP V 180); sun as lamp of the ~ (*jagad-dīpa*) 66,166 (TP V 190) and 74,108 (TP VI 147); moon as eye of the ~ (*jagan-netra*) 89,5 (TP VII 40, cf. 59,51 [TP V 29f.]); this versatile ~ perishes in a moment and is like the show of juggler (*saṃsārasya kṣaṇa-bhaṅgināḥ indrajālôpamānasya kathaṃ vimuhyasi ?*) 111,87 (TP VIII 103); *Gandharva* kings go to the inviolable (*a-dhṛṣya*) ~ of the moon (*soma-loka*) 115,78 (TP IX 149); – see also: *jagad-rakṣamāṇa*

worms (*kīṭa*) in bull’s excretions may enter lion’s body 60,123 (TP V 51)

worship of Śaṅkara-Śiva with garlands in order to become a Gaṇa 7,109 (TP I 86); ~ of Gaṇeśa to get husband 20,56f. (TP II 99f.); ~ of Daitya princess Vidyutprabhā by brahmin under fig tree at night 26,210 (TP II 233); ; ~ of Lakṣmī to get a son 69,78 (TP VI 14); ~ of Fate (*praṇamya bhavitavyatām*) 86,65 (TP VII 18); ~ of Gokaṇa 90,159 (TP VII 60); – see further: names of deities

worship of *liṅga* 115,115 (TP VIII 152); 119,177 (TP VIII 205); 123,111 (TP IX 52); ~ by brahmin and *cāṇḍāla* see Feldhaus 1990: 96f.

wound healed with the aid of a Piśāca 28,163 (TP III 33); ~ = vulva 28,178 (TP III 34); ~s of animals magically cured by king 38,28 (TP III 208);

wrath, Pārvatī in ~ abandons body 1,37 and Śiva in ~ destroys sacrifice of Dakṣa 1,39 (TP I 5); angry brahmin leaves house of host because laughed at by his sons 7,46 (TP I 78); ~ of Brahmā and Indra 9,26 (TP I 96); Tilottamā in ~ curses king 9,33 (TP I 96); ~ as one of six enemies of man 20,134 (TP II 106); ~ of Kālarātrī tearing her own body with bites 20,121 (TP II 165); man who conquers ~ is not subject to grief 60,9 (TP V 41); king’s ~ at impudent because inviolable (*a-vadhya*) ambassador 102,146 (TP VII 173)

wreath of entrails of a *brahma-rākṣasa*, see: entrails

wrestler (*mahā-malla*) from Deccan 25,121 (TP II 200)¹⁶⁷⁸

wrestling champion, brahmin as ~ 25,120 (TP II 200)

wrestling for inheritance of Maya 3,47f. (TP I 22); sons of ministers from the Deccan conquered in ~ (*bāhu-yuddha*) by brahmin 10,25 (TP I 107); overcoming lion in ~ 10,47 (TP I 109); ~ combat 25,122 (TP II 200); playful ~ (*bāhu-yuddha-keli*) of princes 74,51 (TP VI 144); ~ of *vetāla* with *brahma-rākṣasas* 121,66 (TP IX 16)

writing of stanza on garment by princess 71,98 (TP VI 43)¹⁶⁷⁹; ~ without letters, see: impossibility; – see also: letter

yad-ṛcchayā ‘wantonly’ (?) 21,76 (TP II 131 “on the most affectionate terms”; note 2:

¹⁶⁷⁸ Bollée 1977: 50f. note 98; 1981: 178ff.

¹⁶⁷⁹ See Gode III 1969: 13ff.

“wantonly”. ORC 180: “à son bon plaisir”; M I 257: “in höchster Liebeslust”)

Yājñavalkya knows sciences of bewildering and counteracting (*mohinī-parivartinyau*) 46,118f. (TP IV 56)

*yajñopavīta*¹⁶⁸⁰ qualifies to read the Vedas 2,74 (TP I 17); enchanter’s (*mantra-sādhaka*) ~ made of hair (*dhṛta-keśōpavītaka*) 73,283 (TP VI 120); *brahmarākṣasa* wearing ~ made of hair 94,69 (TP VII 91); brahmin corpse with ~ made of hair (*keśa-°*) 99,11 (TP VII 123); princes get ~ at eight years 118,46 (TP VIII 181)¹⁶⁸¹; – see also: hair
*yakṣa(s)*¹⁶⁸² cursed by Kubera to become a *piśāca* in Vindhya forest 1,59 (TP I 7); ~ powerless in the day because dazed by the sun 7,35 (TP I 77); ~ cursed by Kubera to become lion 10,42 (TP I 109); adulterers put into ~ Mañibhadra’s temple within the city of Tāmraliptī at night 13,165ff. (TP I 162)¹⁶⁸³; mountainlike ~, guarding treasure and rising from the earth 18,41 (TP II 52); brahmin ~ speaks from *aśvattha* tree 20,37 (TP II 97)¹⁶⁸⁴; mechanical ~ (*yantramayaṃ ~m*) 29,38 (TP III 41); ~ slays brahmin treasure-hunters 34,74 (TP III 134); ~ prevents copper to be turned into gold 35,85 (TP III 162); ~ propitiated by spell to bestow his own genitals on eunuch 56,96 (TP IV 226); ~ cursed by Bhairava to be eunuch 56,101 (TP IV 227); ~s give man inexhaustible pitcher 57,41 (TP V 4); ~ disappears in tree 63,85 (TP V 126); ~ in tree joking with his wife 66,20 (TP V 179); ~ strikes wife with garland 66,21 (TP V 179); ~ followers of Kubera in shape of waterbirds (*cakra-haṃsādi vāri-cara*) playing in Mānasa lake 72,40 (TP VI 71 with note 3); ~ heals exhausted minister 73,13 and 17 (TP VI 101); ~ wives eat after husband 73,14 (TP VI 101); ~ with feet turned backward (*viparītāṅghri* [q. v.]) 73,245 (TP VI 118); wine and meat sacrificed to ~ 105,57 (TP VIII 25); *kāpālika* possesses spells for mastering ~s (*yakṣa-sādhana-mantra*) 121,10 (TP IX 12); – see also: feet; spell(s);

yakṣ(īn)ī(s) princess emerges from fig tree trunk 26,210 (TP II 233); ~s transform themselves into rain of gold 28,65 (TP III 25); ~ descends as mortal girl without being born and makes brahmin husband surmount curse 34,82 (TP III 134); ~ devours visitors to empty temple of Śiva 37,57 (TP III 186f.); ~ charms Pāśupata ascetics out of their magic circle, bakes them in fire and devours them 37,64ff. (TP III 187f.); ~ unable to be active at daylight 37,80 (TP III 189); merchant conveyed at night by ~ whom he had subdued by his courage (*dhairya*) 37,140 (TP III 193 with “presence of mind” for *dhairya*; ORC 379: “courage”; M I 532: “Weisheit und Standhaftigkeit”); ~ obtained by hermit with spell 49,169 (TP IV 96); ~ pretending to be dead (*mṛta-kalpam kṛtvā*) says black man took her to Yama who sent her back 66,24ff. (TP V 180); brahmin with spell gets ~ into his power 73,25 (TP VI 102); ~ surrounded by many *yakṣas*, with feet turned the wrong way and squinting eyes 73,245 (TP

¹⁶⁸⁰ Kane 1974: 287ff., esp. 291f. The y. of a brahmin has to be made of cotton. Kane does not mention the hair-*yajñopavīta* as in our passage. Jackmuth 2002: 91.

¹⁶⁸¹ Kane ???

¹⁶⁸² On *yakṣas* see, e.g. Mitterwallner 1989; Misra 1979.

¹⁶⁸³ Zin 2003b: 266 note 11.

¹⁶⁸⁴ Zin 2003b: 253.

VI 118); beautiful ~ surrounded with a hundred ladies-in-waiting, like a protecting herb that shines in the night 108,46 (TP VIII 56)¹⁶⁸⁵; ~ demands brahmin mortal to marry her in order to end her curse 108,48 (TP VIII 56); ~ addressed as *devi* 121,227 (TP IX 28); ~ opens mouth from heaven to earth 123,22 (TP IX 44)¹⁶⁸⁶

yakṣman,¹⁶⁸⁷ ('consumption') king attacked by ~ 73,259 (TP VI 119); drug against ~ 73,112 (TP VI 123);

Yama's glances, swords red with blood falling on heroes' heads like ~ (*Kṛtāntasyēva dr̥ṣṭayaḥ*) 44,147 (TP IV 10); ~ amuses himself with the severed heads of heroes in combat flying up and down like a game of ball (*kanduka-kriḍā*) 50,7 (TP IV 108); ~ as noose-handed (*pāśa-hasta*) 55,165 (TP IV 213); hunter compared to servant of ~ (*Yama-kiṃkara*) 59,47 (TP V 29); whoever returned from the house of ~ ? 66,28 (TP V 180); Caṇḍikā's temple resembling palace of ~ 72,17 (TP VI 69); ~'s question to sinner: stay first in hell or in heaven ? 72,350 (TP VI 95); ~ silent 72,360 (TP VI 95); fire produced by loud clashing of swords seems as if kindled by gnashing teeth of angry Yama (*analo ... kupya- Kṛtānta-dantāgra-danalōttha*) 74,283 (TP VI 160); saw sharp as points of ~'s (eye) teeth (*Yama-damṣṭrāgra*) 121,86 (TP IX 18)¹⁶⁸⁸; – see also: sword; teeth; tongue

yāmā 'watch', night consisting of three ~s 109,107 (TP VIII 78 with note)

Yama-sabhā 'hall of Yama' 72,349 (TP VI 95)

yantra-dvāra 'magic gate', tank serves as a ~ 86,150 (TP VII 24; ORC 919: "le bassin dont un mécanisme secret faisait déboucher sur le monde terrestre"; M II 265: "Teich mit dem Zaubertor, das in die Welt der Menschen führt")

yantra-hastin, see: elephant; Vindhya

yantra-kalpa-druma 'movable wishing-tree' 86,108 (TP VII 21; M II 262 similar; ORC 917: "arbre à désirs que met en mouvement un mécanisme secret")

yantra-karaṇḍikā 'magical basket' 29,21 (TP III 40)

yantram vyoma-gāmi chariot travelling through the air 30,19 (TP III 65)

yaṣṭi, magic ~ ('wand') turns true what is written on it¹⁶⁸⁹ 3,50 (TP I 22); – see also: *danḍa yat karma-bījam uptaṃ yena purā, niścitaṃ sa tad bhuṅkte* "whatever seed of works any man has sown in a former life, of that he, without doubt, eats the fruit", *āryā*-song of a mermaid in the middle of the ocean 86,44f. (TP VII 16) and 79f. (TP VII 18f.)

yātrā, beauty of the world is short-lived like that of a ~ ('religious festival') 66,33 (TP V 180)

¹⁶⁸⁵ Zin 2003b: 220.

¹⁶⁸⁶ This reminds us a little of the *kīrti-mukha*, Kala Boma on the isle of Bali, on top of temple gates, the lower jaw of which is the threshold, see Bollée 1986: 200ff.

¹⁶⁸⁷ Meulenbeld 1975: 628.

¹⁶⁸⁸ Asuras have this kind of teeth, cf. ???

¹⁶⁸⁹ Winternitz 1920:330 thinks the *yaṣṭi* to be a dowsing rod (*Wünschelrute*) which his translator perhaps not knowing the word renders by 'magic stick' (1985 III 364) or else he looked at the text and saw the explanation which makes clear that no dowsing rod is meant here. Winternitz may have thought of Latin *virga divina* and Greek *πόβδος*.

yātrōtsava, see: procession; religious festival; spring

yauvana–dvir-ada (not MW) ‘elephant of youth’, maiden like lake for the ~ to plunge in 84,8 (TP VII 5)

yauvanâpagame ‘when his youth was gone,’ said of a father getting a son 113,21 (TP VIII 125)

yawn (*jṛmbhikā*), of hero rising from bed 45,120 (TP IV 26); king rising from pyre with ~ 58,32 (TP V 17); yawning *brahma-rākṣasa* 94,115 (TP VII 95); demon of destruction yawned (*vyajṛmbhata saṃgrāma-kālah*) 108,106 (TP VIII 62)

years, four days of separation felt as four ~ 54,79 (TP IV 189); five ~ of duty without pay 55,15 (TP IV 203)); six or twelve ~ for learning grammar 6,144f. (TP I 71); seven ~ old brahmin to be sacrificed 94,78 (TP VII 92); golden image of seven ~ old boy to be made 94,90 (TP VII 93); eight ~ of austerities to propitiate Hara 118,132 (TP VIII 187); Rājput lives ten ~ on *āmalakas* 81,21 (TP VI 210); wife waits eleven ~ for husband 124,58 (TP IX 72); twelve ~ of drought 5,72 (TP I 52); carrying twelve ~ someone’s shoes on one’s head 6,149 (TP I 71); twelve ~ search for Pāśupata ascetic 56,224 (TP IV 236); object of human existence is *mokṣa* by twelve ~ of meditation and *tapas* 73,171 (TP VI 113); *kārpaṭika* serves king for twelve ~ 124,52 (TP IX 72); twelve ~ old boy steals father’s bed 124,212 (TP IX 83); Tilottamā curses king to fourteen ~ of separation from love 9,33 (TP I 96); sixteen ~ of fever 97,11 (TP VII 112f.); living for one hundred ~ 78,51 (TP VI 194); *tapas* of eating fruits for three hundred ~ 115,19 (TP VIII 144); eight hundred ~ of living in *āśram* 25,20 (TP II 189); – see also: asceticism; infant prodigy

yell of she-jackal (q. v.)

yellow (*piṅga*) tufts of Śiva’s matted hair 1,18 (TP I 3); ~ body of nymph with dust of flowers 35,12 (TP III 156); peaks of Himavat ~ with brightness of *vidyādharas*’s bodies 35,20 (TP III 156); head of snake Śeṣa, ~ with rays of jewels (*ratnâṃśu-piñjara*) 72,38 (TP VI 71); ~ matted hair (*piṅgalâgra-jāta*) of ascetic 73,100 (TP VI 108); ~ pollen of flowers compared to fires of separation 81,63 (TP VI 213); waves of lake slightly ~ (*piñjarī-kṛta*) with the unguents which its embraces rubbed off from bathing women’s bodies 104,89 (TP VIII 7); *vidyādhara* king becoming ~ by worshipping Agni 106,73 (TP VIII 33)¹⁶⁹⁰; – ~ powder of bones (q.v.);

yoga ‘Yoga doctrine’ 45,79 (TP IV 22); (‘supernatural power’), by ~ Bodhisattva turns himself into deer 72,380 (TP VI 97); – see also: magic

yoga-gulikā (not MW) ‘magic pill’, Mūladeva puts ~ for transformation into old brahmin in his mouth 89,25 (TP VII 41f.);

yoga-dhāraṇā ‘continuous meditation’ to avert evil (*duṣṭa-ghnī*) 73,135 (TP VI 111)

Yoga doctrine taught by *Asura* Maya 45,79 (TP IV 22) and *pratta-yoga* 114 (TP IV 25);

yoga-mahā-siddhi ‘supernatural powers through yoga’ 72,368 (TP VI 96)

yoga-siddha–muni ‘hermit with supernatural power’ 68,17 (TP VI 2);

yoga-siddhimān, see: entering

¹⁶⁹⁰ This may remind one of the fiery munis with their yellowish rags of ṚV 10,136,1f.

yogin ('magician'), out of curiosity and unnoticed by his magic power (*kutūhalāt a-lakṣito yoga-vaśāt*) the *gaṇa* Puṣpadanta enters the closed place where Hara-Śiva tells Pārvatī stories 1,50 and *yogī bhūtvā* 1,55 (TP I 6); *guru* of the ~s 73,103 (TP VI 108)
yogēśvarī 'witch' 68,65 (TP VI 6)
yoginī, see: witch
yoginī-cakra 'coven of witches' in charnel ground at night 75,173 (TP VI 176)¹⁶⁹¹; – cf. *khecarī-cakra*
yoginī-grāma = prec., emerging from temple of Mātaras 123,212 (TP IX 58)
yoginī-sakha (not MW) 'friend of witches (i. e. Mātaras)' = Bhairava-Śiva 56,106 (TP IV 226)
youngest brother, solicited by elder brothers' wives, scorns them 33,40 (TP III 109); – see also: *niyoga*
youth, pride of ~ is like creeper weighed down with many flowers 18,277 (TP II 70); ~ (*vayas*) most desirable quality of suitor 30,29 (TP III 66); pride of ~ makes princess refuse marriage 52,171 (TP IV 150); *kokilas* say: "youthful body does not return" 55,110 (TP IV 210); dancing-girl like wave of the sea of beauty tossed up by the wind of ~ > juvenile tempestuousness (*tāruṇya-vāta*) 57,75 (TP V 7); ~ is wealth to creatures 61,116 (TP V 78); creeper of tree of love agitated by wind of ~ (*yauvanânīla*) 68,77 (TP VI 41)
yuga, names of Ujjayinī in four ~s, 83,6 (TP VII 1)
yukti 'stratagem' to kill someone 71,208 (TP VI 50)
yukti-pāṭava (not MW) 'clever reasoning, skill in speaking' 62,222 (TP V 118)
yuva-rājā inaugurated 34,125 (TP III 137); – see also: crown-prince
zenana, see: *antaḥpura*

Śravaṇa-phala

*etāṃ mad-vadanôdgataṃ paṭhati yo yo vā śṛṇoty ādarād
yaś cāitāṃ su-kathāṃ bibharti, na cirāt sa dhvasta-pāpaḥ kṛtī
sad-vidyādharaṭām avāpya niyataṃ lokaṃ mama prāpnuyād*

“whoever recites this tale that issued from my mouth, and whoever attentively listens to it, and whoever possesses it, shall soon be released from his transgressions, and enter my everlasting world as a splendid *vidyādhara*.”

¹⁶⁹¹ See Dehejia 1986: 14f. with an 18th century painting of witches in a charnel ground.

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¹⁶⁹³ For this reprint the author has overlooked, and was kindly notified by Professor Oberlies of, J.J. Meyer's article Two Twice-told Tales in the Decennial Publications of the John Rockefeller University of Chicago. 1903: 117-125. A volume of Meyer's Collected Papers is an urgent desideratum.

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¹⁶⁹⁸ For the comfort of the readers of the present study the many above quotations of this dissertation are only intended to refer to metaphors in Kālidāsa (whose text Jackmuth gives handy with one or more translations) similar to those in KSS, and are not meant as an opinion about her discussions on imagery. – For a review of Jackmuth see Hanneder 2005a.

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¹⁷⁰¹ This book describes the modern Durgā cult and uses only English secondary literature. Thus Rgvedic quotations are translated by Ralph Griffith (1889); Geldner seems unknown to the author.

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